

Handbook of Plant Health

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This handbook is aimed to **the most important parameters to measure the health of crop plants**. Different crops demand different parameters, so that some of the parameters included in this handbook are just measured in one specific crop (i.e., starch in potato), while others (i.e., protein content, humidity, nitrogen content, etc.) are measured in more than one crop. Moreover, two of the parameters here presented (isotopic discrimination and elemental analyses) will be done in the University of Vigo for all the crops included in the AGROSUS project. The parameters here listed are presented with a detailed protocol, the material needed for their measurement, the most relevant references, and the principles for why these parameters are so important for evaluating the health of the crop plants, and will be done by the different partners from the different eleven biogeographic regions from Europe in the agroecological and conventional farming systems established in AGROSUS.

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1. Case studies setup and experimental design

1.1. Experimental Units

Work packages 3 and 4 (WP3 and WP4) have been designed to develop solid and robust scientific understanding about the impacts of agroecological strategies (AE) on crop productivity, weed management and soil health and biodiversity, which is related to other ecosystem services such as soil fertility and carbon sequestration in different biogeographic regions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Biogeographical regions of Europe.

To correctly address the projects' objectives, short, medium, and long-term farm systems will be analysed, and 83 experimental units (68 short-term + 15 medium to long-term) will be considered in the 11 European biogeographic regions (Figure 2). Short, medium and long-term impact of AE on crop productivity, weed management, and soil health will be measured along the AGROSUS project. The short-term impact will be measured in experimental units developed by the different partners in conventional, organic, or mixed farm systems. However, considering the duration of the project (4 years), the medium to long-term impact of AE will be evaluated in in-course AE fields already identified in some of the different regions, and different measures to evaluate crop quality, weed control, soil health, ecotoxicological, environmental and socioeconomic impact will be recorded in the frame of AGROSUS.

Figure 2. AGROSUS short-term experimental units in the eleven biogeographic regions

1.2. Experimental design

A well-designed and harmonized experimental design is important in any scientific study, as states how laboratory samples must be taken, how they must be collected and from where they must be taken, to achieve the objectives established in the research project. In the comparison of treatments in agronomic experiments, a properly designed experimental scheme is of crucial importance to make adequate statistical inference. The two most common alternatives applied in the case studies of the project are shown below:

1.2.1. Randomized experimental design

This model assumes that the replicates of the different treatments are randomly distributed within the experiment when a randomized complete block design or a split-plot design is carried out (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of a randomized experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2.

1.2.2. Block experimental design

If a block experimental design (not randomized) is going to be carried out (Figure 4), control treatment (the one already performed in the farm as a routine basis; CV) does not represent field variability, since each treatment is located in different areas of the field, and some variations will be present in soil owing to different location. So, initial conditions in each block have to be taken into account. Therefore, when a non-randomized block experimental design is implemented (Figure 4), the conventional treatment and each of the AE will have their own designated area in the study field.

Figure 4. Example of block experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2.

Measurements to be done in all the crops to evaluate the health status of the different crop plants:

1. Isotopic discrimination

PRINCIPLE

Isotopic discrimination in plants, refers to the measurement or evaluation of the differences in isotopic composition between different forms of carbon or other isotopes, as nitrogen, within plants or tissues. This discrimination can provide insights into various aspects of plant physiology, such as photosynthesis, water-use efficiency, and nutrient uptake. Isotopes are atoms of the same element that have different numbers of neutrons, resulting in different atomic masses. Carbon has two stable isotopes, carbon-12 (^{12}C) and carbon-13 (^{13}C), with ^{12}C being more abundant. As far as Rubisco preferentially fixes ^{12}C , the ratio of ^{13}C to ^{12}C can vary due to different processes in plant metabolism, specially under stress conditions.

Carbon Isotope Discrimination ($\Delta^{13}\text{C}$): Carbon isotope discrimination ($\Delta^{13}\text{C}$) is a measure of the difference in isotopic composition between atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO_2) and the carbon fixed during photosynthesis by plants. It is influenced by the relative diffusion rates of $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ and $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ through the stomata of plant leaves.

Measuring $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ can provide insights into plant performance, water-use efficiency, and carbon balance. For example, low $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ values may indicate more efficient water use or higher photosynthetic capacity.

Applications of Isotopic Discrimination in plants: Water-use Efficiency: Isotopic discrimination can be used as an indicator of water-use efficiency in the plants. Lower $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ values are generally related to higher water-use efficiency, suggesting that the plants are effectively using water. Photosynthetic Performance: $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ can provide information about the photosynthetic performance of crop plants. It can reflect the efficiency of carbon assimilation and the interplay between stomatal conductance and photosynthesis. Environmental Conditions: Isotopic discrimination can also be influenced by environmental conditions such as drought stress or nutrient availability. Changes in $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ values can be related to stomata closure and indicate how crop plants respond to different environmental stressors. Crop Management: Isotopic discrimination can help in evaluating the effects of different crop management practices on plants. It can provide insights into the impact of fertilization, irrigation, or other cultivation practices on plant growth and physiology.

Nitrogen isotope discrimination: refers to the difference in the ratio of stable isotopes of nitrogen (specifically, the ratio of $\Delta^{15}\text{N}$ to $\Delta^{14}\text{N}$) between the plant and the nitrogen

source it takes up from the soil. Nitrogen is an essential nutrient for plant growth, and different plants can exhibit variations in their ability to discriminate between isotopes of nitrogen. Isotope discrimination occurs during the process of nitrogen uptake and assimilation by the plants. Plants have the ability to preferentially select light isotopes of nitrogen ($\Delta^{14}\text{N}$) over heavy isotopes ($\Delta^{15}\text{N}$) during nutrient absorption. This discrimination process can lead to differences in the isotopic composition of nitrogen in the plant tissues compared to the available nitrogen sources in the soil.

Several factors can influence nitrogen isotope discrimination in crop plants:

Plant Metabolism: The discrimination against $\Delta^{15}\text{N}$ can vary depending on the metabolic processes within the plant. Different enzymatic reactions involved in nitrogen uptake, assimilation, and transport can affect the isotopic composition.

Environmental Conditions: Environmental factors such as temperature, light intensity, water availability, and nutrient status can influence nitrogen isotope discrimination. For example, water availability and nutrient status can affect the efficiency of nitrogen uptake and assimilation, thereby impacting the isotopic composition.

Genetic Variability: Different cultivars may exhibit variations in their ability to discriminate against $\Delta^{15}\text{N}$. Genetic factors can influence the expression of genes associated with nitrogen metabolism and isotope discrimination.

Nitrogen isotope discrimination in crop plants, can therefore provide valuable insights into various ecological and agricultural processes, such as: Plant Physiology and Metabolism: i.e., understanding the mechanisms underlying nitrogen isotope discrimination can help elucidating plant physiological processes, including nitrogen uptake, assimilation, and allocation within different plant tissues; Plant-Soil Interactions: Nitrogen isotope discrimination can provide information about nitrogen cycling and transformations in the soil environment. It can help identifying nitrogen sources and pathways of nutrient uptake by plants; Crop Nutrient Management: Studying nitrogen isotope discrimination in crop plants can contribute to optimizing fertilizer management practices. It can help assess the efficiency of nitrogen utilization by crops and guide the development of sustainable agricultural practices.

PROCEDURE

Plant leaf samples are collected and dried in an oven at 70 °C. The dry leaf samples are grinded using a ball mill and converted into fine powder. The powdered samples are saved (weight 1.7 – 2.1 mg) in tin capsules (*Elemental Microanalysis*, 5 × 3.5 mm) and sealed. The capsules are introduced in a combustion oven at 1,600–1,800 °C. The stable isotope ratios of carbon and nitrogen are determined through an isotopic ratio mass spectrometer (IRSM, Finnegan: Thermo Fisher Scientific, model MAT-253, Schwerte, Germany).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ball mill
- Tin capsules (*Elemental Microanalysis*, 5 × 3.5 mm)

Equipment:

- Oven
- Mass spectrometer (IRSM, Finnegan: Thermo Fisher Scientific, model MAT-253, Schwerte, Germany).

CALCULATIONS

Results from the isotope ratio deviations are presented using the standard δ notation:

$$\delta^{13}\text{C} \text{ and } \delta^{15}\text{N} (\text{‰}) = (R_{\text{sample}} / R_{\text{standard}}) - 1$$

where R_{sample} is the stable isotopic ratio in the samples and R_{standard} is the ratio in the standard. The Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) is as a standard for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and atmospheric N_2 is used as the standard for $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

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2. Elemental analysis

PRINCIPLE

Crop plants contain several minerals, including nitrogen (N), phosphorous (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), boron (B) and sodium (Na), which play a crucial role in the growth and development of plants. They are essential nutrients that plants need in varying quantities to carry out various physiological processes:

Structural component: Minerals are essential for the formation of structural components in plants. For example, **calcium** is necessary for the structure of the oxygen evolving complex in photosystem II and for the development of strong cell walls, which provide support and structure to the plant.

Enzyme activation: Many minerals act as cofactors for enzymes, which are involved in various metabolic reactions within the plant. These enzymes are responsible for processes such as photosynthesis, respiration, and nutrient uptake. Without the presence of minerals, these enzymes cannot function properly. For example, **potassium** helps activating enzymes that are responsible for important processes in plants, such as protein synthesis, starch formation, and the production of adenosine triphosphate

(ATP), which is the energy currency of cells. Potassium also plays a role in regulating the opening and closing of stomata, which are tiny openings on the leaves that control gas exchange and water loss. **Magnesium** is another essential macronutrient for plants and is involved in enzyme activation. It plays a central role in the photosynthesis process by forming the core of the chlorophyll molecule, which is responsible for capturing light energy. Magnesium also activates enzymes involved in the synthesis of carbohydrates and lipids. Additionally, magnesium is required for the proper functioning of several other enzymes involved in DNA and RNA synthesis.

Nutrient transport: Minerals, are involved in the transport of nutrients within the plant. They help in the movement of water, nutrients, and sugars through the plant's vascular system, ensuring that all parts of the plant receive the necessary resources. In addition to potassium, magnesium and calcium, iron, manganese and zinc play an important role in nutrient transport. **Iron** is important for the synthesis of chlorophyll, which is essential for photosynthesis. It is involved in the transport of electrons during the light reactions of photosynthesis, facilitating the production of ATP. Iron also plays a role in the transport of other nutrients, such as nitrate and sulphate, within the plant. **Manganese** is required for the synthesis of enzymes involved in nutrient transport. It participates in redox reactions, facilitating the movement of electrons during various metabolic processes. Manganese also influences the uptake and transport of other nutrients, such as phosphorus and calcium. **Zinc** is involved in the synthesis and activation of enzymes that are essential for nutrient uptake and transport. It plays a role in the regulation of membrane transporters, facilitating the movement of ions and nutrients across cell membranes. Zinc also influences the synthesis and transport of certain hormones that regulate nutrient allocation within the plant.

Photosynthesis: Minerals like **phosphorus** and **magnesium** are essential for photosynthesis, the process by which plants convert sunlight into energy. Phosphorus is a key component of ATP, the energy molecule used by plants, while magnesium is an essential component of chlorophyll, the pigment responsible for capturing light energy.

Growth and development: Minerals are necessary for the overall growth and development of plants. For example, **nitrogen** is required for the production of proteins, which are essential for cell division and growth. Iron is needed for chlorophyll synthesis and is crucial for proper plant development.

Disease resistance: Some minerals, such as **zinc** and **copper**, play a role in plant's defence mechanisms against diseases and pests. They are involved in the production of enzymes and compounds that help fight off pathogens and protect the plant from damage.

Reproduction: Minerals such as **boron** are essential for plant reproduction. They are involved in the development of flowers, fruits, and seeds, ensuring successful pollination, fertilization, and seed formation.

Osmotic regulation: **Sodium** ions can contribute to the osmotic potential of plant cells, allowing plants to absorb water and maintain turgor pressure. Sodium uptake can be beneficial for plants in building osmotic potential and absorbing water, especially in saline environments or under conditions of water stress.

PROCEDURE

Samples are dried and powdered, and 100 mg are digested with 3 mL of 69% HNO₃ (Aristar grade, VWR) and 1 mL of 30% H₂O₂ (Aristar grade, VWR) in a 1600 W microwave oven with the following program: 2 min at 100 °C, 1 min at 120 °C, 2 min at 160 °C, 20 min at 180 °C and 20 min cooling time. At the end of the procedure, samples are diluted with milliQ high quality sterile water (18.2 MV cm conductivity) to 50 mL and kept at 4 °C prior to analysis. Two blank digestions are performed in the same way as for the samples. The concentration of macro and micronutrients are estimated using inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS Thermofisher Scientific-Serie X7).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 69% HNO₃
- milliQ sterile water

Equipment:

- Microwave oven
- Coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS Thermofisher scientific-Serie X7)

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Measurements to be done in each crop to evaluate the health status of the different crop plants:

1. ARABLE

1.1. Barley

1.1.1. Plant height

PRINCIPLE

Plant height is a key indicator for crop health and growth.

PROCEDURE

1. The measurements are conducted near the end of the growing season. Five individual plants are measured in an area of 50 × 50 cm (one plant in the centre and one plant in each corner). Ten of such areas are measured for each experimental plot.
2. Distance from the base of the plant to the highest point of photosynthetic tissue on the plant is measured with a tape measure.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Tape measure
- Quadrat (50 x 50 cm)

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Weiher, E., Van Der Werf, A., Thompson, K., Roderick, M., Garnier, E. & Eriksson, O. (1999). Challenging Theophrastus: a common core list of plant traits for functional ecology. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 10(5), 609-620. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3237076>

Westoby, M. (1998). A leaf-height-seed (LHS) plant ecology strategy scheme. *Plant and Soil*, 199, 213-227. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004327224729>

1.1.2. Shoot and root fresh and dry weight, root/shoot ratio

PRINCIPLE

For determination of overall health of the crop plants and plant growth, the fresh and dry weight of the crop plants is measured 3 times during the growing season.

PROCEDURE

For measurement of fresh weight:

1. A subsample of a number of plants from each experimental plot is removed from the soil and any soil is washed off with deionized water.
2. Each plant is divided into shoot and root, and weighed.

For dry weight:

1. Shoots and roots are dried at 80 °C until they reach a constant weight.
2. Then, they are transferred to a desiccator to cool.
3. Shoots and roots are weighed.
4. Root to shoot ratio is calculated based on the dry weight measurements.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Scale for weighing
- Drying oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Root/shoot ratio} = \frac{\text{Root weight (g)}}{\text{Shoot weight (g)}}$$

REFERENCES

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1.1.3. Date of emergence

PRINCIPLE

The date of emergence is important for crop management, pest and disease management, yield potential assessment, crop rotation planning, and research purposes. It provides valuable information for making informed decisions throughout the growing season and optimizing rapeseed production.

PROCEDURE

Date of emergence is recorded when 75% of the plants have emerged. The emergence takes place from the fall, under normal humidity conditions, and during the winter or spring when the fall was dry.

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1.1.4. Spike date

PRINCIPLE

Measuring spike data in barley is important for understanding spike architecture, assessing yield potential, studying reproductive development, conducting genetic studies, and making informed crop management decisions. It provides valuable insights into the growth and development of barley spikes, which ultimately impact the productivity and quality of the crop.

PROCEDURE

Spike date is recorded when 75% of the plants have spiked.

REFERENCES

Singh, R., Krishnan, P., Singh, V.K. et al. (2023). Combining biophysical parameters with thermal and RGB indices using machine learning models for predicting yield in yellow rust affected wheat crop. *Scientific Report*, 13, 18814. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-45682-3>.

Thirugnana Sambandham, V., Shankar, P. & Mukhopadhaya, S. (2022). Early onset yellow rust detection guided by remote sensing indices. *Agriculture*, 12(8), 1206. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12081206>.

1.1.5. Technical maturity

PRINCIPLE

Technical maturity in barley involves monitoring growth, development, and characteristics of the crop. It plays a crucial role in determining the optimal harvest timing, ensuring grain quality, making informed crop management decisions, and advancing research and breeding efforts in barley cultivation.

PROCEDURE

Technical maturity is recorded when the humidity of the grains has reached 17%. At this moment, the field is suitable for mechanized harvesting.

REFERENCES

Neagu Frăsin, L.B. (2015). Observations regarding the agronomical value and the use of winter barley cultivars in Southern muntenia's ecosystems. *Annals. Food Science and Technology*, 16(1), 168-174.

1.1.6. Moisture dynamics

PRINCIPLE

The moisture dynamics in barley, can vary throughout its growth stages. During the early stages of growth, barley plants require adequate moisture for germination and establishment. As the plants mature, they become more resilient to drought conditions. However, during the critical stages of flowering and seed development, sufficient moisture is crucial for optimal yield. Insufficient moisture during these stages can lead to poor seed formation and reduced yields. Monitoring the moisture levels in the soil and providing irrigation, when necessary, can help mitigating the impact of drought stress on barley crops.

Harvesting is typically done when the barley pods have reached maturity, and the moisture content of the seeds is around 17%. Harvesting at this moisture level helps ensure proper seed quality and facilitates storage. Monitoring moisture levels during harvesting is essential to prevent issues such as shattering and to optimize the efficiency of the harvesting process.

PROCEDURE

The determinations commence once the grains have attained a dark yellow colour, advanced to a waxy consistency, and the humidity is approximately 27%. Measurements are taken every 2-3 days until the moisture level reaches 17%, which is deemed the date of technical maturity.

REFERENCES

Johnsson, H. & Jansson, P.-E. (1991). Water balance and soil moisture dynamics of field plots with barley and grass ley. *Journal of Hydrology*, 129(1–4), 149-173.

Marchetti, C.F., Ugena, L., Humplík, J.F., Polák, M., Čavar Zeljković, S., Podlešáková, K., Fürst, T., De Diego, N. & Spíchal, L. (2019). A novel image-based screening method to study water-deficit response and recovery of barley populations using canopy dynamics phenotyping and simple metabolite profiling. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 1252. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2019.01252.

1.1.7. Plant density per square meter

PRINCIPLE

Knowing the plant density in barley is important for optimizing production, assessing crop performance, determining yield potential, allocating resources efficiently, and advancing research and breeding efforts. It provides valuable insights into the establishment and growth of the crop, enabling farmers to make informed decisions for successful barley cultivation.

PROCEDURE

In autumn, at the end of vegetation, or in spring at sunrise, determination is made when the rows are finished, the leaves have reached 2 cm in length and the appearance of new plants is no longer recorded. The cessation of vegetation is considered when the average air temperature is below 0 °C for at least 3 days in a row. For this determination, it is necessary to delimit an area of 0.5 m² (with metric frame) in each plot. The metric frame with an inner side of 0.71 m must be fixed in such a way that its diagonal overlaps one of the rows of plants. The sides of the metric frame, so the ends of the 2 diagonals must be marked with stakes that are kept until harvesting. The number of plants per sqm is determined. In the 4 repetitions and in the sheets, the average of the determinations is entered. Ex. 530 plants m⁻².

The density of the plants (in the spring, when the plants started growing) is checked at the same points established previously with the metric frame.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Metric frame

REFERENCES

Panasiewicz, K., Faligowska, A., Szymańska, G., Szukała, J., Ratajczak, K. & Sulewska, H. (2020). The effect of various tillage systems on productivity of narrow-leaved lupin-winter wheat-winter triticale-winter barley rotation. *Agronomy*, 10, 304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10020304>.

1.1.8. Visual observations of disease infection and pest attack

PRINCIPLE

Plant diseases are caused both by the action of unfavourable physical and chemical or other abiotic factors of the environment, and by microorganisms or organisms belonging to higher plants (flower parasites). Each parasitic organism or abiotic factor is capable of causing a peculiar disease, characterized by external signs, or symptoms, or, otherwise, types of damage. Symptoms of diseases can be either clearly visible to the naked eye, or barely noticeable, or hidden, which cannot be seen for some time. In order to properly protect plants from diseases, it is necessary to be able to recognize them, that is, to make the correct diagnosis based on a set of external signs.

PROCEDURE

The disease infection is visually observed and the infected leaf/root/base of the stem/pods tissue samples are taken to the laboratory, and the pathogens are identified under a microscope using aqueous mounting media. The species of fungi are identified on the basis of the mycological keys and monographs. The identification of each isolate

is conducted twice. Fungal and pests' infections are determined on 25 randomly selected plants per plot.

REFERENCES

Dugan, F. (2006). The identification of fungi. In an Illustrated Introduction, with Keys, Glossary, and Guide to Literature; The American Phytopathological Society Press: St. Paul, MA, USA, pp. 176.

1.2. Maize

1.2.1. Phenological observations

PRINCIPLE

Phenological observations in maize refer to the study and monitoring of the different stages of growth and development of maize plants. These observations are important for understanding the timing of key events in the maize life cycle, such as germination, flowering, and maturity. These observations provide valuable information for farmers, researchers, and policymakers in managing agricultural practices, predicting crop yields, and assessing the impact of environmental factors on maize production.

PROCEDURE

Phenological observations are done during plant growth and include the following measurements: seed germination, sprouting, formation of the third leaf, tillering, formation of the fifth, seventh, ninth, and eleventh (odd) leaves, emergence into the tube, throwing out the panicle, flowering of the panicle, flowering of the cob, milk ripeness, waxy ripeness, and full ripeness.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Not equipment needed

REFERENCES

Niu, Q., Li, X., Huang, J., Huang, H., Huang, X., Su, W. & Yuan, W. (2022). A 30 m annual maize phenology dataset from 1985 to 2020 in China. *Earth System Science Data*, 14(6), 2851-2864.

1.2.2. Assessment of disease

PRINCIPLE

Plant diseases are caused both by the action of abiotic factors (unfavourable physical and chemical or other abiotic factors of the environment), and by biotic factors (microorganisms or organisms belonging to higher plants; flower parasites). Each parasitic organism or abiotic factor is capable of causing a peculiar disease, characterized by external signs, or symptoms, or, otherwise, types of damage.

Symptoms of diseases can be either clearly visible to the naked eye, or barely noticeable, or hidden, which cannot be seen for some time. In order to properly protect plants from diseases, it is necessary to be able to recognize them, that is, to make the correct diagnosis based on a set of external signs.

PROCEDURE

The diagnosis of diseases involves employing macroscopic or visual methods, such as external inspection and the comparison of afflicted plants with healthy ones, identifying disease symptoms with the naked eye. The prevalent types of diseases include wilting, rotting, destruction of plant organs, spots, plaques, pustules, mummification, growths, and gum bleeding.

Detection of diseases in plants is carried out by inspecting a specific number of plants in trials or accounting plots. On a field of up to 100 hectares, 100 plants undergo examination—5 each in 20 places or in two adjacent rows in 10 places. For larger areas, an additional 50 plants are inspected for every subsequent 100 hectares. In cases of low pest density or mild plant damage by disease, up to 200 plants in 20 places may be examined.

In the practical aspect of diagnosing plant diseases, instances may arise where external signs of two or more diseases coincide, while the nature and the responsible agents of these diseases differ. In such scenarios, additional diagnostic methods come into play.

The microscopic method is more frequently employed, involving the examination of tissue sections or fungal sporulation, bacterial exudate, and viral inclusions under a microscope. This method facilitates the identification of the causative agent or the nature of changes in affected tissues.

For a more precise definition of the causative agent, the cultural method is utilized—wherein the pathogenic organism is isolated on an artificial nutrient medium and kept in a thermostat at a specific temperature and humidity for a predetermined period. When diagnosing affected organs via the *wet chamber method* for the manifestation of sporulation in fungal diseases or exudate—with bacterial ones, affected organs are kept in conditions favourable for the pathogen, creating increased humidity by decomposing diseased plants or their parts on a moistened substrate (filter paper, sand and other fillers).

DIAGNOSIS OF FUNGAL DISEASES ON PLANTS

Preparation and analysis of microscopic preparations. On a clean glass slide, degreased with a 40% solution of ethyl alcohol, 1–2 drops of water are applied with a pipette. A small amount of mycelial plaque or spore mass is separated with a dissecting needle,

transferred to a drop of water and crushed with a second needle. If the mycelial plaque cannot be separated from the plant tissue, a small piece of the affected tissue is separated with a sharp scalpel or dissecting needle, transferred to a drop of water, crushed with two needles and covered with a cover glass. The dimensions of the studied objects are large, so they are first examined with a small magnification of the microscope and only for a more detailed study, a large magnification is used.

Keeping plant material affected by fungi at high humidity. The bottom and lid of the Petri dish are lined with wet filter paper, preventing the accumulation of water at the bottom of the dish, to avoid rotting of the material.

Stems and similar parts of plants are superficially disinfected with alcohol or potassium permanganate. The material is cut into parts for faster germination of the mycelium on the surface, while the knife or scalpel is periodically burned (sterilized). The leaves or their parts are laid out in a cup.

Wet chambers are kept at a temperature of 15–20 °C. The incubation period is limited to one to three days, but sometimes can be extended up to two weeks. During this time, the humidity is periodically monitored and, if necessary, the filter paper in the cups is moistened.

Isolation of mushrooms in pure culture. Affected plants are washed in running water, and the affected parts are separated. If the plants wither, then the lower part of the stem and roots are taken for research. Plant parts are disinfected, washed with sterile water and cut into 1–2 cm pieces. The material is placed in Petri dishes with agar-agar and placed in a thermostat at 20 °C. As soon as the mycelium of the pathogen begins to germinate from the sections and moves to the nutrient substrate, it is transferred to a clean nutrient medium in another cup. After that, the mushroom is determined by the type of sporulation.

Phytopathogenic fungi are identified mainly by morphological features of fruiting bodies and spores.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Petri dishes
- Filter paper
- Tweezers
- Volumetric flasks
- Distilled water
- Spirit bottle
- Agar-agar
- Meat peptone agar
- Glucose

Equipment:

- UV lamps
- Microscopes
- Test tubes
- Microbiological loops
- Autoclave
- Thermostat
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

Spread of diseases determined using the formula:

$$P = \frac{n \times 100}{N}$$

where P is the spread of the disease;

N – the total number of plants in the sample;

n – the number of affected organs (plants), %.

Development of diseases determined using the formula

$$R = \frac{\sum(a \times b) \times 100}{N \times K}$$

Where R – intensity of disease development (point or percentage);

$\sum(a \times b)$ – the sum of the products of the number of plants by the corresponding score or percentage of damage;

K – the highest score on the accounting scale;

N – the total number of accounting plants.

REMARKS

Keys to identifying disease types

1. (4) The whole plant is affected
2. (3) The plant is depressed. Loss of turgor causes yellowing and wilting. The causes may be blockage of the vascular system by microorganisms, damage to the root system, lack of moisture in the soil, damage by higher flower parasites, mechanical damage, poisoning by toxins..... *Withering*
3. (2). The plant is deformed, the number of shortened shoots is increased, the entire plant may have shortened or wrinkled leaves..... *General deformation*
4. (1). Individual plant organs are affected.
5. (8). On the affected parts of plants, dying areas of tissue or individual organs have changed their shape.
6. (7). On the leaves, less often on other organs, there is a dying off of certain areas of tissues or a decrease in chlorophyll in the green organs of plants. On organs rich in nutrients and water, dying covers only the surface layers of the tissue, without spreading deep. *Spots*

7. (5). Change in the shape of affected plant organs. Ugliness, lignification, adhesions and other forms may be noted. *Deformation*
8. (11). Affected organs are covered with tubercles or mold.
9. (10). On the vegetative or generative organs - gray, white, brown, brown or black, such that the mold is easily erased, the epidermis under it is without damage.
 *Raises*
10. (8). On the affected organs - tubercles, piles of spores, covered with epidermis or protruding from the cracks of plant tissue; tubercles can be yellow, brown, orange, brown, black. *Pustules*
11. (14). Affected organs soften or grow abnormally.
12. (13). Organs rich in nutrients and water (roots, fruits, stems, tubers, etc.) soften and rot. The lesion can cover all tissues, spreading deep into the organ.
 *Rotten*
13. (11). Abnormal growth of individual plant organs of different sizes and shapes.
 *Growths*
14. (8). Other symptoms of damage.
15. (16). Affected organs turn into hard, dark, leathery formations or a black dust-like mass, a liquid that hardens in the air is released from diseased plant parts.
16. (17). Fruits or seeds turn into dark dense formations of black colour with a smooth or rough surface. *Mummification*
17. (18). Affected organs (grain, stems, leaves) are destroyed and turn into a black or brown powdery mass. *Organ destruction (soot)*
18. (14). Cracks form on diseased plants, from which a liquid is released that hardens in the air. *Gum flow*

REFERENCES

Maryutin, F.M. (2008). Phytopathology: a study guide / Ed. F.M. Maryutin. Kharkiv: Espada. p.552

Shevchuk, V.K. & Tanasov, S.S. (2003). General phytopathology. Kamianets-Podilskyi, p.56

1.2.3. Assessment of pest

PRINCIPLE

The methods of pest detection have been improved during the last decades thanks to the increasing knowledge about their development cycles, harmful phases and the nature of their damage. As well, various devices began to be used for this purpose. Therefore, the existing methods for detection and accounting of pests can be divided into visual and instrumental ones.

PROCEDURE

The level of damage by pests is determined only in case of detection of those that cause severe suppression or death of plants (intra-stem, gnawing, leaf-gnawing, etc.).

Recording the number of pests that hibernate or are in the soil in a certain period of its life cycle, determined by the method of excavation, soil sampling and analysis. The following pests are counted in this way: beet weevils, tuber weevils, Colorado potato beetle, beet weevil, larvae of roaches, wireworms, winter caterpillars and gnawing scoops. In the fall, excavations are carried out in the fields intended for winter crops, while in the fields designated for corn, sunflower, sugar beet, and vegetable crops are done in spring, after the soil has dried. The scoring pits are placed on two diagonals of the field or in a checkerboard pattern. The size of the pit is 50 x 50 cm, depth - up to 50 cm. On an area of up to 50 hectares, 12 pits are dug, 51-100 hectares - 16 pits, over 100 hectares - for every next 50 hectares - an additional 4 pits. The soil is selected from the pit gradually, in layers, poured on a tarpaulin or film and carefully sifted with hands. Detected insects are selected, counted and placed in a glass vessel filled with a solution of concentrated table salt. In the room, the insects are washed with clean water and their number is determined by species.

Accounting for pests on the soil surface is conducted to determine their number in the fields in the seedling phase. The number of mealybug larvae on winter crops, beet weevils, tuber weevils, mealybugs and blackworms, shield beetles, etc. is recorded with this method. On each examined field, the 50 x 50 cm registration sites are inspected by overlaying the frame, placing them evenly along two diagonals of the field, the number of pests is counted per 1 m². On a field of 100-200 hectares, it is enough to inspect 20 plots.

Insects that are on plants and feed on stems, leaves, or generative organs (leaf weevils, seed weevils, bugs, thrips bugs, leafhoppers, thrips, adults of flies and sawflies, bread bugs, leeches, Colorado beetle, aphids, caterpillars of leaf-gnawing scoops, etc.), are detected and counted by mowing with an entomological net (ordinary row and narrow-row crops) and by examining individual plants (row crops). On row crops, 100 plants are examined, i.e., 5 each in 20 places or on two adjacent rows in 10 places of the field. On ordinary row and narrow-row crops, the surveyor, moving along the field, sweeps the net in front of him, hits the plants with it, and after 10 sweeps, selects a catch in a bank, at the bottom of which there is cotton wool soaked in ether, and counts indoors. On one field, 50-100 sweeps of the net are made in 5-10 places. For calculations, 2 sweeps are conventionally equated to 1 m.

The accounting of butterflies hiding in the thickets of plants during the day (meadow butterfly, species of scoops, pyaduns) is carried out by counting the number of flying

individuals when crossing the field for a certain length of the route (10-50-100 steps). Petlyuk's box is used to record small jumping insects (cicadas, fleas).

Pests with a hidden way of life are detected using this method. To determine the number of intra-stem species (larvae of stem fleas, grain flies, bread flies, etc.), samples of 10 plants are taken at the registration sites.

The sheaths of the cereal leaves are bent to reveal the larvae of the Hessian fly, then the stem is dissected to reveal the 4 intra-stem species. To detect the cabbage fly, the root neck is inspected immediately after planting the seedlings. When accounting for leaf-mining pests, plants with mines are counted at 10 registration sites, and then, breaking the mines, the number of live larvae in them is counted.

Damage to leguminous crops by insects that feed on seeds (granuloids, pea fruit borer, acacia firefly, etc.) is taken into account before harvesting. To do this, 400 beans are selected in different places of the field and, after opening them, they count the pest.

The number of rodents on field crops is determined by the method of route inspection of a plot of 0.5 ha in fields up to 100 ha and 1 ha in larger areas. To do this, the number of colonies and burrows is counted along the diagonal of the field for 1 km on a strip 5 m wide. The presence of inhabited burrows is established by trampling them during the day and checking that they are open the next morning. Surveys are conducted in spring and autumn.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Entomological net
- Fishing
- Pheromone
- Glue traps
- Ethyl alcohol
- Flasks
- Petlyuk's box
- Accounting frame
- Decoy traps

CALCULATIONS

$$W=A \times a / h$$

where: W– weight loss of harvest from one individual; kg,

A– harvest of undamaged plants; kg

a– harvest of damaged plants; kg,

h– average pest density.

$$V=(A-a)\times 100/A$$

where: V– relative crop loss, %.

$$Te=Z-P/B$$

where: Te is the economic threshold of harmfulness (ex ha⁻¹);

Z — expenses for the protection of 1 ha of sowing, hryvnias;

B — cost of crop loss from one individual, hryvnias;

P — is the culture profitability rate (%)

$$B=A-a/Chn-Cho$$

where: B is the share of the saved crop per one destroyed pest;

A — yield from 1 ha (sq. m) of cultivated area, kg or hryvnias;

a — yield from 1 ha (sq. m) of uncultivated area, kg or hryvnias;

Chn - pest density per 1 ha (sq. m) of uncultivated area;

Cho is the pest density per 1 ha (sq. m) of treated area.

REMARKS

Depending on the location of the pest and its damage to various plant organs, different accounting methods are chosen

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Pokoziy, Y.T., Pysarenko, V.M., Dovhan', S.V., Dolya, M.M., Pysarenko, P.V., Mamchur, R.M. & Pasichnyk, L.P. (2010). Monitoring pests of agricultural crops. Kyiv: Agricultural education [in Ukrainian: Моніторинг шкідників сільськогосподарських культур. К.: Аграрна освіта].

1.3. Oat

1.3.1. Assessment of diseases

PRINCIPLE

The assessment of diseases in oat is essential for maintaining crop health, optimizing yield, minimizing economic losses, promoting sustainable agriculture, and supporting research and development efforts in oat production. By identifying and managing diseases effectively, farmers can ensure the long-term viability and profitability of oat cultivation.

PROCEDURE

The health status of the plants is evaluated twice (cereals BBCH 39-75). For that, fungal infection is determined on 25 randomly selected plants per plot. The plants are visually evaluated for disease severity and rated on a scale from 0 to 4. The disease index (DI) is calculated for the diseases as a percentage.

Moreover, after visual observations of the disease infection are made, infected leaf/root/base of the stem/pods tissue samples are taken to the laboratory, and the pathogens are identified under a microscope using aqueous mounting media. The species of fungi are identified on the basis of the mycological keys and monographs. The identification of each isolate is conducted twice.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Mycological keys and monographs
- Potato dextrose agar

Equipment:

- Light microscope Nikon Eclipse

REFERENCES

Metodyka Integrowanej Produkcji pszenicy ozimej i jarej. (2023)
http://piorin.gov.pl/download/gfx/piorin/pl/defaultstronaopisowa/1328/5/1/metodyka_ip_pszenica_-_zatwierdzona_lipiec_2023_do_obligatoryjnago_stosowania_od_01.01.2024r.pdf

Metodyka Integrowanej Produkcji soi. (2023)
http://piorin.gov.pl/download/gfx/piorin/pl/defaultstronaopisowa/1328/4/1/metodyka_ip_soi_-_zatwierdzona_2023.pdf

Marcinkowska, J. (2012). Determination of sensu lato types of fungi important in plant pathology. Ed: Powszechne Wydawnictwo Rolnicze i Leśne: Warszawa, Poland, p. 622.

Dugan, F. (2006). The identification of fungi. In an Illustrated Introduction, with Keys, Glossary, and Guide to Literature; The American Phytopathological Society Press: St. Paul, MA, USA, p. 176.

1.3.2. Assessment of pests

PRINCIPLE

Visual lustration of pest occurrence or pests' specific damages is the main method in assessing plant health. Assessment of pests is correlated with crop protection and economic impact, as assessing pests in oat is essential for preventing economic losses by maintaining healthy oat crops and ensuring a consistent supply of high-quality plants for various purposes, pest management and environmental impact.

PROCEDURE

Table 1. Protocol for assessment of pests in oat.

Crop	Measurement	Protocol
Oat	<i>Oulema</i> sp.	Evaluation of the occurrence of larvae and the damage area (BBCH 39 - 77) is performed twice during the growing period, by visual inspections on 30

		randomly selected stems/plot (in the case of cereal mixtures - 30 stems of each cereal in the mixture/plot). The number of damaged stems, and the percentage of damage area on leaves are recorded.
	Aphids	Observations on aphids are carried out in the same way as in the case of aphids on potatoes, twice in the growing season (BBCH 39 -77).
	<i>Chlorops pumilionis</i> Bjerk.	Visual assessment on 20 consecutive stems in 5 different randomly selected places/plot (100 stems/plot) (BBCH 71-77). Damage caused by larvae is classified using a three-stage scale, where the individual degrees mean: 1 - weak damage, the spike is completely extended from the leaf sheath, a long, shallow furrow below the spike is visible; 2 - moderate damage, the spike is partially hidden in the leaf sheath; 3 - severe damage, stems not sprouted, strongly shortened, furrow deep.
	Agromyzidae	Evaluation of the damaged area (BBCH 39 - 77), twice during the growing period, visual inspections on 30 randomly selected stems/plot (in the case of cereal mixtures - 30 stems of each cereal in the mixture/plot). The number of damaged stems and the percentage of damage area on leaves are recorded.
	<i>Eurygaster maura</i> (L.)	Inspection of crops for the presence of insects, twice (BBCH 31-77), visual inspections on 30 randomly selected stems/plot (in the case of cereal mixtures - 30 stems of each cereal in the mixture/plot).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Not equipment needed

REFERENCES

Methodology of integrated winter and spring wheat production. (2023) http://piorin.gov.pl/download/gfx/piorin/pl/defaultstronaopisowa/1328/5/1/metodyka_ip_pszienica_za_twierdzona_lipiec_2023_do_obligatoryjnago_stosowania_od_01.01.2024r..pdf

Pisarek, M. (1999). Szkodliwość skrzypionek (*Oulema* spp.) dla zbóż jarych w siewach czystych i mieszanych. *Progress in Plant Protection*. 39(2):413-415.

Guide to signaling the protection of cereals <https://www.ior.poznan.pl/plik,3601,poradnik-sygnalizatora-ochrony-zboz-pdf>

1.4. Potato

1.4.1. Plant growth

PRINCIPLE

Measurements related to plant growth can provide insights into the overall health and vigour of potato plants. These measurements include plant height, stem thickness, leaf area, number of branches, number of leaves, DW/FW aerial part, and shrub volume. Comparing these measurements over time can help assessing the growth rate and identifying abnormalities or stunted growth.

PROCEDURE

Plant height, stem thickness and shrub volume are measured with a measuring tape.

For leaf area, each leaf is first scanned with EPSON Scan and then the leaf area is calculated using ImageJ Software.

Number of branches and number of leaves is calculated manually by observation.

Finally, DW/FW is done by weighing the fresh weight of the plant, letting it to dry for 72 h at 60 °C and re-weighing the resulting material.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Measuring tape

Equipment:

- Oven
- Scan
- Software: ImageJ

CALCULATIONS

$$DW/FW = \frac{\text{Dry weight}}{\text{Fresh weight}} \text{ (g)}$$

REFERENCES

Wagg, C., Hann, S., Kupriyanovich, Y. & Li, S. (2021). Timing of short period water stress determines potato plant growth, yield and tuber quality. *Agricultural Water Management*, 247, 106731.

1.4.2. Root/shoot ratio

PRINCIPLE

For determination of the overall health of the crop plants and plant growth, the fresh and dry weight of the crop plants is measured 3 times during the growing season.

PROCEDURE

For measurement of fresh weight:

1. A subsample of plants from each experimental plot is removed from the soil and any lost soil is washed off with deionized water.
2. Each plant is divided into shoot and root and weighed.

For dry weight:

1. The shoots and roots are dried at 80 °C until they reach a constant weight.
2. Then, they are transferred to a desiccator to cool.
3. Shoots and roots are weighed.
4. Root/shoot ratio is calculated based on the dry weight measurements.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Scale for weighing
- Drying oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Root/shoot ratio} = \frac{\text{Root weight (g)}}{\text{Shoot weight (g)}}$$

REFERENCES

Mokany, K., Raison, R.J. & Prokushkin, A.S. (2006). Critical analysis of root: shoot ratios in terrestrial biomes. *Global Change Biology*, 12(1), 84-96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2005.001043.x>.

Williams, J.D., McCool, D.K., Reardon, C.L., Douglas, C.L., Albrecht, S.L. & Rickman, R.W. (2013). Root: shoot ratios and belowground biomass distribution for Pacific Northwest dryland crops. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 68(5), 349-360. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.68.5.349>.

1.4.3. Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence measurement

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is one of the most widely used parameters in green plants to monitor the modulation and alterations of the photosynthetic process under stress (Misra et al., 2012). A widely used chlorophyll fluorescence technique is the pulse modulated fluorescence measurement method

described by Schrieber et al. (1986). With this technique, 4 parameters of great relevance for the study of the state of photosystem II (PSII) can be determined. These are (López-González et al., 2020):

- F_v/F_m , the maximum efficiency of PSII: following exposure to darkness, reaction centres of PSII are typically open ($F = F_0$), non-photochemical quenching is negligible ($NPQ = 0$) and the fluorescence yield is at its peak. In this state, PSII's quantum yield reaches its maximum and saturation pulses (F_v) cause a rise in fluorescence. A decrease of this parameter usually denotes physical damages in the antenna system of PSII.
- Φ_{II} , the effective photochemical quantum yield of PSII: quantifies the proportion of light absorbed by the PSII-related chlorophyll that is utilized in the quantum yield. It can reveal information about the linear electron flow's speed and, therefore, serves as an indicator of the total photosynthetic capacity *in vivo* (Maxwell and Johnson 2000).
- Φ_{NPQ} , the measurement of regulated non-photochemical non-fluorescent energy dissipation (as heat): is linearly related to heat dissipation and ranges from 0 to infinity. Although this varies amongst different species, the typical values in a healthy plant are in the range of 0.5–3.5 at saturating light intensities (Maxwell and Johnson, 2000). Excessive photon flux density is indicated by high values of this parameter, which causes the plant to defend itself by releasing the energy as heat. If this value rises, it means that the photosynthetic mechanism is producing more energy than it needs, but the plant can control this excess to prevent damage.
- Φ_{NO} , the measurement of non-regulated emission of energy (as fluorescence): it determines the non-regulated energy loss as fluorescence (Klughammer et al., 2008). Elevated values of this parameter suggest that the plant is having problems adjusting to incident radiation due to inefficient photochemical energy conversion and protective regulatory mechanisms. Extremely high values imply that the plant has been damaged or is likely to be damaged because they show that the PSII reaction centres are blocked, inhibiting the development of a trans-thylakoid proton gradient.

PROCEDURE

The measures are carried out *in situ* using the MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0 (PhotosynQ, East Lansing, MI, USA) (Álvarez-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

1. The plant (or branch) is covered with a black bag during at least 20 min before taking the measurement.
2. After 20 min, the fluorimeter is placed on a leaf to measure the maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II (F_v/F_m). The MultispeQ v2.0 is used to run the "Fv/Fm in the dark" protocol, also linked to the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>].

3. With the help the “rapid information dense experimental sequence” (RIDES) protocol (“Photosynthesis RIDES 2.0”), available on the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>, (Kuhlgert et al., 2016)] the different parameters related to chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is obtained: the effective quantum yield of the photosystem II photochemical reactions (Φ_{II}), the regulated energy dissipation in the form of heat (Φ_{NPQ}), and the non-regulated energy dissipation (Φ_{NO} , fluorescence emitted).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Dark bags

Equipment:

- MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0

CALCULATIONS

1. $\Phi_{II} + \Phi_{NPQ} + \Phi_{NO} = 1$
2. $\Phi_{NPQ} = 1 - \Phi_{II} - \Phi_{NO}$
3. $\Phi_{NO} = F_s/F_m$
4. $F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_0)/F_m$

REMARKS

For a correct measurement of F_v/F_m it is essential that the plants (or leaves) are in complete darkness for at least 20 min to open all reaction centres of PSII.

REFERENCES

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1.4.4. Chlorophyll content

PRINCIPLE

The chlorophyll content in potato leaves provides information about plant health, photosynthetic rate, and the concentration of nitrogen. It reflects the growth and physiological status of the plant.

The accurate analysis of chlorophyll concentration in potato plants is important for nitrogen management in precision agriculture (Liu et al., 2020).

PROCEDURE

Sample Preparation

Healthy potato leaves are selected for analysis. The same leaves are chosen in the different plants to ensure representative sampling. Damaged leaves must be removed. A sufficient number of leaves must be collected for accurate measurements.

Leaf Extraction

Leaf discs or small pieces (0.05 to 0.1 g) are cut from the selected leaves using a leaf punch or scissor. The leaf samples are placed in a clean and labelled 2 mL Eppendorf and plant material is crushed with liquid nitrogen.

Extraction Solvent

One mL of ice cold 80% acetone solvent is added to the Eppendorf to extract chlorophyll from the leaf samples. Make sure the solvent is ice-cold and avoid light exposition to prevent chlorophyll degradation.

Incubation

The tubes containing the leaf samples and extraction solvent are sealed and placed in the dark at a cool temperature (4 °C) for a specific period (24 h) to allow the chlorophyll to be released into the solvent.

Centrifugation

After the incubation period, the tubes are centrifuged at 12,000 g at 4 °C for 10 min. This will separate the leaf debris from the extracted chlorophyll solution.

Absorbance Measurement

The clear supernatant is transferred from each tube to a cuvette or microplate. A spectrophotometer is used to measure the absorbance of the chlorophyll solution at specific wavelengths.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Liquid nitrogen
- 80% acetone

Equipment:

- Scissor
- Eppendorf centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer
- 2 mL Eppendorf tubes

CALCULATIONS

For pigment content calculation the equations of Wellburn (1994) will be used:

- Chlorophyll *a* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(12.21 \times A_{663}) - (2.81 \times A_{646})$
- Chlorophyll *b* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(20.13 \times A_{646}) - (5.03 \times A_{663})$
- Total chlorophyll ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = Cl *a* + Cl *b*
- Carotenoids ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(1000 \times A_{470} - 3.27 \times \text{Cl } a - 104 \times \text{Cl } b) / 227$

REFERENCES

Liu, N., Xing, Z., Zhao, R., Qiao, L., Li, M., Liu, G. & Sun, H. (2020). Analysis of chlorophyll concentration in potato crop by coupling continuous wavelet transform and spectral variable optimization. *Remote Sensing*, 12(17), 2826.

1.4.5. Pest and disease monitoring

PRINCIPLE

Regular monitoring and measurement of pests and diseases affecting potato plants is important for early detection and appropriate management actions. This includes identifying and counting pests (such as aphids or potato beetles) or assessing disease severity through visual inspection or quantitative methods.

PROCEDURE

The tubers are randomly dug out from 1 m of potato row from each plot. The number of plants and tubers is counted, and tubers are selected to fractions based on their size. On the tubers diseases are assessed:

1. *Streptomyces scabies* (scale 1-9, where 9 means healthy tubers, 5 – means 16%-20% of the tubers surface covered with *S. scabies*, and 1 – more than 50% of the tuber surface covered with *S. scabies*);
2. Internal heat necrosis (% per tuber);
3. Hollow heart (% per tuber)

Table 2. Protocol for assessment of pests in potato.

Crop	Measurement	Protocol
Potato	<i>Leptinotarsa decemlineata</i> Say.	Percentage of defoliation of plants by Colorado potato beetles is visually estimated and the number of egg masses, instars, and adults per plant are

		assessed twice (31 – 70 BBCH) on 30 randomly selected plants per plot
	Aphids	Evaluation of pest occurrence intensity (31 – 70 BBCH) by visual inspections on 30 randomly selected plants per plot are conducted twice Above-ground parts will be inspected for the presence of pests and the number of aphids will be recorded

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Shovel
- Measuring tape
- Handbooks

REFERENCES

Kolodziejczyk, M., Szmigiel, A. & Ropek, D. (2009). Production effectiveness of potato protection using selected insecticides for potato beetle control (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say). *Acta Scientiarum Polonorum. Agricultura*, 8(4).

Methodology of integrated potato production. Warszawa (2023). http://piorin.gov.pl/download/gfx/piorin/pl/defaultstronaopisowa/1328/5/1/metodyka_ip_ziemniaka_z_atwierdzona_2023_do_obligatoryjnego_stosowania_od_01.01.2024.pdf

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1.4.6. Phenological stage

PRINCIPLE

The BBCH scale is a standardized system used to identify and describe the growth stages of various plant species, including potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum* L.). It provides a common language for researchers, agronomists, and farmers to estimate the development of plants throughout their life cycle.

The BBCH scale for potatoes defines specific stages of development based on observable characteristics, such as leaf appearance, stem elongation, flowering, and tuber

formation. Numerical codes, which allow for consistent tracking and comparison of plant growth among different locations and times, are assigned to the different stages.

PROCEDURE

Table 3. Phenological growth stages and BBCH-identification keys of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.)

Phenological growth stages and BBCH-identification keys of potato (<i>Solanum tuberosum</i> L.)			
Principal growth stage 0: Sprouting/Germination			
Code		Description of development from tuber	Description of development from seed
00	000	Innate or enforced dormancy, tuber not sprouted	Dry seed
01	001	Beginning of sprouting: sprouts visible (< 1 mm)	Beginning of seed imbibition
02	002	Sprouts upright (< 2 mm)	
03	003	End of dormancy: sprouts 2–3 mm	Seed imbibition complete
05	005	Beginning of root formation	Radicle (root) emerged from seed
07	007	Beginning of stem formation	Hypocotyl with cotyledons breaking
08	008	Stems growing towards soil surface, formation of scale leaves in the axils of which stolons will develop later	Hypocotyl with cotyledons growing towards soil surface
09	009	Emergence: stems break through soil surface	Emergence: cotyledons break through soil surface
Principal growth stage 1: Leaf development			
10	100	From tuber: first leaves begin to extend; from seeds: cotyledons completely unfolded	
11	101	1st leaf of main stem unfolded (> 4 cm)	
12	102	2nd leaf of main stem unfolded (> 4 cm)	
13	103	3rd leaf Auf main stem unfolded (> 4 cm)	
1.	10.	Stages continuous till...	
	109	9 or more leaves of main stem unfolded (> 4cm)	
	110	10th leaf of main stem unfolded (> 4 cm)	
	11.	Stages continuous till...	
	119	19. leaf of main stem unfolded (> 4 cm)	
	121	First leaf of 2 nd order branch above first inflorescence unfolded (> 4 cm)	
	122	2 nd leaf of 2 nd order branch above first inflorescence unfolded (> 4 cm)	
	131	First leaf of 3 rd order branch above 2 nd inflorescence unfolded (> 4 cm)	
	132	2nd leaf of 3 rd order branch above 2 nd inflorescence unfolded (> 4 cm)	
Principal growth stage 2: Formation of basal side shoots below and above soil surface (main stem)			
		First basal side shoot visible (> 5 cm)	

22	202	2 nd basal side shoot visible (> 5 cm)
23	203	3 rd basal side shoot visible (> 5 cm)
2.	20.	Stages continuous till . . .
29	209	9 or more basal side shoots visible (> 5 cm)
Principal growth stage 3: Main stem elongation (crop cover)		
31	301	Beginning of crop cover: 10% of plants meet between rows
32	302	20% off plants meet between rows
33	303	30% of plants meet between rows
34	304	40% of plants meet between rows
35	305	50% of plants meet between rows
36	306	60% of plants meet between rows
37	307	70% of plants meet between rows
38	308	80% of plants meet between rows
39	309	Crop cover complete: about 90% of plants meet between rows
Principal growth stage 4: Tuber formation		
40	400	Tuber initiation: swelling of first stolon tips to twice the diameter of subtending stolon
41	401	10% of total final tuber mass reached
42	402	20% of total final tuber mass reached
43	403	30% of total final tuber mass reached
44	404	40% of total final tuber mass reached
45	405	50% of total final tuber mass reached
46	406	60% of total final tuber mass reached
47	407	70% of total final tuber mass reached
48	408	Maximum of total tuber mass reached, tubers detach easily from stolons, skin set not yet complete (skin easily removable with thumb)
49	409	Skin set complete: (skin at apical end of tuber not removable with thumb) 95% of tubers in this stage
Principal growth stage 5: Inflorescence (cyme) emergence		
51	501	First individual buds (1–2 mm) of first inflorescence visible (main stem)
55	505	Buds of first inflorescence extended to 5 mm
59	509	First flower petals of first inflorescence visible
	521	Individual buds of 2 nd inflorescence visible (second order branch)
	525	Buds of 2 nd inflorescence extended to 5 mm open (main stem)
	529	First flower petals of 2 nd inflorescence visible above sepals
	531	Individuell buds of 3 rd inflorescence visible(3rd order branch)
	535	Buds of 3 rd inflorescence extended to 5 mm
	539	First flower petals of 3 rd inflorescence visible above sepals
	5N	N th inflorescence emerging
Principal growth stage 6: Flowering		
60	600	First open flowers in population

61	601	Beginning of flowering: 10% of flowers in the first inflorescence open (main stem)
62	602	20% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
63	603	30% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
64	604	40% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
65	605	Full flowering: 50% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
66	606	60% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
67	607	70% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
68	608	80% of flowers in the first inflorescence open
69	609	End of flowering in the first inflorescence
	621	Beginning of flowering: 10% of flowers in the 2 nd inflorescence open (second order branch)
	625	Full flowering: 50% of flowers in the 2 nd inflorescence open
	629	End of flowering in the 2 nd inflorescence
	631	Beginning of flowering: 10% of flowers in the 3 rd inflorescence open (third order branch)
	635	Full flowering: 50% of flowers in the 3 rd inflorescence open
	639	End of flowering in the 3 rd inflorescence
	6N	Nth inflorescence flowering
	6N9	End of flowering
Principal growth stage 7: Development of fruit		
70	700	First berries visible
71	701	10% of berries in the first fructification have reached full size (main stem)
72	702	20% of berries in the first fructification have reached full size
73	703	30% of berries in the first fructification have reached full size
	721	10% of berries in the 2 nd fructification have reached full size (second order branch)
	7N	Development of berries in N th fructification
	7N9	Nearly all berries in the N th fructification have reached full size (or have been shed)
Principal growth stage 8: Ripening of fruit and seed		
81	801	Berries in the first fructification still green, seed light-coloured (main stem)
85	805	Berries in the first fructification ochre-coloured or brownish
89	809	Berries in the first fructification shrivelled, seed dark
	821	Berries in the 2 nd fructification still green, seed light-coloured (second order branch)
	8N	Ripening of fruit and seed in nth fructification
Principal growth stage 9: Senescence		
91	901	Beginning of leaf yellowing
93	903	Most of the leaves yellowish
95	905	50% of the leaves brownish

97	907	Leaves and stem dead, stems bleached and dry
99	909	Harvested product

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

No equipment needed

REFERENCES

BBCH scale specifically for potato
<https://www.politicheagricole.it/flex/AppData/WebLive/Agrometeo/MIEPFY800/BBCHengl2001.pdf>
 [Accessed 28th August 2023]

1.5. Rapeseed

1.5.1. Date of emergence

PRINCIPLE

The date of emergence is important for crop management, pest and disease management, yield potential assessment, crop rotation planning, and research purposes. It provides valuable information for making informed decisions throughout the growing season and optimizing rapeseed production.

PROCEDURE

Emerging date is recorded when 75% of the plants have emerged. The emergence takes place from the fall, under normal humidity conditions, and during the winter or spring when the fall was dry.

REFERENCES

Oskouie, B. (2012). Effect of mother plant nitrogen application on seed establishment of rapeseed. *International Journal of AgriScience*, 2(5), 444-450.

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1.5.2. Technical maturity

PRINCIPLE

Technical maturity in rapeseed involves monitoring the growth, development, and characteristics of the crop. It plays a crucial role in determining the optimal harvest timing, ensuring grain quality, making informed crop management decisions, and advancing research and breeding efforts in rapeseed cultivation.

PROCEDURE

It is noted when the humidity of the grains has reached 17%. At this moment, the field is suitable for mechanized harvesting.

REFERENCES

Neagu Frăsin, L.B. (2015). Observations regarding the agronomical value and the use of winter barley cultivars in Southern muntenia's ecosystems. *Annals. Food Science and Technology*, 16(1), 168-174.

1.5.3. Moisture dynamics

PRINCIPLE

The moisture dynamics in rapeseed, can vary throughout its growth stages. During the early stages of growth, rapeseed plants require adequate moisture for germination and establishment. As rapeseed plants mature, they become more resilient to drought conditions. However, during the critical stages of flowering and seed development, sufficient moisture is crucial for optimal yield. Insufficient moisture during these stages can lead to poor seed formation and reduced yields. Monitoring the moisture levels in the soil and providing irrigation, when necessary, can help mitigating the impact of drought on rapeseed crops.

Harvesting is typically done when the rapeseed pods have reached maturity and the moisture content of the seeds is around 17%. Harvesting at this moisture level helps ensure proper seed quality and facilitates storage. Monitoring moisture levels during harvesting is essential to prevent issues such as shattering and to optimize the efficiency of the harvesting process.

PROCEDURE

The determinations start once the grains have attained a dark yellow colour, advanced to a waxy consistency, and the humidity is approximately 27%. Measurements are taken every 2-3 days until the moisture level reaches 17%, which is deemed the date of technical maturity.

REFERENCES

Khodabin, G., Lightburn, K., Hashemi, S.M., Moghada, M.S. & Jalilian, A. (2022). Evaluation of nitrate leaching, fatty acids, physiological traits and yield of rapeseed (*Brassica napus*) in response to tillage, irrigation and fertilizer management. *Plant Soil*, 473(1-2), 423-440.

1.5.4. Plant density per square meter

PRINCIPLE

Knowing the plant density in rapeseed is important for optimizing production, assessing crop performance, determining yield potential, allocating resources efficiently, and

advancing research and breeding efforts. It provides valuable insights into the establishment and growth of the crop, enabling farmers to make informed decisions for successful rapeseed cultivation.

PROCEDURE

a) In autumn at the end of vegetation or in spring at sunrise, determination is made when the rows are finished, the leaves have reached 2 cm in length and the appearance of new plants is no longer recorded. The end of vegetation is considered when the average air temperature in a row is below 0 °C for at least 3 days. For this determination, it is necessary to delimit an area of 0.5 sqm (with metric frame) in each plot. The metric frame with an inner side of 0.71 m must be fixed in such a way that its diagonal overlaps one of the rows of plants. The sides of the metric frame, so the ends of the 2 diagonals must be marked with stakes that are kept until harvesting. The number of plants per sqm is determined. In the 4 repetitions and in the sheets, the average of the determinations is entered; i.e., 530 plants m⁻².

b) The density of the plants (in the spring, when the plants started growing) is checked at the same points established previously with the metric frame.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Metric frame

REFERENCES

Panasiewicz, K., Faligowska, A., Szymańska, G., Szukała, J., Ratajczak, K. & Sulewska, H. (2020). The effect of various tillage systems on productivity of narrow-leaved lupin-winter wheat-winter triticale-winter barley rotation. *Agronomy*, 10, 304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10020304>.

1.5.5. Visual observations of disease infection and pest attack

PRINCIPLE

Plant diseases are caused both by the action of unfavourable physical and chemical or other abiotic factors of the environment, and by microorganisms or organisms belonging to higher plants (flower parasites). Each parasitic organism or abiotic factor can cause a peculiar damage or disease, characterized by external signs, or symptoms. Symptoms of diseases can be either clearly visible to the naked eye, or barely noticeable, or hidden, which cannot be seen for some time. In order to properly protect plants from diseases, it is necessary to be able to recognize them, that is, to make the correct diagnosis based on a set of external signs.

PROCEDURE

Disease infection is visually observed, and infected leaf/root/base of the stem/pods tissue samples are taken to the laboratory, for pathogens' identification under a microscope using aqueous mounting media. The species of fungi are identified on the basis of the mycological keys and monographs. The identification of each isolate is conducted twice. Fungal and pests' infection is determined on 25 randomly selected plants per plot.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Microscope

1.5.6. Plant height

PRINCIPLE

Plant height is a key indicator for crop health and growth.

PROCEDURE

Plant height is determined in the waxing phase for 10 plants (taken in a row) from each repetition in the field. Measurements are taken from the base of the stem to the tip of the ear (without aristae).

1.6. Soybean

1.6.1. Date of emergence

PRINCIPLE

The date of emergence is important for crop management, pest and disease management, yield potential assessment, crop rotation planning, and research studies. It provides valuable information for taking informed decisions throughout the growing season and optimizing soybean production.

PROCEDURE

Date of emergence is recorded when 75% of the plants have emerged. The emergence takes place from the fall, under normal humidity conditions, and during the winter or spring when the fall was dry.

REFERENCES

Gao, F., Anderson, M.C., Johnson, D.M., Seffrin, R., Wardlow, B., Suyker, A., Diao, C. & Browning, D.M. (2021). Towards routine mapping of crop emergence within the season using the harmonized landsat and Sentinel-2 Dataset. *Remote Sensing*, 13, 5074. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13245074>.

Ma, C., Liu, M., Ding, F. et al. (2022). Wheat growth monitoring and yield estimation based on remote sensing data assimilation into the SAFY crop growth model. *Scientific Report*, 12, 5473. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-09535-9>.

1.6.2. Technical maturity

PRINCIPLE

Technical maturity in soybean involves monitoring the growth, development, and characteristics of the crop. It plays a crucial role in determining the optimal harvest time, ensuring grain quality, taking informed crop management decisions, and advancing research and breeding efforts in soybean cultivation.

PROCEDURE

It is recorded when the humidity of the grains has reached 17%. At this moment, the field is suitable for mechanized harvesting.

REFERENCES

Neagu Frăsin, L.B. (2015). Observations regarding the agronomical value and the use of winter barley cultivars in Southern muntenia's ecosystems. *Annals. Food Science and Technology*, 16(1), 168-174, 2015

1.6.3. Moisture dynamics

PRINCIPLE

The moisture dynamics in soybean can vary throughout the phenological cycle of the plants. During the early stages of growth, soybean requires adequate moisture for germination and establishment. As the plants mature, they become more resilient to drought conditions. However, during the critical stages of flowering and seed development, an adequate moisture is crucial for optimal yield. Insufficient moisture during these stages can lead to poor seed formation and reduced yields. Monitoring the moisture levels in the soil and providing irrigation, when necessary, can help mitigate the impact of drought stress on soybean crops.

Harvesting is typically done when the soybean pods have reached maturity, and the moisture content of the seeds is around 17%. Harvesting at this moisture level helps ensure proper seed quality and facilitates their storage. Monitoring moisture levels during harvesting is essential to prevent issues such as shattering and to optimize the efficiency of the harvesting process.

PROCEDURE

The determinations start once the grains have a dark yellow colour, waxy consistency, and the humidity is approximately 27%. Measurements are taken every 2-3 days until the moisture level reaches 17%, which is deemed the date of technical maturity.

REFERENCES

Johnsson, H. & Jansson, P.-E. (1991). Water balance and soil moisture dynamics of field plots with barley and grass ley. *Journal of Hydrology*, 129(1–4): 149-173.

Marchetti, C.F., Ugena, L., Humplík, J.F., Polák, M., Čavar Zeljković, S., Podlešáková, K., Fürst, T., De Diego, N. & Spíchal, L. (2019). A novel image-based screening method to study water-deficit response and recovery of barley populations using canopy dynamics phenotyping and simple metabolite profiling. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 10, 1252. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2019.01252

1.6.4. Plant density per square meter

PRINCIPLE

Knowing the plant density in soybean is important for optimizing production, assessing crop performance, determining yield potential, allocating resources efficiently, and advancing in research and breeding efforts. It provides valuable insights into the establishment and growth of the crop, enabling farmers to take informed decisions for successful soybean cultivation.

PROCEDURE

In autumn, at the end of vegetation, or in spring, at sunrise, determination is made when the rows are finished, the leaves have reached 2 cm in length and the appearance of new plants is no longer recorded. The cessation of vegetation is considered when the average air temperature in a row is below 0 °C for at least 3 days. For this determination, it is necessary to delimit an area of 0.5 m² (with metric frame) in each plot. The metric frame with an inner side of 0.71 m must be fixed in such a way that its diagonal overlaps one of the rows of plants. The sides of the metric frame, so the ends of the 2 diagonals must be marked with stakes that are kept until harvesting. The number of plants per m² is determined. In the 4 repetitions and in the sheets, the average of the determinations is entered; i.e., 530 plants m⁻².

The density of the plants (in the spring, when the plants started growing) is checked at the same timing points established previously with the metric frame.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Metric frame

REFERENCES

Panasiewicz, K., Faligowska, A., Szymańska, G., Szukała, J., Ratajczak, K. & Sulewska, H. (2020). The effect of various tillage systems on productivity of narrow-leaved lupin-winter wheat-winter triticale-winter barley rotation. *Agronomy*, 10, 304. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10020304>.

1.6.5. Plant height

PRINCIPLE

Plant height is a key indicator for crop health and growth.

PROCEDURE

It is determined in the waxing phase for 10 plants (taken in a row) from each repetition in the field. Measurements are taken from the base of the stem to the tip of the ear (without aristae).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Measuring tape

1.6.6. Assessment of diseases

PRINCIPLE

Measuring diseases in soybean is vital for effective crop management. Timely and accurate assessments enable early detection, facilitating prompt intervention strategies. Monitoring disease prevalence helps to minimize yield losses, optimize resource use, and ensure the overall health and productivity of soybean crops.

PROCEDURE

The health status of the plants is evaluated twice (soybean BBCH 51-85). Fungal infection is determined on 25 randomly selected plants per plot. The plants are visually evaluated for disease severity and rated on a scale of 0 to 4. The disease index (DI) is calculated as a percentage.

Visual observations of the disease infection are made, and infected leaf/root/base of the stem/pods tissue samples are taken to the laboratory, and the pathogens are identified under a microscope using aqueous mounting media. The species of fungi are identified on the basis of the mycological keys and monographs. The identification of each isolate is conducted twice.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Paper bags to transfer plant samples
- Potato dextrose agar
- Handbook for fungi identification

Equipment:

- Light microscope Nikon Eclipse

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1.6.7. Assessment of pests
PRINCIPLE

Visual lustration of pest occurrence or of the specific damages related to the pests is the main method in assessing plant health.

PROCEDURE

Table 4. Protocol for assessment of pests in soybean

Crop	Measurement	Protocol
Soybean	<i>Sitona</i> spp.	Evaluation of the level of damages by adults (BBCH 10 – 19) by visual inspections on 30 randomly selected plants per plot is conducted twice. The number of plants with damages, and the size of damages, are recorded.
	Aphids	Observations on aphids are carried out in the same way as in the case of aphids on potatoes, twice in growth season (BBCH 30-69).
	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i> Popp.; <i>Adelphocoris lineolatus</i> Goeze	Inspection of crops for the presence of imagines and larvae is done twice (BBCH 21–75) with visual inspections on 30 randomly selected plants / plot.

	<i>Laspeyresia nigricana</i> F.	Analysis of pods harvested from 5 different places per plot (BBCH 70-89) (20 pods per place = 100 pods per plot), is estimated, and the value of damaged pods is given as percentage.
	<i>Bruchus rufimanus</i> Boh.	Analysis of pods harvested from 5 different places per plot (BBCH 89) (20 pods per place = 100 pods per plot), is estimated, and the value of beetles emerging is given as percentage.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Voice recorder

REFERENCES

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1.7. Sunflower

1.7.1. Phenological observations

PRINCIPLE

The growth and development of sunflower is evaluated according to the following indicators: seed yield, fat and protein content, oil yield per kilogram, oil quality, inflorescence diameter, weight of 1000 seeds, huskiness, shell, duration of the vegetation period, suitability for mechanized technology production, resistance to diseases and pests, resistance to lodging and shedding, and to adverse weather conditions. The registered area of the site is 25 m², the repetition is 4 times.

PROCEDURE

During the growing season, the following phenological phases are registered:

1. Full emergence - more than 75% of the unfolded cotyledon leaves appeared on the soil surface;

2. Complete formation of an inflorescence – at least the 75% of plants have formed inflorescences of about 2 cm in diameter;
3. Full flowering – 75% of flowering plants have appeared. Blooming plants are considered to be plants in which reeds have been formed, and tubular flowers have begun to open in the first rows of the inflorescence;
4. Physiological ripeness (cessation of achenes in the 75% of plants) – the back side of the inflorescence has acquired a yellow colour, and the petals of the reed flowers have faded;
5. Harvest ripeness – in the 75% of the plants, the back side of the inflorescence has acquired a brown colour.

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1.7.2. Pest determination

PRINCIPLE

The methods of pest detection have been improved during the last decades thanks to the increasing knowledge about their development cycles, harmful phases and the nature of their damage. As well, various devices began to be used for this purpose. Therefore, the existing methods for detection and accounting of pests can be divided into visual and instrumental ones.

PROCEDURE

The level of damage by pests is determined only in case of detection of those that cause severe suppression or death of plants (intra-stem, gnawing, leaf-gnawing, etc.).

Recording the number of pests that hibernate or are in the soil in a certain period of its life cycle, determined by the method of excavation, soil sampling and analysis. The following pests are counted in this way: beet weevils, tuber weevils, Colorado potato beetle, beet weevil, larvae of roaches, wireworms, winter caterpillars and gnawing scoops. In the fall, excavations are carried out in the fields intended for winter crops, while in the fields designated for corn, sunflower, sugar beet, and vegetable crops are done in spring, after the soil has dried. The scoring pits are placed on two diagonals of the field or in a checkerboard pattern. The size of the pit is 50 x 50 cm, depth - up to 50 cm. On an area of up to 50 hectares, 12 pits are dug, 51-100 hectares - 16 pits, over 100 hectares - for every next 50 hectares - an additional 4 pits. The soil is selected from the pit gradually, in layers, poured on a tarpaulin or film and carefully sifted with hands. Detected insects are selected, counted and placed in a glass vessel filled with a solution

of concentrated table salt. In the room, the insects are washed with clean water and their number is determined by species.

Accounting for pests on the soil surface is conducted to determine their number in the fields in the seedling phase. The number of mealybug larvae on winter crops, beet weevils, tuber weevils, mealybugs and blackworms, shield beetles, etc. is recorded with this method. On each examined field, the 50 x 50 cm registration sites are inspected by overlaying the frame, placing them evenly along two diagonals of the field, the number of pests is counted per square meter. On a field of 100-200 hectares, it is enough to inspect 20 plots.

Insects that are on plants and feed on stems, leaves, or generative organs (leaf weevils, seed weevils, bugs, thrips bugs, leafhoppers, thrips, adults of flies and sawflies, bread bugs, leeches, Colorado beetle, aphids, caterpillars of leaf-gnawing scoops, etc.), are detected and counted by mowing with an entomological net (ordinary row and narrow-row crops) and by examining individual plants (row crops). On row crops, 100 plants are examined, i.e., 5 each in 20 places or on two adjacent rows in 10 places of the field. On ordinary row and narrow-row crops, the surveyor, moving along the field, sweeps the net in front of him, hits the plants with it, and after 10 sweeps, selects a catch in a bank, at the bottom of which there is cotton wool soaked in ether, and counts indoors. On one field, 50-100 sweeps of the net are made in 5-10 places. For calculations, 2 sweeps are conventionally equated to one meter.

The accounting of butterflies hiding in the thickets of plants during the day (meadow butterfly, species of scoops, pyaduns) is carried out by counting the number of flying individuals when crossing the field for a certain length of the route (10-50-100 steps). Petliuk's box is used to record small jumping insects (cicadas, fleas).

Pests with a hidden way of life are detected using this method. To determine the number of intra-stem species (larvae of stem fleas, grain flies, bread flies, etc.), samples of 10 plants are taken at the registration sites.

The sheaths of the cereal leaves are bent to reveal the larvae of the Hessian fly, then the stem is dissected to reveal the 4 intra-stem species. To detect the cabbage fly, the root neck is inspected immediately after planting the seedlings. When accounting for leaf-mining pests, plants with mines are counted at 10 registration sites, and then, breaking the mines, the number of live larvae in them is counted.

Damage to leguminous crops by insects that feed on seeds (granuloids, pea fruit borer, acacia firefly, etc.) is taken into account before harvesting. To do this, 400 beans are selected in different places of the field and, after opening them, they count the pest.

The number of rodents on field crops is determined by the method of route inspection of a plot of 0.5 ha in fields up to 100 ha and 1 ha in larger areas. To do this, the number of colonies and burrows is counted along the diagonal of the field for 1 km on a strip 5

m wide. The presence of inhabited burrows is established by trampling them during the day and checking that they are open the next morning. Surveys are conducted in spring and autumn.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Entomological net
- Fishing
- Pheromone
- Glue traps
- Ethyl alcohol
- Flasks
- Petlyuk's box
- Accounting frame
- Decoy traps

CALCULATIONS

$W=A \times a/h$

where: W– weight loss of harvest from one individual; kg,
A– harvest of undamaged plants; kg
a– harvest of damaged plants; kg,
h– average pest density.

$V=(A-a) \times 100/A$

where: V– relative crop loss,%.

$Te=Z-P/B$

where: Te is the economic threshold of harmfulness (ex ha⁻¹);
Z — expenses for the protection of 1 ha of sowing, hryvnias;
B — cost of crop loss from one individual, hryvnias;
P —is the culture profitability rate (%)

$B=A-a/Chn-Cho$

where: B is the share of the saved crop per one destroyed pest;
A — yield from 1 ha (sq. m) of cultivated area, kg or hryvnias;
a — yield from 1 ha (sq. m) of uncultivated area, kg or hryvnias;
Chn - pest density per 1 ha (sq. m) of uncultivated area;
Cho is the pest density per 1 ha (sq. m) of treated area.

REMARKS

Depending on the location of the pest and its damage to various plant organs, different accounting methods are chosen

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1.7.3. Disease determination

PRINCIPLE

Plant diseases are caused both by the action of unfavourable physical and chemical or other abiotic factors of the environment, and by microorganisms or organisms belonging to plants (flower parasites). Each parasitic organism or abiotic factor can cause a peculiar disease, characterized by external signs, or symptoms, or, otherwise, types of damage. Symptoms of diseases can be either clearly visible to the naked eye, or barely noticeable, or hidden, which cannot be seen for some time. In order to properly protect plants from diseases, it is necessary to be able to recognize them, that is, to make the correct diagnosis based on a set of external signs.

PROCEDURE

The *macroscopic or visual* method is used for the first diagnosis of disease, i.e., external inspection, comparison of damaged plants with healthy ones, with identification of disease symptoms with the naked eye. The most common types of diseases are: wilting, rotting, destruction of plant organs, spots, plaques, pustules, mummification, growths, gum bleeding.

On plants, diseases are detected by inspecting a certain number of plants in samples or on accounting plots. On a field of up to 100 hectares, 100 plants are examined - 5 each in 20 places or in two adjacent rows in 10 places. In the case of a larger area, 50 plants are additionally inspected for each subsequent 100 hectares, and in the case of a low density of the pest or weak plant damage by the disease, up to 200 plants in 20 places are inspected.

In the practice of diagnosing plant diseases, there may be cases when the external signs of two or more diseases coincide with each other, and the nature of these diseases and their causative agents are different. In such cases, additional diagnostic methods are used.

The microscopic method is more frequently employed, involving the examination of tissue sections or fungal sporulation, bacterial exudate, and viral inclusions under a

microscope. This method facilitates the identification of the causative agent or the nature of changes in affected tissues.

For a more precise definition of the causative agent, the cultural method is utilized—wherein the pathogenic organism is isolated on an artificial nutrient medium and kept in a thermostat at a specific temperature and humidity for a predetermined period. When diagnosing affected organs via the *wet chamber method* for the manifestation of sporulation in fungal diseases or exudate—with bacterial ones, affected organs are kept in conditions favourable for the pathogen, creating increased humidity by decomposing diseased plants or their parts on a moistened substrate (filter paper, sand and other fillers).

DIAGNOSIS OF FUNGAL DISEASES OF PLANTS

Preparation and analysis of microscopic preparations. On a clean glass slide, degreased with a 40% solution of ethyl alcohol, 1–2 drops of water are applied with a pipette. A small amount of mycelial plaque or spore mass is separated with a dissecting needle, transferred to a drop of water and crushed with a second needle. If the mycelial plaque cannot be separated from the plant tissue, a small piece of the affected tissue is separated with a sharp scalpel or dissecting needle, transferred to a drop of water, crushed with two needles and covered with a cover glass. The dimensions of the studied objects are large, so they are first examined with a small magnification of the microscope and only for a more detailed study, a large magnification is used.

Keeping plant material affected by fungi at high humidity. The bottom and lid of the Petri dish are lined with wet filter paper, preventing the accumulation of water at the bottom of the dish, to avoid rotting of the material.

Stems and similar parts of plants are superficially disinfected with alcohol or potassium permanganate. The material is cut into parts for faster germination of the mycelium on the surface, while the knife or scalpel is periodically burned (sterilized). The leaves or their parts are laid out in a cup.

Wet chambers are kept at a temperature of 15–20 °C. The incubation period is limited to one to three days, but sometimes can be extended up to two weeks. During this time, the humidity is periodically monitored and, if necessary, the filter paper in the cups is moistened.

Isolation of mushrooms in pure culture. Affected plants are washed in running water, and the affected parts are separated. If the plants wither, then the lower part of the stem and roots are taken for research. Plant parts are disinfected, washed with sterile water and cut into 1–2 cm pieces. The material is placed in Petri dishes with agar-agar and placed in a thermostat at 20 °C. As soon as the mycelium of the pathogen begins to germinate from the sections and moves to the nutrient substrate, it is transferred to a

clean nutrient medium in another cup. After that, the mushroom is determined by the type of sporulation.

Phytopathogenic fungi are identified mainly by morphological features of fruiting bodies and spores.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Petri dishes
- Filter paper
- Tweezers
- Volumetric flasks
- Distilled water
- Spirit bottle
- Agar-agar
- Meat peptone agar
- Glucose

Equipment:

- UV lamps
- Microscopes
- Test tubes
- Microbiological loops
- Autoclave
- Thermostat
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

Spread of diseases determined using the formula:

$$P = \frac{n \times 100}{N}$$

where P is the spread of the disease;

N – the total number of plants in the sample;

n– the number of affected organs (plants), %.

Development of diseases determined using the formula

$$R = \frac{\sum(a \times b) \times 100}{N \times K}$$

Where R – intensity of disease development (point or percentage);

$\sum(a \times b)$ – the sum of the products of the number of plants by the corresponding score or percentage of damage;

K– the highest score on the accounting scale;

N - the total number of accounting plants.

REMARKS

Keys to identifying disease types

1. (4) The whole plant is affected
2. (3) The plant is depressed. Loss of turgor causes yellowing and wilting. The causes may be blockage of the vascular system by microorganisms, damage to the root system, lack of moisture in the soil, damage by higher flower parasites, mechanical damage, poisoning by toxins..... *Withering*
3. (2). The plant is deformed, the number of shortened shoots is increased, the entire plant may have shortened or wrinkled leaves..... *General deformation*
4. (1). Individual plant organs are affected.
5. (8). On the affected parts of plants, dying areas of tissue or individual organs have changed their shape.
6. (7). On the leaves, less often on other organs, there is a dying off of certain areas of tissues or a decrease in chlorophyll in the green organs of plants. On organs rich in nutrients and water, dying covers only the surface layers of the tissue, without spreading deep. *Spots*
7. (5). Change in the shape of affected plant organs. Ugliness, lignification, adhesions and other forms may be noted. *Deformation*
8. (11). Affected organs are covered with tubercles or mold.
9. (10). On the vegetative or generative organs - gray, white, brown, brown or black, such that the mold is easily erased, the epidermis under it is without damage.
..... *Raises*
10. (8). On the affected organs - tubercles, piles of spores, covered with epidermis or protruding from the cracks of plant tissue; tubercles can be yellow, brown, orange, brown, black. *Pustules*
11. (14). Affected organs soften or grow abnormally.
12. (13). Organs rich in nutrients and water (roots, fruits, stems, tubers, etc.) soften and rot. The lesion can cover all tissues, spreading deep into the organ.
..... *Rotten*
13. (11). Abnormal growth of individual plant organs of different sizes and shapes.
..... *Growths*
14. (8). Other symptoms of damage.
15. (16). Affected organs turn into hard, dark, leathery formations or a black dust-like mass, a liquid that hardens in the air is released from diseased plant parts.
16. (17). Fruits or seeds turn into dark dense formations of black colour with a smooth or rough surface. *Mummification*
17. (18). Affected organs (grain, stems, leaves) are destroyed and turn into a black or brown powdery mass. *Organ destruction (soot)*
18. (14). Cracks form on diseased plants, from which a liquid is released that hardens in the air. *Gum flow*

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1.8. Triticale

1.8.1. Assessment of diseases

PRINCIPLE

The assessment of diseases in triticale is essential for maintaining crop health, optimizing yield, minimizing economic losses, promoting sustainable agriculture, and supporting research and development efforts in triticale production. By identifying and managing diseases effectively, farmers can ensure the long-term viability and profitability of triticale cultivation.

PROCEDURE

The health status of the plants is evaluated twice (cereals BBCH 39-75). Fungal infection is determined on 25 randomly selected plants per plot. The plants are visually evaluated for disease severity and rated on a scale of 0 to 4. The disease index (DI) is calculated for the diseases as a percentage.

Visual observations of the disease infection are made, and infected leaf/root/base of the stem/pods tissue samples are taken to the laboratory, and the pathogens are identified under a light microscope using aqueous mounting media. The species of fungi are identified on the basis of the mycological keys and monographs. The identification of each isolate is conducted twice.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Mycological keys and monographs

REFERENCES

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1.8.2. Assessment of pests

PRINCIPLE

Visual illustration of pest occurrence or pest-related specific damages is the main method for assessing plant health. Assessment of pests is correlated with crop protection and economic impact, as assessing pests in triticale is essential for preventing economic losses by maintaining healthy crop plants, and ensuring a consistent supply of high-quality triticale for various purposes, pest management and environmental impact.

PROCEDURE

Table 5. Protocol for assessment of pests in triticale

Crop	Measurement	Protocol
Triticale	<i>Oulema</i> sp.	Evaluation of the occurrence of larvae and the damaged area (BBCH 39 - 77) is performed twice during the growing period, by visual inspections on 30 randomly selected stems / plot (in the case of cereal mixtures - 30 stems of each cereal in the mixture / plot). The number of damaged stems, and the percentage of damage area on leaves, are recorded.
	Aphids	Observations on aphids are carried out in the same way as in the case of aphids on potatoes, twice in growth season (BBCH 39 -77).
	<i>Chlorops pumilionis</i> Bjerk.	Visual assessment on 20 consecutive stems in 5 different randomly selected places/plot (100 stems per plot) (BBCH 71-77). Damages caused by larvae are classified using a three-stage scale, where the individual degrees mean: 1 - weak damage, the spike is completely extended from the leaf sheath, a long, shallow furrow below the spike is visible; 2 - moderate damage, the spike is partially hidden in the leaf sheath; 3 - severe damage, stems not sprouted, strongly shortened, furrow deep.
	Agromyzidae	Evaluation of the area of damages (BBCH 39 - 77) is done twice during the growing period, through visual inspections on 30 randomly selected stems / plot (in the case of cereal mixtures - 30 stems of each cereal in the mixture / plot). The number of damaged stems is recorded as well as the percentage of damaged area on the leaves.

	<i>Eurygaster maura</i> (L.)	Inspection of crops for the presence of insects is made twice (BBCH 31-77), through the visual inspections on 30 randomly selected stems / plot (in the case of cereal mixtures - 30 stems of each cereal in the mixture / plot).
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EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Mycological keys and monographs

REFERENCES

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1.9. Wheat

1.9.1. Plant growth: plant height and leaf area

PRINCIPLE

Plant height is measured as an indicator of growth, while leaf area is measured to assess the plant's ability to capture light for photosynthesis.

PROCEDURE

Plant height is done manually using a ruler or measuring tape, measuring from the soil surface to the tip of the tallest stem. For the leaf area measurement, the leaves are first scanned with the EPSON Scan, and then quantified with the ImageJ software.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Measuring tape
- EPSON Scan
- ImageJ Software

REFERENCES

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1.9.2. Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence measurement

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is one of the most widely used parameters in green plants to monitor the modulation and alterations of the photosynthetic process under stress (Misra et al., 2012). A widely used chlorophyll fluorescence technique is the pulse modulated fluorescence measurement method described by Schrieber et al. (1986). With this technique, 4 parameters of great relevance for the study of the state of photosystem II (PSII) can be determined. These are (López-González et al., 2020):

- F_v/F_m , the maximum efficiency of PSII: following exposure to darkness, reaction centres of PSII are typically open ($F = F_0$), non-photochemical quenching is negligible ($NPQ = 0$) and the fluorescence yield is at its peak. In this state, PSII's quantum yield reaches its maximum and saturation pulses (F_v) cause a rise in fluorescence. A decrease of this parameter usually denotes physical damages in the antenna system of PSII.
- Φ_{II} , the effective photochemical quantum yield of PSII: quantifies the proportion of light absorbed by the PSII-related chlorophyll that is utilized in the quantum yield. It can reveal information about the linear electron flow's speed and, therefore, serves as an indicator of the total photosynthetic capacity *in vivo* (Maxwell and Johnson 2000).
- Φ_{NPQ} , the measurement of regulated non-photochemical non-fluorescent energy dissipation (as heat): is linearly related to heat dissipation and ranges from 0 to infinity. Although this varies amongst different species, the typical values in a healthy plant are in the range of 0.5–3.5 at saturating light intensities (Maxwell and Johnson, 2000). Excessive photon flux density is indicated by high values of this parameter, which causes the plant to defend itself by releasing the energy as heat. If this value rises, it means that the photosynthetic mechanism is producing more energy than it needs, but the plant can control this excess to prevent damage.
- Φ_{NO} , the measurement of non-regulated emission of energy (as fluorescence): it determines the non-regulated energy loss as fluorescence (Klughammer et al., 2008). Elevated values of this parameter suggest that the plant is having problems adjusting to incident radiation due to inefficient photochemical energy conversion and protective regulatory mechanisms. Extremely high values imply that the plant has

been damaged or is likely to be damaged because they show that the PSII reaction centres are blocked, inhibiting the development of a trans-thylakoid proton gradient.

PROCEDURE

The measures are carried out *in situ* using the MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0 (PhotosynQ, East Lansing, MI, USA) (Álvarez-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

4. The plant (or branch) is covered with a black bag during at least 20 min before taking the measurement.
5. After 20 min, the fluorimeter is placed on a leaf to measure the maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II (F_v/F_m). The MultispeQ v2.0 is used to run the "Fv/Fm in the dark" protocol, also linked to the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>].
6. With the help the "rapid information dense experimental sequence" (RIDES) protocol ("Photosynthesis RIDES 2.0"), available on the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>, (Kuhlgert et al., 2016)] the different parameters related to chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is obtained: the effective quantum yield of the photosystem II photochemical reactions (Φ_{II}), the regulated energy dissipation in the form of heat (Φ_{NPQ}), and the non-regulated energy dissipation (Φ_{NO} , fluorescence emitted).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Dark bags

Equipment:

- MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0

CALCULATIONS

5. $\Phi_{II} + \Phi_{NPQ} + \Phi_{NO} = 1$
6. $\Phi_{NPQ} = 1 - \Phi_{II} - \Phi_{NO}$
7. $\Phi_{NO} = F_s/F_m$
8. $F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_0)/F_m$

REMARKS

For a correct measurement of F_v/F_m it is essential that the plants (or leaves) are in complete darkness for at least 20 min to open all reaction centres of PSII.

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Schreiber, U., Schliwa, U. & Bilger, W. (1986) Continuous recording of photochemical and non-photochemical chlorophyll fluorescence quenching with a new type of modulation fluorometer. *Photosynthesis Research*, 10, 51–62.

1.9.3. Water content

PRINCIPLE

Knowing water content, relative water content and dry weight in wheat is crucial for assessing its nutritional value and overall quality. It helps to determine the optimal harvest time, ensuring peak nutritional content. Additionally, understanding water content aids in proper storage and milling processes, influencing the final product's quality and market value.

PROCEDURE

To measure biomass, plants are harvested, weighed, dried to a constant weight, and then weighed again. This provides an estimate of the accumulated dry matter and the ratio DW/FW (DW: dry weight; FW: fresh weight).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Aluminium foil

Equipment:

- Oven

CALCULATIONS

$$(1) \text{ DW/FW} = \frac{\text{Dry weight}}{\text{Fresh weight}} \text{ (g)}$$

$$(2) \text{ RWC (\%)} = [\text{FW-DW}]/(\text{TW-DW}) * 100$$

REFERENCES

Lugojan, C. & Ciulca, S. (2011). Evaluation of relative water content in winter wheat. *Journal of Horticulture, Forestry and Biotechnology*, 15(2), 173-177.

1.9.4. Tiller count

PRINCIPLE

Tillers are additional stems or shoots that develop from the base of the wheat plant. Counting the number of tillers can indicate weak or strong plant vigour and growth potential.

PROCEDURE

A ruler or a 50 cm length of rope is placed at random between two rows of crop. The number of tillers along each row on both sides of the ruler is counted and recorded. This is the total tiller number per meter row of crop. It is repeated at 10 sites along the monitoring path. The average of the 10 counts is calculated, and enter into the equation below.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

No equipment needed

CALCULATIONS

To convert tillers /m to tillers m² =
$$\frac{\text{Average tiller n}^{\circ} / \text{meter of row} \times 100}{\text{Row spacing (cm)}}$$

Ex:
$$\frac{60 \text{ tillers/m} \times 100}{15 \text{ cm}} = 400 \text{ tiller m}^2$$

REMARKS

Tiller counts below 70 per m² may indicate the need for nitrogen application.

REFERENCES

Department of Agriculture and Food. Government of Western Australia. Monitoring cereal tiller counts. Available at: <https://www.agric.wa.gov.au/mycrop/monitoring-cereal-tiller-counts>

1.9.5. Ear development

PRINCIPLE

Ear development in wheat refers to the growth and formation of the wheat spikelet, which contain the grain or seeds. The ear is an important part of the wheat plant as it determines the yield potential and grain quality.

PROCEDURE

These can be visually assessed or counted during specific growth stages.

REFERENCES

Kirby, E.J.M. (1974). Ear development in spring wheat. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, 82(3), 437-447. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859600051339>

1.9.6. Phenological stage

PRINCIPLE

The phenological stages in wheat refers to the specific phases of growth and development of the wheat plant. They are commonly classified with letters or codes to facilitate communication and tracking of growth stages.

PROCEDURE

The phenological stages in wheat can vary slightly depending on the specific classification system used, but they generally include the following key stages:

1. Germination: This is the initial stage where the seed absorbs water and begins to sprout.
2. Seedling establishment: The seedling emerges from the soil and starts developing roots and shoots.
3. Tillering: The plant produces additional shoots called tillers, which contribute to the overall plant density.
4. Stem elongation: The main stem of the wheat plant undergoes rapid growth and elongation.
5. Booting: The growing point of the plant, which contains the future inflorescence, is enclosed within the sheath of the uppermost leaf.
6. Heading: The inflorescence emerges from the boot and becomes visible.
7. Flowering: The wheat plant produces and releases pollen, and the flowers are receptive to pollination.
8. Grain filling: The fertilized flowers develop into grains, and the grains start accumulating starch and nutrients.

9. Ripening and maturity: The grains reach their full size, dry out, and change colour as they mature. The plant senesces, and the grains are ready for harvest.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

No equipment needed

REFERENCES

https://www.bionity.com/en/encyclopedia/B BCH-scale_%28cereals%29.html

2. HORTICULTURAL

2.1. Aromatic plants

2.1.1. Alkaloid profiling

PRINCIPLE

The method described the separation, identification, and quantitative assessment of the major alkaloid compounds in dwarf periwinkle plants.

PROCEDURE

Extraction

1. Plant sample material (50 g) is ground.
2. Sieved sample (0.1-0.5 g) is extracted with 10 mL chloroform using a Sonication (3x10 min, at 25-30 °C).
3. The sample is then treated with hydrochloric acid, filtered, and the pH is adjusted between 8.0 and 9.0 with ammonia. Extracts are concentrated to dryness and diluted to 1 mL with methanol. Samples are stored at 4 °C until analysis by high performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometric analysis.
4. Alternatively, extraction can be carried out using 10 mL of pH 4.0 aqueous acetic acid. After extraction, the extract is concentrated to dryness and diluted to 1 mL with methanol.

Standard Solutions

1. All standards must be prepared in the same solvent as the extract.
2. Solutions of 1 mg mL⁻¹ must be prepared, and dilutions according to real concentrations must be prepared. For mass spectrometric identification 100 ng mL⁻¹ concentrations must be prepared ideally.

Measurement

1. The separations are achieved on a C18 packed column (5 μm , 4.6 x 250 mm). The mobile phase consisted of (A) 0.05 mol L⁻¹ ammonium acetate and (B) acetonitrile. The elution program is run using A and B solvents. The injection volume is 10 μL at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹.
2. Detection is carried out using diode array detection and mass spectrometric detection in positive polarization mode.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Chloroform
- Acetonitrile (LCMS grade)
- Water (LCMS grade)
- Methanol (LCMS grade)
- Ammonium acetate
- *Vinca minor* alkaloid standards (vincamine, vincristine, vinblastine, vindoline, vinorelbine, vindesine)

Equipment:

- Ultrasonic bath
- Centrifuge
- Liquid-chromatograph and mass spectrometer

CALCULATIONS

Results must be evaluated by comparing spectra of recorded compounds to database or standard spectra and establishing calibration plot using UV absorbance.

REFERENCES

Boyadzhiev, L., Mecheva, D. & Yordanov, B. (2002). Extraction of vincamine from periwinkle (*Vinca minor* L.): I. obtaining of total extract. *Comptes rendus de l'Académie bulgare des Sciences*, 55(12).

Liu, J., Liu, Y., Pan, Y., Zu, Y.-G. & Tang, Z.-H. (2016). Determination of alkaloids in *Catharanthus roseus* and *Vinca minor* by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry. *Analytical Letters*, 49(8): 1143-1153.

2.1.2. Polyphenol profiling

PRINCIPLE

The method is based on the high-performance liquid chromatographic separation and subsequent identification of polyphenolic compounds using multistage mass spectrometry.

PROCEDURE

Extraction

1. Plant sample material (100 g) is ground and sieved. The 0.2-0.63 mm fraction is used for analysis.
2. Sieved sample (0.4 g) is extracted with 40 mL 50:50 (v/v) methanol:water mixture using a Sonication (3x10 min, at 25-30 °C).
3. Extracts (2 mL) are centrifuged at 14,000 rpm twice for 10 min each.
4. The supernatant is taken to chromatographic analysis.
5. If extracts are too diluted, they should be concentrated as follows: 1 mL of the centrifuged extract is evaporated to dryness using rotary evaporation at 40 °C. Dry extracts are re-dissolved in 0.1 mL neat solvent and taken to chromatographic analysis.

Standard Solutions

1. All standards are prepared in the same solvent as the extract.
2. Solutions of 1 mg mL⁻¹ are prepared and dilutions according to real concentrations are prepared. For mass spectrometric identification 100 ng mL⁻¹ concentrations are prepared ideally.

Compounds optimization

1. The product ion spectra of each compound are recorded from standard compound solutions in both, negative and positive ionization mode. If possible, mass spectra must be matched with spectra library mass spectra.

Measurement

1. Gradient elution is run using water + 0.1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid (B) solutions.
2. Stationary phase is a C18 or compatible reverse phase column.
3. Mass spectrometer is operated in 150-2000 m/z range in both positive and negative mode by polarity switching.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Acetonitrile (LCMS grade)
- Water (LCMS grade)
- Methanol (LCMS grade)
- Formic acid (98%)
- Polyphenol standard compounds (when applicable)

Equipment:

- Ultrasonic bath
- Centrifuge
- Liquid-chromatograph and mass spectrometer

CALCULATIONS

Results must be evaluated by comparing spectra of recorded compounds to database or standard spectra.

REFERENCES

Hofmann, T., Nebehaj, E. & Albert, L. (2016): Antioxidant properties and detailed polyphenol profiling of European hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.) leaves by multiple antioxidant capacity assays and high-performance liquid chromatography/multistage electrospray mass spectrometry. *Indian Crop Production*, 87, 340-349.

2.2. Cabbage

2.2.1. Measurement of plant height

PRINCIPLE

Plant height is a key indicator for crop health and growth

PROCEDURE

1. A subsample of plants in each experimental unit is selected.
2. The distance from the ground to the highest point of the plant is measured with a tape measure.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tape measure
- Quadrat (50 x 50 cm)

REFERENCES

Weiher, E., Van Der Werf, A., Thompson, K., Roderick, M., Garnier, E. & Eriksson, O. (1999). Challenging Theophrastus: a common core list of plant traits for functional ecology. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 10(5), 609-620. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3237076>

Westoby, M. (1998). A leaf-height-seed (LHS) plant ecology strategy scheme. *Plant and Soil*, 199, 213-227. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004327224729>

2.2.2. Shoot and root fresh and dry weight, root/shoot ratio

PRINCIPLE

For determination of overall health of the crop plants and plant growth, the fresh and dry weight of the crop plants are measured three times during the growing season.

PROCEDURE

Measurement

For measurement of fresh weight:

1. A subsample of plants from each experimental plot is removed from the soil and any loose soil is washed off with deionized water.
2. Each plant is divided into shoot and root and weighed.

For dry weight:

1. The shoots and roots are dried at 80 °C until they reach a constant weight.
2. Then, they are transferred to a desiccator to cool.
3. The shoots and roots are weighed.
4. Root/shoot ratio are calculated based on the dry weight measurements.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Scale for weighing
- Drying oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Root/shoot ratio} = \frac{\text{Root weight (g)}}{\text{Shoot weight (g)}}$$

REFERENCES

Mokany, K., Raison, R.J. & Prokushkin, A.S. (2006). Critical analysis of root: shoot ratios in terrestrial biomes. *Global Change Biology*, 12(1), 84-96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2005.001043.x>.

Williams, J.D., McCool, D.K., Reardon, C.L., Douglas, C.L., Albrecht, S.L. & Rickman, R.W. (2013). Root: shoot ratios and belowground biomass distribution for Pacific Northwest dryland crops. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 68(5), 349-360. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.68.5.349>.

2.3. Carrot

2.3.1. Measurement of plant height

PRINCIPLE

Plant height is a key indicator for crop health and growth

PROCEDURE

1. A subsample of plants in each experimental unit is selected.
2. The distance from the ground to the highest point of the plant is measured with a tape measure.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Tape measure
- Quadrat (50 x 50 cm)

REFERENCES

Mokany, K., Raison, R.J. & Prokushkin, A.S. (2006). Critical analysis of root: shoot ratios in terrestrial biomes. *Global Change Biology*, 12(1), 84-96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2005.001043.x>.

Williams, J.D., McCool, D.K., Reardon, C.L., Douglas, C.L., Albrecht, S.L. & Rickman, R.W. (2013). Root: shoot ratios and belowground biomass distribution for Pacific Northwest dryland crops. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 68(5), 349-360. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.68.5.349>.

2.3.2. Shoot and root fresh and dry weight, root/shoot ratio

PRINCIPLE

For determination of overall health of the crop plants and plant growth, the fresh and dry weight of the crop plants are measured three times during the growing season.

PROCEDURE

Measurement

For measurement of fresh weight:

1. A subsample of plants from each experimental plot is removed from the soil and any loose soil is washed off with deionized water.
2. Each plant is divided into shoot and root, and weighed.

For dry weight:

1. The shoots and roots are dried at 80 °C until they reach a constant weight.
2. Then, they are transferred to a desiccator to cool.
3. The shoots and roots are weighed.
4. Root to shoot ratio is calculated based on the dry weight measurements.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Scale for weighing
- Drying oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Root/shoot ratio} = \frac{\text{Root weight (g)}}{\text{Shoot weight (g)}}$$

REFERENCES

- Evers, A.M. (1988). Effects of different fertilization practices on the growth, yield and dry matter content of carrot. *Agricultural and Food Science*, 60(2), 135-152. <https://doi.org/10.23986/afsci.72284>.
- Suojala, T. (2000). Growth of and partitioning between shoot and storage root of carrot in a northern climate. *Agricultural and Food Science*, 9(1), 49-59. <https://doi.org/10.23986/afsci.5646>.
- Suojala, T. (2000). *Pre-and postharvest development of carrot yield and quality*. [Doctoral dissertation, University of Helsinki]. HELDA University of Helsinki Open Repository <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:951-45-9169-0>.

2.4. Lettuce, Melon, Tomato and Zucchini

2.4.1. Plant growth

PRINCIPLE

Measures of plant growth give an insight into the health and vigour of the plant. These measures include size (height, diameter or cover), number of leaves (or stems), fresh and dry weight, water content, relative water content, and dry matter. It is also important to observe the possible occurrence of pests and diseases, their development and crop damage during the crop cycle.

PROCEDURE

Size Measurement. A ruler or tape measure is used to measure the height of the plant from the soil surface to the tip of the plant, and the width of the plant.

Number of Leaves and Foliar Area. The number of leaves is counted manually and the leaf area of each leaf is estimated by taking a photograph of the leaf and analysing it with image analysis software such as *ImageJ*, *Image-Pro Plus* or *Digimizer*.

Fresh and dry weight, water content, relative water content and dry matter. With a balance, the weight of the leaves (roots or the whole plant) is measured as soon as they are harvested to obtain the fresh weight (FW) of the sample. Subsequently, the leaves are placed in paper envelopes and placed in an oven at 65 °C for 3 days until the weight of the samples is constant to obtain the dry weight (DW). Once the FW and DW values are obtained, the water content (WC) and dry matter content (DMC) can be calculated (Admane et al., 2023) (see calculation section). For the calculation of the relative water content (RWC), it is necessary to obtain the turgent weight (TW). This weight is obtained after placing the plant material in double-distilled water for at least 24 h. Once obtained, the RWC is calculated (Erice et al., 2018).

Pest and Disease Monitoring. Regular monitoring and measurements of pests and diseases affecting crops is carried out throughout the growth of the crop. This includes

identifying and counting pests or assessing disease severity through visual inspection or quantitative methods. To identify pests and diseases, a manual may be used to recognize adequately its symptoms. Integrated Pest Management Manuals "Guías de gestión integrada de plagas" published by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fishery and Food of the Spanish Government (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2023) are proper references for identification of pests and diseases for our key crops.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ruler or tape measure
- Image analysis software
- Paper envelopes

Equipment:

- Balance or precision scale
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

1. Water content (WC) = $[(FW - DW) \div FW] \times 100$
2. Dry matter content (DMC) = $(DW \div FW) \times 100$
3. Relative water content (RWC) = $[(FW - DW) \div (TW - DW)] \times 100$

REFERENCES

Admane, N., Cavallo, G., Hadjila, C., Cavalluzzi, M.M., Rotondo, N.P., Salerno, A., Cannillo, J., Difonzo, G., Caponio, F., Ippolito, A., Lentini, G. & Sanzani, S.M. (2023). Biostimulant formulations and *Moringa oleifera* extracts to improve yield, quality, and storability of hydroponic lettuce. *Molecules*, 28(1), 373.

Erice, G., Pérez-Bueno, M.L., Pineda, M., Barón, M., Aroca, R. & Calvo-Polanco, M. (2018). Determining plant water relations. Sánchez-Moreiras, A.M. & Reigosa, M.J. (Eds) in *Advances in Plant Ecophysiology Techniques*, pp. 109-134.

Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación (2023, 4th December). *Integrated Pest Management Manuals*. (<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/productos-fitosanitarios/guias-gestion-plagas/default.aspx>).

2.4.2. Pigment content

PRINCIPLE

Photosynthetic tissues have different pigments (photosynthetic pigments as chlorophylls and carotenoids, and non-photosynthetic pigments as anthocyanins), whose quantities (or ratio) may vary depending on the situation in which the plant finds itself, affecting its photosynthetic capacity. The determination of pigments can be done by destructive or non-destructive methods. A very common method that allow to

accurately obtain the content of chlorophyll *a*, *b* and carotenoids is by spectrophotometric assays (Lichtenthaler and Wellburn, 1983; Porra, 2002; Zhao et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2018).

PROCEDURE

Chlorophyll and carotenoids determination

1. Cold conditions are mandatory.
2. Between 50-100 mg of fresh material are weighed, noted and placed in Eppendorf tubes together with two glass or metal beads (for crushing in the sample crusher) and dropped into liquid nitrogen.
3. One mL of 80% acetone (4:1) is added with a micropipette:

Reagent	Volume
Acetone	80 mL
H ₂ O	20 mL

4. The samples are placed in a shaker in the dark (aluminium foil) at 4 °C for 24 h.
5. The samples are centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 15 min.
6. The supernatant is diluted 10-fold with 80% acetone with a micropipette (100 µL extract-900 µL 80% acetone).
7. Optical density is measured with plastic or glass cuvettes at 470, 646 and 663 nm. The work must be done on ice.
8. Pigments contents are calculated as described in calculations section.

Anthocyanins determination

1. 300 mg frozen plant material is mixed with 3 mL of 95% methanol:1.5 M hydrochloric acid (85:15) at 4 °C for 24 h.
2. The extract is centrifuged at 12,000 *g* for 5 min and the supernatant is collected.
3. Optical density is measured with plastic cuvettes at 470, 646 and 663 nm.
4. Anthocyanin content is calculated as described in calculations section.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Eppendorf tubes
- Glass or metal balls
- Liquid nitrogen
- 80% Acetone
- Methanol
- Hydrochloric acid

- Double-distilled water
- Ice
- Plastic or glass cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Micropipette
- Sample grinder
- Centrifuge
- Shaker at 4 °C
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. Chlorophyll *a* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $12.21A_{663} - 2.81A_{646}$
2. Chlorophyll *b* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $20.13A_{646} - 5.03A_{663}$
3. Carotenoids ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(1000A_{470} - 3.27[\text{Chl } a] - 104[\text{Chl } b])/229$
4. Anthocyanins ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) = $46,200 \times [(A_{530} - A_{620}) - 0.1 \times (A_{650} - A_{620})]$

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- The work must be done always under cold and dark conditions.
- 80% acetone is used as blank for chlorophyll and carotenoids measurement and 95% methanol:1.5 M hydrochloric acid (85:15) for anthocyanin quantification.
- Optical density measurements should be between 0.1 -1. Otherwise, the sample must be diluted or concentrated using 80% acetone in the case of pigments or 95% methanol:1.5 M hydrochloric acid (85:15) for anthocyanin quantification.
- Photosynthetic pigment contents are expressed in $\text{mg g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$.

REFERENCES

Lichtenthaler, H.K. & Wellburn, A.R. (1983). Determinations of total carotenoids and chlorophylls *a* and *b* of leaf extracts in different solvents. *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 11, 591-592.

Porra, R.J. (2002). The chequered history of the development and use of simultaneous equations for the accurate determination of chlorophylls *a* and *b*. *Photosynthesis Research*, 73, 149-156.

Yang, C.-M., Chang, K.-W., Yin, M.H. & Huang, H.-M. (1998). Methods for the determination of the chlorophylls and their derivatives. *Taiwania*, 43, 116-122.

Zhao, J., Xie, X., Shen, X., & Wang, Y. (2016). Effect of sunlight-exposure on antioxidants and antioxidant enzyme activities in 'd'Anjou' pear in relation to superficial scald development. *Food Chemistry*, 210, 18-25.

2.4.3. Chlorophyll a fluorescence measurement

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of chlorophyll a fluorescence is one of the most widely used parameters in green plants to monitor the modulation and alterations of the photosynthetic process under stress (Misra et al., 2012). A widely used chlorophyll fluorescence technique is the pulse modulated fluorescence measurement method described by Schrieber et al. (1986). With this technique, 4 parameters of great relevance for the study of the state of photosystem II (PSII) can be determined. These are (López-González et al., 2020):

- F_v/F_m , the maximum efficiency of PSII: following exposure to darkness, reaction centres of PSII are typically open ($F = F_0$), non-photochemical quenching is negligible ($NPQ = 0$) and the fluorescence yield is at its peak. In this state, PSII's quantum yield reaches its maximum and saturation pulses (F_v) cause a rise in fluorescence. A decrease of this parameter usually denotes physical damages in the antenna system of PSII.
- Φ_{II} , the effective photochemical quantum yield of PSII: quantifies the proportion of light absorbed by the PSII-related chlorophyll that is utilized in the quantum yield. It can reveal information about the linear electron flow's speed and, therefore, serves as an indicator of the total photosynthetic capacity *in vivo* (Maxwell and Johnson 2000).
- Φ_{NPQ} , the measurement of regulated non-photochemical non-fluorescent energy dissipation (as heat): is linearly related to heat dissipation and ranges from 0 to infinity. Although this varies amongst different species, the typical values in a healthy plant are in the range of 0.5–3.5 at saturating light intensities (Maxwell and Johnson, 2000). Excessive photon flux density is indicated by high values of this parameter, which causes the plant to defend itself by releasing the energy as heat. If this value rises, it means that the photosynthetic mechanism is producing more energy than it needs, but the plant can control this excess to prevent damage.
- Φ_{NO} , the measurement of non-regulated emission of energy (as fluorescence): it determines the non-regulated energy loss as fluorescence (Klughammer et al., 2008). Elevated values of this parameter suggest that the plant is having problems adjusting to incident radiation due to inefficient photochemical energy conversion and protective regulatory mechanisms. Extremely high values imply that the plant has been damaged or is likely to be damaged because they show that the PSII reaction centres are blocked, inhibiting the development of a trans-thylakoid proton gradient.

PROCEDURE

The measures are carried out *in situ* using the MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0 (PhotosynQ, East Lansing, MI, USA) (Álvarez-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

7. The plant (or branch) is covered with a black bag during at least 20 min before taking the measurement.
8. After 20 min, the fluorimeter is placed on a leaf to measure the maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II (F_v/F_m). The MultispeQ v2.0 is used to run the "Fv/Fm in the dark" protocol, also linked to the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>].
9. With the help the "rapid information dense experimental sequence" (RIDES) protocol ("Photosynthesis RIDES 2.0"), available on the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>, (Kuhlgert et al., 2016)] the different parameters related to chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is obtained: the effective quantum yield of the photosystem II photochemical reactions (Φ_{II}), the regulated energy dissipation in the form of heat (Φ_{NPQ}), and the non-regulated energy dissipation (Φ_{NO} , fluorescence emitted).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Dark bags

Equipment:

- MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0

CALCULATIONS

9. $\Phi_{II} + \Phi_{NPQ} + \Phi_{NO} = 1$
10. $\Phi_{NPQ} = 1 - \Phi_{II} - \Phi_{NO}$
11. $\Phi_{NO} = F_s/F_m$
12. $F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_0)/F_m$

REMARKS

For a correct measurement of F_v/F_m it is essential that the plants (or leaves) are in complete darkness for at least 20 min to open all reaction centres of PSII.

REFERENCES

- Álvarez-Rodríguez, S., Spinozzi, E., Sánchez-Moreiras, A.M., López-González, D., Ferrati, M., Lucchini, G., Maggi, F., Petrelli, R. & Araniti, F. (2023). Investigating the phytotoxic potential of *Carlina acaulis* essential oil against the weed *Bidens pilosa* through a physiological and metabolomic approach. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 203, 117149.
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2.4.4. Hydrogen Peroxide Quantification

PRINCIPLE

Oxidative stress is the imbalance between prooxidants and antioxidants. The amount of reactive oxygen species (ROS), among other prooxidants, gives information about the status of the redox imbalance during the plant response to a stress factor. Chloroplasts are quantitatively and qualitatively one of the most important sources of ROS in illuminated plant cells (Foyer and Noctor, 2003). Thus, the measurement of ROS, such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), are good markers to evaluate the status of the photosynthetic apparatus (Alexieva et al., 2001; Loreto and Velikova, 2001; Velikova et al., 2001).

PROCEDURE

1. The samples (50-100 mg of fresh plant material) are homogenized in 0.5 mL 0.1% w/v trichloroacetic acid (TCA) on ice.
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 15,000 g at 4 °C for 15 min.
3. From each supernatant, an aliquot of 0.5 mL is added to 0.5 mL of 10 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 1.0 mL of 1 M KI (w/v in fresh double-distilled water H₂O). Mix gently.
4. The reaction is developed for 1 h in darkness (in a card box) and the absorbance is measured at 390 nm for 1 min.
5. H₂O₂ is quantified taking into account a calibration curve using solutions with known H₂O₂ concentrations.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Trichloroacetic acid (TCA)
- 10 mM potassium phosphate (KH₂PO₄) buffer (pH 7.0)
- 1 M potassium iodide (KI)
- Double-distilled water

- H₂O₂ for calibration curve
- Ice
- Double-distilled water
- Card box
- Cuvettes
- Eppendorf

Equipment:

- Pipette
- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the plant extract samples is measured, and the standard curve equation is used to calculate the concentration of H₂O₂ in the samples.

REMARKS

The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure. The blank probe consists of 0.5 mL of 0.1% TCA in the absence of leaf extract and follow the same procedure described as for the samples.

Results are expressed as $\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}\text{DW}$ calculated from the H₂O₂ calibration curve.

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2.4.5. Protein quantification**PRINCIPLE**

The Bradford method (Bradford, 1976) is a colorimetric technique used for the quantification of proteins. This parameter is especially interesting when measuring the plant health and knowing whether a plant is encountering any abiotic or biotic stress factor, as one of the first detected responses is the synthesis of stress proteins when

plant is under acclimation or protein degradation when is under senescence (Batista-Silva et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE

Bradford Reagent Preparation:

1. 100 mg of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye is weighed.
2. 50 mL 95% ethanol is added.
3. 100 mL 85% phosphoric acid is added slowly and carefully.
4. All is mixed until the blue dye is completely dissolved.
5. The dye/ethanol/phosphoric acid solution is added to 850 mL pure sterile H₂O.
6. Any precipitates are filtered.
7. Bradford reagent can be stored at 4 °C for months.

Measuring Protein Standard

1. First, the spectrophotometer is warmed up.
2. Seven different volumes of 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ BSA corresponding to different BSA concentrations [0 µL (0 µg), 10 µL (1 µg), 20 µL (2 µg), 30 µL (3 µg), 50 µL (5 µg), 70 µL (7 µg) and 100 µL (10 µg)] are pipetted into separate plastic cuvettes. Pure water is added until 800 µL.
3. 200 µL of Bradford Reagent is added to each cuvette.
4. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film or taps and mixed by gently inverting.
5. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 2-3 min. The reaction is stable for 1 h.
6. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.

Measuring Samples (unknown quantity)

1. Protein extraction can be performed by using PEB (HEPES) method: 100 mg of fresh material is needed (already conserved at -70 °C), to be extracted in 1 mL Protein Extraction Buffer (PEB):

PEB preparation:

- HEPES (20 mM final concentration)
- Potassium chloride (KCl) (50 mM final concentration)
- Triton x-100 (0.1 v/v final concentration)
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) (0.2% w/v final concentration)
- Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP) (0.2% w/v final concentration)
- Glycerol (5% final concentration)

And water till reach the desired volume.

Also is necessary prepare High Salt Buffer (HSB):

- HEPES (225 mM final concentration)
- Potassium chloride (KCl) (1.5 M final concentration)
- Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) (22.5 mM final concentration)

2. The sample (100 mg of fresh material) is crushed and 1 mL PEB is added, vortexed and put in ice for 5-10 min.
3. 10% of the volume of PEB used is added to HSB (100 µL), vortex and then leave in ice for 10-15 minutes.
4. The tubes are centrifuged at 13,500 rpm at 4 °C for 15 min, and the supernatant is divided into aliquots of about 50-100 µL and saved at -70 °C (this extract is used for enzymatic assays, section 1.6)
5. Between 10 to 50 µL of the extract previously prepared with PEB and HSB are pipetted into a cuvette.
6. 200 µL of Bradford Reagent is added to the cuvette.
7. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film or tap and mixed by gently inverting.
7. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 2-3 min.
8. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.
 - a. If the absorbance does not fall within the range of the standard curve, the dilution of the sample must be changed and measured again, or a new standard curve with new concentrations must be done.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye
- 95% ethanol
- 85% phosphoric acid
- Double-distilled water
- Bovine serum albumin (BSA)
- HEPES
- Potassium chloride (KCl)
- Triton x-100
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP)
- Glycerol
- Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂)
- Ice
- Plastic cuvettes

- Eppendorf

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipettes
- Vortex

CALCULATIONS

Standard Curve Generation:

- A scatter plot is made for the standard curve values.
- The X-axis must be micrograms (μg) of standard protein that were assayed, while the Y-axis must be the value obtained when measuring the absorbance at 595 nm.
- A linear trendline to the graph is fitted.
- The linear regression equation is showed.
- The unknown amount of protein is calculated by using the linear regression equation, as shown in the following equations.
- The unknown concentration of the original protein solution is calculated by dividing the amount of protein by the volume of protein assayed, and then multiplying the quotient by the dilution factor, as shown in the calculations section.
- Alternatively, a curvilinear (polynomial) trendline can be fitted to the graph. This polynomial regression equation may sometimes give a better estimation of protein concentration.

$$\mu\text{g of protein} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - y \text{ intercept}}{\text{Slope}}$$

$$\text{Concentration assayed} = \frac{\mu\text{g protein}}{\mu\text{L assayed}}$$

$$\text{Concentration of original solution} = \text{Concentration assayed} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- The timing for the addition of Bradford to the samples must be similar to test the concentration in similar reactions conditions.
- The samples can be diluted by using EEB (elution extraction buffer).
- EEB, which is used to stabilise the sample and dilute it in most of the enzyme assays, is the same as the PEB buffer minus the PVP and PVPP components.
- In the blank, the volume of sample is replaced by EEB.

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2.4.6. Enzymatic Antioxidant Capacity

PRINCIPLE

Excessive production of ROS during stress conditions acts as signal for the activation of stress response in terms of efficient enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant pathways (Baxter et al., 2014). Among the enzymatic mechanisms, superoxide dismutase (SOD), ascorbate peroxidase (APx), catalase (CAT) and glutathione reductase (GR), are the enzymes most frequently studied as defence mechanisms against ROS. These antioxidant enzymes are located in different sites of plant cells where ROS are generally produced under both normal and stressful conditions (chloroplasts, mitochondria, peroxisomes, plasma membranes, ER, and the cell wall), and work together to detoxify ROS (Noctor et al., 2017).

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

Ascorbate peroxidase plays a crucial role in protecting plants and other organisms from damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS). This enzyme catalyses the reduction of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) using ascorbate as the reducing agent. The electron donor for the scavenging of hydrogen peroxide in chloroplasts is L-ascorbate and that the L-ascorbate is regenerated from dehydroascorbate (DHA) by the system: photosystem I \rightarrow ferredoxin \rightarrow NADP \rightarrow glutathione. The activity of APx is determined by the measurement of the diminution of the absorbance of oxidized ascorbate at 290 nm, according to Nakano and Asada (1981).

Catalase (CAT)

Catalase plays a crucial role in breaking down hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) into water and oxygen, but also in the oxidation of H donors with a consumption of 1 mol of peroxide. The catalase assay involves monitoring the rate of decomposition of H_2O_2 according to Aebi (1984), and it provides insight into the enzyme's efficiency in catalysing this reaction.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) is a critical enzyme that plays a fundamental role in cellular defence mechanisms, by catalysing the dismutation of superoxide radicals (O_2^-) into O_2 and H_2O_2 . This enzymatic reaction is a pivotal part of the cellular antioxidant defence

system, serving to neutralize and detoxify ROS generated during normal cellular processes or under conditions of oxidative stress. Total SOD activity is assayed using a modified NBT method.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

Glutathione reductase (GR) is an enzyme that plays a crucial role in the maintenance of cellular redox balance by catalysing the reduction of oxidized glutathione (GSSG) to reduced glutathione (GSH). Glutathione is a tripeptide composed of glutamate, cysteine, and glycine, and is a major cellular antioxidant.

In this reaction, glutathione reductase uses NADPH as a reducing agent to convert oxidized glutathione (GSSG) into its reduced form (2GSH), recycling glutathione and maintaining a reducing environment within the cell.

PROCEDURE

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

1. The volume of the reaction is 2 mL containing 0.5 mM ascorbate, 0.1 mM EDTA, 1.2 mM H₂O₂, sample extract (50-100 μL, from the supernatant prepared in Bradford Assay) and EEB until a volume of 2 mL.
2. A blank (minus the sample and the substrate, in this case H₂O₂) and oxidation reaction (substrate minus the sample) is carried out.
3. The reaction starts by adding H₂O.
4. The absorbance decrease is recorded in quartz cuvettes 10 to 30 seconds after this addition (time 0), and the kept-on bench and measured again after few minutes until the O.D. is constant at 290 nm.

Catalase (CAT)

1. The volume of the reaction is 1 mL containing:

	Blank (μL)	Oxidation (μL)	Sample (μL)
Water	850	750	750
EEB	100	100	50-80
Sample	0	0	50-20
Tris (1M)	50	50	50
H₂O₂ (10 mM)	0	100	100

2. The reaction starts by adding H₂O₂.
3. The measurement is done at 240 nm using a quartz cuvette, then the activity is checked through O.D. at time 0 and about 1 min.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

1. The volume of the reaction is 2 mL containing:

	Blank (μL)	Oxidation (μL)	Sample (μL)
KPO₄ buffer (100 mM)	500	500	500
Triton (10%)	2.5	2.5	2.5
EEB Buffer	10	10	0
H₂O	388.5	388.5	388.5
L-Methionine (100 mM)	99	99	99
Sample	0	0	10
NBT (10 mM)	0	5.8	5.8
Riboflavin (0.5 mM)	0	4.8	4.8

2. The reaction is initiated by adding riboflavin.
3. Immediately, the samples are exposed to light (15 W fluorescent tube) for 10 min.
4. The measurement is done at 560 nm using plastic cuvettes.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

1. The volume of the reaction is 1 mL containing:

	Blank (μL)	Oxidation (μL)	Sample (μL)
Mix	110	110	110
Pure Water	390	380	380
EEB Buffer	500	500	450-480
NAPDH (20 mM)	0	10	10
Sample	0	0	50-20

100 mL mix is made with:

- 100 mM HEPES
- 1 mM Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)
- 3 mM Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂)
- 0.5 mM Glutathione disulphide (GSSG)
- Pure water till 100 mL

2. The reaction starts by adding NADPH.
3. All samples are measured at t=0, and then put in water bath or thermoblock at 25 °C for 25 min, and then measured again keeping the same timing at 340 nm using quartz cuvettes.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

Material:

- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂)
- L-ascorbic acid
- EDTA
- Quartz cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer

Catalase (CAT)**Material:**

- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂)
- Double-distilled water
- Tris
- Quartz cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)**Material:**

- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- Double-distilled water
- KPO₄ buffer
- Triton
- L-Methionine
- Nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT)
- Riboflavin
- Plastic cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer
- Box with 15 W fluorescent tube

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

Material:

- Double-distilled water
- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- HEPES
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)
- Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂)
- Glutathione disulphide (GSSG)
- NADPH
- Quartz cuvettes
- Eppendorf

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer
- Water bath or thermoblock

CALCULATIONS

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

Enzymatic activity is determined by measuring absorbance and using the coefficient of extinction. Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

Catalase (CAT)

Enzymatic activity is determined by measuring absorbance and using the coefficient of extinction. Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

$$\text{Percent inhibition (\%)} = \frac{OD_{ox} - OD_{t10}}{OD_{ox}}$$

$$\text{SOD activity (U/mg protein)} = \frac{\text{Percent inhibition}}{50\% \times \text{Sample volume (mL)} \times U \text{ mg}^{-1} \text{ protein}}$$

Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

Enzymatic activity is determined by measuring absorbance and using the coefficient of extinction. Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

REMARKS

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- Work must be always done under cold conditions.
- The substrate is H₂O₂ and its extinction coefficient is 2.8 mM cm⁻¹ at 290 nm and 1 mmol H₂O₂. mL⁻¹ min⁻¹ is defined as 1 unit of APx.

Catalase (CAT)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- Work must be always done under cold conditions.
- The substrate is H₂O₂ and its extinction coefficient is 39.4 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 240 nm and 1 mmol H₂O₂. mL⁻¹ min⁻¹ is defined as 1 unit of CAT.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- KPO₄ buffer (pH 7.8) contains 2 mM EDTA.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- The oxidation allows to eliminate any background error due to the activity of the enzyme without the presence of the experimental samples.
- NADPH is the last compound to be added.
- Each sample must be measured after having the same duration of the reaction, by pacing yourself to have a minute of wait in between each sample for example.
- For each mole of GSSG reduced, one mole of NADPH is oxidised resulting in loss of absorbance at 340 nm. One-unit GR activity is defined as the amount of enzyme that will reduce 1 mmol GSSG per minute at pH 7.6 and 25 °C.
- The NADPH molar extinction coefficient ϵ is 6.22 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

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2.4.7. Non-enzymatic Antioxidants

PRINCIPLE

In addition to enzymatic mechanisms against oxidative stress, there are non-enzymatic mechanisms to combat ROS. Among them are phenols and flavonoids, which are metabolites belonging to the secondary ROS scavenging systems that are activated only when the activity of the antioxidant enzymes declines under severe stress (Fini et al., 2011). The flavonoid quantification protocol presented here (Zhishen et al., 1999) is commonly used to quantify 'total flavonoid' content in plant and food samples. Yet this is not strictly correct, since the method relies on the nitration of aromatic rings with a catechol group and can only identify phenolic compounds with this chemical structure. However, the approach is selected since all of the metabolites identified by the $AlCl_3$ reaction are antioxidants, and there is a strong relationship between their concentrations and the samples' overall antioxidant activity (Bautista et al., 2016).

PROCEDURE

Total Phenolic Compounds (TPC) Quantification Essay

1. 100 μ L of sample of 50-100 mg of fresh weight extracted with methanol 80% is used, and 1.4 mL H_2O is added in 2.0 mL tubes.
2. The gallic acid standard curve is prepared:
 - a. The blank tube is prepared with 100 μ L of 80% methanol + 1.4 mL H_2O .
 - b. Gallic acid standard curve + (100 μ L of 80% methanol + 1.3 mL H_2O) or 1.4 mL H_2O :

Tube	Gallic acid (0.2 μ g μ L ⁻¹)	H ₂ O	Gallic Ac μ g
0	0.0 μ L	100	0
1	20 μ L	80	4
2	30 μ L	70	6
3	40 μ L	60	8

4	60 μL	40	12
5	80 μL	20	16
6	100 μL	0	20

c. Gallic acid stock should be diluted previously to a final concentration of $0.2 \mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ in H_2O .

3. 100 μL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent is added to the 2 mL tubes, which are vortexed. After vortex, the sample must be incubated at room temperature for 5 min.
4. 350 μL of 15% Na_2CO_3 (w/v) is added to all tubes and vortexed.

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
Na_2CO_3	15 g	1.5 g
mQH_2O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

5. The mixture is incubated at room temperature in darkness for at least 90 min.
6. The solution is read at 765 nm in plastic cuvettes.
7. The quantity of total polyphenols is calculated as μg eq. gallic acid according to the standard curve.

Total Flavonoids (TF) Quantification Essay

1. 50 μL of sample extracted with methanol 80% is added to 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes.
2. 450 μL H_2O is also added.
3. The catechin standard curve is prepared
 - a. The blank tube is prepared with 50 μL of 80% methanol + 450 μL H_2O .
 - b. Catechin standard curve:

Tube	Catechin ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	H_2O	Catechin μg
0	0 μL	500	0
1	50 μL	450	5
2	100 μL	400	10
3	150 μL	350	15
4	200 μL	300	20
5	250 μL	250	25
6	300 μL	200	30

4. 30 μL of 5% NaNO_2 (w/v) is added to all samples (blank, samples and standard curve tubes). This step starts the nitration of the catechol group. The mixture is vortexed and incubated at room temperature for 5 min.

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
NaNO_2	5 g	0.5 g

H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL
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5. 30 μ L of 10% AlCl₃ (w/v) is added to all tubes. The mixture is vortexed and incubated at room temperature for 6 min.

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
AlCl ₃	10 g	1 g
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

6. 200 μ L of 1 M NaOH is added.

7. 240 μ L of H₂O is added and then the mixture is vortexed.

8. The absorbance is read at 510 nm in plastic cuvettes.

9. The quantity of total flavonoids is calculated as mg eq. catechin g⁻¹_{DW}.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

TPC Material:

- Double-distilled water
- 80% Methanol
- Gallic acid
- Folin-Ciocalteu reagent
- Sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃)
- Eppendorf tubes
- Plastic cuvettes

TF Material:

- Double-distilled water
- 80% Methanol
- Catechin
- Sodium nitrite (NaNO₂)
- Aluminium chloride (AlCl₃)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Eppendorf tubes
- Plastic cuvettes

Equipment:

- Vortex
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the plant extract samples is measured and the standard curve equation is used to calculate the concentration of gallic acid or catechin in the samples, depending on the assay.

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- In case the standard curve or any value do not follow a linear reaction; both the samples and the blank must be diluted with double-distilled water.
- TPC is expressed as mg eq gallic acid g^{-1}_{DW} .
- TF is expressed as mg eq catechin g^{-1}_{DW} .

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2.4.8. Oxidations products: malondialdehyde (MDA)

PRINCIPLE

As a result of photo-oxidative stress, if ROS are not counterbalanced by antioxidant defences, oxidative damage occurs over different biomolecules (oxidized compounds, such as primary or secondary lipid peroxidation products and modified proteins), which constitute excellent photo-oxidative stress markers focusing on the consequences after the damage. Malondialdehyde (MDA) is one of the oxidation products derived from lipid peroxidation and is usually measured by several studies assessing the degree of oxidative stress (Fenollosa and Munné-Bosh, 2018). The method presented here is based on the methods of Du et al. (1992), Hodges et al. (1999), and Taulavuori et al. (2001).

PROCEDURE

1. 80% methanolic extracts: 50-100 mg of leaf fresh tissue are homogenized in 2 mL of 80% methanol, macerated O/N in agitation and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm at 4 °C for 15 min. The supernatants are transferred into new tubes (kept in liquid nitrogen).
2. 200 μ L of the methanolic extract is added into two tubes, and 400 μ L of 80% methanol is added.

Note: depending on the value of the absorbance, the volume of the aliquots can be changed while keeping the 600 µL final volume: (1:1, 2:1, 5:1, etc). Absorbance should not be above 1.0.

3. 600 µL of 20% TCA is added together with 0.5% TBA to **TUBE 1**.

Reagent	100 mL	50 mL	20 mL
TBA	0.5 g	0.250 g	0.1 g
TCA	20 mL	10 mL	4 mL
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL	Up to 20 mL

600 µL of 20% TCA is added to **TUBE 2**. This tube is the blank.

Reagent	100 mL	50 mL	10 mL
TCA	20 mL	10 mL	2 mL
H ₂ O	80 mL	40 mL	8 mL

- The samples are vigorously mixed, heated in water bath at 95 °C for 15 min and cooled in ice for 5 min to stop the reaction.
- Then, the samples are centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 10 min.
- The absorbance of the supernatant is measured at 440, 532 and 600 nm with a reference (blank) without TBA in plastic cuvettes.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 80% Methanol
- Liquid nitrogen
- 20% and 0.1% TCA (Trichloroacetic Acid)
- 0.5% TBA (Thiobarbituric acid)
- Double-distilled water
- Ice
- Tubes
- Plastic cuvettes

Equipment:

- Centrifuge
- Hot water bath 95 °C
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

MDA equivalents (nmol mL⁻¹) are calculated following the equations (Hodges et al., 1999):

$$1) A = [(Abs_{532+TBA}) - (Abs_{600+TBA}) - (Abs_{532-TBA} - Abs_{600-TBA})]$$

$$2) B = [(Abs_{440+TBA} - Abs_{600+TBA}) \times 0.0571]$$

$$3) MDA \left(\frac{\text{nmol}}{\text{mL}} \right) = \left(\frac{(A-B)}{157000} \right) 10^6 \text{ (Du and Bramlage, 1992).}$$

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- Eppendorf with safety screw cap or special caps must be used to put the samples in the water bath at 95 °C.

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2.4.9. Osmolyte Quantification

PRINCIPLE

Osmolytes are a collection of metabolites with diverse functions such as maintaining water uptake and cell turgor, plasma membrane protection, enzyme stabilisers and protectants against oxidative stress (Plazas et al., 2019). Their accumulation in cells generally does not interfere with metabolism (Singh et al., 2015). Proline, glycine betaine or soluble sugars are examples of osmolytes whose levels increase under stress situations. The protocol for proline quantification is based on Bates et al. (1973) and Vicente et al. (2004) methods. The protocol for betaine glycine is based on Grieve and Grattan (1983), and the protocol for total soluble sugars is based on Dubois et al. (1955; 1956).

PROCEDURE

Proline Determination with Colorimetric Assay

- **Reactive preparation**

1. Preparation of acidic ninhydrin:

- Water bath is preheated to 60 °C and a bottle is placed inside.
- The ninhydrin is measured in a precision balance and placed into a falcon covered in aluminium foil.
- It is diluted using glacial acetic acid.
- The solution is warmed by placing into the bottle preheated in the water bath and vortexed every 10 min for one hour.
- The orthophosphoric acid (6 M) is added and kept in the fridge. It is stable at 4 °C for 24 h.

Reagent	20 samples	100 samples
Ninhydrin	0.25 g	1.25 g
Glacial acetic acid	6 mL	30 mL
6 M Orthophosphoric acid	4 mL	20 mL

2. Preparation of 3% sulfosalicylic acid:

- 3 g of 5-sulfosalicylic acid (2-hydroxy-5-sulfobenzoic acid) is dissolved in 80 mL distilled water and make up to 100 mL. Solution can be stored at room temperature for weeks.

Reagent	100 samples
5-sulfosalicylic acid dihydrate	3 g
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL

3. Preparation of 85% orthophosphoric acid solution:

Reagent	Weight/Volume
Orthophosphoric acid	85 mL
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL

4. Preparation of 6 M orthophosphoric acid solution:

Reagent	Weight/Volume
85% Orthophosphoric acid	48 mL
H ₂ O	72 mL

5. Preparation of 2 mM L-Proline (Mw = 115.13 g mol⁻¹):

- First, 100 mM solution is prepared:

Reagent	10 mL
L-Proline	0.115 g
H ₂ O	Up to 10 mL

- A dilution of 1/10: 1 mL of 100 mM L-proline + 9 mL of H₂O is done to obtain 10 mM L-proline.
- A dilution of 1/5: 2 mL of 10 mM L-proline + 8 mL of H₂O is done to obtain 2 mM L-proline.

- **Protocol**

1. The samples are harvested and approximately 100 mg of fresh leaf material is used for measurement.
2. The tissue is grinded with liquid nitrogen in mortar and pestle. Samples can be stored at -80 °C.
3. 500 µL (5 µL mg⁻¹ fresh weight) of 3% sulfosalicylic acid is added, and the plant material is grinded or vortexed. The tubes are kept on ice until finishing with all samples. Again, 500 µL of 3% sulfosalicylic acid is added and the crushing or vortexing is repeated.
4. The mixture is transferred to a 2 mL Eppendorf tube with a blue (1000 µL) tip (it might be cut).
5. Samples are centrifuged in a benchtop centrifuge with maximum speed at room temperature for 15 min.
6. 500 µL sample is transferred into a new Falcon / Kornig tube (15 mL) and 500 µL acidic ninhydrin and 500 µL glacial acetic acid (volumes 1:1:1) are added.
7. The patron curve tubes are prepared.
8. The tubes are incubated at 98 °C in a water bath (at 96 °C in a thermoblock) for 60 min.
9. The reaction is stopped on ice for 10 min.
10. The tubes are incubated at room temperature for 5 min.
11. The samples are extracted with toluene: 3 mL toluene is added (2:1 volume of toluene and sample) to the reaction mixture, the samples are vortexed for 20 s, and left on the bench for 5 min to allow the separation of the organic and water phases.
12. The chromophore containing toluene is removed into a fresh tube: two phases must appear, the upper one containing toluene and all the proline. The toluene must be carefully handled considering that is neurotoxic.
13. 1 mL of the superior phase is transferred to a glass cuvette.
14. The absorbance is measured at 520 nm using toluene as reference. The proline concentration is determined using a standard concentration curve and calculated on fresh weight basis (usually expressed as µg g⁻¹_{FW} or µmol g⁻¹_{FW}).
15. The blank (toluene) must be kept till the measurements are finished. The same cuvette is used to measure the standard curve, measuring always from the lowest to

the highest concentration. The same cuvette might be used for measurement of all the samples of one species but not of different species.

16. The standard curve:

Tube	2 mM L-proline	[mM] _f	Sulfosalicylic acid	μmol
Blank	0.00 μL	0.00	500.0 μL	0
1	12.5 μL	0.05	487.5 μL	0.025
2	25.00 μL	0.10	475.0 μL	0.05
3	37.5 μL	0.15	462.5 μL	0.075
4	62.5 μL	0.25	437.5 μL	0.125
5	100 μL	0.40	400.0 μL	0.2
6	150 μL	0.60	350.0 μL	0.3
7	200 μL	0.80	300.0 μL	0.4

17. 500 μL acidic ninhydrin and 500 μL glacial acetic acid are added (volumes 1:1:1). Add two volumes of toluene after the incubation at 98/96 °C.

18. Blank tube is used as blank (to make the zero), and the standard curve is built up.

19. Values of absorbance above two must be dilute with toluene. Then, a new blank is prepared by diluting the old blank following the same ratio as with the sample with toluene.

20. Sample values of ABS >1.0: a dilution with toluene 1:3 to 1:10 (abs>3.0) is prepared and the same with the blank.

21. First standardised to the original volume of the sample (1 mL) and then to the dry weight of the sample, independently of working with fresh tissue): μmol g⁻¹_{DW}.

Glycine Betaine Essay

- 1.5 mL of double-distilled water is added to each sample (50-100 mg, fresh weight).
- The mixture is shaken for 24 h.
- Then, the sample is centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min and the supernatant is collected.
- 400 μL of 2 N H₂SO₄ is added to 400 μL of the mixture and incubated in ice for 1 h.
- 50 μL of cold KI-I₂ is added to 125 μL of the mixture.
- The mixture is shaken very gently to favour the crystallisation of glycine and then is incubated at 4 °C in the dark for 16 h.
- It is centrifuged at maximum speed at 0 °C for 45 min and the supernatant is discarded.
- The pellet (crystals) is diluted in 1.4 mL of cold 1,2 dichloroethane and the measurement of OD is done at 365 nm after 2.5 h.
- A standard curve is made with known concentrations of betaine (1 mg mL⁻¹).
- It is expressed in μmol eq. betaine g⁻¹_{DW}.

Total Soluble Sugars (TSS) Quantification Essay

- **Reactive preparation**

1. 5% Phenol

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
90% Phenol	5.56 mL	0.556 mL
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

2. 1 mM Glucose

Reagent	1 M Glucose	10 mM Glucose	1 mM Glucose
Glucose	1.802 g	100 µL 1 M Glu	1 mL 10 mM Glu
H ₂ O	Up to 10 mL	Up to 10 mL	Up to 10 mL

All solutions must be vortexed during the process

- **Protocol**

1. 25 µL (or up to 100 µL depending on the species) sample extracted with 80% methanol is used in large glass assay tubes, and within a fumes hood.
2. H₂O is added up to 500 µL (475-400 µL).
 - a. The blank tube is prepared with 25 µL of 80% methanol + 475 µL H₂O.
 - b. Standard curve:

Tube	1 mM Glucose	H ₂ O	µg Glucose
0	0.00 µL	500	0
1	25 µL	475	4.505
2	50 µL	450	9.01
3	75 µL	425	13.515
4	100 µL	400	18.02
5	125 µL	375	22.525
6	150 µL	350	27.03

3. 500 µL of 5% phenol is added to all samples (blank, samples and standard curve tubes).
4. 2.5 mL of H₂SO₄ is added to all tubes.
5. All the samples are left at room temperature between 20-30 min. Never more than 30 min.
6. The sample is poured directly from tubes into glass cuvettes and read at 490 nm.
7. TSS contents are expressed in mg eq. glucose g⁻¹_{DW}.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Proline determination material:

- 3% Sulfosalicylic acid
- Acidic ninhydrin
- Orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄)
- Glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH)
- Toluene
- L-Proline
- Double-distilled water
- Liquid nitrogen
- Glass cuvettes

Glycine betaine determination material:

- Hydrogen chloride (HCl)
- Betaine
- KI-I₂
- 1,2-Dichloroethane
- Double-distilled water
- Ice
- Iodine (I₂)
- Potassium iodide (KI)
- Orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄)
- Acidic ninhydrin
- Glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH)
- Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)
- Glass cuvettes

TSS Quantification

- 90% Phenol
- Double-distilled water
- Glucose
- 80% Methanol
- Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)
- Glass cuvettes

Equipment:

- Falcon tubes
- Aluminium foil

- Mortar and pestle
- Hot water bath
- Vortex
- Shaker
- Precision scale
- Microcentrifuge
- Spectrophotometer
- Fumes hood
- Large glass essay tubes (also double) with taps

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the plant extract samples must be measured, and the standard curve equation must be used to calculate the concentration of proline, betaine or glucose, depending on the assay, in the samples.

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.

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3. PERENNIAL

3.1. Almond

3.1.1. Trunk cross-sectional area

PRINCIPLE

Trunk cross sectional area measurements are related to tree height, tree phenological development, weight and fruit yield (Westwood and Roberts, 1970). This parameter can be linked to external and internal factors serving as a proxy parameter for the response of trees to modifications in environmental conditions, soil management, fertilization or irrigation strategies (Neely et al., 1972; Goldhamer and Fereres, 2001). Measurement may be carried out with the help of a diameter tape (tape whose diameter unit is in centimetres), or with the use of a calliper. Tree diameter is measured in cm to avoid overestimation of the volume and to compensate measurement errors (FAO, 2009).

PROCEDURE

1. First, the point at which to measure the tree's diameter is located 1.3 m above the trunk base of the tree. If there is a branch at this height, then, locate the point 30 cm below or above the branch, where the swelling around the branch junction no longer exists.
2. The tree trunk is wrapped around with tape measure. Avoid accidentally placing it at an angle or getting it caught on a branch.
3. The number, in centimetres, where the measuring tape reaches the starting point and the end of the tape is noted. This is the tree's circumference at breast height.
4. The tree vegetative growth is evaluated at the end of the growing season in 3 trees per treatment.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tape measure or calliper.

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3.2. Apple

3.2.1. Tree general health

PROCEDURE

In spring and summer (points 0–9, where 0 - tree perished, 9 – excellent tree health) (Ikase, Rubauskis, 2020; Univer 2020).

3.2.2. Flowering and yielding intensity

PROCEDURE

(points 0–9, where 0 - none, 9 - abundant),

3.2.3. Scab and mildew damages

PROCEDURE

(points 0–9, where 0 – no visible infection, 9 - > 90% infection, almost all tree damaged),

3.3. Apricot, Persimmon, Hazelnut and Pistachio

3.3.1. Pigmentation- Chlorophyll α , Chlorophyll b , Carotenoids and Total Chlorophyll Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Photosynthetic pigments are the key components of the photosynthetic machinery of plants that impart a significant role in light harvesting and generation of reducing agents, and their production level shows their photosynthetic abilities. Therefore, the content of photosynthetic pigments has been extensively employed as a relevant parameter to evaluate the photosynthetic efficiency and to determine the response of plants to environmental stress. Carotenoids are fat-soluble molecules localized to the plastids of plant tissues. Carotenoids protect all photosynthetic organisms against damage caused by light by releasing too much light into the environment in the form of heat or by detoxifying ROS and reducing lipid peroxidation (Sali et al., 2015; Sarwar et al., 2020; Luqman et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

Pigment extraction

1. 1 g of leaf sample is homogenized in 50 mL acetone in a porcelain mortar, in 3 replicates for each group.
2. The samples are homogenized with a shaking incubator for 30 min.
3. At the end of this period, the samples are kept in the refrigerator at 4 °C for 24 h.
4. The samples are filtered, 1/5 water is added to the homogenate, and the mouths is covered with parafilm.
5. The samples are then homogenized again in the shaking incubator for 15 min and kept in the refrigerator at 4 °C for 24 h.
6. At the end of this period, the samples are centrifuged at 5,000 g for 10 min (De Kok and Graham, 1980).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. The absorbance values of the centrifuged samples are read on a spectrophotometer at 662, 645, 470 nm

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Acetone
- Distilled water

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- Porcelain mortar
- Tape measure

CALCULATIONS

1. Chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*) = $11.75 \times A_{662} - 2.35 \times A_{645}$
2. Chlorophyll *b* (Chl *b*) = $18.61 \times A_{645} - 3.96 \times A_{662}$
3. Carotenoid = $(1000 \times A_{470} - 2.27 \times \text{Chl } a - 81.4 \times \text{Chl } b) / 227$
4. Total chlorophyll = Chl *a* + Chl *b* (Lichtenthaler and Wellburn, 1983).

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3.3.2. Lipid Peroxidation – Malondialdehyde Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) that contain two or more double bonds are particularly susceptible to oxidation by free radicals and other highly reactive species. In brief, an allylic hydrogen is abstracted by a reactive species, such as the hydroxyl radical (HO[•]), resulting in the formation of lipid peroxy radicals (LOO[•]). This radical can then react with a second PUFA, forming a lipid hydroperoxide (LOOH) and a second LOO[•], resulting in the propagation of the lipid oxidation. Alternatively, LOO[•] can attack an intramolecular double bond and form a cyclic endoperoxide which decomposes to malondialdehyde. Malondialdehyde (MDA) is one of many low molecular weight end-products of lipid hydroperoxide decomposition and is the most often measured as an index of lipid peroxidation (Esterbauer et al., 1991; Halliwell and Gutteridge, 2015; Ding et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

1. Heath and Packer's (1968) method is used for MDA analysis.
2. After homogenizing 0.5 g of leaf sample with 5 mL of 0.1% trichloroacetic acid (TCA), the homogenate is centrifuged at 10,000 *g* for 10 min.
3. Then, 2 mL of the supernatant of the centrifuged sample is taken and 2 mL of 0.5% thiobarbituric acid (TBA) is added.
4. The mixture is kept in a water bath at 95 °C for 30 min.
5. At the end of the period, the samples are quickly cooled in an ice bath.
6. Then, the sample is centrifuged at 10,000 *g* for 15 min.
7. Finally, the absorbance of the supernatant is measured at 532 and 600 nm (Heath and Packer (1968)).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Trichloroacetic acid (TCA)
- Thiobarbituric acid (TBA)

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Vortex mixer
- Magnetic stirrer
- Dry heating block or water bath set to 90 °C
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

1. (Absorbance at 532) - (Absorbance at 600) is absorbance due to MDA-TBA adduct.
2. Extinction coefficient of this MDA-TBA adduct is 155 mM⁻¹cm⁻¹.

REFERENCES

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3.3.3. Enzyme quantification - Peroxidase Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Peroxidases are classified as oxidoreductases and are the second largest class of enzymes applied in biotechnological processes. These enzymes are used to catalyse various oxidative reactions using hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and other substrates as electron donors (Cárdenas-Moreno et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.

3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. 3 mL of 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 6.0), 0.04 mL of 0.03 M H₂O₂, and 0.05 mL of 0.2 M guaiacol are vortexed to make a solution.
2. The change in 1 minute of the enzymatic activity is evaluated at a wavelength of 436 nm by adding 0.1 mL of extract to 0.9 mL of solution.
3. The extinction coefficient of guaiacol is 26.6 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (MacAdam et al., 1992; Peters et al., 1989).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- H₂O₂
- Guaiacol
- KH₂PO₄
- K₂HPO₄

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- pH meter
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

1. Enzyme activity (Units L⁻¹) = (Δ Abs × Total assay volume) / (Δ t × ϵ × l × Enzyme sample volume)
2. Specific activity: Units mg⁻¹ protein

REFERENCES

Andrews, C.J., Cummins, I., Skipsey, M., Grundy, N.M., Jepson, I., Townson, J. & Edwards, R. (2005). Purification and characterisation of a family of glutathione transferases with roles in herbicide detoxification in soybean (*Glycine max* L.); selective enhancement by herbicides and herbicide safeners. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 82(3), 205-219.

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3.3.4. Enzyme quantification – Ascorbate Peroxidase Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Ascorbate peroxidase (APX) is an important antioxidant and integral component of the AsA-GSH cycle. While CAT predominantly scavenges H₂O₂ in the peroxisomes, APX performs the same function in the cytosol and the chloroplast. The APX reduces H₂O₂ to H₂O and DHA, using ascorbic acid (AA) as a reducing agent (Rather et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.
3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. The reaction mixture is made up with 250 µL of extract, 550 µL of phosphate buffer (pH 7.6), 100 µL of 10 mM EDTA, 12 mM H₂O₂, and 100 µL of 0.25 mM ascorbic acid.
2. The absorbance change is observed in a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 290 nm for 1 min.
3. The extinction coefficient for APX activity is 2.8 mM⁻¹cm⁻¹ (Çakmak, 1994; Asada, 2000).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- H₂O₂
- KH₂PO₄
- K₂HPO₄
- Ascorbic acid

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer

- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- pH meter
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

1. Enzyme activity (Units L⁻¹) = $(\Delta\text{Abs} \times \text{Total assay volume}) / (\Delta t \times \epsilon \times l \times \text{Enzyme sample volume})$
2. Specific activity = Units mg⁻¹ protein

REFERENCES

Andrews, C.J., Cummins, I., Skipsey, M., Grundy, N.M., Jepson, I., Townson, J. & Edwards, R. (2005). Purification and characterisation of a family of glutathione transferases with roles in herbicide detoxification in soybean (*Glycine max* L.); selective enhancement by herbicides and herbicide safeners. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 82(3), 205-219.

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3.3.5. Enzyme quantification – Superoxide Dismutase Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) is the most important antioxidant defence system against reactive oxygen species (ROS) and superoxide anion radicals. The accumulation of ROS, resulting from metabolic changes in response to abiotic stress, leads to oxidative stress, which damages cell membranes (lipid peroxidation), proteins, DNA, and RNA molecules. SOD converts a superoxide radical into O₂ molecule and forms another superoxide radical into hydrogen peroxide, which is a less reactive molecule (Iqbal et al., 2023; Tounsi et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.
3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. Solution A is prepared by mixing the solution prepared with 24.8 mg cytochrome-c in 100 mL of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.8) and the solution prepared by adding 0.76 mg xanthine to 10 mL of distilled water.
2. Solution B containing 0.2 U mL⁻¹ xanthine oxidase is prepared.
3. The reaction mixture is prepared using 900 µL A solution, 50 µL B solution and 100 µL sample.
4. Enzyme activity is determined by the absorbance change in 1 minute at a wavelength of 550 nm in a spectrophotometer (McCord and Fridovich, 1969).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- KH₂PO₄
- K₂HPO₄
- Cytochrome c
- Xanthine
- Xanthine oxidase

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- pH meter
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

1. SOD solutions at specific concentrations are graphed against known values at 5 µL, 10 µL, and 15 µL in order to create a calibration chart. This process is done with pure SOD enzyme.
2. Inhibition ratio = $\frac{\text{OD control} - \text{OD sample}}{\text{OD control}} \times 100$
3. The amount of SOD when the inhibition ratio reaches 50% in 1 mL reaction solution is defined as one SOD activity unit (U).

REFERENCES

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- Tounsi, S., Jemli, S., Feki, K., Brini, F. & Najib Saïdi, M. (2023). Superoxide dismutase (SOD) family in durum wheat: promising candidates for improving crop resilience. *Protoplasma*, 260(1), 145-158.

3.3.6. Enzyme quantification – Catalase Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Catalase (CAT) is an antioxidant enzyme present in all aerobic organisms. It is known to catalyse H_2O_2 into water and oxygen in an energy-efficient manner in the cells exposed to environmental stress. Catalase is located in all major sites of H_2O_2 production in the cellular environment (such as peroxisomes, mitochondria, cytosol and chloroplast) of higher plants. Multiple molecular forms of catalase isozymes indicate its versatile role within the plant system. The modulation of H_2O_2 by the catalase isozymes within specific cells or organelles at specific time and developmental phases directly or indirectly interferes with signal transduction in plants (Sharma and Ahmad, 2014; Baker et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.
3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. 1/15 M potassium sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) is prepared.
2. 160 μ L H_2O_2 is added to 100 mL of this buffer.
3. 200 μ L of the sample is added to 800 μ L of the potassium phosphate buffer to which H_2O_2 has been added.
4. The absorbance change obtained in 1 min is determined at 240 nm in the spectrophotometer.
5. The extinction coefficient for H_2O_2 is 0.0396 $cm^2 \mu mol^{-1}$ (Luck 1963).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- KH_2PO_4
- Na_2HPO_4
- H_2O_2

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- pH meter
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

1. Enzyme activity (Units L^{-1}) = $(\Delta\text{Abs} \times \text{Total assay volume}) / (\Delta t \times \epsilon \times l \times \text{Enzyme sample volume})$
2. Specific activity: Units mg^{-1} protein

REFERENCES

- Andrews, C.J., Cummins, I., Skipsey, M., Grundy, N.M., Jepson, I., Townson, J. & Edwards, R. (2005). Purification and characterisation of a family of glutathione transferases with roles in herbicide detoxification in soybean (*Glycine max* L.); selective enhancement by herbicides and herbicide safeners. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 82(3), 205-219.
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- Sharma, I. & Ahmad, P. (2014). Catalase: a versatile antioxidant in plants. In *Oxidative Damage to Plants*, pp. 131-148. Academic Press.

3.3.7. Enzyme quantification – Glutathione S-Transferase Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Glutathione S-transferases (GST) belong to a super-family of multifunctional proteins and are one of the most important families of detoxifying enzymes in nature. There are involved in diverse intracellular events such as, primary and secondary metabolisms, stress metabolism, herbicide detoxification and plant protection against ozone damages, heavy metals, xenobiotics and microbes' infections as well as in various

aspects of seedling development, including hypocotyl elongation, anthocyanin accumulation, and the like. The crucial functions of GSTs have stimulated the development of novel applications in analytical and agricultural biotechnology (Estévez and Hernández, 2020; Russell and Richardson, 2023).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.
3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. A solution of 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer, 0.002 M reduced glutathione in 0.01 M Tris- HCl (pH 7.4), and 0.15 M CDNB (1-chloro,2-4dinitrobenzene) is prepared in 96% ethanol.
2. The reaction mixture is prepared with 400 µL of 0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer, 400 µL of reduced glutathione, 100 µL of sample, and 150 µL of CDNB.
3. The enzyme activity is determined as the absorbance change obtained in 3 min at a wavelength of 344 nm in the spectrophotometer.
4. The extinction coefficient of CDNB is $9.6 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Habig et al., 1974).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- KH_2PO_4
- K_2HPO_4
- 1-chloro,2-4dinitrobenzene (CDNB)
- Ethanol
- Reduced glutathione

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- pH meter
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

1. Enzyme activity (Units L⁻¹) = (Δ Abs × Total assay volume) / (Δ t × ϵ × l × Enzyme sample volume)
2. Specific activity: Units mg⁻¹ protein

REFERENCES

Andrews, C.J., Cummins, I., Skipsey, M., Grundy, N.M., Jepson, I., Townson, J. & Edwards, R. (2005). Purification and characterisation of a family of glutathione transferases with roles in herbicide detoxification in soybean (*Glycine max* L.); selective enhancement by herbicides and herbicide safeners. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 82(3), 205-219.

Estévez, I.H. & Hernández, M.R. (2020). Plant glutathione S-transferases: an overview. *Plant Gene*, 23, 100233.

Habig, W.H. (1974). The first enzymatic step in mercapturic acid formation. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 249, 7130-7139.

Russell, T.M. & Richardson, D.R. (2023). The good Samaritan glutathione-S-transferase P1: An evolving relationship in nitric oxide metabolism mediated by the direct interactions between multiple effector molecules. *Redox Biology*, 59, 102568.

3.3.8. Enzyme quantification – Glutathione Reductase Analysis

PRINCIPLE

Glutathione reductase (GR) is a part of the glutathione system and belongs to a family of flavin-containing pyridine nucleotide-disulphide oxidoreductases. GR is one of the central enzymes in the antioxidant defence system that catalyses the reduction of oxidized glutathione (GSSG) to reduced glutathione (GSH) (Baek et al., 2022; Vyas et al., 2022).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.
3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. 0.2 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 2 mM EDTA, 2 mM NADPH in 10 mM Tris-HCL (pH 7) and 20 mM GSSG is prepared in 10 mL distilled water.
2. The reaction mixture is prepared with 500 μ L of 0.2 M potassium phosphate buffer, 50 μ L of 2 mM NADPH, 50 μ L of 20 mM GSSG, 250 μ L distilled water and 150 μ L of the sample.

- The enzyme activity is determined as the absorbance change obtained in 1 minute at a wavelength of 340 nm in the spectrophotometer.
- NADPH is calculated with an extinction coefficient of $6.2 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Carlberg and Mannervick, 1985).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- KH_2PO_4
- K_2HPO_4
- NADPH
- GSSG

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer
- Microcentrifuge

CALCULATIONS

- Enzyme activity (Units L^{-1}) = $(\Delta\text{Abs} \times \text{Total assay volume}) / (\Delta t \times \epsilon \times l \times \text{Enzyme sample volume})$
- Specific activity: $\text{Units mg}^{-1} \text{ protein}$

REFERENCES

- Andrews, C.J., Cummins, I., Skipsey, M., Grundy, N.M., Jepson, I., Townson, J. & Edwards, R. (2005). Purification and characterisation of a family of glutathione transferases with roles in herbicide detoxification in soybean (*Glycine max* L.); selective enhancement by herbicides and herbicide safeners. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 82(3), 205-219.
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- Carlberg, I. & Mannervik, B. (1985). Glutathione reductase. In *Methods in Enzymology*, Vol. 113, pp. 484-490. Academic Press.
- Vyas, B., Bhowmik, R., Akhter, M. & Ahmad, F.J. (2022). Identification, analysis of deleterious SNPs of the human GSR gene and their effects on the structure and functions of associated proteins and other diseases. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 5474.

3.3.9. Antioxidant molecule – Total Glutathione (GSH)

PRINCIPLE

Glutathione (GSH) is a ubiquitous, abundant, and indispensable thiol for plants that participates in various biological processes, such as scavenging reactive oxygen species, redox signaling, storage and transport of sulphur, detoxification of harmful substances, and metabolism of several compounds. Therefore, knowledge of GSH metabolism is essential for plant science. It is an important thiol antioxidant as well as a scavenger of reactive electrophilic compounds that functions with glutathione-S-transferases. Glutathione has multiple physiological functions through its ability to maintain intracellular redox homeostasis in addition to functions in various defence reactions. Glutathione is essential for plant growth and development (Cheng et al., 2015; Ito and Ohkama-Ohtsu, 2023).

PROCEDURE

Enzyme extraction

1. 0.5 g of leaves are homogenized with 2.5 mL of 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), 2.5 mL of 0.1 mM EDTA and 0.5 mL of 1% polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP).
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 30 min.
3. The supernatant is stored in a -80 °C deep freezer until reading (Andrews et al., 2005).

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. For reduced glutathione quantification, 125 mM sodium disulphate buffer ($\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4\text{-NaH}_2\text{PO}_4$) containing 6.3 mM EDTA is prepared.
2. The buffer is prepared freshly (pH: 7.5) containing 0.248 mg NADPH per millilitre.
3. Likewise, DTNB is prepared freshly at 2.378 mg per millilitre of buffer.
4. 700 μL NADPH and 100 μL DTNB are kept in a hot water bath at 30 °C for 10-12 min.
5. At the end of this period, 150 μL distilled water, 5 μL GR and 50 μL sample are added.
6. Absorbance is read at 412 nm for 1 minute (Akerboom and Sies, 1981).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tris
- HCl
- EDTA
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- Na_2HPO_4
- NaH_2PO_4
- NADPH
- DTNB

- GR

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette

CALCULATIONS

1. After reading the absorbance of the samples, the standard graph is drawn to determine reduced glutathione.
2. Specific activity is calculated by dividing the values found by the milligrams of protein per millilitre of supernatant.

REFERENCES

Akerboom, T.P. & Sies, H. (1981). Assay of glutathione, glutathione disulfide, and glutathione mixed disulfides in biological samples. In *Methods in Enzymology* 77, 373-382. Academic Press.

Andrews, C.J., Cummins, I., Skipsey, M., Grundy, N.M., Jepson, I., Townson, J. & Edwards, R. (2005). Purification and characterisation of a family of glutathione transferases with roles in herbicide detoxification in soybean (*Glycine max* L.) selective enhancement by herbicides and herbicide safeners. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 82(3), 205-219.

Cheng, M.C., Ko, K., Chang, W.L., Kuo, W.C., Chen, G.H. & Lin, T.P. (2015). Increased glutathione contributes to stress tolerance and global translational changes in Arabidopsis. *The Plant Journal* 83(5), 926-939.

Ito, T. & Ohkama-Ohtsu, N. (2023). Degradation of glutathione and glutathione conjugates in plants. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 74(11), 3313-3327.

3.3.10. Protein quantification - Bradford method**PRINCIPLE**

The Bradford method is a colorimetric technique used for the **quantification of proteins**. This parameter is especially interesting when measuring the plant health and analysing whether a plant is encountering any abiotic or biotic stress factor, as one of the first detected responses is the synthesis of stress proteins when plant is under acclimation or protein degradation when is under senescence (Batista-Silva et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE**Bradford Reagent Preparation**

1. 100 mg of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye is weighed.
2. 50 mL 95% ethanol is added.
3. 100 mL 85% phosphoric acid is added slowly and carefully
4. All is mixed until the blue dye is completely dissolved.
5. The dye/ethanol/phosphoric acid solution is added to 850 mL pure sterile H₂O.
6. Any precipitates are filtered.

7. Bradford reagent can be stored at 4 °C for months.

Measuring Protein Standard

1. First, the spectrophotometer is warmed up.
2. Six different volumes of 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ BSA are pipetted into separate cuvettes [0 µL (0 µg), 10 µL (5 µg), 20 µL (10 µg), 30 µL (15 µg), 40 µL (20 µg), 50 µL (25 µg)].
3. 1.5 mL of Bradford Reagent is added to each cuvette.
4. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film and mixed by gently inverting.
5. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 10 min.
6. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. Between 10 to 50 µL of the protein that is to be quantified are pipetted into a cuvette; a dilution may be necessary.
 - a. The goal is to get an absorbance reading that is in the middle of the standard curve.
 - b. An equal volume of 1 M NaOH can be added to help solubilize membrane proteins.
When choosing this option, be sure to include NaOH in the standards.
2. 1.5 mL of Bradford Reagent is added to the cuvette.
3. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film and mixed by gently inverting.
4. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 10 min.
5. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.
 - a. If the absorbance does not fall within the range of the standard curve, change the dilution of the sample and measure absorbance again.

Standard Curve Generation

1. A scatter plot is made for the standard curve values.
2. The X-axis will be micrograms (µg) of standard protein that were assayed; the Y-axis will be Abs₅₉₅ that was measured.
3. Fit a linear trendline to the graph.
4. Show the linear regression equation.
5. Calculate the unknown amount of protein by using the linear regression equation, as shown in the calculations section of this document.
6. The unknown concentration of the original protein solution can be calculated by dividing the amount of protein by the volume of protein assayed and multiplying the quotient by the dilution factor, as shown in the calculations section.
7. Alternatively, a curvilinear (polynomial) trendline can be fitted to the graph. This polynomial regression equation may sometimes give a better estimation of protein concentration.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye
- 95% ethanol
- 85% phosphoric acid
- 850 mL pure sterile H₂O
- NaOH
- Bovine serum albumin (BSA)

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. $\mu\text{g of protein} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - y \text{ intercept}}{\text{slope}}$
2. $\frac{\mu\text{g of protein}}{\mu\text{L assayed}} = \text{concentration assayed}$
3. Concentration assayed \times dilution factor = concentration of original solution

REFERENCES

Batista-Silva, W., Heinemann, B., Rugen, N., Nunes-Nesi, A., Araújo, W.L., Braun, H.P. & Hildebrandt, T.M. (2019). The role of amino acid metabolism during abiotic stress release. *Plant, Cell and Environment*, 42(5), 1630-1644.

Bradford, M.M. (1976) A rapid sensitive method for the quantification of microgram quantities of protein utilising the principle of protein-dye binding. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 72, 248-254.

3.4. Berry

3.4.1. Visual examination for plant health

PRINCIPLE

Visual examination plays a vital role in proactive plant management, enabling growers to identify, assess, and address potential threats to berry plant health in a timely manner, ultimately contributing to the overall success and sustainability of berry production.

PROCEDURE

100 leaves per plot

Twice per vegetation (end of May and end of September)

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Chewer (% of the leaf surface)
- Skeletoniser (% of the leaf surface)
- Life miner (piece/leaf, possibly specifying the species)
- Roller
- Sucker (size of the settlement with five categories: free, diffuse specimens, small, middle, extended settlements)
- Plant pathogens (covering of the leaf surface, possibly specifying the species)

3.5. Custard Apple

3.5.1. Number of flowers

PRINCIPLE

The number of flowers in custard apple is important for several reasons. First, custard apple flowers require pollination for fruit set. The number of flowers directly affects the potential fruit yield. Each flower that is successfully pollinated and develops into a fruit contributes to the overall crop production. By counting the number of flowers, farmers and researchers can estimate the potential yield of custard apple. This information helps in planning harvest and post-harvest activities, such as storage and marketing. Moreover, studying the number of flowers can provide insights into the flowering behaviour of custard apple trees. It helps in understanding the timing and duration of flowering, which can be influenced by factors such as weather conditions, tree age, and variety (Chaudari et al., 2014).

PROCEDURE

After pruning, four branches are marked per plant, in the middle part of the plant, one in each position (north, south, east and west), the flower buds are counted.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Marker

REFERENCES

Chaudhari, J.C., Patel, K.D., Yadav, L., Patel, U.I. & Varu, D.K. (2014). Effect of plant growth regulators on flowering, fruit set and yield of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) cv. Sindhan. *Advances in Life Science*, 5(4), 1202-1204.

3.5.2. Height, crown diameter, and trunk diameter

PROCEDURE

These measurements are carried out at the beginning and at the end of each cycle. A graduated tape measure is used for height and crown diameter, and a calliper is used to measure trunk diameter at 10 cm from the ground.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tape measure

REFERENCES

Hiwale, S. & Hiwale, S. (2015). Custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.). *Sustainable Horticulture in Semiarid Dry Lands*, 135-152.

3.6. Olive

3.6.1. Trunk cross-sectional area

PRINCIPLE

Trunk cross sectional area measurements are related to tree height, tree phenological development, weight, and fruit yield (Westwood and Roberts, 1970). This parameter can be linked to external and internal factors serving as a proxy parameter for the response of trees to modifications in environmental conditions, soil management, fertilization or irrigation system (Neely et al., 1972; Goldhamer and Fereres, 2001). Measurement may be carried out with the help of a diameter tape (tape whose diameter unit is in centimetres), or with the use of a calliper. To avoid overestimation of the volume and to compensate measurement errors tree diameter is measured in cm (FAO, 2009).

PROCEDURE

1. First, the point at which to measure the tree's diameter is located 1.3 m above the trunk base of the tree. If there is a branch at this height, then, locate the point 30 cm below or above the branch, where the swelling around the branch junction no longer exists.
2. The tree trunk is wrapped around with tape measure. Avoid accidentally placing it at an angle or getting it caught on a branch.

3. The number, in centimetres, where the measuring tape reaches the starting point and the end of the tape is noted. This is the tree's circumference at breast height.
4. The tree vegetative growth is evaluated at the end of the growing season in 3 trees per treatment.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tape measure or calliper.

REFERENCES

FAO (2009). Monitoring and Evaluation of National Forest Resources - Handbook for the integrated field data collection. Version 2.2. Monitoring and Evaluation Working Paper National Forest Resources Assessment. NFMA 37/S. Rome.

Goldhamer, D.A. & Fereres, E. (2001). Irrigation scheduling protocols using continuously recorded trunk diameter measurements. *Irrigation Science*, 20, 115-125. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002710000034>

Neely, D., Himelick, E.B. & Crowley, W.R. (1972). Fertilization of established trees: A report of field studies. *Illinois Natural History Survey Bulletin*, 30(1-8), 235-266. <https://doi.org/10.21900/j.inhs.v30.158>

Westwood, M.N. & Roberts, A.N. (1970). The relationship between trunk cross-sectional area and weight of apple trees. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 95(1), 28-30. <https://doi.org/10.21273/JASHS.95.1.28>

3.7. Orange and Peach

3.7.1. Plant growth

PRINCIPLE

Measures of plant growth give an insight into the health and vigour of the plant. These measures include size (height, diameter or cover), number of leaves (or stems), fresh and dry weights, water content, relative water content and dry matter. It is also important to observe the possible occurrence of pests and diseases, their development and crop damage during the crop cycle.

PROCEDURE

Size Measurement

A ruler or tape measure is to measure the height of the plant from the soil surface to the tip of the plant, and the width of the plant.

Number of Leaves and Foliar Area

The number of leaves is counted manually and the leaf area of each leaf is estimated by taking a photograph of the leaf and analysing it with image analysis software such as *ImageJ*, *Image-Pro Plus* or *Digimizer*.

Fresh and dry weight, water content, relative water content and dry matter

With a balance, the weight of the leaves (roots or the whole plant) is measured as soon as they are harvested to obtain the fresh weight (FW) of the sample. Subsequently, the leaves are placed in paper envelopes and placed in an oven at 65 °C for 3 days until the weight of the samples is constant, dry weight (DW). Once the FW and DW values are obtained, the water content (WC) and dry matter content (DMC) can be calculated (Admane et al., 2023) (see calculation section). For the calculation of the relative water content (RWC), it is necessary to obtain the turgent weight (TW). This weight is obtained after placing the plant material in double-distilled water for at least 24 h. Once obtained, the RWC is calculated (Erice et al., 2018).

Pest and Disease Monitoring

Regular monitoring and measurements of pests and diseases affecting crops is carried out throughout the growth of the crop. This includes identifying and counting pests or assessing disease severity through visual inspection or quantitative methods. To identify pests and diseases, a manual may be used to recognize adequately its symptoms. Integrated Pest Management Manuals "Guías de gestión integrada de plagas" published by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fishery and Food of the Spanish Government (Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación, 2023) are proper references for identification of pests and diseases for our key crops.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ruler or tape measure
- Image analysis software
- Paper envelopes

Equipment:

- Balance or precision scale
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

1. Water content (WC) = $[(FW - DW) \div FW] \times 100$
2. Dry matter content (DMC) = $(DW \div FW) \times 100$
3. Relative water content (RWC) = $[(FW - DW) \div (TW - DW)] \times 100$

REFERENCES

Admane, N., Cavallo, G., Hadjila, C., Cavalluzzi, M.M., Rotondo, N. P., Salerno, A., Cannillo, J., Difonzo, G., Caponio, F., Ippolito, A., Lentini, G. & Sanzani, S.M. (2023). Biostimulant formulations and *Moringa oleifera* extracts to improve yield, quality, and storability of hydroponic lettuce. *Molecules*, 28(1), 373.

Erice, G., Pérez-Bueno, M.L., Pineda, M., Barón, M., Aroca, R. & Calvo-Polanco, M. (2018). Determining plant water relations. Sánchez-Moreiras, A.M. & Reigosa, M.J. (Eds) in *Advances in Plant Ecophysiology Techniques*, pp. 109-134.

Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación. (2023, 4th December). *Integrated Pest Management Manuals*. (<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/sanidad-vegetal/productos-fitosanitarios/guias-gestion-plagas/default.aspx>).

3.7.2. Pigment content

PRINCIPLE

Photosynthetic tissues have different pigments (chlorophylls *a*, *b*, carotenoids and anthocyanins) whose quantities (or ratio) may vary depending on the situation in which the plant finds itself, affecting its photosynthetic capacity. The determination of pigments can be done by destructive or non-destructive methods. A very common method that allows us to accurately obtain the content of chlorophyll *a*, *b* and carotenoids is by spectrophotometric assays (Lichtenthaler and Wellburn, 1983; Porra 2002; Zhao et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2018).

PROCEDURE

Chlorophyll and carotenoids determination

1. Cold conditions are mandatory.
2. Between 50-100 mg of fresh material is weighed and placed in Eppendorf tubes together with two glass or metal beads (for crushing in the sample crusher) and dropped into liquid nitrogen.
3. 1 mL of 80% acetone (4:1) is added with a micropipette:

Reagent	Volume
Acetone	80 mL
H ₂ O	20 mL

4. The samples are placed in a shaker in the dark (aluminium foil) at 4 °C for 24 h.
5. The samples are centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 15 min.
6. The supernatant is diluted 10-fold with 80% acetone with micropipette (100 µL extract-900 µL 80% acetone).
7. Optical density is measured with plastic or glass cuvettes at 470, 646 and 663 nm. The work must be done on ice.

8. Pigments contents are calculated as described in calculations section.

Anthocyanins determination

1. 300 mg of frozen plant material is mixed with 3 mL 95% methanol:1.5 M hydrochloric acid (85:15) at 4 °C for 24 h.
2. The extract is centrifuged at 12,000 g for 5 min and the supernatant is collected.
3. Optical density is measured with plastic cuvettes at 470, 646 and 663 nm.
4. Anthocyanin content is calculated as described in calculations section.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Eppendorf tubes
- Glass or metal balls
- Liquid nitrogen
- 80% Acetone
- Methanol
- Hydrochloric acid
- Double-distilled water
- Ice
- Plastic or glass cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Micropipette
- Sample grinder
- Centrifuge
- Shaker at 4 °C
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. Chlorophyll *a* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $12.21A_{663} - 2.81A_{646}$
2. Chlorophyll *b* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $20.13A_{646} - 5.03A_{663}$
3. Carotenoids ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(1000A_{470} - 3.27[\text{Chl } a] - 104[\text{Chl } b])/229$
4. Anthocyanins ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) = $46,200 \times [(A_{530} - A_{620}) - 0.1 \times (A_{650} - A_{620})]$

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- The work must be done always under cold and dark conditions.

- 80% acetone is used as blank for chlorophyll and carotenoids measurement and 95% methanol:1.5 M hydrochloric acid (85:15) for anthocyanin quantification.
- Optical density measurements should be between 0.1 -1. Otherwise, the sample must be diluted or concentrated using 80% acetone in the case of pigments or 95% methanol:1.5 M hydrochloric acid (85:15) for anthocyanin quantification.
- Photosynthetic pigment contents are expressed in $\text{mg g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$.

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3.7.3. Chlorophyll *a* fluorescence measurement

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is one of the most widely used parameters in green plants to monitor the modulation and alterations of the photosynthetic process under stress (Misra et al., 2012). A widely used chlorophyll fluorescence technique is the pulse modulated fluorescence measurement method described by Schrieber et al. (1986). With this technique, 4 parameters of great relevance for the study of the state of photosystem II (PSII) can be determined. These are (López-González et al., 2020):

- F_v/F_m , the maximum efficiency of PSII: following exposure to darkness, reaction centres of PSII are typically open ($F = F_0$), non-photochemical quenching is negligible (NPQ = 0) and the fluorescence yield is at its peak. In this state, PSII's quantum yield reaches its maximum and saturation pulses (F_v) cause a rise in fluorescence. A decrease of this parameter usually denotes physical damages in the antenna system of PSII.
- Φ_{II} , the effective photochemical quantum yield of PSII: quantifies the proportion of light absorbed by the PSII-related chlorophyll that is utilized in the quantum yield. It can reveal information about the linear electron flow's speed and, therefore, serves as an indicator of the total photosynthetic capacity *in vivo* (Maxwell and Johnson 2000).

- Φ_{NPQ} , the measurement of regulated non-photochemical non-fluorescent energy dissipation (as heat): is linearly related to heat dissipation and ranges from 0 to infinity. Although this varies amongst different species, the typical values in a healthy plant are in the range of 0.5–3.5 at saturating light intensities (Maxwell and Johnson, 2000). Excessive photon flux density is indicated by high values of this parameter, which causes the plant to defend itself by releasing the energy as heat. If this value rises, it means that the photosynthetic mechanism is producing more energy than it needs, but the plant can control this excess to prevent damage.
- Φ_{NO} , the measurement of non-regulated emission of energy (as fluorescence): it determines the non-regulated energy loss as fluorescence (Klughammer et al., 2008). Elevated values of this parameter suggest that the plant is having problems adjusting to incident radiation due to inefficient photochemical energy conversion and protective regulatory mechanisms. Extremely high values imply that the plant has been damaged or is likely to be damaged because they show that the PSII reaction centres are blocked, inhibiting the development of a trans-thylakoid proton gradient.

PROCEDURE

The measures are carried out *in situ* using the MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0 (PhotosynQ, East Lansing, MI, USA) (Álvarez-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

1. The plant (or branch) is covered with a black bag during at least 20 min before taking the measurement.
2. After 20 min, the fluorimeter is placed on a leaf to measure the maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II (F_v/F_m). The MultispeQ v2.0 is used to run the "Fv/Fm in the dark" protocol, also linked to the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>].
3. With the help the "rapid information dense experimental sequence" (RIDES) protocol ("Photosynthesis RIDES 2.0"), available on the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>, (Kuhlgert et al., 2016)] the different parameters related to chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is obtained: the effective quantum yield of the photosystem II photochemical reactions (Φ_{II}), the regulated energy dissipation in the form of heat (Φ_{NPQ}), and the non-regulated energy dissipation (Φ_{NO} , fluorescence emitted).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Dark bags

Equipment:

- MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0

CALCULATIONS

1. $\Phi_{II} + \Phi_{NPQ} + \Phi_{NO} = 1$
2. $\Phi_{NPQ} = 1 - \Phi_{II} - \Phi_{NO}$
3. $\Phi_{NO} = F_s/F_m$
4. $F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_0)/F_m$

REMARKS

For a correct measurement of F_v/F_m it is essential that the plants (or leaves) are in complete darkness for at least 20 min to open all reaction centres of PSII.

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3.7.4. Hydrogen Peroxide Quantification

PRINCIPLE

Oxidative stress is the imbalance between prooxidants and antioxidants. The amount of reactive oxygen species (ROS), among other prooxidants, gives information about the status of the redox imbalance during the plant response to a stress factor. Chloroplasts are quantitatively and qualitatively one of the most important sources of ROS in illuminated plant cells (Foyer and Noctor, 2003). Thus, the measurement of ROS, such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), is a good marker of the status of the photosynthetic apparatus (Alexieva et al., 2001; Loreto and Velikova, 2001; Velikova et al., 2001).

PROCEDURE

1. The samples (50-100 mg of fresh plant material) are homogenized in 0.5 mL 0.1% w/v trichloroacetic acid (TCA) on ice.
2. The homogenate is centrifuged at 15,000 *g* at 4 °C for 15 min.
3. From each supernatant, an aliquot of 0.5 mL is added to 0.5 mL of 10 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 1.0 mL of 1 M KI (w/v in fresh double-distilled water H₂O). Mix gently.
4. The reaction is developed for 1 h in darkness (in a card box) and the absorbance is measured at 390 nm for 1 min.
5. H₂O₂ is quantified taking into account a calibration curve using solutions with known H₂O₂ concentrations.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Trichloroacetic acid (TCA)
- 10 mM potassium phosphate (KH₂PO₄) buffer (pH 7.0)
- 1 M potassium iodide (KI)
- Double-distilled water
- H₂O₂ for calibration curve
- Ice
- Double-distilled water
- Card box
- Cuvettes
- Eppendorf

Equipment:

- Pipette
- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the plant extract samples is measured, and the standard curve equation is used to calculate the concentration of H₂O₂ in the samples.

REMARKS

The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure. The blank probe consists of 0.5 mL 0.1% TCA in the absence of leaf extract and follow the same procedure described as for the samples.

Results are expressed as $\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$ calculated from the H₂O₂ calibration curve.

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3.7.5. Protein quantification

PRINCIPLE

The Bradford method (Bradford, 1976) is a colorimetric technique used for the quantification of proteins. This parameter is especially interesting when measuring the plant health and knowing whether a plant is encountering any abiotic or biotic stress factor, as one of the first detected responses is the synthesis of stress proteins when plant is under acclimation or protein degradation when is under senescence (Batista-Silva et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE

Bradford Reagent Preparation:

1. 100 mg of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye is weighed.
2. 50 mL 95% ethanol is added.
3. 100 mL 85% phosphoric acid is added slowly and carefully.
4. All is mixed until the blue dye is completely dissolved.
5. The dye/ethanol/phosphoric acid solution is added to 850 mL pure sterile H₂O.
6. Any precipitates are filtered.
7. Bradford reagent can be stored at 4 °C for months.

Measuring Protein Standard

1. First, the spectrophotometer is warmed up.
2. Seven different volumes of 0.1 mg mL⁻¹ BSA corresponding to different BSA concentrations [0 µL (0 µg), 10 µL (1 µg), 20 µL (2 µg), 30 µL (3 µg), 50 µL (5 µg), 70 µL (7 µg) and 100 µL (10 µg)] are pipetted into separate plastic cuvettes. Pure water is added until 800 µL.
3. 200 µL of Bradford Reagent is added to each cuvette.
4. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film or taps and mixed by gently inverting.

5. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 2-3 min. The reaction is stable for 1 h.
6. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.

Measuring Samples (unknown quantity)

1. Protein extraction can be performed by using PEB (HEPES) method:
100 mg of fresh material is needed (already conserved at -70 °C), to be extracted in 1 mL Protein Extraction Buffer (PEB):

PEB preparation:

- HEPES (20 mM final concentration)
- Potassium chloride (KCl) (50 mM final concentration)
- Triton x-100 (0.1 v/v final concentration)
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) (0.2% w/v final concentration)
- Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP) (0.2% w/v final concentration)
- Glycerol (5% final concentration)

And water till reach the desired volume.

Also is necessary prepare High Salt Buffer (HSB):

- HEPES (225 mM final concentration)
- Potassium chloride (KCl) (1.5 M final concentration)
- Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂) (22.5 mM final concentration)

2. The sample (100 mg of fresh material) is crushed and 1 mL PEB is added, vortexed and put in ice for 5-10 min.
3. 10% of the volume of PEB used is added to HSB (100 µL), vortex and then leave in ice for 10-15 minutes.
4. The tubes are centrifuged at 13,500 rpm at 4 °C for 15 min, and the supernatant is divided into aliquots of about 50-100 µL and saved at -70 °C (this extract is used for enzymatic assays, section 1.6)
5. Between 10 to 50 µL of the extract previously prepared with PEB and HSB are pipetted into a cuvette.
6. 200 µL of Bradford Reagent is added to the cuvette.
7. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film or tap and mixed by gently inverting.
8. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 2-3 min.
9. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.
 - a. If the absorbance does not fall within the range of the standard curve, the dilution of the sample must be changed and measured again, or a new standard curve with new concentrations must be done.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye
- 95% ethanol
- 85% phosphoric acid
- Double-distilled water
- Bovine serum albumin (BSA)
- HEPES
- Potassium chloride (KCl)
- Triton X-100
- Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)
- Polyvinylpolypyrrolidone (PVPP)
- Glycerol
- Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂)
- Ice
- Plastic cuvettes
- Eppendorf

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipettes
- Vortex

CALCULATIONS

Standard Curve Generation:

- A scatter plot is made for the standard curve values.
- The X-axis must be micrograms (μg) of standard protein that were assayed, while the Y-axis must be the value obtained when measuring the absorbance at 595 nm.
- A linear trendline to the graph is fitted.
- The linear regression equation is showed.
- The unknown amount of protein is calculated by using the linear regression equation, as shown in the following equations.
- The unknown concentration of the original protein solution is calculated by dividing the amount of protein by the volume of protein assayed, and then multiplying the quotient by the dilution factor, as shown in the calculations section.
- Alternatively, a curvilinear (polynomial) trendline can be fitted to the graph. This polynomial regression equation may sometimes give a better estimation of protein concentration.

$$\mu\text{g of protein} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - y \text{ intercept}}{\text{Slope}}$$

$$\text{Concentration assayed} = \frac{\mu\text{g protein}}{\mu\text{L assayed}}$$

Concentration of original solution = *Concentration assayed* × *dilution factor*

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- The timing for the addition of Bradford to the samples must be similar to test the concentration in similar reactions conditions.
- The samples can be diluted by using EEB (elution extraction buffer).
- EEB, which is used to stabilise the sample and dilute it in most of the enzyme assays, is the same as the PEB buffer minus the PVP and PVPP components.
- In the blank, the volume of sample is replaced by EEB.

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3.7.6. Enzymatic Antioxidant Capacity

PRINCIPLE

Excessive production of ROS during stress conditions acts as signal for the activation of stress response in terms of efficient enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant pathways (Baxter et al., 2014). Among the enzymatic mechanisms, superoxide dismutase (SOD), ascorbate peroxidase (APx), catalase (CAT) and glutathione reductase (GR), are the enzymes most frequently studied as defence mechanisms against ROS. These antioxidant enzymes are located in different sites of plant cells where ROS are generally produced under both normal and stressful conditions (chloroplasts, mitochondria, peroxisomes, plasma membranes, ER, and the cell wall), and work together to detoxify ROS (Noctor et al., 2017).

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

Ascorbate peroxidase plays a crucial role in protecting plants and other organisms from damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS). This enzyme catalyses the reduction

of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) using ascorbate as the reducing agent. The electron donor for the scavenging of hydrogen peroxide in chloroplasts is L-ascorbate and that the L-ascorbate is regenerated from dehydroascorbate (DHA) by the system: photosystem I → ferredoxin → NADP → glutathione. The activity of APx is determined by the measurement of the diminution of the absorbance of oxidized ascorbate at 290 nm, according to Nakano and Asada (1981).

Catalase (CAT)

Catalase plays a crucial role in breaking down hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) into water and oxygen, but also in the oxidation of H donors with a consumption of 1 mol of peroxide. The catalase assay involves monitoring the rate of decomposition of H₂O₂ according to Aebi (1984), and it provides insight into the enzyme's efficiency in catalysing this reaction.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

Superoxide dismutase (SOD) is a critical enzyme that plays a fundamental role in cellular defence mechanisms, by catalysing the dismutation of superoxide radicals (O₂⁻) into O₂ and H₂O₂. This enzymatic reaction is a pivotal part of the cellular antioxidant defence system, serving to neutralize and detoxify ROS generated during normal cellular processes or under conditions of oxidative stress. Total SOD activity is assayed using a modified NBT method.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

Glutathione reductase (GR) is an enzyme that plays a crucial role in the maintenance of cellular redox balance by catalysing the reduction of oxidized glutathione (GSSG) to reduced glutathione (GSH). Glutathione is a tripeptide composed of glutamate, cysteine, and glycine, and is a major cellular antioxidant.

In this reaction, glutathione reductase uses NADPH as a reducing agent to convert oxidized glutathione (GSSG) into its reduced form (2GSH), recycling glutathione and maintaining a reducing environment within the cell.

PROCEDURE

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

1. The volume of the reaction is 2 mL containing 0.5 mM ascorbate, 0.1 mM EDTA, 1.2 mM H₂O₂, sample extract (50-100 μL from the supernatant prepared in Bradford Assay) and EEB until a volume of 2 mL.
2. A blank (minus the sample and the substrate, in this case H₂O₂) and oxidation reaction (substrate minus the sample) is carried out.
3. The reaction starts by adding H₂O.

- The absorbance decrease is recorded in quartz cuvettes 10 to 30 s after this addition (time 0), and the kept-on bench and measured again after few min until the O.D. is constant at 290 nm.

Catalase (CAT)

- The volume of the reaction is 1 mL containing:

	Blank (μL)	Oxidation (μL)	Sample (μL)
Water	850	750	750
EEB	100	100	50-80
Sample	0	0	50-20
Tris (1 M)	50	50	50
H₂O₂ (10 mM)	0	100	100

- The reaction starts by adding H₂O₂.
- The measurement is done at 240 nm using a quartz cuvette, then the activity is checked through O.D. at time 0 and about 1 min.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

- The volume of the reaction is 2 mL containing:

	Blank (μL)	Oxidation (μL)	Sample (μL)
KPO₄ buffer (100 mM)	500	500	500
Triton (10%)	2.5	2.5	2.5
EEB Buffer	10	10	0
H₂O	388.5	388.5	388.5
L-Methionine (100 mM)	99	99	99
Sample	0	0	10
NBT (10 mM)	0	5.8	5.8
Riboflavin (0.5 mM)	0	4.8	4.8

- The reaction is initiated by adding riboflavin.
- Immediately, the samples are exposed to light (15 W fluorescent tube) for 10 min.
- The measurement is done at 560 nm using plastic cuvettes.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

- The volume of the reaction is 1 mL containing:

	Blank (μL)	Oxidation (μL)	Sample (μL)
Mix	110	110	110

Pure Water	390	380	380
EEB Buffer	500	500	450-480
NAPDH (20 mM)	0	10	10
Sample	0	0	50-20

100 mL mix is made with:

- 100 mM HEPES
- 1 mM Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)
- 3 mM Magnesium chloride (MgCl₂)
- 0.5 mM Glutathione disulphide (GSSG)
- Pure water till 100 mL

2. The reaction starts by adding NADPH.

3. All samples are measured at t=0, and then put in water bath or thermoblock at 25 °C for 25 min, and then measured again keeping the same timing at 340 nm using quartz cuvettes.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

Material:

- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂)
- L-ascorbic acid
- EDTA
- Quartz cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer

Catalase (CAT)

Material:

- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂)
- Double-distilled water
- Tris
- Quartz cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes

- Spectrophotometer

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

Material:

- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- Double-distilled water
- KPO_4 buffer
- Triton
- L-Methionine
- Nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT)
- Riboflavin
- Plastic cuvettes

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer
- Box with 15W fluorescent tube

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

Material:

- Double-distilled water
- EEB Buffer (previous explained in 1.5.5 section)
- HEPES
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)
- Magnesium chloride (MgCl_2)
- Glutathione disulphide (GSSG)
- NADPH
- Quartz cuvettes
- Eppendorf

Equipment:

- Pipettes
- Spectrophotometer
- Water bath or thermoblock

CALCULATIONS

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

Enzymatic activity is determined by measuring absorbance and using the coefficient of extinction. Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

Catalase (CAT)

Enzymatic activity is determined by measuring absorbance and using the coefficient of extinction. Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

$$\text{Percent inhibition (\%)} = \frac{OD_{ox} - OD_{t10}}{OD_{ox}}$$

$$\text{SOD activity (U/mg protein)} = \frac{\text{Percent inhibition}}{50\% \times \text{Sample volume (mL)} \times U \text{ mg}^{-1} \text{ protein}}$$

Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

Enzymatic activity is determined by measuring absorbance and using the coefficient of extinction. Enzyme activity is calculated in units per milligram of protein.

REMARKS

Ascorbate peroxidase (APx)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- Work must be always done under cold conditions.
- The substrate is H₂O₂ and its extinction coefficient is 2.8 mM cm⁻¹ at 290 nm and 1 mmol H₂O₂. mL⁻¹ min⁻¹ is defined as 1 unit of APx.

Catalase (CAT)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- Work must be always done under cold conditions.
- The substrate is H₂O₂ and its extinction coefficient is 39.4 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 240 nm and 1 mmol H₂O₂. mL⁻¹ min⁻¹ is defined as 1 unit of CAT.

Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- KPO₄ buffer (pH 7.8) contains 2 mM EDTA.

Glutathione Reductase (GR)

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- The oxidation allows to eliminate any background error due to the activity of the enzyme without the presence of the experimental samples.
- NADPH is the last compound to be added.
- Each sample must be measured after having the same duration of the reaction, by pacing yourself to have a minute of wait in between each sample for example.
- For each mole of GSSG reduced, one mole of NADPH is oxidised resulting in loss of absorbance at 340 nm. One-unit GR activity is defined as the amount of enzyme that will reduce 1 mmol GSSG per min at pH 7.6 and 25 °C.
- The NADPH molar extinction coefficient ϵ is $6.22 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

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3.7.7. Non-enzymatic Antioxidants

PRINCIPLE

In addition to enzymatic mechanisms against oxidative stress, there are non-enzymatic mechanisms to combat ROS. Among them are phenols and flavonoids, which are metabolites belonging to the secondary ROS scavenging systems that are activated only when the activity of the antioxidant enzymes declines under severe stress (Fini et al., 2011). The flavonoid quantification protocol presented here (Zhishen et al., 1999) is commonly used to quantify 'total flavonoid' content in plant and food samples. Yet this

is not strictly correct, since the method relies on the nitration of aromatic rings with a catechol group and can only identify phenolic compounds with this chemical structure. However, the approach is selected since all of the metabolites identified by the $AlCl_3$ reaction are antioxidants, and there is a strong relationship between their concentrations and the samples' overall antioxidant activity (Bautista et al., 2016).

PROCEDURE

Total Phenolic Compounds (TPC) Quantification Essay

1. 100 μ L of sample of 50-100 mg of fresh weight extracted with 80% methanol is used, and 1.4 mL H_2O is added in 2.0 mL tubes.
2. The gallic acid standard curve is prepared:
 - a. The blank tube is prepared with 100 μ L of 80% methanol + 1.4 mL H_2O .
 - b. Gallic acid standard curve + (100 μ L of 80% methanol + 1.3 mL H_2O) or 1.4 mL H_2O :

Tube	Gallic acid ($0.2 \mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$)	H_2O	Gallic Ac μg
0	0.0 μ L	100	0
1	20 μ L	80	4
2	30 μ L	70	6
3	40 μ L	60	8
4	60 μ L	40	12
5	80 μ L	20	16
6	100 μ L	0	20

- c. Gallic acid stock should be diluted previously to a final concentration of $0.2 \mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ in H_2O .
3. 100 μ L of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent is added to the 2 mL tubes, which are vortexed. After vortex, the sample must be incubated at room temperature for 5 min.
4. 350 μ L of 15% Na_2CO_3 (w/v) is added to all tubes and vortexed.

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
Na_2CO_3	15 g	1.5 g
mQH_2O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

5. The mixture is incubated at room temperature in darkness for at least 90 min.
6. The solution is read at 765 nm in plastic cuvettes.
7. The quantity of total polyphenols is calculated as gallic acid μg equivalent according to the standard curve.

Total Flavonoids (TF) Quantification Essay

1. 50 μL of sample extracted with 80% methanol is added to 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes.
2. 450 μL H_2O is also added.
3. The catechin standard curve is prepared
 - a. The blank tube is prepared with 50 μL of 80% methanol + 450 μL H_2O .
 - b. Catechin standard curve:

Tube	Catechin ($100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	H_2O	Catechin (μg)
0	0 μL	500	0
1	50 μL	450	5
2	100 μL	400	10
3	150 μL	350	15
4	200 μL	300	20
5	250 μL	250	25
6	300 μL	200	30

4. 30 μL of 5% NaNO_2 (w/v) is added to all samples (blank, samples and standard curve tubes). This step starts the nitration of the catechol group. The mixture is vortexed and incubated at room temperature for 5 min.

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
NaNO_2	5 g	0.5 g
H_2O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

5. 30 μL of 10% AlCl_3 (w/v) is added to all tubes. The mixture is vortexed and incubated at room temperature for 6 min.

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
AlCl_3	10 g	1 g
H_2O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

6. 200 μL of 1 M NaOH is added.
7. 240 μL of H_2O is added and then the mixture is vortexed.
8. The absorbance is read at 510 nm in plastic cuvettes.
9. The quantity of total flavonoids is calculated as catechin mg equivalent per gram of dry weight.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

TPC Material:

- Double-distilled water

- 80% Methanol
- Gallic acid
- Folin-Ciocalteu reagent
- Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3)
- Eppendorf tubes
- Plastic cuvettes

TF Material:

- Double-distilled water
- 80% Methanol
- Catechin
- Sodium nitrite (NaNO_2)
- Aluminium chloride (AlCl_3)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Eppendorf tubes
- Plastic cuvettes

Equipment:

- Vortex
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the plant extract samples is measured and the standard curve equation is used to calculate the concentration of gallic acid or catechin in the samples, depending on the assay.

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- In case the standard curve or any value do not follow a linear reaction; both the samples and the blank must be diluted with double-distilled water.
- TPC is expressed as mg eq gallic acid $\text{g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$.
- TF is expressed as mg eq catechin $\text{g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$.

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3.7.8. Oxidations products: malondialdehyde (MDA)

PRINCIPLE

As a result of photo-oxidative stress, if ROS are not counterbalanced by antioxidant defences, oxidative damage occurs over different biomolecules (oxidized compounds, such as primary or secondary lipid peroxidation products and modified proteins), which constitute excellent photo-oxidative stress markers focusing on the consequences after the damage. Malondialdehyde (MDA) is one of the oxidation products derived from lipid peroxidation and is usually measured by several studies assessing the degree of oxidative stress (Fenollosa and Munné-Bosh, 2018). The method presented here is based on the methods of Du et al. (1992), Hodges et al. (1999), and Taulavuori et al. (2001).

PROCEDURE

1. 80% Methanolic extracts: 50-100 mg of leaf fresh tissue are homogenized in 2 mL of 80% methanol, macerated O/N in agitation and centrifuged at 13,000 rpm at 4 °C for 15 min. The supernatants are transferred into new tubes (kept in liquid nitrogen).
2. 200 µL of the methanolic extract is added into two tubes, and 400 µL of 80% methanol is added.

Note: depending on the value of the absorbance, the volume of the aliquots can be changed while keeping the 600 µL final volume: (1:1, 2:1, 5:1, etc). Absorbance should not be above 1.0.

3. 600 µL 20% TCA is added together with 0.5% TBA to **TUBE 1**.

Reagent	100 mL	50 mL	20 mL
TBA	0.5 g	0.250 g	0.1 g
TCA	20 mL	10 mL	4 mL
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL	Up to 20 mL

600 µL 20% TCA is added to **TUBE 2**. This tube is the blank.

Reagent	100 mL	50 mL	10 mL
TCA	20 mL	10 mL	2 mL
H ₂ O	80 mL	40 mL	8 mL

4. The samples are vigorously mixed, heated in water bath at 95 °C for 15 min and cooled in ice for 5 min to stop the reaction.
5. Then, the samples are centrifuged at 12,000 rpm at 4 °C for 10 min.
6. The absorbance of the supernatant is measured at 440, 532 and 600 nm with a reference (blank) without TBA in plastic cuvettes.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 80% Methanol
- Liquid nitrogen
- 20% and 0.1% TCA (Trichloroacetic Acid)
- 0.5% TBA (Thiobarbituric acid)
- Double-distilled water
- Ice
- Tubes
- Plastic cuvettes

Equipment:

- Centrifuge
- Hot water bath at 95 °C
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

MDA equivalents (nmol mL⁻¹) are calculated following the equations (Hodges et al., 1999):

$$1) A = [(Ab_{S532+TBA}) - (Ab_{S600+TBA}) - (Abs_{532-TBA} - Abs_{600-TBA})]$$

$$2) B = [(Ab_{S440+TBA} - Ab_{S600+TBA}) \times 0.0571]$$

$$3) MDA \left(\frac{\text{nmol}}{\text{mL}} \right) = \left(\frac{(A-B)}{157000} \right) 10^6 \text{ (Du and Bramlage, 1992).}$$

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- Eppendorf with safety screw cap or special caps must be used to put the samples in the water bath at 95 °C.

REFERENCES

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3.7.9. Osmolyte Quantification

PRINCIPLE

Osmolytes are a collection of metabolites with diverse functions such as maintaining water uptake and cell turgor, plasma membrane protection, enzyme stabilisers and protectants against oxidative stress (Plazas et al., 2019). Their accumulation in cells generally does not interfere with metabolism (Singh et al., 2015). Proline, glycine betaine or soluble sugars are examples of osmolytes whose levels increase under stress situations. The protocol for proline quantification is based on Bates et al. (1973) and Vicente et al. (2004) methods. The protocol for betaine glycine is based on Grieve and Grattan (1983), and the protocol for total soluble sugars is based on Dubois et al. (1955, 1956).

PROCEDURE

Proline Determination with Colorimetric Assay

- **Reactive preparation**

1. Preparation of acidic ninhydrin:

- Water bath is preheated to 60 °C and a bottle is placed inside.
- The ninhydrin is measured in a precision balance and placed into a falcon covered in aluminium foil.
- It is diluted using glacial acetic acid.
- The solution is warmed by placing into the bottle preheated in the water bath. and vortexed every 10 min for one hour.
- The orthophosphoric acid (6 M) is added and kept in the fridge. It is stable at 4 °C for 24 h.

Reagent	20 samples	100 samples
Ninhydrin	0.25 g	1.25 g
Glacial acetic acid	6 mL	30 mL
6 M Orthophosphoric acid	4 mL	20 mL

2. Preparation of 3% sulfosalicylic acid:

- 3 g of 5-sulfosalicylic acid (2-hydroxy-5-sulfobenzoic acid) is dissolved in 80 mL distilled water and make up to 100 mL. Solution can be stored at room temperature for weeks.

Reagent	100 samples
5-sulfosalicylic acid dihydrate	3 g
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL

3. Preparation of 85% orthophosphoric acid solution:

Reagent	Weight/Volume
Orthophosphoric acid	85 mL
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL

4. Preparation of 6 M orthophosphoric acid solution:

Reagent	Weight/Volume
85% Orthophosphoric acid	48 mL
H ₂ O	72 mL

5. Preparation of 2 mM L-Proline (Mw = 115.13 g mol⁻¹):

- First, 100 mM solution is prepared:

Reagent	10 mL
L-Proline	0.115 g
H ₂ O	Up to 10 mL

- A dilution of 1/10: 1 mL of 100 mM L-proline + 9 mL of H₂O is done to obtain 10 mM L-proline.
- A dilution of 1/5: 2 mL of 10 mM L-proline + 8 mL of H₂O is done to obtain 2 mM L-proline.

- **Protocol**

1. The samples are harvested and approximately 100 mg of fresh leaf material is used for measurement.
2. The tissue is grinded with liquid nitrogen in mortar and pestle. Samples can be stored at -80 °C.

3. 500 μL (5 $\mu\text{L mg}^{-1}$ fresh weight) of 3% sulfosalicylic acid is added, and the plant material is grinded or vortexed. The tubes are kept on ice until finishing with all samples. Again, 500 μL of 3% sulfosalicylic acid is added and the crushing or vortexing is repeated.
4. The mixture is transferred to a 2 mL Eppendorf tube with a blue (1000 μL) tip (it might be cut).
5. Samples are centrifuged in a benchtop centrifuge with maximum speed at room temperature for 15 min.
6. 500 μL sample is transferred into a new Falcon / Kornig tube (15 mL) and 500 μL acidic ninhydrin and 500 μL glacial acetic acid (volumes 1:1:1) are added.
7. The patron curve tubes are prepared.
8. The tubes are incubated at 98 °C in a water bath (at 96 °C in a thermoblock) for 60 min.
9. The reaction is stopped on ice for 10 min.
10. The tubes are incubated at room temperature for 5 min.
11. The samples are extracted with toluene: 3 mL toluene is added (2:1 volume of toluene and sample) to the reaction mixture, the samples are vortexed for 20 s, and left on the bench for 5 min to allow the separation of the organic and water phases.
12. The chromophore containing toluene is removed into a fresh tube: two phases must appear, the upper one containing toluene and all the proline. The toluene must be carefully handled considering that is neurotoxic.
13. 1 mL of the superior phase is transferred to a glass cuvette.
14. The absorbance is measured at 520 nm using toluene as reference. The proline concentration is determined using a standard concentration curve and calculated on fresh weight basis (usually expressed as $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}\text{FW}$ or $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{FW}$).
15. The blank (toluene) must be kept till the measurements are finished. The same cuvette is used to measure the standard curve, measuring always from the lowest to the highest concentration. The same cuvette might be used for measurement of all the samples of one species but not of different species.
16. The standard curve:

Tube	2 mM L-proline	[mM]_f	Sulfosalicylic acid	μmol
Blank	0.00 μL	0.00	500.0 μL	0
1	12.5 μL	0.05	487.5 μL	0.025
2	25.00 μL	0.10	475.0 μL	0.05
3	37.5 μL	0.15	462.5 μL	0.075
4	62.5 μL	0.25	437.5 μL	0.125
5	100 μL	0.40	400.0 μL	0.2
6	150 μL	0.60	350.0 μL	0.3

7	200 µL	0.80	300.0 µL	0.4
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17. 500 µL acidic ninhydrin and 500 µL glacial acetic acid are added (volumes 1:1:1). Add two volumes of Toluene after the incubation at 98/96 °C.
18. Blank tube is used as blank (to make the zero), and the standard curve is built up.
19. Values of absorbance above two must be dilute with toluene. Then, a new blank is prepared by diluting the old blank following the same ratio as with the sample with toluene.
20. Sample values of ABS > 1.0: a dilution with toluene 1:3 to 1:10 (abs>3.0) is prepared and the same with the blank.
21. First standardised to the original volume of the sample (1 mL) and then to the dry weight of the sample, independently of working with fresh tissue): µmol g⁻¹_{DW}.

Glycine Betaine Essay

- 1.5 mL of double-distilled water is added to each sample (50-100 mg, fresh weight).
- The mixture is shaken for 24 h.
- Then, the sample is centrifuged at 13,000 rpm for 20 min and the supernatant is collected.
- 400 µL of 2 N H₂SO₄ is added to 400 µL of the mixture and incubated in ice for 1 h.
- 50 µL of cold KI-I₂ is added to 125 µL of the mixture.
- The mixture is shaken very gently to favour the crystallisation of glycine and then is incubated at 4 °C in the dark for 16 h.
- It is centrifuged at maximum speed at 0 °C for 45 min and the supernatant is discarded.
- The pellet (crystals) is diluted in 1.4 mL of cold 1,2 dichloroethane and the measurement of OD is done at 365 nm after 2.5 h.
- A standard curve is made with known concentrations of betaine (1 mg mL⁻¹).
- It is expressed in µmol eq. betaine g⁻¹_{DW}.

Total Soluble Sugars (TSS) Quantification Essay

- **Reactive preparation**

3. 5% Phenol

Reagent	100 mL	10 mL
90% Phenol	5.56 mL	0.556 mL
H ₂ O	Up to 100 mL	Up to 10 mL

4. 1 mM Glucose

Reagent	1 M Glucose	10 mM Glucose	1 mM Glucose
Glucose	1.802 g	100 μ L 1 M Glu	1 mL 10 mM Glu
H ₂ O	Up to 10 mL	Up to 10 mL	Up to 10 mL

All solutions must be vortexed during the process

- **Protocol**

- 25 μ L (or up to 100 μ L depending on the species) sample extracted with 80% methanol is used in large glass assay tubes, and within a fumes hood.
- H₂O is added up to 500 μ L (475-400 μ L).
 - The blank tube is prepared with 25 μ L of 80% methanol + 475 μ L H₂O.
 - Standard curve:

Tube	1 mM Glucose	H ₂ O	μ g Glucose
0	0.0 μ L	500	0
1	25 μ L	475	4.505
2	50 μ L	450	9.01
3	75 μ L	425	13.515
4	100 μ L	400	18.02
5	125 μ L	375	22.525
6	150 μ L	350	27.03

- 500 μ L of 5% phenol is added to all samples (blank, samples and standard curve tubes).
- 2.5 mL of H₂SO₄ is added to all tubes.
- All the samples are left at room temperature between 20-30 min. Never more than 30 min.
- The sample is poured directly from the tubes into glass cuvettes and read at 490 nm.
- TSS contents are expressed in mg eq. glucose g⁻¹_{DW}.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Proline determination material:

- 3% Sulfosalicylic acid
- Acidic ninhydrin
- Orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄)
- Glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH)
- Toluene
- L-Proline
- Double-distilled water

- Liquid nitrogen
- Glass cuvettes

Glycine betaine determination material:

- Hydrogen chloride (HCl)
- Betaine
- KI-I₂
- 1,2-Dichloroethane
- Double-distilled water
- Ice
- Iodine (I₂)
- Potassium iodide (KI)
- Orthophosphoric acid (H₃PO₄)
- Acidic ninhydrin
- Glacial acetic acid (CH₃COOH)
- Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)
- Glass cuvettes

TSS Quantification

- 90% Phenol
- Double-distilled water
- Glucose
- 80% Methanol
- Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)
- Glass cuvettes

Equipment:

- Falcon tubes
- Aluminium foil
- Mortar and pestle
- Hot water bath
- Vortex
- Shaker
- Precision scale
- Microcentrifuge
- Spectrophotometer
- Fumes hood
- Large glass essay tubes (also double) with taps

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the plant extract samples must be measured, and the standard curve equation must be used to calculate the concentration of proline, betaine or glucose, depending on the assay, in the samples.

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.

REFERENCES

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3.8. Vineyard

3.8.1. Chlorophyll α fluorescence measurement

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of chlorophyll α fluorescence is one of the most widely used parameters in green plants to monitor the modulation and alterations of the photosynthetic process under stress (Misra et al., 2012). A widely used chlorophyll fluorescence technique is the pulse modulated fluorescence measurement method described by Schrieber et al. (1986). With this technique, 4 parameters of great relevance for the study of the state of photosystem II (PSII) can be determined. These are (López-González et al., 2020):

- F_v/F_m , the maximum efficiency of PSII: following exposure to darkness, reaction centres of PSII are typically open ($F = F_0$), non-photochemical quenching is negligible ($NPQ = 0$) and the fluorescence yield is at its peak. In this state, PSII's quantum yield reaches its maximum and saturation pulses (F_v) cause a rise in fluorescence. A

decrease of this parameter usually denotes physical damages in the antenna system of PSII.

- Φ_{II} , the effective photochemical quantum yield of PSII: quantifies the proportion of light absorbed by the PSII-related chlorophyll that is utilized in the quantum yield. It can reveal information about the linear electron flow's speed and, therefore, serves as an indicator of the total photosynthetic capacity *in vivo* (Maxwell and Johnson 2000).
- Φ_{NPQ} , the measurement of regulated non-photochemical non-fluorescent energy dissipation (as heat): is linearly related to heat dissipation and ranges from 0 to infinity. Although this varies amongst different species, the typical values in a healthy plant are in the range of 0.5–3.5 at saturating light intensities (Maxwell and Johnson, 2000). Excessive photon flux density is indicated by high values of this parameter, which causes the plant to defend itself by releasing the energy as heat. If this value rises, it means that the photosynthetic mechanism is producing more energy than it needs, but the plant can control this excess to prevent damage.
- Φ_{NO} , the measurement of non-regulated emission of energy (as fluorescence): it determines the non-regulated energy loss as fluorescence (Klughammer et al., 2008). Elevated values of this parameter suggest that the plant is having problems adjusting to incident radiation due to inefficient photochemical energy conversion and protective regulatory mechanisms. Extremely high values imply that the plant has been damaged or is likely to be damaged because they show that the PSII reaction centres are blocked, inhibiting the development of a trans-thylakoid proton gradient.

PROCEDURE

The measures are carried out *in situ* using the MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0 (PhotosynQ, East Lansing, MI, USA) (Álvarez-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

1. The plant (or branch) is covered with a black bag during at least 20 min before taking the measurement.
2. After 20 min, the fluorimeter is placed on a leaf to measure the maximum quantum efficiency of photosystem II (F_v/F_m). The MultispeQ v2.0 is used to run the "Fv/Fm in the dark" protocol, also linked to the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>].
3. With the help the "rapid information dense experimental sequence" (RIDES) protocol ("Photosynthesis RIDES 2.0"), available on the PhotosynQ platform [<https://photosynq.org/>, (Kuhlgert et al., 2016)] the different parameters related to chlorophyll *a* fluorescence is obtained: the effective quantum yield of the photosystem II photochemical reactions (Φ_{II}), the regulated energy dissipation in the form of heat (Φ_{NPQ}), and the non-regulated energy dissipation (Φ_{NO} , fluorescence emitted).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Dark bags

Equipment:

- MultispeQ fluorimeter v2.0

CALCULATIONS

$$13. \quad \Phi_{II} + \Phi_{NPQ} + \Phi_{NO} = 1$$

$$14. \quad \Phi_{NPQ} = 1 - \Phi_{II} - \Phi_{NO}$$

$$15. \quad \Phi_{NO} = F_s/F_m$$

$$16. \quad F_v/F_m = (F_m - F_0)/F_m$$

REMARKS

For a correct measurement of F_v/F_m it is essential that the plants (or leaves) are in complete darkness for at least 20 min to open all reaction centres of PSII.

REFERENCES

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3.8.2. Leaf quality

PRINCIPLE

Leaf colour, size, and shape can provide information about nutrient deficiency or stress.

PROCEDURE

Diagnosis and recognition of grape leaf diseases by visual inspection:

Figure 5. Examples of diseases in vineyard leaves. Source: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2210537918303718>

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3.8.3. Growth and Yield

PRINCIPLE

Monitoring plant growth and yield is crucial for assessing plant health. Parameters such as number of leaves, shoot length and berry weight are indicators of plant vitality.

PROCEDURE

The number of leaves is measured manually. Shoot length is measured using a tape measure.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Tape measure

3.8.4. Buds sprout

PRINCIPLE

Counting the % of sprouted buds is important for several reasons:

Assessing Vineyard Health: Bud sprout counting allows vineyard managers to assess the overall health and vigour of the vines. It provides valuable information about the vineyard's ability to produce new shoots and leaves, which are essential for photosynthesis and fruit development.

Monitoring Frost Damage: Bud sprout counting helps in monitoring and assessing the impact of frost events on the vineyard. By counting the number of buds that have successfully sprouted, vineyard managers can determine the extent of damage caused by frost.

Evaluating Pruning Effectiveness: Bud sprout counting allows vineyard managers to evaluate the effectiveness of pruning practices. It helps in determining if the pruning technique used has resulted in the desired bud break and shoots growth, ensuring that the vineyard receives adequate sunlight and airflow.

Estimating Crop Yield: Bud sprout counting provides an indication of the potential crop yield in the vineyard. By quantifying the number of sprouted buds, vineyard managers can estimate the number of potential clusters and, subsequently, the overall grape production.

Identifying Disease and Pest Issues: Bud sprout counting can help identify disease or pest issues early in the growing season. If a significant number of buds fail to sprout or show signs of damage, it may indicate the presence of diseases, pests, or other issues that require immediate attention.

Optimizing Vineyard Management: Bud sprout counting provides important data for vineyard management decisions. It helps to determine if adjustments are needed in terms of irrigation, fertilization, or canopy management practices to optimize vineyard growth and fruit quality.

PROCEDURE

Sprouts are counted manually.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

No equipment needed

Figure 6. Bud sprout

REFERENCES

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3.8.5. Number of bunches per branch

PRINCIPLE

Measuring the number of bunches per branch provides valuable data for optimizing crop yield, quality, and plant health, ultimately contributing to the overall success and sustainability of the vineyard or orchard operation.

PROCEDURE

Bunches are counted manually in a significant number of plants.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

No equipment needed

REFERENCE

May, P. (2000). From bud to berry, with special reference to inflorescence and bunch morphology in *Vitis vinifera* L. *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research*, 6(2), 82-98.

3.8.6. Phenological stage

PRINCIPLE

The BBCH scale for vineyards typically includes stages such as bud burst, leaf development, flowering, fruit set, berry development, veraison (colour change), and harvest. Each stage is assigned a specific code or number according to the BBCH scale, allowing for consistent monitoring and comparison across different vineyards and regions.

By using the BBCH scale, vineyard managers, researchers, and viticulturists can effectively track the phenological development of grapevines, plan and schedule vineyard management practices, and assess the overall health and condition of the vineyards.

PROCEDURE

BBCH specific for vineyard:

- 00-09 - Germination (bud development/germination)
- 10-19 - Leaf development (leaf development)
- 20-29 - tillering (does not apply to grapevine)
- 30-39 - Shooting (does not apply to grapevine)
- 40-49 - ear swelling (does not apply to grapevine)

- 50-59 - ear emergence (formation of the shoots)
- 60-69 - Flowering (blooming)
- 70-79 - Fruit development (fruit development)
- 80-89 - Seed ripening (ripening of berries)
- 90-99 - Death of annual plants or entry into dormancy of perennial plants

The vine-specific developmental macro-stages in detail are:

0 - Winter dormancy: budbreak

- 00 - dormancy: winter eyes pointed to rounded, light to dark brown depending on the grape variety; bud scales more or less closed depending on the grape variety.
- 01 - Beginning of bud swelling: eyes begin to enlarge.
- 03 - End of bud swelling: buds swollen but not yet green
- 05 - Wool stage: wool-like brown hair clearly visible
- 07 - Beginning of bud break: green shoot tips become visible
- 09 - Bud burst: green shoot tips clearly visible

Figure 7. First steps from dormancy to the first shoots in the vineyard. Source: <https://glossary.wein.plus/bbch-code>

1 - Leaf development

- 11 - first leaf unfolded and spreading from the shoot
- 12 - two stem leaves unfolded
- 13 - three leaves unfolded
- 14-19 - more and more leaves unfolded

5 - Development of the flowering plants (flower bud)

- 53 - Inflorescences clearly visible
- 55 - Inflorescences enlarge; individual flowers are crowded together
- 57 - Inflorescences are fully developed; single flowers spread out

6 – Flower

- 60 - First flower capsules detach from the flower base

- 61 - Beginning of flowering: 10% of flower capsules shed
- 62 - 20% of the flower heads shed
- 63 - Pre-flowering: 30% of calyxes shed
- 64 - 40% of the flower heads shed
- 65 - Full flowering: 50% of the calyxes shed
- 66 - 60% of the calyxes shed
- 67 - 70% of the calyxes shed
- 68 - 80% of the flower heads dropped
- 69 - End of flowering

Figure 8. Flowering process. Source: <https://glossary.wein.plus/bbch-code>

7 - Fruit development = fruit set

- 71 - Ovaries begin to enlarge; "cleaning of the berries" is completed
- 73 - Berries are coarse-grained; clusters begin to descend
- 75 - Berries are pea-sized; grapes droop
- 77 - Beginning of grape closure
- 79 - End of grape closure

Figure 9. Fruiting and ripening process in vineyard. Source: <https://glossary.wein.plus/bbch-code>

8 - Fruit ripening = veraison, maturation, engustment, physiological ripeness

- 81 - Beginning of ripening, berries begin to lighten (or begin to discolour)
- 83 - Progression of berry lightening (or berry discolouration)

- 85 - Softening of the berries
- 89 - Full ripeness of the berries (readiness for harvest)

9 - Dormancy = leaf fall

- 91 - After the harvest: Completion of wood ripeness
- 92 - Beginning of leaf discolouration
- 93 - Beginning of leaf fall
- 95 - 50% of the leaves have fallen
- 97 - End of leaf fall
- 99 - Harvest crop/clusters

REFERENCES

<https://glossary.wein.plus/bbch-code>

3.8.7. Leaf area

PRINCIPLE

The calculation of leaf area provides a very useful index for assessing the effects of cultural techniques, particularly with regard to foliage management techniques and the potential of the management system, estimating vigour (Champagnol, 1984), characterizing hedge density and the light microclimate (Lopes, 1994), among other possibilities. Leaf area was estimated according to the methodology defined by Lopes and Pinto (2005).

PROCEDURE

On each vine, an average, fruitful shoot is chosen, representative in terms of vigour, and the following records were made:

Number of main leaves (NFP); Length of lateral, left and right veins of the largest leaf (L2E and L2D) and the smallest leaf (L2e and L2d) of the main leaves (Fig. 10); Number of granddaughter leaves (NFN); Length of lateral, left and right veins of the largest leaf (L2E and L2D) and the smallest leaf (L2e and L2d) of the granddaughters (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Example of the left (L2e) and right (L2d) secondary veins and the main vein (L1)

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material

- Graduated ruler
- Pencil
- Notebook

CALCULATIONS

To calculate the leaf area of a leaf (LA_{leaf}), an equation is used which relates the area of the leaf to the sum of the lengths of the secondary widths.

The unit leaf area (LA_{leaf}) is estimated using a mathematical model proposed by Lopes and Pinto (2005), which is based on the relationship between leaf area and the sum of the length of the upper left and right lateral veins (L2E and L2D).

$$LA_{leaf} = 0.2365 \times L2^{2.2162} \text{ (eq. 1)}$$

Where:

LA_{leaf} is the leaf area of the leaf (cm^2)

L2 is the sum of the left vein (cm) and the right vein (cm)

The average AF of the main leaves (LA_{ave}) was determined according to the following equation:

$$LA_{ave} = \frac{(LA_{larger} + LA_{smaller})}{2}$$

Where:

LA_{larger} is the LA of the largest leaf (cm^2)

$LA_{smaller}$ is the LA of the smallest leaf (cm^2)

To calculate the secondary leaf area, the parameters will be the number of net leaves with a main vein longer than 3 cm (NF), the length of the lateral veins of the largest net leaf (L2E and L2D) and the smallest leaf (L2e and L2d).

The estimation of leaf area can be calculated using a model created by the same authors, which is based on measuring the same shoot at different stages of the cycle, where three explanatory variables are recorded: number of main leaves (main vein > 3 cm), leaf area of the largest leaf and leaf area of the smallest leaf.

The main leaf area per shoot is estimated using the following equation:

$$LA_{main}(cm^2) = Exp[0.0835 + 0.992 \times Ln(LA_{ave} \times NL)]$$

The secondary leaf area (La_{sec}) per shoot is also calculated using the methodology of Lopes and Pinto (2005). Three explanatory variables were recorded at different stages

of the vegetative cycle: number of granddaughter leaves (main vein > 3 cm) ($N_{L_{gra}}$), leaf area of the largest granddaughter (LA_{lar}) and leaf area of the smallest granddaughter (LA_{sma}). The secondary leaf area per shoot was calculated using the following equation:

$$LA_{sec}(cm^2) = Exp [0.346 + 1.029 \times Ln (LA_{sma} + NL_{gra}) - 0.125 \times Ln (LA_{lar})]$$

The total leaf area per shoot (TLA) is determined by adding the secondary and main leaf areas. The leaf area per vine is calculated by multiplying the average number of shoots per vine by the leaf area per shoot.

$$TLA = LA_{main} + LA_{sec}$$

REFERENCES

Champagnol, F. (1984). *Éléments de physiologie de la vigne et de viticulture générale* (pp. 351-p).

Lopes, C.M.A. (1994). Influência do sistema de condução no microclima do coberto, vigor e produtividade da videira (*Vitis vinifera* L.). PhD Thesis Dissertation.

Lopes, C. & Pinto, P.A. (2005). Easy and accurate estimation of grapevine leaf area with simple mathematical models. *Vitis*, 44(2), 55-61.

3.8.8. Ravaz index

PRINCIPLE

The Ravaz index can be used to quantify production potential and is obtained from the ratio between production and pruning wood. the Ravaz index is more sensitive than productivity in interpreting the effect of cultural practices on vigour, berry weight and wine quality (Pinto, 2015).

With regard to the Ravaz Index, according to Smart & Robinson (1991), the value of this index should remain between 5-10 in order to obtain a good fruit/vegetation ratio and balanced vines (Pinto, 2015).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

CALCULATIONS

$$Ravaz\ Index = \frac{Production\ (kg)}{Weight\ of\ pruning\ wood\ (kg)}$$

REFERENCES

Pinto, M.C.D.O. (2015). *Viticultura de Precisão: Avaliação da variabilidade espacial da produtividade e qualidade na casta Touriga Nacional no Alentejo* (Doctoral dissertation, ISA/UL).

Smart, R. & Robinson, M. (1991). *Sunlight into wine: a handbook for winegrape canopy management*. Winetitles.

3.8.9. Production

PROCEDURE

To determine this parameter, it is necessary to collect all the production from the vineyards under study individually, so that the production of each vine can be weighed and the production per plant (kg) obtained.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

3.8.10. Plant growth

PROCEDURE

Height from the base of the plant: measurements are taken from the ground near the trunk of the vine to the beginning of the canopy.

Plant crown height: measurements should be taken from the beginning of the crown to the end of the crown.

Neck diameter at 20 cm from the ground: to obtain this parameter, measurements are taken from the ground next to the trunk up to 20 centimetres, and then the neck diameter is measured with a calliper in centimetres.

Number of eyes and stalks per plant: to obtain this parameter, it is necessary to count the stems and eyes remaining after pruning on each vine under study.

Handbook of Agricultural Products

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PROJECT ACRONYM: AGROSUS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This handbook is aimed to **the most important parameters to measure the yield of plant crops and the quality of the commercialized agricultural products**. Different agricultural products demand different parameters, so that some of the parameters included in this handbook are just measured in one specific crop (i.e., gluten content in wheat), while others (i.e., number of seeds, fat, starch, etc.) are measured in more than one crop. The parameters here listed are presented with a detailed protocol, the material needed for their measurement, the most relevant references, and the principles for why these parameters are so important for evaluating the productivity of crop plants and the quality of agricultural products from the agroecological farming systems established in the different eleven biogeographic regions from Europe.

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1. Case studies setup and experimental design

1.1. Experimental Units

Work packages 3 and 4 (WP3 and WP4) have been designed to develop solid and robust scientific understanding about the impacts of agroecological strategies (AE) on crop productivity, weed management and soil health and biodiversity, which is related to other ecosystem services such as soil fertility and carbon sequestration in different biogeographical regions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Biogeographical regions of Europe.

To correctly address the projects' objectives, short, medium, and long-term farm systems will be analysed, and 83 experimental units (68 short-term + 15 medium to long-term) will be considered in the 11 European biogeographic regions (Figure 2). Short, medium and long-term impact of AE on crop productivity, weed management, and soil health will be measured along the AGROSUS project. The short-term impact will be measured in experimental units developed by the different partners in conventional, organic, or mixed farm systems. However, considering the duration of the project (4 years), the medium to long-term impact of AE will be evaluated in in-course AE fields already identified in some of the different regions. Different measures to evaluate crop quality, weed control, soil health, ecotoxicological, environmental and socioeconomic impact will be recorded in the frame of AGROSUS.

Figure 2. AGROSUS short-term experimental units in the eleven biogeographical regions

1.2. Experimental design

A well-designed and harmonized experimental design is important in any scientific study, as states how laboratory samples must be taken, how they must be collected and from where they must be taken, to achieve the objectives established in the research project. In the comparison of treatments in agronomic experiments, a properly designed experimental scheme is of crucial importance to make adequate statistical inference. The two most common alternatives applied in the case studies of the project are shown below:

1.2.1. Randomized experimental design

This model assumes that the replicates of the different treatments are randomly distributed within the experiment when a randomized complete block design or a split-plot design is carried out (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of a randomized experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2

1.2.2. Block experimental design

If a block experimental design (not randomized) is going to be carried out (Figure 4), control treatment (the one already performed in the farm as a routine basis, called “conventional”; CV) does not represent field variability since each treatment is located in different areas of the field, and some variations will be present in soil owing to different locations. So, initial conditions in each block have to be taken into account. Therefore, when a non-randomized block experimental design is implemented (Figure 4), the conventional treatment and each of the AE implemented will have their own designated area in the studied field.

Figure 4. Example of block experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2

2. ARABLE

2.1. Barley

2.1.1. Moisture

PRINCIPLE

To determine the quality of agricultural products, laboratory equipment is used in order to obtain moisture automated results.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded, or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in the equipment. The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- BROKER MPA II – moisture, fat, protein, fibre

REMARKS

The obtained results are correlated with the Romanian Grain Inspection Handbook and with the ISO 7970 standards.

REFERENCES

Romanian Grain Inspection Handbook
ISO Standard -7970

2.1.2. Dry matter content

PRINCIPLE

Dry matter content is an indicator of the amount of nutrients (e.g., carbohydrates, protein, fibre, and minerals) in grains used as animal feed.

PROCEDURE

A subsample of the harvest from each experimental plot is weighed and oven dried at 103 °C overnight or until it reaches a steady weight. The dry matter content is calculated based on the wet and dry weights.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance
- Drying oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Eurofins (2024). *Dry matter (DM)*. <https://www.eurofins-agro.com/en/dm>

2.1.3. Grain yield

PRINCIPLE

Yield is calculated for each experimental plot to compare the harvest of barley for the different treatments.

PROCEDURE

The barley plants in the experimental plots are harvested with a Haldrup C-70 combine that threshes and weighs the grains. Yield is calculated based on wet weight, dry matter percentage (85-90%) and area harvested. Results are reported in tonnes of dry matter per hectare.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Haldrup C-70 combine
- Drying oven
- Balance

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{yield} = \frac{\text{wet weight} \times \text{dry matter content (\%)}}{\text{area harvested}}$$

REFERENCES

Skeggjadóttir, S., Svavarsdóttir, J. & Hilmarsson, H.S. (2020). *Áburðartilraunir á höfrum til þroska á tveimur mismunandi jarðvegsgerðum á Hvanneyri 2020* (Rit Lbhí 156). Agricultural University of Iceland. https://www.lbhi.is/images/pdf/rit%20lbhi/rit_lbhi_nr_156_akurhafri.pdf.

2.1.4. Density

PRINCIPLE

Density (bulk density) of grain is an indication of the maturity and health of grains.

PROCEDURE

The volume of the barley kernels is measured using a 100 mL measuring cylinder, and the weight of the kernels is recorded. The density is calculated as the weight divided by volume. The measurement is done by triplicate for each experimental plot.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

Equipment:

- Balance

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{density} = \frac{\text{weight}}{\text{volume}}$$

REFERENCES

Tavakoli, M., Tavakoli, H., Rajabipour, A., Ahmadi, H. & Gharib-Zahedi, S.M.T. (2010). Moisture-dependent physical properties of barley grains. *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, 2(4), 84-91. <https://doi.org/10.3965/j.issn.1934-6344.2009.04.084-091>.

2.1.5. Thousand kernel weight

PRINCIPLE

The mass of 1000 grains from barley, also known as Thousand Kernel Weight (TKW), can vary depending on the variety and growing conditions. The average mass of 1000 grains typically ranges from 30 to 50 grams in barley. However, it is important to note that this is a general range, and specific measurements may vary. Thousand Kernel Weight is an important characteristic to consider when sowing barley to achieve the desired plant population target.

PROCEDURE

A random sample of 1000 grains will be counted using a seed counter, Data count S-25, and the grains weighed. The counting will be done in triplicates for each experimental plot.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Data Count S-25 seed counter
- Balance

REFERENCES

Tavakoli, M., Tavakoli, H., Rajabipour, A., Ahmadi, H. & Gharib-Zahedi, S.M.T. (2010). Moisture-dependent physical properties of barley grains. *International Journal of Agricultural and Biological Engineering*, 2(4), 84-91. <https://doi.org/10.3965/j.issn.1934-6344.2009.04.084-091>.

2.1.6. Hectolitre mass (MHL)

PRINCIPLE

The hectolitre mass in barley refers to the weight of a specific volume of barley grain, typically expressed in kilograms per hectolitre (kg hL^{-1}). It is a measure of the bulk density or volume weight of the grain. The specific hectolitre mass of barley can vary depending on factors such as the variety, growing conditions, and grain quality. The hectolitre mass is important because:

- Is one of the price setting parameters.
- Serves as a basis for calculating the sizing of silage cells.
- Constitutes the basic parameter of flour extractions, with an important role in determining the yield in flour.

PROCEDURE

It is determined after harvesting for each variety. It is expressed in kg, without decimals. The hectolitre mass is determined by measuring the weight of a known volume of barley, usually 100 L, and is used as an indicator of grain quality and soundness.

REFERENCES

Hoyle, A., Brennan, M., Pitts, N., Jackson, G.E., Hoad, S. (2020). Relationship between specific weight of spring barley and malt quality. *Journal of Cereal Science*, 95, 103006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2020.103006>.

2.1.7. Spectroscopic analysis of ash, fat, fibre, humidity, starch, and protein content

PRINCIPLE

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is considered one of the main routine analytical methods used by the food industry. This technique is utilised to determine proximate chemical compositions e.g., protein, dry matter, fat and fibre of a wide range of food ingredients and products.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in special ampoules.

The humidity, ash, fat, fibre, starch, and protein content (%) is determined using the InfraXact™ analyser based on the near-infrared spectroscopy.

The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample in the 570–1850 nm wavelengths. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- InfraXact™ analyser (Foss, Hillerod, Denmark)
- Ampoule

REFERENCES

Yang, Z., Cai, L., Han, L., Fan, X., & Liu, X. (2021). Review of standards for near infrared spectroscopy methods. *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 29(6), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670335211042016>

Cozzolino, D. (2021). The ability of near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to predict functional properties in foods: Challenges and opportunities. *Molecules*, 26(22), 6981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226981>

Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

2.1.8. Ammonium and amine nitrogen content

PRINCIPLE

A method for determining ammonium and amine nitrogen, e.g., occurring in water, soil or food products. Using it, nitrogen bound in organic compounds is converted into ammonium and analysed together with the ammonium compounds present in the sample.

PROCEDURE

Clean plant material is first dried in oven in 50-60 °C and finely grounded.

A sample of 0.5-0.7 g is taken and mixed with concentrated sulfuric acid (10 cm³) and a hint of selenium mix. The mixture is put aside, and the next day is burned in the oven at 400-450 °C for ca. 1 h. Next, the nitrogen is analysed in Kjeltex apparatus.

The protein content [%] is calculated by multiplying N content by a factor of 6.25.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean seeds, grains and potato tubers
- sulfuric acid
- selenium mix

Equipment:

- Laboratory oven
- Kjelttec TM8100 (Foss, Hilleroed, Denmark)

REFERENCES

Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.1.9. Micro and macro-elements

PRINCIPLE

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), is the technique for many applications that require analysing a sample for its elemental content. Typical samples include those in the environmental, metallurgical, geological, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, materials, and food safety arenas. The advantages of using ICP- OES include its wide linear dynamic range, high matrix tolerance, and the enhanced speed of analysis that can be achieved.

PROCEDURE

The plant material is dried, grounded, and 0.5 g is weighed and mixed with 7 mL of HNO₃ and 1 mL of H₂O₂, placed into Teflon vessels and in a microwave rotor at 190 °C for 20 min and then 190 °C for 25 min. Next the material is transferred to 25 cm³ flasks, topped up with distilled water and the determination of elements is performed on the Optical Emission Spectrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- HNO₃
- H₂O₂
- Distilled water
- Teflon vessels
- 25 cm³ flasks

Equipment:

- Microwave rotor
- ICP Perkin Elmer Optical Emission Spectrometer Optima 7300DV

REFERENCES

Szara-Bąk, M., Baran, A. & Klimkowicz-Pawlas, A. (2023). Recycling of bottom sediment to agriculture: effects on plant growth and soil properties. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 23(1), 539-551.

2.2. Maize

2.2.1. Thousand kernel weight

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the mass of 1000 seeds as one of the important indicators characterizing the value of the seed lot. The analysis consists of selecting, weighing, and calculating the mass of 1000 seeds according to their number in the sample. For this, a seed sample of the main crop is used after analysing its purity. Accounting is carried out manually or with the help of counters.

PROCEDURE

1. All or part of the sample is used for analysis. If the entire sample is used, then the number of seeds in it is counted and weighed. The mass of 1000 seeds is calculated by dividing the total mass of the sample by the number of seeds in it and multiplying the result by 1000.
2. Under the conditions of using a certain number of seeds selected from the sample, form eight repetitions of 100 seeds each.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Collapsible boards
- Set of kettlebells
- Tweezers

Equipment:

- Electric scales (type VLKT 500 g M),
- Laboratory scales
- Counter-disintegrator of seeds

CALCULATIONS

Eight replicates of 100 seeds (without selection) are counted from the seeds of the main crop, which are weighed to the accuracy provided during the purity analysis. Then calculate:

a) variance (V) according to the formula

$$V = \frac{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2}{n(n-1)}, \quad (1)$$

where x is the mass of 100 seeds of each repetition, g;
 n is the number of repetitions; \sum is the sum;

b) standard deviation (∂), as the square root of the variance, i.e

$$\partial = \sqrt{V}; \quad (2)$$

average arithmetic mass (\bar{x}) of 100 seeds according to the formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}; \quad (3)$$

coefficient of variation (k) according to the formula

$$k = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} 100 \quad (4)$$

The mass of 1000 seeds are calculated by multiplying by 10 the average arithmetic mass (\bar{x}) 100 pieces.

REFERENCES

DSTU 4138-2002 Seeds of agricultural crops. Methods of determining quality

2.2.2. Purity seed analysis

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the content of the components that make up the seed batch, which include the primary crop, other plants, and waste (impurities). The seeds of the primary crop include all its botanical breeds and varieties. Among them are:

- Intact seeds (caryopses, achenes, fruits, etc.);
- Achenes and similar fruits, regardless of the content of actual seeds;
- Seeds (fruits) that have microtraumas or have lost less than half of their size due to mechanical damage or destruction;
- Caryopses of grain crops with flower palea;
- Hulled seeds that have lost half or more of the hull or palea;
- Seeds that remain on the cleaning screen. Seeds of other plants include seeds (fruits) and seed-like structures of botanical plant species that do not belong to the primary crop, namely seeds of cultivated plants or weeds.

Waste (impurities) comprises the following:

- Residues of seeds (fruits) that have lost half or more of their original size;
- Seeds of legumes and cabbage crops without a seed hull;
- Empty spikelet and flower palea, husks, fragments of stems, leaves, etc;
- Rotten seeds, sprouted seeds (roots or sprouts are half or more of the seed length, and in rounded seeds half or more of the diameter);
- Fungal formations (sooty sacs, lumps, spikelet, horns, sclerotia, and their fragments), nematode galls;
- Lumps of soil, stones, sand, excrement, insects, etc;
- Seeds that have passed through the cleaning screen;
- Seeds of other plants.

PROCEDURE

1. The middle sample is poured onto a smooth surface and mixed thoroughly, then the colour, shine, odour, mold, and other organoleptic features are used to assess the condition of the seeds. If large impurities (lumps of soil, stones, stem fragments, etc.) are discovered and cannot be evenly distributed in the middle sample, they are separated and weighed to the hundredth of a gram.
2. The content of the primary crop seeds and waste in work samples is determined according to Table 1.

Table 1. Maize: conditions of sieve analysis of seeds for determining purity

Crop	Size of holes, mm	Duration of hand sifting, min
Corn (apart from popcorn and self-pollinated line)	3.0×20	3
Popcorn and self-pollinated line	2.5×20	3

3. The content of the primary crop seeds and waste in work samples is determined according to Table 2.

Table 2. Maize: maximum weight limits for seed batches and samples.

Crop	Maximum batch weight (control unit) kg (±5%)	Weight of average sample, g			
		Average		Work	
		To determine			
		sowing qualities (±5%)	moisture content	purity	content of other species
<i>Zea mays</i> L.	25,000	1,000	100	900	1,000
<i>Zea mays</i> sweetcorn and popcorn	25,000	1,000	100	200	1,000

- 3.1. The analysis of each crop sample begins with sifting the work sample through a sieve (Table 1).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Thick paper bags

Equipment:

- Electric scales (type БЛКТ 500 g M)
- Laboratory scales according to State Standard GOST 24104

- Dial scales with a weighing limit of at least 2 kg
- Timing device
- Diaphanoscope
- Mechanical seed divider
- Air seed classifier
- Sieve seed classifier
- Fluorescent lamp
- Laboratory bench (table)
- Exhaust hood
- Sandglasses (1-3 min)
- Preparation needles
- Selection boards
- Set of laboratory seeds
- Lid
- Bottom plate
- Corex
- Grain focuser (x4, x5) according to State Standard GOST 25706
- Set of weights according to State Standard GOST 7328
- Set of grain magnifiers (type ШНЛ-1)
- Set of small-sized sieves for herbs with a lid and a bottom plate
- Tweezers according to State Standard GOST 21241
- Respirators
- Laboratory scoops
- Spatulas

CALCULATIONS

1. After sieving the seed samples, the number of nodules on each sieve and the percentage of each fraction are calculated.
2. To remove the waste, the second sample is sifted through one cleaning screen.
3. The work sample, which is divided into two halves (sub-samples), is analysed. In each sub-sample, the components are weighed with the required accuracy.

Table 3. Maize: weighing accuracy for seed analysis.

Weight grading of the component	Number of decimal places
less than 99.99	2
between 100.0 and 999.9	1
from 1,000.0 and heavier	0

4. The masses of the components are added, and the sum is compared with the initial mass of the work sample. If the difference between them does not surpass 5% (by weight of the work sample), the analysis results are considered reliable. If it is greater than 5%, the analysis is carried out on a re-sampled sample. The content of each component is calculated (in percent) to one decimal place based on the total of their masses. The sum must equal 100%. A deviation of 0.1% from it is corrected by the content of the largest of the components. A deviation of more than 0.1% indicates an error in the analysis or calculation.
5. The mixture components are distributed according to Table 4. Seeds of other crops are classified as waste.

Table 4. Maize: types of seed mixtures depending on components

Mixture	Mixture components
Grain	Grain crops, grain legumes, sunflower, soybeans, annual grasses
Perennial grasses	Perennial grasses (except couch grass, if the mixture is sown on crop rotation fields)
Annual grasses	Annual grasses, grain crops, grain legumes, sunflower, soybeans

6. The seeds of the primary crop of each component of the mixture are weighed to the second decimal place and indicated in the document separately. Seeds of other cultivated plants that are classified as waste are accounted for following the requirements of the State Standard of Ukraine DSTU 2240 for the predominant crop. Seeds of couch grass in a mixture of perennial grasses, if its components are cereal grasses, are accounted for in pieces per kilogram of the mixture.

REFERENCES

State Standard of Ukraine DSTU 4138-2002. Seeds of Farm Crops. Methods for Determination of Quality.

2.2.3. Seed germination

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the number of seeds (in percent) capable of forming normally developed seedlings under optimal germination conditions. Normal seedlings include those in which the most important structures (roots, subcotyledon and supracotyledon knee, tubercle, cotyledons, coleoptile) are well and proportionally developed, intact, healthy, and with minor defects on those structures, which do not affect the normal development of the seedling. They also include normally developed seedlings with signs of surface infection acquired from neighbouring diseased seeds.

In crops whose seeds germinate by several germinal roots (cereal spike crops), normally germinated grains include those that have at least two normally developed roots, longer

than the length of the grain, and a sprout no less than half its length. In the seeds of peas, corn, millet and other crops that germinate by one root, normally germinated grains include grains that have a developed main germinal root, the size of which is not less than the length (diameter) of the grain, and a formed sprout, which is not less than half the length (diameter) seeds. In normally germinated sunflower seeds, the cotyledons should be easily freed from the fruit and seed coats.

Abnormal seedlings include those that are unable to develop into full-fledged plants even under favourable conditions. These include: — seedlings in which any structure is missing or severely damaged, which makes their further proportional development impossible; — poorly developed seedlings due to physiological disorders, as well as seedlings with deformed structures; — rotten seedlings.

Hard seeds are seeds that do not swell due to the impermeability of the skin.

A healthy ungerminated seed is a seed that, due to deep physiological rest, remains ungerminated and has no signs of decay.

PROCEDURE

1. Thermostats once every 10 days, and Jacobsen-type devices and utensils before each analysis, are washed with hot water and detergents and disinfected with a 1% solution of potassium permanganate or alcohol.
2. A tray with water is placed in the working chamber of the thermostat, and the Jacobsen apparatus is rinsed and filled with water. Petri and Koch dishes can be sterilized in an oven at (130 ± 2) °C for an hour or boiled in water for 40 min.
3. Analysis of germination is carried out on the seeds of the main crop, isolated during purity determination. For this, 400 seeds of 100 or 50 (for large-seeded crops) pieces are arbitrarily counted in each repetition. The seeds are evenly placed on a moistened substrate.

The conditions that are mandatory (substrate, temperature) for the analysis, as well as additional instructions for breaking seed dormancy are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Maize: similarity analysis conditions

Crops	Substrate	Temperature in °C ± 2 °C	Accounting periods, days		Additional conditions for overcoming seed dormancy
			first	final	
Corn <i>Zea mays</i> L.	on sand, in sand, on paper	20; 25; 20-30	4	7	Preheating, lighting

Sweet corn <i>Zea mays</i> L.	on sand, in sand, on paper	20; 25; 20-30	4	7	Extend the germination period for 3 days
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4. According to the table 5, the mode that is most acceptable should be chose according to the availability of the laboratory, considering the condition of the seeds and the crop. It is recommended to give preference to the regime of variable temperatures, as biologically more natural.
5. During the analysis, filter paper (F) and sand (S) are used. Filter paper as a substrate is used in two ways: "on paper" and "in paper". To moisten the paper, immerse it in water, take it out and let the excess water drain (when pressing with a finger, a water film does not form around it). During the "on paper" analysis, seeds are spread on one or more layers of moistened paper placed in Petri dishes. Cover Petri dishes with lids. During the "in paper" analysis, seeds are spread horizontally or vertically between two layers of moistened paper with the germs down. The device with seeds prepared in this way is placed in a thermostat. Sand as a substrate for germinating seeds (sifted through a sieve with holes with a diameter of 1 mm, washed, roasted) is used according to the following options: "on sand" - seeds are pressed into the surface of the sand to their thickness (diameter); or "in the sand" - the seed laid out on the bed is covered with a layer of sand 1-2 cm thick, leaving it loose.
6. Seeds of corn, sunflower, and other large-seeded crops are placed with the embryo down. Before analysis, the sand is moistened to 60% of its full moisture content. The moisture content (B) is determined in a metal cylinder 30 cm high, 8 cm in diameter, with a mesh bottom. A circle of moistened filter paper is placed on the bottom of the cylinder and weighed (T). The cylinder is filled 3/4 with fresh baked sand, weighed again (T1) and placed in a vessel with water so that it is at the level of the sand. When the water wets the surface of the sand, the cylinder is removed from the vessel, excess water is allowed to drain, the walls are dried on the outside with filter paper and weighed (T2). The moisture content of sand (in cm³ per 100 g) is calculated by the formula:

$$B = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 - T} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

7. After the analysis, the sand is washed, dried, sieved, roasted and stored for reuse.
8. The seeds are laid out in prepared nurseries using a spreader counter or manually using a marker, after which they are wrapped and smoothed with a rammer.

9. The filter paper is moistened with a 0.005% solution of gibberellic acid (50 mg per 1 dm³). During the entire period of germination, the is moistened with the same solution, which is stored in a refrigerator at a temperature of 8-10 °C.
10. During the analysis of freshly collected seeds with an incomplete period of physiological maturation, measures are taken to overcome the state of dormancy, namely: pre-cooling, warming, washing, treatment of the bed with chemicals, etc.
 - 10.1. Pre-cooling. Seeds sown on a wet substrate are kept at a temperature of 5-10 °C for the time provided for the first accounting of seedlings (germination energy), after which they are transferred to the temperature conditions provided for this crop. The period of pre-cooling is not included in the term of determination of similarity, but its duration and temperature must be noted in the document; the first accounting (germination energy) is carried out two days after the end of preliminary cooling. If necessary, pre-cooling is repeated or its term is extended.
 - 10.2. Preheating. The seeds are warmed for 7 days at a temperature of 30-40 °C. If necessary, the duration of heating is extended. Freshly harvested corn seeds with a moisture content of 30% and less before germination are dried in a cabinet at a temperature of (36 ± 2) °C in open greenhouses (in a layer of one grain) for 24 hours, and with a moisture content of more than 30% - for 48 hours. Then they germinate on sand, observing the technical conditions adopted for corn.
 - 10.3. To remove dormancy, seeds are illuminated (O) for 8 hours every day with an intensity of 750-1250 lx (250 lx is enough for seeds that are not in a state of rest). During germination in the regime of variable temperatures, illumination is given during the period of application of high temperature.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride (-bromide)
- Cotton wool is hygroscopic
- Distilled water
- Drinking water
- Glucose crystalline hydrate
- Potassium nitrate
- Potassium permanganate according to GOST 20490
- Sulfuric acid according to GOST 2184 or GOST 4204
- Succinic acid according to GOST 6341
- Measuring flask (500 cm³)

- Filter paper
- Quartz sand (particle size 0.5-2 mm)
- Ethyl alcohol 96%
- Adhesive transparent tape
- A cup with a capacity of 500 cm³
- Petri and Koch cup

Equipment:

- Apparatus for germinating seeds in the light (Jacobsen type)
- Dial scales with a weighing limit of at least 2 kg
- Fluorescent lamp
- Counter-decomposer of seeds
- Lux meter
- Furnace for calcination of sand
- Heating thermostat (t = 20-40 ± 2 °C)
- Cooling and heating thermostat (t = 0-40 ± 2 °C)
- Laboratory drying cabinet (t = 50-150 ± 2 °C)
- Small inventory:
 - Dissecting needles
 - Substrate humidifiers (dropper, watering can, pipette)
 - Measuring ruler
 - Markers for sand
 - A set of grain scoops (type ShNL⁻¹)
 - Tweezers according to GOST 21241
 - Dishes for washing and moistening the substrate
 - Planters (faience, plastic, polystyrene)
 - Sieves for sieving sand
 - Glass
 - Laboratory scoops, thermometers (t = 0-50 °C)
 - Rammers
 - A metal cylinder with a mesh bottom, 30 cm high and 8 cm in diameter

CALCULATIONS

The moisture content of sand (in cm³ per 100 g) is calculated by the formula:

$$B = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 - T} \cdot 100$$

During the first accounting, normally germinated seeds are separately evaluated and taken into account, as well as seeds with pronounced signs of anomalies and rotten ones. The last two groups are removed, and normally germinated ones are removed if necessary.

The term of the final accounting is allowed to be extended up to 3 days, and if necessary, more, to allow germination of healthy ungerminated seeds, or shortened if the picture is understood ahead of time.

The results obtained during the similarity analysis are expressed as percentages for each of the identified categories (normal and abnormal seedlings, germinated and ungerminated seeds, in particular hard, dead, rotten). The reliability of the analysis is established by comparing the extreme values of the repetitions with the arithmetic mean. The result is considered reliable if the difference between them and the arithmetic mean value, which is calculated to a whole number, does not exceed the maximum permissible deviations.

REFERENCES

DSTU 4138-2002. Seeds of agricultural crops. Methods of determining quality.

2.2.4. Moisture content

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the content of free moisture in the seeds.

PROCEDURE

1. *Number of determinations.* Separate determinations are carried out on two test portions taken from the laboratory sample. If the absolute difference between the two values obtained is greater than the repeatability limit, the determination is repeated until requirements are satisfied.
2. *Test portion.* 5 ± 1 g of the laboratory is rapidly weighed, to the nearest 0.001 g, in the metal dish. The mass of the undried test portion is recorded and named “ m'_0 ”. This dish is previously dried and tarred, together with its lid, and record the mass is recorded and named “ m_d ” to the nearest 0.001 g.
3. *Drying.* The open dish containing the test portion (2), together with the lid is placed in the oven and left for 120 ± 5 min (90 min for flours). In certain cases, and particularly in hot air-dry countries, the drying period may be reduced to 60 ± 5 min, which is sufficient time for the test portions to attain constant mass. These times must be controlled regularly. The door of the oven can't be opened during drying and moist products can't be placed in the oven before removing the dry test portions, as this would result in partial rehydration of the latter. After drying, the dish is quickly removed from the oven, covered, and placed in the desiccator.

4. *Weighing.* When the dish has cooled to laboratory temperature (generally between 30 min and 45 min after it has been placed in the desiccator), it is weighed to the nearest 0.001 g. Record the mass of the dried test portion is recorded and named as “m’1”

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Analytical balance (accuracy ± 0.001 g).
- Grinding mill
- Metal dish
- Constant-temperature oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

Without preconditioning.

The moisture content, W_{H_2O} expressed in grams per 100 g of the product as received, is given by:

$$W_{H_2O} = \left(1 - \frac{m_1}{m_0}\right) \times 100$$

where

$m_0 = m'_0 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the test portion (2)

$m_1 = m'_1 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the test portion after drying (4).

With preconditioning.

The moisture content, W_{H_2O} , expressed in grams per 100 g of the product as received, is given by:

$$W_{H_2O} = \left[(m_0 - m_1) \frac{m_3}{m_0} + m_2 - m_3 \right] \times \frac{100}{m_2} = \left(1 - \frac{m_1 m_3}{m_0 m_2}\right) \times 100$$

where

$m_2 = m'_2 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the sample taken before preconditioning (2);

$m_3 = m_3 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the preconditioned sample.

REFERENCES

State Standard of Ukraine DSTU ISO 712:2015(ISO 712:2009, IDT). Cereals and cereal products - Determination of moisture content - Reference method.

2.2.5. Nitrogen content in seeds

PRINCIPLE

Document specifies a method for the determination of the nitrogen content of cereals, pulses and derived products, according to the Kjeldahl method, and a method for calculating the crude protein content.

A test portion is digested by sulfuric acid in the presence of a catalyst. The reaction products are made alkaline, and then distilled. The liberated ammonia is collected in a boric acid solution, which is titrated with a sulfuric acid solution, in order to determine the nitrogen content and calculate the crude protein content.

PROCEDURE

1. Test portion

A mass of test sample is weighed, to the nearest 0.001 g, chosen on the basis of the assumed nitrogen content, so that the test portion contains between 0.005 g and 0.2 g of nitrogen and preferably more than 0.02 g.

2. Determination

2.1 Digestion. The test portion is transferred to the digestion flask. Then, the required number of catalyst tablets are added, containing 10 g of potassium sulphate, 0.30 g of copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate and 0.30 g of titanium oxide. In the end, 20 mL of sulfuric acid are added. The quantity of acid may be adjusted depending on the apparatus, but only after having made certain that this measure indeed leads to a recovery rate of 99.5% for acetanilide and 99.0% for tryptophan. It is mixed thoroughly to ensure complete wetting of the test portion. The flasks are placed in the digestion unit preheated to (420 ± 10) °C. After a minimum of 2 h of digestion, counted from the time when the temperature of the unit reaches again (420 ± 10) °C, it is left to cool down.

NOTE: It is advisable to add pumice stone or glass boiling rods as a boiling regulator and an antifoaming agent. The minimum digestion time shall be checked on that reference material with which it was most difficult to reach the recovery rate. The recommendations of the equipment manufacturer must be followed as far as evacuation of the vapours is concerned, because too strong a suction can result in a loss of nitrogen.

2.2 Distillation. Cautiously 50 mL of water are added to the cooled flask and left to cool down. Then, 50 mL of boric acid are transferred into the collecting flask and, for visual colourimetry or using an optical probe, at least 10 drops of coloured indicator. An excess of 5 mL of the sodium hydroxide solution is added as is required for neutralizing the quantity of sulfuric acid used. Then carry out the distillation.

2.3 Titration. The titration is carried out using the sulfuric acid solution, either continuously during the distillation or at the end of distillation on all of the distillate. The end-point determination is judged by visual colourimetry, or using an optical probe, or by potentiometric analysis with a pH measurement system.

3. Blank test

A blank test is performed with the reagents used in 2.1 to 2.3 but without the test sample (2).

NOTE: It is possible to replace the test sample with 1 g of sucrose.

4. Test with reference material (check test)

The reference material(s) used is dried at a temperature of between 60 °C and 80 °C, under vacuum, in the presence of di-phosphorus pentoxide. A check test is carried out on a test portion of a minimum of 0.15 g by determining the nitrogen content of the tryptophan and/or of the acetanilide. NOTE It is possible to add 1 g of sucrose to reference material. The nitrogen recovery rate from acetanilide shall be at least 99.5% and at least 99.0% from tryptophan.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- Nitrogen-free reagents of recognized analytical grade are only used, except for the reference materials, and distilled or demineralized water or water of equivalent purity.
- Kjeldahl tablets, corresponding to the following composition: copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) = 2.8%, titanium oxide (TiO_2) = 2.8% and potassium sulphate (K_2SO_4) = 94.3%. Alternatively, copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate, titanium oxide and potassium sulphate may also be mixed in the corresponding ratio.
- Sulfuric acid, $c(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 18 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $\rho_{20}(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 1.84 \text{ g mL}^{-1}$.
- Antifoaming agent: Paraffin oil, silicone or even antifoam tablets may be used to prevent foaming.
- Acetanilide ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}$) or tryptophan ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), of minimum assay 99% (mass fraction).
- Boric acid, aqueous solution, $\rho_{20}(\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3) = 40 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, or any other concentration recommended for the apparatus being used.
- Coloured indicator. Add volumes of Solution A and Solution B as recommended for the apparatus being used (for example: 5 volumes of Solution A and 1 volume of Solution B) or any other coloured indicator recommended for the apparatus.
- *NOTE 1.* It is possible to use a ready-to-use solution of boric acid containing the coloured indicator (8 and 9).

- *NOTE 2.* The ratio of Solutions A and B can be adjusted depending on the apparatus.
- The titration may also be carried out potentiometrically by the use of a pH electrode, which shall be checked every day.
- *Solution A:* Bromocresol green ($C_{21}H_{14}Br_4O_5S$): 200 mg, Ethanol (C_2H_5OH), with a volume fraction of 95%: quantity sufficient for 100 mL of solution.
- *Solution B:* Methyl red ($C_{15}H_{15}N_3O_2$): 200 mg. Ethanol (C_2H_5OH), with a volume fraction of 95%: quantity sufficient for 100 mL of solution.
- Sodium hydroxide, aqueous solution (NaOH), having a mass fraction of between 30% and 40%, with nitrogen content less than or equal to 0.001%. Technical grade sodium hydroxide may also be used when its nitrogen content is less than or equal to 0.001%.
- Sulfuric acid, standard volumetric solution, $c(H_2SO_4) = 0.05 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. The use of H_2SO_4 instead of HCl is recommended because H_2SO_4 does not have the tendency to produce bubbles in the connecting tubes.
- Ammonium sulphate, standard volumetric solution, $c(NH_4)_2SO_4 = 0.05 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.
- Alternatively, a salt such as $(NH_4)_2Fe(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ may be used.
- Pumice stone, granulated, washed in hydrochloric acid and ignited or glass boiling rods may be used to prevent bumping.
- Sucrose (optional), free from nitrogen.
- Diphosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5).

Equipment:

- Mechanical grinder.
- Sieve, with aperture size 0.8 mm.
- Analytical balance, capable of weighing to the nearest 0.001 g.
- Digestion, distillation and titration apparatus.

CALCULATIONS

Nitrogen content. The nitrogen content, w_N , expressed as a mass fraction of dry product, as a percentage (%), is obtained using Formula (1):

$$w_N = \frac{(V_1 - V_0) \times T \times 0.014 \times 100}{m} \times \frac{100}{100 - w_H} = \frac{140T(V_1 - V_0)}{m(100 - w_H)}$$

Where:

V_0 is the volume, in millilitres, of the sulfuric acid solution required for the blank test;
 V_1 is the volume, in millilitres, of the sulfuric acid solution required for the test portion;
 0.014 is the value, in grams, of the quantity of nitrogen equivalent to the use of 1 mL of a 0.5 mol L^{-1} sulfuric acid solution;
 T is the normality of the sulfuric acid solution used for the titration;
 m is the mass, in grams, of the test portion;

w_H is the moisture content.

Express the result to two decimal places.

Crude protein content. The content of crude protein in a dry product is calculated by multiplying the value of the nitrogen content obtained during the determination by a conversion factor that depends on the type of cereal or legume used. The result is rounded to one decimal place. Note. Some conversion factors that are used for cereals are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Maize: conversion coefficient of nitrogen content to protein content

Product	Coefficient of conversion of nitrogen to protein
<i>Zea mays</i>	6.25

REFERENCES

ISO 20483:2013(E) Cereals and pulses — Determination of the nitrogen content and calculation of the crude protein content — Kjeldahl method.

ISO 712 Cereals and cereal products — Determination of moisture content — Routine reference method.

ISO 6540 Maize — Determination of moisture content (on milled grains and on whole grains).

ISO 24557 Pulses — Determination of moisture content — Air-oven method.

2.2.6. Ash yield

PRINCIPLE

Method used for determining the ash yield by cereals, pulses, and their milled products intended for human consumption. The source materials covered are:

- a) grains of cereals;
- b) flours and semolinas;
- c) milled products (bran and high bran content products, sharps);
- d) mixed cereal flours (mixes);
- e) cereal by-products other than milled products
- f) pulses and their by-products.

PROCEDURE

A test portion is incinerated until combustion of organic matter is complete, then the residue obtained is weighed. The residue obtained is flaky after incineration at 550 °C and vitrified after incineration at 900 °C.

In general, products containing salts (e.g., sodium chloride, pyrophosphate) shall be incinerated at (550 ± 10) °C.

Table 7 summarizes incineration temperatures according to product type.

Table 7. Incineration temperatures and product type.

Product type	Incineration temperature	
Flours	(550 ± 10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C

Semolinas	(550 ±10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Cereal grains	(550 ±10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Other milled products (e.g., bran, high bran content products, sharps)	(550 ±10) °C	
Mixed cereal products (mixes)	(550 ±10) °C	
Cereal by-products other than milled products	(550 ±10) °C	
Pulses and their by-products	(550 ±10) °C	

1. Determination of the moisture content.

The moisture content of the test sample is determined beforehand in accordance with ISO 712 for cereals other than maize or ISO 6540 in the case of maize or ISO 24557 in the case of pulses.

2. The preparation of the ashing dishes

For ashing dishes suitable for use at 900 °C, the previously cleaned dishes are brought up to the incineration temperature being employed by being put in the muffle furnace for 5 min, being left to cool in the desiccator, and then being weighed to within 0.1 mg.

For ashing dishes suitable for use at 550 °C, the cleaned dishes are placed in an oven for the time required for drying (e.g., 90 min at 130 °C). Immediately before use, the dishes are removed from the oven and left to cool in a desiccator, then weighed to within 0.1 mg.

3. Preparation of the test portion

From the test sample carefully mixed, a test portion between 3.9 g and 4.1 g is rapidly weighed to within 0.1 mg in the case of incineration at 900 °C and between 4.9 g and 5.1 g in the case of incineration at 550 °C. In the case of low-density products, the test portion can be between 2 (± 0.1) g and 3 (± 0.1) g. In the ashing dish, prepared and weighed as described in 2, the product is spread out without packing it to form a uniform layer.

4. Pre-ashing

The ashing dish and its contents are placed at the entrance of the furnace brought up to the ashing temperature. At 900 °C, the products are burst into flame spontaneously. At 550 °C, they are necessary to be ignited with ethanol. For pre-ashing at 550 °C, it is permissible to put the dishes in the cold furnace and let the temperature of the furnace rise to the target temperature.

5. Ashing

The dish is placed inside the furnace once the product has finished burning. The furnace door is closed. The ashing continues until the combustion of the entire product,

including the carbon particles contained in the residue, is complete, namely 1 h minimum at 900 °C, and 4 h minimum at 550 °C. In order to maintain the efficiency of the desiccator, dishes are not stacked. Once the ashing is completed, the dish is removed from the furnace and placed in the desiccator to cool. Due to the hygroscopic nature of the ash, as soon as the dish has reached ambient temperature (namely 15 min to 20 min for metallic dishes and 60 min to 90 min minimum for quartz or silica dishes), it is weighed rapidly to within 0.1 mg. For test portions incinerated at 550 °C, special precautions are taken to avoid flaky residues being swept away with the influx of air on opening the desiccator. The validity of the results obtained on this sample is checked with respect to the laboratory's self-inspection criteria (e.g., control chart).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- Hydrochloric acid, aqueous solution of one part by volume of HCl (35% volume fraction) and one part by volume of water.
- Purified diphosphorus pentoxide (P₄O₁₀).
- Ethanol.

Equipment:

- Grinding mill
- Ashing dish, of capacity not less than 20 mL, rectangular or round shape, flat-bottomed and having a surface area of not less than 12 cm². Suitable materials for the ashing dish which do not deteriorate under test conditions at the temperature of operation are:
 - at 900 °C — platinum or rhodium
 - at 550 °C — quartz or silica.
 - a. The dishes shall be cleaned by complete immersion for at least 1 h in hydrochloric acid, then rinsed with running water and then with distilled water.
 - b. After rinsing, the dishes shall be dried in an oven at a temperature and for a period sufficient to eliminate water.
- Electrically heated muffle furnace, with adequate ventilation, provided with temperature control system and a refractory coating which is not liable to lose particles at the ashing temperature, and capable of being maintained at (900 ± 25) °C or at (550 ± 10) °C.
- Vacuum desiccator, equipped with a perforated aluminium or porcelain plate, and diphosphorus pentoxide (5.2) as drying agent.
- Analytical balance, with an accuracy of 0.01 mg.
- Riffle splitter or cone-shaped divider.
- Oven for drying the ashing dishes.

CALCULATIONS

The ash yield, as a mass fraction on the dry matter basis expressed as a percentage, $w_{a,d}$, is given by Equation (1):

$$W_{a,d} = (m_2 - m_1) \times \frac{100}{m_0} \times \frac{100}{100 - w_m} \quad (1)$$

where

m_0 is the mass, in grams, of the test portion (3)

m_1 is the mass, in grams, of the ashing dish (2);

m_2 is the mass, in grams, of the ashing dish (2) and the incinerated residue (5);

w_m is the moisture content, as a percentage by mass, of the sample.

Take as a result the arithmetic mean of the two determinations if the repeatability conditions are fulfilled.

If needed, the ash yield, as mass fraction on the wet matter basis expressed as a percentage, w_a , w , is given by Equation (2):

$$W_{a,d} = (m_2 - m_1) \times \frac{100}{m_0}$$

REFERENCES

DSTU ISO 2171:2007 Cereals, pulses and by-products — Determination of ash yield by incineration.

2.3. Oat

2.3.1. TKW- thousand kernel weight

PRINCIPLE

The 1,000 kernel weight (TKW) is a measure of seed size. It is the weight in grams of 1,000 seeds. TKW is measured by using seed counter CONTADOR. The CONTADOR Seed counter is used to count cleaned seeds such as grain, oil seeds, corn legumes and similar, dust-free products in order to establish, for example, the thousand seed weight.

PROCEDURE

The filled feed container is positioned at the place intended for the CONTADOR. The slider on the feed container is adjusted according to the grain size. The machine automatically detects the feed container (container no. 2 for grain, sunflower seeds and rye) and then loads the optimum parameters for this.

Having set the counted quantity, the count starts.

The feed container is held by a magnet and is kept vibrating by means of a vibration element. The vibration causes the product to be counted to flow through the gate of the feed container in the outlet channel. The counting product falls through the photoelectric counting device into the drawer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Counter

REFERENCES

Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Lóczy D., Thiele-Bruhn, S. & Zornoza, R. (2019). Handbook of plant and soil analysis for agricultural systems. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/185619949.pdf>

Operating Instructions. Seed counter Contador. <https://www.pfeuffer.com/product/contador>

2.3.2. Specific weight (volume weight)

PRINCIPLE

Specific weight is one of the longest-standing measures of grain quality for cereals and oilseeds; it is a measure of the weight of grain per unit volume (kg hL^{-1}). It tested by using Aquamatic 5200 FARM. The AM 5200 Farm is a grain analyser, designed to determine moisture, temperature and volume weight. The instrument measures the dielectric constant of grain at 150 MHz. The instrument requires no sample preparation other than cleaning or the removal of large impurities.

PROCEDURE

700 mL sample is poured into the hopper. After the user presses “Go” analysis starts and results are calculated and displayed.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Aquamatic 5200 FARM

REFERENCES

Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Lóczy D., Thiele-Bruhn, S. & Zornoza, R. (2019). Handbook of plant and soil analysis for agricultural systems. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/185619949.pdf>

<https://www.perten.com/Global/Other%20docs/AM5200%20FARM%20User%20Man-26714%20v1.0.pdf>

2.3.3. Total N

PRINCIPLE

Evaluating the total nitrogen content in oats provides valuable information for assessing nutritional value, optimizing crop management, and considering environmental sustainability

PROCEDURE

Total N (N_{tot}) content of grain samples is determined by the dry combustion method

CALCULATIONS

The protein calculated by multiplying nitrogen content by 5.75.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

VarioMAX CNS elemental analyser (Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Langenselbold, Germany).

REFERENCES

Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

ISO 16634-2:2016. Determination of the total nitrogen content by combustion according to the Dumas principle and calculation of the crude protein content. <https://www.iso.org/standard/66661.html>

MTTK. Methods of Soil and Plant Analysis; Agricultural Research Centre, Department of Soil Science: Jokioinen, Finland, 1986; p. 45.

2.3.4. Spectroscopy analysis of ash, fat, fibre, humidity, starch and protein content

PRINCIPLE

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is considered one of the main routine analytical methods used by the food industry. This technique is utilised to determine proximate chemical compositions e.g., protein, dry matter, fat and fibre of a wide range of food ingredients and products.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in special ampoules.

The humidity, ash, fat, fibre, starch and protein content (%) is determined using the InfraXact™ analyser based on the near-infrared spectroscopy.

The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample in the 570–1850 nm wavelengths. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- InfraXact™ analyser (Foss, Hillerod, Denmark)
- Ampoule

REFERENCES

- Yang, Z., Cai, L., Han, L., Fan, X. & Liu, X. (2021). Review of standards for near infrared spectroscopy methods. *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 29(6), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670335211042016>
- Cozzolino, D. (2021). The ability of near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to predict functional properties in foods: Challenges and opportunities. *Molecules*, 26(22), 6981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226981>
- Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

2.3.5. Ammonium and amine N content

PRINCIPLE

A method for determining ammonium and amine nitrogen, e.g., occurring in water, soil or food products. Using it, nitrogen bound in organic compounds is converted into ammonium and analysed together with the ammonium compounds present in the sample.

PROCEDURE

Clean plant material is first dried in oven in 50-60 °C and finely grounded.

A sample of 0.5-0.7 g is taken and mixed with concentrated sulfuric acid (10 cm³) and a hint of selenium mix. The mixture is put aside, and the next day is burned in the oven at 400-450 °C for ca. 1 hour. Next, the nitrogen is analysed in Kjeltex apparatus.

The protein content [%] is calculated by multiplying N content by a factor of 6.25.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean seeds, grains and potato tubers
- Sulfuric acid
- Selenium mix

Equipment:

- Laboratory oven
- Kjeltex TM8100 (Foss, Hilleroed, Denmark)

REFERENCES

- Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.
- Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.3.6. Micro and macro-elements

PRINCIPLE

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), is the technique for many applications that require analysing a sample for its elemental content. Typical samples include those in the environmental, metallurgical, geological, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, materials, and food safety arenas. The advantages of using ICP-OES include its wide linear dynamic range, high matrix tolerance, and the enhanced speed of analysis that can be achieved.

PROCEDURE

The plant material is dried and grounded. Then, 0.5 g is weighed and mixed with 7 mL HNO₃ and 1 mL H₂O₂, placed into Teflon vessels and in a microwave rotor at 190 °C for 20 min and at 190 °C for 25 min. Next, the material is transferred to 25 cm³ flasks, topped up with distilled water and the determination of elements is performed on the Optical Emission Spectrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- HNO₃
- H₂O₂
- Distilled water
- Teflon vessels
- 25 cm³ flasks

Equipment:

- Microwave rotor
- ICP Perkin Elmer Optical Emission Spectrometer Optima 7300DV

REFERENCES

Szara-Bąk, M., Baran, A. & Klimkowicz-Pawlas, A. (2023). Recycling of bottom sediment to agriculture: effects on plant growth and soil properties. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 23(1), 539-551.

2.3.7. Dry mass of seeds

PRINCIPLE

Dry matter is a basic characteristics of crop products. Assessing the dry matter content of seeds is essential for determining their viability, storage requirements, quality, and processing needs. It helps ensure successful germination, longer shelf life, and optimal performance in agricultural practices.

PROCEDURE

The fresh grains are weighed with accuracy of 0.01 g.

Next, the samples are dried to constant weight in 105 °C for 3 h. After cooling the sample in air for approximately 1 h, it is weighed with a reading accuracy of 0.01 g.

Dry mass is calculated based on a difference between the weight of fresh and dry biomass.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Laboratory scale with an accuracy of 0.001 g
- Laboratory oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Grudzińska, M., Czerko, Z. & Jankowska, J. (2015). Zmiany zawartości suchej masy i skrobi w bulwach ziemniaka w czasie przechowywania oraz ich wpływ na straty masy surowca w procesie smażenia chipsów. *Inżynieria i Aparatura Chemiczna*, 54(5), 243-246.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.4. Potato

2.4.1. Spectroscopy analysis of ash, fat, fibre, humidity and protein content (%)

PRINCIPLE

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is considered one of the main routine analytical methods used by the food industry. This technique is utilised to determine proximate chemical compositions e.g., protein, dry matter, fat and fibre of a wide range of food ingredients and products.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in special ampoules.

The humidity, ash, fat, fibre and protein content (%) is determined using the InfraXact™ analyser based on the near-infrared spectroscopy.

The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample in the 570–1850 nm wavelengths. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- InfraXact™ analyser (Foss, Hillerod, Denmark)
- Ampoule

REFERENCES

Yang, Z., Cai, L., Han, L., Fan, X. & Liu, X. (2021). Review of standards for near infrared spectroscopy methods. *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 29(6), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670335211042016>

Cozzolino, D. (2021). The ability of near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to predict functional properties in foods: Challenges and opportunities. *Molecules*, 26(22), 6981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226981>

Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

2.4.2. Ammonium and amine nitrogen content

PRINCIPLE

A method for determining ammonium and amine nitrogen, e.g., occurring in water, soil or food products. With this method, nitrogen bound in organic compounds is converted into ammonium and analysed together with the ammonium compounds present in the sample.

PROCEDURE

Clean plant material is first dried in oven in 50-60 °C and finely grounded.

A sample of 0.5-0.7 g is taken and mixed with concentrated sulfuric acid (10 cm³) and a hint of selenium mix. The mixture is put aside, and the next day is burned in the oven at 400-450 °C for ca. 1 h. Next, the nitrogen is analysed in Kjeltex apparatus.

The protein content [%] is calculated by multiplying N content by a factor of 6.25.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean seeds, grains and potato tubers
- sulfuric acid

- selenium mix

Equipment:

- laboratory oven
- Kjelttec TM8100 (Foss, Hilleroed, Denmark)

REFERENCES

Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant, Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.4.3. Micro and macro-elements**PRINCIPLE**

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), is the technique for many applications that require analysing a sample for its elemental content. Typical samples include those in the environmental, metallurgical, geological, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, materials, and food safety arenas. The advantages of using ICP- OES include its wide linear dynamic range, high matrix tolerance, and the enhanced speed of analysis that can be achieved.

PROCEDURE

The plant material is dried, grounded. 0.5 g is weighed and mixed with 7 mL of HNO₃ and 1 mL of H₂O₂, placed into Teflon vessels and in a microwave rotor at 190 °C for 20 min and then 190 °C for 25 min. Next the material is transferred to 25 cm³ flasks, topped up with distilled water and the determination of elements is performed on the Optical Emission Spectrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL**Material:**

- HNO₃
- H₂O₂
- Distilled water
- Teflon vessels
- 25 cm³ flasks

Equipment:

- Microwave rotor
- ICP Perkin Elmer Optical Emission Spectrometer Optima 7300DV

REFERENCES

Szara-Bąk, M., Baran, A. & Klimkowicz-Pawlas, A. (2023). Recycling of bottom sediment to agriculture: effects on plant growth and soil properties. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 23(1), 539-551.

2.4.4. Protein content

PRINCIPLE

The Bradford method is a colorimetric technique used for the quantification of proteins. This parameter is especially interesting when measuring the plant health and knowing whether a plant is encountering any abiotic or biotic stress factor, as one of the first detected responses is the synthesis of stress proteins when plant is under acclimation or protein degradation when is under senescence (Batista-Silva et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE

Bradford Reagent Preparation

1. 100 mg of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye is weighed.
2. 50 mL 95% ethanol is added.
3. 100 mL 85% phosphoric acid is added slowly and carefully
4. All is mixed until the blue dye is completely dissolved.
5. The dye/ethanol/phosphoric acid solution is added to 850 mL pure sterile H₂O.
6. Any precipitates are filtered.
7. Bradford reagent must be stored at 4 °C for months.

Measuring Protein Standard

1. First, the spectrophotometer is warmed up.
2. Six different volumes are pipetted [0 µL (0 µg), 10 µL (5 µg), 20 µL (10 µg), 30 µL (15 µg), 40 µL (20 µg), 50 µL (25 µg)] of 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ BSA into separate cuvettes.
3. 1.5 mL of Bradford Reagent is added to each cuvette.
4. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film and mixed by gently inverting.
5. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 10 min.
6. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. Between 10 to 50 µL of the protein that is to be quantified are pipetted into a cuvette; a dilution may be necessary.
 - a. The goal is to get an absorbance reading that is in the middle of the standard curve.

- b. An equal volume of 1 M NaOH can be added to help solubilize membrane proteins. When choosing this option, be sure to include NaOH in the standards.
2. 1.5 mL of Bradford Reagent is added to the cuvette.
3. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film and mixed by gently inverting.
4. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 10 min.
5. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.
 - a. If the absorbance does not fall within the range of the standard curve, change the dilution of the sample and measure absorbance again.

Standard Curve Generation

1. A scatter plot is made for the standard curve values.
2. The X-axis will be micrograms (μg) of standard protein that were assayed; the Y-axis will be Abs_{595} that was measured.
3. Fit a linear trendline to the graph.
4. Show the linear regression equation.
5. Calculate the unknown amount of protein by using the linear regression equation, as shown in the calculations section of this document.
6. The unknown concentration of the original protein solution can be calculated by dividing the amount of protein by the volume of protein assayed and multiplying the quotient by the dilution factor, as shown in the calculations section.
7. Alternatively, a curvilinear (polynomial) trendline can be fitted to the graph. This polynomial regression equation may sometimes give a better estimation of protein concentration.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye
- 95% ethanol
- 85% phosphoric acid
- 850 mL pure sterile H_2O
- NaOH
- Bovine serum albumin (BSA)

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. $\mu\text{g of protein} = \frac{\text{absorbance} - y \text{ intercept}}{\text{slope}}$
2. $\frac{\mu\text{g of protein}}{\mu\text{L assayed}} = \text{concentration assayed}$
3. Concentration assayed \times dilution factor = concentration of original solution

REFERENCES

Batista-Silva, W., Heinemann, B., Rugen, N., et al. (2019) The role of amino acid metabolism during abiotic stress release. *Plant, Cell and Environment*, 42, 1630–1644.

Bradford, M.M. (1976). A rapid sensitive method for the quantification of microgram quantities of protein utilising the principle of protein-dye binding. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 72, 248-254.

2.4.5. Dry mass of tubers

PRINCIPLE

Dry matter is a basic characteristics of crop products. For example, the dry matter content determines the culinary and nutritional value of the potato. Its increased content directly affects the consistency of fried, dried, sterilized and cooked products.

PROCEDURE

The fresh seeds/grains are weighed. The potato tubers (25 pieces) are washed and cleaned and next cut into thin slices along the top-stolon axis. The fresh samples are weighed with accuracy of 0.01 g.

Next, the samples are dried to constant weight in 105 °C for 3 h. After cooling the sample in air for approximately 1 h, it is weighed with a reading accuracy of 0.01 g.

Dry mass is calculated based on a difference between the weight of fresh and dry biomass.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Laboratory scale with an accuracy of 0.001 g
- Laboratory oven

REFERENCES

Grudzińska, M., Czerko, Z. & Jankowska, J. (2015). Zmiany zawartości suchej masy i skrobi w bulwach ziemniaka w czasie przechowywania oraz ich wpływ na straty masy surowca w procesie smażenia chipsów. *Inżynieria i Aparatura Chemiczna*, 54(5), 243-246.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.4.6. Starch content

PRINCIPLE

Reimann-Steam balance - a type of hydrostatic balance used to determine the starch content in potatoes (measuring the density of solids). It uses the relationship between the starchiness of potatoes and their density.

PROCEDURE

5.0 kg of clean potato tubers is weighed in air and then in clean water of 17.5 °C. Based on the obtained measurement results, the density of potatoes and the dry matter content are calculated. The difference between two samples must be <0.5%. If the difference is higher, then a third sample should be measured.

The starches value of potatoes is obtained after subtracting the content of non-starch ingredients from the dry matter, which is on average 5.75% (Maercker's constant).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean tubers, two samples of 5 kg each
- technical scale with an accuracy of 0.01 g

REFERENCES

Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant, Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.

2.4.7. Content of nitrates in tubers

PRINCIPLE

The content of nitrates(V) in fresh vegetables is determined by the potentiometric method using a combination ion-selective nitrate electrode. A nitrate electrode consists of a membrane selective towards nitrate(V) ions, embedded in a glass shaft. Only nitrate ions can overcome the barrier of the membrane. When the membrane is in contact with a solution containing nitrate ions, potential appears on it. The potential depends on the content of free nitrate ions in the studied solution. The determination consists in measuring the potential difference of the ion-selective nitrate electrode relative to the reference electrode using an ionometer. The difference in potentials between the electrodes is proportional to the logarithm of the concentration of nitrate ions, expressed by the equation:

$$E = E_o - S \log x$$

where: E – measured electrode potential, E_o – standard potential, S – electrode's goodness, x – activity of nitrate(V) ions.

PROCEDURE

1. The standard series is prepared, and the electrode is calibrated.

Successively, 1, 10, and 100 cm³ of the stock standard solution of sodium nitrate(V) are measured into three 100 cm³ volumetric flasks, filled up with distilled water to the measuring line, and mixed. The NO₃⁻ concentrations in the solutions prepared in this way are 10, 100, and 1000 mg dm⁻³, successively. The prepared standard solutions are transferred to 150 cm³ beakers, and 2 cm³ of solution (NH₄)₂SO₄ at a concentration of 2 mol · dm⁻³ (conditioning solution) are added to each. Then, the ion-selective electrode is immersed in individual standard solutions (from the lowest to the highest concentration), and the instructions at the electrode are followed. Before immersing the electrode in another standard, it is thoroughly rinsed in distilled water. After a three-point calibration, the meter automatically goes into measurement mode.

2. Nitrates(V) are extracted from three vegetable species.

Washed potato tubers are homogenized. Five g of plant material are weighed into a 500 cm³ bottle. 200 cm³ of distilled water are added, and the solution is shaken for 20 min. Then, the solution is filtered through a filter into a 300 cm³ conical flask.

3. The content of nitrates(V) is determined, and the result is given in mg NO₃⁻ kg⁻¹ fresh matter.

Using a cylinder, 100 cm³ of the filtrate is drawn into a 150 cm³ beaker, and 2 cm³ of (NH₄)₂SO₄ solution at a concentration of 2 mol dm⁻³ is added. The beaker with the test sample is placed on a magnetic mixer, the electrode is immersed, and the measurement is started. The determination is made in 3 replications for each plant material.

4. The content of nitrates(V) in the studied potato tubers is assessed and compared.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents

- Ammonium sulphate (NH₄)₂SO₄ solution at a concentration of 2 mol dm⁻³: 264.28 g (NH₄)₂SO₄ is weighed and transferred to a 1 dm³ volumetric flask, filled with distilled water up to the measuring line and mixed.
- Sodium nitrate(V) NaNO₃ stock standard solution: 0.14 g NaNO₃ is dissolved in water in a 100 cm³ volumetric flask filled up with distilled water to the measuring line and mixed. 1 cm³ of this solution contains 1 mg NO₃⁻.

Material

- Tubers washed with tap water, then distilled water
- Qualitative filters

Apparatus

- Meter – ionometer
- Ion-selective nitrate electrode, combined
- Homogenizer
- Magnetic mixer, stirrers

Glass and laboratory equipment

- Laboratory scale with an accuracy of 0.001 g
- 500 cm³ bottle
- 150 cm³ beaker
- 300 cm³ conical flask
- 100 cm³ volumetric flask
- 2 cm³ pipette
- 250 cm³ cylinder
- 100 cm³ cylinder
- Qualitative funnel

REFERENCES

Gruszecka-Kosowska, A. & Baran, A. (2017). Concentration and health risk assessment of nitrates in vegetables from conventional and organic farming. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 23(4), 727-740.

2.4.8. Vitamin C in tubers**PRINCIPLE**

The method involves the extraction of vitamin C with oxalic acid or a mixture of metaphosphoric (V) and acetic acids and the oxidation of L-ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid in an acidic environment using the dye 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol. This dye is then reduced to a colourless leucocompound, which turns red at pH = 4.2. The reaction proceeds quantitatively.

PROCEDURE

A standard solution of ascorbic acid with a concentration of 1 mg in 1 mL is prepared in the extraction solution of 2% oxalic acid solution in ice-cooled acetic acid.

The titration of the 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol solution is determined as follows: 1 mL of the standard ascorbic acid solution is measured and titrated with the 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol dye solution until a light pink colour remains for 10 seconds.

In parallel, a blank titration is performed with 5 mL of the extraction solution. The blank test result is subtracted from the titration result.

Homogenized tubers (10-20 g) are mixed with 1 g of diastase in 20 mL of distilled water. They are left in a thermostat at 30 °C for 15 min. After that time, they are quantitatively transferred to 100 mL volumetric flasks using the extraction solution. The mixture is mixed and filtered, removing the first few millilitres.

10 mL of the filtrate is taken into 50 mL beakers and immediately titrated with 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol solution until a light pink colour persists for 10 seconds. For calculations, the average value of three titrations performed in parallel is taken.

The vitamin C content is calculated using the formula:

$$K = \frac{(V_0 - V_1)d}{m'V_2m_0} \times 100$$

where: K - vitamin C content in mg per 100 g of sample; V_0 - the amount of dye used to titrate the tested sample, V_1 - the amount of dye solution used to titrate the tested sample; m' - dye titration in millilitres per 1 mg of vitamin C; V_2 - amount of filtrate taken for titration in millilitres; m_0 - weight of the tested material in grams.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 10 mL Burette
- 50 mL, 100 mL, 500 mL, and 1000 mL Volumetric flasks
- 50 mL, and 100 mL Beakers
- Glass funnels
- Glass sticks
- 1-20 mL Pipette
- 100 and 250 mL Measuring cylinders
- 750 mL Flat-bottomed spherical flask
- Filter paper (medium)

Equipment:

- Analytical scale with weighing accuracy 0.0001
- Technical scale with weighing accuracy 0.01
- Homogenizer, mixer

REFERENCES

Polish Norm PN-A-04019:1998. Food products: determination of vitamin C.

2.4.9. Tuber yield, marketable yield, tube size and distribution

PRINCIPLE

Assessing tuber yield and size is crucial for evaluating the productivity and quality of potato plants. Measurements include the total weight of harvested tubers, the average size of individual tubers and the tuber distribution. Monitoring these measurements can provide insights into crop performance. Total weight provides an estimate of the total yield and is expressed in kilograms. Monitoring changes in total tuber weight over time can help assess the efficiency of different cultivation methods, irrigation practices, and fertilization regimes. By tracking the average tuber size, growers can evaluate the impact of various factors such as nutrient management, planting density, and disease control on tuber development and understanding the size distribution can aid in managing storage requirements, market preferences, and processing needs.

PROCEDURE

Total weight of harvested tubers

This measurement involves weighing the harvested tubers collectively with a balance.

Average size of individual tubers:

Measuring the average size of individual tubers involves recording the diameter and length of representative tubers. This measurement is done using callipers.

Tuber distribution

It can also be useful to assess the distribution of tuber sizes within a crop. It is done by sorting tubers into different size categories (small, medium, large) and determining the percentage of tubers falling into each category. Following The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) quality and consistency grading system and United Nations Economic Commission for Europe:

Small < 3.81 cm // ~141 g

Medium = 3.81 – 5.71 // 141 – 283 g

Large = 4.45 – 6.35 cm // 283 g

Marketable yield

The weight of all potatoes selected to be marketable is measured.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment

- Balance
- Calliper or measuring tape

CALCULATIONS

Total weight = Σ weight of all tubers

Average size = $\frac{\Sigma \text{ of the diameter of all tubers measured}}{\text{Total number of tubers measured}}$

REFERENCES

United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (2005). Standard for seed potatoes. https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trade/agr/standard/potatoes/pot_e/S-1.pdf [Accessed on 28th August, 2023].

The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) (2013). United States Standards for Grades of Potatoes. https://www.ams.usda.gov/sites/default/files/media/Potato_Standard%5B1%5D.pdf [Accessed 28th August, 2023]

2.4.10. Pest and disease monitoring

PRINCIPLE

Regular monitoring helps in early detection of pests and diseases, allowing for timely intervention and control measures. It helps prevent the spread of pests and diseases, minimize crop damage, and optimize the use of pesticides. Some common pests that affect potato tubers include potato cyst nematodes, wireworms, and tuber moth. Diseases that commonly affect potato crops include late blight, early blight, black scurf, and pink rot diseases (Yuen, 2021; Weiner and Quan, 2021; Chaudhary et al., 2023).

PROCEDURE

Monitoring methods may vary depending on the specific pest being targeted. It includes visual inspections, sticky traps, pheromone traps, and crop scouting. A threshold level must be determined to know when intervention is necessary. Thresholds are typically based on economic or damage levels, and they vary depending on the specific pest or disease being monitored. Keeping records of pest and disease monitoring activities is important for tracking trends, evaluating the effectiveness of control measures, and making informed decisions in future cropping seasons.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material (depending on the pathogen or disease):

- Sticky traps
- Pheromone traps

REFERENCES

Chaudhary, S., Lal, M., Sagar, S., Sharma, S. & Kumar, M. (2023). Black scurf of potato: Insights into biology, diagnosis, detection, host-pathogen interaction, and management strategies. *Tropical Plant Pathology*, 1-24.

Wainer, J. & Quang D. (2021). Taxonomy, morphological and molecular identification of the potato cyst nematodes *Globodera pallida* and *G. rostochiensis*. *Plants*, 10(1), 184.

Yuen, J. (2021). Pathogens which threaten food security: *Phytophthora infestans*, the potato late blight pathogen. *Food Security*, 13(2), 247-253.

2.4.11. Phytochemicals

PRINCIPLE

Phenolic compounds are a group of natural plant chemicals that have been found to possess various health benefits, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Potatoes are known to contain phenolic compounds, and their content can vary depending on factors such as the potato variety, growing conditions, and processing methods. Phenolic acids are reported to be the most abundant phytochemical compounds in potatoes. Specifically, chlorogenic acid is mentioned as one of the predominant phenolic acids (Brown, 2005). The total phenolic content in potatoes can vary between different parts of the potato, such as the peel and flesh. The amount of total phenolic content in various parts of the potato has been reported to range from 79.14 to 181.85 mg GAE (gallic acid equivalents) per gram of extract (Kim et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE

Preparation of potato extracts

The tuber is washed with water, dried, and manually peeled to a depth of ~ 1 mm, and then the peel and the peeled potato (flesh) are blended separately with a commercial mixer. The tuber (unpeeled whole potato) and microtuber (1 kg) are washed with water and blended separately. The tuber, microtuber, peel, and flesh are dried and powdered using a freeze dryer. Powdered potato (100 g) is added to 800 mL of acetone, methanol, and a mixture of methanol:water (80:20, v/v), respectively. After adding the solvent, the mixtures are shaken at 200 rpm overnight, and the extracts are filtered through filter paper. The collected extracts are concentrated in a rotary evaporator to remove the major amounts of the organic solvents and further dried in a freeze dryer.

Chromatography conditions

Phenolic compounds are quantified using an HPLC–MS (1260 Series; Agilent Technologies) is performed using a system consisted of compact mass detector equipment (TRIPLE QUAD 3500; AB SCIEX Instruments). Polyphenols are separated using a C18 column (Phenomenex Luna, 150 mm × 2 mm and 3 µm; Phenomenex). The flow rate used is 300 µL min⁻¹, column temperature is 40 °C, injection volume is 10 µL and column is equilibrated for 6 min between runs. The used gradient elution is a mixture of two solvents: A, consisting of 0.1% formic acid in water, and B, consisting of 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile. Initial conditions (98% A and 2% B) are held for 4 min before ramping

to 20% B at 7 min and 90% B at 14 min. Initial conditions are recovered at 15 min and held until 21 min. Instrument parameters were as follows: CUR, 25 psi; CAD, 7 psi; IS, -4500 V; TEM, 400 °C; GS1, 55 psi; GS2, 55 psi; interface heater, on.

Determination of total phenolic contents

The total phenolic content in each extract is determined using a Folin–Ciocalteu reagent. In brief, gallic acid (as a standard phenolic compound) and 100 µL of each extract are distributed in the test tube and mixed with 500 µL of the diluted Folin–Ciocalteu (1:1 ratio in distilled water). After a 10 min incubation at room temperature, 1 mL of sodium carbonate (7.5% w/v) is mixed in the same tube and allowed to react for 20 min at room temperature. The absorbance of the mixture is measured at 760 nm and calculated the percentage of phenolics. The content of total phenolics is expressed as gallic acid equivalent (GAE).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material

- 800 mL acetone
- 800 mL methanol
- 800 mL mixture of methanol:water (80:20, v/v).
- Folin–Ciocalteu reagent
- 1 mL sodium carbonate (7.5% w/v)
- Gallic acid as standard

Equipment

- Shaker
- Rotary evaporator
- Freeze dryer
- HPLC–MS
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

The absorbance of the mixture is measured at 760 nm and calculated the percentage of phenolics. The content of total phenolics is expressed as gallic acid equivalent (GAE).

REFERENCES

Brown, C.R. (2005). Antioxidants in potato. *American Journal of Potato Research*, 82, 163-172.

Kim, J., Soh, S.Y., Bae, H. & Nam, S.Y. (2019). Antioxidant and phenolic contents in potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) and micropropagated potatoes. *Applied Biological Chemistry*, 62(1), 1-9.

2.5. Rapeseed

2.5.1. Moisture and fat content

PRINCIPLE

Rapeseed is known for its high fat content, which can reach up to 49% of its composition. The fat content in rapeseed makes it a valuable raw material for the fat and oil industry, as well as the animal feed industry. Rapeseed oil is widely used for culinary and industrial purposes due to its low saturated fat content and high unsaturated fat content. Regarding moisture content, can vary depending on factors such as the variety of rapeseed, growing conditions, and storage conditions.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in the equipment.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

The moisture and fat are determined. The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

CALCULATIONS

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- BROKER MPA II

REMARKS

The obtained results are correlated with the Romanian Grain Inspection Handbook and with the ISO 7970 standards.

REFERENCES

Romanian Grain Inspection Handbook.

ISO Standard -7970.

Nicolescu, C.M., Bumbac, M., Radulescu, C., Buruleanu, L., Olteanu, R., Gorghiu, L., Teodorescu, G. & Holban, C. (2021). Romanian Organic and Conventional Red Grapes Vineyards as Potential Sources of High Value-Added Products, in a Circular Economy Approach. 10.5772/intechopen.98972.

2.5.2. TKW

PRINCIPLE

The mass of 1,000 grains in rapeseed, also known as Thousand Kernel Weight (TKW), can vary depending on the variety and growing conditions. It is important to note that

this is a general range, and specific measurements may vary. Thousand Kernel Weight is an important characteristic to consider when sowing rapeseed to achieve the desired plant population target.

PROCEDURE

It is established after harvesting. It is expressed in grams. It is determined as follows: the seeds are counted at random and grouped by 10, after which they are grouped by 100 and then by 500. The two samples of 500 are weighed separately and the results are added up. The mass of 1,000 seeds is thus obtained.

REFERENCES

Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Lóczy D., Thiele-Bruhn, S. & Zornoza, R. (2019). Handbook of plant and soil analysis for agricultural systems. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/185619949.pdf>

Operating Instructions. Seed counter Contador. <https://www.pfeuffer.com/product/contador>

2.5.3. Hectolitre mass (MHL)

PRINCIPLE

The hectolitre mass in rapeseed refers to the weight of a specific volume of rapeseed grain, typically expressed in kilograms per hectolitre (kg hL^{-1}). It is a measure of the bulk density or volume weight of the grain. The specific hectolitre mass of rapeseed can vary depending on factors such as the variety, growing conditions, and grain quality. The importance of the hectolitre mass:

- is one of the price setting parameters;
- serves as a basis for calculating the sizing of silage cells;
- constitutes the basic parameter of flour extractions, with an important role in determining the yield in flour.

PROCEDURE

It is determined after harvesting for each variety. It is expressed in kg, without decimals. The hectolitre mass is determined by measuring the weight of a known volume of barley, usually 100 litres, and is used as an indicator of grain quality and soundness.

REFERENCES

Matej, Gh., Dodocioiu, A.M., Imbrea, F. & Dobre, C.Ş. (2017). The productivity of some rapeseed genotypes in the climatic conditions of ARDS Caracal. *Research Journal of Agricultural Science*, 49(3), 113-121.

2.6. Soybean

2.6.1. TKW

PRINCIPLE

The mass of 1,000 grains in soybean, also known as Thousand Kernel Weight (TKW), can vary depending on the variety and growing conditions. The average mass of 1,000 grains in barley typically ranges from 30 to 50 grams. However, it is important to note that this is a general range, and specific measurements may vary. Thousand Kernel Weight is an important characteristic to consider when sowing soybean to achieve the desired plant population target.

PROCEDURE

TKW is established after harvesting and expressed in grams. It is determined as follows: the seeds are counted at random and grouped by 10, after which they are grouped by 100 and then by 500. The two samples of 500 are weighed separately and the results are added up. The mass of 1,000 seeds is thus obtained.

REFERENCES

Álvaro-Fuentes, J., Lóczy D., Thiele-Bruhn, S. & Zornoza, R. (2019). Handbook of plant and soil analysis for agricultural systems. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/185619949.pdf>

Operating Instructions. Seed counter Contador. <https://www.pfeuffer.com/product/contador>

2.6.2. Hectolitre mass (MHL)

PRINCIPLE

The hectolitre mass in soybean refers to the weight of a specific volume of soybean grain, typically expressed in kilograms per hectolitre (kg hL^{-1}). It is a measure of the bulk density or volume weight of the grain. The specific hectolitre mass of soybean can vary depending on factors such as the variety, growing conditions, and grain quality. The hectolitre mass is important because:

- is one of the price setting parameters;
- serves as a basis for calculating the sizing of silage cells;
- constitutes the basic parameter of flour extractions, with an important role in determining the yield in flour.

PROCEDURE

It is determined after harvesting for each variety. It is expressed in kg, without decimals. The hectolitre mass is determined by measuring the weight of a known volume of soybean, usually 100 litres, and is used as an indicator of grain quality and soundness.

REFERENCES

Crista, M.M., Curchi, S.C., Nița, S. & Okros A. (2021). Research on soybean growing technology in Giera pedoclimate conditions. *Research Journal of Agricultural Science*, 53(3), 60-68.

2.6.3. Spectroscopic analysis of ash, fat, fibre, starch, protein content and humidity

PRINCIPLE

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is considered one of the main routine analytical methods used by the food industry. This technique is utilised to determine proximate chemical compositions e.g., protein, dry matter, fat and fibre of a wide range of food ingredients and products.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in special ampoules.

The humidity, ash, fat, fibre, starch and protein content (%) is determined using the InfraXact™ analyzer based on the near-infrared spectroscopy.

The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample in the 570–1850 nm wavelengths. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- InfraXact™ analyzer (Foss, Hillerod, Denmark)
- Ampoule

REFERENCES

Yang, Z., Cai, L., Han, L., Fan, X. & Liu, X. (2021). Review of standards for near infrared spectroscopy methods. *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 29(6), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670335211042016>

Cozzolino, D. (2021). The ability of near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to predict functional properties in foods: Challenges and opportunities. *Molecules*, 26(22), 6981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226981>

Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

2.6.4. Ammonium and amine N content

PRINCIPLE

A method for determining ammonium and amine nitrogen, e.g., occurring in water, soil or food products. Using it, nitrogen bound in organic compounds is converted into ammonium and analysed together with the ammonium compounds present in the sample.

PROCEDURE

Clean plant material is first dried in oven in 50-60 °C and finely grounded.

A sample of 0.5-0.7 g is taken and mixed with concentrated sulfuric acid (10 cm³) and a hint of selenium mix. The mixture is put aside, and the next day is burned in the oven at 400-450 °C for *ca.* 1 hour. Next, the nitrogen is analysed in Kjeltex apparatus.

The protein content [%] is calculated by multiplying N content by a factor of 6.25.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean seeds, grains and potato tubers
- Sulfuric acid
- Selenium mix

Equipment:

- Laboratory oven
- Kjeltex TM8100 (Foss, Hilleroed, Denmark)

REFERENCES

Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant, Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.6.5. Micro and macro-elements

PRINCIPLE

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), is the technique for many applications that require analysing a sample for its elemental content. Typical samples include those in the environmental, metallurgical, geological, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, materials, and food safety arenas. The advantages of using ICP- OES include its wide linear dynamic range, high matrix tolerance, and the enhanced speed of analysis that can be achieved.

PROCEDURE

The plant material is dried and grounded. Then, 0.5 g is weighed and mixed with 7 mL of HNO₃ and 1 mL of H₂O₂, placed into Teflon vessels and in a microwave rotor at 190 °C for 20 min and then 190 °C for 25 min. Next, the material is transferred to 25 cm³ flasks, topped up with distilled water, and the determination of elements is performed on the Optical Emission Spectrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- HNO₃
- H₂O₂
- Distilled water
- Teflon vessels
- 25 cm³ flasks

Equipment:

- Microwave rotor
- ICP Perkin Elmer Optical Emission Spectrometer Optima 7300DV

REFERENCES

Szara-Bąk, M., Baran, A. & Klimkowicz-Pawlas, A. (2023). Recycling of bottom sediment to agriculture: effects on plant growth and soil properties. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 23(1), 539-551.

2.6.6. Content of fatty acids in soybean oil GC/MS method

PRINCIPLE

GC–MS has the advantages of high sensitivity, good reproducibility, low cost, and comprehensive metabolic standard atlas database, which are beneficial to qualitative analysis.

PROCEDURE

Saponification of acylglycerols is performed using a methanolic sodium hydroxide solution. The soaps are converted to methyl esters by reaction with a boron trifluoride/methanol complex. Fatty acid methyl esters are extracted from the reaction mixture with heptane.

The obtained esters are analysed using a Varian 4000, GC-FID Varian GC/MS 4000 gas chromatograph, equipped with a BPX70 capillary column with a length of 30 m, an internal diameter of 0.25 mm and a film thickness of 0.25 µm; helium was used as the carrier gas.

Conditions for the separation of fatty acid methyl esters: initial temperature 60 °C for 1 min; temperature increase from 60 to 170 °C at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹; injector temperature 225 °C, FID detector temperature 250 °C, total time of analyses 32 min.

All determinations are performed in two parallel repetitions.

Qualitative identification of fatty acid ester peaks is performed by comparison with the retention times of appropriate Sigma fatty acid methyl ester standards.

The percentages of fatty acid esters calculated is based on the integration of peak areas made by the computer system of the chromatography set and expressed as the percentage of individual esters in relation to the total amount of fatty acid esters in the sample.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Methanolic sodium hydroxide solution
- BF₃ in methanol
- NaOH in methanol
- NaCl, r-r
- Na₂SO₄ anhydrous
- Fatty acids (C10, C12, C14, C16, C18:0, C18:1, C18:2, C18:3, C20, C22)
- Temperature controlled water bath
- Glass pipettes: 2 mL, 5 mL
- Test tubes tightly closed
- 2 mL and 10 mL chromatography vials
- Helium 6.0
- Nitrogen 6.0
- Synthetic air

Equipment:

- PS-100 press (OLA Company, PL)
- Varian 4000, GC-FID, BPX70 (30 m, 0.25 mm, 0.25 μm)

REFERENCES

Folch, J., Lees, M. & Sloane Stanley, G.H. (1957). A simple method for the isolation and purification of total lipids from animal tissues. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 226(1), 497-509.

Ilić, M., Pastor, K., Romanić, R., Vujić, Đ. & Ačanski, M. (2023). A GC-MS based fatty acid profiling approach for uncovering the composition of edible oil blends. *Food Analytical Methods*, 1-7.

Gambus, H., Borowiec, F. & Zajàc, T. (2003). Chemical composition of linseed with different colour of bran layer. *Polish Journal of Food and Nutrition Sciences*, 12(3), 67-70.

Zięć, G., Gambuś, H., Lukaszewicz, M. & Gambuś, F. (2021). Wheat bread fortification: the supplement of teff flour and chia seeds. *Applied Sciences*, 11(11), 5238.

2.6.7. Dry mass of seeds

PRINCIPLE

Dry matter is a basic characteristics of crop products. Assessing the dry matter content of seeds is essential for determining their viability, storage requirements, quality, and processing needs. It helps ensure successful germination, longer shelf life, and optimal performance in agricultural practices.

PROCEDURE

The fresh grains are weighed with accuracy of 0.01 g.

Next, the samples are dried to constant weight in 105 °C for 3 h. After cooling the sample in air for approximately 1 h, it is weighed with a reading accuracy of 0.01 g.

Dry mass is calculated based on a difference between the weight of fresh and dry biomass.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Laboratory scale with an accuracy of 0.001 g
- Laboratory oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Grudzińska, M., Czerko, Z. & Jankowska, J. (2015). Zmiany zawartości suchej masy i skrobi w bulwach ziemniaka w czasie przechowywania oraz ich wpływ na straty masy surowca w procesie smażenia chipsów. *Inżynieria i Aparatura Chemiczna*, 54(5), 243-246.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.7. Sunflower

2.7.1. Thousand kernel weight

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the mass of 1,000 seeds as one of the important indicators characterizing the value of the seed lot. The analysis consists of selecting, weighing, and calculating the mass of 1,000 seeds according to their number in the sample. For this, a seed sample of the main crop is used after analysing its purity. Accounting is carried out manually or with the help of counters.

PROCEDURE

1. All or part of the sample is used for analysis. If the entire sample is used, then the number of seeds in it is counted and weighed. The mass of 1,000 seeds is calculated by dividing the total mass of the sample by the number of seeds and multiplying the result by 1,000.
2. Under the conditions of using a certain number of seeds selected from the sample, form eight repetitions of 100 seeds each.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Collapsible boards,
- Set of kettlebells,
- Tweezers

Equipment:

- Electric scales (type VLKT 500 g M),
- Laboratory scales,
- Counter-disintegrator of seeds.

CALCULATIONS

Eight replicates of 100 seeds (without selection) are counted from the seeds of the main crop, which are weighed to the accuracy provided during the purity analysis. Then calculate:

a) variance (V) according to the formula

$$V = \frac{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2}{n(n-1)}, \quad (1)$$

where x is the mass of 100 seeds of each repetition, g;

n is the number of repetitions; \sum is the sum;

b) standard deviation (∂), as the square root of the variance, i.e

$$\partial = \sqrt{V}; \quad (2)$$

average arithmetic mass (\bar{x}) of 100 seeds according to the formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n}; \quad (3)$$

coefficient of variation (k) according to the formula

$$k = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} 100 \quad (4)$$

The mass of 1000 seeds are calculated by multiplying by 10 the average arithmetic mass (\bar{x}) 100 pieces.

REFERENCES

DSTU 4138-2002 Seeds of agricultural crops. Methods of determining quality.

2.7.2. Purity seed analysis

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the content of the components that make up the seed batch, which include the primary crop, other plants, and waste (impurities). The seeds of the primary crop include all its botanical breeds and varieties. Among them are:

- Intact seeds (caryopses, achenes, fruits, etc.);
- Achenes and similar fruits, regardless of the content of actual seeds;
- Seeds (fruits) that have microtraumas or have lost less than half of their size due to mechanical damage or destruction;
- Caryopses of grain crops with flower palea;
- Hulled seeds that have lost half or more of the hull or palea;
- Seeds that remain on the cleaning screen. Seeds of other plants include seeds (fruits) and seed-like structures of botanical plant species that do not belong to the primary crop, namely seeds of cultivated plants or weeds.

Waste (impurities) comprises the following:

- Residues of seeds (fruits) that have lost half or more of their original size;
- Seeds of legumes and cabbage crops without a seed hull;
- Empty spikelet and flower palea, husks, fragments of stems, leaves, etc
- Rotten seeds, sprouted seeds (roots or sprouts are half or more of the seed length, and in rounded seeds half or more of the diameter);
- Fungal formations (sooty sacs, lumps, spikelet, horns, sclerotia, and their fragments), nematode galls;
- Lumps of soil, stones, sand, excrement, insects, etc;
- Seeds that have passed through the cleaning screen;
- Seeds of other plants.

PROCEDURE

1. The middle sample is poured onto a smooth surface and mixed thoroughly, then the colour, shine, odour, mold, and other organoleptic features are used to assess the condition of the seeds. If large impurities (lumps of soil, stones, stem fragments, etc.) are discovered and cannot be evenly distributed in the middle sample, they are separated and weighed to the hundredth of a gram.
2. The content of the primary crop seeds and waste in work samples is determined according to Table 8.

Table 8. Sunflower: conditions of sieve analysis of seeds for determining purity

Crop	Duration of hand sifting, min
Sunflower	2.2×20
- varieties and crosses	2.0×20
- cross female parent	1.5×20
- cross male parent	

3. The content of the primary crop seeds and waste in work samples is determined according to Table 9.

Table 9. Sunflower: maximum weight limits for seed batches and samples

Crop	Maximum batch weight (control unit) kg (±5%)	Weight of average sample, g			
		Average		Work	
		To determine			
		sowing qualities (±5%)	moisture content	purity	content of other species
Sunflower <i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.	25,000	1,000	50	200	1,000

The analysis of each crop sample begins with sifting the work sample through a sieve (Table 1).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Thick paper bags

Equipment:

- Electric scales (type ВЛКТ 500 g M)
- Laboratory scales according to State Standard GOST 24104
- Dial scales with a weighing limit of at least 2 kg

- Timing device
- Diaphanoscope
- Mechanical seed divider
- Air seed classifier
- Sieve seed classifier
- Fluorescent lamp
- Laboratory bench (table)
- Exhaust hood
- Sandglasses (1-3 min)
- Preparation needles
- Selection boards
- Set of laboratory seeds
- Lid
- Bottom plate
- Corex
- Grain focuser (x4, x5) according to State Standard GOST 25706
- Set of weights according to State Standard GOST 7328
- Set of grain magnifiers (type ШНЛ-1)
- Set of small-sized sieves for herbs with a lid and a bottom plate
- Tweezers according to State Standard GOST 21241
- Respirators
- Laboratory scoops
- Spatulas.

CALCULATIONS

1. After sieving the seed samples, the number of nodules on each sieve and the percentage of each fraction are calculated.
2. To remove the waste, the second sample is sifted through one cleaning screen.
3. The work sample, which is divided into two halves (sub-samples), is analysed. In each sub-sample, the components are weighed with the required accuracy.

Table 10. Sunflower: weighing accuracy for seed analysis

Weight grading of the component	Number of decimal places
less than 99.99	2
between 100.0 and 999.9	1

from 1,000.0 and heavier	0
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4. The masses of the components are added, and the sum is compared with the initial mass of the work sample. If the difference between them does not surpass 5% (by weight of the work sample), the analysis results are considered reliable. If it is greater than 5%, the analysis is carried out on a re-sampled sample. The content of each component is calculated (in percent) to one decimal place based on the total of their masses. The sum must equal 100%. A deviation of 0.1% from it is corrected by the content of the largest of the components. A deviation of more than 0.1% indicates an error in the analysis or calculation.

5. The mixture components are distributed according to Table 11. Seeds of other crops are classified as waste.

Table 11. Sunflower: types of seed mixtures depending on components

Mixture	Mixture components
Grain	Grain crops, grain legumes, sunflower, soybeans, annual grasses
Perennial grasses	Perennial grasses (except couch grass, if the mixture is sown on crop rotation fields)
Annual grasses	Annual grasses, grain crops, grain legumes, sunflower, soybeans

6. The seeds of the primary crop of each component of the mixture are weighed to the second decimal place and indicated in the document separately. Seeds of other cultivated plants that are classified as waste are accounted for following the requirements of the State Standard of Ukraine DSTU 2240 for the predominant crop. Seeds of couch grass in a mixture of perennial grasses, if its components are cereal grasses, are accounted for in pieces per kilogram of the mixture.

REFERENCES

State Standard of Ukraine. DSTU 4138-2002 Seeds of Farm Crops. Methods for Determination of Quality.

2.7.3. Seed germination

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the number of seeds (in percent) capable of forming normally developed seedlings under optimal germination conditions. Normal seedlings include those in which the most important structures (roots, subcotyledon and supracotyledon knee, tubercle, cotyledons, coleoptile) are well and proportionally developed, intact, healthy, as well as with minor defects of those structures, which do

not affect the normal development of the seedling. They also include normally developed seedlings with signs of surface infection acquired from neighbouring diseased seeds.

In crops whose seeds germinate by several germinal roots (cereal spike crops), normally germinated grains include those that have at least two normally developed roots, longer than the length of the grain, and a sprout no less than half its length. In the seeds of peas, corn, millet and other crops that germinate by one root, normally germinated grains include grains that have a developed main germinal root, the size of which is not less than the length (diameter) of the grain, and a formed sprout, which is not less than half the length (diameter) seeds. In normally germinated sunflower seeds, the cotyledons should be easily freed from the fruit and seed coats.

Abnormal seedlings include those that are unable to develop into full-fledged plants even under favourable conditions. These include: — seedlings in which any structure is missing or severely damaged, which makes their further proportional development impossible; — poorly developed seedlings due to physiological disorders, as well as seedlings with deformed structures; — rotten seedlings.

Hard seeds are seeds that do not swell due to the impermeability of the skin.

A healthy ungerminated seed is a seed that, due to deep physiological rest, remains ungerminated and has no signs of decay.

PROCEDURE

1. Thermostats are washed with hot water and detergents and disinfected with a 1% solution of potassium permanganate or alcohol once every 10 days, while Jacobsen-type devices and utensils are washed and disinfected in the same way before each analysis,.
2. A tray with water is placed in the working chamber of the thermostat, and the Jacobsen apparatus is rinsed and filled with water. Petri and Koch dishes can be sterilized in an oven at $(130 \pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$ for one hour or boiled in water for 40 min.
3. Analysis of germination is carried out on the seeds of the main crop, isolated during purity determination. For this, 400 seeds of 100 or 50 (for large-seeded crops) pieces are arbitrarily counted in each repetition. The seeds are evenly placed on a moistened substrate.

The conditions that are mandatory (substrate, temperature) for the analysis, as well as additional instructions for breaking seed dormancy are given in Table 12.

Table 12. Sunflower: similarity analysis conditions

Crops	Substrate	Temperature in $^\circ\text{C} \pm 2 ^\circ\text{C}$	Accounting periods, days	

			first	final	Additional conditions for overcoming seed dormancy
Sunflower <i>Helianthus annuus</i> L.	on the sand, in the sand, in the paper (between the paper)	20-30; 25; 20	4	10	Preheating (30 °C) — 10 days; Pre-cooling

4. According to the table, the mode that is most acceptable should be chosen according to the availability of the laboratory, taking into account the condition of the seeds and the crop. It is recommended to give preference to the regime of variable temperatures, as biologically more natural.

5. During the analysis, filter paper (F) and sand (S) are used. Filter paper as a substrate is used in two ways: "on paper" and "in paper". To moisten the paper, immerse it in water, take it out and let the excess water drain (when pressing with a finger, a water film does not form around it). During the "on paper" analysis, seeds are spread on one or more layers of moistened paper placed in Petri dishes. Cover Petri dishes with lids. During the "in paper" analysis, seeds are spread horizontally or vertically between two layers of moistened paper with the germs down. The device with seeds prepared in this way is placed in a thermostat.

Sand is used as a substrate for germinating seeds (sifted through a sieve with holes with a diameter of 1 mm, washed, roasted), according to the following options: "on sand" - seeds are pressed into the surface of the sand to their thickness (diameter); or "in the sand" - the seed laid out on the bed is covered with a layer of sand 1-2 cm thick, leaving it loose.

6. Seeds of corn, sunflower, and other large-seeded crops are placed with the embryo down. Before analysis, the sand is moistened to 60% of its full moisture content. The moisture content (B) is determined in a metal cylinder 30 cm high, 8 cm in diameter, with a mesh bottom. A circle of moistened filter paper is placed on the bottom of the cylinder and weighed (T). The cylinder is filled 3/4 with fresh baked sand, weighed again (T₁) and placed in a vessel with water so that it is at the level of the sand. When the water wets the surface of the sand, the cylinder is removed from the vessel, excess water is allowed to drain, the walls are dried on the outside with filter paper and weighed (T₂). The moisture content of sand (in cm³ per 100 g) is calculated by the formula:

$$B = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 - T} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

7. After the analysis, the sand is washed, dried, sieved, roasted and stored for reuse.
8. The seeds are laid out in prepared nurseries using a spreader counter or manually using a marker, after which they are wrapped and smoothed with a rammer.
9. The filter paper is moistened with a 0.005% solution of gibberellic acid (50 mg per 1 dm³). During the entire period of germination, the is moistened with the same solution, which is stored in a refrigerator at a temperature of 8-10 °C.
10. During the analysis of freshly collected seeds with an incomplete period of physiological maturation, measures are taken to overcome the state of dormancy, namely: pre-cooling, warming, washing, treatment of the bed with chemicals, etc.
 - 10.1. Pre-cooling. Seeds sown on a wet substrate are kept at a temperature of 5-10 °C for the time provided for the first accounting of seedlings (germination energy), after which they are transferred to the temperature conditions provided for this crop. The period of pre-cooling is not included in the term of determination of similarity, but its duration and temperature must be noted in the document; the first accounting (germination energy) is carried out two days after the end of preliminary cooling. If necessary, pre-cooling is repeated or its term is extended.
 - 10.2. Preheating. The seeds are warmed for 7 days at a temperature of 30-40 °C. If necessary, the duration of heating is extended. Freshly harvested corn seeds with a moisture content of 30% and less before germination are dried in a cabinet at a temperature of (36 ± 2) °C in open greenhouses (in a layer of one grain) for 24 h, and with a moisture content of more than 30% - for 48 h. Then, they germinate on sand, observing the technical conditions adopted for corn.
 - 10.3. To remove dormancy, seeds are illuminated (O) for 8 hours every day with an intensity of 750-1250 lx (250 lx is enough for seeds that are not in a state of rest). During germination in the regime of variable temperatures, illumination is given during the period of application of high temperature.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride (-bromide)
- Cotton wool is hygroscopic
- Distilled water
- Drinking water
- Glucose crystalline hydrate
- Potassium nitrate

- Potassium permanganate according to GOST 20490
- Sulfuric acid according to GOST 2184 or GOST 4204
- Succinic acid according to GOST 6341
- Measuring flask (500 cm³)
- Filter paper
- Quartz sand (particle size 0.5-2 mm)
- Ethyl alcohol 96%
- Adhesive transparent tape
- A cup with a capacity of 500 cm³
- Petri and Koch cup

Equipment:

- Apparatus for germinating seeds in the light (Jacobsen type)
- Dial scales with a weighing limit of at least 2 kg
- Fluorescent lamp
- Counter-decomposer of seeds
- Lux meter
- Furnace for calcination of sand
- Heating thermostat (t = 20-40 ± 2 °C)
- Cooling and heating thermostat (t = 0-40 ± 2 °C)
- Laboratory drying cabinet (t = 50-150 ± 2 °C)
- Small inventory:
- Dissecting needles
- Substrate humidifiers (dropper, watering can, pipette)
- Measuring ruler
- Markers for sand
- A set of grain scoops (type ShNL⁻¹)
- Tweezers according to GOST 21241
- Dishes for washing and moistening the substrate
- Planters (faience, plastic, polystyrene)
- Sieves for sieving sand
- Glass
- Laboratory scoops, thermometers (t = 0-50 °C)
- Rammers
- A metal cylinder with a mesh bottom, 30 cm high and 8 cm diameter

CALCULATIONS

The moisture content of sand (in cm³ per 100 g) is calculated by the formula:

$$B = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 - T} \cdot 100$$

During the first accounting, normally germinated seeds are separately evaluated and taken into account, as well as seeds with pronounced signs of anomalies and rotten ones. The last two groups are removed, and normally germinated ones are removed if necessary.

The term of the final accounting is allowed to be extended up to 3 days, and if necessary, more, to allow germination of healthy ungerminated seeds, or shortened if the picture is understood ahead of time.

The results obtained during the similarity analysis are expressed as percentages for each of the identified categories (normal and abnormal seedlings, germinated and ungerminated seeds, in particular hard, dead, rotten). The reliability of the analysis is established by comparing the extreme values of the repetitions with the arithmetic mean. The result is considered reliable if the difference between them and the arithmetic mean value, which is calculated to a whole number, does not exceed the maximum permissible deviations.

REFERENCES

DSTU 4138-2002 Seeds of agricultural crops. Methods of determining quality.

2.7.4. Moisture content

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the content of free moisture in the seeds.

PROCEDURE

1. *Number of determinations.* Separate determinations are carried out on two test portions taken from the laboratory sample. If the absolute difference between the two values obtained is greater than the repeatability limit, the determination is repeated until requirements are satisfied.
2. *Test portion.* 5 ± 1 g of the laboratory is rapidly weighed, to the nearest 0.001 g, in the metal dish. The mass of the undried test portion is recorded and named "m'₀". This dish is previously dried and tarred, together with its lid, and record the mass is recorded and named "m_d" to the nearest 0.001 g.

3. *Drying.* The open dish containing the test portion (2), together with the lid is placed in the oven and left for 120 min ± 5 min (90 min for flours). In certain cases, and particularly in hot-air dry countries, the drying period may be reduced to 60 min ± 5 min, which is sufficient time for the test portions to attain constant mass. These times must be controlled regularly. The door of the oven can't be opened during drying and moist products can't be placed in the oven before removing the dry test portions, as this would result in partial rehydration of the latter. After drying, the dish is quickly removed from the oven, covered, and placed in the desiccator.
4. *Weighing.* When the dish has cooled to laboratory temperature (generally between 30 min and 45 min after it has been placed in the desiccator), it is weighed to the nearest 0.001 g. The mass of the dried test portion is recorded and named as "m₁"

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Analytical balance (accuracy ± 0.001 g).
- Grinding mill
- Metal dish
- Constant-temperature oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

Without preconditioning:

The moisture content, W_{H_2O} expressed in grams per 100 g of the product as received, is given by:

$$W_{H_2O} = \left(1 - \frac{m_1}{m_0}\right) \times 100$$

Where:

$m_0 = m'_0 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the test portion (2)

$m_1 = m'_1 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the test portion after drying (4).

With preconditioning.

The moisture content, W_{H_2O} , expressed in grams per 100 g of the product as received, is given by:

$$W_{H_2O} = \left[(m_0 - m_1) \frac{m_3}{m_0} + m_2 - m_3 \right] \times \frac{100}{m_2} = \left(1 - \frac{m_1 m_3}{m_0 m_2}\right) \times 100$$

Where:

$m_2 = m'_2 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the sample taken before preconditioning (2);

$m_3 = m_3 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the preconditioned sample.

REFERENCES

State Standard of Ukraine. DSTU ISO 712:2015(ISO 712:2009, IDT). Cereals and cereal products - Determination of moisture content - Reference method.

2.7.5. Ash yield

PRINCIPLE

Method used for determining the ash yielded by cereals, pulses, and their milled products intended for human consumption. The source materials covered are:

- a) grains of cereals;
- b) flours and semolinas;
- c) milled products (bran and high bran content products, sharps);
- d) mixed cereal flours (mixes);
- e) cereal by-products other than milled products
- f) pulses and their by-products.

PROCEDURE

A test portion is incinerated until combustion of organic matter is complete, then the residue obtained is weighed. The residue obtained is flaky after incineration at 550 °C and vitrified after incineration at 900 °C.

In general, products containing salts (e.g., sodium chloride, pyrophosphate) shall be incinerated at (550 ± 10) °C.

Table 13 summarizes incineration temperatures according to product type.

Table 13. Incineration temperatures and product type

Product type	Incineration temperature	
Flours	(550 ± 10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Semolinas	(550 ± 10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Cereal grains	(550 ± 10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Other milled products (e.g., bran, high bran content products, sharps)	(550 ± 10) °C	
Mixed cereal products (mixes)	(550 ± 10) °C	
Cereal by-products other than milled products	(550 ± 10) °C	
Pulses and their by-products	(550 ± 10) °C	

1. Determination of the moisture content

The moisture content of the test sample is determined beforehand in accordance with ISO 712 for cereals other than maize or ISO 6540 in the case of maize or ISO 24557 in the case of pulses.

2. The preparation of the ashing dishes

For ashing dishes suitable for use at 900 °C, the previously cleaned dishes are brought up to the incineration temperature being employed by being put in the muffle furnace for 5 min, being left to cool in the desiccator, and then being weighed to within 0.1 mg. For ashing dishes suitable for use at 550 °C, the cleaned dishes are placed in an oven for the time required for drying (e.g., 90 min at 130 °C). Immediately before use, the dishes are removed from the oven and left to cool in a desiccator, then weighed to within 0.1 mg.

3. Preparation of the test portion

From the test sample carefully mixed, a test portion between 3.9 g and 4.1 g is rapidly weighed to within 0.1 mg in the case of incineration at 900 °C and between 4.9 g and 5.1 g in the case of incineration at 550 °C. In the case of low-density products, the test portion can be between 2 (\pm 0.1) g and 3 (\pm 0.1) g. In the ashing dish, prepared and weighed as described in 2, the product is spread out without packing it to form a uniform layer.

4. Pre-ashing

The ashing dish and its contents are placed at the entrance of the furnace brought up to the ashing temperature. At 900 °C, the products are burst into flame spontaneously. At 550 °C, they are necessary to be ignited with ethanol. For pre-ashing at 550 °C, it is permissible to put the dishes in the cold furnace and let the temperature of the furnace rise to the target temperature.

5. Ashing

The dish is placed inside the furnace once the product has finished burning. The furnace door is closed. The ashing continues until the combustion of the entire product, including the carbon particles contained in the residue, is complete, namely 1 h minimum at 900 °C, and 4 h minimum at 550 °C. In order to maintain the efficiency of the desiccator, dishes are not stacked. Once the ashing is completed, the dish is removed from the furnace and placed in the desiccator to cool. Due to the hygroscopic nature of the ash, as soon as the dish has reached ambient temperature (namely 15 min to 20 min for metallic dishes and 60 min to 90 min minimum for quartz or silica dishes), it is weighed rapidly to within 0.1 mg. For test portions incinerated at 550 °C, special precautions are taken to avoid flaky residues being swept away with the influx of air on

opening the desiccator. The validity of the results obtained on this sample is checked with respect to the laboratory's self-inspection criteria (e.g., control chart).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagent:

- Hydrochloric acid, aqueous solution of one part by volume of HCl (35% volume fraction) and one part by volume of water.
- Purified diphosphorus pentoxide (P₄O₁₀).
- Ethanol.

Equipment:

- Grinding mill
- Ashing dish, of capacity not less than 20 mL, rectangular or round shape, flat-bottomed and having a surface area of not less than 12 cm². Suitable materials for the ashing dish which do not deteriorate under test conditions at the temperature of operation are:
 - at 900 °C — platinum or rhodium
 - at 550 °C — quartz or silica.
 - a. The dishes shall be cleaned by complete immersion for at least 1 h in hydrochloric acid, then rinsed with running water and then with distilled water.
 - b. After rinsing, the dishes shall be dried in an oven at a temperature and for a period sufficient to eliminate water.
- Electrically heated muffle furnace, with adequate ventilation, provided with temperature control system and a refractory coating which is not liable to lose particles at the ashing temperature, and capable of being maintained at 900 (± 25) °C or at 550 (± 10) °C.
- Vacuum desiccator, equipped with a perforated aluminium or porcelain plate, and diphosphorus pentoxide (5.2) as drying agent.
- Analytical balance, with an accuracy of 0.01 mg.
- Riffle splitter or cone-shaped divider.
- Oven for drying the ashing dishes.

CALCULATIONS

The ash yield, as a mass fraction on the dry matter basis expressed as a percentage, $w_{a,d}$, is given by Equation (1):

$$W_{a,d} = (m_2 - m_1) \times \frac{100}{m_0} \times \frac{100}{100 - w_m} \quad (1)$$

Where:

m_0 is the mass, in grams, of the test portion (3)

m_1 is the mass, in grams, of the ashing dish (2);

m_2 is the mass, in grams, of the ashing dish (2) and the incinerated residue (5);

w_m is the moisture content, as a percentage by mass, of the sample.

Take as a result the arithmetic mean of the two determinations if the repeatability conditions are fulfilled.

If needed, the ash yield, as mass fraction on the wet matter basis expressed as a percentage, $W_{a,w}$, is given by Equation (2):

$$W_{a,d} = (m_2 - m_1) \times \frac{100}{m_0}$$

REFERENCES

DSTU ISO 2171:2007 Cereals, pulses and by-products — Determination of ash yield by incineration.

2.7.6. Oil content

PRINCIPLE

This is a reference method for the determination of the hexane extract, called “oil content”, of oil seeds used as industrial raw materials. The method has been tested on rapeseed, soya beans and sunflower seeds. Extraction of a test portion, in a suitable apparatus, with technical hexane or light petroleum. Elimination of the solvent and weighing of the extract obtained.

PROCEDURE

1. Test sample preparation

1.1 It is essential that the oil extractions are carried out within 30 min of grinding, especially if the free fatty acids content of the extracted oil is to be determined.

Care shall be taken to clean all mills thoroughly before and after each sample has been ground. Any material adhering to the mill shall be incorporated with the bulk of the ground material.

1.2. The test sample of sunflower seeds is grinded in the mechanical mill, until the major dimension of the particles obtained is not greater than 2 mm. The first particles (about one-twentieth of a sample) are rejected and the rest is collected and mixed carefully. The determination is carried out without delay.

For sunflower is used the UCM Mill with 1 mm screen.

1.3. 10 g ± 0.5 g of the test sample is weighed, to the nearest 1 mg. The test portion transferred to the thimble, using a small wad of cotton wool moistened with solvent to transfer the last traces of ground seed from the weighing container to the thimble. This cotton wool is used to plug the thimble.

2. Determination

2.1 Preparation of flask. A flask containing a few granules of pumice stone is weighed, to the nearest 1 mg, which has been previously dried in an oven and cooled in a desiccator.

2.2 Solvent extraction. The times stipulated for the three extractions may be varied slightly (for example by ± 10 min).

First extraction – The thimble containing the test portion is placed in the extraction apparatus. Then, the necessary quantity of solvent is poured into the flask. the flask is fit to the extraction apparatus on the electric heating bath or hot-plate. The heating is carried out so that the rate of reflux is at least 3 drops per second (boiling moderately, not violently). After extracting for 4 h, it is left to cool down. The thimble is removed from the extraction apparatus and place in a current of air in order to expel the greater part of the residual solvent.

Second extraction – the contents of the thimble is put into the microgrinder cylinder and grinded for 7 min. For most seeds, six 1 cm diameter steel balls in a 150 mL cylinder have been found to be satisfactory; for cottonseed with adherent linters, three 2 cm balls are satisfactory. The mixture is put back into the thimble, using a small piece of cotton wool to remove any residual seed particles from the grinding apparatus. This is added to the thimble. The thimble is put back into the extraction apparatus and re-extracted for a further 2 h, using the same flask containing the first extract. It is allowed to drain and cool, the thimble is removed again, most of the solvent is eliminate and the grinding process is repeated as above.

Third extraction - The mixture is put back into the thimble, cleaning the grinding apparatus as before, and the thimble is put back into the extraction apparatus. The extraction is done as before for 2 h, using the same flask.

2.3 Removal of solvent and weighing of the extract.

The greater part of the solvent is removed from the flask by distillation on the electric heating bath or hot-plate. The removal of solvent is assisted either by blowing air or, preferably, an inert gas (such as nitrogen or carbon dioxide) into the flask for short periods. The last traces of solvent are removed by heating the flask for between 30 min and 60 min in the oven at $103 (\pm 2) ^\circ\text{C}$ and atmospheric pressure, or at $80 ^\circ\text{C}$ under vacuum.

The flask is allowed to cool in the desiccator, for at least 1 h, to ambient temperature and weighed to the nearest 1 mg. It is heated again for between 20 min and 30 min under the same conditions, and allowed to cool again and finally weighed.

The difference between the two weights shall not exceed 5 mg. If it does, the operations of heating, cooling and weighing shall be repeated until the difference between two successive weights does not exceed 5 mg. The final mass of the flask is noted.

If there is a significant increase in mass (over 5 mg), oxidation of a drying oil may be taking place and a further analysis should be carried out, taking precautions to exclude oxygen.

2.4 Impurities content of the extracted oil.

The oil extracted shall be clear; if it is not, determine the impurities content. For this purpose, the fatty matter is dissolved in the solvent used for extraction; then, it is filtered through a filter paper, previously dried at 103 (± 2) °C to constant mass. The filter paper is washed several times with the same solvent to remove the oil completely and dried again at 103 (± 2) °C to constant mass. To cool and weigh the filter paper, a suitable vessel provided with a lid is used. The result is corrected accordingly.

3 “Oil content” of impurities

To determine the “oil content” of the impurities, the analysis in the same manner as for the seeds is carried out. However, in this case:

- the test portion may be 5 g to 10 g;
- only one extraction, for a period of 4 h, is necessary, the small error thus introduced into the “oil content” of the product is received being negligible.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- Technical hexane, n-hexane or light petroleum, essentially composed of hydrocarbons with 6 carbon atoms, of which less than 5% distils below 40 °C and more than 95% distils between 40 °C and 60 °C or between 50 °C and 70 °C.

Equipment:

- Analytical balance.
- Mechanical mill
- Mechanical micro-grinder, capable of producing a fineness of grinding of the oilseeds of less than 160 μm , with the exception of the “shell”, particles of which may reach 400 μm
- Extraction thimble and cotton wool, free from matter soluble in hexane or light petroleum
- Suitable extraction apparatus, fitted with a flask of capacity from 200 mL to 250 mL

- Pumice stone, in small particles, or other anti-bumping granules, previously dried in an oven at (130 ± 2) °C and cooled in a desiccator
- Apparatus for safely removing solvent from extraction thimble
- Electric heating bath
- Electrically heated oven.
- Desiccator
- Electrically heated oven
- Metal dish

CALCULATIONS

The "oil content", expressed as a percentage by mass of the product, as received [tale quale], is equal to w_0 :

$$w_0 = \frac{m_1}{m_0} \times 100\%$$

Where:

m_0 is the mass, in grams, of the test portion;

m_1 is the mass, in grams of the dried extract.

"Oil content" expressed relative to dry matter.

If necessary, "oil content" can be expressed as a percentage of dry material and calculated according to the formula:

$$w_0 \cdot \left[\frac{100}{100 - U} \right] \%$$

Where:

w_0 is the percentage of oil obtained from the total mass of the product;

U is the percentage of water and volatile substances in the total mass of the product calculated according to ISO 665.

Determination of oil content based on any specified moisture content.

It may be necessary to convert the oil content of a sample determined at one moisture content to another moisture content, for example when the sample is partially dried before weighing.

In such a case:

$$w' = w \cdot \left[\frac{100 - U'}{100 - U} \right] \%,$$

Where:

w is the oil content in the sample according to moisture and the content of volatile substances in it U

w' is the oil content in the sample according to humidity and the content of volatile substances in it U'

REFERENCES

- ISO 658:1988, Oilseeds — Determination of impurities.
 ISO 664:1990, Oilseeds — Reduction of laboratory sample to test sample.
 ISO 665:1977, Oilseeds — Determination of moisture and volatile matter content.
 ISO 659:1998, Oilseeds — Determination of oil content (Reference method).

2.7.7. Acid number

PRINCIPLE

The acid value is a measure of the extent to which the glycerides in the oil have been hydrolysed by lipase action. The glycerides are also hydrolysed with water in the presence of air and possibly bacteria. The decomposition is accelerated by heat and light.

As rancidity is usually accompanied by free fatty acid formation, determination of acid value is often used as a general indication of the condition and edibility of oils.

The acid value is the number of milligrams of potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the free fatty acids in 1.0 g of fat or oil.

PROCEDURE

- 0.1-0.3 g of fat sample or A mL of the extract containing 0.1-0.3 g of fat is put in a 100 mL Erlenmeyer flask.
- [10 — A] mL of n-Hexane and 1-2 drops of indicator are added.
- The solution is titrated against 0.02 N KOH solution. The end point is reached when pink (phenolphthalein) or blue (thymolphthalein) colour persists for 30 s.
- A blank test is carried out using A mL of C-M Mixture instead of the extract.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- 0.02 N KOH in ethyl alcohol

- Potassium hydroxide
- Ethyl alcohol
- n-Hexane
- 1% phenolphthalein or thymolphthalein

Equipment:

1. Microburette (2 mL with 0.01 mL intervals)
2. Conical flasks (100 mL)
3. 5 mL pipettes

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Acid value (mg/g)} = \frac{56.11 \times 0.02 \times (V_s - V_b) \times F}{W}$$

Where:

V_s – titration volume of sample (ml); V_b – titration volume of blank (ml); W – weight of fat in the volume of extract used (g); F – factor of 0.02 KOH solution,

$$F = \frac{5}{V_f}$$

Where:

V_f is the volume of 0.02 N KOH required to neutralize 5 mL of the 0.02 N H_2SO_4 solution

56.11 – molecular weight of KOH

0.02 – concentration of KOH

REFERENCES

DSTU EN ISO 660:2019 Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Determination of acid value and acidity (ISO 660:2009, IDT).

ISO 661, Animal and vegetable fats and oils — Preparation of test sample.

ISO 3696, Water for analytical laboratory use — Specification and test methods.

2.8. Triticale

2.8.1. Spectroscopy analysis of ash, fat, fibre, humidity, starch and protein content (%)

PRINCIPLE

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is considered one of the main routine analytical methods used by the food industry. This technique is utilised to determine proximate chemical compositions e.g., protein, dry matter, fat and fibre of a wide range of food ingredients and products.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in special ampoules. The humidity, ash, fat, fibre, starch and protein content (%) is determined using the InfraXact™ analyzer based on the near-infrared spectroscopy. The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample in the 570–1850 nm wavelengths. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- InfraXact™ analyzer (Foss, Hillerod, Denmark)
- Ampoule

REFERENCES

Yang, Z., Cai, L., Han, L., Fan, X. & Liu, X. (2021). Review of standards for near infrared spectroscopy methods. *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 29(6), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670335211042016>

Cozzolino, D. (2021). The ability of near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to predict functional properties in foods: Challenges and opportunities. *Molecules*, 26(22), 6981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226981>

Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

2.8.2. Ammonium and amine nitrogen content

PRINCIPLE

A method for determining ammonium and amine nitrogen, e.g., occurring in water, soil or food products. Using it, nitrogen bound in organic compounds is converted into ammonium and analysed together with the ammonium compounds present in the sample.

PROCEDURE

Clean plant material is first dried in oven in 50-60 °C and finely grounded. A sample of 0.5-0.7 g is taken and mixed with concentrated sulfuric acid (10 cm³) and a hint of selenium mix. The mixture is put aside, and the next day is burned in the oven at 400-450 °C for ca. 1 hour. Next, the nitrogen is analysed in Kjeltac apparatus. The protein content [%] is calculated by multiplying N content by a factor of 6.25.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean seeds, grains and potato tubers
- Sulfuric acid
- Selenium mix

Equipment:

- Laboratory oven
- Kjelttec TM8100 (Foss, Hilleroed, Denmark)

REFERENCES

Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant, Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.8.3. Micro and macro-elements**PRINCIPLE**

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), is the technique for many applications that require analysing a sample for its elemental content. Typical samples include those in the environmental, metallurgical, geological, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, materials, and food safety arenas. The advantages of using ICP- OES include its wide linear dynamic range, high matrix tolerance, and the enhanced speed of analysis that can be achieved.

PROCEDURE

The plant material is dried and grounded. Then, 0.5 g is weighed and mixed with 7 mL of HNO₃ and 1 mL of H₂O₂, placed into Teflon vessels and in a microwave rotor at 190 °C for 20 min and then 190 °C for 25 min. Next the material is transferred to 25 cm³ flasks, topped up with distilled water and the determination of elements is performed on the Optical Emission Spectrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL**Material:**

- HNO₃
- H₂O₂
- Distilled water
- Teflon vessels
- 25 cm³ flasks

Equipment:

- Microwave rotor

- ICP Perkin Elmer Optical Emission Spectrometer Optima 7300DV

REFERENCES

Szara-Bąk, M., Baran, A. & Klimkowicz-Pawlas, A. (2023). Recycling of bottom sediment to agriculture: effects on plant growth and soil properties. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 23(1), 539-551.

2.8.4. Dry mass of seeds

PRINCIPLE

Dry matter is a basic characteristics of crop products. Assessing the dry matter content of seeds is essential for determining their viability, storage requirements, quality, and processing needs. It helps ensure successful germination, longer shelf life, and optimal performance in agricultural practices.

PROCEDURE

The fresh grains are weighed with accuracy of 0.01 g. Next, the samples are dried to constant weight in 105 °C for 3 h. After cooling the sample in air for approximately 1 hour, it is weighed with a reading accuracy of 0.01 g. Dry mass is calculated based on a difference between the weight of fresh and dry biomass.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Laboratory scale with an accuracy of 0.001 g
- Laboratory oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content(\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Grudzińska, M., Czerko, Z. & Jankowska, J. (2015). Zmiany zawartości suchej masy i skrobi w bulwach ziemniaka w czasie przechowywania oraz ich wpływ na straty masy surowca w procesie smażenia chipsów. *Inżynieria i Aparatura Chemiczna*, 54(5), 243-246.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.9. Wheat

2.9.1. Spectroscopy analysis of ash, fat, fibre, humidity, starch and protein content (%)

PRINCIPLE

Near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy is considered one of the main routine analytical methods used by the food industry. This technique is utilised to determine proximate chemical compositions e.g., protein, dry matter, fat and fibre of a wide range of food ingredients and products.

PROCEDURE

Clean, air-dried plant material is either fine grounded or intact seeds/grains are used and placed in special ampoules. The humidity, ash, fat, fibre, starch and protein content (%) is determined using the InfraXact™ analyzer based on the near-infrared spectroscopy. The analysis is conducted in three technical replications per sample in the 570–1850 nm wavelengths. Each sample is scanned six times and compared with two internal standards (references) before calculating the mean value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Air-dried and clean seeds, grains and vegetative parts of crops

Equipment:

- InfraXact™ analyzer (Foss, Hillerod, Denmark)
- Ampoule

REFERENCES

Yang, Z., Cai, L., Han, L., Fan, X. & Liu, X. (2021). Review of standards for near infrared spectroscopy methods. *Journal of Near Infrared Spectroscopy*, 29(6), 313-320. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670335211042016>

Cozzolino, D. (2021). The ability of near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy to predict functional properties in foods: Challenges and opportunities. *Molecules*, 26(22), 6981. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26226981>

Pużyńska, K., Pużyński, S., Synowiec, A., Bocianowski, J. & Lepiarczyk, A. (2021). Grain yield and total protein content of organically grown oats–vetch mixtures depending on soil type and oats' cultivar. *Agriculture*, 11(1), 79.

2.9.2. Ammonium and amine nitrogen content

PRINCIPLE

A method for determining ammonium and amine nitrogen, e.g., occurring in water, soil or food products. Using it, nitrogen bound in organic compounds is converted into

ammonium and analysed together with the ammonium compounds present in the sample.

PROCEDURE

Clean plant material is first dried in oven in 50-60 °C and finely grounded. A sample of 0.5-0.7 g is taken and mixed with concentrated sulfuric acid (10 cm³) and a hint of selenium mix. The mixture is put aside, and the next day is burned in the oven at 400-450 °C for *ca.* 1 hour. Next, the nitrogen is analysed in Kjeltex apparatus. The protein content [%] is calculated by multiplying N content by a factor of 6.25.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Clean seeds, grains and potato tubers
- Sulfuric acid
- Selenium mix

Equipment:

- Laboratory oven
- Kjeltex TM8100 (Foss, Hilleroed, Denmark)

REFERENCES

Kołodziejczyk, M. (2014). Effect of nitrogen fertilization and microbial preparations on potato yielding. *Plant, Soil and Environment*, 60(8), 379-386.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.9.3. Ammonium and amine nitrogen content

PRINCIPLE

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), is the technique for many applications that require analysing a sample for its elemental content. Typical samples include those in the environmental, metallurgical, geological, petrochemical, pharmaceutical, materials, and food safety arenas. The advantages of using ICP- OES include its wide linear dynamic range, high matrix tolerance, and the enhanced speed of analysis that can be achieved.

PROCEDURE

The plant material is dried and grounded. Then, 0.5 g is weighed and mixed with 7 mL of HNO₃ and 1 mL of H₂O₂, placed into Teflon vessels and in a microwave rotor at 190 °C for 20 min and then 190 °C for 25 min. Next the material is transferred to 25 cm³ flasks,

topped up with distilled water and the determination of elements is performed on the Optical Emission Spectrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- HNO₃
- H₂O₂
- Distilled water
- Teflon vessels
- 25 cm³ flasks

Equipment:

- Microwave rotor
- ICP Perkin Elmer Optical Emission Spectrometer Optima 7300DV

REFERENCES

Szara-Bąk, M., Baran, A. & Klimkowicz-Pawlas, A. (2023). Recycling of bottom sediment to agriculture: effects on plant growth and soil properties. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 23(1), 539-551.

2.9.4. Dry mass of seeds

PRINCIPLE

Dry matter is a basic characteristics of crop products. Assessing the dry matter content of seeds is essential for determining their viability, storage requirements, quality, and processing needs. It helps ensure successful germination, longer shelf life, and optimal performance in agricultural practices.

PROCEDURE

The fresh grains are weighed with accuracy of 0.01 g. Next, the samples are dried to constant weight in 105 °C for 3 h. After cooling the sample in air for approximately 1 hour, it is weighed with a reading accuracy of 0.01 g. Dry mass is calculated based on a difference between the weight of fresh and dry biomass.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Laboratory scale with an accuracy of 0.001 g
- Laboratory oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content}(\%) = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Grudzińska, M., Czerko, Z. & Jankowska, J. (2015). Zmiany zawartości suchej masy i skrobi w bulwach ziemniaka w czasie przechowywania oraz ich wpływ na straty masy surowca w procesie smażenia chipsów. *Inżynieria i Aparatura Chemiczna*, 54(5), 243-246.

Ostrowska, A., Gawliński, S. & Szczubiałka, Z. (1991). Methods of analysis and assessment of soil and plant properties. *A Catalogue*. Publisher: Institute of Environmental Protection–National Research Institute, Warsaw, 334.

2.9.5. Thousand kernel weight TKW

PRINCIPLE

TKW (thousand kernel weight) is an important parameter in seed analysis and agriculture, and it is often used as an indicator of seed quality, productivity, and crop yield potential. It provides information about seed size, density, and viability. Higher TKW values generally indicate larger and potentially more vigorous seeds, which are desirable for planting purposes

PROCEDURE

To determine the TKW, a representative sample of seeds or kernels is counted and weighed.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

CALCULATIONS

The weight of the counted seeds is multiplied by a factor of 1,000 to obtain the TKW. The unit of measurement for TKW is typically grams (g) or kilograms (kg) per 1,000 seeds.

REFERENCES

Groos, C., Robert, N., Bervas, E. & Charmet, G. (2003). Genetic analysis of grain protein-content, grain yield and thousand-kernel weight in bread wheat. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*, 106, 1032-1040.

2.9.6. Purity seed analysis

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the content of the components that make up the seed batch, which include the primary crop, other plants, and waste (impurities). The seeds of the primary crop include all its botanical breeds and varieties. Among them are:

- Intact seeds (caryopses, achenes, fruits, etc.);

- Achenes and similar fruits, regardless of the content of actual seeds;
- Seeds (fruits) that have microtraumas or have lost less than half of their size due to mechanical damage or destruction;
- Caryopses of grain crops with flower palea;
- Hulled seeds that have lost half or more of the hull or palea;
- Seeds that remain on the cleaning screen. Seeds of other plants include seeds (fruits) and seed-like structures of botanical plant species that do not belong to the primary crop, namely seeds of cultivated plants or weeds.

Waste (impurities) comprises the following:

- Residues of seeds (fruits) that have lost half or more of their original size;
- Seeds of legumes and cabbage crops without a seed hull;
- Empty spikelet and flower palea, husks, fragments of stems, leaves, etc
- Rotten seeds, sprouted seeds (roots or sprouts are half or more of the seed length, and in rounded seeds half or more of the diameter);
- Fungal formations (sooty sacs, lumps, spikelet, horns, sclerotia, and their fragments), nematode galls;
- Lumps of soil, stones, sand, excrement, insects, etc;
- Seeds that have passed through the cleaning screen;
- Seeds of other plants.

PROCEDURE

1. The middle sample is poured onto a smooth surface and mixed thoroughly, then the colour, shine, odour, mold, and other organoleptic features are used to assess the condition of the seeds. If large impurities (lumps of soil, stones, stem fragments, etc.) are discovered and cannot be evenly distributed in the middle sample, they are separated and weighed to the hundredth of a gram.
2. The content of the primary crop seeds and waste in work samples is determined according to Table 14.

Table 14. Wheat: conditions of sieve analysis of seeds for determining purity

Crop		Size of holes, mm	Duration of hand sifting, min
Wheat	elongated	1.7×20	1

3. The content of the primary crop seeds and waste in work samples is determined according to Table 15.

Table 15. Wheat: maximum weight limits for seed batches and samples of wheat

Crop		Weight of average sample, g

	Maximum batch weight (control unit) kg ($\pm 5\%$)	Average		Work	
		To determine			
		sowing qualities ($\pm 5\%$)	moisture content	purity	content of other species
Soft and hard wheat <i>Triticum aestivum</i> L. T. <i>durum</i> Desf.	25,000	1,000	100	120	1,000

The analysis of each crop sample begins with sifting the work sample through a sieve.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Thick paper bags

Equipment:

- Electric scales (type ВЛКТ 500 g M)
- Laboratory scales according to State Standard GOST 24104
- Dial scales with a weighing limit of at least 2 kg
- Timing device
- Diaphanoscope
- Mechanical seed divider
- Air seed classifier
- Sieve seed classifier
- Fluorescent lamp
- Laboratory bench (table)
- Exhaust hood
- Sandglasses (1-3 min)
- Preparation needles
- Selection boards
- Set of laboratory seeds
- Lid
- Bottom plate
- Corex
- Grain focuser (x4, x5) according to State Standard GOST 25706
- Set of weights according to State Standard GOST 7328
- Set of grain magnifiers (type ШНЛ-1)
- Set of small-sized sieves for herbs with a lid and a bottom plate

- Tweezers according to State Standard GOST 21241
- Respirators
- Laboratory scoops
- Spatulas.

CALCULATIONS

1. After sieving the seed samples, the number of nodules on each sieve and the percentage of each fraction are calculated.
2. To remove the waste, the second sample is sifted through one cleaning screen.
3. The work sample, which is divided into two halves (sub-samples), is analysed. In each sub-sample, the components are weighed with the required accuracy.

Table 16. Wheat: weighing accuracy for seed analysis

Weight grading of the component	Number of decimal places
less than 99.99	2
between 100.0 and 999.9	1
from 1,000.0 and heavier	0

4. The masses of the components are added, and the sum is compared with the initial mass of the work sample. If the difference between them does not surpass 5% (by weight of the work sample), the analysis results are considered reliable. If it is greater than 5%, the analysis is carried out on a re-sampled sample. The content of each component is calculated (in percent) to one decimal place based on the total of their masses. The sum must equal 100%. A deviation of 0.1% from it is corrected by the content of the largest of the components. A deviation of more than 0.1% indicates an error in the analysis or calculation.
5. The mixture components are distributed according to Table 17. Seeds of other crops are classified as waste.

Table 17. Wheat: types of seed mixtures depending on components.

Mixture	Mixture components
Grain	Grain crops, grain legumes, sunflower, soybeans, annual grasses
Perennial grasses	Perennial grasses (except couch grass, if the mixture is sown on crop rotation fields)
Annual grasses	Annual grasses, grain crops, grain legumes, sunflower, soybeans

6. The seeds of the primary crop of each component of the mixture are weighed to the second decimal place and indicated in the document separately. Seeds of other cultivated plants that are classified as waste are accounted for following the requirements of the State Standard of Ukraine DSTU 2240 for the predominant crop. Seeds of couch grass in a mixture of perennial grasses, if its components are cereal grasses, are accounted for in pieces per kilogram of the mixture.

REFERENCES

State Standard of Ukraine. DSTU 4138-2002 Seeds of Farm Crops. Methods for Determination of Quality.

2.9.7. Seed germination

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the number of seeds (in percent) capable of forming normally developed seedlings under optimal germination conditions. Normal seedlings include those in which the most important structures (roots, subcotyledon and supracotyledon knee, tubercle, cotyledons, coleoptile) are well and proportionally developed, intact, healthy, as well as with minor defects of those structures, which do not affect the normal development of the seedling. They also include normally developed seedlings with signs of surface infection acquired from neighbouring diseased seeds.

In crops whose seeds germinate by several germinal roots (cereal spike crops), normally germinated grains include those that have at least two normally developed roots, longer than the length of the grain, and a sprout no less than half its length. In the seeds of peas, corn, millet and other crops that germinate by one root, normally germinated grains include grains that have a developed main germinal root, the size of which is not less than the length (diameter) of the grain, and a formed sprout, which is not less than half the length (diameter) seeds. In normally germinated sunflower seeds, the cotyledons should be easily freed from the fruit and seed coats.

Abnormal seedlings include those that are unable to develop into full-fledged plants even under favourable conditions. These include: — seedlings in which any structure is missing or severely damaged, which makes their further proportional development impossible; — poorly developed seedlings due to physiological disorders, as well as seedlings with deformed structures; — rotten seedlings.

Hard seeds are seeds that do not swell due to the impermeability of the skin.

A healthy ungerminated seed is a seed that, due to deep physiological rest, remains ungerminated and has no signs of decay.

PROCEDURE

1. Thermostats once every 10 days, and Jacobsen-type devices and utensils before each analysis, are washed with hot water and detergents and disinfected with a 1% solution of potassium permanganate or alcohol.
2. A tray with water is placed in the working chamber of the thermostat, and the Jacobsen apparatus is rinsed and filled with water. Petri and Koch dishes can be sterilized in an oven at 130 (± 2) °C for an hour or boiled in water for 40 min.
3. Analysis of germination is carried out on the seeds of the main crop, isolated during purity determination. For this, 400 seeds of 100 or 50 (for large-seeded crops) pieces are arbitrarily counted in each repetition. The seeds are evenly placed on a moistened substrate.

The conditions that are mandatory (substrate, temperature) for the analysis, as well as additional instructions for breaking seed dormancy are given in Table 18.

Table 18. Wheat: similarity analysis conditions

Crops	Substrate	T in °C \pm 2 °C	Accounting periods, days		Additional conditions for overcoming seed dormancy
			first	final	
Soft and hard wheat <i>Triticum aestivum</i> L.	on the sand, in the sand, on the paper, in the paper (between the paper)	20	4	8	Pre-cooling, pre-heating (30-35 °C); lighting

4. According to the table, the mode that is most acceptable should be chosen according to the availability of the laboratory, taking into account the condition of the seeds and the crop. It is recommended to give preference to the regime of variable temperatures, as biologically more natural.
5. During the analysis, filter paper (F) and sand (S) are used. Filter paper as a substrate is used in two ways: "on paper" and "in paper". To moisten the paper, immerse it in water, take it out and let the excess water drain (when pressing with a finger, a water film does not form around it). During the "on paper" analysis, seeds are spread on one or more layers of moistened paper placed in Petri dishes. Cover Petri dishes with lids. During the "in paper" analysis, seeds are spread horizontally or vertically between two layers of moistened paper with the germs down. The device with seeds prepared in this way is placed in a thermostat. Sand as a substrate for germinating seeds (sifted through a sieve with holes with a diameter of 1 mm, washed, roasted) is used according to the following options: "on sand" - seeds are pressed into the surface of the sand to their

thickness (diameter); or "in the sand" - the seed laid out on the bed is covered with a layer of sand 1-2 cm thick, leaving it loose.

6. Seeds of corn, sunflower, and other large-seeded crops are placed with the embryo down. Before analysis, the sand is moistened to 60% of its full moisture content. The moisture content (B) is determined in a metal cylinder 30 cm high, 8 cm in diameter, with a mesh bottom. A circle of moistened filter paper is placed on the bottom of the cylinder and weighed (T). The cylinder is filled 3/4 with fresh baked sand, weighed again (T₁) and placed in a vessel with water so that it is at the level of the sand. When the water wets the surface of the sand, the cylinder is removed from the vessel, excess water is allowed to drain, the walls are dried on the outside with filter paper and weighed (T₂). The moisture content of sand (in cm³ per 100 g) is calculated by the formula:

$$B = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 - T} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

7. After the analysis, the sand is washed, dried, sieved, roasted and stored for reuse.

8. The seeds are laid out in prepared nurseries using a spreader counter or manually using a marker, after which they are wrapped and smoothed with a rammer.

9. The filter paper is moistened with a 0.005% solution of gibberellic acid (50 mg per 1 dm³). During the entire period of germination, the is moistened with the same solution, which is stored in a refrigerator at a temperature of 8-10 °C.

10. During the analysis of freshly collected seeds with an incomplete period of physiological maturation, measures are taken to overcome the state of dormancy, namely: pre-cooling, warming, washing, treatment of the bed with chemicals, etc.

10.1. Pre-cooling. Seeds sown on a wet substrate are kept at a temperature of 5-10 °C for the time provided for the first accounting of seedlings (germination energy), after which they are transferred to the temperature conditions provided for this crop. The period of pre-cooling is not included in the term of determination of similarity, but its duration and temperature must be noted in the document; the first accounting (germination energy) is carried out two days after the end of preliminary cooling. If necessary, pre-cooling is repeated or its term is extended.

10.2. Preheating. The seeds are warmed for 7 days at a temperature of 30-40 °C. If necessary, the duration of heating is extended. Freshly harvested corn seeds with a moisture content of 30% and less before germination are dried in a cabinet at a temperature of 36 (± 2) °C in open greenhouses (in a layer of one

grain) for 24 h, and with a moisture content of more than 30% - for 48 h. Then they germinate on sand, observing the technical conditions adopted for corn.

10.3. To remove dormancy, seeds are illuminated (O) for 8 h every day with an intensity of 750-1250 lx (250 lx is enough for seeds that are not in a state of rest). During germination in the regime of variable temperatures, illumination is given during the period of application of high temperature.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 2,3,5-triphenyltetrazolium chloride (-bromide)
- Cotton wool is hygroscopic
- Distilled water
- Drinking water
- Glucose crystalline hydrate
- Potassium nitrate
- Potassium permanganate according to GOST 20490
- Sulfuric acid according to GOST 2184 or GOST 4204
- Succinic acid according to GOST 6341
- Measuring flask (500 cm³)
- Filter paper
- Quartz sand (particle size 0.5-2 mm)
- 96% Ethyl alcohol
- Adhesive transparent tape
- A cup with a capacity of 500 cm³
- Petri and Koch cup

Equipment:

- Apparatus for germinating seeds in the light (Jacobsen type)
- Dial scales with a weighing limit of at least 2 kg
- Fluorescent lamp
- Counter-decomposer of seeds
- Lux meter
- Furnace for calcination of sand
- Heating thermostat ($t = 20-40 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)
- Cooling and heating thermostat ($t = 0-40 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)
- Laboratory drying cabinet ($t = 50-150 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)
- Small inventory:
- Dissecting needles

- Substrate humidifiers (dropper, watering can, pipette)
- Measuring ruler
- Markers for sand
- A set of grain scoops (type ShNL-1)
- Tweezers according to GOST 21241
- Dishes for washing and moistening the substrate
- Planters (faience, plastic, polystyrene)
- Sieves for sieving sand
- Glass
- Laboratory scoops, thermometers (t = 0-50 °C)
- Rammers
- A metal cylinder with a mesh bottom, 30 cm high and 8 cm in diameter

CALCULATIONS

The moisture content of sand (in cm³ per 100 g) is calculated by the formula:

$$B = \frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 - T} \cdot 100$$

During the first accounting, normally germinated seeds are separately evaluated and taken into account, as well as seeds with pronounced signs of anomalies and rotten ones. The last two groups are removed, and normally germinated ones are removed if necessary.

The term of the final accounting is allowed to be extended up to 3 days, and if necessary, more, to allow germination of healthy ungerminated seeds, or shortened if the picture is understood ahead of time.

The results obtained during the similarity analysis are expressed as percentages for each of the identified categories (normal and abnormal seedlings, germinated and ungerminated seeds, in particular hard, dead, rotten). The reliability of the analysis is established by comparing the extreme values of the repetitions with the arithmetic mean. The result is considered reliable if the difference between them and the arithmetic mean value, which is calculated to a whole number, does not exceed the maximum permissible deviations.

REFERENCES

DSTU 4138-2002. Seeds of Agricultural Crops. Methods of Determining Quality.

2.9.8. Moisture content

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the analysis is to determine the content of free moisture in the seeds.

PROCEDURE

1. *Number of determinations.* Separate determinations are carried out on two test portions taken from the laboratory sample. If the absolute difference between the two values obtained is greater than the repeatability limit, the determination is repeated until requirements are satisfied.
2. *Test portion.* 5 ± 1 g of the laboratory is rapidly weighed, to the nearest 0.001 g, in the metal dish. The mass of the undried test portion is recorded and named “ m'_0 ”. This dish is previously dried and tarred, together with its lid, and record the mass is recorded and named “ m_d ” to the nearest 0.001 g.
3. *Drying.* The open dish containing the test portion (2), together with the lid is placed in the oven and left for 120 ± 5 min (90 min for flours). In certain cases, and particularly in hot-air dry countries, the drying period may be reduced to 60 ± 5 min, which is sufficient time for the test portions to attain constant mass. These times must be controlled regularly. The door of the oven can't be opened during drying and moist products can't be placed in the oven before removing the dry test portions, as this would result in partial rehydration of the latter. After drying, the dish is quickly removed from the oven, covered, and placed in the desiccator.
4. *Weighing.* When the dish has cooled to laboratory temperature (generally between 30 min and 45 min after it has been placed in the desiccator), is weighed to the nearest 0.001 g. The mass of the dried test portion is recorded and named as “ m_1 ”

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Analytical balance (accuracy ± 0.001 g).
- Grinding mill
- Metal dish
- Constant-temperature oven
- Desiccator

CALCULATIONS

Without preconditioning.

The moisture content, W_{H_2O} expressed in grams per 100 g of the product as received, is given by:

$$W_{H_2O} = \left(1 - \frac{m_1}{m_0}\right) \times 100$$

Where:

$m_0 = m'_0 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the test portion (2)

$m_1 = m'_1 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the test portion after drying (4).

With preconditioning.

The moisture content, W_{H_2O} , expressed in grams per 100 g of the product as received, is given by:

$$W_{H_2O} = \left[(m_0 - m_1) \frac{m_3}{m_0} + m_2 - m_3 \right] \times \frac{100}{m_2} = \left(1 - \frac{m_1 m_3}{m_0 m_2}\right) \times 100$$

Where:

$m_2 = m'_2 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the sample taken before preconditioning (2);

$m_3 = m_3 - m_d$ is the mass, in grams, of the preconditioned sample.

REFERENCES

State Standard of Ukraine DSTU ISO 712:2015(ISO 712:2009, IDT). Cereals and cereal products - Determination of moisture content - Reference method.

2.9.9. Nitrogen content in seeds

PRINCIPLE

This is a method for the determination of the nitrogen content of cereals, pulses and derived products, according to the Kjeldahl method, and a method for calculating the crude protein content.

A test portion is digested by sulfuric acid in the presence of a catalyst. The reaction products are made alkaline, and then distilled. The liberated ammonia is collected in a boric acid solution, which is titrated with a sulfuric acid solution, in order to determine the nitrogen content and calculate the crude protein content.

PROCEDURE

1. Test portion.

A mass of test sample is weighed, to the nearest 0.001 g, chosen on the basis of the assumed nitrogen content, so that the test portion contains between 0.005 g and 0.2 g of nitrogen and preferably more than 0.02 g.

2. Determination

2.1 Digestion. The test portion is transferred to the digestion flask. Then, the required number of catalyst tablets are added, containing 10 g of potassium sulphate, 0.30 g of copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate and 0.30 g of titanium oxide. In the end,

20 mL of sulfuric acid are added. The quantity of acid may be adjusted depending on the apparatus, but only after having made certain that this measure indeed leads to a recovery rate of 99.5% for acetanilide and 99.0% for tryptophan. It is mixed thoroughly to ensure complete wetting of the test portion. The flasks are placed in the digestion unit preheated to (420 ± 10) °C. After a minimum of 2 h of digestion, counted from the time when the temperature of the unit reaches again (420 ± 10) °C, it is left to cool down.

NOTE: It is advisable to add pumice stone or glass boiling rods as a boiling regulator and an antifoaming agent. The minimum digestion time shall be checked on that reference material with which it was most difficult to reach the recovery rate. The recommendations of the equipment manufacturer must be followed as far as evacuation of the vapours is concerned, because too strong a suction can result in a loss of nitrogen.

2.2 Distillation. Cautiously 50 mL of water are added to the cooled flask and left to cool down. Then, 50 mL of boric acid are transferred into the collecting flask and, for visual colourimetry or using an optical probe, at least 10 drops of coloured indicator. An excess of 5 mL of the sodium hydroxide solution is added to neutralize the quantity of sulfuric acid used. Then, the distillation is carried out.

2.3 Titration. The titration is carried out using the sulfuric acid solution, either continuously during the distillation or at the end of distillation on all of the distillate. The end-point determination is judged by visual colourimetry, or using an optical probe, or by potentiometric analysis with a pH measurement system.

3. Blank test

A blank test is performed with the reagents used in 2.1 to 2.3 but without the test sample (2).

NOTE: It is possible to replace the test sample with 1 g of sucrose.

4. Test with reference material (check test)

The reference material(s) used is dried at a temperature of between 60 °C and 80 °C, under vacuum, in the presence of di-phosphorus pentoxide. A check test is carried out on a test portion of a minimum of 0.15 g by determining the nitrogen content of the tryptophan and/or of the acetanilide. NOTE It is possible to add 1 g of sucrose to reference material. The nitrogen recovery rate from acetanilide shall be at least 99.5% and at least 99.0% from tryptophan.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- Nitrogen-free reagents of recognized analytical grade are only used, except for the reference materials, and distilled or demineralized water or water of equivalent purity.
- Kjeldahl tablets, corresponding to the following composition: copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate ($\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) = 2.8%, titanium oxide (TiO_2) = 2.8% and potassium sulphate (K_2SO_4) = 94.3%. Alternatively, copper (II) sulphate pentahydrate, titanium oxide and potassium sulphate may also be mixed in the corresponding ratio.
- Sulfuric acid, $c(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 18 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$, $\rho_{20}(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 1.84 \text{ g mL}^{-1}$.
- Antifoaming agent: Paraffin oil, silicone or even antifoam tablets may be used to prevent foaming.
- Acetanilide ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}$) or tryptophan ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$), of minimum assay 99% (mass fraction).
- Boric acid, aqueous solution, $\rho_{20}(\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3) = 40 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, or any other concentration recommended for the apparatus being used.
- Coloured indicator. Add volumes of Solution A and Solution B as recommended for the apparatus being used (for example: 5 volumes of Solution A and 1 volume of Solution B) or any other coloured indicator recommended for the apparatus.
- *NOTE 1.* It is possible to use a ready-to-use solution of boric acid containing the coloured indicator (8 and 9).
- *NOTE 2.* The ratio of Solutions A and B can be adjusted depending on the apparatus.
- The titration may also be carried out potentiometrically by the use of a pH electrode, which shall be checked every day.
- *Solution A:* Bromocresol green ($\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{Br}_4\text{O}_5\text{S}$): 200 mg, Ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$), with a volume fraction of 95%: quantity sufficient for 100 mL of solution.
- *Solution B:* Methyl red ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$): 200 mg. Ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$), with a volume fraction of 95%: quantity sufficient for 100 mL of solution.
- Sodium hydroxide, aqueous solution (NaOH), having a mass fraction of between 30% and 40%, with nitrogen content less than or equal to 0.001%. Technical grade sodium hydroxide may also be used when its nitrogen content is less than or equal to 0.001%.
- Sulfuric acid, standard volumetric solution, $c(\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4) = 0.05 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. The use of H_2SO_4 instead of HCl is recommended because H_2SO_4 does not have the tendency to produce bubbles in the connecting tubes.
- Ammonium sulphate, standard volumetric solution, $c(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.05 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$.
- Alternatively, a salt such as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{Fe}(\text{SO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be used.
- Pumice stone, granulated, washed in hydrochloric acid and ignited or glass boiling rods may be used to prevent bumping.
- Sucrose (optional), free from nitrogen.
- Diphosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5).

Equipment:

- Mechanical grinder.
- Sieve, with aperture size 0.8 mm.
- Analytical balance, capable of weighing to the nearest 0.001 g.
- Digestion, distillation and titration apparatus.

CALCULATIONS

Nitrogen content. The nitrogen content, w_N , expressed as a mass fraction of dry product, as a percentage (%), is obtained using Formula (1):

$$w_N = \frac{(V_1 - V_0) \times T \times 0.014 \times 100}{m} \times \frac{100}{100 - w_H} = \frac{140T(V_1 - V_0)}{m(100 - w_H)}$$

Where:

V_0 is the volume, in millilitres, of the sulfuric acid solution required for the blank test;
 V_1 is the volume, in millilitres, of the sulfuric acid solution required for the test portion;
 0.014 is the value, in grams, of the quantity of nitrogen equivalent to the use of 1 mL of a 0.5 mol L⁻¹ sulfuric acid solution;

T is the normality of the sulfuric acid solution used for the titration;

m is the mass, in grams, of the test portion;

w_H is the moisture content.

Express the result to two decimal places.

Crude protein content. The content of crude protein in a dry product is calculated by multiplying the value of the nitrogen content obtained during the determination by a conversion factor that depends on the type of cereal or legume used. The result is rounded to one decimal place. Note. Some conversion factors that are used for cereals are given in Table 19.

Table 19. Wheat: conversion coefficient of nitrogen content to protein content

Product	Coefficient of conversion of nitrogen to protein
Common wheat	5.7

REFERENCES

ISO 20483:2013(E) Cereals and pulses — Determination of the nitrogen content and calculation of the crude protein content — Kjeldahl method.

ISO 712 Cereals and cereal products — Determination of moisture content — Routine reference method.

ISO 6540 Maize — Determination of moisture content (on milled grains and on whole grains).

ISO 24557 Pulses — Determination of moisture content — Air-oven method.

2.9.10. Ash yield

PRINCIPLE

Method used for determining the ash yielded by cereals, pulses, and their milled products intended for human consumption. The source materials covered are:

- a) grains of cereals;
- b) flours and semolinas;
- c) milled products (bran and high bran content products, sharps);
- d) mixed cereal flours (mixes);
- e) cereal by-products other than milled products
- f) pulses and their by-products.

PROCEDURE

A test portion is incinerated until combustion of organic matter is complete, then the residue obtained is weighed. The residue obtained is flaky after incineration at 550 °C and vitrified after incineration at 900 °C.

In general, products containing salts (e.g., sodium chloride, pyrophosphate) shall be incinerated at 550 (± 10) °C.

Table 20 summarizes incineration temperatures according to product type.

Table 20. Incineration temperatures and product type

Product type	Incineration temperature	
Flours	(550 ±10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Semolinas	(550 ±10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Cereal grains	(550 ±10) °C	(900 ± 25) °C
Other milled products (e.g., bran, high bran content products, sharps)	(550 ±10) °C	
Mixed cereal products (mixes)	(550 ±10) °C	
Cereal by-products other than milled products	(550 ±10) °C	
Pulses and their by-products	(550 ±10) °C	

1. Determination of the moisture content

The moisture content of the test sample is determined beforehand in accordance with ISO 712 for cereals other than maize or ISO 6540 in the case of maize or ISO 24557 in the case of pulses.

2. The preparation of the ashing dishes

For ashing dishes suitable for use at 900 °C, the previously cleaned dishes are brought up to the incineration temperature being employed by being put in the muffle furnace for 5 min, being left to cool in the desiccator, and then being weighed to within 0.1 mg.

For ashing dishes suitable for use at 550 °C, the cleaned dishes are placed in an oven for the time required for drying (e.g., 90 min at 130 °C). Immediately before use, the dishes are removed from the oven and left to cool in a desiccator, then weighed to within 0.1 mg.

3. Preparation of the test portion

From the test sample carefully mixed, a test portion between 3.9 g and 4.1 g is rapidly weighed to within 0.1 mg in the case of incineration at 900 °C and between 4.9 g and 5.1 g in the case of incineration at 550 °C. In the case of low-density products, the test portion can be between 2 ± 0.1 g and 3 ± 0.1 g. In the ashing dish, prepared and weighed as described in 2, the product is spread out without packing it to form a uniform layer.

4. Pre-ashing

The ashing dish and its contents are placed at the entrance of the furnace brought up to the ashing temperature. At 900 °C, the products are burst into flame spontaneously. At 550 °C, they are necessary to be ignited with ethanol. For pre-ashing at 550 °C, it is permissible to put the dishes in the cold furnace and let the temperature of the furnace rise to the target temperature.

5. Ashing

The dish is placed inside the furnace once the product has finished burning. The furnace door is closed. The ashing continues until the combustion of the entire product, including the carbon particles contained in the residue, is complete, namely 1 h minimum at 900 °C, and 4 h minimum at 550 °C. In order to maintain the efficiency of the desiccator, dishes are not stacked. Once the ashing is completed, the dish is removed from the furnace and placed in the desiccator to cool. Due to the hygroscopic nature of the ash, as soon as the dish has reached ambient temperature (namely 15 min to 20 min for metallic dishes and 60 min to 90 min minimum for quartz or silica dishes), it is weighed rapidly to within 0.1 mg. For test portions incinerated at 550 °C, special precautions are taken to avoid flaky residues being swept away with the influx of air on opening the desiccator. The validity of the results obtained on this sample is checked with respect to the laboratory's self-inspection criteria (e.g., control chart).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagent:

- Hydrochloric acid, aqueous solution of one part by volume of HCl (35% volume fraction) and one part by volume of water.
- Purified diphosphorus pentoxide (P_4O_{10}).
- Ethanol.

Equipment:

- Grinding mill
- Ashing dish, of capacity not less than 20 mL, rectangular or round shape, flat-bottomed and having a surface area of not less than 12 cm². Suitable materials for the ashing dish which do not deteriorate under test conditions at the temperature of operation are:
 - at 900 °C — platinum or rhodium
 - at 550 °C — quartz or silica.
 - a. The dishes shall be cleaned by complete immersion for at least 1 h in hydrochloric acid, then rinsed with running water and then with distilled water.
 - b. After rinsing, the dishes shall be dried in an oven at a temperature and for a period sufficient to eliminate water.
- Electrically heated muffle furnace, with adequate ventilation, provided with temperature control system and a refractory coating which is not liable to lose particles at the ashing temperature, and capable of being maintained at 900 (± 25) °C or at 550 (± 10) °C.
- Vacuum desiccator, equipped with a perforated aluminium or porcelain plate, and diphosphorus pentoxide (5.2) as drying agent.
- Analytical balance, with an accuracy of 0.01 mg.
- Riffle splitter or cone-shaped divider.
- Oven for drying the ashing dishes.

CALCULATIONS

The ash yield, as a mass fraction on the dry matter basis expressed as a percentage, $w_{a,d}$, is given by Equation (1):

$$W_{a,d} = (m_2 - m_1) \times \frac{100}{m_0} \times \frac{100}{100 - w_m} \quad (1)$$

Where:

m_0 is the mass, in grams, of the test portion (3)

m_1 is the mass, in grams, of the ashing dish (2);

m_2 is the mass, in grams, of the ashing dish (2) and the incinerated residue (5);

w_m is the moisture content, as a percentage by mass, of the sample.

Take as a result the arithmetic mean of the two determinations if the repeatability conditions are fulfilled.

If needed, the ash yield, as mass fraction on the wet matter basis expressed as a percentage, $W_{a,w}$, is given by Equation (2):

$$W_{a,d} = (m_2 - m_1) \times \frac{100}{m_0}$$

REFERENCES

DSTU ISO 2171:2007 Cereals, pulses and by-products — Determination of ash yield by incineration.

2.9.11. Gluten manual method

PRINCIPLE

Knowing the quantity of gluten in wheat is crucial for various reasons. Firstly, it aids in catering to individuals with celiac disease or gluten sensitivity, as gluten can trigger adverse reactions in these populations. Accurate measurement ensures compliance with labelling regulations, facilitating informed dietary choices for those who must avoid gluten. Additionally, understanding gluten levels is essential for food processing and quality control, allowing manufacturers to adjust formulations to achieve desired product characteristics. Moreover, quantifying gluten content helps consumers make informed decisions about nutritional composition and supports research efforts aimed at developing wheat varieties suitable for specialized diets or food products. Overall, knowledge of gluten quantity in wheat promotes public health, food safety, and innovation in agriculture and food industries.

PROCEDURE

1. Test portion

1.1. 0.01 g of the sample is weighed and transferred quantitatively to the mortar vessel.

2. Dough preparation

2.1. Drop by drop, 5.5 mL of the sodium chloride solution is added from the burette while is continuously stirring the flour with the spatula.

2.2. After adding the sodium chloride solution, the mixture is compressed with the spatula and formed a dough ball, taking care to avoid loss of flour. Dough residues adhering to the wall of the vessel or to the spatula shall be collected with the dough ball.

2.3. To homogenise, the ball is rolled out to a length of 7 to 8 cm with the flat of the hand on the roughened glass plate, then is folded. During this operation the hands shall be covered with rubber gloves in order to protect the dough from warmth and perspiration from the hands.

2.4. This operation (point 2.3) is repeated five times.

3. Washing out.

This may be carried out by hand washing (3.1).

3.1. The operations described in 3.2 and 3.3 shall be carried out over the wooden frame covered with gauze (5:6) to avoid the possible loss of dough.

3.2. The dough ball is taken in the hand and allowed the sodium chloride solution to drip onto it from the container at a rate such that 750 mL flow in 8 min. During this time, successively the dough ball is rolled out, flattened, and stretched to make two pieces, then they are moulded together into one piece; these operations are repeated seven times.

3.3 The washing out time depends on the gluten content, but in general is about 8 min.

4. Verification of completeness of washing

The washing is considered to be complete when more sodium chloride solution pressed out from the gluten ball obtained as in contains only traces of starch. Use the iodine solution for detection of starch.

5. Removal of excess washing solution

5.1 Most of the washing solution adhering to the gluten ball is eliminated by being held between the fingers of one hand and compressed briefly three times.

5.2 The gluten ball is formed into a laminate shape and placed in the gluten press.

The gluten press is closed and re-opened after 5 s; the gluten leaf, without being deformed, is transferred to another dry spot in the press and pressed again. This operation is repeated 15 times; the glass plates of the gluten press are dried after each operation.

6. Determination of the mass of the wet gluten.

The pressed gluten is weighed to the nearest 0.01 g.

7. Number of determinations.

In the same test sample, two determinations are carried out.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Mortar vessel
- Sodium chloride

CALCULATIONS

The wet gluten, expressed as a percentage by mass of the original flour weight, is equal to

$$\text{Wet gluten content} = \frac{\text{total gluten (g)} \times 100}{10 \text{ (g)}} = \text{total gluten} \times 10$$

REMARKS

NOTE – Generally, the result of the determination is not referred to the dry matter content. The mean of the two determinations provided is taken to show that the requirement for repeatability was satisfied. Otherwise, a third determination must be done on the same test sample and the mean of the three determinations is taken as the result if the difference between the lowest and highest values obtained does not exceed 1% wet gluten. If the difference exceeds 1%, a fourth determination must be done on the same test sample and the mean of all four values obtained is taken as the result.

REFERENCES

ISO 712, Cereals and cereal products — Determination of moisture content — Routine reference method.
ISO 21415-1:2006, Wheat and wheat flour - Gluten content - Part 1: Determination of wet gluten by a manual method.

ISO 21415-2:2015 - Wheat and wheat flour - Gluten content - Part 2: Determination of wet gluten and gluten index by mechanical means.

2.9.12. Pest and Disease monitoring

PRINCIPLE

Typical pests of wheat can vary depending on the region and specific conditions. The most common pests that are known to affect wheat crops are:

- Wheat midge (*Sitodiplosis mosellana*): This small fly is a major pest of wheat, causing damage to the developing kernels. The larvae feed on the wheat kernels, resulting in yield losses.
- Hessian fly (*Mayetiola destructor*): Hessian fly larvae feed on the stem and leaf tissues of wheat plants, causing stunted growth and reduced yield.
- Wheat stem sawfly (*Cephus cinctus*): The larvae of wheat stem sawfly bore into the stems of wheat plants, weakening the stems and causing lodging.
- Aphids: Various species of aphids can infest wheat crops, such as the Russian wheat aphid (*Diuraphis noxia*) and the greenbug (*Schizaphis graminum*). Aphids suck sap from the plants, leading to stunted growth and transmission of viral diseases.
- Cutworms: Several species of cutworms, including armyworms and cutworms, can feed on young wheat plants, causing damage to the leaves and stems
- Cereal leaf beetle (*Oulema melanopus*): The larvae and adults of cereal leaf beetles feed on the leaves of wheat plants, leading to defoliation and reduced photosynthesis.

PROCEDURE

Monitoring methods may vary depending on the specific pest being targeted. It includes visual inspections, sticky traps, pheromone traps, and crop scouting. A threshold level must be determined to know when intervention is necessary. Thresholds are typically based on economic or damage levels, and they vary depending on the specific pest or disease being monitored. Keeping records of pest and disease monitoring activities is important for tracking trends, evaluating the effectiveness of control measures, and making informed decisions in future cropping seasons.

To sustainably manage pest techniques such as crop rotation, use of resistant varieties, cultural practices and biological controls can be done.

2.9.13. Carbohydrate composition

PRINCIPLE

Understanding the quantity of carbohydrates in wheat is essential for various reasons. Carbohydrates are a primary source of energy in the human diet, and wheat is a significant contributor to carbohydrate intake worldwide. By knowing the carbohydrate content of wheat, individuals can make informed dietary choices to meet their energy needs and maintain balanced nutrition. Additionally, for people managing conditions like diabetes or insulin resistance, monitoring carbohydrate intake is crucial for blood sugar control. Food manufacturers also rely on carbohydrate information to formulate products and meet labelling requirements, ensuring consumers have accurate information about the nutritional composition of wheat-based foods. Furthermore, researchers and policymakers use carbohydrate data to assess dietary patterns, conduct nutrition research, and develop dietary guidelines for promoting public health. Overall, knowing the quantity of carbohydrates in wheat supports informed food choices, dietary management, food labelling accuracy, and public health initiatives.

PROCEDURE

Plant Collection and Processing

After collecting plant samples, samples are flash-frozen by dipping plant material into liquid nitrogen with forceps and are stored at -80 °C. If the plant samples collected are too large to flash-freeze, the samples must be quickly cooled using dry ice and transferred to a -80 °C freezer as soon as possible.

Plant material is lyophilized using a freeze-dryer to ensure that the tissues are metabolically inactive while water is being removed. The sample is dried until the mass of the sample is stabilized to ensure all water has been removed.

Once samples are dry, they are grinded into a fine powder using a grinder or mill. The samples are stored in a desiccating cabinet until analysis.

Digestible Carbohydrate Assay

Sample Preparation

Each tissue replication is weighed out, approximately 20 mg each, and put into 15 mL glass tubes with rubber-lined screw caps (100 mm length). Tubes are labelled with a waterproof marker or with labelling tape on the lids and the exact mass of each sample is recorded, as this information will be required to calculate the % carbohydrates in each unknown sample.

Extract digestible carbohydrates from each sample:

1. 1 mL of 0.1 M H₂SO₄ is added to each tube and screwed caps onto tubes tightly. The tubes are placed in a boiling water bath for 1 h. CAUTION: Sulfuric acid is very corrosive. Please wear gloves, eye goggles, and an apron when handling H₂SO₄ and perform this step in a fume hood.
2. Tubes are cooled in a tepid water bath. Tube contents are poured into labelled 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes.
3. Tubes are centrifuged at 15,000 *g* for 10 min. The supernatant liquid is removed with a micro-pipettor and placed into new labelled 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes. Tubes can be refrigerated overnight at this point.

Mix standard solutions and quantify the total digestible carbohydrate content of samples.

1. First, D (+) glucose standard solutions with an appropriate range of concentration is prepared. Six glass tubes with 400 µL of each standard solution are also prepared.
2. 15 µL of each sample is pipetted into its own test tube and 385 µL of distilled water are added to each for a total volume of 400 µL in each test tube. In a fume hood, 400 µL of 5% phenol is added to each standard and sample test tube, and then 2 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ is quickly pipetted into each tube. The test tube contents must not be touched with the pipette tip, just added to the solution surface (a repeater pipette works best for this).
3. Tubes are incubated for 10 min, and then carefully vortexed to mix contents. The tubes are incubated for additional 30 min.

CAUTION: Phenol and sulfuric acid are corrosive irritants. To protect from exposure to skin, eyes, and inhalation, this step should be performed in a chemical fume hood using the proper PPE, which includes: face shield or eye goggles, rubber gloves, lab

apron, and boots. Mixing phenol with sulfuric acid also results in an exothermic reaction, which will result in the tubes becoming hot.

4. 800 μL of sample from each tube is pipetted into each of 3 polystyrene 1.5 mL semi-micro cuvettes (3 technical replicates per sample). The spectrophotometer is set up at 490 nm. The blank is calibrated using a cuvette containing distilled water before reading standards or unknown samples, and intermittently throughout sample readings. Each cuvette is run through a spectrophotometer and the absorbance is recorded. The average across technical replicates is done for each sample.

Note: In some cases, samples may surpass the upper absorbance threshold. If so, samples should be diluted. Dilutions must also be accounted for in subsequent calculations.

5. The average absorbance for each standard is calculated.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Liquid nitrogen
- 1 mL of 0.1 M H_2SO_4
- 15 mL glass tubes
- 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes.
- D-(+)-glucose standard solutions
- 5% phenol
- 3 polystyrene 1.5 mL semi-micro cuvettes

Equipment:

- Freeze-dryer
- Grinder
- Microcentrifuge
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

The standard curve is calculated by plotting the average absorbance against the total amount of D-(+)-glucose (μg) in each standard solution. A linear regression line is fit to these data, and then the following equation is used to calculate the total amount of carbohydrates (μg) in each sample: **$\text{Mc} = ((\text{Ax} - \text{b})/\text{m})/15) * 1000$** .

Where:

- Mc = μg of carbohydrates in sample;
- Ax = average absorbance of unknown sample;
- b = y-intercept (standard regression line);

- m = slope (standard regression line)

The correlation coefficient of this line should be greater than 0.98 and routinely near 0.99. Then, the following equation is used to determine the percentage of carbohydrates in each sample: **$P_c = ((M_c/1000)/M_i) * 100$** .

Where P_c = % carbohydrates and M_i = initial mass of sample (mg)

REMARKS

To calculate the amount of total digestible carbohydrates, present in each sample using the standard curve, it is easiest to regress the average absorbance of each standard against the micrograms of D-(+)-glucose present in each standard, but one can also plot the D-(+)-glucose concentration ($\mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$) of each standard if desirable. The calculations, however, refer to a standard curve based on micrograms, not concentrations ($\mu\text{g } \mu\text{L}^{-1}$).

REFERENCES

Deans, C.A., Sword, G.A., Lenhart, P.A., Burkness, E., Hutchison, W.D., & Behmer, S.T. (2018). Quantifying plant soluble protein and digestible carbohydrate content, using corn (*Zea mays*) as an exemplar. *JoVE (Journal of Visualized Experiments)*, 138, e58164.

2.9.14. Allelochemical composition

PRINCIPLE

Allelochemicals are specialized metabolites produced by plants that can influence the growth, development, or behaviour of other organisms. These compounds are involved in allelopathy, which is the ability of plants to release chemicals that affect the growth and survival of neighbouring plants or organisms.

PROCEDURE

Shoots and roots are harvested for and immediately freeze-dried. Freeze-dried wheat shoots or roots (0.1 g) are cut into 2-mm lengths, ground into powder with a mortar and pestle after the addition of liquid nitrogen, and macerated with 3 mL of 0.001 M HCl. The entire macerate is transferred to labelled glass scintillation vial and sonicated at 5 °C for 15 min. The resulting mixture is centrifuged at 20,000 rpm at 10 °C for 15 min to remove debris. The supernatant is collected and extracted three times with 10 mL portions of diethyl ether (GC grade, BDH Laboratory Supplies). The ether layers are combined and evaporated on a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 35 °C until the volume of residual solution is approximately 1 mL. The solution is dried with N_2 . Methanol (500 μL) is used to dissolve the remaining powder and to prepare the final vials for HPLC.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Mortar and pestle
- Liquid nitrogen
- 0.001 M HCl
- Falcon tubes (50 mL)
- Diethyl ether
- N₂
- Methanol
- Decantation funnel

Equipment:

- Sonicator
- HPLC-MS
- Centrifuge
- Rotavapor

REFERENCES

Wu, H., Haig, T., Pratley, J., Lemerle, D. & An, M. (2000). Distribution and exudation of allelochemicals in wheat *Triticum aestivum*. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, 26, 2141-2154.

2.9.15. Protein content

PRINCIPLE

The Bradford method is a colorimetric technique used for the **quantification of proteins**. This parameter is especially interesting when measuring the plant health and knowing whether a plant is encountering any abiotic or biotic stress factor, as one of the first detected responses is the synthesis of stress proteins when plant is under acclimation or protein degradation when is under senescence (Batista-Silva et al., 2019).

PROCEDURE

Bradford Reagent Preparation

1. 100 mg of Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye is weighed.
2. 50 mL 95% ethanol is added.
3. 100 mL 85% phosphoric acid is added slowly and carefully
4. All is mixed until the blue dye is completely dissolved.
5. The dye/ethanol/phosphoric acid solution is added to 850 mL pure sterile H₂O.
6. Any precipitates are filtered.

7. Bradford reagent can be stored at 4 °C for months.

Measuring Protein Standard

1. First, the spectrophotometer is warmed up.
2. Six different volumes are pipetted [0 μL (0 μg), 10 μL (5 μg), 20 μL (10 μg), 30 μL (15 μg), 40 μL (20 μg), 50 μL (25 μg)] of 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ BSA into separate cuvettes.
3. 1.5 mL of Bradford Reagent is added to each cuvette.
4. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film and mixed by gently inverting.
5. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 10 min.
6. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.

Measuring Unknown Quantity

1. Between 10 to 50 μL of the protein that is to be quantified are pipetted into a cuvette; a dilution may be necessary.
 - a. The goal is to get an absorbance reading that is in the middle of the standard curve.
 - b. An equal volume of 1 M NaOH can be added to help solubilize membrane proteins. When choosing this option, be sure to include NaOH in the standards.
2. 1.5 mL of Bradford Reagent is added to the cuvette.
3. The cuvettes are covered with plastic paraffin film and mixed by gently inverting.
4. The cuvettes are incubated at room temperature for 10 min.
5. The absorbance of each cuvette is measured at 595 nm.
 - a. If the absorbance does not fall within the range of the standard curve, the dilution of the sample must be changed and the absorbance measured again.

Standard Curve Generation

1. A scatter plot is made for the standard curve values.
2. The X-axis will be the micrograms (μg) of standard protein that were assayed; the Y-axis will be the measured Abs₅₉₅.
3. A linear trendline is fitted to the graph.
4. The linear regression equation is showed.
5. The unknown amount of protein is calculated by using the linear regression equation, as shown in the calculations section of this document.
6. The unknown concentration of the original protein solution can be calculated by dividing the amount of protein by the volume of protein assayed and multiplying the quotient by the dilution factor, as shown in the calculations section.

7. Alternatively, a curvilinear (polynomial) trendline can be fitted to the graph. This polynomial regression equation may sometimes give a better estimation of protein concentration.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 dye
- 95% ethanol
- 85% phosphoric acid
- 850 mL pure sterile H₂O
- NaOH
- Bovine serum albumin (BSA)

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. $\mu\text{g of protein} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - y \text{ intercept}}{\text{slope}}$
2. $\frac{\mu\text{g of protein}}{\mu\text{L assayed}} = \text{concentration assayed}$
3. $\text{Concentration assayed} \times \text{dilution factor} = \text{concentration of original solution}$

REFERENCES

Batista-Silva, W., Heinemann, B., Rugen, N., et al. (2019) The role of amino acid metabolism during abiotic stress release. *Plant, Cell and Environment*, 42, 1630–1644.

Bradford, M.M. (1976). A rapid sensitive method for the quantification of microgram quantities of protein utilising the principle of protein-dye binding. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 72, 248-254.

3. HORTICULTURAL

3.1. Aromatic plants

3.1.1. Alkaloid profile

PRINCIPLE

Method described the separation identification and quantitative assessment of major alkaloid compounds in dwarf periwinkle plant.

PROCEDURE

Extraction

1. Plant sample material (50 g) is ground.
2. Sieved sample (0.1-0.5 g) is extracted with 10 mL chloroform using a Sonication (3x10 min, at 25-30 °C).
3. The product is treated with mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid, filtered, and the pH adjusted between 8.0 and 9.0 with ammonia. Extracts are concentrated to dryness and diluted to 1 mL with methanol. Samples are stored at 4 °C until analysis by high performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometric analysis.
4. Alternatively, extraction can be carried out using 10 mL of pH 4.0 aqueous acetic acid. After, extraction extract is concentrated to dryness and diluted to 1 mL with methanol.

Standard Solutions

1. All standards must be prepared in the same solvent as the extract.
2. Solutions of 1 mg mL⁻¹ must be prepared and dilutions according to real concentrations must be prepared. For mass spectrometric identification 100 ng mL⁻¹ concentrations must be prepared ideally.

Measurement

1. The separations are achieved on a C18 packed column (5 µm, 4.6 x 250 mm). The mobile phase consisted of (A) 0.05 mol L⁻¹ ammonium acetate and (B) acetonitrile. The elution program is run using A and B solvents. The injection volume is 10 µL at a flow rate of 1 mL min⁻¹.
2. Detection is carried out using diode array detection and mass spectrometric detection in positive polarization mode.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Chloroform

- Acetonitrile (LCMS grade)
- Water (LCMS grade)
- Methanol (LCMS grade)
- Ammonium acetate
- *Vinca minor* alkaloid standards (vincamine, vincristine, vinblastine, vindoline, vinorelbine, vindesine)

Equipment:

- Ultrasonic bath
- Centrifuge
- Liquid-chromatograph and mass spectrometer

CALCULATIONS

Results must be evaluated by comparing spectra of recorded compounds to database or standard spectra and establishing calibration plot using UV absorbance.

REFERENCES

Boyadzhiev, L., Mecheva, D. & Yordanov, B. (2002). Extraction of vincamine from periwinkle (*Vinca minor* L.): I. Obtaining of total extract. *Comptes Rendus de l'Academie Bulgare des Sciences*, 55(12), 12-49.

Liu, J., Liu, Y., Pan, Y.J., Zu, Y.G. & Tang, Z.H. (2016). Determination of alkaloids in *Catharanthus roseus* and *Vinca minor* by high-performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry. *Analytical Letters*, 49(8), 1143-1153.

3.1.2. Crop measurement**PRINCIPLE**

Yield is calculated for each plot to compare the harvest of aromatic plants for the different treatments.

PROCEDURE

Method: Twice one-meter long randomly selected section is cut with a sickle in 10 cm (for *Rumex acetosa* L.) and 6 cm (for *Plantago lanceolata* L. and *Vinca minor* L.) height in every line. Altogether ten meters are collected. Wet weight of the crop is measured on spot.

Time and Frequency: three times during the vegetation period. May, July, and September for *R. acetosa* and *P. lanceolata*, and end of September for *V. minor*.

- Control plot
- Bee pasture plot
- Mulch plot

- Agricultural tissue plot

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

3.2. Cabbage

3.2.1. Dry matter content

PRINCIPLE

Knowing the dry matter content in cabbage is crucial because it helps determine its nutritional value, shelf life, and suitability for processing. It provides insight into the concentration of nutrients and influences factors like taste, texture, and cooking properties. Additionally, it aids in quality control during production and ensures consistency in food products utilizing cabbage as an ingredient.

PROCEDURE

A subsample of the harvest from each experimental plot is weighed, oven dried at 55 °C for 3 days or until it reaches a steady weight. The dry matter content is calculated based on the wet and dry weights.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance
- Drying oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Eurofins (2024). *Dry matter (DM)*. <https://www.eurofins-agro.com/en/dm>.

3.2.2. Total yield and marketable yield

PRINCIPLE

Total yield and marketable yield are measured for cabbage in each experimental plot for comparison.

PROCEDURE

1. Total yield: The weight of all cabbage heads without outer leaves is measured, including heads that are considered too small, or have been damaged, split or rotten.
2. Marketable yield: The weight of all cabbage heads considered to be marketable is measured.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

REFERENCES

Kleinhenz, M.D. (2003). A proposed tool for preharvest estimation of cabbage yield. *HortTechnology*, 13(1), 182-185. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTTECH.13.1.0182>

3.2.3. Cabbage head diameter

PRINCIPLE

To compare the size of cabbage heads from different treatment plots.

PROCEDURE

The head diameter is measured in the field with a measuring stick.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Measuring stick

REFERENCES

Radovich, T.J., Kleinhenz, M.D. & Honeck, N.J. (2004). Important cabbage head traits and their relationships at five points in development. *Journal of Vegetable Crop Production*, 10(2), 19-32. https://doi.org/10.1300/J068v10n02_03.

3.2.4. Cabbage head weight

PRINCIPLE

To compare the weight of cabbage heads from different treatment plots.

PROCEDURE

1. Loose leaves on the plant are removed and the head weighed.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

REFERENCES

Radovich, T.J., Kleinhenz, M.D. & Honeck, N.J. (2004). Important cabbage head traits and their relationships at five points in development. *Journal of Vegetable Crop Production*, 10(2), 19-32. https://doi.org/10.1300/J068v10n02_03.

3.3. Carrot

3.3.1. Dry matter content

PRINCIPLE

Understanding the dry matter content in carrots is essential as it indicates their overall quality, nutritional value, and suitability for various culinary and industrial applications.

PROCEDURE

A subsample of the harvest from each experimental plot is weighed, oven dried at 55°C for 3 days or until it reaches a steady weight. The dry matter content is calculated based on the wet and dry weights.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance
- Drying oven

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Dry matter content (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight (g)}}{\text{Wet weight (g)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Eurofins (2024). *Dry matter (DM)*. <https://www.eurofins-agro.com/en/dm>.

3.3.2. Root yield and marketable yield

PRINCIPLE

Root yield and marketable yield is measured for carrots in each experimental plot for comparison.

PROCEDURE

1. Root yield: The weight of all carrots harvested is measured, including roots that are considered too small or are damaged.
2. Marketable yield: The weight of all carrots determined to be marketable is measured.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

REFERENCES

Seljåsen, R., Lea, P., Torp, T., Riley, H., Berentsen, E., Thomsen, M. & Bengtsson, G.B. (2012). Effects of genotype, soil type, year and fertilisation on sensory and morphological attributes of carrots (*Daucus carota* L.). *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 92(8), 1786-1799. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.5548>

3.3.3. Root diameter and length

PRINCIPLE

To compare the size of the harvest from different experimental treatments.

PROCEDURE

A subsample of carrots from each experimental plot is measured for:

1. Root length, the length from the end of the root to the top is measured with a tape measure.
2. Root diameter, the diameter of the roots is measured across the middle of the root.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Tape measure

REFERENCES

D'Hooghe, P., Diaz, D., Brunel-Muguet, S., Davy, M., Vial, F., Dubois, J. & Kauffmann, F. (2018). Spatial variation of root yield within cultivated carrot fields is strongly impacted by plant spacing. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 241, 29-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2018.06.072>.

3.4. Lettuce, Melon, Tomato and Zucchini

3.4.1. Yield determination

PRINCIPLE

In order to assess the yield of a crop, measure different parameters related to fruit formation on the plant, i.e., from flowering to fruit ripening, are measured. These measurements are carried out on all crops except lettuce.

PROCEDURE

Yield measurements

The number of days between sowing and the appearance of the first flower (or the first male and female flower, depending on the species) is counted.

To assess fruit set, the number of flowers fruitless at the initial set (i.e., 15 days after full bloom) is counted. Selected main branches per plant (where possible, 4 branches, one per cardinal point) are used, and fruit set is calculated by the following equation (see 2.1.4) (Lo'ay et al., 2021).

The number of fruits per plant is counted. The yield of fresh fruit in terms of weight per plant (g plant^{-1}) is measured using a sensitive weight balance. At the end of harvesting, the total fruits weight is equalled to accumulate the total yield (t ha^{-1}) (Zhang et al., 2020).

Number of Leaves and Foliar Area

For lettuce, the number of leaves is counted, and one by one, its area is estimated by taking a photograph of the leaf and analysing it with image analysis software such as ImageJ, Image-Pro Plus, or *Digimizer*.

Fresh and dry weight, water content, relative water content and dry matter

For lettuce and other crops as appropriate, the leaves (for lettuce) or representative parts of the fruit (other crops) are weighed on a balance as soon as they are harvested to obtain the fresh weight of the sample (FW). Subsequently, the plant material is placed in paper envelopes and introduced into an oven at 70 °C for 3 days until the weight of the samples is constant (DW). Once the FW and DW values are obtained, the water content and dry matter content are calculated (Admane et al., 2023) (see calculation section). For the calculation of the relative water content (RWC), it is necessary to obtain the turgent weight (TW). This weight is obtained after placing the plant material in double-distilled water for at least 24 hours. Once obtained, the RWC is calculated (Erice et al., 2018).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ruler, tape measure, etc.
- Image analysis software
- Paper envelopes

Equipment:

- Balance
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

1. Fruit set (%) = $(\text{Number of fruitless} \div \text{Number of flowers}) \times 100$

2. Water content (WC) = $[(FW - DW) \div FW] \times 100$
3. Dry matter = $(DW \div FW) \times 100$
4. Relative water content (RWC) = $[(FW - DW) \div (TW - DW)] \times 100$

REFERENCES

- Admane, N., Cavallo, G., Hadjila, C., Cavalluzzi, M.M., Rotondo, N.P., Salerno, A., Cannillo, J., Difonzo, G., Caponio, F., Ippolito, A., Lentini, G. & Sanzani, S.M. (2023). Biostimulant formulations and *Moringa oleifera* extracts to improve yield, quality, and storability of hydroponic lettuce. *Molecules*, 28(1), 373.
- Erice, G., Pérez-Bueno, M.L., Pineda, M., Barón, M., Aroca, R. & Calvo-Polanco, M. (2018). Determining plant water relations. *Advances in Plant Ecophysiology Techniques*, pp. 109-134.
- Lo'ay, A.A., EL-Ezz, S.F.A. & Awadeen, A.A. (2021). Effect of different foliar potassium fertilization forms on vegetative growth, yield, and fruit quality of kaki trees grown in sandy soil. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 288, 110420.
- Zhang, C., Li, X., Yan, H., Ullah, I., Zuo, Z., Li, L. & Yu, J. (2020). Effects of irrigation quantity and biochar on soil physical properties, growth characteristics, yield and quality of greenhouse tomato. *Agricultural Water Management*, 241, 106263.

3.4.2. Physical traits of fruit quality

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of fruit dimensions, firmness or colour are some of the characteristics that allow us to evaluate the quality of the fruit from a morphological point of view.

PROCEDURE

Fruit dimensions

The equatorial and longitudinal diameters (cm) of harvested fruits are measured.

Firmness and peel thickness

The firmness is measured using a penetrometer with an 8 mm tip (Scarano et al., 2020). Additionally, fruits are cut along the equatorial area, and peel thickness is measured at three different points (Nissi et al., 2021).

Colour measurement

Colorimetric analysis is performed on the skin and flesh of harvested fruits. A colourimeter is used to obtain the colour space parameters (lightness, L; and chromaticity coordinates a and b) and then to calculate the colour index (CI) and HUE angle values (Pérez-Pérez et al., 2008; Ciriello et al., 2021).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ruler or tape measure

Equipment:

- Penetrometer
- Colourimeter

CALCULATIONS

1. $CI = a \times 10^3 \times (L \times b)^{-1}$
2. HUE angle = $\arctan(b \div a)$

REFERENCES

Ciriello, M., Formisano, L., Pannico, A., El-Nakhel, C., Fascella, G., Duri, L.G., Cristofano, F., Gentile, B.R., Giordano, M., Roupheal, Y., Fusco, G.M., Woodrow, P. & Carillo, P. (2021). Nutrient solution deprivation as a tool to improve hydroponics sustainability: Yield, physiological, and qualitative response of lettuce. *Agronomy*, 11(8), 1469.

Nissi, F.G., Lakshmi, M.L., Swami, D.V., Rajashekaram, T., Salomi, D.R. & Krishna, U.K. (2021). Effect of antitranspirants on growth and fruit parameters of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* (L.) Osbeck). *Pharma Innovation Journal*, 10(5), 577-581.

Pérez-Pérez, J.G., Romero, P., Navarro, J.M. & Botía, P. (2008). Response of sweet orange cv 'Lane late' to deficit-irrigation strategy in two rootstocks. II: Flowering, fruit growth, yield and fruit quality. *Irrigation Science*, 26(6), 519-529.

Scarano, A., Olivieri, F., Gerardi, C., Liso, M., Chiesa, M., Chieppa, M., Frusciante, L., Barone, A., Santino, A. & Rigano, M.M. (2020). Selection of tomato landraces with high fruit yield and nutritional quality under elevated temperatures. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 100(6), 2791-2799.

3.4.3. Acidity determination (pH and titratable acidity)

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of acidity is one of the main criteria indicating the freshness and composition of raw materials and perishable foods. Also, acidity is an important component of fruit quality. It influences the perception of acidity and sweetness. Acidity can be measured in various ways, such as pH determination or titratable acidity. Both parameters have a different signification: pH represents the free hydrogen ion activity (active acidity), while titratable acidity is the amount of weakly bound hydrogen ions that can be released from the acids (total acidity) (Lobit et al., 2002).

PROCEDURE

The liquid extract obtained from the mesocarp of each fruit (tomato, zucchini, melon, peach, orange, and persimmon) is liquefied and filtered.

pH Determination

1. The juice is put into a glass.
2. A pH strip is inserted, and the result is read.

- The pH can also be measured with a pH meter. The probe is inserted into the juice, and the pH value is waited to be read.

Titrateable Acidity Determination

- A burette is filled with 1 M NaOH solution.
- 10 mL of juice is put into an Erlenmeyer flask.
- A few drops of phenolphthalein are added to the juice.
- The NaOH solution is incorporated dropwise over the juice, shaking.
- The process continues until the phenolphthalein turns colour. The burette is closed and the NaOH volume used is noted.
- The results are expressed as % of citric acid per 100 mL of juice.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material

- NaOH
- Phenolphthalein
- Erlenmeyer flask
- Burette
- Glass

Equipment

- pH meter

CALCULATIONS

- Citric acid concentration (M) = $\left[\frac{[NaOH\ Volume\ (L) \times NaOH\ Concentration\ (M)]}{3} \right] \times juice\ Volume\ (L)$
- Malic acid concentration (M) = $\left[\frac{[NaOH\ Volume\ (L) \times NaOH\ Concentration\ (M)]}{2} \right] \times juice\ Volume\ (L)$

REMARKS

- Considering the stoichiometry of the reaction, 1 mole of citric acid reacts with 3 moles of NaOH:

$$C_6H_8O_7 + 3NaOH = Na_3C_6H_5O_7 + 3H_2O$$
- Considering the stoichiometry of the reaction, 1 mole of malic acid reacts with 2 moles of NaOH:

$$C_4H_6O_5 + 2NaOH = Na_2C_4H_4O_5 + 2H_2O$$
- To calculate the % of acid in 100 mL of juice, consider the molecular weight of the acid and its density.

REFERENCES

Lobit, P., Soing, P., Génard, M. & Habib, R. (2002). Theoretical analysis of relationships between composition, pH, and titratable acidity of peach fruit. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 25(12), 2775-2792.

3.4.4. Antioxidant Capacity (DPPH radical scavenging method)

PRINCIPLE

Free radicals are known to indicate oxidative damage to biomolecules, which can lead to serious pathologies or diseases in humans. Various studies indicate that a diet rich in fruit and vegetables is effective against oxidative damage (Pyrzynska and Pękal, 2013). As these foods are a rich source of antioxidant molecules, the concept of antioxidant capacity arises, including the synergic and redox interactions between the different molecules present in the food (Pellegrini et al., 2018). For this reason, the application of tests to measure the effectiveness of antioxidants in food systems and human metabolism has increased concurrently. Numerous bioanalytical techniques are available now to quantify the antioxidant impact on foods. Of these, the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazil (DPPH) removing assay is the most widely used, well-liked, and potentially effective technique for assessing antioxidant capacity among them (Gulcin and Alwasel, 2023). Here is presented a modification of Magalhães et al. (2006).

PROCEDURE

1. Aliquots of the extract ranging from 5 μL to 120 μL are diluted to a volume of 10 mL.
2. 100 μL of the diluted extract is mixed with 1.5 mL aqueous methanolic solution (82%) of DPPH radical in plastic tubes (2 mL).
3. The macro-cuvettes are covered, shaken, and kept in the dark for 1 h. Then, the absorbance is measured at 517 nm (A_{sample}).
4. The absorbance of the DPPH radical without antioxidant is used as the control (A_{control}).
5. The percentage of scavenging of DPPH radical is calculated according to the formula (see calculations).
6. The spectrophotometer is zeroed using methanol.
7. Caffeic acid (0.8-6.3 ppm) or ascorbic acid is used for comparison.
8. The molar concentration of DPPH is calculated using the literature value of 12.509 $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ for molar absorptivity.
9. TEAC (Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity) is determined as the amount of Trolox equivalent to the amount of the test substance that results in 50% scavenging of DPPH radical.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Aqueous methanolic solution (82%) of 2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH): 32 mg of DPPH diluted in 1 L.
- Caffeic acid
- Ascorbic acid
- Plastic tubes
- Macro-cuvettes

Equipment:

- Shaker
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

$$1. \% \text{ Scavenging} = 100 \times (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) \div A_{\text{control}}$$

REMARKS

The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 minutes before starting to measure.

REFERENCES

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3.4.5. Non-enzymatic Antioxidants (Total Phenols and Flavonoids)

Flavonoids, together with other phenolic compounds, are molecules of special interest for their benefits on human health, as they possess multiple pharmacological activities related to their antioxidant capacity and their capacity to scavenge 'reactive oxygen species' (ROS) (Bautista et al., 2016). The determination of these molecules in fruits is carried out in the same way as explained in section 1.7, differentiating only the starting material.

Ascorbic Acid (AsA-DHA Assay)
PRINCIPLE

Ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) is a nutrient, mainly found in fruit and vegetables, essential for human diet with beneficial effects on health due to its primary defensive function of

free radical scavenger of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species. It is important to mention that humans cannot synthesise vitamin C, so we must incorporate it from food. Ascorbic acid is frequently added to processed foods including fruit and vegetables as an antioxidant and anti-browning agent, either for fortification or enrichment purposes or to prevent oxidation of other nutrients (such as phenolic compounds) (Ruiz et al., 2016). Ascorbic acid can be oxidised to form dehydroascorbic acid, which possesses *in vivo* vitamin C activity, as it can be reduced back in the human body to ascorbic acid. Therefore, the measurement of both, ascorbic acid and its oxidised form, is important to assess the total amount of vitamin C in a food product (Ruiz et al., 2016). We present two methods for the quantification of vitamin C, one by spectrophotometry based on the method of Desai and Desai (2019) and the other by HPLC based on the method of Chebrolu et al. (2012).

PROCEDURE

Spectrophotometric determination

1. 0.1 – 1 g fresh material is ground and mixed with 4 mL of cold 2% HPO_3 (containing 2 mM EDTA).
2. The pH is adjusted to approximately 5.0 by adding 2 mL of 10% sodium citrate (containing 2 mM EDTA).
3. The mixture is centrifuged at 4,000 *g* for 7 min, and the supernatant is collected for the assay.
4. In a quartz spectrophotometer cuvette, a final volume of 1 mL is added containing: 50 μmol of sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 2 μmol of EDTA, 0.5 μmol of β -mercaptoethanol, 50 μL (containing approximately 35 μg of protein) of ascorbic acid, and sufficient tissue extract (10 – 100 μL) to give an absorbance of between 0.5 – 1 at 265 nm.
5. The initial absorbance is recorded, and then the reaction is initiated by the addition of 5 μL of 50 mM H_2O_2 .
6. The absorbance decreases until a final constant value is reached.

HPLC determination

1. The plant sample is liquidated.
2. 0.9 mL of the liquid is mixed with 0.9 mL of 6% metaphosphoric acid.
3. The mixture is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
4. The sample is diluted with distilled water if necessary and mixed with a vortex.
5. The mixture is centrifuged again at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
6. The supernatant is filtered with 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters directly into the amber HPLC vial.
7. The sample is spiked in the HPLC to determine the ascorbic acid content.

8. For the determination of dehydroascorbic acid, an aliquot from step 6 is taken, and the reducing agent (TCEP (Tris (2-carboxy ethyl) phosphine hydrochloride) at a concentration of 5 mmol L⁻¹) is added in a 1:1 ratio. It is allowed to react for at least 30 minutes at room temperature and subsequently spiked on HPLC to calculate the amount of total ascorbic acid.
9. An external calibration line is used to convert the HPLC data (given in area units) to a known concentration. A concentrated stock solution is prepared, and then serial dilutions are made. The values of the sample must be within the range of the calibration curve for accurate quantification.
10. HPLC conditions:
 - Column: Teknokroma BRISA LC2 LC2 C18 3 μm, 150 x 4.6 mm
 - Chromatographic conditions: injection 5 μL, flow rate 1 mL min⁻¹, λ = 254 nm, time 15 min. Ascorbic acid migrates over 2.3 min.
 - Mobile phase: 5:95 v/v methanol: water with 1% acetic acid.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material for spectrophotometric determination:

- Metaphosphoric acid (HPO₃)
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)
- Sodium Citrate
- Sodium Phosphate buffer (pH 7.0)
- β-mercaptoethanol
- Ascorbic acid
- Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂)

Material for HPLC determination:

- Metaphosphoric acid (HPO₃)
- Double-distilled water
- Methanol
- Acetic acid
- Ascorbic acid
- Tris (2-carboxy ethyl) phosphine hydrochloride (TCEP)
- 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters
- Amber HPLC vials

Equipment:

- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer

- HPLC

CALCULATIONS

1. The ascorbic acid content is calculated from the difference between the initial and final absorbance readings and the millimolar extinction coefficient for ascorbate at pH 7.0 determined with a standard solution of ascorbic acid ($14.1 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).
2. For HPLC, the levels of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid are calculated using the regression equation obtained from the calibration

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- For HPLC, it is taken into account that the higher the amount of ascorbic acid in the sample, the higher the dilution that has to be made.

REFERENCES

Chebrolu, K.K., Jayaprakasha, G.K., Yoo, K.S., Jifon, J.L. & Patil, B.S. (2012). An improved sample preparation method for quantification of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid by HPLC. *LWT*, 47(2), 443-449.

Ruiz, B.G., Roux, S., Courtois, F. & Bonazzi, C. (2016). Spectrophotometric method for fast quantification of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid in simple matrix for kinetics measurements. *Food Chemistry*, 211, 583-589.

Desai, AP. & Desai, S. (2019). UV spectroscopic method for determination of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content in different fruits in South Gujarat region. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Natural Resources*, 21(1), 0041-044.

3.4.6. Carotenoid content

PRINCIPLE

Carotenes are pigments which, in addition to being indicators of plant health, are of great importance to humans, as many of these molecules are precursors in the biosynthesis of vitamin A, as well as functioning as antioxidant molecules (Hermanns et al., 2020), and are therefore an indicator of quality in many foodstuffs. The protocol explained here is that of Hornero-Méndez and Mínguez-Mosquera (2001), with some modifications. The method makes it possible to differentiate carotenoids into two groups: red carotenoids (capsanthin and capsorubin) and yellow carotenoids (zeaxanthin and beta-carotene, among others). However, the method is optimised for the detection of pepper carotenoids, previous studies have shown that this method could also be reliable for determining carotenoid concentrations of other vegetables or fruits, after removing potentially interfering chlorophylls (Biehler et al., 2010).

PROCEDURE

1. 0.1 g of dry material is placed in a 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask.
2. 20 mL of acetone is added.
3. The flask is covered with parafilm.
4. The flask is shaken for 1 h.
5. The contents of the Erlenmeyer flask are filtered under vacuum with filter paper, wetting the paper with acetone, and transferring little by little.
6. The filtered liquid is transferred into a 25 mL volumetric flask.
7. The volume is made up to the mark with acetone.
8. Acetone is used as a blank.
9. The absorbances are read at 472 nm and 508 nm.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Acetone

Equipment:

- 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask
- Parafilm
- Vacuum
- Filter paper
- Volumetric flask
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. *Red Carotenoids* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(A_{508} \times 2144 - A_{472} \times 403.3) \div 270.9$
2. *Yellow Carotenoids* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(A_{472} \times 1724.3 - A_{508} \times 2450.1) \div 270.9$

REMARKS

- Note the exact weight of dry material used.
- Turn on the spectrophotometer at least 30 minutes before starting to measure.

REFERENCES

Biehler, E., Mayer, F., Hoffmann, L., Krause, E. & Bohn, T. (2010). Comparison of 3 spectrophotometric methods for carotenoid determination in frequently consumed fruits and vegetables. *Journal of Food Science*, 75(1), C55-C61.

Hermanns, A.S., Zhou, X., Xu, Q., Tadmor, Y. & Li, L. (2020). Carotenoid pigment accumulation in horticultural plants. *Horticultural Plant Journal*, 6(6), 343-360.

Hornero-Méndez, D. & Mínguez-Mosquera, M.I. (2001). Rapid spectrophotometric determination of red and yellow isochromic carotenoid fractions in paprika and red pepper oleoresins. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 49(8), 3584-3588.

3.4.7. Sugars determination

PRINCIPLE

The quality of food products is an abstract concept that depends on the needs of the consumer and the product to be consumed (Cantín et al., 2009). Among the most remarkable in many fruits and vegetables is the sweetness, which is determined by the different proportion of soluble sugars present in the consumed plant organ. The main sugars present in fruits and vegetables are sucrose, fructose and glucose, although depending on the species, other major sugars may be present and the proportion of them also varies, and even within the state of ripeness (Ma et al., 2015; Bertín and Génard, 2018; Kyriacou et al., 2018).

These sugars can be measured in total, by destructive techniques (see section 1.9) or non-destructive techniques such as near infrared reflectance (NIR) spectroscopy (Flores et al., 2008), or the concentration of each sugar individually by HPLC.

PROCEDURE

Total Soluble Solids (TSS)

1. Juice is obtained from the fruit to be analysed.
2. A few drops of the juice are taken and dropped into a hand-held refractometer.
3. The results are expressed as °Brix (g of sucrose in 100 g of solution).

HPLC quantification of sugars

- **Sugar extraction**

1. The juice or liquefied plant material is extracted. It can be stored at -80 °C until processing.
2. The samples are thawed in the dark, preferably in the fridge. Once thawed, they are centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
3. The sample is diluted with distilled water. Depending on the species to be analysed, the dilution will be greater or lesser (the more sugars, the greater the dilution).
4. The diluted samples are shaken with a vortex.
5. They are centrifuged again at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
6. The supernatant is filtered with 0.22 µm PVDF syringe filters directly into the amber HPLC vial.

- **External calibration line**

1. To convert the HPLC data (given in area units) to a known concentration, a calibration line is needed. In this case, three lines are needed, one for fructose, one for glucose,

and one for sucrose. If any additional sugars are to be analysed, another line will be necessary.

2. A concentrated stock solution is prepared, and then serial dilutions are made. In this case, the standard is weighed, the weight is noted, and diluted with pure water. An example of stock solutions:

- Fructose: 400 mg in 10 mL, purity 99%.
- Glucose: 400 mg in 10 mL, purity 99.5%.
- Sucrose: 100 mg in 5 mL, purity 99.5%.

3. For calibration, the most concentrated point takes 0.5 mL of each stock solution, and 0.5 mL of pure water. That is, starting with a $\frac{1}{4}$ dilution of the stock solution, and then making serial dilutions 4 times.

- **HPLC Analysis**

1. Column: Phenomenex Luna Omega Sugar, 150 mm, 4.6 mm, 3 μm .
2. Chromatographic conditions: injection 10 μL , flow 0.8 mL min^{-1} , time 15 min.
3. Mobile phase: 75:25 v/v acetonitrile:water.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Acetonitrile
- Distilled water
- Fructose
- Glucose
- Sucrose

Equipment:

- Refractometer
- Centrifuge
- Vortex
- 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters
- Amber HPLC vials
- HPLC column

CALCULATIONS

- The HPLC data, such as the retention time of the peak in question and the area units for that peak, are obtained. Subsequently, the concentrations of each sugar are calculated using the calibration lines.

REMARKS

- This is only an example of a protocol, which can be modified depending on the species to be analysed.
- It is important to have the fresh weight (or dry weight) value of the starting material.
- The processing of the plant material may vary depending on the species.
- Depending on the quantity of sugars in the plant material, the homogenate will have to be diluted.
- The type of column shown is only an example. Depending on the HPLC model, or sugars to be determined, this may vary.

REFERENCES

- Bertin, N. & Génard, M. (2018). Tomato quality as influenced by preharvest factors. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 233, 264-276.
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4. PERENNIAL

4.1. Almond

4.1.1. Moisture

PRINCIPLE

Like other factors of crop quality (i.e., protein, ash, falling number) the moisture is also greatly influenced by the growing and harvesting conditions (Koubouris et al., 2009). The moisture of olive, almond, grains and legumes is a fundamental aspect that indicates the maturation and can be used to point the moment of the harvest. The moisture is the loss in weight, expressed as a percentage, of a product as a result of evaporation in the oven at a defined temperature. This product is dried in a thermostatic oven at 60 °C and atmospheric pressure until a constant weight is obtained.

PROCEDURE

- Almonds are grinded with a grinder until a homogeneous paste is formed.
- 5 g of almond paste are weighed. It is important to write down the exact weight.
- The tray with the almond paste is introduced in an oven at 60 °C until constant weight.
- The almond paste is reweighed when constant weight is reached.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Aluminium tray
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Oven
- Spatula
- Grinder

CALCULATIONS

The percentage of moisture in the olive or almond is calculated with the equation:

$$\%H = \frac{M_T - M_{dry}}{M_T} \times 100$$

Where,

M_T is the weight of olive or almond past at room temperature.

M_{dry} is the weight of dry olive or almond past.

REFERENCES

Massantini, R. & Frangipane, M.T. (2022). Progress in almond quality and sensory assessment: an overview. *Agriculture*, 12, 710. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture12050710>.

4.2. Apple

4.2.1. Yield

PROCEDURE

Yield amount from each tree (kg)

4.3. Apricot

4.3.1. Fruit characteristics

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of fruit dimensions, firmness or colour are some of the characteristics that allow us to evaluate the quality of the fruit from a morphological point of view.

PROCEDURE

Fruit width (mm):

Fruit width is determined in mm by measuring with a digital calliper with a sensitivity of 0.01 mm in 3 groups of 20 randomly selected fruits.

Fruit length (mm):

Fruit size is determined in mm by measuring with a digital calliper with 0.01 mm sensitivity in 3 groups of 20 randomly picked fruits.

Fruit weight (g):

It is determined in g by weighing on a scale sensitive to 0.01 g in 3 groups of 20 fruits taken randomly.

Fruit external colour:

Fruit external colour (Minolta CR 300, Osoka, Japan) is determined with a colour measuring device. In 3 groups of 20 fruits, the external colour of the fruit is determined from centre of the fruit (equatorial region) as two-way L*, "Chroma" (C), and "Hue" (h°) (McGuire, 1992; Sacks and Shaw, 1994). L* is the change in the brightness of the colour. "Chroma" (C); is the colour density. $C = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$. "Hue" (h°); is the colour angle value. 0 is red-violet, 90 is yellow, 180 is bluish green, 270 is blue ($h^\circ = \tan^{-1} \frac{b}{a}$)

Fruit firmness:

Fruit firmness is determined in kg by measuring 20 randomly selected fruits in 3 groups, by penetrometer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Calliper
- Balance
- Minolta CR 300
- Penetrometer

REFERENCES

Haffner, K. & Vestheim, S. (1996, April). Fruit quality of strawberry cultivars. In *III International Strawberry Symposium 439* (pp. 325-332).

McGuire, R.G. (1992). Reporting of objective colour measurements. *HortScience*, 27(12), 1254-1255.

Sacks, E.J. & Shaw, D.V. (1994). Optimum allocation of objective colour measurements for evaluating fresh strawberries. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 119(2), 330-334.

4.3.2. pH determination

PRINCIPLE

The pH indicates the acidity or alkalinity of a food or beverage. The pH-meter measures this acidity based on the potential difference between a reference electrode (such as calomel or Ag/AgCl) and a pH electrode (glass electrode). This difference is then related to the concentration of H⁺ ions in the solution, corresponding to the acidity of the solution.

PROCEDURE

The juices of each genotype are determined by reading with a pH meter under laboratory conditions.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- pH-meter

4.3.3. Titratable acid ratio (%):

PRINCIPLE

Titratable acidity refers to the total amount of acid in a solution and is commonly used to measure the acidity of fruits, including apricots. Apricots contain organic acids such as malic acid, quinic acid, citric acid, tartaric acid, oxalic acid, and fumaric acid. The dominant organic acids in ripened apricots are malic acid, quinic acid, and citric acid. The titratable acidity of apricots can vary depending on the cultivar and growing conditions

PROCEDURE

For the amount of titratable acid, 10 mL of fruit juice is taken and made up to 100 mL with distilled water and titrated with 0.1 N NaOH until the pH reaches 8.10 and calculated as malic acid with the help of the following formula (Haffner and Vestrheim, 1997).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- pH-meter

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Acid Amount (\%)} = \frac{\text{NaOH factor} \times \text{Amount of NaOH consumed} \times \text{Acidity constant}}{\text{Amount of juice taken (ml)}} \times 100$$

REFERENCES

Razouk, R., Kajji, A., Hamdani, A., Charafi, J., Hssaini, L., Bouda, S. (2021). Yield and fruit quality of almond, peach and plum under regulated deficit irrigation. *Frontiers in Agricultural Science and Engineering*, 8(4), 583–593 <https://doi.org/10.15302/J-FASE-2020325>.

4.3.4. Soluble Solid Content

PRINCIPLE

The soluble solid content in apricots refers to the concentration of dissolved solids, such as sugars and organic compounds, in the fruit.

PROCEDURE

SS is determined using a handheld refractometer (Westover Model RHB-32; Southwest United Industries, Tulsa, OK, USA). Results are reported in percent SS (w/w) on a fresh weight (FW) basis.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Refractometer

REFERENCES

Torres, I., Sánchez, M.-T. & Pérez-Marín, D. (2020). Integrated soluble solid and nitrate content assessment of spinach plants using portable NIRS sensors along the supply chain. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 168, 111273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2020.111273>.

4.3.5. Total phenolic content (TPC)

PRINCIPLE

Measuring the total phenolic content in apricots is important for assessing their nutritional value, antioxidant capacity, fruit quality, breeding programs, and research and development purposes. It helps in understanding the health benefits and potential applications of apricots and their phenolic compounds.

PROCEDURE

TPC content is measured according to the Singleton and Rossi (1965) procedure. Fruit samples are extracted with buffer containing acetone, water, and acetic acid (70:29.5:0.5 v/v) for 1 h in room conditions the dark. Three parallel extracts are made for each cultivar. Then, extract, Folin–Ciocalteu’s phenol reagent and water are incubated for 8 min followed by the addition of 7% sodium carbonate. After 2 h, the absorbance is measured by an automated UV–VIS spectrophotometer at 750 nm. Gallic acid is used as standard. Standard curve is used to determine the concentration of total phenolics. For this purpose, 0, 50, 100, 200, 400, 800 and 1600 mg L⁻¹ gallic acid

concentration is used as a quality assurance. The results are expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent in kg fresh weight basis (GAE kg⁻¹_{FW}).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Folin–Ciocalteu’s phenol reagent
- Gallic acid
- Buffer (acetic acid + water + acetone)
- 7% sodium carbonate

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Shui, G. & Leong, L.P. (2002). Separation and determination of organic acids and phenolic compounds in fruit juices and drinks by high-performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of Chromatography A*, 977(1), 89-96.

Singleton, V.L. & Rossi, J.A. (1965). Colorimetry of total phenolics with phosphomolybdic-phosphotungstic acid reagents. *American Journal of Enology and Viticulture*, 16(3), 144-158.

4.3.6. Total antioxidant capacity (AOC)

PRINCIPLE

The total antioxidant capacity in apricots is important to know their potential health benefits, fruit quality, breeding programs, research and development, and consumer awareness. It provides valuable information about the antioxidant properties of apricots and their role in promoting overall health and well-being.

PROCEDURE

AOC is estimated by two standard procedures FRAP and TEAC assays as suggested by Ozgen et al. (2006). Ferric Reducing Ability of Plasma (FRAP) is determined according to the method of Benzie and Strain (1996). The assay is conducted using three aqueous stock solutions containing 0.1 mol L⁻¹ acetate buffer (pH 3.6), 10 mmol L⁻¹ TPTZ [2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-1,3,5-triazine] acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (1000:3.3 v/v), and 20 mmol L⁻¹ ferric chloride. These solutions are prepared and stored in the dark under refrigeration. Stock solutions are combined (10:1:1 v/v/v) to form the FRAP reagent just prior to analysis. For each assay in duplicate, 2.97 mL of FRAP reagent and 30 µL of sample extract are mixed. After 10 min, the absorbance of the reaction mixture is determined at 593 nm in a spectrophotometer. For the standard trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC) assay, ABTS is dissolved in acetate buffer and prepared with potassium persulfate, as described (Ozgen et al., 2006). The mixture is diluted in acidic medium of 20 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 4.5) to an absorbance of 0.700 ± 0.01 at

734 nm for longer stability (Ozgen et al., 2006). For the spectrophotometric assay, 2.98 mL of the ABTS solution and 20 μL of fruit extract are mixed and incubated for 10 min and the absorbance is determined at 734 nm. Trolox is used as positive control and linear regression curves are drawn. For this purpose, 1–20 μL to 1 mM trolox and appropriate water were used to bring volume to 20 μL . Results are expressed as mmol trolox equivalent in kg fresh weight basis ($\text{TE kg}^{-1}_{\text{FW}}$).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material

- mol L^{-1} acetate buffer (pH 3.6)
- 10 mmol L^{-1} TPTZ [2,4,6-tris(2-pyridyl)-1,3,5-triazine]
- Concentrated hydrochloric acid (1000:3.3 v/v)
- 20 mmol L^{-1} ferric chloride
- 20 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 4.5)
- Trolox

Equipment

- Spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Benzie, I. F. & Strain, J. J. (1996). The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”: the FRAP assay. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 239(1), 70-76.

Ozgen, M., Reese, R.N., Tulio, A.Z., Scheerens, J.C. & Miller, A.R. (2006). Modified 2, 2-azino-bis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid (ABTS) method to measure antioxidant capacity of selected small fruits and comparison to ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) and 2, 2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) methods. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 54(4), 1151-1157.

4.4. Berry

4.4.1. ABTS method

PRINCIPLE

The assay is run as described by Stratil et al. (2007) using the ABTS + radical ion and trolox standard for 10 min of reaction time. ABTS antioxidant power is given in mg equivalents of Trolox per g of dry weight ($\text{mg TE g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$).

PROCEDURE

The ABTS scavenging assay, which measures the inhibitory effect of the extract on the oxidation of the ABTS free radicals, is carried out according to an established procedure. In a typical experiment, 40 μL of the extract is mixed with 1960 μL of ABTS⁺ solution (aqueous solution of 7 mM ABTS and 12.5 mM potassium persulfate, with an absorbance

of 0.70 ± 0.02 at 734 nm). The reaction mixture is incubated in the dark at ambient temperature for 10 min and the absorbance is measured at 734 nm. All the measurements are done in dim light. Serial dilutions of trolox standard solution (1 mM) are used for plotting the calibration curve. The ABTS mean values are expressed in mg equivalents of trolox/g dry weight ($\text{mg TE g}^{-1}_{\text{DW}}$).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Potassium persulfate
- 2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) (ABTS)
- Trolox (6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchromane-2-carboxylic acid)
- Distilled water

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Stratil, P., Klejdus, B. & Kubáň, V. (2007). Determination of phenolic compounds and their antioxidant activity in fruits and cereals. *Talanta*, 71(4), 1741-1751.

4.4.2. Anthocyanin content

PRINCIPLE

Anthocyanins are plant extractives with red/purple colour. They are readily soluble in acidic solutions. The method is based on the extraction of anthocyanins from plant tissues and by the spectrophotometric quantification of the compounds using cyanidin-3-O-glucoside standard.

PROCEDURE

Extraction

1. Plant sample material (100 g) is homogenized using a blender.
2. Homogenized sample (0.4 - 2 g) is extracted with 40 mL 50:49.5:0.5 methanol:water:acetic acid (v/v/v) mixture using a Sonication (3x10 min, at 25-30 °C).
3. Extracts (2 mL) are centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 2 x 10 min.
4. The supernatant is taken to analysis.

Standard Solutions

Solution of 1 mg mL^{-1} must be prepared from cyaniding-3-O-glucoside in neat extraction solvent.

Measurement

Total monomeric anthocyanin content is determined by the pH differential method. Solutions used are potassium chloride buffer (KCl) at pH 1.0 (0.025 M) and sodium acetate buffer (C₂H₃NaO₂) at pH 4.5 (0.8 M). The anthocyanin extract of each variety is prepared twice: once with potassium chloride buffer (pH 1.0) and then with sodium acetate buffer (pH 4.5). They are settled for 15 min before their absorbances are measured in the spectrophotometer. Absorbance (A) is measured at 500 nm and 700 nm for each sample in both buffers. Samples are analysed in triplicate.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Water
- Methanol
- Acetic acid (96%)
- Sodium acetate
- Potassium chloride
- Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside

Equipment:

- Ultrasonic bath
- Centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

1. The following formulae are applied to estimate the total anthocyanin content:

$$A = (A_{500} - A_{700})_{\text{pH 1.0}} - (A_{500} - A_{700})_{\text{pH 4.5}}$$

$$\text{TAC (mg/100 g}_{\text{FW}}) = (A \times \text{MW} \times 1000) / (\epsilon \times 1)$$

where MW is the molecular weight of cyanidin-3-O-glucoside (cy-3-O-glu) (MW = 449.2 g mol⁻¹), and ϵ its molar absorptivity (26,900 L cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹). Total anthocyanin content (TAC) is expressed as mg cy-3-O-glu/100 g of fresh weight.

REFERENCES

Cerezo, A.B., Cătuțescu, G.M., González, M.M.P., Hornedo-Ortega, R., Pop, C.R., Rusu, C.C., Chirilă, F., Rotar, A.M., Garcia-Parrilla, M.C. & Troncoso, A.M. (2020). Anthocyanins in blueberries grown in hot climate exert strong antioxidant activity and may be effective against urinary tract bacteria. *Antioxidants*, 9(6), 478.

4.4.3. Brix degrees

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of sugar content, or Brix, as it is commonly known, is an essential part of the quality analysis of the agricultural products and alcoholic beverages. Degrees or Percentage Brix (symbol °Bx) is the sugar content of an aqueous solution. One-degree Brix is 1 gram of sucrose in 100 grams of solution and represents the strength of the solution as percentage by mass. If the solution contains dissolved solids other than pure sucrose, then the °Bx only approximates the dissolved solid content. A refractometer is an optical instrument to measure the Brix level in fruits, vegetables, juices, jams, wines and beers. It is a standard technique based on the measurement of the refractive index of the liquid.

PROCEDURE

Sample preparation

1. The sample is poured into 500 mL beaker and stirred for 10 min (the gases must be removed)

Calibration the refractometer

1. The refractometer is washed with distilled water
2. It is cleaned with tissue paper
3. Calibration adjuster is adjusted to zero before dropping the sample on the slide

Measuring Brix Percentage

1. A sample solution is added to the refractometer's prism and the lid is closed.
2. The device is hold perpendicular to a light source to look through the lens and see an internal scale.
3. The Brix reading is where the light and dark areas meet on the scale.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Calibration solution
- Distilled water

Equipment:

- Refractometer
- 500 mL baker
- Magnetic stirrer
- Magnetic rod

REFERENCES

<https://www.instrumentchoice.com.au/news/what-is-a-brix-refractometer-and-how-do-they-work>

Jaywant, S.A., Singh, H. & Arif, K.M. (2022). Sensors and instruments for brix measurement: A review. *Sensors*, 22(6), 2290.

4.4.4. Crop yield

PRINCIPLE

Yield will be calculated for each plots for comparison of the different treatments

PROCEDURE

Each section with different treatment will be harvested by hand. Wet weight of the crop will be measured on spot.

- Agroforestry treatment
- Bioherbicide treatment
- Control plot

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Balance

4.4.5. DPPH

PRINCIPLE

Scavenging of DPPH free radical is the basis of a common antioxidant assay. 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH) is a stable free radical which has an unpaired valence electron at one atom of nitrogen bridge. Scavenging of DPPH radical is the basis of the popular DPPH antioxidant assay.

PROCEDURE

The DPPH radical scavenging activity of the extracts is determined as follows: 2800 μL methanolic DPPH solution (80 μM) and 200 μL extract are mixed and incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 min. The decrease in absorbance is measured at 515. nm and the results are expressed as mg equivalents of trolox per gram dry weight (mg TE g^{-1}dw)

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH)
- Methanol
- Trolox
- Distilled water

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Hofmann, T., Visi-Rajczi, E., Vaculciakova, S., Guran, R., Voberkova, S., Vrsanska, M. & Albert, L. (2023). Direct microwave treatment enhances antioxidant and antibacterial properties of the seed extracts of Kékfrankos grapes. *Heliyon*, 9(11), e21497.

4.4.6. FRAP**PRINCIPLE**

A simple, automated test measuring the ferric reducing ability of plasma, the FRAP assay, is presented as a novel method for assessing “antioxidant power.” Ferric to ferrous ion reduction at low pH causes a coloured ferrous-tripyridyltriazine complex to form. FRAP values are obtained by comparing the absorbance change at 593 nm in test reaction mixtures with those containing ferrous ions in known concentration.

PROCEDURE

The FRAP is determined according to a standard method by Benzie and Strain that measures the antioxidant capacity by reducing the ferric ions to ferrous ions confirmed by their dark violet colour. A typical procedure involved mixing of 50 µL of the extract with 1500 µL of the reagent and allowing the reaction in the dark at ambient conditions for 5 min. The absorbance is measured at 593 nm against the blank solution using ascorbic acid standards for the calibration curve. The FRAP mean values are expressed in mg equivalents of ascorbic acid/g dry weight of bark (mg AAE g⁻¹_{DW}).

The FRAP assay is inexpensive, reagents are simple to prepare, results are highly reproducible, and the procedure is straightforward and speedy.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL**Material:**

- Trolox
- Ascorbic acid
- 2,4,6-tripyridyl-S-triazine (TPTZ)
- Iron(III)-chloride
- Acetic acid
- Sodium acetate
- Distilled water

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Benzie, I. F. & Strain, J. J. (1996). The ferric reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) as a measure of “antioxidant power”: the FRAP assay. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 239(1), 70-76.

4.4.7. pH**PRINCIPLE**

The pH indicates the acidity or alkalinity of a food or beverage. The pH meter measures this acidity based on the potential difference between a reference electrode (such as calomel or Ag/AgCl) and a pH electrode (glass electrode). This difference is then related to the concentration of H⁺ ions in the solution, corresponding to the acidity of the solution.

PROCEDURE**Calibration of the pH meter**

The calibration should be performed with at least two buffer solutions with known pH. For general purposes, buffer solutions with pH 4 and pH 10 are used. For more precise measurements, three buffer solution calibrations are preferred.

Measuring

1. First, the pH meter is warmed up.
2. Before measurement, the electrodes are visually checked. Refillable electrodes are checked for the absence of air bubbles in the glass bulb and to ensure that the inner electrolyte solution level is satisfactory.
3. Immerse the electrode into the sample, then wait while pH value appears.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL**Material:**

- Buffer solution

Equipment:

- pH meter
- Electrode

CALCULATIONS

The pH value is read from the device.

REFERENCES

Appendix V L. Determination of pH Values (Ph. Eur. method 2.2.3).

4.4.8. Polyphenol profiling

PRINCIPLE

The method is based on the high-performance liquid chromatographic separation and subsequent identification of polyphenolic compounds using multistage mass spectrometry.

PROCEDURE

Extraction

1. Plant sample material (100 g) is ground and sieved. The 0.2-0.63 mm fraction is used for analysis.
2. Sieved sample (0.4 g) is extracted with 40 mL methanol:water 50:50 (v/v) mixture using a Sonication (3x10 min, at 25-30 °C).
3. Extracts (2 mL) are centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 2x10 min.
4. The supernatant is taken to chromatographic analysis.
5. If extracts are too diluted, they should be concentrated as follows: 1 mL of the centrifuged extract is evaporated to dryness using rotary evaporation at 40 °C. Dry extracts are re-dissolved in 0.1 mL neat solvent and taken to chromatographic analysis.

Standard Solutions

6. All standards must be prepared in the same solvent as the extract.
7. Solutions of 1 mg mL⁻¹ must be prepared and dilutions according to real concentrations must be prepared. For mass spectrometric identification 100 ng mL⁻¹ concentrations must be prepared ideally.

Compounds optimization

8. From standard compound solutions the product ion spectra of each compound must be recorded in both negative and positive ionization mode. When possible, mass spectra must be matched with spectra library mass spectra.

Measurement

9. Gradient elution must be run using water + 0.1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid (B) solutions.
10. Stationary phase must be a C18 or compatible reverse phase column.
11. Mass spectrometer must be operated in 150-2000 m/z range in both positive and negative mode by polarity switching.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Acetonitrile (LCMS grade)
- Water (LCMS grade)
- Methanol (LCMS grade)
- Formic acid (98%)
- Polyphenol standard compounds (when applicable)

Equipment:

- Ultrasonic bath
- Centrifuge
- Liquid-chromatograph and mass spectrometer

CALCULATIONS

Results must be evaluated by comparing spectra of recorded compounds to database or standard spectra.

REFERENCES

Hofmann, T., Nebehaj, E. & Albert, L. (2016). Antioxidant properties and detailed polyphenol profiling of European hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus* L.) leaves by multiple antioxidant capacity assays and high-performance liquid chromatography/multistage electrospray mass spectrometry. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 87, 340-349.

4.4.9. TPC

PRINCIPLE

The improvements include the use of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent rather than the Folin-Denis reagent, gallic acid as a reference standard, and a more reproducible time-temperature colour development period. The values obtained are less subject to variation and interference from several non-phenols, yet are directly comparable to the "tannin" values obtained by the previously standard method.

PROCEDURE

TPC determination is completed by applying the Folin-Ciocalteu assay (Singleton – Rossi, 1965) using quercetin as the standard as follows: extract solution is mixed with 2.5 mL 10-fold diluted Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. After 1 min, 2 mL 0.7 M Na₂CO₃ solution is added and the reaction mixture is heated for 5 min in a 50 °C water bath. Reaction is stopped by cooling to room temperature in a cold-water bath. Solution absorbance is measured at 760 nm. The results are expressed as mg equivalents of gallic acid per g of dry weight units (mg GAE g⁻¹_{DW}).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Folin-Ciocalteu reagent
- Sodium carbonate
- 85% phosphoric acid
- Distilled water
- Gallic acid

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer
- Pipette
- Cuvette for spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Singleton, V.L. & Rossi, J.A. (1965). Colorimetry of total phenolics with phosphomolybdic-phosphotungstic acid reagents. *American Journal of Enology and Viticulture*, 16(3), 144-158.

4.5. Custard apple

4.5.1. pH determination

PRINCIPLE

The difference in potential between two electrodes immersed in the liquid under test is measured. One of these two electrodes has a potential that is a function of the pH of the liquid, while the other has a fixed and known potential and constitutes the reference electrode.

PROCEDURE

1. Zeroing of the apparatus

Zeroing is carried out before any measurement is made, according to the instructions provided with the apparatus used.

2. Calibration of the pH meter

The pH meter must be calibrated at 20 °C using standard buffer solutions connected to the SI. The pH values selected must encompass the range of values that may be encountered in musts and wines. If the pH meter used is not compatible with calibration at sufficiently low values, a verification using a standard buffer solution linked to the SI and which has a pH value close to the values encountered in the musts and wines may be used.

3. Determination

The electrode is dipped into the sample to be analysed, the temperature of which should be between 20 and 25 °C and as close as possible to 20 °C. The pH value is read directly off the scale. Carry out at least two determinations on the same sample. The final result is taken to be the arithmetic mean of two determinations.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- pH meter with a scale calibrated in pH units and enabling measurements to be made to at least ± 0.01 pH units.

Electrodes:

- Glass electrode, kept in distilled water;
- Calomel-saturated potassium chloride reference electrode, kept in a saturated solution of potassium chloride; or,
- A combined electrode, kept in distilled water.

Buffer solutions:

Saturated potassium hydrogen tartrate solution, containing 5.7 g L⁻¹ potassium hydrogen tartrate (CO₂HC₂H₄O₂CO₂K) at 20 °C. This solution may be kept for up to two months by adding 0.1 g of thymol per 200 mL.

3.57 at 20 °C

pH 3.56 at 25 °C

3.55 at 30 °C

Potassium hydrogen phthalate solution, 0.05 M, containing 10.211 g L⁻¹ potassium hydrogen phthalate, CO₂HC₆H₄CO₂K, at 20 °C. This solution may be kept for up to two months.

3.999 at 15 °C

pH 4.003 at 20 °C

4.008 at 25 °C

4.015 at 30 °C

Solution containing:

- Potassium *di*-hydrogen phosphate, KH₂PO₄ → 3.402 g
- *Di*-potassium hydrogen phosphate, K₂HPO₄ → 4.354 g
- Water to → 1 L

(This solution could be kept for up to two months).

6.90 at 15 °C
pH 6.88 at 20 °C
6.86 at 25 °C
6.85 at 30 °C

Note: commercial reference buffer solutions traceable to the SI may be used.

For example: pH 1.679 ± 0.01 at 25 °C

pH 4.005 ± 0.01 at 25 °C

pH 7.000 ± 0.01 at 25 °C

REMARKS

The pH of the must or the wine is reported to two decimals.

REFERENCES

OIV-MA-AS313-15. pH (A31 revised by Oeno 438-2011). Compendium of international methods of wine and must analysis, vol. 1. Paris, France: International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV); 491–3.

4.5.2. Titratable acidity (ta)

PRINCIPLE

The presence of dissolved organic acids in the cell vacuoles serves as substrates for fruit respiration and determines its acidity (Brody, 1996). These acids not only contribute to the acidity of the fruit, but also to its characteristic aroma, given the presence of volatile components. Their content tends to decrease as a result of the respiratory process or their conversion into sugars; during this phase, there is a greater energy demand due to increased metabolism (Brody, 1996; Chitarra; Chitarra, 2005). The variation in acidity can indicate the stage of ripeness of the fruit, as acidity generally decreases as ripeness progresses.

PROCEDURE

1. 5 g of the sample are weighed into a previously identified 50 mL flask.
2. 50 mL of distilled water are added to the flask and shaken vigorously on an orbital shaker.
3. It is left to stand for 1 hour.
4. Then, it is shaken gently and 17.6 mL of the sample is pipetted from previous point (3) into another empty, previously labelled 50 mL bottle.
5. 17.6 mL are exactly added of distilled water to point 4

6. 0.5 mL of phenolphthalein indicator (1%) are added (about 2 drops).
7. It is titrated with standardized 0.1 N NaOH until a pale pink colour is obtained and persists for at least 30 seconds.

CALCULATIONS

$$\%(v/p)Lactic\ acid = \frac{NaOH\ 0.01N\ spent\ (mL) \times N \times f \times 0.9}{(sample\ weight) \times 100}$$

Where:

N – concentration of NaOH 0.1N;

f – correction factor for the normality of NaOH;

0.9 – acidity constant for lactic acid.

Calculation of the normality correction factor (f)

$$f = \frac{KHP\ weight\ (g)}{0.2042 \times V\ tritand\ spent\ (ml) \times N}$$

Where:

KHP – Potassium hydrogenphthalate

NOTE:

Eq. g acid = gram equivalent of the acid expressed which corresponds to the gram equivalents of 1 mL of NaOH in the standard used.

OBS: Eq. g of some acids: citric acid = 64.04; malic acid = 67.05; tartaric acid = 75.05; acetic acid = 60.05; oxalic acid = 45.01; lactic acid = 90.08; oleic acid = 282.0.

REMARKS

Warning: NaOH is extremely corrosive. Protect skin and eyes. Add the NaOH tablets to the water, not the water to the tablets.

Note: Preparation of phenolphthalein indicator (1%): Dissolve 1 g of phenolphthalein in 50 mL of ethyl alcohol (95%) and dilute to 100 mL with distilled water.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

Equipment:

- Orbital shaker (Innova 2100)
- 25 mL graduated burette (with 0.1 mL divisions)
- 50 mL Bottles
- Volumetric pipettes

Reagents

- Indicator Phenolphthalein (1%)
- Standardized 0.1 N sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution (AACC Method 70-70.01)

REFERENCES

AACC. (2000). *Association of Cereal Chemists (AACC) International, Method 02-31.01*.

Titrate acidity. St. Paul, MN, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1094/AACCIntMethod-02-31.01>

AOAC. (1995). *Official Methods of Analysis of AOAC International, 16th ed.*, Method 947.05. Arlington, VA.

Brody, A.L. (1996). *Envasado de alimentos en atmósferas controladas, modificadas y vacío*. Zaragoza: Acribia, 220.

Chitarra, M.I.F. & Chitarra, A.B. (2005). *Pós-colheita de frutos e hortaliças: fisiologia e manuseio*. Lavras: ESAL/FAEFE, 320.

4.5.3. Total soluble solid content

PRINCIPLE

The refractive index at 20 °C, expressed either as an absolute value or as a percentage by mass of sucrose, is given in the appropriate table to provide a means of obtaining the sugar concentration in grams per litre and in grams per kilogram for custard apple juice.

PROCEDURE

Determined using a field/table refractometer at a temperature of 20 °C, with the juice read directly on the device that automatically compensates for the temperature.

A small test sample is placed on the lower prism of the refractometer, taking care (because the prisms are pressed firmly against each other) that this test sample covers the glass surface uniformly. The measurement is done in accordance with the operating instructions of the instrument used.

The percentage is read by mass of sucrose to within 0.1 or by the refractive index to four decimals. At least two determinations are done on the same prepared sample. The temperature is recorded as °C.

CALCULATIONS

1. Temperature correction

- Instruments graduated in percentage by mass of sucrose: Table 21 is used to obtain the temperature correction.
- Instruments graduated in refractive index: find the index measured at t °C in Table 22 to obtain (column 1) the corresponding value of the percentage by mass of sucrose at t °C. This value is corrected for temperature and expressed as a concentration at 20 °C by using the Table 21.

2. Sugar concentration in juice and concentrated juice

Find the percentage by mass of sucrose at 20 °C in Table 22 and read from the same row the sugar concentration in grams per litre and grams per kilogram. The sugar concentration is expressed in terms of invert sugar to one decimal place.

3. Sugar concentration in rectified concentrated must

Find the percentage by mass of sucrose at 20 °C in Table 23 and read from the same row the sugar concentration in grams per litre and grams per kilogram. The sugar concentration is expressed in terms of invert sugar to one decimal place. If the measurement was made on diluted rectified concentrated must, multiply the result by the dilution factor.

4. Refractive index of must, concentrated must and rectified concentrated juice

Find the percentage by mass of sucrose at 20 °C in Table 22 and read from the same row the refractive index at 20 °C. This index is expressed to four decimal places.

Table 21. Correction to be made in the casa where the % by mass of saccharose was determined at a temperature different by 20 °C.

Temperat ure °C	Percentage by mass measured in %													
	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75
5	-0.82	-0.87	-0.92	-0.95	-0.99									
6	-0.80	-0.82	-0.87	-0.90	-0.94									
7	-0.74	-0.78	-0.82	-0.84	-0.88									
8	-0.69	-0.73	-0.76	-0.79	-0.82									
9	-0.64	-0.67	-0.71	-0.73	-0.75									
10	-0.59	-0.62	-0.65	-0.67	-0.69	-0.71	-0.72	-0.73	-0.74	-0.75	-0.75	-0.75	-0.75	-0.75
11	-0.54	-0.57	-0.59	-0.61	-0.63	-0.64	-0.65	-0.66	-0.67	-0.68	-0.68	-0.68	-0.68	-0.67
12	-0.49	-0.51	-0.53	-0.55	-0.56	-0.57	-0.58	-0.59	-0.60	-0.60	-0.61	-0.61	-0.60	-0.60
13	-0.43	-0.45	-0.47	-0.48	-0.50	-0.51	-0.52	-0.52	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53
14	-0.38	-0.39	-0.40	-0.42	-0.43	-0.44	-0.44	-0.45	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46	-0.46	-0.46	-0.45
15	-0.32	-0.33	-0.34	-0.35	-0.36	-0.37	-0.37	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38
16	-0.26	-0.27	-0.28	-0.28	-0.29	-0.30	-0.30	-0.30	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.30
17	-0.20	-0.20	-0.21	-0.21	-0.22	-0.22	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23
18	-0.13	-0.14	-0.14	-0.14	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15
19	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08
20	R E F E R E N C E													
21	+0.07	+0.07	+0.07	+0.07	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08
22	+0.14	+0.14	+0.15	+0.15	+0.15	+0.15	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.15	+0.15
23	+0.21	+0.22	+0.22	+0.23	+0.23	+0.23	+0.23	+0.24	+0.24	+0.24	+0.24	+0.23	+0.23	+0.23
24	+0.29	+0.29	+0.30	+0.30	+0.31	+0.31	+0.31	+0.32	+0.32	+0.32	+0.32	+0.31	+0.31	+0.31
25	+0.36	+0.37	+0.38	+0.38	+0.39	+0.39	+0.40	+0.40	+0.40	+0.40	+0.40	+0.39	+0.39	+0.39
26	+0.44	+0.45	+0.46	+0.46	+0.47	+0.47	+0.48	+0.48	+0.48	+0.48	+0.48	+0.47	+0.47	+0.46
27	+0.52	+0.53	+0.54	+0.55	+0.55	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.55	+0.55	+0.54
28	+0.60	+0.61	+0.62	+0.63	+0.64	+0.64	+0.64	+0.65	+0.65	+0.64	+0.64	+0.64	+0.63	+0.62
29	+0.68	+0.69	+0.70	+0.71	+0.72	+0.73	+0.73	+0.73	+0.73	+0.73	+0.72	+0.72	+0.71	+0.70
30	+0.77	+0.78	+0.79	+0.80	+0.81	+0.81	+0.81	+0.82	+0.81	+0.81	+0.81	+0.80	+0.79	+0.78
31	+0.85	+0.87	+0.88	+0.89	+0.89	+0.90	+0.90	+0.90	+0.90	+0.90	+0.89	+0.88	+0.87	+0.86
32	+0.94	+0.95	+0.96	+0.97	+0.98	+0.99	+0.99	+0.99	+0.99	+0.98	+0.97	+0.96	+0.95	+0.94
33	+1.03	+1.04	+1.05	+1.06	+1.07	+1.08	+1.08	+1.08	+1.07	+1.07	+1.06	+1.05	+1.03	+1.02
34	+1.12	+1.19	+1.15	+1.15	+1.16	+1.17	+1.17	+1.17	+1.16	+1.15	+1.14	+1.13	+1.12	+1.10
35	+1.22	+1.23	+1.24	+1.25	+1.25	+1.26	+1.26	+1.25	+1.25	+1.24	+1.23	+1.21	+1.20	+1.18
36	+1.31	+1.32	+1.33	+1.34	+1.35	+1.35	+1.35	+1.35	+1.34	+1.33	+1.32	+1.30	+1.28	+1.26
37	+1.41	+1.42	+1.43	+1.44	+1.44	+1.44	+1.44	+1.43	+1.42	+1.40	+1.38	+1.36	+1.34	+1.34
38	+1.51	+1.52	+1.53	+1.53	+1.54	+1.54	+1.53	+1.53	+1.52	+1.51	+1.49	+1.47	+1.45	+1.42
39	+1.61	+1.62	+1.62	+1.63	+1.63	+1.63	+1.63	+1.62	+1.61	+1.60	+1.58	+1.56	+1.53	+1.50
40	+1.71	+1.72	+1.72	+1.73	+1.73	+1.73	+1.72	+1.71	+1.70	+1.69	+1.67	+1.64	+1.62	+1.59

It is preferable that the variations in temperature in relation to 20°C do not exceed ± 5°C.

Table 22. Saccharose refractive index in custard apple. Table giving the sugar content of musts and concentrated musts in grammes per litre and in grammes per kilogram, determined using a graduated refractometer, either in % by mass of saccharose at 20 °C, or refractive index at 20 °C. The mass density at 20 °C is also given.

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
10.0	1.34782	1.0391	82.2	79.1	4.89
10.1	1.34798	1.0395	83.3	80.1	4.95
10.2	1.34813	1.0399	84.3	81.1	5.01
10.3	1.34829	1.0403	85.4	82.1	5.08
10.4	1.34844	1.0407	86.5	83.1	5.14
10.5	1.34860	1.0411	87.5	84.1	5.20
10.6	1.34875	1.0415	88.6	85.0	5.27
10.7	1.34891	1.0419	89.6	86.0	5.32
10.8	1.34906	1.0423	90.7	87.0	5.39
10.9	1.34922	1.0427	91.8	88.0	5.46
11.0	1.34937	1.0431	92.8	89.0	5.52
11.1	1.34953	1.0436	93.9	90.0	5.58
11.2	1.34968	1.0440	95.0	91.0	5.65
11.3	1.34984	1.0444	96.0	92.0	5.71
11.4	1.34999	1.0448	97.1	92.9	5.77
11.5	1.35015	1.0452	98.2	93.9	5.84
11.6	1.35031	1.0456	99.3	94.9	5.90
11.7	1.35046	1.0460	100.3	95.9	5.96
11.8	1.35062	1.0464	101.4	96.9	6.03
11.9	1.35077	1.0468	102.5	97.9	6.09
12.0	1.35093	1.0472	103.5	98.9	6.15
12.1	1.35109	1.0477	104.6	99.9	6.22
12.2	1.35124	1.0481	105.7	100.8	6.28
12.3	1.35140	1.0485	106.8	101.8	6.35
12.4	1.35156	1.0489	107.8	102.8	6.41
12.5	1.35171	1.0493	108.9	103.8	6.47
12.6	1.35187	1.0497	110.0	104.8	6.54
12.7	1.35203	1.0501	111.1	105.8	6.60
12.8	1.35219	1.0506	112.2	106.8	6.67
12.9	1.35234	1.0510	113.2	107.8	6.73
13.0	1.35250	1.0514	114.3	108.7	6.79
13.1	1.35266	1.0518	115.4	109.7	6.86
13.2	1.35282	1.0522	116.5	110.7	6.92
13.3	1.35298	1.0527	117.6	111.7	6.99
13.4	1.35313	1.0531	118.7	112.7	7.05
13.5	1.35329	1.0535	119.7	113.7	7.11
13.6	1.35345	1.0539	120.8	114.7	7.18
13.7	1.35361	1.0543	121.9	115.6	7.24
13.8	1.35377	1.0548	123.0	116.6	7.31
13.9	1.35393	1.0552	124.1	117.6	7.38
14.0	1.35408	1.0556	125.2	118.6	7.44
14.1	1.35424	1.0560	126.3	119.6	7.51
14.2	1.35440	1.0564	127.4	120.6	7.57
14.3	1.35456	1.0569	128.5	121.6	7.64
14.4	1.35472	1.0573	129.6	122.5	7.70
14.5	1.35488	1.0577	130.6	123.5	7.76
14.6	1.35504	1.0581	131.7	124.5	7.83
14.7	1.35520	1.0586	132.8	125.5	7.89
14.8	1.35536	1.0590	133.9	126.5	7.96
14.9	1.35552	1.0594	135.0	127.5	8.02

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
15.0	1.35568	1.0598	136.1	128.4	8.09
15.1	1.35584	1.0603	137.2	129.4	8.15
15.2	1.35600	1.0607	138.3	130.4	8.22
15.3	1.35616	1.0611	139.4	131.4	8.28
15.4	1.35632	1.0616	140.5	132.4	8.35
15.5	1.35648	1.0620	141.6	133.4	8.42
15.6	1.35664	1.0624	142.7	134.3	8.48
15.7	1.35680	1.0628	143.8	135.3	8.55
15.8	1.35696	1.0633	144.9	136.3	8.61
15.9	1.35713	1.0637	146.0	137.3	8.68
16.0	1.35729	1.0641	147.1	138.3	8.74
16.1	1.35745	1.0646	148.2	139.3	8.81
16.2	1.35761	1.0650	149.3	140.2	8.87
16.3	1.35777	1.0654	150.5	141.2	8.94
16.4	1.35793	1.0659	151.6	142.2	9.01
16.5	1.35810	1.0663	152.7	143.2	9.07
16.6	1.35826	1.0667	153.8	144.2	9.14
16.7	1.35842	1.0672	154.9	145.1	9.21
16.8	1.35858	1.0676	156.0	146.1	9.27
16.9	1.35874	1.0680	157.1	147.1	9.34
17.0	1.35891	1.0685	158.2	148.1	9.40
17.1	1.35907	1.0689	159.3	149.1	9.47
17.2	1.35923	1.0693	160.4	150.0	9.53
17.3	1.35940	1.0698	161.6	151.0	9.60
17.4	1.35956	1.0702	162.7	152.0	9.67
17.5	1.35972	1.0707	163.8	153.0	9.73
17.6	1.35989	1.0711	164.9	154.0	9.80
17.7	1.36005	1.0715	166.0	154.9	9.87
17.8	1.36021	1.0720	167.1	155.9	9.93
17.9	1.36038	1.0724	168.3	156.9	10.00
18.0	1.36054	1.0729	169.4	157.9	10.07
18.1	1.36070	1.0733	170.5	158.9	10.13
18.2	1.36087	1.0737	171.6	159.8	10.20
18.3	1.36103	1.0742	172.7	160.8	10.26
18.4	1.36120	1.0746	173.9	161.8	10.33
18.5	1.36136	1.0751	175.0	162.8	10.40
18.6	1.36153	1.0755	176.1	163.7	10.47
18.7	1.36169	1.0760	177.2	164.7	10.53
18.8	1.36185	1.0764	178.4	165.7	10.60
18.9	1.36202	1.0768	179.5	166.7	10.67
19.0	1.36219	1.0773	180.6	167.6	10.73
19.1	1.36235	1.0777	181.7	168.6	10.80
19.2	1.36252	1.0782	182.9	169.6	10.87
19.3	1.36268	1.0786	184.0	170.6	10.94
19.4	1.36285	1.0791	185.1	171.5	11.00
19.5	1.36301	1.0795	186.2	172.5	11.07
19.6	1.36318	1.0800	187.4	173.5	11.14
19.7	1.36334	1.0804	188.5	174.5	11.20
19.8	1.36351	1.0809	189.6	175.4	11.27
19.9	1.36368	1.0813	190.8	176.4	11.34

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
20.0	1.36384	1.0818	191.9	177.4	11.40
20.1	1.36401	1.0822	193.0	178.4	11.47
20.2	1.36418	1.0827	194.2	179.3	11.54
20.3	1.36434	1.0831	195.3	180.3	11.61
20.4	1.36451	1.0836	196.4	181.3	11.67
20.5	1.36468	1.0840	197.6	182.3	11.74
20.6	1.36484	1.0845	198.7	183.2	11.81
20.7	1.36501	1.0849	199.8	184.2	11.87
20.8	1.36518	1.0854	201.0	185.2	11.95
20.9	1.36535	1.0858	202.1	186.1	12.01
21.0	1.36551	1.0863	203.3	187.1	12.08
21.1	1.36568	1.0867	204.4	188.1	12.15
21.2	1.36585	1.0872	205.5	189.1	12.21
21.3	1.36602	1.0876	206.7	190.0	12.28
21.4	1.36619	1.0881	207.8	191.0	12.35
21.5	1.36635	1.0885	209.0	192.0	12.42
21.6	1.36652	1.0890	210.1	192.9	12.49
21.7	1.36669	1.0895	211.3	193.9	12.56
21.8	1.36686	1.0899	212.4	194.9	12.62
21.9	1.36703	1.0904	213.6	195.9	12.69
22.0	1.36720	1.0908	214.7	196.8	12.76
22.1	1.36737	1.0913	215.9	197.8	12.83
22.2	1.36754	1.0917	217.0	198.8	12.90
22.3	1.36771	1.0922	218.2	199.7	12.97
22.4	1.36787	1.0927	219.3	200.7	13.03
22.5	1.36804	1.0931	220.5	201.7	13.10
22.6	1.36821	1.0936	221.6	202.6	13.17
22.7	1.36838	1.0940	222.8	203.6	13.24
22.8	1.36855	1.0945	223.9	204.6	13.31
22.9	1.36872	1.0950	225.1	205.5	13.38
23.0	1.36889	1.0954	226.2	206.5	13.44
23.1	1.36906	1.0959	227.4	207.5	13.51
23.2	1.36924	1.0964	228.5	208.4	13.58
23.3	1.36941	1.0968	229.7	209.4	13.65
23.4	1.36958	1.0973	230.8	210.4	13.72
23.5	1.36975	1.0977	232.0	211.3	13.79
23.6	1.36992	1.0982	233.2	212.3	13.86
23.7	1.37009	1.0987	234.3	213.3	13.92
23.8	1.37026	1.0991	235.5	214.2	14.00
23.9	1.37043	1.0996	236.6	215.2	14.06
24.0	1.37060	1.1001	237.8	216.2	14.13
24.1	1.37078	1.1005	239.0	217.1	14.20
24.2	1.37095	1.1010	240.1	218.1	14.27
24.3	1.37112	1.1015	241.3	219.1	14.34
24.4	1.37129	1.1019	242.5	220.0	14.41
24.5	1.37146	1.1024	243.6	221.0	14.48
24.6	1.37164	1.1029	244.8	222.0	14.55
24.7	1.37181	1.1033	246.0	222.9	14.62
24.8	1.37198	1.1038	247.1	223.9	14.69
24.9	1.37216	1.1043	248.3	224.8	14.76

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20°C	Mass Density at 20°C	Sugars In g/l	Sugars In g/Kg	ABV % vol At 20°C
25.0	1.37233	1.1047	249.5	225.8	14.83
25.1	1.37250	1.1052	250.6	226.8	14.89
25.2	1.37267	1.1057	251.8	227.7	14.96
25.3	1.37285	1.1062	253.0	228.7	15.04
25.4	1.37302	1.1066	254.1	229.7	15.10
25.5	1.37319	1.1071	255.3	230.6	15.17
25.6	1.37337	1.1076	256.5	231.6	15.24
25.7	1.37354	1.1080	257.7	232.5	15.32
25.8	1.37372	1.1085	258.8	233.5	15.38
25.9	1.37389	1.1090	260.0	234.5	15.45
26.0	1.37407	1.1095	261.2	235.4	15.52
26.1	1.37424	1.1099	262.4	236.4	15.59
26.2	1.37441	1.1104	263.6	237.3	15.67
26.3	1.37459	1.1109	264.7	238.3	15.73
26.4	1.37476	1.1114	265.9	239.3	15.80
26.5	1.37494	1.1118	267.1	240.2	15.87
26.6	1.37511	1.1123	268.3	241.2	15.95
26.7	1.37529	1.1128	269.5	242.1	16.02
26.8	1.37546	1.1133	270.6	243.1	16.08
26.9	1.37564	1.1138	271.8	244.1	16.15
27.0	1.37582	1.1142	273.0	245.0	16.22
27.1	1.37599	1.1147	274.2	246.0	16.30
27.2	1.37617	1.1152	275.4	246.9	16.37
27.3	1.37634	1.1157	276.6	247.9	16.44
27.4	1.37652	1.1161	277.8	248.9	16.51
27.5	1.37670	1.1166	278.9	249.8	16.58
27.6	1.37687	1.1171	280.1	250.8	16.65
27.7	1.37705	1.1176	281.3	251.7	16.72
27.8	1.37723	1.1181	282.5	252.7	16.79
27.9	1.37740	1.1185	283.7	253.6	16.86
28.0	1.37758	1.1190	284.9	254.6	16.93
28.1	1.37776	1.1195	286.1	255.5	17.00
28.2	1.37793	1.1200	287.3	256.5	17.07
28.3	1.37811	1.1205	288.5	257.5	17.15
28.4	1.37829	1.1210	289.7	258.4	17.22
28.5	1.37847	1.1214	290.9	259.4	17.29
28.6	1.37864	1.1219	292.1	260.3	17.36
28.7	1.37882	1.1224	293.3	261.3	17.43
28.8	1.37900	1.1229	294.5	262.2	17.50
28.9	1.37918	1.1234	295.7	263.2	17.57
29.0	1.37936	1.1239	296.9	264.2	17.64
29.1	1.37954	1.1244	298.1	265.1	17.72
29.2	1.37972	1.1248	299.3	266.1	17.79
29.3	1.37989	1.1253	300.5	267.0	17.86
29.4	1.38007	1.1258	301.7	268.0	17.93
29.5	1.38025	1.1263	302.9	268.9	18.00
29.6	1.38043	1.1268	304.1	269.9	18.07
29.7	1.38061	1.1273	305.3	270.8	18.14
29.8	1.38079	1.1278	306.5	271.8	18.22
29.9	1.38097	1.1283	307.7	272.7	18.29

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
30.0	1.38115	1.1287	308.9	273.7	18.36
30.1	1.38133	1.1292	310.1	274.6	18.43
30.2	1.38151	1.1297	311.3	275.6	18.50
30.3	1.38169	1.1302	312.6	276.5	18.58
30.4	1.38187	1.1307	313.8	277.5	18.65
30.5	1.38205	1.1312	315.0	278.5	18.72
30.6	1.38223	1.1317	316.2	279.4	18.79
30.7	1.38241	1.1322	317.4	280.4	18.86
30.8	1.38259	1.1327	318.6	281.3	18.93
30.9	1.38277	1.1332	319.8	282.3	19.01
31.0	1.38296	1.1337	321.1	283.2	19.08
31.1	1.38314	1.1342	322.3	284.2	19.15
31.2	1.38332	1.1346	323.5	285.1	19.23
31.3	1.38350	1.1351	324.7	286.1	19.30
31.4	1.38368	1.1356	325.9	287.0	19.37
31.5	1.38386	1.1361	327.2	288.0	19.45
31.6	1.38405	1.1366	328.4	288.9	19.52
31.7	1.38423	1.1371	329.6	289.9	19.59
31.8	1.38441	1.1376	330.8	290.8	19.66
31.9	1.38459	1.1381	332.1	291.8	19.74
32.0	1.38478	1.1386	333.3	292.7	19.81
32.1	1.38496	1.1391	334.5	293.7	19.88
32.2	1.38514	1.1396	335.7	294.6	19.95
32.3	1.38532	1.1401	337.0	295.6	20.03
32.4	1.38551	1.1406	338.2	296.5	20.10
32.5	1.38569	1.1411	339.4	297.5	20.17
32.6	1.38587	1.1416	340.7	298.4	20.25
32.7	1.38606	1.1421	341.9	299.4	20.32
32.8	1.38624	1.1426	343.1	300.3	20.39
32.9	1.38643	1.1431	344.4	301.3	20.47
33.0	1.38661	1.1436	345.6	302.2	20.54
33.1	1.38679	1.1441	346.8	303.2	20.61
33.2	1.38698	1.1446	348.1	304.1	20.69
33.3	1.38716	1.1451	349.3	305.0	20.76
33.4	1.38735	1.1456	350.6	306.0	20.84
33.5	1.38753	1.1461	351.8	306.9	20.91
33.6	1.38772	1.1466	353.0	307.9	20.98
33.7	1.38790	1.1471	354.3	308.8	21.06
33.8	1.38809	1.1476	355.5	309.8	21.13
33.9	1.38827	1.1481	356.8	310.7	21.20
34.0	1.38846	1.1486	358.0	311.7	21.28
34.1	1.38864	1.1491	359.2	312.6	21.35
34.2	1.38883	1.1496	360.5	313.6	21.42
34.3	1.38902	1.1501	361.7	314.5	21.50
34.4	1.38920	1.1507	363.0	315.5	21.57
34.5	1.38939	1.1512	364.2	316.4	21.64
34.6	1.38958	1.1517	365.5	317.4	21.72
34.7	1.38976	1.1522	366.7	318.3	21.79
34.8	1.38995	1.1527	368.0	319.2	21.87
34.9	1.39014	1.1532	369.2	320.2	21.94

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
35.0	1.39032	1.1537	370.5	321.1	22.02
35.1	1.39051	1.1542	371.8	322.1	22.10
35.2	1.39070	1.1547	373.0	323.0	22.17
35.3	1.39088	1.1552	374.3	324.0	22.24
35.4	1.39107	1.1557	375.5	324.9	22.32
35.5	1.39126	1.1563	376.8	325.9	22.39
35.6	1.39145	1.1568	378.0	326.8	22.46
35.7	1.39164	1.1573	379.3	327.8	22.54
35.8	1.39182	1.1578	380.6	328.7	22.62
35.9	1.39201	1.1583	381.8	329.6	22.69
36.0	1.39220	1.1588	383.1	330.6	22.77
36.1	1.39239	1.1593	384.4	331.5	22.84
36.2	1.39258	1.1598	385.6	332.5	22.92
36.3	1.39277	1.1603	386.9	333.4	22.99
36.4	1.39296	1.1609	388.1	334.4	23.06
36.5	1.39314	1.1614	389.4	335.3	23.14
36.6	1.39333	1.1619	390.7	336.3	23.22
36.7	1.39352	1.1624	392.0	337.2	23.30
36.8	1.39371	1.1629	393.2	338.1	23.37
36.9	1.39390	1.1634	394.5	339.1	23.45
37.0	1.39409	1.1640	395.8	340.0	23.52
37.1	1.39428	1.1645	397.0	341.0	23.59
37.2	1.39447	1.1650	398.3	341.9	23.67
37.3	1.39466	1.1655	399.6	342.9	23.75
37.4	1.39485	1.1660	400.9	343.8	23.83
37.5	1.39504	1.1665	402.1	344.7	23.90
37.6	1.39524	1.1671	403.4	345.7	23.97
37.7	1.39543	1.1676	404.7	346.6	24.05
37.8	1.39562	1.1681	406.0	347.6	24.13
37.9	1.39581	1.1686	407.3	348.5	24.21
38.0	1.39600	1.1691	408.6	349.4	24.28
38.1	1.39619	1.1697	409.8	350.4	24.35
38.2	1.39638	1.1702	411.1	351.3	24.43
38.3	1.39658	1.1707	412.4	352.3	24.51
38.4	1.39677	1.1712	413.7	353.2	24.59
38.5	1.39696	1.1717	415.0	354.2	24.66
38.6	1.39715	1.1723	416.3	355.1	24.74
38.7	1.39734	1.1728	417.6	356.0	24.82
38.8	1.39754	1.1733	418.8	357.0	24.89
38.9	1.39773	1.1738	420.1	357.9	24.97
39.0	1.39792	1.1744	421.4	358.9	25.04
39.1	1.39812	1.1749	422.7	359.8	25.12
39.2	1.39831	1.1754	424.0	360.7	25.20
39.3	1.39850	1.1759	425.3	361.7	25.28
39.4	1.39870	1.1765	426.6	362.6	25.35
39.5	1.39889	1.1770	427.9	363.6	25.43
39.6	1.39908	1.1775	429.2	364.5	25.51
39.7	1.39928	1.1780	430.5	365.4	25.58
39.8	1.39947	1.1786	431.8	366.4	25.66
39.9	1.39967	1.1791	433.1	367.3	25.74

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
40.0	1.39986	1.1796	434.4	368.3	25.82
40.1	1.40006	1.1801	435.7	369.2	25.89
40.2	1.40025	1.1807	437.0	370.1	25.97
40.3	1.40044	1.1812	438.3	371.1	26.05
40.4	1.40064	1.1817	439.6	372.0	26.13
40.5	1.40083	1.1823	440.9	373.0	26.20
40.6	1.40103	1.1828	442.2	373.9	26.28
40.7	1.40123	1.1833	443.6	374.8	26.36
40.8	1.40142	1.1839	444.9	375.8	26.44
40.9	1.40162	1.1844	446.2	376.7	26.52
41.0	1.40181	1.1849	447.5	377.7	26.59
41.1	1.40201	1.1855	448.8	378.6	26.67
41.2	1.40221	1.1860	450.1	379.5	26.75
41.3	1.40240	1.1865	451.4	380.5	26.83
41.4	1.40260	1.1871	452.8	381.4	26.91
41.5	1.40280	1.1876	454.1	382.3	26.99
41.6	1.40299	1.1881	455.4	383.3	27.06
41.7	1.40319	1.1887	456.7	384.2	27.14
41.8	1.40339	1.1892	458.0	385.2	27.22
41.9	1.40358	1.1897	459.4	386.1	27.30
42.0	1.40378	1.1903	460.7	387.0	27.38
42.1	1.40398	1.1908	462.0	388.0	27.46
42.2	1.40418	1.1913	463.3	388.9	27.53
42.3	1.40437	1.1919	464.7	389.9	27.62
42.4	1.40457	1.1924	466.0	390.8	27.69
42.5	1.40477	1.1929	467.3	391.7	27.77
42.6	1.40497	1.1935	468.6	392.7	27.85
42.7	1.40517	1.1940	470.0	393.6	27.93
42.8	1.40537	1.1946	471.3	394.5	28.01
42.9	1.40557	1.1951	472.6	395.5	28.09
43.0	1.40576	1.1956	474.0	396.4	28.17
43.1	1.40596	1.1962	475.3	397.3	28.25
43.2	1.40616	1.1967	476.6	398.3	28.32
43.3	1.40636	1.1973	478.0	399.2	28.41
43.4	1.40656	1.1978	479.3	400.2	28.48
43.5	1.40676	1.1983	480.7	401.1	28.57
43.6	1.40696	1.1989	482.0	402.0	28.65
43.7	1.40716	1.1994	483.3	403.0	28.72
43.8	1.40736	1.2000	484.7	403.9	28.81
43.9	1.40756	1.2005	486.0	404.8	28.88
44.0	1.40776	1.2011	487.4	405.8	28.97
44.1	1.40796	1.2016	488.7	406.7	29.04
44.2	1.40817	1.2022	490.1	407.6	29.13
44.3	1.40837	1.2027	491.4	408.6	29.20
44.4	1.40857	1.2032	492.8	409.5	29.29
44.5	1.40877	1.2038	494.1	410.4	29.36
44.6	1.40897	1.2043	495.5	411.4	29.45
44.7	1.40917	1.2049	496.8	412.3	29.52
44.8	1.40937	1.2054	498.2	413.3	29.61
44.9	1.40958	1.2060	499.5	414.2	29.69

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
45.0	1.40978	1.2065	500.9	415.1	29.77
45.1	1.40998	1.2071	502.2	416.1	29.85
45.2	1.41018	1.2076	503.6	417.0	29.93
45.3	1.41039	1.2082	504.9	417.9	30.01
45.4	1.41059	1.2087	506.3	418.9	30.09
45.5	1.41079	1.2093	507.7	419.8	30.17
45.6	1.41099	1.2098	509.0	420.7	30.25
45.7	1.41120	1.2104	510.4	421.7	30.33
45.8	1.41140	1.2109	511.7	422.6	30.41
45.9	1.41160	1.2115	513.1	423.5	30.49
46.0	1.41181	1.2120	514.5	424.5	30.58
46.1	1.41201	1.2126	515.8	425.4	30.65
46.2	1.41222	1.2131	517.2	426.3	30.74
46.3	1.41242	1.2137	518.6	427.3	30.82
46.4	1.41262	1.2142	519.9	428.2	30.90
46.5	1.41283	1.2148	521.3	429.1	30.98
46.6	1.41303	1.2154	522.7	430.1	31.06
46.7	1.41324	1.2159	524.1	431.0	31.15
46.8	1.41344	1.2165	525.4	431.9	31.22
46.9	1.41365	1.2170	526.8	432.9	31.31
47.0	1.41385	1.2176	528.2	433.8	31.39
47.1	1.41406	1.2181	529.6	434.7	31.47
47.2	1.41427	1.2187	530.9	435.7	31.55
47.3	1.41447	1.2192	532.3	436.6	31.63
47.4	1.41468	1.2198	533.7	437.5	31.72
47.5	1.41488	1.2204	535.1	438.5	31.80
47.6	1.41509	1.2209	536.5	439.4	31.88
47.7	1.41530	1.2215	537.9	440.3	31.97
47.8	1.41550	1.2220	539.2	441.3	32.04
47.9	1.41571	1.2226	540.6	442.2	32.13
48.0	1.41592	1.2232	542.0	443.1	32.21
48.1	1.41612	1.2237	543.4	444.1	32.29
48.2	1.41633	1.2243	544.8	445.0	32.38
48.3	1.41654	1.2248	546.2	445.9	32.46
48.4	1.41674	1.2254	547.6	446.8	32.54
48.5	1.41695	1.2260	549.0	447.8	32.63
48.6	1.41716	1.2265	550.4	448.7	32.71
48.7	1.41737	1.2271	551.8	449.6	32.79
48.8	1.41758	1.2277	553.2	450.6	32.88
48.9	1.41779	1.2282	554.6	451.5	32.96
49.0	1.41799	1.2288	556.0	452.4	33.04
49.1	1.41820	1.2294	557.4	453.4	33.13
49.2	1.41841	1.2299	558.8	454.3	33.21
49.3	1.41862	1.2305	560.2	455.2	33.29
49.4	1.41883	1.2311	561.6	456.2	33.38
49.5	1.41904	1.2316	563.0	457.1	33.46
49.6	1.41925	1.2322	564.4	458.0	33.54
49.7	1.41946	1.2328	565.8	458.9	33.63
49.8	1.41967	1.2333	567.2	459.9	33.71
49.9	1.41988	1.2339	568.6	460.8	33.79

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
50.0	1.42009	1.2345	570.0	461.7	33.88
50.1	1.42030	1.2350	571.4	462.7	33.96
50.2	1.42051	1.2356	572.8	463.6	34.04
50.3	1.42072	1.2362	574.2	464.5	34.12
50.4	1.42093	1.2368	575.6	465.4	34.21
50.5	1.42114	1.2373	577.1	466.4	34.30
50.6	1.42135	1.2379	578.5	467.3	34.38
50.7	1.42156	1.2385	579.9	468.2	34.46
50.8	1.42177	1.2390	581.3	469.2	34.55
50.9	1.42199	1.2396	582.7	470.1	34.63
51.0	1.42220	1.2402	584.2	471.0	34.72
51.1	1.42241	1.2408	585.6	471.9	34.80
51.2	1.42262	1.2413	587.0	472.9	34.89
51.3	1.42283	1.2419	588.4	473.8	34.97
51.4	1.42305	1.2425	589.9	474.7	35.06
51.5	1.42326	1.2431	591.3	475.7	35.14
51.6	1.42347	1.2436	592.7	476.6	35.22
51.7	1.42368	1.2442	594.1	477.5	35.31
51.8	1.42390	1.2448	595.6	478.4	35.40
51.9	1.42411	1.2454	597.0	479.4	35.48
52.0	1.42432	1.2460	598.4	480.3	35.56
52.1	1.42454	1.2465	599.9	481.2	35.65
52.2	1.42475	1.2471	601.3	482.1	35.74
52.3	1.42496	1.2477	602.7	483.1	35.82
52.4	1.42518	1.2483	604.2	484.0	35.91
52.5	1.42539	1.2488	605.6	484.9	35.99
52.6	1.42561	1.2494	607.0	485.8	36.07
52.7	1.42582	1.2500	608.5	486.8	36.16
52.8	1.42604	1.2506	609.9	487.7	36.25
52.9	1.42625	1.2512	611.4	488.6	36.34
53.0	1.42647	1.2518	612.8	489.5	36.42
53.1	1.42668	1.2523	614.2	490.5	36.50
53.2	1.42690	1.2529	615.7	491.4	36.59
53.3	1.42711	1.2535	617.1	492.3	36.67
53.4	1.42733	1.2541	618.6	493.2	36.76
53.5	1.42754	1.2547	620.0	494.2	36.85
53.6	1.42776	1.2553	621.5	495.1	36.94
53.7	1.42798	1.2558	622.9	496.0	37.02
53.8	1.42819	1.2564	624.4	496.9	37.11
53.9	1.42841	1.2570	625.8	497.9	37.19
54.0	1.42863	1.2576	627.3	498.8	37.28
54.1	1.42884	1.2582	628.7	499.7	37.36
54.2	1.42906	1.2588	630.2	500.6	37.45
54.3	1.42928	1.2594	631.7	501.6	37.54
54.4	1.42949	1.2600	633.1	502.5	37.63
54.5	1.42971	1.2606	634.6	503.4	37.71
54.6	1.42993	1.2611	636.0	504.3	37.80
54.7	1.43015	1.2617	637.5	505.2	37.89
54.8	1.43036	1.2623	639.0	506.2	37.98
54.9	1.43058	1.2629	640.4	507.1	38.06

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
55.0	1.43080	1.2635	641.9	508.0	38.15
55.1	1.43102	1.2641	643.4	508.9	38.24
55.2	1.43124	1.2647	644.8	509.9	38.32
55.3	1.43146	1.2653	646.3	510.8	38.41
55.4	1.43168	1.2659	647.8	511.7	38.50
55.5	1.43189	1.2665	649.2	512.6	38.58
55.6	1.43211	1.2671	650.7	513.5	38.67
55.7	1.43233	1.2677	652.2	514.5	38.76
55.8	1.43255	1.2683	653.7	515.4	38.85
55.9	1.43277	1.2689	655.1	516.3	38.93
56.0	1.43299	1.2695	656.6	517.2	39.02
56.1	1.43321	1.2701	658.1	518.1	39.11
56.2	1.43343	1.2706	659.6	519.1	39.20
56.3	1.43365	1.2712	661.0	520.0	39.28
56.4	1.43387	1.2718	662.5	520.9	39.37
56.5	1.43410	1.2724	664.0	521.8	39.46
56.6	1.43432	1.2730	665.5	522.7	39.55
56.7	1.43454	1.2736	667.0	523.7	39.64
56.8	1.43476	1.2742	668.5	524.6	39.73
56.9	1.43498	1.2748	669.9	525.5	39.81
57.0	1.43520	1.2754	671.4	526.4	39.90
57.1	1.43542	1.2760	672.9	527.3	39.99
57.2	1.43565	1.2766	674.4	528.3	40.08
57.3	1.43587	1.2773	675.9	529.2	40.17
57.4	1.43609	1.2779	677.4	530.1	40.26
57.5	1.43631	1.2785	678.9	531.0	40.35
57.6	1.43653	1.2791	680.4	531.9	40.44
57.7	1.43676	1.2797	681.9	532.8	40.53
57.8	1.43698	1.2803	683.4	533.8	40.61
57.9	1.43720	1.2809	684.9	534.7	40.70
58.0	1.43743	1.2815	686.4	535.6	40.79
58.1	1.43765	1.2821	687.9	536.5	40.88
58.2	1.43787	1.2827	689.4	537.4	40.97
58.3	1.43810	1.2833	690.9	538.3	41.06
58.4	1.43832	1.2839	692.4	539.3	41.15
58.5	1.43855	1.2845	693.9	540.2	41.24
58.6	1.43877	1.2851	695.4	541.1	41.33
58.7	1.43899	1.2857	696.9	542.0	41.42
58.8	1.43922	1.2863	698.4	542.9	41.51
58.9	1.43944	1.2870	699.9	543.8	41.60
59.0	1.43967	1.2876	701.4	544.8	41.68
59.1	1.43989	1.2882	702.9	545.7	41.77
59.2	1.44012	1.2888	704.4	546.6	41.86
59.3	1.44035	1.2894	706.0	547.5	41.96
59.4	1.44057	1.2900	707.5	548.4	42.05
59.5	1.44080	1.2906	709.0	549.3	42.14
59.6	1.44102	1.2912	710.5	550.2	42.23
59.7	1.44125	1.2919	712.0	551.1	42.31
59.8	1.44148	1.2925	713.5	552.1	42.40
59.9	1.44170	1.2931	715.1	553.0	42.50

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
60.0	1.44193	1.2937	716.6	553.9	42.59
60.1	1.44216	1.2943	718.1	554.8	42.68
60.2	1.44238	1.2949	719.6	555.7	42.77
60.3	1.44261	1.2956	721.1	556.6	42.85
60.4	1.44284	1.2962	722.7	557.5	42.95
60.5	1.44306	1.2968	724.2	558.4	43.04
60.6	1.44329	1.2974	725.7	559.4	43.13
60.7	1.44352	1.2980	727.3	560.3	43.22
60.8	1.44375	1.2986	728.8	561.2	43.31
60.9	1.44398	1.2993	730.3	562.1	43.40
61.0	1.44420	1.2999	731.8	563.0	43.49
61.1	1.44443	1.3005	733.4	563.9	43.59
61.2	1.44466	1.3011	734.9	564.8	43.68
61.3	1.44489	1.3017	736.4	565.7	43.76
61.4	1.44512	1.3024	738.0	566.6	43.86
61.5	1.44535	1.3030	739.5	567.6	43.95
61.6	1.44558	1.3036	741.1	568.5	44.04
61.7	1.44581	1.3042	742.6	569.4	44.13
61.8	1.44604	1.3049	744.1	570.3	44.22
61.9	1.44627	1.3055	745.7	571.2	44.32
62.0	1.44650	1.3061	747.2	572.1	44.41
62.1	1.44673	1.3067	748.8	573.0	44.50
62.2	1.44696	1.3074	750.3	573.9	44.59
62.3	1.44719	1.3080	751.9	574.8	44.69
62.4	1.44742	1.3086	753.4	575.7	44.77
62.5	1.44765	1.3092	755.0	576.6	44.87
62.6	1.44788	1.3099	756.5	577.5	44.96
62.7	1.44811	1.3105	758.1	578.5	45.05
62.8	1.44834	1.3111	759.6	579.4	45.14
62.9	1.44858	1.3118	761.2	580.3	45.24
63.0	1.44881	1.3124	762.7	581.2	45.33
63.1	1.44904	1.3130	764.3	582.1	45.42
63.2	1.44927	1.3137	765.8	583.0	45.51
63.3	1.44950	1.3143	767.4	583.9	45.61
63.4	1.44974	1.3149	769.0	584.8	45.70
63.5	1.44997	1.3155	770.5	585.7	45.79
63.6	1.45020	1.3162	772.1	586.6	45.89
63.7	1.45043	1.3168	773.6	587.5	45.98
63.8	1.45067	1.3174	775.2	588.4	46.07
63.9	1.45090	1.3181	776.8	589.3	46.17
64.0	1.45113	1.3187	778.3	590.2	46.25
64.1	1.45137	1.3193	779.9	591.1	46.35
64.2	1.45160	1.3200	781.5	592.0	46.44
64.3	1.45184	1.3206	783.0	592.9	46.53
64.4	1.45207	1.3213	784.6	593.8	46.63
64.5	1.45230	1.3219	786.2	594.7	46.72
64.6	1.45254	1.3225	787.8	595.6	46.82
64.7	1.45277	1.3232	789.3	596.5	46.91
64.8	1.45301	1.3238	790.9	597.4	47.00
64.9	1.45324	1.3244	792.5	598.3	47.10

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
65.0	1.45348	1.3251	794.1	599.3	47.19
65.1	1.45371	1.3257	795.6	600.2	47.28
65.2	1.45395	1.3264	797.2	601.1	47.38
65.3	1.45418	1.3270	798.8	602.0	47.47
65.4	1.45442	1.3276	800.4	602.9	47.57
65.5	1.45466	1.3283	802.0	603.8	47.66
65.6	1.45489	1.3289	803.6	604.7	47.76
65.7	1.45513	1.3296	805.1	605.6	47.85
65.8	1.45537	1.3302	806.7	606.5	47.94
65.9	1.45560	1.3309	808.3	607.4	48.04
66.0	1.45584	1.3315	809.9	608.3	48.13
66.1	1.45608	1.3322	811.5	609.2	48.23
66.2	1.45631	1.3328	813.1	610.1	48.32
66.3	1.45655	1.3334	814.7	611.0	48.42
66.4	1.45679	1.3341	816.3	611.9	48.51
66.5	1.45703	1.3347	817.9	612.8	48.61
66.6	1.45726	1.3354	819.5	613.7	48.70
66.7	1.45750	1.3360	821.1	614.6	48.80
66.8	1.45774	1.3367	822.7	615.5	48.89
66.9	1.45798	1.3373	824.3	616.3	48.99
67.0	1.45822	1.3380	825.9	617.2	49.08
67.1	1.45846	1.3386	827.5	618.1	49.18
67.2	1.45870	1.3393	829.1	619.0	49.27
67.3	1.45893	1.3399	830.7	619.9	49.37
67.4	1.45917	1.3406	832.3	620.8	49.46
67.5	1.45941	1.3412	833.9	621.7	49.56
67.6	1.45965	1.3419	835.5	622.6	49.65
67.7	1.45989	1.3425	837.1	623.5	49.75
67.8	1.46013	1.3432	838.7	624.4	49.84
67.9	1.46037	1.3438	840.3	625.3	49.94
68.0	1.46061	1.3445	841.9	626.2	50.03
68.1	1.46085	1.3451	843.6	627.1	50.14
68.2	1.46109	1.3458	845.2	628.0	50.23
68.3	1.46134	1.3464	846.8	628.9	50.33
68.4	1.46158	1.3471	848.4	629.8	50.42
68.5	1.46182	1.3478	850.0	630.7	50.52
68.6	1.46206	1.3484	851.6	631.6	50.61
68.7	1.46230	1.3491	853.3	632.5	50.71
68.8	1.46254	1.3497	854.9	633.4	50.81
68.9	1.46278	1.3504	856.5	634.3	50.90
69.0	1.46303	1.3510	858.1	635.2	51.00
69.1	1.46327	1.3517	859.8	636.1	51.10
69.2	1.46351	1.3524	861.4	636.9	51.19
69.3	1.46375	1.3530	863.0	637.8	51.29
69.4	1.46400	1.3537	864.7	638.7	51.39
69.5	1.46424	1.3543	866.3	639.6	51.48
69.6	1.46448	1.3550	867.9	640.5	51.58
69.7	1.46473	1.3557	869.5	641.4	51.67
69.8	1.46497	1.3563	871.2	642.3	51.78
69.9	1.46521	1.3570	872.8	643.2	51.87

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
70.0	1.46546	1.3576	874.5	644.1	51.97
70.1	1.46570	1.3583	876.1	645.0	52.07
70.2	1.46594	1.3590	877.7	645.9	52.16
70.3	1.46619	1.3596	879.4	646.8	52.26
70.4	1.46643	1.3603	881.0	647.7	52.36
70.5	1.46668	1.3610	882.7	648.5	52.46
70.6	1.46692	1.3616	884.3	649.4	52.55
70.7	1.46717	1.3623	886.0	650.3	52.65
70.8	1.46741	1.3630	887.6	651.2	52.75
70.9	1.46766	1.3636	889.3	652.1	52.85
71.0	1.46790	1.3643	890.9	653.0	52.95
71.1	1.46815	1.3650	892.6	653.9	53.05
71.2	1.46840	1.3656	894.2	654.8	53.14
71.3	1.46864	1.3663	895.9	655.7	53.24
71.4	1.46889	1.3670	897.5	656.6	53.34
71.5	1.46913	1.3676	899.2	657.5	53.44
71.6	1.46938	1.3683	900.8	658.3	53.53
71.7	1.46963	1.3690	902.5	659.2	53.64
71.8	1.46987	1.3696	904.1	660.1	53.73
71.9	1.47012	1.3703	905.8	661.0	53.83
72.0	1.47037	1.3710	907.5	661.9	53.93
72.1	1.47062	1.3717	909.1	662.8	54.03
72.2	1.47086	1.3723	910.8	663.7	54.13
72.3	1.47111	1.3730	912.5	664.6	54.23
72.4	1.47136	1.3737	914.1	665.5	54.32
72.5	1.47161	1.3743	915.8	666.3	54.43
72.6	1.47186	1.3750	917.5	667.2	54.53
72.7	1.47210	1.3757	919.1	668.1	54.62
72.8	1.47235	1.3764	920.8	669.0	54.72
72.9	1.47260	1.3770	922.5	669.9	54.82
73.0	1.47285	1.3777	924.2	670.8	54.93
73.1	1.47310	1.3784	925.8	671.7	55.02
73.2	1.47335	1.3791	927.5	672.6	55.12
73.3	1.47360	1.3797	929.2	673.5	55.22
73.4	1.47385	1.3804	930.9	674.3	55.32
73.5	1.47410	1.3811	932.6	675.2	55.42
73.6	1.47435	1.3818	934.3	676.1	55.53
73.7	1.47460	1.3825	935.9	677.0	55.62
73.8	1.47485	1.3831	937.6	677.9	55.72
73.9	1.47510	1.3838	939.3	678.8	55.82
74.0	1.47535	1.3845	941.0	679.7	55.92
74.1	1.47560	1.3852	942.7	680.6	56.02
74.2	1.47585	1.3859	944.4	681.4	56.13
74.3	1.47610	1.3865	946.1	682.3	56.23
74.4	1.47635	1.3872	947.8	683.2	56.33
74.5	1.47661	1.3879	949.5	684.1	56.43
74.6	1.47686	1.3886	951.2	685.0	56.53
74.7	1.47711	1.3893	952.9	685.9	56.63
74.8	1.47736	1.3899	954.6	686.8	56.73
74.9	1.47761	1.3906	956.3	687.7	56.83

Table 23. Sucrose refractive index. Table giving the sugar concentration in rectified concentrated must in grams L⁻¹ or grams Kg⁻¹. Determined by means of a refractometer graduated either in % by mass sucrose at 20 °C or in refractive index at 20 °C.

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
50.0	1.42008	1.2342	627.6	508.5	37.30
50.1	1.42029	1.2348	629.3	509.6	37.40
50.2	1.42050	1.2355	630.9	510.6	37.49
50.3	1.42071	1.2362	632.4	511.6	37.58
50.4	1.42092	1.2367	634.1	512.7	37.68
50.5	1.42113	1.2374	635.7	513.7	37.78
50.6	1.42135	1.2381	637.3	514.7	37.87
50.7	1.42156	1.2386	638.7	515.7	37.96
50.8	1.42177	1.2391	640.4	516.8	38.06
50.9	1.42198	1.2396	641.9	517.8	38.15
51.0	1.42219	1.2401	643.4	518.8	38.24
51.1	1.42240	1.2406	645.0	519.9	38.33
51.2	1.42261	1.2411	646.5	520.9	38.42
51.3	1.42282	1.2416	648.1	522.0	38.52
51.4	1.42304	1.2421	649.6	523.0	38.61
51.5	1.42325	1.2427	651.2	524.0	38.70
51.6	1.42347	1.2434	652.9	525.1	38.80
51.7	1.42368	1.2441	654.5	526.1	38.90
51.8	1.42389	1.2447	656.1	527.1	38.99
51.9	1.42410	1.2454	657.8	528.2	39.09
52.0	1.42432	1.2461	659.4	529.2	39.19
52.1	1.42453	1.2466	661.0	530.2	39.28
52.2	1.42475	1.2470	662.5	531.3	39.37
52.3	1.42496	1.2475	664.1	532.3	39.47
52.4	1.42517	1.2480	665.6	533.3	39.56
52.5	1.42538	1.2486	667.2	534.4	39.65
52.6	1.42560	1.2493	668.9	535.4	39.75
52.7	1.42581	1.2500	670.5	536.4	39.85
52.8	1.42603	1.2506	672.2	537.5	39.95
52.9	1.42624	1.2513	673.8	538.5	40.04
53.0	1.42645	1.2520	675.5	539.5	40.14
53.1	1.42667	1.2525	677.1	540.6	40.24
53.2	1.42689	1.2530	678.5	541.5	40.32
53.3	1.42711	1.2535	680.2	542.6	40.42
53.4	1.42733	1.2540	681.8	543.7	40.52
53.5	1.42754	1.2546	683.4	544.7	40.61
53.6	1.42776	1.2553	685.1	545.8	40.72
53.7	1.42797	1.2560	686.7	546.7	40.81
53.8	1.42819	1.2566	688.4	547.8	40.91
53.9	1.42840	1.2573	690.1	548.9	41.01
54.0	1.42861	1.2580	691.7	549.8	41.11
54.1	1.42884	1.2585	693.3	550.9	41.20
54.2	1.42906	1.2590	694.9	551.9	41.30
54.3	1.42927	1.2595	696.5	553.0	41.39
54.4	1.42949	1.2600	698.1	554.0	41.49
54.5	1.42971	1.2606	699.7	555.1	41.58
54.6	1.42993	1.2613	701.4	556.1	41.68
54.7	1.43014	1.2620	703.1	557.1	41.79
54.8	1.43036	1.2625	704.7	558.2	41.88
54.9	1.43058	1.2630	706.2	559.1	41.97

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
55.0	1.43079	1.2635	707.8	560.2	42.06
55.1	1.43102	1.2639	709.4	561.3	42.16
55.2	1.43124	1.2645	711.0	562.3	42.25
55.3	1.43146	1.2652	712.7	563.3	42.36
55.4	1.43168	1.2659	714.4	564.3	42.46
55.5	1.43189	1.2665	716.1	565.4	42.56
55.6	1.43211	1.2672	717.8	566.4	42.66
55.7	1.43233	1.2679	719.5	567.5	42.76
55.8	1.43255	1.2685	721.1	568.5	42.85
55.9	1.43277	1.2692	722.8	569.5	42.96
56.0	1.43298	1.2699	724.5	570.5	43.06
56.1	1.43321	1.2703	726.1	571.6	43.15
56.2	1.43343	1.2708	727.7	572.6	43.25
56.3	1.43365	1.2713	729.3	573.7	43.34
56.4	1.43387	1.2718	730.9	574.7	43.44
56.5	1.43409	1.2724	732.6	575.8	43.54
56.6	1.43431	1.2731	734.3	576.8	43.64
56.7	1.43454	1.2738	736.0	577.8	43.74
56.8	1.43476	1.2744	737.6	578.8	43.84
56.9	1.43498	1.2751	739.4	579.9	43.94
57.0	1.43519	1.2758	741.1	580.9	44.04
57.1	1.43542	1.2763	742.8	582.0	44.14
57.2	1.43564	1.2768	744.4	583.0	44.24
57.3	1.43586	1.2773	745.9	584.0	44.33
57.4	1.43609	1.2778	747.6	585.1	44.43
57.5	1.43631	1.2784	749.3	586.1	44.53
57.6	1.43653	1.2791	751.0	587.1	44.63
57.7	1.43675	1.2798	752.7	588.1	44.73
57.8	1.43698	1.2804	754.4	589.2	44.83
57.9	1.43720	1.2810	756.1	590.2	44.94
58.0	1.43741	1.2818	757.8	591.2	45.04
58.1	1.43764	1.2822	759.5	592.3	45.14
58.2	1.43784	1.2827	761.1	593.4	45.23
58.3	1.43909	1.2832	762.6	594.3	45.32
58.4	1.43832	1.2837	764.3	595.4	45.42
58.5	1.43854	1.2843	766.0	596.4	45.52
58.6	1.43877	1.2850	767.8	597.5	45.63
58.7	1.43899	1.2857	769.5	598.5	45.73
58.8	1.43922	1.2863	771.1	599.5	45.83
58.9	1.43944	1.2869	772.9	600.6	45.93
59.0	1.43966	1.2876	774.6	601.6	46.03
59.1	1.43988	1.2882	776.3	602.6	46.14
59.2	1.44011	1.2889	778.1	603.7	46.24
59.3	1.44034	1.2896	779.8	604.7	46.34
59.4	1.44057	1.2902	781.6	605.8	46.45
59.5	1.44079	1.2909	783.3	606.8	46.55
59.6	1.44102	1.2916	785.2	607.9	46.66
59.7	1.44124	1.2921	786.8	608.9	46.76
59.8	1.44147	1.2926	788.4	609.9	46.85
59.9	1.44169	1.2931	790.0	610.9	46.95

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
60.0	1.44192	1.2936	791.7	612.0	47.05
60.1	1.44215	1.2942	793.3	613.0	47.15
60.2	1.44238	1.2949	795.2	614.1	47.26
60.3	1.44260	1.2956	796.9	615.1	47.36
60.4	1.44283	1.2962	798.6	616.1	47.46
60.5	1.44305	1.2969	800.5	617.2	47.57
60.6	1.44328	1.2976	802.2	618.2	47.67
60.7	1.44351	1.2981	803.9	619.3	47.78
60.8	1.44374	1.2986	805.5	620.3	47.87
60.9	1.44397	1.2991	807.1	621.3	47.97
61.0	1.44419	1.2996	808.7	622.3	48.06
61.1	1.44442	1.3002	810.5	623.4	48.17
61.2	1.44465	1.3009	812.3	624.4	48.27
61.3	1.44488	1.3016	814.2	625.5	48.39
61.4	1.44511	1.3022	815.8	626.5	48.48
61.5	1.44534	1.3029	817.7	627.6	48.60
61.6	1.44557	1.3036	819.4	628.6	48.70
61.7	1.44580	1.3042	821.3	629.7	48.81
61.8	1.44603	1.3049	823.0	630.7	48.91
61.9	1.44626	1.3056	824.8	631.7	49.02
62.0	1.44648	1.3062	826.6	632.8	49.12
62.1	1.44672	1.3068	828.3	633.8	49.23
62.2	1.44695	1.3075	830.0	634.8	49.33
62.3	1.44718	1.3080	831.8	635.9	49.43
62.4	1.44741	1.3085	833.4	636.9	49.53
62.5	1.44764	1.3090	835.1	638.0	49.63
62.6	1.44787	1.3095	836.8	639.0	49.73
62.7	1.44810	1.3101	838.5	640.0	49.83
62.8	1.44833	1.3108	840.2	641.0	49.93
62.9	1.44856	1.3115	842.1	642.1	50.05
63.0	1.44879	1.3121	843.8	643.1	50.15
63.1	1.44902	1.3128	845.7	644.2	50.26
63.2	1.44926	1.3135	847.5	645.2	50.37
63.3	1.44949	1.3141	849.3	646.3	50.47
63.4	1.44972	1.3148	851.1	647.3	50.58
63.5	1.44995	1.3155	853.0	648.4	50.69
63.6	1.45019	1.3161	854.7	649.4	50.79
63.7	1.45042	1.3168	856.5	650.4	50.90
63.8	1.45065	1.3175	858.4	651.5	51.01
63.9	1.45088	1.3180	860.0	652.5	51.11
64.0	1.45112	1.3185	861.6	653.5	51.20
64.1	1.45135	1.3190	863.4	654.6	51.31
64.2	1.45158	1.3195	865.1	655.6	51.41
64.3	1.45181	1.3201	866.9	656.7	51.52
64.4	1.45205	1.3208	868.7	657.7	51.63
64.5	1.45228	1.3215	870.6	658.8	51.74
64.6	1.45252	1.3221	872.3	659.8	51.84
64.7	1.45275	1.3228	874.1	660.8	51.95
64.8	1.45299	1.3235	876.0	661.9	52.06
64.9	1.45322	1.3241	877.8	662.9	52.17

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
65.0	1.45347	1.3248	879.7	664.0	52.28
65.1	1.45369	1.3255	881.5	665.0	52.39
65.2	1.45393	1.3261	883.2	666.0	52.49
65.3	1.45416	1.3268	885.0	667.0	52.60
65.4	1.45440	1.3275	886.9	668.1	52.71
65.5	1.45463	1.3281	888.8	669.2	52.82
65.6	1.45487	1.3288	890.6	670.2	52.93
65.7	1.45510	1.3295	892.4	671.2	53.04
65.8	1.45534	1.3301	894.2	672.3	53.14
65.9	1.45557	1.3308	896.0	673.3	53.25
66.0	1.45583	1.3315	898.0	674.4	53.37
66.1	1.45605	1.3320	899.6	675.4	53.46
66.2	1.45629	1.3325	901.3	676.4	53.56
66.3	1.45652	1.3330	903.1	677.5	53.67
66.4	1.45676	1.3335	904.8	678.5	53.77
66.5	1.45700	1.3341	906.7	679.6	53.89
66.6	1.45724	1.3348	908.5	680.6	53.99
66.7	1.45747	1.3355	910.4	681.7	54.11
66.8	1.45771	1.3361	912.2	682.7	54.21
66.9	1.45795	1.3367	913.9	683.7	54.31
67.0	1.45820	1.3374	915.9	684.8	54.43
67.1	1.45843	1.3380	917.6	685.8	54.53
67.2	1.45867	1.3387	919.6	686.9	54.65
67.3	1.45890	1.3395	921.4	687.9	54.76
67.4	1.45914	1.3400	923.1	688.9	54.86
67.5	1.45938	1.3407	925.1	690.0	54.98
67.6	1.45962	1.3415	927.0	691.0	55.09
67.7	1.45986	1.3420	928.8	692.1	55.20
67.8	1.46010	1.3427	930.6	693.1	55.31
67.9	1.46034	1.3434	932.6	694.2	55.42
68.0	1.46060	1.3440	934.4	695.2	55.53
68.1	1.46082	1.3447	936.2	696.2	55.64
68.2	1.46106	1.3454	938.0	697.2	55.75
68.3	1.46130	1.3460	939.9	698.3	55.86
68.4	1.46154	1.3466	941.8	699.4	55.97
68.5	1.46178	1.3473	943.7	700.4	56.08
68.6	1.46202	1.3479	945.4	701.4	56.19
68.7	1.46226	1.3486	947.4	702.5	56.30
68.8	1.46251	1.3493	949.2	703.5	56.41
68.9	1.46275	1.3499	951.1	704.6	56.52
69.0	1.46301	1.3506	953.0	705.6	56.64
69.1	1.46323	1.3513	954.8	706.6	56.74
69.2	1.46347	1.3519	956.7	707.7	56.86
69.3	1.46371	1.3526	958.6	708.7	56.97
69.4	1.46396	1.3533	960.6	709.8	57.09
69.5	1.46420	1.3539	962.4	710.8	57.20
69.6	1.46444	1.3546	964.3	711.9	57.31
69.7	1.46468	1.3553	966.2	712.9	57.42
69.8	1.46493	1.3560	968.2	714.0	57.54
69.9	1.46517	1.3566	970.0	715.0	57.65

REMARKS

The refractometer used must be fitted with a scale giving:

Either percentage by mass of sucrose to 0.1% or refractive indices to four decimal places.

The refractometer must be equipped with a thermometer having a scale extending at least from +15 °C to +25 °C and with a system for circulating water that will enable measurements to be made at a temperature of 20 ± 5 °C. The operating instructions for this instrument must be strictly adhered to, particularly with regard to calibration and the light source.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Abbe refractometer

REFERENCES

OIV-MA-AS2-02. Evaluation by refractometry of the sugar concentration in grape musts, concentrated grape musts, and rectified concentrated grape musts (Oeno 466/2012). Compendium of international methods of wine and must analysis, vol. 1. Paris, France: International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV); 61–82.

4.5.4. Ratio of soluble solids to titratable acidity (ss/ta)

PRINCIPLE

The ratio between titratable acidity and soluble solids content increases as the fruit ripens and can also be used as a maturity index. The ratio (TA/SS) is apparently more closely related to quality than the soluble solids content or titratable acidity analysed separately (Casquero and Guerra, 2009).

PROCEDURE

Determined by dividing the soluble solid content by the titratable acidity obtained in the samples.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment not needed

REFERENCES

Casquero, P.A. & Guerra, M. (2009). Harvest parameters to optimise storage life of European plum 'Oullins Gage'. *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, 44(10), 2049-2054.

4.5.5. Ascorbic acid (vitamin C)

PRINCIPLE

The determination of ascorbic acid content is based on the method proposed by Terada et al. (1979), using spectrophotometry.

PROCEDURE

1. 1 g of the fresh tissue is mixed with 10 mL of AM.
2. It is centrifuged at 15,000 rpm at 4 °C for 20 min, and the supernatant is filtered
3. 1 mL is pipetted, 50 µL (1 drop) of 0.2% DCPIP is added and then, the mixture is shake and incubated at room temperature for 1 hour.
4. 1 mL of 2% thiourea is added and shaken well.

5. 0.5 mL of 2% DNPH (except for the white) is added. The solution is mixed, covered and left in a water bath at 60 °C for 3 hours (except for the white).
6. Then, it is placed in an ice bath and carefully 2.5 mL of ice-cold H₂SO₄ are added (including the blank) and stirred to dissolve the osazone (heat destroys DHA-osazone along with interfering osazones).
7. 0.5 mL of 2% DNPH are added to the blank and shake.
8. The absorbance is read at 540 nm at room temperature.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Sample homogenizer
- Spectrophotometer
- Refrigerated centrifuge
- Vortex
- 50 mL falcon tubes
- Spatula
- 100 mL beaker
- 15 mL test tubes
- Automatic pipettes

Solutions:

Acid Mixture (AM):

- 6% HPO₃ (metaphosphoric acid) containing 2 N acetic acid
- 60 g metaphosphoric acid - grind the material in plastic wrap
- 120 g (~115.3 mL) glacial acetic acid (MM = 60.05; 99.7% w/w)
- Distilled water (V_f = 1 L) (add water, even without topping up, to dissolve the metaphosphoric acid)
- Store in the fridge for 7 - 10 days

0.2% 2,6 dichlorophenolindophenol (DCPIP):

- 200 mg DCPIP
- Distilled water (V_f = 100 mL)
- Filter if necessary and store cold in a dark bottle

5% Thiourea in 2% HPO₃:

- 4 g thiourea
- 10 g metaphosphoric acid
- Distilled water (V_f = 200 mL)
- Dissolve HPO₃ in distilled water, add thiourea and mix
- Store in a dark bottle in the cold for up to 2 months

2% Dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) in 9 N H₂SO₄:

- g DNPH (MW = 198.14)
- 44.14 of H₂SO₄ (MW = 98.08; 95 to 98% w/w)
- Slowly dissolve DNPH in H₂SO₄ in an ice bath
- Carefully top up to 100 mL with distilled water (if you get a white cloud because of the H₂SO₄, you should centrifuge)
- Place a bowl of ice on top of a magnetic stirrer in the hood. Place the beaker (100 mL, 50 mL) with H₂SO₄ as the stirring magnet. Add DNPH little by little.
- The solution can be clarified by filtration or centrifugation and stored for 2 weeks.
- 90% H₂SO₄
- 450 mL H₂SO₄ + 50 mL distilled water
- Standard solution of ascorbic acid (AA)
- 100 mg of ascorbic acid in 100 mL of acid mixture. Prepared at the time of use.

Calibration curve

Dilution of the standard solution

5 µg AA mL⁻¹ = 50 µL of AA + 9.95 mL of AM

10 µg AA mL⁻¹ = 100 µL of AA + 9.9 mL of AM

20 µg AA mL⁻¹ = 200 µL of AA + 9.8 mL of AM

30 µg AA mL⁻¹ = 300 µL of AA + 9.7 mL of AM

REFERENCES

Terada, M., Watanabe, Y., Kunitomo, M. & Hayashi, E. (1978). Differential rapid analysis of ascorbic acid and ascorbic acid 2-sulfate by dinitrophenylhydrazine method. *Analytical Biochemistry*, 84(2), 604-608.

4.5.6. Ash content

PRINCIPLE

Quantified by gravimetry after incineration in a muffle furnace at 550 °C.

PROCEDURE

The Vulcan 3-550 Muffle is switched on. Then the crucibles are washed and is proceeded with their calcination.

Calcination of crucibles

- The clean crucibles are placed in the muffle furnace at 550 °C for 1 h. The crucibles must be properly identified in pencil.

Note: Programming the Muffle for calcination: Click on the number 5 and then ENTER. The Muffle is automatically programmed for temperature and calcination time.

Crucible calcination program: R1= 20 °C; R2= 20 °C; R3= 40 °C; T1= 100 °C; T2= 200 °C; T3= 550 °C; H1= 0.05 min. H2= 0.05 min. H3= 1 h.

- START and the calcination process begins.
- An audible alarm sounds once the crucibles have finished calcining.
- The temperature is allowed to drop to 100 °C and the muffle furnace is carefully opened wearing suitable gloves.
- Using tweezers, the crucibles are removed from the Muffle and they are placed in a desiccator until they are cooled down.
- The crucibles are weighed on an analytical balance, recording their weight accurately.

Calcination of the samples

- One gram of sample is weighed on an analytical balance into the previously calcined and weighed crucibles, recording its weight. Always work in duplicate.

Note: When weighing the sample, it is also necessary to determine its % R.S (dry residue) using the Kern MRS 120-3 analytical balance.

- The crucibles are placed with the flour in the muffle furnace at 550 °C for 6 hours to determine the ash.

Note: The muffle furnace must be programmed for ash determination: Click on the number 9 and then ENTER. The Muffle is automatically programmed to the specific parameters for ash quantification.

Sample calcination program: R1= 5 °C; R2= 5 °C; R3= 40 °C; T1= 100 °C; T2= 200 °C; T3= 550 °C; H1= 15 min; H2= 5 min; H3= 5H.

R = Rate of temperature increase in degrees per minute

T = Maximum temperature reached in each stage or "ramp"

H = Time in minutes or hours that each stage remains at temperature T1, T2 and T3.

- The steps described in A2 to A5 are repeated.
- The crucibles are weighed on an analytical balance and the ash content is quantified gravimetrically.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Muffle Vulcan 3-550

CALCULATIONS

The % ash is calculated as follows:

$$\%ash = \frac{(m \times 100)}{(100 - H)}$$

Where:

m= Ash mass expressed in grams;

H= Moisture content of the sample expressed as a percentage;

REFERENCES

Norma Portuguesa NP 518. (1986). *Cereais e Leguminosas - Determinação do teor de cinza. Processo por incineração a 550 °C*. Lisboa: Instituto Português da Qualidade.

4.5.7. DPPH antioxidant capacity

PRINCIPLE

The DPPH method (Brand-Williams et al., 1995) is based on the capture of the DPPH radical (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) by antioxidants, producing a decrease in absorbance at 515 nm. This method was modified by Sánchez-Moreno et al. (1998) to measure the kinetic parameters.

PROCEDURE

DPPH curve

From the initial DPPH solution (60 M), 10 mL volumetric flasks are prepared, with solutions varying in concentration from 10 M to 50 M according to Table 24.

Table 24. Preparation of solutions for DPPH curve

DPPH solution (mL)	Methyl alcohol (mL)	Final DPPH concentration (µM)
0	10	0
1.7	8.3	10
3.3	6.7	20
5.0	5.0	30
6.7	3.3	40
8.3	1.7	50
10	0	60

Determination of DPPH curve

In a dark environment, an aliquot of approximately 4 mL is transferred of each DPPH solution (10 µM, 20 µM, 30 µM, 40 µM, 50 µM and 60 µM) into glass cuvettes and they are read in a spectrophotometer at 515 nm. Methyl alcohol is used as a blank to calibrate the spectrophotometer.

The DPPH concentrations (µM) are plot on the X axis and the respective absorbance on the Y axis and the straight line equation is calculated.

Obtaining fruit extracts

From 1 to 25 g of sample are used, depending on the fruit. The sample is weighed into a 100 mL beaker and 40 mL of 50% methanol are added. The solution is mixed and left to stand at room temperature for 60 min. It is centrifuged at 25,406.55 g (15,000 rpm) for 15 min, and then, the supernatant is transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. To the residue of the first extraction, 40 mL of 70% acetone are added, homogenized, left to stand at room temperature for 60 min, and centrifuged again at 25,406.55 g (15,000 rpm) for 15 min. The supernatant is transferred to the volumetric flask containing the first supernatant and the volume is top up to 100 mL with distilled water.

Determination of total antioxidant activity (TAA)

Using the extract obtained in the previous section, at least three different dilutions are prepared in triplicate in test tubes. In a dark environment, a 0.1 mL aliquot of each dilution is transferred of the extract to test tubes containing 3.9 mL of the DPPH radical (item 0.06 mM DPPH solution) and homogenized in a tube shaker. 0.1 mL of the control solution (control solution of methyl alcohol, acetone and water) is used with 3.9 mL of the DPPH radical and mixed. Methyl alcohol is used as a blank to calibrate the spectrophotometer. The readings (515 nm) should be monitored every minute, observing the reduction in absorbance until it stabilizes. The final absorbance reading for calculating the EC₅₀ should only be taken after the absorbance has stabilized (EC₅₀ time). For subsequent experiments with the same fruit, the reading can only be taken at the time previously established (EC₅₀ time), accompanied by the initial reading of the control.

After reading, (Eq. 1) the value corresponding to half the initial absorbance of the control is substituted for the y of the DPPH curve equation to find the consumption in μM DPPH and then transform to g DPPH.

Control equivalence and DPPH

$$y = ax - b \quad \text{eq.1}$$

y = Initial absorbance of control / 2 (item determination of total antioxidant activity)

x = result in μM DPPH

Note: convert to g DPPH using the transformation:

$$g \text{ DPPH} = \left(\frac{\mu\text{M DPPH}}{1.000.000} \right) \times 394.3 \text{ (molecular weight of DPPH)}$$

From the absorbances obtained from the different dilutions of the extracts, the absorbance on the Y axis and the dilution (mg L⁻¹) on the X axis are plot and the equation of the line (Eq. 2) is determined. To calculate the TAA, the absorbance equivalent to 50%

of the DPPH concentration (item determination of total antioxidant activity) is replaced with y (Eq.2) and the result that corresponds to the sample needed to reduce the initial concentration of the DPPH radical by 50% (EC_{50}) is found.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Test tube shaker
- Analytical balance
- 100 mL and 1,000 mL volumetric flask
- Digital chronometer
- Glass cubes (4 x 1 cm)
- Spectrophotometer
- Automatic pipette
- 50 mL beaker
- Test tubes with screw cap (8 mL)

Reagents:

- Acetone
- Methyl alcohol
- Distilled water
- DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picryl-hydrazyl) (PM = 394.3) - Sigma, code 095K1452, or equivalent

Solutions:

- 50% methyl alcohol solution:

500 mL of methyl alcohol is added to 1 L volumetric flask. It is made up to 1,000 mL with distilled water, mixed, and transferred to a labelled glass jar. It is stored at room temperature for an indefinite period.

- 70% acetone solution:

A 70% acetone solution is prepared by adding 700 mL of ketone to a 1 L volumetric flask. It is made up to 1,000 mL with distilled water, mixed, and transferred to a labelled glass bottle. It is stored at room temperature indefinitely.

- Control solution of methyl alcohol, acetone and water:

In a 100 mL volumetric flask, 40 mL of the 50% methyl alcohol solution and 40 mL of the 70% ketone solution are added. It is made up to 100 mL with distilled water, mixed, and transferred to a labelled glass jar. It is stored at room temperature for an indefinite period.

- 0.06 mM DPPH solution:

A 0.06 mM DPPH solution is prepared by dissolving 2.4 mg of DPPH in methyl alcohol and making up to 100 mL in a volumetric flask filled with methyl alcohol. It is homogenized and transferred to an amber glass flask, labelled accordingly. It is prepared and used only on the day of analysis.

CALCULATIONS

EC₅₀ calculation

$$y = -ax + b \quad \text{eq.2}$$

Where:

y = Initial absorbance of control / 2 (item determination of total antioxidant activity)

x = EC₅₀ (mg L⁻¹)

From the result (mg L⁻¹) found in equation 2, divide by 1,000 to get the value in g and then divide by the value found in g DPPH (Eq. 1) to get the final result (Eq. 3) which is expressed in g fruit (edible portion) / g DPPH.

EC₅₀ expressed in g fruit / g DPPH

$$\frac{g \text{ fruit}}{g \text{ DPPH}} = \frac{\left(\frac{EC_{50}}{1000 \times 1}\right)}{g \text{ DPPH}} \quad \text{eq.3}$$

REFERENCES

Brand-Williams, W., Cuvelier, M.E. & Berset, C.L.W.T. (1995). Use of a free radical method to evaluate antioxidant activity. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*, 28(1), 25-30.

Rufino, M.D.S.M., Alves, R.E., de Brito, E.S., de Moraes, S.M., Sampaio, C.D.G., Pérez-Jimenez, J. & Saura-Calixto, F.D. (2007). Metodologia científica: determinação da atividade antioxidante total em frutas pela captura do radical livre DPPH.

4.5.8. Characteristics of the fruit

PRINCIPLE

Understanding the fruit characteristics of custard apple is important for various reasons. It helps in assessing the fruit's ripeness, quality, and suitability for consumption. Knowledge of its physical attributes such as size, shape, colour, and texture aids in grading and sorting for market purposes. Additionally, understanding its nutritional composition provides valuable information for dietary and culinary purposes.

PROCEDURE

Perimeter and length of the fruit: It is analysed fortnightly, starting when they are around 2 cm long until they are harvested, using a calliper. Perimeter measurements are taken based on the median part of the fruit. The length is measured from the base to the apical part of the fruit with a pachymeter.

Mass and number of fruits: Fruit mass is obtained by weighing the fruit at harvest using a precision scale. The number of fruits is obtained by counting them at the time of harvest.

Percentage of pulp and peel: To determine the percentage of pulp and peel, the average weight of six fruits per plot and their respective pulps and peels are taken as a sample, determining the percentage index of each of the items.

Percentage of seeds in relation to fruit mass: Percentage of seeds in relation to fruit mass is determined based on the average weight of the seeds concerning the weight of the fruit, obtained randomly at the time of harvest.

Number of seeds per fruit: The average number of seeds per fruit is determined by counting the seeds of the six fruits used for pulp and peel analysis.

Productivity: The average fruit weight per plot is calculated and, through the product of the average weight with the number of fruits harvested per production cycle, the productivity of the plot is determined.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Pachymeter
- Precision scale

4.6. Hazelnut and Pistachio

4.6.1. Moisture

PRINCIPLE

Knowing the moisture content in hazelnuts or pistachios is essential for ensuring product quality and safety during storage and transportation. Monitoring moisture levels helps prevent mild growth, rancidity, and spoilage, preserving the nuts' flavour, texture, and nutritional value. Additionally, accurate moisture measurements contribute to regulatory compliance and market competitiveness.

PROCEDURE

Moisture determination is made on a moisture determination device with an infrared heater, and 3-5 grams of ground hazelnuts or pistachio are weighed into the sample container and spread into the Petri dish in its chamber to check the moisture content. (Corredor et al., 2011).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Petri dishes

Equipment:

- Infrared heater

REFERENCES

Corredor, C.C., Bu, D. & Both, D. (2011). Comparison of near infrared and microwave resonance sensors for at-line moisture determination in powders and tablets. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 696(1-2), 84-93.

4.6.2. Ash determination

PRINCIPLE

Understanding the ash yield in hazelnuts or pistachios is crucial for assessing their nutritional composition and quality. Ash content indicates the mineral content present in the nuts, providing insight into their overall nutritional value. Monitoring ash yield helps ensure product consistency and adherence to quality standards, facilitating consumer confidence and market competitiveness.

PROCEDURE

Ash determination is made based on the principle of burning organic materials and finding inorganic materials. 3 g of ground hazelnuts or pistachio are placed in each crucible and pre-combustion is applied with 1-2 mL of ethyl alcohol. It is burned in a pre-heated muffle furnace at 600 °C for 30-45 min and at 550 °C overnight. At the end of the firing process, the crucibles cooled in the desiccator are weighed and the calculation is made according to Equation 1 (on a dry basis) (Uylaşer and Başoğlu, 2004).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ethyl alcohol

Equipment:

- Oven
- Desiccator
- Balance

CALCULATIONS

$$(1) \text{ Total ash amount \%} = \frac{100(a-b)}{T} \times \frac{100}{N}$$

a: sum of weights of ash and porcelain crucible (g), b: weight of porcelain crucible (g), T: sample amount (g), N: for example, the amount of moisture (%).

REFERENCES

Uylaşer, V. & Başoğlu, F. (2000). Food Analysis I-II. Uludağ University Faculty of Agriculture. Application Guide No: 9: 16-17.

4.6.3. Protein determination

PRINCIPLE

The purpose of the method is to calculate the amount of protein by finding the amount of nitrogen in foods. The amount of nitrogen is determined according to the Kjeldahl method and the factor N x 6.25 is used in the calculation. Accordingly, 10 g of potassium sulphate, 0.3 g of copper sulphate, 1 g of ground

PROCEDURE

After the hazelnut or pistachio kernels are weighed and placed in the tube of the protein determination device, 25 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid is added. The sample is burned in the device for 3 h until it gave a blue-green colour. It is distilled with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in the distillation device by adding 50 mL of pure water. The ammonia obtained during distillation is kept in 25 mL of 4% boric acid to which 4 drops of methylene blue and methylene red are added. The retained ammonia is titrated with 0.2 N hydrochloric acid (HCl). The amount of protein (equation 2) is calculated from the calculated %N (Equation 3) (James, 1995).

Obtaining oil from seeds by cold pressing

After thermal pre-treatment and ultrasound pre-treatment, the hazelnuts and pistachio are prepared for pressing to obtain oil from their kernels. Hazelnuts and pistachio are ground in an Arçelik brand Valso model robot and weighed as 50 grams each. Fred S. Carver Inc. in the study. brand (America) hydraulic press is used (Figure 5).

Hazelnuts and pistachio are ground and 50 g are placed in the device and pressed for 20 min with a squeezing force of 9,071.85 kg (20,000 lbs). At the end of the pressing process, the remaining press pulp is weighed and the amount of remaining oil is calculated using the Soxhlet method. The amount and yield of oil obtained by pressing are calculated based on the mass balance of the amounts of seeds and oil entering and

exiting the pressing. Press efficiency and total oil amount calculations are shown in Equation 4 and Equation 5.

Figure 5. Hydraulic press

The amount of oil obtained from the press in the formula: It is found by subtracting the amount of oil in the meal from the total amount of oil. The amount of oil in the meal is analysed with the help of the Soxhlet device and the amount of oil remaining in it is calculated from its % composition.

Total amount of fat: The amount of oil obtained from the press is found by subtracting the amount of pulp from the pressed hazelnuts or pistachio, and when added together with the amount of oil in the pulp, the total amount of oil is obtained. Equation 5 is used to calculate the amount of oil (%) that can be obtained from hazelnuts or pistachio. Total amount of fat in hazelnuts or pistachio.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Sulfuric acid
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Pure water
- 0.2 N hydrochloric acid (HCl).
- 4% Boric acid
- Methylene blue
- Methylene red

Equipment:

- Oven
- Distillation device
- Arçelik brand Valso model robot
- Hydraulic press

CALCULATIONS

$$(2) N \left(\frac{g}{100g} \right) \% = \frac{(V_1 - V_0) \times N \times 0.014}{m} \times 10$$

$$(3) \text{Protein } \% = \text{Nitrogen } \% \times 100$$

$$(4) \text{Press efficiency } \% = \frac{\text{Amount of oil obtained from the press}}{\text{Total amount of fat}} \times 100$$

$$(5) \text{Total Oil Amount } \% = \frac{\text{Total amount of fat in hazelnuts}}{\text{Amount of pressed hazelnuts}} \times 100$$

V1 = Amount of HCl solution spent in titration (mL)

V0 = Amount of HCl solution spent in blind trial titration (mL)

N = Normality of the HCl solution used in the titration (0.2 N)

0.014 = Mile equivalent weight of nitrogen

m: Amount of food sample taken (g or mL)

F: 6.25 was used as the general factor.

REFERENCES

James, C.J. (1995). The Analytical Chemistry of Foods. Chapman and Hall Press, New York, p. 86.

4.6.4. Determination of free fatty acid content

PRINCIPLE

Free fatty acidity (FFA) is the amount of NaOH in mg required to neutralize the free acids in 100 g of fat. The free fatty acidity of the oils obtained after different pre-treatments and pressing is determined according to the AOAC (1990) method.

PROCEDURE

0.5-1.0 g of oil is weighed to an accuracy of 0.0001 g in a conical flask and 40 mL of

diethyl ether-ethanol (1:1 by volume) mixture is added. It is titrated with 0.1 N NaOH solution of known factor as phenolphthalein indicator. Free fatty acid (FFA) in terms of oleic acid is calculated as a percentage with the help of Equation 6 below, according to the amount of NaOH consumed in the titration (Paquot and Hautfenne, 1987). Analyses are performed in at least two replicates and two parallels for each oil.

Determination of total phenolic substances

For the determination of total phenolic substances, Fuentes et al. (2012), the Folin-Ciocalteu method is used. Extraction of phenolic compounds from hazelnut or pistachio oils are also done as in this study.

Extraction of phenolic substances

To extract phenolic substances from oils, 2.5 g of oil samples are dissolved in 5 mL hexane and vortexed with 3 mL methanol/water (60:40, v/v) for 2 min. After mixing, it is centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 10 min to easily separate the two phases and phenolic components. The hexane phase separated at the top of the tubes is taken into separate tubes with a pipette and the vortex and centrifugation process is continued with 3 mL methanol/water (60:40, v/v) mixture. The hexane phase is taken again and the methanolic extracts obtained after the two processes are combined (Fuentes et al., 2012).

Preparation of standard solution and drawing of the calibration curve

In total phenolic substance analysis, gallic acid standard solutions are used in the preparation of the calibration curve. For calibration curve preparation, gallic acid solutions at concentrations (1, 2, 3, 4, 5 mg L⁻¹ and 0 – blank) are prepared with methanol/water (60:40, v/v). After applying all the procedures to the samples according to the Folin-Ciocalteu method, these prepared dilutions are read at 725 nm on the spectrophotometer.

Folin-Ciocalteu Method: 0.2 mL of methanolic extracts obtained from hazelnuts or pistachio are taken and completed to 2.5 mL with pure water. After 0.25 mL of Folin reagent are added, 0.5 mL of sodium carbonate (35%) are added and mixed. 1.75 mL of pure water is added to complete the total amount to 5 mL, and after 2 h, the absorbance is read against the blank solution at 725 nm in the spectrophotometer (Fuentes et al., 2012). All processes are run in 3 parallels.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Diethyl ether-ethanol
- N NaOH
- Hexane

- Methanol
- Sodium carbonate (35%)
- Pure water

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

$$(6) FYA \% = \frac{282 \times N_{\text{NaOH}} \times V_{\text{NaOH}}}{10 \times m}$$

In the formula;

N NaOH: Normality of the NaOH solution used in titration

V NaOH: Volume of NaOH solution spent in titration (mL) m: Amount of sample taken for analysis (g)

282: Molecular weight of oleic acid is (g mol^{-1}).

REFERENCES

AOAC (1990). Official Methods for the Analysis (15th ed.). Arlington, Washington DC: Association of Official Analytical Chemists.

Paquot, C. & Hautfenne, A. (1987). Standard methods for the analysis of oils, fats and derivatives. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 201, 373.

Fuentes, E., Baez, M.E., Bravo, M., Cid, C. & Labra, F. (2012). Determination of total phenolic content in olive oil samples by UV–visible spectrometry and multivariate calibration. *Food Analytical Methods*, 5(6), 1311-1319.

4.7. Olive

4.7.1. Juice pH

PRINCIPLE

The pH value is used as an indicator of the acid content that exists in a specific food; the value varies between 0 and 14. In this way when a food or drink presents a pH value lower than 7.0 it is considered acid. The fruit quality is of vital importance when it is directed at fresh consumption. The bibliography points out that the soil moisture has a determinant effect on the quality of citrus fruits, so Levy et al. (1979) used parameters of grapefruit fruit quality to diagnose the degree of water stress. On the other hand, it has been demonstrated that moderate water stress can improve the fruit quality in certain fruit trees (Galindo et al., 2017).

PROCEDURE

To determine the pH of juice, after the harvest, between 10 and 20 fruits per repetition will be randomly selected and taken to the laboratory. In the laboratory, the juice will be obtained by means of a squeezer. The juice from these fruits will then in part be placed in a beaker and the multiparameter pH-meter will be used to obtain a direct measurement of the juice obtained, for each repetition.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

pH-meter (multiparameter) PC 80+ DHS STIRRER Bench with Cell VPT 80⁻¹ and Standard electrode.

REFERENCES

Levy, Y., Shalhevet, J. & Bielorai, H. (1979). Effect of Irrigation Regime and Water Salinity on Grapefruit Quality1. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 104(3), 356-359.

Galindo, A., Calín-Sánchez, Á., Griñán, I., Rodríguez, P., Cruz, Z.N., Girón, I.F. & Hernández, F. (2017). Water stress at the end of the pomegranate fruit ripening stage produces earlier harvest and improves fruit quality. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 226, 68-74.

4.7.2. Moisture

PRINCIPLE

Like other factors of crop quality (i.e., protein, ash, falling number) the moisture is also greatly influenced by the growing and harvesting conditions (Koubouris, et al., 2009). The moisture of olive is a fundamental aspect that indicates the maturation and can be used to point the moment of the harvest. The moisture is the loss in weight, expressed as a percentage, of a product as a result of evaporation in the oven at a defined temperature. This product is dried in a thermostatic oven at 60 °C atmospheric pressure until a constant weight is obtained.

PROCEDURE

- Olives are grinded with a grinder until a homogeneous paste is formed.
- 25 g of olive paste are weighed. It is important to write down the exact weight.
- The tray with the olive or almond paste is introduced in an oven at 60°C until constant weight.
- The olive paste is reweighed when constant weight is reached.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Aluminium tray
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Oven

- Spatula
- Grinder

CALCULATIONS

The percentage of moisture in the olive or almond is calculated with the equation:

$$\%H = \frac{M_T - M_{dry}}{M_T} \times 100$$

Where,

M_T is the weight of olive or almond past at room temperature.

M_{dry} is the weight of dry olive or almond past.

REFERENCES

Koubouris, G.C., Metzidakis, I.T. & Vasilakakis, M.D. (2009). Impact of temperature on olive (*Olea europaea* L.) pollen performance in relation to relative humidity and genotype. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 67(1), 209-214.

4.7.3. Fat content

PRINCIPLE

Spectrophotometric examination in the ultraviolet radiation can provide information on the fat content and quality, its state of preservation and changes brought about by technological processes. The absorption at the wavelengths specified in the method is due to the presence of conjugated diene and triene systems resulting from oxidation processes and/or refining practices. These absorptions are expressed as specific extinctions $E_1 \%$ 1 cm (the extinction of 1% w/v solution of the fat in the specified solvent, in a 10 mm cell) conventionally indicated by K (also referred to as “extinction coefficient”). A sample is dissolved in the required solvent and the absorbance of the solution is measured at the specified wavelengths with reference to pure solvent. The specific extinctions at 232 nm and 268 nm in iso-octane or 232 nm and 270 nm in cyclohexane are calculated for a concentration of 1% w/v in a 10 mm cell.

PROCEDURE

- a. If the sample is not perfectly homogeneous and contains suspended impurities, it must be filtered through paper at a temperature of approximately 30 °C.
- b. Approximately 0.25 g (to the nearest 1 mg) of the prepared sample is accurately weighed into a 25 mL graduated flask. The flask is then filled up to the mark with the specified solvent and homogenized. The resulting solution must be perfectly clear. If opalescence or turbidity is present, the solution should be quickly filtered through paper.

c. If necessary, the baseline (220-290 nm) is corrected with solvent in both quartz cells (sample and reference). Then, the sample quartz cell is filled with the test solution, and the extinctions are measured at 232, 268, or 270 nm against the solvent used as a reference.

d. After measuring the absorbance at 268 or 270 nm, the absorbance at λ_{\max} , $\lambda_{\max} + 4$, and $\lambda_{\max} - 4$ is measured. These absorbance values are used to determine the variation in the specific extinction (ΔK).

CALCULATIONS

Record the specific extinctions (extinction coefficients) at the various wavelengths calculated as follows:

$$K\lambda = \frac{E\lambda}{c * s}$$

where:

$K\lambda$ = the specific extinction at wavelength λ ;

$E\lambda$ = the extinction measured at wavelength λ ;

c = the concentration of the solution in g/100 mL;

s = the path length of the quartz cell in cm;

Variation of the specific extinction (ΔK)

The variation of the absolute value of the extinction (ΔK) is given by:

$$\Delta K = KmV - \left(\frac{K\lambda m - 4 + K\lambda + 4}{2} \right)$$

where Km is the specific extinction at the wavelength for maximum absorption at 270 nm and 268 nm depending on the solvent used.

REMARKS

- Generally, a mass of 0.25 to 0.30 g is sufficient for absorbance measurements of virgin and extra virgin olive oils at 268 nm and 270 nm. For measurements at 232 nm, 0.05 g of sample are usually required, so two distinct solutions are usually prepared. For absorbance measurements of olive pomace oils, refined olive oils and adulterated olive oils, a smaller portion of sample e.g., 0.1 g is usually needed due to their higher absorbance.

- The extinction values recorded must lie within the range 0.1 to 0.8 or within the range of linearity of the spectrophotometer which should be verified. If not, the measurements must be repeated using more concentrated or more dilute solutions, as appropriate.
- λ_{\max} is 268 nm for isooctane used as solvent and 270 nm for cyclohexane.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- A spectrophotometer suitable for measurements at ultraviolet wavelengths (220 nm to 360 nm), with the capability of reading individual nanometric units.
- Wavelength scale: This may be checked using a reference material consisting of an optical glass filter containing holmium oxide or a holmium oxide solution (sealed or not) that has distinct absorption bands.
- Absorbance scale: This may be checked using commercially available sealed reference materials consisting of acidic potassium dichromate solutions, in certain concentrations and certified values of absorbance at its λ_{\max} (of 4 solutions of potassium dichromate in perchloric acid sealed in four UV quartz cells to measure the linearity and photometric accuracy reference in the UV). The potassium dichromate solutions are measured against a blank of the acid used, after baseline correction, according to the instructions enclosed with the reference material. The absorbance values are listed in the certificate of the reference material.
- Another possibility to check the response of the photocell and the photomultiplier is to proceed as follows: 0.2 g of pure potassium chromate is weighed for spectrophotometry and dissolved in 0.05 N potassium hydroxide solution in a 1000 mL graduated flask, making up to the mark. Precisely 25 mL of the solution obtained is taken, transferred to a 500 mL graduated flask, and diluted up to the mark using the same potassium hydroxide solution. The extinction of the solution thus obtained is measured at 275 nm, using the potassium hydroxide solution as a reference. The extinction measured using a 1 cm cuvette should be 0.200 ± 0.005 .
- Rectangular quartz cuvettes, with covers, suitable for measurements at ultraviolet wavelengths (220 to 360 nm) having an optical path-length of 10 mm. When filled with water or other suitable solvent the cuvettes should not show differences between them of more than 0.01 extinction units.
- One-mark volumetric flasks, capacity 25 mL, class A.
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g).

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Boskou, D. (2006). Olive oil: Chemistry and Technology (2^o ed.). Edit. AOCs PRESS. Illinois. Commission of the European Communities, Regulation 2568/91., 1991. On the Characteristics of Olive Oil and Olive-residue Oil and on the Relevant Methods of Analysis.

Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2015/1833 of 12 October 2015 amending Regulation (EEC) No 2568/91 on the characteristics of olive oil and olive-residue oil and on the relevant methods of analysis (2015).

4.8. Orange, Peach and Persimmon

4.8.1. Yield determination

PRINCIPLE

In order to assess the yield of a crop, measure different parameters related to fruit formation on the plant, i.e., from flowering to fruit ripening, are measured.

PROCEDURE

Yield measurements

The number of days between sowing and the appearance of the first flower (or the first male and female flower, depending on the species) is counted.

To assess fruit set, the number of flowers fruitless at the initial set (i.e., 15 days after full bloom) is counted. Selected main branches per plant (where possible, 4 branches, one per cardinal point) are used, and fruit set is calculated by the following equation (see 2.1.4) (Lo'ay et al., 2021).

The number of fruits per plant is counted. The yield of fresh fruit in terms of weight per plant (g plant^{-1}) is measured using a sensitive weight balance. At the end of harvesting, the total fruits weight is equalled to accumulate the total yield (t ha^{-1}) (Zhang et al., 2020).

Fresh and dry weight, water content, relative water content and dry matter

Representative parts of the fruit are weighed on a balance as soon as they are harvested to obtain the fresh weight of the sample (FW). Subsequently, the plant material is placed in paper envelopes and introduced into an oven at 70 °C for 3 days until the weight of the samples is constant (DW). Once the FW and DW values are obtained, the water content and dry matter content are calculated (Admane et al., 2023) (see calculation section). For the calculation of the relative water content (RWC), it is necessary to obtain the turgent weight (TW). This weight is obtained after placing the plant material in double-distilled water for at least 24 h. Once obtained, the RWC is calculated (Erice et al., 2018).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ruler, tape measure, etc.
- Image analysis software
- Paper envelopes

Equipment:

- Balance
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

1. Fruit set (%) = $(\text{Number of fruitless} \div \text{Number of flowers}) \times 100$
2. Water content (WC) = $[(FW - DW) \div FW] \times 100$
3. Dry matter = $(DW \div FW) \times 100$
4. Relative water content (RWC) = $[(FW - DW) \div (TW - DW)] \times 100$

REFERENCES

Admane, N., Cavallo, G., Hadjila, C., Cavalluzzi, M.M., Rotondo, N.P., Salerno, A., Cannillo, J., Difonzo, G., Caponio, F., Ippolito, A., Lentini, G. & Sanzani, S.M. (2023). Biostimulant Formulations and Moringa oleifera Extracts to Improve Yield, Quality, and Storability of Hydroponic Lettuce. *Molecules*, 28(1), 373.

Erice, G., Pérez-Bueno, M.L., Pineda, M., Barón, M., Aroca, R. & Calvo-Polanco, M. (2018). Determining plant water relations. *Advances in Plant Ecophysiology Techniques*, 109-134.

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Zhang, C., Li, X., Yan, H., Ullah, I., Zuo, Z., Li, L. & Yu, J. (2020). Effects of irrigation quantity and biochar on soil physical properties, growth characteristics, yield and quality of greenhouse tomato. *Agricultural Water Management*, 241, 106263.

4.8.2. Physical traits of fruit quality

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of fruit dimensions, firmness or colour are some of the characteristics that allow us to evaluate the quality of the fruit from a morphological point of view.

PROCEDURE

Fruit dimensions

The equatorial and longitudinal diameters (cm) of harvested fruits are measured.

Firmness and peel thickness

The firmness is measured using a penetrometer with an 8 mm tip (Scarano et al., 2020). Additionally, fruits are cut along the equatorial area, and peel thickness is measured at three different points (Nissi et al., 2021).

Color measurement

Colorimetric analysis is performed on the skin and flesh of harvested fruits. A colourimeter is used to obtain the colour space parameters (lightness, L; and chromaticity coordinates a and b) and then to calculate the colour index (CI) and HUE angle values (Pérez-Pérez et al., 2008; Ciriello et al., 2021).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ruler or tape measure

Equipment:

- Penetrometer
- Colourimeter

CALCULATIONS

1. $CI = a \times 10^3 \times (L \times b)^{-1}$
2. HUE angle = $\arctan(b \div a)$

REFERENCES

Ciriello, M., Formisano, L., Pannico, A., El-Nakhel, C., Fascella, G., Duri, L.G., Cristofano, F., Gentile, B.R., Giordano, M., Roupheal, Y., Fusco, G.M., Woodrow, P. & Carillo, P. (2021). Nutrient solution deprivation as a tool to improve hydroponics sustainability: Yield, physiological, and qualitative response of lettuce. *Agronomy*, 11(8), 1469.

Nissi, F.G., Lakshmi, M.L., Swami, D.V., Rajashekaram, T., Salomi, D.R. & Krishna, U.K. (2021). Effect of antitranspirants on growth and fruit parameters of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* (L.) Osbeck). *Pharma Innovation Journal*, 10(5), 577-581.

Pérez-Pérez, J.G., Romero, P., Navarro, J.M. & Botía, P. (2008). Response of sweet orange cv 'Lane late' to deficit-irrigation strategy in two rootstocks. II: Flowering, fruit growth, yield and fruit quality. *Irrigation Science*, 26(6), 519-529.

Scarano, A., Olivieri, F., Gerardi, C., Liso, M., Chiesa, M., Chieppa, M., Frusciantè, L., Barone, A., Santino, A. & Rigano, M.M. (2020). Selection of tomato landraces with high fruit yield and nutritional quality under elevated temperatures. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 100(6), 2791-2799.

4.8.3. Acidity determination (pH and titratable acidity)

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of acidity is one of the main criteria indicating the freshness and composition of raw materials and perishable foods. Also, acidity is an important component of fruit quality. It influences the perception of acidity and sweetness. Acidity can be measured in various ways, such as pH determination or titratable acidity. Both parameters have a different signification: pH represents the free hydrogen ion activity (active acidity), while titratable acidity is the amount of weakly bound hydrogen ions that can be released from the acids (total acidity) (Lobit et al., 2002).

PROCEDURE

The liquid extract obtained from the mesocarp of each fruit (tomato, zucchini, melon, peach, orange, and persimmon) is liquefied and filtered.

pH Determination

1. The juice is put into a glass.
2. A pH strip is inserted, and the result is read.
3. The pH can also be measured with a pH-meter. The probe is inserted into the juice, and the pH value is waited to be read.

Titratable Acidity Determination

4. A burette is filled with 1M NaOH solution.
5. 10 mL of juice is put into an Erlenmeyer flask.
6. A few drops of phenolphthalein are added to the juice.
7. The NaOH solution is incorporated dropwise over the juice, shaking.
8. The process continues until the phenolphthalein turns colour. The burette is closed and the NaOH volume used is noted.
9. The results are expressed as % of citric acid per 100 mL of juice.

CALCULATIONS

$$\text{Citric acid concentration (M)} = \left[\frac{[\text{NaOH Volume (L)} \times \text{NaOH Concentration (M)}]}{3} \right] \times \text{juice Volume (L)}$$

$$\text{Malic acid concentration (M)} = \left[\frac{[\text{NaOH Volume (L)} \times \text{NaOH Concentration (M)}]}{2} \right] \times \text{juice Volume (L)}$$

REMARKS

- Considering the stoichiometry of the reaction, 1 mole of citric acid reacts with 3 moles of NaOH:

- Considering the stoichiometry of the reaction, 1 mole of malic acid reacts with 2 moles of NaOH:
$$\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5 + 2\text{NaOH} = \text{Na}_2\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_5 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$$
- To calculate the % of acid in 100 mL of juice, consider the molecular weight of the acid and its density.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- NaOH
- Phenolphthalein
- Erlenmeyer flask
- Burette
- Glass

Equipment:

- pH-meter

REFERENCES

Lobit, P., Soing, P., Génard, M. & Habib, R. (2002). Theoretical analysis of relationships between composition, pH, and titratable acidity of peach fruit. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 25(12), 2775-2792.

4.8.4. Antioxidant Capacity (DPPH radical scavenging method)

PRINCIPLE

Free radicals are known to indicate oxidative damage to biomolecules, which can lead to serious pathologies or diseases in humans. Various studies indicate that a diet rich in fruit and vegetables is effective against oxidative damage (Pyrzynska and Pełkal, 2013). As these foods are a rich source of antioxidant molecules, the concept of antioxidant capacity arises, including the synergic and redox interactions between the different molecules present in the food (Pellegrini et al., 2018). For this reason, the application of tests to measure the effectiveness of antioxidants in food systems and human metabolism has increased concurrently. Numerous bioanalytical techniques are available now to quantify the antioxidant impact on foods. Of these, the 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazil (DPPH) removing assay is the most widely used, well-liked, and potentially effective technique for assessing antioxidant capacity among them (Gulcin and Alwasel, 2023). Here we present a modification of Magalhães et al., 2006 method.

PROCEDURE

1. Aliquots of the extract ranging from 5 µL to 120 µL are diluted to a volume of 10 mL.

2. 100 µL of the diluted extract is mixed with 1.5 mL aqueous methanolic solution (82%) of DPPH radical in plastic tubes (2 mL).
3. The macro-cuvettes are covered, shaken, and kept in the dark for 1 h, then the absorbance at 517 nm (A_{sample}) is measured.
4. The absorbance of the DPPH radical without antioxidant is used as the control (A_{control}).
5. The percentage of scavenging of DPPH radical is calculated according to the formula (see calculations).
6. The spectrophotometer is zeroed using methanol.
7. Caffeic acid (0.8-6.3 ppm) or ascorbic acid is used for comparison.
8. The molar concentration of DPPH is calculated using the literature value of $12.509 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for molar absorptivity.
9. TEAC (Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity) is determined as the amount of Trolox equivalent to the amount of the test substance that results in 50% scavenging of DPPH radical.

CALCULATIONS

$$\% \text{ Scavenging} = 100 \times (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) \div A_{\text{control}}$$

REMARKS

- Turn on the spectrophotometer at least 30 minutes before starting to measure.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Aqueous methanolic solution (82%) of 2,2'-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). 32 mg of DPPH diluted in 1 L.
- Caffeic acid
- Ascorbic acid
- Plastic tubes
- Macro-cuvettes

Equipment:

- Shaker
- Spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Gulcin, I. & Alwasel, S.H. (2023). DPPH radical scavenging assay. *Processes*, 11(8), 2248.

Pellegrini, N., Vitaglione, P., Granato, D. & Fogliano, V. (2020). Twenty-five years of total antioxidant capacity measurement of foods and biological fluids: merits and limitations. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 100(14), 5064-5078.

Pyrzynska, K. & Pełal, A. (2013). Application of free radical diphenylpicrylhydrazyl (DPPH) to estimate the antioxidant capacity of food samples. *Analytical Methods*, 5(17), 4288-4295.

Magalhães, L.M., Segundo, M.A., Reis, S. & Lima, J.L. (2006). Automatic method for determination of total antioxidant capacity using 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl assay. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 558(1-2), 310-318.

4.8.5. Non-enzymatic Antioxidants (Total Phenols and Flavonoids)

Flavonoids, together with other phenolic compounds, are molecules of special interest for their benefits on human health, as they possess multiple pharmacological activities related to their antioxidant capacity and their capacity to scavenge 'reactive oxygen species' (ROS) (Bautista et al., 2016). The determination of these molecules in fruits is carried out in the same way as explained in section 1.7, differentiating only the starting material.

Ascorbic Acid (AsA-DHA Assay)

PRINCIPLE

Ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) is a nutrient, mainly found in fruit and vegetables, essential for human diet with beneficial effects on health due to its primary defensive function of free radical scavenger of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species. It is important to mention that humans cannot synthesise vitamin C, so we must incorporate it from food. Ascorbic acid is frequently added to processed foods including fruit and vegetables as an antioxidant and anti-browning agent, either for fortification or enrichment purposes or to prevent oxidation of other nutrients (such as phenolic compounds) (Ruiz et al., 2016). Ascorbic acid can be oxidised to form dehydroascorbic acid, which possesses *in vivo* vitamin C activity, as it can be reduced back in the human body to ascorbic acid. Therefore, the measurement of both, ascorbic acid and its oxidised form, is important to assess the total amount of vitamin C in a food product (Ruiz et al., 2016). We present two methods for the quantification of vitamin C, one by spectrophotometry based on the method of Desai and Desai (2019) and the other by HPLC based on the method of Chebrolu et al. (2012).

PROCEDURE

Spectrophotometric determination

1. 0.1 – 1 g of fresh material is ground and mixed with 4 mL of cold 2% HPO_3 (containing 2 mM of EDTA).
2. The pH is adjusted to approximately 5.0 by adding 2 mL of 10% sodium citrate (containing 2 mM EDTA).
3. The mixture is centrifuged at 4,000 g for 7 min, and the supernatant is collected for the assay.

4. In a quartz spectrophotometer cuvette, a final volume of 1 mL is added containing: 50 μmol sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 2 μmol EDTA, 0.5 μmol β -mercaptoethanol, 50 μL (containing approximately 35 μg protein) ascorbic acid, and sufficient tissue extract (10 – 100 μL) to give an absorbance at 265 nm of between 0.5 – 1.
5. The initial absorbance is recorded, and then the reaction is initiated by the addition of 5 μL of 50 mM H_2O_2 .
6. The absorbance decreases until a final constant value is reached.

HPLC determination

1. The plant sample is liquidated.
2. 0.9 mL of the liquid is mixed with 0.9 mL of 6% metaphosphoric acid.
3. The mixture is centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
4. The sample is diluted with distilled water if necessary and mixed with a vortex.
5. The mixture is centrifuged again at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
6. The supernatant is filtered with 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters directly into the amber HPLC vial.
7. The sample is spiked in the HPLC to determine the ascorbic acid content.
8. For the determination of dehydroascorbic acid, an aliquot from step 6 is taken, and the reducing agent (TCEP (Tris (2-carboxy ethyl) phosphine hydrochloride) at a concentration of 5 mmol L^{-1}) is added in a 1:1 ratio. It is allowed to react for at least 30 minutes at room temperature and subsequently spiked on HPLC to calculate the amount of total ascorbic acid.
9. An external calibration line is used to convert the HPLC data (given in area units) to a known concentration. A concentrated stock solution is prepared, and then serial dilutions are made. The values of the sample must be within the range of the calibration curve for accurate quantification.
10. HPLC conditions:
 - Column: Teknokroma BRISA LC2 LC2 C18 3 μm , 150 x 4.6 mm
 - Chromatographic conditions: injection 5 μL , flow rate 1 mL min^{-1} , $\lambda = 254 \text{ nm}$, time 15 min. Ascorbic acid migrates over 2.3 min.
 - Mobile phase: 5:95 v/v methanol: water with 1% acetic acid.

CALCULATIONS

1. The ascorbic acid content is calculated from the difference between the initial and final absorbance readings and the millimolar extinction coefficient for ascorbate at pH 7.0 determined with a standard solution of ascorbic acid ($14.1 \text{ mM}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).
2. For HPLC, the levels of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid are calculated using the regression equation obtained from the calibration

REMARKS

- The spectrophotometer must be turned on at least 30 min before starting to measure.
- For HPLC, it is taken into account that the higher the amount of ascorbic acid in the sample, the higher the dilution that has to be made.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material for spectrophotometric determination:

- Metaphosphoric acid (HPO₃)
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)
- Sodium Citrate
- Sodium Phosphate buffer (pH 7.0)
- β-mercaptoethanol
- Ascorbic acid
- Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂)

Material for HPLC determination:

- Metaphosphoric acid (HPO₃)
- Double-distilled water
- Methanol
- Acetic acid
- Ascorbic acid
- Tris (2-carboxy ethyl) phosphine hydrochloride (TCEP)
- 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters
- Amber HPLC vials

Equipment:

- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer
- HPLC

REFERENCES

Chebrolu, K.K., Jayaprakasha, G.K., Yoo, K.S., Jifon, J.L. & Patil, B.S. (2012). An improved sample preparation method for quantification of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid by HPLC. *LWT*, 47(2), 443-449.

Ruiz, B.G., Roux, S., Courtois, F. & Bonazzi, C. (2016). Spectrophotometric method for fast quantification of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid in simple matrix for kinetics measurements. *Food Chemistry*, 211, 583-589.

Desai, A.P. & Desai, S. (2019). UV spectroscopic method for determination of vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content in different fruits in South Gujarat region. *International Journal of Environmental Science of Natural Resources*, 21(1), 0041-044.

4.8.6. Carotenoid content

PRINCIPLE

Carotenes are pigments which, in addition to being indicators of plant health, are of great importance to humans, as many of these molecules are precursors in the biosynthesis of vitamin A, as well as functioning as antioxidant molecules (Hermanns et al., 2020), and are therefore an indicator of quality in many foodstuffs. The protocol explained here is that of Hornero-Méndez and Mínguez-Mosquera (2001), with some modifications. The method makes it possible to differentiate carotenoids into two groups: red carotenoids (capsanthin and capsorubin) and yellow carotenoids (zeaxanthin and beta-carotene, among others). However, the method is optimised for the detection of pepper carotenoids, previous studies have shown that this method could also be reliable for determining carotenoid concentrations of other vegetables or fruits, after removing potentially interfering chlorophylls (Biehler et al., 2010).

PROCEDURE

1. 0.1 g of dry material is placed in a 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask.
2. 20 mL of acetone is added.
3. The flask is covered with parafilm.
4. The flask is shaken for 1 h.
5. The contents of the Erlenmeyer flask are filtered under vacuum with filter paper, wetting the paper with acetone, and transferring little by little.
6. The filtered liquid is transferred into a 25 mL volumetric flask.
7. The volume is made up to the mark with acetone.
8. Acetone is used as a blank.
9. The absorbances are read at 472 nm and 508 nm.

CALCULATIONS

1. *Red Carotenoids* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(A_{508} \times 2144 - A_{472} \times 403.3) \div 270.9$
2. *Yellow Carotenoids* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) = $(A_{472} \times 1724.3 - A_{508} \times 2450.1) \div 270.9$

REMARKS

- Note the exact weight of dry material used.
- Turn on the spectrophotometer at least 30 minutes before starting to measure.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Acetone

Equipment:

- 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask
- Parafilm

- Vacuum
- Filter paper
- Volumetric flask
- Spectrophotometer

REFERENCES

Biehler, E., Mayer, F., Hoffmann, L., Krause, E. & Bohn, T. (2010). Comparison of 3 spectrophotometric methods for carotenoid determination in frequently consumed fruits and vegetables. *Journal of Food Science*, 75(1), C55-C61.

Hermanns, A.S., Zhou, X., Xu, Q., Tadmor, Y. & Li, L. (2020). Carotenoid pigment accumulation in horticultural plants. *Horticultural Plant Journal*, 6(6), 343-360.

Hornero-Méndez, D. & Mínguez-Mosquera, M.I. (2001). Rapid spectrophotometric determination of red and yellow isochromic carotenoid fractions in paprika and red pepper oleoresins. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 49(8), 3584-3588.

4.8.7. Sugars determination

PRINCIPLE

The quality of food products is an abstract concept that depends on the needs of the consumer and the product to be consumed (Cantín et al., 2009). Among the most remarkable in many fruits and vegetables is the sweetness, which is determined by the different proportion of soluble sugars present in the consumed plant organ. The main sugars present in fruits and vegetables are sucrose, fructose and glucose, although depending on the species, other major sugars may be present and the proportion of them also varies, and even within the state of ripeness (Ma et al., 2015; Bertín and Génard, 2018; Kyriacou et al., 2018).

These sugars can be measured in total, by destructive techniques (see section 1.9) or non-destructive techniques such as near infrared reflectance (NIR) spectroscopy (Flores et al., 2008), or the concentration of each sugar individually by HPLC.

PROCEDURE

Total Soluble Solids (TSS)

1. Juice is obtained from the fruit to be analysed.
2. A few drops of the juice are taken and dropped into a hand-held refractometer.
3. The results are expressed as °Brix (grams of sucrose in 100 g of solution).

HPLC quantification of sugars

- **Sugar extraction**
1. The juice or liquefied plant material is extracted. It can be stored at -80 °C until processing.

2. The samples are thawed in the dark, preferably in the fridge. Once thawed, they are centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
3. The sample is diluted with distilled water. Depending on the species to be analysed, the dilution will be greater or lesser (the more sugars, the greater the dilution).
4. The diluted samples are shaken with a vortex.
5. They are centrifuged again at 12,000 rpm for 5 min.
6. The supernatant is filtered with 0.22 μm PVDF syringe filters directly into the amber HPLC vial.

- **External calibration line**

1. To convert the HPLC data (given in area units) to a known concentration, a calibration line is needed. In this case, three lines are needed, one for fructose, one for glucose, and one for sucrose. If any additional sugars are to be analysed, another line will be necessary.
2. A concentrated stock solution is prepared, and then serial dilutions are made. In this case, the standard is weighed, the weight is noted, and diluted with pure water. An example of stock solutions:
 - Fructose: 400 mg in 10 mL, purity 99%.
 - Glucose: 400 mg in 10 mL, purity 99.5%.
 - Sucrose: 100 mg in 5 mL, purity 99.5%.
3. For calibration, the most concentrated point takes 0.5 mL of each stock solution, and 0.5 mL of pure water. That is, starting with a $\frac{1}{4}$ dilution of the stock solution, and then making serial dilutions 4 times.

- **HPLC Analysis**

1. Column: Phenomenex Luna Omega Sugar, 150 mm, 4.6 mm, 3 μm .
2. Chromatographic conditions: injection 10 μL , flow 0.8 mL min⁻¹, time 15 min.
3. Mobile phase: 75:25 v/v acetonitrile:water.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Materials:

- Acetonitrile
- Distilled water
- Fructose
- Glucose
- Sucrose

Equipment:

- Refractometer
- Centrifuge

- Vortex
- 0.22 µm PVDF syringe filters
- Amber HPLC vials
- HPLC column

CALCULATIONS

- The HPLC data, such as the retention time of the peak in question and the area units for that peak, are obtained. Subsequently, the concentrations of each sugar are calculated using the calibration lines.

REMARKS

- This is only an example of a protocol, which can be modified depending on the species to be analysed.
- It is important to have the fresh weight (or dry weight) value of the starting material.
- The processing of the plant material may vary depending on the species.
- Depending on the quantity of sugars in the plant material, the homogenate will have to be diluted.
- The type of column shown is only an example. Depending on the HPLC model, or sugars to be determined, this may vary.

REFERENCES

Bertin, N. & Génard, M. (2018). Tomato quality as influenced by preharvest factors. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 233, 264-276.

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Kyriacou, M.C., Leskovar, D.I., Colla, G. & Roupael, Y. (2018). Watermelon and melon fruit quality: The genotypic and agro-environmental factors implicated. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 234, 393-408.

Ma, B., Chen, J., Zheng, H., Fang, T., Ogutu, C., Li, S., Han, Y. & Wu, B. (2015). Comparative assessment of sugar and malic acid composition in cultivated and wild apples. *Food Chemistry*, 172, 86-91.

4.9. Vineyard

4.9.1. Bunch weight and grape size

PRINCIPLE

The size of grapes is an important attribute that can impact both the commercial value and the quality of the fruit. Grape size can play a role in meeting market requirements. Consistency in berry size is often desired to ensure uniformity in appearance and presentation of table grapes. Berry size can influence consumers' preference for grapes. Larger berries are often associated with juiciness and perceived sweetness, which can be desirable qualities for many consumers. Grape berry size is a component of yield. Larger berries, depending on the variety, can contribute to higher overall fruit weight, potentially increasing the yield per vine or per acre. Larger grapes can be easier to handle during harvesting and processing, which can be advantageous for efficiency and reducing labour costs. In the context of winemaking, grape size can impact wine quality and characteristics. Berry size can influence the ratio of skin to juice, affecting the extraction of colour, tannins, and flavour compounds during fermentation (Nuzzo and Matthews, 2005).

PROCEDURE

For measuring grape size callipers, ruler, measuring tape or grape sizer (Fig. 6) are used. Brunch weight is determined with a balance.

Figure 6. Grape sizer

REFERENCES

Nuzzo, V. & Matthews, M.A. (2005). Berry size and yield paradigms on grapes and wines quality. In *International Workshop on Advances in Grapevine and Wine Research 754*, pp. 423-436.

4.9.2. Brix degrees

PRINCIPLE

Brix degrees in grapes refer to a measurement of the sugar content in grapes, specifically the concentration of soluble solids, mostly as sucrose. Brix is commonly used in the wine industry to determine the potential alcohol content of the wine before it is made. The measurement is taken using a refractometer and is expressed in degrees Brix (°Bx). The Brix measurement is important in winemaking as it provides an indication of the ripeness of the grapes and helps winemakers determine the optimal time to harvest. The sugar content in grapes affects the final alcohol level and flavour profile of the wine. Each gram of sugar per liter of grape juice roughly translates to about 0.55% alcohol by volume in the finished wine.

PROCEDURE

A representative sample of grapes are randomly selected from different parts of the vineyard or vine.

1. The skin and seeds from grape sample are removed. The Brix measurement is typically taken from the juice or pulp of the grapes. Then, the sample is poured into 500 mL beaker and stirred for 10 min (remove the gases).
2. A small amount of the grape juice is placed on the prism of the refractometer and the value of the refractometer is compared to the Brix scale.
3. The process of Brix measurement is recorded and repeated for multiple grape samples to obtain an average or representative value.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Calibration solution
- Distilled water
- Snap-lock sandwich bags for crushing grape samples.
- Lint free tissue (kimwipes or equivalent).
- Plastic Pasteur pipettes.

Equipment:

- Refractometer
- 500 mL beaker
- Magnetic stirrer
- Thermometer

REFERENCES

<https://www.agw.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Industry-Endorsed-Standard-Procedure-for-Measurement-of-Brix-or-Baume.pdf>

4.9.3. Acidity

PRINCIPLE

Titrateable acidity (TA) measurement: Titrateable acidity measures the total amount of acids present in grape juice or must, including both fixed acids (such as tartaric acid) and volatile acids. The measurement is typically done through titration using a standardized solution of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to reach a designated pH endpoint. During titration, a known volume of grape juice or must is mixed with an indicator solution that changes colour at the endpoint. Sodium hydroxide solution is then slowly added to the mixture until the colour change occurs, indicating that all the acids have been neutralized. The amount of sodium hydroxide solution used is equivalent to the total acidity present. The measurement is often expressed as grams of tartaric acid per liter (g L^{-1}) or as a percentage of tartaric acid. It provides winemakers with valuable information about the grape's acid profile, helping them make decisions about blending, acid adjustments, and overall wine quality. It's worth noting that titrateable acidity is different from pH measurement, which focuses on the strength and concentration of acid in a solution. While pH gives an indication of acidity or alkalinity, titrateable acidity quantifies the actual concentration of acids present.

PROCEDURE

1. 200 mL of boiled and cooled distilled water is placed into a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask and 1 mL of phenolphthalein indicator is added to the water. If using a disposable transfer pipet, approximately 20 drops is equal to 1 mL. Then, a burette with standardized 0.1 N sodium hydroxide is filled and secured in the stand.
2. The flask of water/indicator solution is placed under the beaker. Titrant and sample need mixing during titration, a stir plate with stirrer is optional or use manual swirling of the flask.
3. The water is titrated with 0.1 N sodium hydroxide from the burette to a definite pink endpoint. The endpoint is defined when the water turns a pale/rose pink that holds for at least 15–30 seconds.
4. Using a pipet, 5 mL of degassed, room temperature must or wine sample is added to the flask.
5. The initial volume of sodium hydroxide is written in the burette.
6. The sample is titrated by adding 0.1 N sodium hydroxide from the burette to the beaker containing the sample. The titration is complete when the same distinct endpoint is reached (as in step 3).

7. Finally, the final volume of sodium hydroxide is written down from the burette. The initial volume is subtracted from the final volume of sodium hydroxide to determine the total volume used in the titration.

CALCULATIONS

TA as tartaric acid (g L^{-1}) = $(V) (N) (75) / (v)$

V = volume (mL) of sodium hydroxide solution used for titration

N = normality of sodium hydroxide solution

v = must/wine sample volume (mL)

REMARKS

Given the normality (N) of sodium hydroxide is 0.1 and the sample volume (v) is 5 mL, the equation can be simplified to: TA as tartaric acid (g L^{-1}) = $(V) * 1.5$

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material

- 250 mL beaker
- 500 mL wide mouth Erlenmeyer flask
- 2550 mL burette and burette stand
- 1 mL pipette or disposable transfer pipette
- 5 mL or 10 mL pipette
- Stir plate and magnetic stirrer (optional)
- Pipet bulb or pump
- Distilled water
- 0.1 N sodium hydroxide, standardized
- Phenolphthalein indicator

REFERENCES

Estimating Grape Maturity by Titratable Acidity. IOWA University. store.extension.iastate.edu.

4.9.4. pH determination

PRINCIPLE

The measurement of pH in grapes and wine is essential for several reasons. pH is used as a measure of acidity in grapes and wine. It indicates the balance between acid and other components in the wine, such as sugars and tannins. Monitoring pH helps winemakers ensure the desired acid profile, which is crucial for the overall taste, structure, and balance of the wine. pH also plays a significant role during fermentation. Yeast activity and the growth of beneficial bacteria in wine are influenced by pH so monitoring and adjusting pH levels can help create an optimal environment for yeast

fermentation and prevent the growth of spoilage microorganisms that thrive in certain pH ranges.

pH influences the perceived taste of wine. Lower pH levels contribute to a sharper, crisper, and more tart taste, while higher pH levels can result in a softer, smoother, and more rounded flavour profile. Measuring and adjusting pH allows winemakers to control and fine-tune the sensory characteristics of the wine. It is also a significant factor in determining the stability and aging potential of wine. A lower pH (higher acidity) can help preserve the colour, flavour, and structure of the wine, acting as a natural preservative. It can also provide protection against microbial spoilage and oxidation. Monitoring pH throughout the winemaking process ensures that the wine has the desired stability and potential for aging. Finally, measuring pH is an integral part of quality control in the wine industry. It helps ensure consistency and uniformity across different batches of wine, as well as adherence to specific regional or stylistic standards. Winemakers can make informed decisions about blending, fermentation techniques, and adjustments based on pH measurements (O'Donnell, 2023).

PROCEDURE

Calibration of the pH meter

The calibration is performed with at least two buffer solutions with known pH (4.0-7.0).

Measuring

1. First, the pH-meter is warmed up.
2. The electrode is immersed into the sample, then wait while pH value appears.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Buffer solution

Equipment:

- pH meter

REFERENCES

O'Donnell, D. (2023). Measuring the pH of Grapes at Harvest Time. Online: <https://sensorex.com/measuring-ph-grapes-harvest/> [Accessed 2/09/2023].

4.9.5. Anthocyanins

PRINCIPLE

Anthocyanins is a class of pigments responsible for the red, purple, and blue colours in many fruits, including grapes. Measuring anthocyanins in grapes is important for several

reasons. Anthocyanin accumulation in grapes is closely related to ripeness and maturity. Measuring anthocyanin levels can provide valuable information about the stage of grape development, helping winemakers determine the optimal time for harvest. Anthocyanin levels can indicate the grape's readiness to produce desirable flavours, aromas, and phenolic compounds. Anthocyanins contribute significantly to the colour and appearance of red and purple wines. Measuring anthocyanin content in grapes can help predict the colour intensity and hue of the resulting wine. Winemakers can use this information to make decisions regarding maceration time, extraction techniques, and blending to achieve the desired colour characteristics in the final product. This type of phenolic compounds is also considered markers of grape and wine quality. Measuring anthocyanin content allows winemakers to assess the potential sensory characteristics of the wine, such as its fruity, floral, or spicy notes. Higher levels of anthocyanins are generally associated with wines of better quality, as they contribute to complexity and depth of flavour. Finally, anthocyanins are known for their potential health benefits, including antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Measuring anthocyanin levels in grapes can provide an indication of their potential health-promoting properties in the resulting wine. This information may be of interest to consumers seeking wines with higher anthocyanin content for potential health benefits.

PROCEDURE

1. A representative grape sample is taken just prior to homogenisation using the following procedure:
 - a) All berries are placed into a tray or container.
 - b) The berries are gently mixed by hand, being careful not to split the skins of any of them.
 - c) The berries are taken randomly from different areas within the tray or container until there is approximately 200 berries (or approximately 200 g), and are placed into a clearly labelled 250 mL container.
 - d) Any berries that are left after taking the random sample can be disposed of in an appropriate manner.
2. All samples are thoroughly remixed by stirring, immediately before subsampling, to ensure no settling out of material before subsampling.
3. 1.0 ± 0.1 g is weighed into a 10 mL centrifuge tube and the weight is recorded.
4. 10 mL of 50% acidified v/v ethanol/Milli-Q water is added and the tube is capped.
5. Samples are rotated on the rotating wheel mixer for 1 h.
6. The homogenate/ethanol mixture is centrifuged at approximately 3,500 rpm for 5 min.

7. The supernatant liquid is poured into an appropriately sized measuring cylinder to, and the volume of the extract is measured to the nearest 0.2 mL. This is the final extract volume required for the calculation step.

8. 1 mL of the extract is added to 10 mL of 1 M HCl (total volume is 11 mL).

9. This is incubated at room temperature for at least 1 h and no longer than 4 h in a dark place (e.g., cupboard).

10. Instrument for measurement is set at 520 nm.

11. Zero is 1 M HCl in 10 mm quartz cuvette.

absorbance of the extract is measured at 520 nm.

CALCULATIONS

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total anthocyanins } \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{g}} \text{ fruit} \right) &= \\ &= \frac{A_{HCl520nm}}{500} \times \frac{\text{Final extract volume (mL)}}{100} \times \frac{1000}{\text{Weight of homogenate taken for extraction (g)}} \end{aligned}$$

REMARKS

NOTE: If 1.0 mL of 'the extract' is added into 10 mL of 1 M HCl, the dilution factor is 11.

NOTE: As a general guide, 1 g of homogenate extracted with 10 mL of 50% v/v aqueous ethanol will result in a 'final extract volume' of approximately 10.5 mL, but this value can vary depending on berry weight.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- 1 M Hydrochloric Acid. Prepared by adding 83 mL of concentrated HCl (approximately 37%) to approximately 600 mL Milli-Q water in a 1 L volumetric flask, temperate to 20 °C, then filled to the 1 L mark with Milli-Q water and mix thoroughly. Prepare fresh every 3 months.
- 50% v/v ethanol in Milli-Q water. Prepared by adding 500 mL of absolute ethanol to approximately 400 mL of Milli-Q water in a 1 L volumetric flask, temperate to 20 °C, then filled to the 1 L mark with Milli-Q water. Prepare fresh every 3 months.
- Acidified 50% v/v ethanol in Milli-Q water. Prepared by adding 4.4 mL of concentrated HCl (37%) to approximately 600 mL 50% v/v ethanol in a 1 L volumetric flask, temperate to 20 °C, then filled to the 1 L mark with 50% v/v ethanol. Prepare fresh every 3 months

Material:

- 10 mm path length quartz cuvette
- Fixed volume pipettes (calibrated only) to deliver volumes of 1 mL and 10 mL
- 10 mL Centrifuge tubes with caps
- 1 L Volumetric flasks
- Analytical balance with minimum scale reading of 0.01 g
- 250 mL Plastic containers with lids

Equipment:

- UV/Visible spectrophotometer capable of measuring in the range 250-520 nm
- Centrifuge capable of maintaining speeds of approximately 3,500 rpm
- Rotating wheel mixer (if available)

REFERENCES

The Australian Wine Research Institute (2021). Determination of Total Anthocyanins in Grapes Online available at: <https://www.agw.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Industry-Endorsed-Standard-Procedure-for-Determination-of-Total-Anthocyanins-Grape-Colour.pdf> [Accessed 20/08/2023].

4.9.6. Polyphenols*PRINCIPLE*

Polyphenols are specialized metabolites ubiquitous in many plants with beneficial functions in plants and humans such as antioxidant activity.

*PROCEDURE***Preparation of Shoot or Root Extracts**

1. Shoots and roots are harvested for and immediately freeze-dried. Freeze-dried shoots or roots (0.3 g) are cut into 2-mm lengths, ground into powder with a mortar and pestle after the addition of liquid nitrogen, and macerated with 9 mL of 0.001 M HCl.
2. The entire macerate is transferred to a labelled glass scintillation vial and sonicated at 5 °C for 15 min.
3. The resulting mixture is centrifuged at 20,000 rpm at 10 °C for 15 min to remove debris.
4. The supernatant is collected and extracted three times with 10 mL portions of diethyl ether (GC grade, BDH Laboratory Supplies).
5. The ether layers are combined and evaporated on a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure at 35 °C until the volume of residual solution is approximately 1 mL.
6. The solution is dried with N₂.

7. Methanol (500 μL) is used to dissolve the remaining powder and to prepare the final vials for HPLC analyses (1260 Series; Agilent Technologies), which is performed using a system consisted of compact mass detector equipment (TRIPLE QUAD 3500; AB SCIEX Instruments).
8. Polyphenols are separated using a C18 column (Phenomenex Luna, 150 mm \times 2 mm and 3 μm ; Phenomenex). The flow rate used is 300 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$, column temperature is 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, injection volume is 10 μL and column is equilibrated for 6 min between runs. The used gradient elution is a mixture of two solvents: A, consisting of 0.1% formic acid in water, and B, consisting of 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile. Initial conditions (98% A and 2% B) are held for 4 min before ramping to 20% B at 7 min and 90% B at 14 min. Initial conditions are recovered at 15 min and held until 21 min. Instrument parameters were as follows: CUR, 25 psi; CAD, 7 psi; IS, -4500 V ; TEM, 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; GS1, 55 psi; GS2, 55 psi; interface heater, on.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Mortar and pestle
- Liquid nitrogen
- 0.001 M HCl
- Falcon tubes (50 mL)
- Diethyl ether
- N_2
- Methanol
- Decantation funnel

Equipment:

- Sonicator
- HPLC-MS
- Centrifuge
- Rotavapor

REFERENCES

Wu, H., Haig, T., Pratley, J., Lemerle, D. & An, M. (2000). Distribution and exudation of allelochemicals in wheat *Triticum aestivum*. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, 26, 2141-2154.

4.9.7. Total Soluble Content

PRINCIPLE

The refractive index at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, expressed either as an absolute value or as a percentage by mass of sucrose, is given in the appropriate table to provide a means of obtaining the

sugar concentration in grams per litre and in grams per kilogram for grape musts, concentrated grape musts and rectified concentrated grape musts.

PROCEDURE

First, the sample is prepared. Must and concentrated must is passed, if necessary, through a dry gauze folded into four and, after discarding the first drops of the filtrate, the determination on the filtered product is carried out. Depending on the concentration, either the rectified concentrated must itself or a solution obtained by making up 200 g of rectified concentrated must to 500 g with water is used, all weights being carried out accurately.

Then, the sample is heat to a temperature close to 20 °C. A small test sample is placed on the lower prism of the refractometer, taking care (because the prisms are pressed firmly against each other) that this test sample covers the glass surface uniformly. The measurement is carried out in accordance with the operating instructions of the instrument used. The percentage is read by mass of sucrose to within 0.1 or read the refractive index to four decimal places. At least two determinations must be carried out on the same prepared sample. The temperature (°C) is recorded.

CALCULATIONS

Temperature correction

- Instruments graduated in percentage by mass of sucrose: use Table 25 to obtain the temperature correction.
- Instruments graduated in refractive index: find the index measured at t °C in Table 26 to obtain (column 1) the corresponding value of the percentage by mass of sucrose at t °C. This value is corrected for temperature and expressed as a concentration at 20 °C by means of Table 25.

Sugar concentration in must and concentrated must

Find the percentage by mass of sucrose at 20 °C in Table 26 and read from the same row the sugar concentration in grams per litre and grams per kilogram. The sugar concentration is expressed in terms of invert sugar to one decimal.

Sugar concentration in rectified concentrated must

Find the percentage by mass of sucrose at 20 °C in Table 27 and read from the same row the sugar concentration in grams per litre and grams per kilogram. The sugar concentration is expressed in terms of invert sugar to one decimal place. If the measurement was made on diluted rectified concentrated must, multiply the result by the dilution factor.

Refractive index of must, concentrated must and rectified concentrated must

Find the percentage by mass of sucrose at 20 °C in Table 26 and read from the same row the refractive index at 20 °C. This index is expressed to four decimals.

Table 25. Correction to be made in the case where the % by mass of saccharose was determined at a temperature different by 20 °C.

Temperat ure °C	Percentage by mass measured in %														
	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	
5	-0.82	-0.87	-0.92	-0.95	-0.99										
6	-0.80	-0.82	-0.87	-0.90	-0.94										
7	-0.74	-0.78	-0.82	-0.84	-0.88										
8	-0.69	-0.73	-0.76	-0.79	-0.82										
9	-0.64	-0.67	-0.71	-0.73	-0.75										
10	-0.59	-0.62	-0.65	-0.67	-0.69	-0.71	-0.72	-0.73	-0.74	-0.75	-0.75	-0.75	-0.75	-0.75	
11	-0.54	-0.57	-0.59	-0.61	-0.63	-0.64	-0.65	-0.66	-0.67	-0.68	-0.68	-0.68	-0.68	-0.67	
12	-0.49	-0.51	-0.53	-0.55	-0.56	-0.57	-0.58	-0.59	-0.60	-0.60	-0.61	-0.61	-0.60	-0.60	
13	-0.43	-0.45	-0.47	-0.48	-0.50	-0.51	-0.52	-0.52	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	-0.53	
14	-0.38	-0.39	-0.40	-0.42	-0.43	-0.44	-0.44	-0.45	-0.45	-0.46	-0.46	-0.46	-0.46	-0.45	
15	-0.32	-0.33	-0.34	-0.35	-0.36	-0.37	-0.37	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	-0.38	
16	-0.26	-0.27	-0.28	-0.28	-0.29	-0.30	-0.30	-0.30	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.30	
17	-0.20	-0.20	-0.21	-0.21	-0.22	-0.22	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	-0.23	
18	-0.13	-0.14	-0.14	-0.14	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	-0.15	
19	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.07	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	
20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
R E F E R E N C E															
21	+0.07	+0.07	+0.07	+0.07	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	+0.08	
22	+0.14	+0.14	+0.15	+0.15	+0.15	+0.15	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.16	+0.15	+0.15	
23	+0.21	+0.22	+0.22	+0.23	+0.23	+0.23	+0.23	+0.24	+0.24	+0.24	+0.24	+0.23	+0.23	+0.23	
24	+0.29	+0.29	+0.30	+0.30	+0.31	+0.31	+0.31	+0.32	+0.32	+0.32	+0.32	+0.31	+0.31	+0.31	
25	+0.36	+0.37	+0.38	+0.38	+0.39	+0.39	+0.40	+0.40	+0.40	+0.40	+0.40	+0.39	+0.39	+0.39	
26	+0.44	+0.45	+0.46	+0.46	+0.47	+0.47	+0.48	+0.48	+0.48	+0.48	+0.48	+0.47	+0.47	+0.46	
27	+0.52	+0.53	+0.54	+0.55	+0.55	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.56	+0.55	+0.55	+0.54	
28	+0.60	+0.61	+0.62	+0.63	+0.64	+0.64	+0.64	+0.65	+0.65	+0.64	+0.64	+0.64	+0.63	+0.62	
29	+0.68	+0.69	+0.70	+0.71	+0.72	+0.73	+0.73	+0.73	+0.73	+0.73	+0.72	+0.72	+0.71	+0.70	
30	+0.77	+0.78	+0.79	+0.80	+0.81	+0.81	+0.81	+0.82	+0.81	+0.81	+0.81	+0.80	+0.79	+0.78	
31	+0.85	+0.87	+0.88	+0.89	+0.89	+0.90	+0.90	+0.90	+0.90	+0.90	+0.89	+0.88	+0.87	+0.86	
32	+0.94	+0.95	+0.96	+0.97	+0.98	+0.99	+0.99	+0.99	+0.99	+0.98	+0.97	+0.96	+0.95	+0.94	
33	+1.03	+1.04	+1.05	+1.06	+1.07	+1.08	+1.08	+1.08	+1.07	+1.07	+1.06	+1.05	+1.03	+1.02	
34	+1.12	+1.19	+1.15	+1.15	+1.16	+1.17	+1.17	+1.17	+1.16	+1.15	+1.14	+1.13	+1.12	+1.10	
35	+1.22	+1.23	+1.24	+1.25	+1.25	+1.26	+1.26	+1.25	+1.25	+1.24	+1.23	+1.21	+1.20	+1.18	
36	+1.31	+1.32	+1.33	+1.34	+1.35	+1.35	+1.35	+1.35	+1.34	+1.33	+1.32	+1.30	+1.28	+1.26	
37	+1.41	+1.42	+1.43	+1.44	+1.44	+1.44	+1.44	+1.44	+1.43	+1.42	+1.40	+1.38	+1.36	+1.34	
38	+1.51	+1.52	+1.53	+1.53	+1.54	+1.54	+1.53	+1.53	+1.52	+1.51	+1.49	+1.47	+1.45	+1.42	
39	+1.61	+1.62	+1.62	+1.63	+1.63	+1.63	+1.63	+1.62	+1.61	+1.60	+1.58	+1.56	+1.53	+1.50	
40	+1.71	+1.72	+1.72	+1.73	+1.73	+1.73	+1.72	+1.71	+1.70	+1.69	+1.67	+1.64	+1.62	+1.59	

It is preferable that the variations in temperature in relation to 20°C do not exceed $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 26. Saccharose refractive index in vineyard. Table giving the sugar content of must and concentrated musts in grams per litre and in grams per kilogram, determined using a graduated refractometer, either in % by mass saccharose at 20 °C, or refractive index at 20 °C. The mass density at 20 °C is also given.

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
10.0	1.34782	1.0391	82.2	79.1	4.89
10.1	1.34798	1.0395	83.3	80.1	4.95
10.2	1.34813	1.0399	84.3	81.1	5.01
10.3	1.34829	1.0403	85.4	82.1	5.08
10.4	1.34844	1.0407	86.5	83.1	5.14
10.5	1.34860	1.0411	87.5	84.1	5.20
10.6	1.34875	1.0415	88.6	85.0	5.27
10.7	1.34891	1.0419	89.6	86.0	5.32
10.8	1.34906	1.0423	90.7	87.0	5.39
10.9	1.34922	1.0427	91.8	88.0	5.46
11.0	1.34937	1.0431	92.8	89.0	5.52
11.1	1.34953	1.0436	93.9	90.0	5.58
11.2	1.34968	1.0440	95.0	91.0	5.65
11.3	1.34984	1.0444	96.0	92.0	5.71
11.4	1.34999	1.0448	97.1	92.9	5.77
11.5	1.35015	1.0452	98.2	93.9	5.84
11.6	1.35031	1.0456	99.3	94.9	5.90
11.7	1.35046	1.0460	100.3	95.9	5.96
11.8	1.35062	1.0464	101.4	96.9	6.03
11.9	1.35077	1.0468	102.5	97.9	6.09
12.0	1.35093	1.0472	103.5	98.9	6.15
12.1	1.35109	1.0477	104.6	99.9	6.22
12.2	1.35124	1.0481	105.7	100.8	6.28
12.3	1.35140	1.0485	106.8	101.8	6.35
12.4	1.35156	1.0489	107.8	102.8	6.41
12.5	1.35171	1.0493	108.9	103.8	6.47
12.6	1.35187	1.0497	110.0	104.8	6.54
12.7	1.35203	1.0501	111.1	105.8	6.60
12.8	1.35219	1.0506	112.2	106.8	6.67
12.9	1.35234	1.0510	113.2	107.8	6.73
13.0	1.35250	1.0514	114.3	108.7	6.79
13.1	1.35266	1.0518	115.4	109.7	6.86
13.2	1.35282	1.0522	116.5	110.7	6.92
13.3	1.35298	1.0527	117.6	111.7	6.99
13.4	1.35313	1.0531	118.7	112.7	7.05
13.5	1.35329	1.0535	119.7	113.7	7.11
13.6	1.35345	1.0539	120.8	114.7	7.18
13.7	1.35361	1.0543	121.9	115.6	7.24
13.8	1.35377	1.0548	123.0	116.6	7.31
13.9	1.35393	1.0552	124.1	117.6	7.38
14.0	1.35408	1.0556	125.2	118.6	7.44
14.1	1.35424	1.0560	126.3	119.6	7.51
14.2	1.35440	1.0564	127.4	120.6	7.57
14.3	1.35456	1.0569	128.5	121.6	7.64
14.4	1.35472	1.0573	129.6	122.5	7.70
14.5	1.35488	1.0577	130.6	123.5	7.76
14.6	1.35504	1.0581	131.7	124.5	7.83
14.7	1.35520	1.0586	132.8	125.5	7.89
14.8	1.35536	1.0590	133.9	126.5	7.96
14.9	1.35552	1.0594	135.0	127.5	8.02

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
15.0	1.35568	1.0598	136.1	128.4	8.09
15.1	1.35584	1.0603	137.2	129.4	8.15
15.2	1.35600	1.0607	138.3	130.4	8.22
15.3	1.35616	1.0611	139.4	131.4	8.28
15.4	1.35632	1.0616	140.5	132.4	8.35
15.5	1.35648	1.0620	141.6	133.4	8.42
15.6	1.35664	1.0624	142.7	134.3	8.48
15.7	1.35680	1.0628	143.8	135.3	8.55
15.8	1.35696	1.0633	144.9	136.3	8.61
15.9	1.35713	1.0637	146.0	137.3	8.68
16.0	1.35729	1.0641	147.1	138.3	8.74
16.1	1.35745	1.0646	148.2	139.3	8.81
16.2	1.35761	1.0650	149.3	140.2	8.87
16.3	1.35777	1.0654	150.5	141.2	8.94
16.4	1.35793	1.0659	151.6	142.2	9.01
16.5	1.35810	1.0663	152.7	143.2	9.07
16.6	1.35826	1.0667	153.8	144.2	9.14
16.7	1.35842	1.0672	154.9	145.1	9.21
16.8	1.35858	1.0676	156.0	146.1	9.27
16.9	1.35874	1.0680	157.1	147.1	9.34
17.0	1.35891	1.0685	158.2	148.1	9.40
17.1	1.35907	1.0689	159.3	149.1	9.47
17.2	1.35923	1.0693	160.4	150.0	9.53
17.3	1.35940	1.0698	161.6	151.0	9.60
17.4	1.35956	1.0702	162.7	152.0	9.67
17.5	1.35972	1.0707	163.8	153.0	9.73
17.6	1.35989	1.0711	164.9	154.0	9.80
17.7	1.36005	1.0715	166.0	154.9	9.87
17.8	1.36021	1.0720	167.1	155.9	9.93
17.9	1.36038	1.0724	168.3	156.9	10.00
18.0	1.36054	1.0729	169.4	157.9	10.07
18.1	1.36070	1.0733	170.5	158.9	10.13
18.2	1.36087	1.0737	171.6	159.8	10.20
18.3	1.36103	1.0742	172.7	160.8	10.26
18.4	1.36120	1.0746	173.9	161.8	10.33
18.5	1.36136	1.0751	175.0	162.8	10.40
18.6	1.36153	1.0755	176.1	163.7	10.47
18.7	1.36169	1.0760	177.2	164.7	10.53
18.8	1.36185	1.0764	178.4	165.7	10.60
18.9	1.36202	1.0768	179.5	166.7	10.67
19.0	1.36219	1.0773	180.6	167.6	10.73
19.1	1.36235	1.0777	181.7	168.6	10.80
19.2	1.36252	1.0782	182.9	169.6	10.87
19.3	1.36268	1.0786	184.0	170.6	10.94
19.4	1.36285	1.0791	185.1	171.5	11.00
19.5	1.36301	1.0795	186.2	172.5	11.07
19.6	1.36318	1.0800	187.4	173.5	11.14
19.7	1.36334	1.0804	188.5	174.5	11.20
19.8	1.36351	1.0809	189.6	175.4	11.27
19.9	1.36368	1.0813	190.8	176.4	11.34

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
20.0	1.36384	1.0818	191.9	177.4	11.40
20.1	1.36401	1.0822	193.0	178.4	11.47
20.2	1.36418	1.0827	194.2	179.3	11.54
20.3	1.36434	1.0831	195.3	180.3	11.61
20.4	1.36451	1.0836	196.4	181.3	11.67
20.5	1.36468	1.0840	197.6	182.3	11.74
20.6	1.36484	1.0845	198.7	183.2	11.81
20.7	1.36501	1.0849	199.8	184.2	11.87
20.8	1.36518	1.0854	201.0	185.2	11.95
20.9	1.36535	1.0858	202.1	186.1	12.01
21.0	1.36551	1.0863	203.3	187.1	12.08
21.1	1.36568	1.0867	204.4	188.1	12.15
21.2	1.36585	1.0872	205.5	189.1	12.21
21.3	1.36602	1.0876	206.7	190.0	12.28
21.4	1.36619	1.0881	207.8	191.0	12.35
21.5	1.36635	1.0885	209.0	192.0	12.42
21.6	1.36652	1.0890	210.1	192.9	12.49
21.7	1.36669	1.0895	211.3	193.9	12.56
21.8	1.36686	1.0899	212.4	194.9	12.62
21.9	1.36703	1.0904	213.6	195.9	12.69
22.0	1.36720	1.0908	214.7	196.8	12.76
22.1	1.36737	1.0913	215.9	197.8	12.83
22.2	1.36754	1.0917	217.0	198.8	12.90
22.3	1.36771	1.0922	218.2	199.7	12.97
22.4	1.36787	1.0927	219.3	200.7	13.03
22.5	1.36804	1.0931	220.5	201.7	13.10
22.6	1.36821	1.0936	221.6	202.6	13.17
22.7	1.36838	1.0940	222.8	203.6	13.24
22.8	1.36855	1.0945	223.9	204.6	13.31
22.9	1.36872	1.0950	225.1	205.5	13.38
23.0	1.36889	1.0954	226.2	206.5	13.44
23.1	1.36906	1.0959	227.4	207.5	13.51
23.2	1.36924	1.0964	228.5	208.4	13.58
23.3	1.36941	1.0968	229.7	209.4	13.65
23.4	1.36958	1.0973	230.8	210.4	13.72
23.5	1.36975	1.0977	232.0	211.3	13.79
23.6	1.36992	1.0982	233.2	212.3	13.86
23.7	1.37009	1.0987	234.3	213.3	13.92
23.8	1.37026	1.0991	235.5	214.2	14.00
23.9	1.37043	1.0996	236.6	215.2	14.06
24.0	1.37060	1.1001	237.8	216.2	14.13
24.1	1.37078	1.1005	239.0	217.1	14.20
24.2	1.37095	1.1010	240.1	218.1	14.27
24.3	1.37112	1.1015	241.3	219.1	14.34
24.4	1.37129	1.1019	242.5	220.0	14.41
24.5	1.37146	1.1024	243.6	221.0	14.48
24.6	1.37164	1.1029	244.8	222.0	14.55
24.7	1.37181	1.1033	246.0	222.9	14.62
24.8	1.37198	1.1038	247.1	223.9	14.69
24.9	1.37216	1.1043	248.3	224.8	14.76

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20°C	Mass Density at 20°C	Sugars In g/l	Sugars In g/Kg	ABV % vol At 20°C
25.0	1.37233	1.1047	249.5	225.8	14.83
25.1	1.37250	1.1052	250.6	226.8	14.89
25.2	1.37267	1.1057	251.8	227.7	14.96
25.3	1.37285	1.1062	253.0	228.7	15.04
25.4	1.37302	1.1066	254.1	229.7	15.10
25.5	1.37319	1.1071	255.3	230.6	15.17
25.6	1.37337	1.1076	256.5	231.6	15.24
25.7	1.37354	1.1080	257.7	232.5	15.32
25.8	1.37372	1.1085	258.8	233.5	15.38
25.9	1.37389	1.1090	260.0	234.5	15.45
26.0	1.37407	1.1095	261.2	235.4	15.52
26.1	1.37424	1.1099	262.4	236.4	15.59
26.2	1.37441	1.1104	263.6	237.3	15.67
26.3	1.37459	1.1109	264.7	238.3	15.73
26.4	1.37476	1.1114	265.9	239.3	15.80
26.5	1.37494	1.1118	267.1	240.2	15.87
26.6	1.37511	1.1123	268.3	241.2	15.95
26.7	1.37529	1.1128	269.5	242.1	16.02
26.8	1.37546	1.1133	270.6	243.1	16.08
26.9	1.37564	1.1138	271.8	244.1	16.15
27.0	1.37582	1.1142	273.0	245.0	16.22
27.1	1.37599	1.1147	274.2	246.0	16.30
27.2	1.37617	1.1152	275.4	246.9	16.37
27.3	1.37634	1.1157	276.6	247.9	16.44
27.4	1.37652	1.1161	277.8	248.9	16.51
27.5	1.37670	1.1166	278.9	249.8	16.58
27.6	1.37687	1.1171	280.1	250.8	16.65
27.7	1.37705	1.1176	281.3	251.7	16.72
27.8	1.37723	1.1181	282.5	252.7	16.79
27.9	1.37740	1.1185	283.7	253.6	16.86
28.0	1.37758	1.1190	284.9	254.6	16.93
28.1	1.37776	1.1195	286.1	255.5	17.00
28.2	1.37793	1.1200	287.3	256.5	17.07
28.3	1.37811	1.1205	288.5	257.5	17.15
28.4	1.37829	1.1210	289.7	258.4	17.22
28.5	1.37847	1.1214	290.9	259.4	17.29
28.6	1.37864	1.1219	292.1	260.3	17.36
28.7	1.37882	1.1224	293.3	261.3	17.43
28.8	1.37900	1.1229	294.5	262.2	17.50
28.9	1.37918	1.1234	295.7	263.2	17.57
29.0	1.37936	1.1239	296.9	264.2	17.64
29.1	1.37954	1.1244	298.1	265.1	17.72
29.2	1.37972	1.1248	299.3	266.1	17.79
29.3	1.37989	1.1253	300.5	267.0	17.86
29.4	1.38007	1.1258	301.7	268.0	17.93
29.5	1.38025	1.1263	302.9	268.9	18.00
29.6	1.38043	1.1268	304.1	269.9	18.07
29.7	1.38061	1.1273	305.3	270.8	18.14
29.8	1.38079	1.1278	306.5	271.8	18.22
29.9	1.38097	1.1283	307.7	272.7	18.29

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
30.0	1.38115	1.1287	308.9	273.7	18.36
30.1	1.38133	1.1292	310.1	274.6	18.43
30.2	1.38151	1.1297	311.3	275.6	18.50
30.3	1.38169	1.1302	312.6	276.5	18.58
30.4	1.38187	1.1307	313.8	277.5	18.65
30.5	1.38205	1.1312	315.0	278.5	18.72
30.6	1.38223	1.1317	316.2	279.4	18.79
30.7	1.38241	1.1322	317.4	280.4	18.86
30.8	1.38259	1.1327	318.6	281.3	18.93
30.9	1.38277	1.1332	319.8	282.3	19.01
31.0	1.38296	1.1337	321.1	283.2	19.08
31.1	1.38314	1.1342	322.3	284.2	19.15
31.2	1.38332	1.1346	323.5	285.1	19.23
31.3	1.38350	1.1351	324.7	286.1	19.30
31.4	1.38368	1.1356	325.9	287.0	19.37
31.5	1.38386	1.1361	327.2	288.0	19.45
31.6	1.38405	1.1366	328.4	288.9	19.52
31.7	1.38423	1.1371	329.6	289.9	19.59
31.8	1.38441	1.1376	330.8	290.8	19.66
31.9	1.38459	1.1381	332.1	291.8	19.74
32.0	1.38478	1.1386	333.3	292.7	19.81
32.1	1.38496	1.1391	334.5	293.7	19.88
32.2	1.38514	1.1396	335.7	294.6	19.95
32.3	1.38532	1.1401	337.0	295.6	20.03
32.4	1.38551	1.1406	338.2	296.5	20.10
32.5	1.38569	1.1411	339.4	297.5	20.17
32.6	1.38587	1.1416	340.7	298.4	20.25
32.7	1.38606	1.1421	341.9	299.4	20.32
32.8	1.38624	1.1426	343.1	300.3	20.39
32.9	1.38643	1.1431	344.4	301.3	20.47
33.0	1.38661	1.1436	345.6	302.2	20.54
33.1	1.38679	1.1441	346.8	303.2	20.61
33.2	1.38698	1.1446	348.1	304.1	20.69
33.3	1.38716	1.1451	349.3	305.0	20.76
33.4	1.38735	1.1456	350.6	306.0	20.84
33.5	1.38753	1.1461	351.8	306.9	20.91
33.6	1.38772	1.1466	353.0	307.9	20.98
33.7	1.38790	1.1471	354.3	308.8	21.06
33.8	1.38809	1.1476	355.5	309.8	21.13
33.9	1.38827	1.1481	356.8	310.7	21.20
34.0	1.38846	1.1486	358.0	311.7	21.28
34.1	1.38864	1.1491	359.2	312.6	21.35
34.2	1.38883	1.1496	360.5	313.6	21.42
34.3	1.38902	1.1501	361.7	314.5	21.50
34.4	1.38920	1.1507	363.0	315.5	21.57
34.5	1.38939	1.1512	364.2	316.4	21.64
34.6	1.38958	1.1517	365.5	317.4	21.72
34.7	1.38976	1.1522	366.7	318.3	21.79
34.8	1.38995	1.1527	368.0	319.2	21.87
34.9	1.39014	1.1532	369.2	320.2	21.94

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
35.0	1.39032	1.1537	370.5	321.1	22.02
35.1	1.39051	1.1542	371.8	322.1	22.10
35.2	1.39070	1.1547	373.0	323.0	22.17
35.3	1.39088	1.1552	374.3	324.0	22.24
35.4	1.39107	1.1557	375.5	324.9	22.32
35.5	1.39126	1.1563	376.8	325.9	22.39
35.6	1.39145	1.1568	378.0	326.8	22.46
35.7	1.39164	1.1573	379.3	327.8	22.54
35.8	1.39182	1.1578	380.6	328.7	22.62
35.9	1.39201	1.1583	381.8	329.6	22.69
36.0	1.39220	1.1588	383.1	330.6	22.77
36.1	1.39239	1.1593	384.4	331.5	22.84
36.2	1.39258	1.1598	385.6	332.5	22.92
36.3	1.39277	1.1603	386.9	333.4	22.99
36.4	1.39296	1.1609	388.1	334.4	23.06
36.5	1.39314	1.1614	389.4	335.3	23.14
36.6	1.39333	1.1619	390.7	336.3	23.22
36.7	1.39352	1.1624	392.0	337.2	23.30
36.8	1.39371	1.1629	393.2	338.1	23.37
36.9	1.39390	1.1634	394.5	339.1	23.45
37.0	1.39409	1.1640	395.8	340.0	23.52
37.1	1.39428	1.1645	397.0	341.0	23.59
37.2	1.39447	1.1650	398.3	341.9	23.67
37.3	1.39466	1.1655	399.6	342.9	23.75
37.4	1.39485	1.1660	400.9	343.8	23.83
37.5	1.39504	1.1665	402.1	344.7	23.90
37.6	1.39524	1.1671	403.4	345.7	23.97
37.7	1.39543	1.1676	404.7	346.6	24.05
37.8	1.39562	1.1681	406.0	347.6	24.13
37.9	1.39581	1.1686	407.3	348.5	24.21
38.0	1.39600	1.1691	408.6	349.4	24.28
38.1	1.39619	1.1697	409.8	350.4	24.35
38.2	1.39638	1.1702	411.1	351.3	24.43
38.3	1.39658	1.1707	412.4	352.3	24.51
38.4	1.39677	1.1712	413.7	353.2	24.59
38.5	1.39696	1.1717	415.0	354.2	24.66
38.6	1.39715	1.1723	416.3	355.1	24.74
38.7	1.39734	1.1728	417.6	356.0	24.82
38.8	1.39754	1.1733	418.8	357.0	24.89
38.9	1.39773	1.1738	420.1	357.9	24.97
39.0	1.39792	1.1744	421.4	358.9	25.04
39.1	1.39812	1.1749	422.7	359.8	25.12
39.2	1.39831	1.1754	424.0	360.7	25.20
39.3	1.39850	1.1759	425.3	361.7	25.28
39.4	1.39870	1.1765	426.6	362.6	25.35
39.5	1.39889	1.1770	427.9	363.6	25.43
39.6	1.39908	1.1775	429.2	364.5	25.51
39.7	1.39928	1.1780	430.5	365.4	25.58
39.8	1.39947	1.1786	431.8	366.4	25.66
39.9	1.39967	1.1791	433.1	367.3	25.74

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
40.0	1.39986	1.1796	434.4	368.3	25.82
40.1	1.40006	1.1801	435.7	369.2	25.89
40.2	1.40025	1.1807	437.0	370.1	25.97
40.3	1.40044	1.1812	438.3	371.1	26.05
40.4	1.40064	1.1817	439.6	372.0	26.13
40.5	1.40083	1.1823	440.9	373.0	26.20
40.6	1.40103	1.1828	442.2	373.9	26.28
40.7	1.40123	1.1833	443.6	374.8	26.36
40.8	1.40142	1.1839	444.9	375.8	26.44
40.9	1.40162	1.1844	446.2	376.7	26.52
41.0	1.40181	1.1849	447.5	377.7	26.59
41.1	1.40201	1.1855	448.8	378.6	26.67
41.2	1.40221	1.1860	450.1	379.5	26.75
41.3	1.40240	1.1865	451.4	380.5	26.83
41.4	1.40260	1.1871	452.8	381.4	26.91
41.5	1.40280	1.1876	454.1	382.3	26.99
41.6	1.40299	1.1881	455.4	383.3	27.06
41.7	1.40319	1.1887	456.7	384.2	27.14
41.8	1.40339	1.1892	458.0	385.2	27.22
41.9	1.40358	1.1897	459.4	386.1	27.30
42.0	1.40378	1.1903	460.7	387.0	27.38
42.1	1.40398	1.1908	462.0	388.0	27.46
42.2	1.40418	1.1913	463.3	388.9	27.53
42.3	1.40437	1.1919	464.7	389.9	27.62
42.4	1.40457	1.1924	466.0	390.8	27.69
42.5	1.40477	1.1929	467.3	391.7	27.77
42.6	1.40497	1.1935	468.6	392.7	27.85
42.7	1.40517	1.1940	470.0	393.6	27.93
42.8	1.40537	1.1946	471.3	394.5	28.01
42.9	1.40557	1.1951	472.6	395.5	28.09
43.0	1.40576	1.1956	474.0	396.4	28.17
43.1	1.40596	1.1962	475.3	397.3	28.25
43.2	1.40616	1.1967	476.6	398.3	28.32
43.3	1.40636	1.1973	478.0	399.2	28.41
43.4	1.40656	1.1978	479.3	400.2	28.48
43.5	1.40676	1.1983	480.7	401.1	28.57
43.6	1.40696	1.1989	482.0	402.0	28.65
43.7	1.40716	1.1994	483.3	403.0	28.72
43.8	1.40736	1.2000	484.7	403.9	28.81
43.9	1.40756	1.2005	486.0	404.8	28.88
44.0	1.40776	1.2011	487.4	405.8	28.97
44.1	1.40796	1.2016	488.7	406.7	29.04
44.2	1.40817	1.2022	490.1	407.6	29.13
44.3	1.40837	1.2027	491.4	408.6	29.20
44.4	1.40857	1.2032	492.8	409.5	29.29
44.5	1.40877	1.2038	494.1	410.4	29.36
44.6	1.40897	1.2043	495.5	411.4	29.45
44.7	1.40917	1.2049	496.8	412.3	29.52
44.8	1.40937	1.2054	498.2	413.3	29.61
44.9	1.40958	1.2060	499.5	414.2	29.69

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
45.0	1.40978	1.2065	500.9	415.1	29.77
45.1	1.40998	1.2071	502.2	416.1	29.85
45.2	1.41018	1.2076	503.6	417.0	29.93
45.3	1.41039	1.2082	504.9	417.9	30.01
45.4	1.41059	1.2087	506.3	418.9	30.09
45.5	1.41079	1.2093	507.7	419.8	30.17
45.6	1.41099	1.2098	509.0	420.7	30.25
45.7	1.41120	1.2104	510.4	421.7	30.33
45.8	1.41140	1.2109	511.7	422.6	30.41
45.9	1.41160	1.2115	513.1	423.5	30.49
46.0	1.41181	1.2120	514.5	424.5	30.58
46.1	1.41201	1.2126	515.8	425.4	30.65
46.2	1.41222	1.2131	517.2	426.3	30.74
46.3	1.41242	1.2137	518.6	427.3	30.82
46.4	1.41262	1.2142	519.9	428.2	30.90
46.5	1.41283	1.2148	521.3	429.1	30.98
46.6	1.41303	1.2154	522.7	430.1	31.06
46.7	1.41324	1.2159	524.1	431.0	31.15
46.8	1.41344	1.2165	525.4	431.9	31.22
46.9	1.41365	1.2170	526.8	432.9	31.31
47.0	1.41385	1.2176	528.2	433.8	31.39
47.1	1.41406	1.2181	529.6	434.7	31.47
47.2	1.41427	1.2187	530.9	435.7	31.55
47.3	1.41447	1.2192	532.3	436.6	31.63
47.4	1.41468	1.2198	533.7	437.5	31.72
47.5	1.41488	1.2204	535.1	438.5	31.80
47.6	1.41509	1.2209	536.5	439.4	31.88
47.7	1.41530	1.2215	537.9	440.3	31.97
47.8	1.41550	1.2220	539.2	441.3	32.04
47.9	1.41571	1.2226	540.6	442.2	32.13
48.0	1.41592	1.2232	542.0	443.1	32.21
48.1	1.41612	1.2237	543.4	444.1	32.29
48.2	1.41633	1.2243	544.8	445.0	32.38
48.3	1.41654	1.2248	546.2	445.9	32.46
48.4	1.41674	1.2254	547.6	446.8	32.54
48.5	1.41695	1.2260	549.0	447.8	32.63
48.6	1.41716	1.2265	550.4	448.7	32.71
48.7	1.41737	1.2271	551.8	449.6	32.79
48.8	1.41758	1.2277	553.2	450.6	32.88
48.9	1.41779	1.2282	554.6	451.5	32.96
49.0	1.41799	1.2288	556.0	452.4	33.04
49.1	1.41820	1.2294	557.4	453.4	33.13
49.2	1.41841	1.2299	558.8	454.3	33.21
49.3	1.41862	1.2305	560.2	455.2	33.29
49.4	1.41883	1.2311	561.6	456.2	33.38
49.5	1.41904	1.2316	563.0	457.1	33.46
49.6	1.41925	1.2322	564.4	458.0	33.54
49.7	1.41946	1.2328	565.8	458.9	33.63
49.8	1.41967	1.2333	567.2	459.9	33.71
49.9	1.41988	1.2339	568.6	460.8	33.79

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
50.0	1.42009	1.2345	570.0	461.7	33.88
50.1	1.42030	1.2350	571.4	462.7	33.96
50.2	1.42051	1.2356	572.8	463.6	34.04
50.3	1.42072	1.2362	574.2	464.5	34.12
50.4	1.42093	1.2368	575.6	465.4	34.21
50.5	1.42114	1.2373	577.1	466.4	34.30
50.6	1.42135	1.2379	578.5	467.3	34.38
50.7	1.42156	1.2385	579.9	468.2	34.46
50.8	1.42177	1.2390	581.3	469.2	34.55
50.9	1.42199	1.2396	582.7	470.1	34.63
51.0	1.42220	1.2402	584.2	471.0	34.72
51.1	1.42241	1.2408	585.6	471.9	34.80
51.2	1.42262	1.2413	587.0	472.9	34.89
51.3	1.42283	1.2419	588.4	473.8	34.97
51.4	1.42305	1.2425	589.9	474.7	35.06
51.5	1.42326	1.2431	591.3	475.7	35.14
51.6	1.42347	1.2436	592.7	476.6	35.22
51.7	1.42368	1.2442	594.1	477.5	35.31
51.8	1.42390	1.2448	595.6	478.4	35.40
51.9	1.42411	1.2454	597.0	479.4	35.48
52.0	1.42432	1.2460	598.4	480.3	35.56
52.1	1.42454	1.2465	599.9	481.2	35.65
52.2	1.42475	1.2471	601.3	482.1	35.74
52.3	1.42496	1.2477	602.7	483.1	35.82
52.4	1.42518	1.2483	604.2	484.0	35.91
52.5	1.42539	1.2488	605.6	484.9	35.99
52.6	1.42561	1.2494	607.0	485.8	36.07
52.7	1.42582	1.2500	608.5	486.8	36.16
52.8	1.42604	1.2506	609.9	487.7	36.25
52.9	1.42625	1.2512	611.4	488.6	36.34
53.0	1.42647	1.2518	612.8	489.5	36.42
53.1	1.42668	1.2523	614.2	490.5	36.50
53.2	1.42690	1.2529	615.7	491.4	36.59
53.3	1.42711	1.2535	617.1	492.3	36.67
53.4	1.42733	1.2541	618.6	493.2	36.76
53.5	1.42754	1.2547	620.0	494.2	36.85
53.6	1.42776	1.2553	621.5	495.1	36.94
53.7	1.42798	1.2558	622.9	496.0	37.02
53.8	1.42819	1.2564	624.4	496.9	37.11
53.9	1.42841	1.2570	625.8	497.9	37.19
54.0	1.42863	1.2576	627.3	498.8	37.28
54.1	1.42884	1.2582	628.7	499.7	37.36
54.2	1.42906	1.2588	630.2	500.6	37.45
54.3	1.42928	1.2594	631.7	501.6	37.54
54.4	1.42949	1.2600	633.1	502.5	37.63
54.5	1.42971	1.2606	634.6	503.4	37.71
54.6	1.42993	1.2611	636.0	504.3	37.80
54.7	1.43015	1.2617	637.5	505.2	37.89
54.8	1.43036	1.2623	639.0	506.2	37.98
54.9	1.43058	1.2629	640.4	507.1	38.06

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
55.0	1.43080	1.2635	641.9	508.0	38.15
55.1	1.43102	1.2641	643.4	508.9	38.24
55.2	1.43124	1.2647	644.8	509.9	38.32
55.3	1.43146	1.2653	646.3	510.8	38.41
55.4	1.43168	1.2659	647.8	511.7	38.50
55.5	1.43189	1.2665	649.2	512.6	38.58
55.6	1.43211	1.2671	650.7	513.5	38.67
55.7	1.43233	1.2677	652.2	514.5	38.76
55.8	1.43255	1.2683	653.7	515.4	38.85
55.9	1.43277	1.2689	655.1	516.3	38.93
56.0	1.43299	1.2695	656.6	517.2	39.02
56.1	1.43321	1.2701	658.1	518.1	39.11
56.2	1.43343	1.2706	659.6	519.1	39.20
56.3	1.43365	1.2712	661.0	520.0	39.28
56.4	1.43387	1.2718	662.5	520.9	39.37
56.5	1.43410	1.2724	664.0	521.8	39.46
56.6	1.43432	1.2730	665.5	522.7	39.55
56.7	1.43454	1.2736	667.0	523.7	39.64
56.8	1.43476	1.2742	668.5	524.6	39.73
56.9	1.43498	1.2748	669.9	525.5	39.81
57.0	1.43520	1.2754	671.4	526.4	39.90
57.1	1.43542	1.2760	672.9	527.3	39.99
57.2	1.43565	1.2766	674.4	528.3	40.08
57.3	1.43587	1.2773	675.9	529.2	40.17
57.4	1.43609	1.2779	677.4	530.1	40.26
57.5	1.43631	1.2785	678.9	531.0	40.35
57.6	1.43653	1.2791	680.4	531.9	40.44
57.7	1.43676	1.2797	681.9	532.8	40.53
57.8	1.43698	1.2803	683.4	533.8	40.61
57.9	1.43720	1.2809	684.9	534.7	40.70
58.0	1.43743	1.2815	686.4	535.6	40.79
58.1	1.43765	1.2821	687.9	536.5	40.88
58.2	1.43787	1.2827	689.4	537.4	40.97
58.3	1.43810	1.2833	690.9	538.3	41.06
58.4	1.43832	1.2839	692.4	539.3	41.15
58.5	1.43855	1.2845	693.9	540.2	41.24
58.6	1.43877	1.2851	695.4	541.1	41.33
58.7	1.43899	1.2857	696.9	542.0	41.42
58.8	1.43922	1.2863	698.4	542.9	41.51
58.9	1.43944	1.2870	699.9	543.8	41.60
59.0	1.43967	1.2876	701.4	544.8	41.68
59.1	1.43989	1.2882	702.9	545.7	41.77
59.2	1.44012	1.2888	704.4	546.6	41.86
59.3	1.44035	1.2894	706.0	547.5	41.96
59.4	1.44057	1.2900	707.5	548.4	42.05
59.5	1.44080	1.2906	709.0	549.3	42.14
59.6	1.44102	1.2912	710.5	550.2	42.23
59.7	1.44125	1.2919	712.0	551.1	42.31
59.8	1.44148	1.2925	713.5	552.1	42.40
59.9	1.44170	1.2931	715.1	553.0	42.50

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
60.0	1.44193	1.2937	716.6	553.9	42.59
60.1	1.44216	1.2943	718.1	554.8	42.68
60.2	1.44238	1.2949	719.6	555.7	42.77
60.3	1.44261	1.2956	721.1	556.6	42.85
60.4	1.44284	1.2962	722.7	557.5	42.95
60.5	1.44306	1.2968	724.2	558.4	43.04
60.6	1.44329	1.2974	725.7	559.4	43.13
60.7	1.44352	1.2980	727.3	560.3	43.22
60.8	1.44375	1.2986	728.8	561.2	43.31
60.9	1.44398	1.2993	730.3	562.1	43.40
61.0	1.44420	1.2999	731.8	563.0	43.49
61.1	1.44443	1.3005	733.4	563.9	43.59
61.2	1.44466	1.3011	734.9	564.8	43.68
61.3	1.44489	1.3017	736.4	565.7	43.76
61.4	1.44512	1.3024	738.0	566.6	43.86
61.5	1.44535	1.3030	739.5	567.6	43.95
61.6	1.44558	1.3036	741.1	568.5	44.04
61.7	1.44581	1.3042	742.6	569.4	44.13
61.8	1.44604	1.3049	744.1	570.3	44.22
61.9	1.44627	1.3055	745.7	571.2	44.32
62.0	1.44650	1.3061	747.2	572.1	44.41
62.1	1.44673	1.3067	748.8	573.0	44.50
62.2	1.44696	1.3074	750.3	573.9	44.59
62.3	1.44719	1.3080	751.9	574.8	44.69
62.4	1.44742	1.3086	753.4	575.7	44.77
62.5	1.44765	1.3092	755.0	576.6	44.87
62.6	1.44788	1.3099	756.5	577.5	44.96
62.7	1.44811	1.3105	758.1	578.5	45.05
62.8	1.44834	1.3111	759.6	579.4	45.14
62.9	1.44858	1.3118	761.2	580.3	45.24
63.0	1.44881	1.3124	762.7	581.2	45.33
63.1	1.44904	1.3130	764.3	582.1	45.42
63.2	1.44927	1.3137	765.8	583.0	45.51
63.3	1.44950	1.3143	767.4	583.9	45.61
63.4	1.44974	1.3149	769.0	584.8	45.70
63.5	1.44997	1.3155	770.5	585.7	45.79
63.6	1.45020	1.3162	772.1	586.6	45.89
63.7	1.45043	1.3168	773.6	587.5	45.98
63.8	1.45067	1.3174	775.2	588.4	46.07
63.9	1.45090	1.3181	776.8	589.3	46.17
64.0	1.45113	1.3187	778.3	590.2	46.25
64.1	1.45137	1.3193	779.9	591.1	46.35
64.2	1.45160	1.3200	781.5	592.0	46.44
64.3	1.45184	1.3206	783.0	592.9	46.53
64.4	1.45207	1.3213	784.6	593.8	46.63
64.5	1.45230	1.3219	786.2	594.7	46.72
64.6	1.45254	1.3225	787.8	595.6	46.82
64.7	1.45277	1.3232	789.3	596.5	46.91
64.8	1.45301	1.3238	790.9	597.4	47.00
64.9	1.45324	1.3244	792.5	598.3	47.10

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
65.0	1.45348	1.3251	794.1	599.3	47.19
65.1	1.45371	1.3257	795.6	600.2	47.28
65.2	1.45395	1.3264	797.2	601.1	47.38
65.3	1.45418	1.3270	798.8	602.0	47.47
65.4	1.45442	1.3276	800.4	602.9	47.57
65.5	1.45466	1.3283	802.0	603.8	47.66
65.6	1.45489	1.3289	803.6	604.7	47.76
65.7	1.45513	1.3296	805.1	605.6	47.85
65.8	1.45537	1.3302	806.7	606.5	47.94
65.9	1.45560	1.3309	808.3	607.4	48.04
66.0	1.45584	1.3315	809.9	608.3	48.13
66.1	1.45608	1.3322	811.5	609.2	48.23
66.2	1.45631	1.3328	813.1	610.1	48.32
66.3	1.45655	1.3334	814.7	611.0	48.42
66.4	1.45679	1.3341	816.3	611.9	48.51
66.5	1.45703	1.3347	817.9	612.8	48.61
66.6	1.45726	1.3354	819.5	613.7	48.70
66.7	1.45750	1.3360	821.1	614.6	48.80
66.8	1.45774	1.3367	822.7	615.5	48.89
66.9	1.45798	1.3373	824.3	616.3	48.99
67.0	1.45822	1.3380	825.9	617.2	49.08
67.1	1.45846	1.3386	827.5	618.1	49.18
67.2	1.45870	1.3393	829.1	619.0	49.27
67.3	1.45893	1.3399	830.7	619.9	49.37
67.4	1.45917	1.3406	832.3	620.8	49.46
67.5	1.45941	1.3412	833.9	621.7	49.56
67.6	1.45965	1.3419	835.5	622.6	49.65
67.7	1.45989	1.3425	837.1	623.5	49.75
67.8	1.46013	1.3432	838.7	624.4	49.84
67.9	1.46037	1.3438	840.3	625.3	49.94
68.0	1.46061	1.3445	841.9	626.2	50.03
68.1	1.46085	1.3451	843.6	627.1	50.14
68.2	1.46109	1.3458	845.2	628.0	50.23
68.3	1.46134	1.3464	846.8	628.9	50.33
68.4	1.46158	1.3471	848.4	629.8	50.42
68.5	1.46182	1.3478	850.0	630.7	50.52
68.6	1.46206	1.3484	851.6	631.6	50.61
68.7	1.46230	1.3491	853.3	632.5	50.71
68.8	1.46254	1.3497	854.9	633.4	50.81
68.9	1.46278	1.3504	856.5	634.3	50.90
69.0	1.46303	1.3510	858.1	635.2	51.00
69.1	1.46327	1.3517	859.8	636.1	51.10
69.2	1.46351	1.3524	861.4	636.9	51.19
69.3	1.46375	1.3530	863.0	637.8	51.29
69.4	1.46400	1.3537	864.7	638.7	51.39
69.5	1.46424	1.3543	866.3	639.6	51.48
69.6	1.46448	1.3550	867.9	640.5	51.58
69.7	1.46473	1.3557	869.5	641.4	51.67
69.8	1.46497	1.3563	871.2	642.3	51.78
69.9	1.46521	1.3570	872.8	643.2	51.87

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
70.0	1.46546	1.3576	874.5	644.1	51.97
70.1	1.46570	1.3583	876.1	645.0	52.07
70.2	1.46594	1.3590	877.7	645.9	52.16
70.3	1.46619	1.3596	879.4	646.8	52.26
70.4	1.46643	1.3603	881.0	647.7	52.36
70.5	1.46668	1.3610	882.7	648.5	52.46
70.6	1.46692	1.3616	884.3	649.4	52.55
70.7	1.46717	1.3623	886.0	650.3	52.65
70.8	1.46741	1.3630	887.6	651.2	52.75
70.9	1.46766	1.3636	889.3	652.1	52.85
71.0	1.46790	1.3643	890.9	653.0	52.95
71.1	1.46815	1.3650	892.6	653.9	53.05
71.2	1.46840	1.3656	894.2	654.8	53.14
71.3	1.46864	1.3663	895.9	655.7	53.24
71.4	1.46889	1.3670	897.5	656.6	53.34
71.5	1.46913	1.3676	899.2	657.5	53.44
71.6	1.46938	1.3683	900.8	658.3	53.53
71.7	1.46963	1.3690	902.5	659.2	53.64
71.8	1.46987	1.3696	904.1	660.1	53.73
71.9	1.47012	1.3703	905.8	661.0	53.83
72.0	1.47037	1.3710	907.5	661.9	53.93
72.1	1.47062	1.3717	909.1	662.8	54.03
72.2	1.47086	1.3723	910.8	663.7	54.13
72.3	1.47111	1.3730	912.5	664.6	54.23
72.4	1.47136	1.3737	914.1	665.5	54.32
72.5	1.47161	1.3743	915.8	666.3	54.43
72.6	1.47186	1.3750	917.5	667.2	54.53
72.7	1.47210	1.3757	919.1	668.1	54.62
72.8	1.47235	1.3764	920.8	669.0	54.72
72.9	1.47260	1.3770	922.5	669.9	54.82
73.0	1.47285	1.3777	924.2	670.8	54.93
73.1	1.47310	1.3784	925.8	671.7	55.02
73.2	1.47335	1.3791	927.5	672.6	55.12
73.3	1.47360	1.3797	929.2	673.5	55.22
73.4	1.47385	1.3804	930.9	674.3	55.32
73.5	1.47410	1.3811	932.6	675.2	55.42
73.6	1.47435	1.3818	934.3	676.1	55.53
73.7	1.47460	1.3825	935.9	677.0	55.62
73.8	1.47485	1.3831	937.6	677.9	55.72
73.9	1.47510	1.3838	939.3	678.8	55.82
74.0	1.47535	1.3845	941.0	679.7	55.92
74.1	1.47560	1.3852	942.7	680.6	56.02
74.2	1.47585	1.3859	944.4	681.4	56.13
74.3	1.47610	1.3865	946.1	682.3	56.23
74.4	1.47635	1.3872	947.8	683.2	56.33
74.5	1.47661	1.3879	949.5	684.1	56.43
74.6	1.47686	1.3886	951.2	685.0	56.53
74.7	1.47711	1.3893	952.9	685.9	56.63
74.8	1.47736	1.3899	954.6	686.8	56.73
74.9	1.47761	1.3906	956.3	687.7	56.83

Table 27. Sucrose refractive index in vineyard. Table giving the sugar concentration in rectified concentrated must in grams per litre and in grams per kilogram, determined using a graduated refractometer, either in % by mass sucrose at 20 °C, or refractive index at 20 °C.

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
50.0	1.42008	1.2342	627.6	508.5	37.30
50.1	1.42029	1.2348	629.3	509.6	37.40
50.2	1.42050	1.2355	630.9	510.6	37.49
50.3	1.42071	1.2362	632.4	511.6	37.58
50.4	1.42092	1.2367	634.1	512.7	37.68
50.5	1.42113	1.2374	635.7	513.7	37.78
50.6	1.42135	1.2381	637.3	514.7	37.87
50.7	1.42156	1.2386	638.7	515.7	37.96
50.8	1.42177	1.2391	640.4	516.8	38.06
50.9	1.42198	1.2396	641.9	517.8	38.15
51.0	1.42219	1.2401	643.4	518.8	38.24
51.1	1.42240	1.2406	645.0	519.9	38.33
51.2	1.42261	1.2411	646.5	520.9	38.42
51.3	1.42282	1.2416	648.1	522.0	38.52
51.4	1.42304	1.2421	649.6	523.0	38.61
51.5	1.42325	1.2427	651.2	524.0	38.70
51.6	1.42347	1.2434	652.9	525.1	38.80
51.7	1.42368	1.2441	654.5	526.1	38.90
51.8	1.42389	1.2447	656.1	527.1	38.99
51.9	1.42410	1.2454	657.8	528.2	39.09
52.0	1.42432	1.2461	659.4	529.2	39.19
52.1	1.42453	1.2466	661.0	530.2	39.28
52.2	1.42475	1.2470	662.5	531.3	39.37
52.3	1.42496	1.2475	664.1	532.3	39.47
52.4	1.42517	1.2480	665.6	533.3	39.56
52.5	1.42538	1.2486	667.2	534.4	39.65
52.6	1.42560	1.2493	668.9	535.4	39.75
52.7	1.42581	1.2500	670.5	536.4	39.85
52.8	1.42603	1.2506	672.2	537.5	39.95
52.9	1.42624	1.2513	673.8	538.5	40.04
53.0	1.42645	1.2520	675.5	539.5	40.14
53.1	1.42667	1.2525	677.1	540.6	40.24
53.2	1.42689	1.2530	678.5	541.5	40.32
53.3	1.42711	1.2535	680.2	542.6	40.42
53.4	1.42733	1.2540	681.8	543.7	40.52
53.5	1.42754	1.2546	683.4	544.7	40.61
53.6	1.42776	1.2553	685.1	545.8	40.72
53.7	1.42797	1.2560	686.7	546.7	40.81
53.8	1.42819	1.2566	688.4	547.8	40.91
53.9	1.42840	1.2573	690.1	548.9	41.01
54.0	1.42861	1.2580	691.7	549.8	41.11
54.1	1.42884	1.2585	693.3	550.9	41.20
54.2	1.42906	1.2590	694.9	551.9	41.30
54.3	1.42927	1.2595	696.5	553.0	41.39
54.4	1.42949	1.2600	698.1	554.0	41.49
54.5	1.42971	1.2606	699.7	555.1	41.58
54.6	1.42993	1.2613	701.4	556.1	41.68
54.7	1.43014	1.2620	703.1	557.1	41.79
54.8	1.43036	1.2625	704.7	558.2	41.88
54.9	1.43058	1.2630	706.2	559.1	41.97

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
55.0	1.43079	1.2635	707.8	560.2	42.06
55.1	1.43102	1.2639	709.4	561.3	42.16
55.2	1.43124	1.2645	711.0	562.3	42.25
55.3	1.43146	1.2652	712.7	563.3	42.36
55.4	1.43168	1.2659	714.4	564.3	42.46
55.5	1.43189	1.2665	716.1	565.4	42.56
55.6	1.43211	1.2672	717.8	566.4	42.66
55.7	1.43233	1.2679	719.5	567.5	42.76
55.8	1.43255	1.2685	721.1	568.5	42.85
55.9	1.43277	1.2692	722.8	569.5	42.96
56.0	1.43298	1.2699	724.5	570.5	43.06
56.1	1.43321	1.2703	726.1	571.6	43.15
56.2	1.43343	1.2708	727.7	572.6	43.25
56.3	1.43365	1.2713	729.3	573.7	43.34
56.4	1.43387	1.2718	730.9	574.7	43.44
56.5	1.43409	1.2724	732.6	575.8	43.54
56.6	1.43431	1.2731	734.3	576.8	43.64
56.7	1.43454	1.2738	736.0	577.8	43.74
56.8	1.43476	1.2744	737.6	578.8	43.84
56.9	1.43498	1.2751	739.4	579.9	43.94
57.0	1.43519	1.2758	741.1	580.9	44.04
57.1	1.43542	1.2763	742.8	582.0	44.14
57.2	1.43564	1.2768	744.4	583.0	44.24
57.3	1.43586	1.2773	745.9	584.0	44.33
57.4	1.43609	1.2778	747.6	585.1	44.43
57.5	1.43631	1.2784	749.3	586.1	44.53
57.6	1.43653	1.2791	751.0	587.1	44.63
57.7	1.43675	1.2798	752.7	588.1	44.73
57.8	1.43698	1.2804	754.4	589.2	44.83
57.9	1.43720	1.2810	756.1	590.2	44.94
58.0	1.43741	1.2818	757.8	591.2	45.04
58.1	1.43764	1.2822	759.5	592.3	45.14
58.2	1.43784	1.2827	761.1	593.4	45.23
58.3	1.43909	1.2832	762.6	594.3	45.32
58.4	1.43832	1.2837	764.3	595.4	45.42
58.5	1.43854	1.2843	766.0	596.4	45.52
58.6	1.43877	1.2850	767.8	597.5	45.63
58.7	1.43899	1.2857	769.5	598.5	45.73
58.8	1.43922	1.2863	771.1	599.5	45.83
58.9	1.43944	1.2869	772.9	600.6	45.93
59.0	1.43966	1.2876	774.6	601.6	46.03
59.1	1.43988	1.2882	776.3	602.6	46.14
59.2	1.44011	1.2889	778.1	603.7	46.24
59.3	1.44034	1.2896	779.8	604.7	46.34
59.4	1.44057	1.2902	781.6	605.8	46.45
59.5	1.44079	1.2909	783.3	606.8	46.55
59.6	1.44102	1.2916	785.2	607.9	46.66
59.7	1.44124	1.2921	786.8	608.9	46.76
59.8	1.44147	1.2926	788.4	609.9	46.85
59.9	1.44169	1.2931	790.0	610.9	46.95

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
60.0	1.44192	1.2936	791.7	612.0	47.05
60.1	1.44215	1.2942	793.3	613.0	47.15
60.2	1.44238	1.2949	795.2	614.1	47.26
60.3	1.44260	1.2956	796.9	615.1	47.36
60.4	1.44283	1.2962	798.6	616.1	47.46
60.5	1.44305	1.2969	800.5	617.2	47.57
60.6	1.44328	1.2976	802.2	618.2	47.67
60.7	1.44351	1.2981	803.9	619.3	47.78
60.8	1.44374	1.2986	805.5	620.3	47.87
60.9	1.44397	1.2991	807.1	621.3	47.97
61.0	1.44419	1.2996	808.7	622.3	48.06
61.1	1.44442	1.3002	810.5	623.4	48.17
61.2	1.44465	1.3009	812.3	624.4	48.27
61.3	1.44488	1.3016	814.2	625.5	48.39
61.4	1.44511	1.3022	815.8	626.5	48.48
61.5	1.44534	1.3029	817.7	627.6	48.60
61.6	1.44557	1.3036	819.4	628.6	48.70
61.7	1.44580	1.3042	821.3	629.7	48.81
61.8	1.44603	1.3049	823.0	630.7	48.91
61.9	1.44626	1.3056	824.8	631.7	49.02
62.0	1.44648	1.3062	826.6	632.8	49.12
62.1	1.44672	1.3068	828.3	633.8	49.23
62.2	1.44695	1.3075	830.0	634.8	49.33
62.3	1.44718	1.3080	831.8	635.9	49.43
62.4	1.44741	1.3085	833.4	636.9	49.53
62.5	1.44764	1.3090	835.1	638.0	49.63
62.6	1.44787	1.3095	836.8	639.0	49.73
62.7	1.44810	1.3101	838.5	640.0	49.83
62.8	1.44833	1.3108	840.2	641.0	49.93
62.9	1.44856	1.3115	842.1	642.1	50.05
63.0	1.44879	1.3121	843.8	643.1	50.15
63.1	1.44902	1.3128	845.7	644.2	50.26
63.2	1.44926	1.3135	847.5	645.2	50.37
63.3	1.44949	1.3141	849.3	646.3	50.47
63.4	1.44972	1.3148	851.1	647.3	50.58
63.5	1.44995	1.3155	853.0	648.4	50.69
63.6	1.45019	1.3161	854.7	649.4	50.79
63.7	1.45042	1.3168	856.5	650.4	50.90
63.8	1.45065	1.3175	858.4	651.5	51.01
63.9	1.45088	1.3180	860.0	652.5	51.11
64.0	1.45112	1.3185	861.6	653.5	51.20
64.1	1.45135	1.3190	863.4	654.6	51.31
64.2	1.45158	1.3195	865.1	655.6	51.41
64.3	1.45181	1.3201	866.9	656.7	51.52
64.4	1.45205	1.3208	868.7	657.7	51.63
64.5	1.45228	1.3215	870.6	658.8	51.74
64.6	1.45252	1.3221	872.3	659.8	51.84
64.7	1.45275	1.3228	874.1	660.8	51.95
64.8	1.45299	1.3235	876.0	661.9	52.06
64.9	1.45322	1.3241	877.8	662.9	52.17

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density at 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
65.0	1.45347	1.3248	879.7	664.0	52.28
65.1	1.45369	1.3255	881.5	665.0	52.39
65.2	1.45393	1.3261	883.2	666.0	52.49
65.3	1.45416	1.3268	885.0	667.0	52.60
65.4	1.45440	1.3275	886.9	668.1	52.71
65.5	1.45463	1.3281	888.8	669.2	52.82
65.6	1.45487	1.3288	890.6	670.2	52.93
65.7	1.45510	1.3295	892.4	671.2	53.04
65.8	1.45534	1.3301	894.2	672.3	53.14
65.9	1.45557	1.3308	896.0	673.3	53.25
66.0	1.45583	1.3315	898.0	674.4	53.37
66.1	1.45605	1.3320	899.6	675.4	53.46
66.2	1.45629	1.3325	901.3	676.4	53.56
66.3	1.45652	1.3330	903.1	677.5	53.67
66.4	1.45676	1.3335	904.8	678.5	53.77
66.5	1.45700	1.3341	906.7	679.6	53.89
66.6	1.45724	1.3348	908.5	680.6	53.99
66.7	1.45747	1.3355	910.4	681.7	54.11
66.8	1.45771	1.3361	912.2	682.7	54.21
66.9	1.45795	1.3367	913.9	683.7	54.31
67.0	1.45820	1.3374	915.9	684.8	54.43
67.1	1.45843	1.3380	917.6	685.8	54.53
67.2	1.45867	1.3387	919.6	686.9	54.65
67.3	1.45890	1.3395	921.4	687.9	54.76
67.4	1.45914	1.3400	923.1	688.9	54.86
67.5	1.45938	1.3407	925.1	690.0	54.98
67.6	1.45962	1.3415	927.0	691.0	55.09
67.7	1.45986	1.3420	928.8	692.1	55.20
67.8	1.46010	1.3427	930.6	693.1	55.31
67.9	1.46034	1.3434	932.6	694.2	55.42
68.0	1.46060	1.3440	934.4	695.2	55.53
68.1	1.46082	1.3447	936.2	696.2	55.64
68.2	1.46106	1.3454	938.0	697.2	55.75
68.3	1.46130	1.3460	939.9	698.3	55.86
68.4	1.46154	1.3466	941.8	699.4	55.97
68.5	1.46178	1.3473	943.7	700.4	56.08
68.6	1.46202	1.3479	945.4	701.4	56.19
68.7	1.46226	1.3486	947.4	702.5	56.30
68.8	1.46251	1.3493	949.2	703.5	56.41
68.9	1.46275	1.3499	951.1	704.6	56.52
69.0	1.46301	1.3506	953.0	705.6	56.64
69.1	1.46323	1.3513	954.8	706.6	56.74
69.2	1.46347	1.3519	956.7	707.7	56.86
69.3	1.46371	1.3526	958.6	708.7	56.97
69.4	1.46396	1.3533	960.6	709.8	57.09
69.5	1.46420	1.3539	962.4	710.8	57.20
69.6	1.46444	1.3546	964.3	711.9	57.31
69.7	1.46468	1.3553	966.2	712.9	57.42
69.8	1.46493	1.3560	968.2	714.0	57.54
69.9	1.46517	1.3566	970.0	715.0	57.65

Saccharose % (m/m)	Refractive Index at 20 °C	Mass Density à 20 °C	Sugars in g/l	Sugars in g/kg	ABV % vol at 20 °C
70.0	1.46544	1.3573	971.8	716.0	57.75
70.1	1.46565	1.3579	973.8	717.1	57.87
70.2	1.46590	1.3586	975.6	718.1	57.98
70.3	1.46614	1.3593	977.6	719.2	58.10
70.4	1.46639	1.3599	979.4	720.2	58.21
70.5	1.46663	1.3606	981.3	721.2	58.32
70.6	1.46688	1.3613	983.3	722.3	58.44
70.7	1.46712	1.3619	985.2	723.4	58.55
70.8	1.46737	1.3626	987.1	724.4	58.66
70.9	1.46761	1.3633	988.9	725.4	58.77
71.0	1.46789	1.3639	990.9	726.5	58.89
71.1	1.46810	1.3646	992.8	727.5	59.00
71.2	1.46835	1.3653	994.8	728.6	59.12
71.3	1.46859	1.3659	996.6	729.6	59.23
71.4	1.46884	1.3665	998.5	730.7	59.34
71.5	1.46908	1.3672	1000.4	731.7	59.45
71.6	1.46933	1.3678	1002.2	732.7	59.56
71.7	1.46957	1.3685	1004.2	733.8	59.68
71.8	1.46982	1.3692	1006.1	734.8	59.79
71.9	1.47007	1.3698	1008.0	735.9	59.91
72.0	1.47036	1.3705	1009.9	736.9	60.02
72.1	1.47056	1.3712	1012.0	738.0	60.14
72.2	1.47081	1.3718	1013.8	739.0	60.25
72.3	1.47106	1.3725	1015.7	740.0	60.36
72.4	1.47131	1.3732	1017.7	741.1	60.48
72.5	1.47155	1.3738	1019.5	742.1	60.59
72.6	1.47180	1.3745	1021.5	743.2	60.71
72.7	1.47205	1.3752	1023.4	744.2	60.82
72.8	1.47230	1.3758	1025.4	745.3	60.94
72.9	1.47254	1.3765	1027.3	746.3	61.05
73.0	1.47284	1.3772	1029.3	747.4	61.17
73.1	1.47304	1.3778	1031.2	748.4	61.28
73.2	1.47329	1.3785	1033.2	749.5	61.40
73.3	1.47354	1.3792	1035.1	750.5	61.52
73.4	1.47379	1.3798	1037.1	751.6	61.63
73.5	1.47404	1.3805	1039.0	752.6	61.75
73.6	1.47429	1.3812	1040.9	753.6	61.86
73.7	1.47454	1.3818	1042.8	754.7	61.97
73.8	1.47479	1.3825	1044.8	755.7	62.09
73.9	1.47504	1.3832	1046.8	756.8	62.21
74.0	1.47534	1.3838	1048.6	757.8	62.32
74.1	1.47554	1.3845	1050.7	758.9	62.44
74.2	1.47579	1.3852	1052.6	759.9	62.56
74.3	1.47604	1.3858	1054.6	761.0	62.67
74.4	1.47629	1.3865	1056.5	762.0	62.79
74.5	1.47654	1.3871	1058.5	763.1	62.91
74.6	1.47679	1.3878	1060.4	764.1	63.02
74.7	1.47704	1.3885	1062.3	765.1	63.13
74.8	1.47730	1.3892	1064.4	766.2	63.26
74.9	1.47755	1.3898	1066.3	767.2	63.37
75.0	1.47785	1.3905	1068.3	768.3	63.49

REMARKS

The refractometer used must be fitted with a scale giving:

- Either percentage by mass of sucrose to 0.1%;
- Or refractive indices to four decimals.

The refractometer must be equipped with a thermometer having a scale extending at least from 15 °C to 25 °C and with a system for circulating water that will enable measurements to be made at a temperature of 20 ± 5 °C. The operating instructions for this instrument must be strictly adhered to, particularly with regard to calibration and the light source.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment:

- Abbe refractometer

REFERENCES

OIV-MA-AS2-02 (2021). Evaluation by refractometry of the sugar concentration in grape musts, concentrated grape musts, and rectified concentrated grape musts (Oeno 466/2012). Compendium of international methods of wine and must analysis, vol. 1. Paris, France: International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV); pp. 61–82.

4.9.8. Total acidity

PRINCIPLE

The total acidity of the wine is the sum of its titratable acidities when it is titrated to pH 7.0 against a standard alkaline solution. Carbon dioxide is not included in the total acidity. Potentiometric titration or titration with bromothymol blue as indicator and comparison with an end-point colour standard.

PROCEDURE

Preparation of sample: elimination of carbon dioxide.

Approximately 50 mL of wine is placed in a vacuum flask and the vacuum is applied to the flask using a water pump for one to two min, while shaking continuously. Other CO₂ elimination systems may be used if the CO₂ elimination is guaranteed.

Potentiometric titration

Calibration of pH-meter: the pH meter is calibrated for use at 20 °C, according to the manufacturer's instructions, with the pH 7.0 buffer solution at 20 °C.

Method of measurement: Into a beaker, introduce a volume of the sample is introduced, prepared as described in below, equal to 10 mL in the case of wine and 50 mL in the case of rectified concentrated must. About 10 mL of distilled water and then 0.1 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide solution is added, from a burette until the pH is equal to 7.0 at 20 °C. The sodium hydroxide must be added slowly and the solution stirred continuously. Let n mL be the volume of 0.1 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide is added.

Titration with indicator (bromothymol blue)

Preliminary test: end-point colour determination. Into a beaker are added 25 mL of boiled distilled water, 1 mL of bromothymol blue solution and a volume prepared as in 2.5.1 equal to 10 mL in the case of wine and 50 mL in the case of rectified concentrated must. Sodium hydroxide solution, 0.1 mol L⁻¹ is added until the colour changes to blue-green. Then, 5 mL of the pH 7.0 buffer solution is added.

Measurement

30 mL of boiled distilled water, 1 mL of bromothymol blue solution and a volume of the sample, prepared as described in the first step, equal to 10 mL in the case of wine and

50 mL in the case of rectified concentrated must, are placed into a beaker. Sodium hydroxide solution, 0.1 mol L^{-1} is added, until the same colour is obtained as in the preliminary test above. Let $n \text{ mL}$ be the volume of sodium hydroxide solution, 0.1 mol L^{-1} , added.

CALCULATIONS

Method of calculation

The total acidity expressed in milliequivalents per litre is given by:

$$A = 10 n.$$

It is recorded to one decimal place.

- The total acidity expressed in grams of tartaric acid per litre is given by:

$$A' = 0.075 \times A$$

The result is quoted to two decimal places.

- The total acidity expressed in grams of sulfuric acid per litre is given by:

$$A' = 0.049 \times A$$

The result is quoted to two decimal places.

Repeatability (r) for titration with the indicator

$$r = 0.9 \text{ meq L}^{-1}$$

$$r = 0.04 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ sulfuric acid}$$

$$r = 0.07 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ tartaric acid}$$

Reproducibility (R) for titration with the indicator

For white and rosé wines:

$$R = 3.6 \text{ meq L}^{-1}$$

$$R = 0.2 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ sulfuric acid}$$

$$R = 0.3 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ tartaric acid}$$

For red wines:

$$R = 5.1 \text{ meq L}^{-1}$$

$$R = 0.3 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ sulfuric acid}$$

$$R = 0.4 \text{ g L}^{-1} \text{ tartaric acid}$$

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Reagents:

- Buffer solution pH 7.0:
 - Potassium di-hydrogen phosphate, $\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4 \rightarrow 107.3 \text{ g}$
 - Sodium hydroxide solution, NaOH , $1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \rightarrow 500 \text{ mL}$

- water to → 1000 mL
- Alternatively, ready-made buffer solutions are available commercially.
- Sodium hydroxide solution, NaOH, 0.1 mol L⁻¹.
- Bromothymol blue indicator solution, 4 g L⁻¹:
 - Bromothymol blue → 4 g
 - Neutral ethanol, 96% (v/v) → 200 mL
 - Dissolve and add water free of CO₂ → 200 mL
- Sodium hydroxide solution, 1 mol L⁻¹, sufficient to produce:
 - Blue green colour (pH 7.0) → 7.5 mL
 - Water to → 1000 mL

Equipment:

- Water vacuum pump
- 500 mL Vacuum flask
- Potentiometer with scale graduated in pH values, and electrodes. The glass electrode must be kept in distilled water. The calomel/saturated potassium chloride electrode must be kept in a saturated potassium chloride solution
- Beakers of 12 cm diameter or any appropriate recipient

REFERENCES

Jaulmes, P. & Bull, O.I.V. (1955). 26, no 274, 42; *Ann. Fals. Fraudes*, 48, 157.

OIV-MA-AS313-01 (2021). Total acidity (Oeno 551/2015). Compendium of international methods of wine and must analysis, vol. 1. Paris, France: International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV); 433–5.

Semichon, L. & Flanzy, M. (1930). *Ann. Fals. Fraudes*, 23,5.

4.9.9. L-Malic Acid
PRINCIPLE

L-malic acid (L-malate) is oxidized by nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) to oxaloacetate in a reaction catalysed by L-malate dehydrogenase (L-MDH). The equilibrium of the reaction normally lies more strongly in favour of the malate. Removal of the oxaloacetate from the reaction mixture displaces the equilibrium towards the formation of oxaloacetate. In the presence of L-glutamate, the oxaloacetate is transformed into L-aspartate in a reaction catalysed by glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (GOT):

The amount of NADH formed, measured by the increase in absorbance at the wavelength of 340 nm, is proportional to the quantity of L-malate originally present.

PROCEDURE

L-malate determination is normally carried out directly on the wine, without prior removal of pigmentation (colouration) and without dilution provided that the L-malic acid concentration is less than 350 mg L⁻¹ (measured at 365 mg L⁻¹). If this is not so, the wine must be diluted with doubly distilled water until the L-malate concentration lies between 30 and 350 mg L⁻¹ (i.e., amount of L-malate in the test sample lies between 3 and 35 µg).

If the malate concentration in the wine is less than 30 mg L⁻¹, the volume of the test sample may be increased up to 1 mL. In this case, the volume of water to be added is reduced in such a way that the total volumes in the two cells are equal.

With the spectrophotometer adjusted to a wavelength of 340 nm, the absorbance is determined using the cells having optical paths of 1 cm, with air as the zero absorbance (reference) standard (no cell in the optical path) or with water as the standard. Place the following in the cells having 1 cm optical paths:

	Reference cell	Sample cell
	(mL)	(mL)
Solution 1*	1.00	1.00
Solution 2*	0.20	0.20
Doubly distilled water.....	1.00	0.90
Suspension 3*	0.01	0.01
Sample to be measured.....	-	0.10

After about three minutes is mixed and the absorbance of the solutions are measured in the reference and sample cells (A₁).

Then is added:

Solution 4*	0.01	0.01
-------------------	------	------

It is mixed again and wait for the reaction to be completed (about 5 to 10 minutes). The absorbance of the solutions is measured in the reference and sample cells (A₂).

The differences (A₂ – A₁) in the absorbance of the solutions in the reference and sample cells, ΔA_R and ΔA_S are calculated.

Finally, the difference between those differences: $\Delta A = \Delta A_S - \Delta A_R$ are calculated.

Note: The time needed for the completion of enzyme activity can vary from one batch to another. The above value is given only for guidance and it is recommended that it be determined for each batch.

CALCULATIONS

L-malic acid concentration is given in grams per litre to one decimal place.

Method of calculation

The general formula for calculating the concentration in g L^{-1} is:

$$C = \frac{V \times PM}{\epsilon \times \delta \times 1000} \times \Delta A$$

Where:

V = volume of test solution in ml (here 2.22 mL)

v = volume of the sample in ml (here 0.1 mL)

M= molecular mass of the substance to be determined (here, for L-malic acid, M=134.09)

δ = optical path in the cell in cm (here, 1 cm)

ϵ = absorption coefficient of NADH, (at 340 nm $\epsilon = 6.3 \text{ m mol}^{-1} \times \text{l} \times \text{cm}^{-1}$), so that for L-malate:

$$C = 0.473 \times \Delta A \text{ g L}^{-1}$$

If the sample was diluted during its preparation, the result must be multiplied by the dilution factor.

NOTE:

- Measurement at 334 nm, $\epsilon = 6,2 \text{ (mmole}^{-1} \times \text{l} \times \text{cm}^2)$
 $C = 0,482 \times \Delta A$

- Measurement at 365 nm, $\epsilon = 6,2 \text{ (mmole}^{-1} \times \text{l} \times \text{cm}^2)$
 $C = 0,876 \times \Delta A$

Repeatability (r)

$$r = 0.03 + 0.034 \text{ xi}$$

xi is the malic acid concentration in the sample in g L^{-1} .

Reproducibility (R)

$$R = 0.05 + 0.071 \text{ xi}$$

xi is the malic acid concentration in the sample in g L^{-1} .

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Doubly distilled water
- (1*) Buffer solution, pH 10: (glycylglycine 0.6 M; L-glutamate 0.1 M): dissolve 4.75 g of glycylglycine and 0.88 g of L-glutamic acid in approximately 50 mL of doubly distilled water; adjust the pH to 10 with about 4.6 mL of 10 M sodium hydroxide and make up to 60 mL with doubly distilled water. This solution will remain stable for at least 12 weeks at 4 °C.
- (2*) Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD) solution, approximately 47×10^3 M: dissolve 420 mg of NAD in 12 mL of doubly distilled water. This solution will remain stable for at least four weeks at 4 °C.
- (3*) Glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase (GOT) suspension, 2 mg mL⁻¹. The suspension remains stable for at least a year at 4 °C.
- (4*) L-malate dehydrogenase (L-MDH) solution, 5 mg mL⁻¹. This solution remains stable for at least a year at 4 °C.

Equipment:

- A spectrophotometer permitting measurement to be made at 340 nm, the wavelength at which absorption by NADH is at a maximum. Failing that, a spectrophotometer, with a discontinuous spectrum source permitting measurements to be made at 334 or 365 nm, may be used. Since absolute measurements of absorbance are involved (i.e., calibration curves are not used, but standardization is made by consideration of the extinction coefficient of NADH), the wavelength scales and spectral absorbance of the apparatus must be checked.
- Glass cells with optical path lengths of 1 cm or single-use cells
- Micropipettes for pipetting sample volumes in the range 0.01 to 2 mL

NOTE: All the reagents above are available commercially.

REFERENCES

- Bergmeyer, H.U. (1970). *Méthodes d'analyse enzymatique*, 2e éd., Verlag-Chemie Weinheim/Bergstrasse.
- Boerhinger, M. (1982). *Méthodes d'analyse enzymatique en chimie alimentaire*, documentation technique.
- OIV-MA-AS313-11. L-Malic acid. Compendium of international methods of wine and must analysis, vol. 1. Paris, France: International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV); 467–471.
- Van Den Driessche S. et al. (1982). THYS L., F.C. O.I.V., 755.

4.9.10. Tartaric Acid

PRINCIPLE

Tartaric acid is a natural component found in grapes and is one of the primary acids in wine. It contributes to the acidity of grapes, which is essential for the balance and flavour profile of the wine. In vineyards, monitoring tartaric acid levels is important for determining the ripeness of grapes and guiding decisions about when to harvest.

PROCEDURE

Mobile phase: solution of ultrapure water and phosphoric acid (pH 2.5) in a ratio of 98.8:1.2 v/v, with a flow rate of 0.9 mL min⁻¹.

Temperature: ambient

Pressure: 100 atmospheres.

Volume injected: 20 µL.

UV detector: 212 nm.

Sensitivity: 0.5 O.D.

The 10% wine sample is diluted with ultrapure water, homogenized and filtered through a cellulose membrane with a pore size of 25 µm. The sample is injected thus prepared into the apparatus. The same procedure is carried out with the standard solutions of tartaric and malic acids.

The separation of tartaric and malic acid peaks is shown in the chromatogram in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Chromatogram of tartaric and malic acids in a wine, with peak identification of the peaks.

CALCULATIONS

The tartaric acid and malic acid content in g L⁻¹ is obtained by comparing the surface of the tartaric acid peak in the wine sample with the surface of the peak in the standard solutions.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Tartaric acid solution L (+) at 1 g L⁻¹ prepared with ultrapure water.
- Malic acid solution L (-) at 1 g L⁻¹ prepared with ultrapure water.
- Phosphoric acid solution (pH 2.5) prepared by diluting 1.2 mL of phosphoric acid in a 1 L flask with ultrapure water.

Equipment:

- Liquid chromatograph equipped with a 20 µL Rheodyne injector operating under isocratic conditions
- Diode array detector at 212 nm wavelength
- Varian MCH-NCAP-5 column, 15 cm long and 4.6 mm internal diameter
- 100 microsyringe
- 100 mL volumetric flasks
- 1 mL and 10 mL volumetric pipettes
- Membrane filtration equipment
- 25 µm cellulose filter membrane

REFERENCES

Fruit and vegetable juice (1999). Determination of tartaric acid in grape juice. Method by high-performance liquid chromatography. EN 12137.

Rizzon, L.A. (2010). *Metodologia para análise de vinho*. Brasília, DF: Embrapa 820 Informação Tecnológica.

4.9.11. Anthocyanins

PRINCIPLE

The determination of anthocyanins in wines is based on the difference in coloration of anthocyanins in relation to pH, since the variation in colour intensity at two pH values is proportional to the anthocyanin content.

PROCEDURE

1 mL of the wine to be analysed, 1 mL of ethanol with 0.1% hydrochloric acid and 10 mL of 2% hydrochloric acid are placed in a test tube.

1 mL of the wine to be analysed, 1 mL of ethanol with 0.1% hydrochloric acid and 10 mL of pH 3.5 buffer solution are placed in a second test tube.

The absorption of the samples from the two tubes are read at 520 nm using 1 cm optical path cuvettes, and calibrating the apparatus with distilled water.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- Ethanol with 0.1% hydrochloric acid.
- 2% hydrochloric acid.
- Buffer solution pH 3.5, prepared with 0.2 M disodium phosphate (303.5 mL) and 0.1 M citric acid (696.5 mL).

Equipment:

- Spectrophotometer.
- Quartz cuvettes with an optical path length of 1 cm.
- Test tubes with screw caps.
- 1 mL and 10 mL pipettes

CALCULATIONS

The concentration of free anthocyanin, expressed in mg L^{-1} , is obtained by relating the differences in optical density to a standard curve established with the values below:

$$\text{Anthocyanin (mg L}^{-1}\text{)} = 388 \times \Delta d$$

where: Δd = reading difference between the two tubes

REFERENCES

Ribéreau-Gayon, P. & Stonestreet, E. (1965). Le dosage des anthocyanes dans les vins rouges. *Bulletin de la Société Chimique de France*, 9, 2649-2652.

Rizzon, L.A. (2010). *Metodologia para análise de vinho*. Brasília, DF: Embrapa 820, Informação Tecnológica.

4.9.12. Characteristic of grapes

Weight of bunch with stalk: To determine this parameter, a representative bunch from each vineyard under study is weighed.

Number of berries in the bunch: This parameter consists of determining the number of berries in the chosen bunch (Bunch weight).

Weight of 200 berries: Collect random berries are selected until 200 berries are reached.

Average weight of a Berry: To obtain this parameter it is necessary to divide the weight of the 200 berries by 200.

SOIL HANDBOOK

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PROJECT ACRONYM: AGROSUS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This handbook is aimed to **the most important parameters to measure the diversity and quality of the soil in the crop fields included in the short-term and medium-to-long-term agroecological and conventional fields of the AGROSUS project**. The parameters here listed are presented with a detailed protocol, the material needed for their measurement, the most relevant references, and the principles for why these parameters are so important for evaluating the health of the crop plants, and will be done by the different partners from the different eleven biogeographic regions from Europe in the agroecological and conventional farming systems established in AGROSUS.

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1. CASE STUDIES SETUP AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

1.1. Experimental Units

Work packages 3 and 4 (WP3 and WP4) have been designed to develop a solid and robust scientific understanding about the impacts of agroecological strategies (AE) on crop productivity, weed management and soil health and biodiversity, which is related to other ecosystem services such as soil fertility and carbon sequestration in different pedoclimatic regions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Biogeographical regions of Europe.

To correctly address the projects' objectives, short, medium, and long-term farm systems will be analysed, and 83 experimental units (68 short-term + 15 medium to long-term) will be considered in total corresponding to the 11 European biogeographic regions (Figure 2). Short, medium and long-term impact of AE on crop productivity, weed management, and soil health will be measured along the AGROSUS project. The short-term impact will be measured in experimental units developed by the different partners in conventional, organic, or mixed farm systems. However, considering the duration of the project (4 years), the medium to long-term impact of AE will be evaluated in in-course AE fields already identified in some of the different regions, and different measures to evaluate crop quality, weed control, soil health, ecotoxicological, environmental and socioeconomic impact will be recorded in the frame of AGROSUS.

Figure 2. AGROSUS short-term experimental units in the eleven biogeographic regions.

1.2. Experimental design

Experimental design is important in any scientific study, as, among other things, involves what laboratory samples are to be taken, how they are to be collected and from where they are to be taken, in order that the objectives of the investigation programme can be achieved. In the comparison of treatments in agronomic experiments, a properly designed experimental scheme is of crucial importance to make adequate statistical inference. The two most common alternatives applied in the case studies of the project are shown below:

1.2.1. Randomized experimental design

This model assumes that the replicates of the different treatments are randomly distributed within the experiment when a randomized complete block design or a split-plot design is carried out (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of a randomized experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2.

1.2.2. Block experimental design.

If a block experimental design (not randomized) is going to be carried out (Figure 4), control treatment (the one already performed in the farm as a routine basis; CV) does not represent field variability since each treatment is located in different areas of the field, and some variations will be present in soil owing to different location. So, initial conditions in each block have to be taken into account. Therefore, when a non-randomized block experimental design is implemented (Figure 3), the conventional treatment and each of the AE will have their own designated area in the study field.

Figure 4. Example of block experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2.

2. SOIL SAMPLING GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Soil sampling is the process to collect the most representative volume of soil for subsequent analysis at a lab. Soil sampling is a key step to making effective farm evaluation of soil management and soil fertility. Each sample collected must be a true representative of the area being sampled. The results obtained measure the concentration of certain components in the soil and are useful for soil characterization and AE management practices evaluation.

2.1. Sampling for General Soil Characteristics and Microbial Diversity

In each case study, once the sampling area is selected, the following procedure should be carried out to determine soil physical, chemical, and microbiological properties. At each of the sampling points, a composite sample consisting of 5 soil sub-samples (0–30 cm depth) should be collected (Figure 5). The proposed scheme in Figure 5 can be followed for this purpose: one sub-sample at the sampling point (central point), 4 additional sub-samples at each site, 2 m distant from the central point in the shape of a cross (distance can be modified in terms of specific characteristics of each location). In total, for each of the sampling points, approximately 1 kg of soil should be sampled. Five soil sub-samples will be mixed together and manually homogenized to create a composite sample. After homogenization, 30–50 g soil should be separated for the biological analyses, which must be stored in a cooler with ice (in the field). The remaining soil (± 1 kg) can be stored at room temperature. Each composite soil sample should be labelled as L (from long term) followed by the name of the biogeographic region (Alpine: ALP–Anatolian: ANA–Arctic: ARC–Atlantic: ATL–Black-Sea: BS–Boreal: BOR–Continental: CNT–Macaronesian: MAC–Mediterranean: MED–Pannonian: PAN–Steppic: STP) and an internal numerical code, as shown in the example of the Atlantic region attached.

Figure 5. Scheme for 5 sub-sampling methodology for one composite soil sample in each sampling point.

Once in laboratory:

- Soil samples for biological analyses (30 –50 g) should be stored at -20 °C (-80 °C for long storage). Send to UPCT with ice plates and express delivery (**max. 24 h**). Shipping address (For all except Turkey and Ukraine-see Section 5-): *Raúl Zornoza. Departamento de Ingeniería Agronómica. Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena. Paseo Alfonso XIII 42, 30203, Cartagena (Spain)*. Telephone: +34968177746. E-mail: *raul.zornoza@upct.es*
- Soil samples for physicochemical analyses (± 1 kg) should be dried at room temperature for 7 –10 days. Once dried, soil samples can be stored at room temperature. Send to UVigo for physicochemical properties analyses. Shipping address (For all except Turkey and Ukraine-see Section 5-): *David Fernández Calviño. Facultad de Ciencias de Ourense, Edificio Politécnico. Campus As Lagoas, s/n. 32004, Ourense (Spain)*. Telephone: +34988368888. E-mail: *davidfc@uvigo.gal*

PROCEDURE

1. Prior to the field sampling, label strong plastic sampling bags appropriately.
2. After arriving at the location, note the GPS coordinates if not known yet.
3. Take five soil sub-samples with auger at 0-30 cm depth and place them in plastic bags.
4. Soil sub-samples will be mixed together and manually homogenized to create a composite sample. After homogenization, 30–50 g soil should be separated for the biological analyses, which must be stored in a cooler with ice (in the field) (Figure 6).
5. Before going to the next field, the sampling material (auger and spatula) is disinfected with 70% ethanol and wiped dry with paper. This should especially prevent carry-over of soil containing organisms from one sample to the other.

Figure 6. Storage of soil samples in field prior to subsequent biological and physicochemical analyses.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

A short list of the material needed for soil sampling is: spatula, bags, permanent marker, box, auger, cooler, ice plates, shovel, gloves, alcohol, paper.

- Sampling bags and twist tie
- Permanent Marker
- Core sampler with thumb
- Spray bottle with 70% ethanol
- Gloves
- Roll of paper
- Cool box with cool packs (when temperature is above 15 °C)

2.2. Sampling for Bulk Density

PRINCIPLE

Soil bulk density determination is important for assessment of soil health and the provision of ecosystem services. Bulk density varies with structural condition of the soil and refers to the weight (mass) of soil per unit of volume and is generally expressed in g per cm³. The core method uses a soil cylinder (of known volume, cm³) to determine the dry mass of an undisturbed sample. In this method, the cylinder is pressed or hammered into the soil to take undisturbed soil sample and extracting a sample of known volume.

PROCEDURE

For bulk density, soil cylinder should be collected at 5–10 cm depth at each sampling point (Figure 7).

1. Prepare a flat soil surface at the first selected sampling point by scraping away the upper soil centimetre with a shovel or spatula.
2. Press the cylinder completely into the soil. This can be done manually or mechanically using a hammer and a piece of flat wooden board placed on top of the ring.
3. Remove the cylinder with the help of a spatula or shovel. Be sure to avoid that soil falls down from the ring.
4. Remove excessive soil with a spatula or knife until the upper and lower surface of the soil in the cylinder is flat.
5. Close both sides of the ring if you are going to transport the soil within the ring. If you are going to use the same ring for several samples or you do not have the lids to close the rings, transfer the soil of a ring to a plastic bag and code it properly. Close the bag.

Figure 7. Example of bulk density sampling methodology.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Bulk density cylinder or metal ring preferably with removable lids at both ends.
- Sampling bags
- Permanent Marker
- Spatula and/or shovel
- Hammer
- Knife or spatula
- Wooden board
- Retractable tape measure

3. SOIL STRUCTURE, WATER AVAILABILITY AND SOIL CARBON SEQUESTRATION

3.1. Particle size distribution

PRINCIPLE

The mineral components of the soil can be studied according to several criteria, their size, shape, chemical or mineralogical composition, the aggregation in larger units, etc. The texture of a soil refers to the size distribution of individual mineral particles. The result (percentage by weight) expresses the granulometric composition of the soil

sample. In order to classify soil constituents according to their particle size distribution (Figure 8), each textural class corresponds to a certain quantitative composition grouped into three main groups: clay (<0.002 mm), silt (0.05-0.002 mm) and sand (2-0.05 mm). Soil particle size is a basic and essential property in soils science. This is due to the importance it plays in the interpretation of soil characteristics in relation, to hydrologic cycle, erosion processes and nutrient retention, among others.

Figure 8. USDA soil textural classification triangle (Adapted from Meyer et al., 2013).

For particle size distribution determination several methods have been used. The sedimentation method used to separate silts from clays is based on the falling velocity of a sphere in a liquid at repose which will depend on the size of the particles, the densities of the particles and the density of the aqueous medium. These variables are governed by Stokes' law.

Two main methods should be distinguished: the pipette and hydrometric methods. In the Bouyoucos hydrometer method (Dewis and Freitas, 1970), a Bouyoucos-type hydrometer is used, the concentration of total solids in the suspension (g L^{-1}), indicated by the scale of the hydrometer at 40 s after agitation, corresponds to particles of diameter $\leq 20 \mu\text{m}$ (0.02 mm) (clay and silt) and that indicated after two hours corresponds to particles of diameter $\leq 2 \mu\text{m}$ (clay). Therefore, the measurement taken at 2 h directly indicates the concentration of clay in the suspension and by subtracting this value from that at 40 s, the concentration of silt is obtained (Porta et al., 1986). The sand content is calculated by the difference between the total weight of the soil and the weight of the clay and silt. In the pipette method the largest fractions (sands) are

separated by sieving, using sieve meshes of 0.2 mm (for coarse sand) and 0.05 mm (for fine sand); and the finest ones (silt and clays) are determined according to their sedimentation rate.

PROCEDURE

For Bouyoucos method:

- Treat the soil sample with 30% H₂O₂, to remove organic material; 10% HCl, Sodium Pyrophosphate (Na₄P₂O₇) or Calgon to remove carbonates.
- Place an air-dried sample (50 g of soil) in a shaker bottle. Weigh the sample and record its weight before placing the sample in the bottle. Use 100 g of soil if the sample is sand.
- Add 2.0 g of sodium metaphosphate.
- Add distilled water until the bottle is two-thirds full.
- Cap the bottle and shake it in a mechanical shaker for at least 4 hours.
- Alternatively, agitate for 5 min using a stirrer (Malt Mixer type)
- Transfer soil from the bottle into a settling cylinder. Rinse the remaining soil from the bottle and cap into the cylinder using distilled water from a wash bottle.
- For cylinders marked at 1,130 mL and 1,205 mL, respectively, add distilled water to approx. 5 cm of the lower graduation on the cylinder. Insert the hydrometer, bulb-end down. Filling the cylinder:
 - 1,130 mL line 50 g sample
 - 1,205 mL line 100 g sample
- After filling to the desired mark, remove the hydrometer from the cylinder.
- For cylinders marked at 1,000 mL only, fill the cylinder to the mark with distilled water without inserting the hydrometer.
- Stopper the cylinder, turn it end-over-end several times, return it to the upright position, record the time, and place it gently in a selected place. It must remain in the location for at least 2 hours.
- Insert the hydrometer into the suspension. Read the hydrometer exactly 40 seconds after the cylinder is returned to the upright position.
- Remove the hydrometer and repeat steps 9 and 10 until a consistent hydrometer reading is obtained.
- Record the 40-second hydrometer reading in the data table.
- Remove the hydrometer. Use a thermometer to measure the temperature of the suspension.
- Record the temperature. Let the cylinder sit undisturbed for 2 hours.
- Obtain a hydrometer reading after a settling period of 2 hours. Measure the temperature. Record the temperature and the hydrometer reading in the data table.

For pipette method:

- Prepare a solution of sodium hexametaphosphate and sodium carbonate in water that will be used as dispersant. 35.70 g of $(\text{NaPO}_3)_6$, and 7.94 g of Na_2CO_3 are diluted in one litre of distilled water, to have a solution 0.06 M $(\text{NaPO}_3)_6$ and 0.08 M Na_2CO_3 .
- 20 g of dry soil (sieved by 2 mm) are weighed.
- Eliminate the organic matter from the soil sample by adding H_2O_2 , carefully until the reaction is stopped.
- Mix the soil sample with 100 mL of distilled water and 50 mL of the solution of sodium hexametaphosphate and sodium carbonate. This suspension is shaken for 2 hours in order to disperse aggregates.
- After that step, the suspension is wet sieved using two mesh sizes, 0.2 and 0.05 mm, to separate the coarse and fine sands respectively. It is necessary to wash these sands to be sure that all materials of a smaller size end up in the effluent.
- The sand fractions are taken to a previously tared crucible, where they are dried in an oven at 105 °C until constant weight.
- The effluent, which only contains silts and clays, is transferred to a one-litre test tube. With the help of a manual shaker, the content of the test tube is agitated.
- Samples of 20 mL are taken after 0, 4.8 minutes and 8 hours in a previously tared crucible and dried in an oven at 105 °C until constant weight. In each case, it is necessary to adjust the position of the Robinson pipette to always take the samples at ten centimetres below the surface.
- Dried samples in the crucibles are weighed and the calculations are performed to determine the proportion of each particle size in the soil.

*EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL***For Bouyoucos method:**

- Electric mixer and cup
- Sedimentation cylinder (1 L)
- Hydrometer (Bouyoucos Scale, 5 to 60 g range)
- Tape (mm)
- Dispersant graduated cylinder
- Scale
- Stopwatch
- Thermometer

For pipette method:

- Sieves (0.2 and 0.05 mm)
- Bottles

- Shaker
- Sodium hexametaphosphate, (NaPO₃)
- Sodium carbonate, Na₂CO₃
- Distilled water
- Hydroxide peroxide, H₂O₂
- Test tubes (1 L)
- Crucibles
- Robinson pipette
- Hand shaker
- Chronometer
- Oven (muffle)

CALCULATIONS

For Bouyoucos method:

The Bouyoucos hydrometer determines the concentration of solids in suspension.

Determine Soil Moisture Correction Factor:

Determine weight of air-dried soil (AD) AD = Weight of pan + air-dried soil-pan weight

Determine weight of oven-dried soil (OD) OD = Weight of pan + oven-dried soil-pan weight

Determine soil moisture correction factor (MCF) $MCF = 1 - [(AD - OD) \div AD]$

Weight of Dry Soil: determined by multiplying the air-dried weight by the moisture correction factor (MCF) Weight of Dry Soil = Air-dried Soil x MCF

Correcting Hydrometer Reading:

For temperatures above 20 °C:

Hydrometer reading = Measured reading g L⁻¹ + [(temperature – 20) x 0.36 g L⁻¹]

For temperatures below 20 °C:

Hydrometer reading = Measured reading g L⁻¹ – [20 – (temperature) x 0.36 g L⁻¹]

To correct the hydrometer readings for temperature, add 0.36 g L⁻¹ for every 1 °C above 20 °C; subtract 0.36 g L⁻¹ for every 1 °C below 20 °C.

Determine the percentages of Sand, Silt and Clay:

% clay = (Corrected 2 h hydrometer reading x 100) (Oven-dried Weight of Soil)⁻¹

% silt + clay = (Corrected 40 s hydrometer reading x 100) (Oven-dried Weight of Soil)⁻¹

% sand = 100 – % silt + clay

For pipette method:

In the case of sands, the calculation is as follows:

$$CSa = CSa_w - CSa_c$$

$$FSa = FSa_w - FSa_c$$

Where:

- CSa is the weight of the coarse sand.
- CSa_w is the weight of the coarse sand plus the crucible.
- CSa_c is the weight of the crucible used to dry the coarse sand.
- FSa is the weight of the fine sand.
- FSa_w is the weight of the fine sand plus the crucible.
- FSa_c is the weight of the crucible used to dry the fine sand.

In the case of coarse silt, fine silt and clays, the calculation is as follows:

$$CSi = \frac{CSi_w - CSi_c}{V_s} * V_1$$

$$FSi = \frac{FSi_w - FSi_c}{V_s} * (V_1 - V_s)$$

$$CL = \frac{CL_w - CL_c}{V_s} * (V_1 - 2V_s)$$

Where:

- CSi is the weight of the coarse silt.
- CSi_w is the weight of the coarse silt plus the crucible.
- CSi_c is the weight of the crucible used to dry the coarse silt.
- FSi is the weight of the fine silt.
- FSi_w is the weight of the fine silt plus the crucible.
- FSi_c is the weight of the crucible used to dry the fine silt.
- CL is the weight of the clay.
- CL_w is the weight of the clay plus the crucible.
- CL_c is the weight of the crucible used to dry the clay.
- Vs is the volume of sample taken with the Robinson pipette.
- V1 is the volume of the test tube.

REMARKS

In the case of soils with gravels and boulders (Regosols, mixed Anthrosol, Technosols) coarse constituents hinder sampling and increase measurement error.

Hydrometer may influence the settling rate.

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3.2. Coarse Fragments

PRINCIPLE

Coarse fragments are a common constituent in soil and are defined as particles with more than 2 millimetres in diameter. Coarse fragments are not included in chemical and some physical analyses however, its determination is important in some calculations, e.g., soil organic carbon stock (Poeplau et al., 2017). Furthermore, coarse soil fractions have relevant effects on ecosystem properties and processes, for example surface coarse fragments dissipate some of the energy of raindrops (Choo et al., 2018). Therefore, soils with a moderate amount of coarse fragments on the surface tend to resist better erosion processes. Percolation of water through soil is often more rapid where the percentage of coarse fragments is greatest (Cousin et al., 2003).

For the determination of the percentage of coarse fragments, a sample of known weight is taken and after sieving the sample, the material larger than 2 mm is weighed, which corresponds to the percentage of coarse fragments in the sample.

PROCEDURE

- Weight the whole soil sample (record precise weight). Soil sample must be completely dried. If aggregates are present, you have to break aggregates by crushing them with a hammer. It is important to break all aggregates in order not to consider them as coarse fragments.
- Sieve the sample at < 2 mm (making sure that aggregates < 2 mm are broken).
- Weight the sieve non-passing fraction (record precise weight).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Sieve (mesh size 2 mm).
- Analytical balance (0.1 g)
- Hammer

CALCULATIONS

Calculate the percentage of coarse fragments by dividing the weight retained on sieve by the original sample mass.

3.3. Aggregate Stability

PRINCIPLE

Soil structure is configuration of soil particles and components (sand, silt, clay, organic matter, and chemicals) into aggregates or porous compounds that vary by shape, size, and composition. Soil structure deteriorates when structural units are deformed thus is a dynamic soil property that can mainly be affected by various agricultural management practices (e.g., tillage, cropping system, crop residues, fertilizers, etc.) (Mikha et al., 2021). Soil aggregate stability is important in mediating soil ecological functions, regulating soil health, affecting physical, chemical, and biological processes and climate change mitigation under different agricultural management practices as well as reducing soil erosion potential (Le Bissonnais, 1996). The environmental factors (i.e., wet-dry cycles and freeze-thaw successions), precipitation intensity and events, anthropogenic factors, land and soil management (i.e., tillage practices, organic amendments) and vegetation type significantly affects soil aggregate stability (Simões-Mota et al., 2022; Mustafa et al., 2020). Several indices have been used to evaluate soil structural stability using aggregate size distribution as the assessment basis. For the analysis of aggregate stability, three sieve sizes (2000 μm , 250 μm , and 53 μm) are generally used to separate the soil into four different aggregate size classes following the wet sieving procedure of Elliot (1986).

PROCEDURE

- Take undisturbed soil samples in the field.
- Dry undisturbed soil samples at room temperature.
- Dry sieving the undisturbed soil sample at 8 mm to obtain 100 g of soil.
- Fill up basin with water until water level is approximately 1 cm above 2000 μm sieve mesh.

- The soil samples are placed on top of a 2000 μm sieve and wetted for 5 min before immersion in water.
- After 5 min, the 2000 μm sieve is manually moved up and down 50 times for 2 min (approx. 3 cm amplitude).
- The soil remaining on the 2000 μm sieve is backwashed and transferred into a pre-weighed small drying pan for drying in an oven at 60 °C. In this way the aggregate size fraction >2000 μm is obtained.
- Soil and water that have passed through the 2000 μm sieve are transferred through the 250 μm sieve that should be placed in another basin to achieve the separation of the following aggregate size fraction.
- The 250 μm sieve is manually moved up and down 50 times for about 2 min (approx. 3 cm amplitude).
- The soil remaining on the 250 μm sieve is backwashed and transferred into a pre-weighed small drying pan for drying in an oven at 60 °C. In this way the aggregate size fraction 250-2000 μm is obtained.
- Soil and water that have passed through the 250 μm sieve are transferred through the 250 μm sieve that should be placed in another basin to achieve the separation of the following aggregate size fraction.
- The soil remaining on the 53 μm sieve is backwashed and transferred into a pre-weighed small drying pan for drying in the oven at 60 °C. In this way the aggregate size fraction 53-250 μm is obtained.
- Soil and water that have passed through the 53 μm sieve with the water can be transferred to a container and dried in an oven at 60 °C. In this way the aggregate size fraction <53 μm is obtained.
- After drying, all soil aggregate size fractions are weighed.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

- 8 mm sieve
- Two white basins with diameter of 50 cm and height of 8 cm.
- 2000 μm , 250 μm , 53 μm sieves.
- Aluminium pans for drying soil samples.
- Air-forced drying oven (60 °C).
- Spatula and brush.
- Rinsing bottle.
- Analytical balance (0.01 g).

CALCULATIONS

The results are generally expressed as a percentage showing the proportions of the different aggregate size classes.

Aggregate stability also can be expressed as the mean weight diameter (MWD):

$$MWD = \sum A_i * P_i$$

Where:

A_i is the mean size of the aggregate size class,

P_i is the proportion of the respective aggregate size class.

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3.4. Soil Bulk Density

PRINCIPLE

Soil bulk density has been one of the most commonly used parameters to describe compaction processes, since it indicates the amount of pores in the soil. Soil bulk density is defined as the ratio of oven-dried soil mass per unit volume (Blake, 1965), is an important property for assessing land management and agricultural practices effects on soil health (Allen et al., 2011). Soil bulk density determination is relevant because of its influence and direct interaction with numerous soil properties such as structure, porosity, infiltration rate, or carbon sequestration. Moreover, it is a soil property highly sensitive to land use and management practices (tillage, use of cover crop residues, crop rotations, etc.) being very useful for detecting improvements in soil physical conditions

or agricultural problems related to high compaction rates (e.g., high bulk density is a limiting factor of root penetration). However, it should be noted that soil bulk density has important limitations as a soil quality indicator, since it does not provide information about the size of the spaces, about the connection between them, or about the forces that have led to a specific soil structure.

The core method (Blake and Hartge, 1986) is a widely used method for soil bulk density determination due to its simplicity of application and replicability. In this method undisturbed soil samples are taken in the field in metal cylinders of known volume.

PROCEDURE

- Follow the indications for soil sampling included in section “2.1. Sampling for soil bulk density”
- In the laboratory, the contents of the cylinder or plastic bags are transferred into a beaker of known weight.
- Put the beaker in the oven for at least 24 hours at 105 °C until constant weight.
- Weigh the beaker and dry soil on the analytical balance and noting the exact weight.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

- Metal cylinder of known volume (100-500 cm³)
- Bulk Density Sampler Cup and Cap
- Hammer
- Spatula
- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

For bulk density calculation, the following formula should be applied:

$$pb = \frac{(m_2 - m_1)}{v}$$

pb is the bulk density of the soil [g m⁻³]

m₁ is the weight of the metal ring [g]

m₂ is the weight of the metal ring + soil after drying [g]

V is the volume of the metal ring [cm⁻³]

REMARKS

In soils with high percentages of gravel, coarse soil fractions hinder sampling and increase measurement error.

In the case of soils with swelling clay minerals, correction calculation is needed related to the field volume/dry volume ratio.

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3.5. Soil water content at field capacity and wilting point

PRINCIPLE

Soil water content is a fundamental part of the characterization of soil hydraulic properties. It depends on soil texture and soil structure (Klute, 1986). Soil moisture conditions are closely linked to pore volume, pore size distribution, capillary rise capacity, organic matter content and soil aggregation (Schlüter et al., 2022; Lipiec et al., 2007). Field capacity (FC) represents the upper limit of available water and corresponds to the soil moisture content left behind after the water contained in the macropores is drained by gravity, at field capacity the water and air contents of the soil are ideal for crop growth. Wilting point (WP) corresponds to the water content when the soil becomes dry and roots can no longer take up water, at this point the soil still contains some water, but it is too difficult for the roots to suck it from the soil. The soil can be compared to a water reservoir for the plants, the available water capacity represents the amount of water that the soil can hold and use for plant root uptake during plant growth (Hanks, 1992). One of the main methods to determine soil water content at field capacity and wilting point in the laboratory is by using a pressure plate extractor (Richards, 1947) at different pressure levels applied (33 kPa and 1500 kPa, respectively) and by measuring the changes in soil water content. The method is based on the injection of compressed air at a pressure equivalent to the matrix potential to be determined.

PROCEDURE

- Saturate the undisturbed soil sample with distilled water.
- Place the samples on the ceramic plate of 0.1 kPa type.
- Set the compressor to the adequate pressure level at 33 kPa (for FC)
- Once the water flow into the tubes ceases, the soil samples inside the pressure vessel have reached the equilibrium water content at the applied pressure.
- Remove the samples from the vessels and weigh them.
- Place samples in the oven and dry the samples at 105 °C for 24 h, then weigh the dried samples. Determine the water content of the sample by weight difference.
- Change the ceramic plate to 1.5 kPa type and place saturate soil samples.
- Set the compressor to the pressure 1500 kPa (for WP).
- Once the water flow into the tubes ceases, the soil samples inside the pressure vessel have reached the equilibrium water content at the applied pressure.
- Remove the samples from the vessels and weigh them.
- Place samples in the oven and dry the samples at 105 °C for 24 h, then weigh the dried samples. Determine the water content of the sample by weight difference.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

- Pressure control panel equipped with manometer
- Pressure vessel(s)
- Compressor (220 V/50 Hz) or compressed air tanks
- Pressure ceramic plates, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 1.5 kPa standards
- Oven

CALCULATIONS

To determine FC and WP and the amount of water available (AW) for plants, apply the followings formulas:

$$FC \text{ or } WP = \frac{(\text{Weight of wet soil (g)} - \text{Weight of oven dry soil (g)})}{\text{Weight of oven dry soil (g)}}$$

$$AW = FC - WP$$

REMARKS

When determining FC and WP it is difficult to know how much time is needed for the wet soil sample to reach the moisture content appropriate at actual pressure (i.e., suction).

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3.6. Carbon sequestration (total, organic and inorganic carbon).

PRINCIPLE

Soil organic matter (SOM) is a complex conglomerate of biogeochemical substances consisting mainly of plant and animal remains and exudates, which are transformed by microorganisms and decomposed under different environmental conditions (Stevenson, 1994). SOM is a source of energy and nutrients for soil organisms and contains essential elements for plants, such as carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, magnesium, calcium, sulphur and micronutrients (Graetz, 1997) and can be formed by various compounds in different degrees of decomposition or humification (Paul, 2014) irregularly distributed in the soil profile. SOM is considered a key element within the agroecosystem, is a dynamic factor responsible for soil structure development and consequently intervenes in the distribution of the porous space, water holding capacity and soil moisture (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2004). Therefore, SOM affects most of the chemical, physical and biological soil properties and is a fundamental indicator in the assessment of soil quality (Jarecki and Lal, 2005), both for its agronomic and environmental interest (Khalid et al., 2019).

The CN elemental analyser is widely employed to determine the amount of Total Carbon (TC), Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) and Soil Inorganic Carbon (SIC) (Duan et al., 2004). In this method, soil samples pass into the combustion reactor where combustion takes place (> 1000 °C) giving oxidised compounds, then the water is removed and the nitrogen dioxide is reduced to molecular nitrogen inside the reduction reactor. Finally, the detector measures the concentration of carbon dioxide and sends a signal to the software where with the help of a series of patterns, allows to calculate the amount of carbon in the samples.

PROCEDURE

Total Organic Carbon

Prepare dried soil samples sieve at 2 mm.

Grind a few grams the sample in a ball mill or agate mortar.

Weigh 50 mg of the grinded sample in a tin capsule and then introduced into the Elemental Analyzer.

Weigh soil calibration standards for known total carbon values.

Soil inorganic carbon

10 g of soil samples 2 mm sieved.

Introduce soil samples into a muffle at 450 °C for 4 hours.

After 4 hours, the soil is reweighed.

Weigh 50 mg of the grinded sample in a tin capsule and then introduced into the Elemental Analyzer.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Elemental Analyzer
- Porcelain crucible
- Micro Spatula
- Tin Capsules
- Analytical balance with a precision of 0.01 g
- Muffle
- Agate mortar or ball mill

CALCULATIONS

The total carbon content (TC) and the soil inorganic carbon (SIC) are obtained in percentage by weight (g of C in 100 grams of dry soil), a unit that can be converted to g of C per kilogram of dry soil by multiplying it by 10. The SOC is calculated by:

$$SOC = TCC - SIC$$

REMARKS

Flat-bottom crucibles are better suited to the determination of organic matter, since, by extending the soil sample over a larger area, soil burning is optimized.

It is important to ensure that soil samples are completely dry before introducing into the analyser.

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4. SOIL FERTILITY AND POLLUTION ASSESSMENT

4.1. pH

PRINCIPLE

pH values provide a preliminary information on the chemical characteristics of the soil, specifically the saturation of bases and, consequently, the availability and mobility of certain nutrients and trace elements (Fig. 9). Soil pH values can be altered by human factors such as the application of fertilisers, manure or compost (Whalen et al., 2000). Environmental factors can also influence in soil pH, e.g., in humid climates, excessive rainfall causes a leaching of calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium ions and thus decrease pH values (Hong et al., 2019).

Measuring soil pH with an electrode there are several factors to consider: the soil:water ratio, the ionic strength in the solution, the position of the electrode in the suspension, and stirring or resting the sample during the measurement. The time of equilibration of the soil:water mixture prior to measurement can affect the measured pH values. In this sense, Conyers and Davey (1988) recommend not to exceed 24 hours in order not to cause solubilisation of salts that may interfere with the ionic potential and recommend an equilibration period of one hour.

Figure 9. The effect of soil pH on nutrient availability (Roques et al. 2013).

PROCEDURE

- Weigh 2 g of soil (sieved 2 mm).
- Add 10 mL of distilled water (1:5 soil: water suspension)
- Shake at 15 rpm for 1 h.
- Let the suspension rest for 1 h.
- Calibrate the pH-meter with pH 4.00, 7.02 and 9.21 standards.
- Measure with a pH-meter before the next 2 h

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- pH meter
- 15 mL beaker
- Shaker
- Distilled water
- Analytical balance (0.1 g)
- Standard buffers pH 4.0, pH 7.0, pH 10.0

REMARKS

At the start of pH measurements (or when a pronounced change in pH value between two successive samples is observed), it is recommended to extend the pH measurement period for a few minutes (using the continuous mode if it is available) in order to favour the stabilization of the measurement before recording the final value.

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4.2. Electrical conductivity

PRINCIPLE

Electrical conductivity (EC) measures the ability of the soil to conduct electric conductivity by taking advantage of the conductive property of salts; therefore, EC measures the concentration of soluble salts present in the soil solution (Porta et al., 2003). Its measurement is based on the principle that the rate at which electric current flows through a salt solution is proportional to the concentration of salts in solution. A solution conducts electricity to a greater extent the higher the salt concentration. Thus, the higher the EC of a salt solution, the higher the salt concentration.

When EC values are excessively high, soil salinisation occurs, which is the process by salts accumulate in the soil, impeding the development of crops and can be caused by natural or anthropic factors (Ondrasek et al., 2011). The most soluble salts are the most harmful, as they give rise to highly concentrated saline solutions, while the less soluble salts precipitate before reaching hazardous levels (Gondek et al., 2020). Two situations can be distinguished with very different morphologies, properties, genesis and uses of the soil, depending on whether the predominant cation in the exchange complex is sodium or calcium.

Based on conductivity, a classification of soils can be made: those soils with a conductivity less than 2 dS m⁻¹ are considered non-saline, while those with a conductivity greater than 16 dS m⁻¹ are considered strongly saline (Table 1). The unit of measurement for EC is the dS m⁻¹. As conductivity varies with temperature, the measurement at 25 °C is generally used.

Table 1 Salinity classes of soils based on electrical conductivity (Soil Science Division Staff, 2017)

Class	Electrical conductivity dS m ⁻¹
Non saline	0-2
Very slightly saline	2-4
Slightly saline	4-8
Moderately saline	8-16
Strongly saline	16

PROCEDURE

- Weigh 2 g of soil (sieved 2 mm) in a 25 mL beaker.
- Add 10 mL of distilled water (1:5 soil:water suspension).
- Shake the mixture for 1 hour.
- The conductivity meter is calibrated with a 0.01 M KCl solution (with an electrical conductivity of 1412 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$).
- The soil suspension is measured by introducing the conductivity electrode.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Conductivity meter
- 25 mL beaker
- KCl standard solution 0.01 M (1412 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ at 25 °C)
- Analytical balance (0.1 g)
- Shaker

CALCULATIONS

Conversion of electrical conductivity (in mS cm^{-1}) to total dissolved ions (TDI) can be done (Hardie and Doyle, 2012):

$$TDI (\text{mgL}^{-1}) = CE (\text{mS cm}^{-1}) * 667$$

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4.3. Cation Exchange Capacity

PRINCIPLE

The cation exchange capacity (CEC) of soils is a chemical soil parameter of overall relevance and represents the total number of negative charges present on the surfaces of minerals and organic soil components (clay, organic matter or humic substances) and represents the amount of cations that the surfaces can retain (Ca, Mg, Na, etc.) (Porta et al., 1999). CEC measurement provides information on the ability of the soil to retain cations, the availability and quantity of nutrients to the plant, its pH potential and others (Rhoades, 1983). A soil with low CEC indicates low nutrient retention capacity, sandy or poor in organic matter. The CEC depends on the types and content of clay minerals as well as soil organic matter and its quality. Thus, CEC is a key parameter of soil fertility as a major ecosystem service of soils. The method to determine the CEC shown here is the determination of the effective cation exchange capacity and base saturation level using barium chloride (BaCl_2) solution as exchangeable salt (ISO, 2018). In this method the soil colloidal complex is saturated with a solution of a cation (barium chloride), so that all cations adsorbed to the complex are released by percolation.

PROCEDURE

Leaching and measurement of soil bases

1. Weigh 2.50 g of air-dried soil into a polyethylene centrifuge tube of about 50 mL capacity. Close cap tightly. Note the combined mass of tube and soil (m_1).
2. Add 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and shake for 1 h. Subsequently centrifuge the tubes at 3,000 g for 10 min. Note: Balance tubes before centrifugation. Transfer the supernatant to a 100 mL volumetric flask. Repeat this procedure, i.e., the addition of 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution, shaking and centrifugation twice more. Collect all three supernatants in the same volumetric flask. Fill with BaCl_2 (0.1 mol L^{-1}) up to the mark. Mix, filter and store the extract I for the determination of the exchangeable concentration of Na, K, Ca and Mg (sum of bases).

3. Calibration for Na, K, Ca and Mg determination: Prepare solutions with 0 mL, 5 mL, 10 mL, 15 mL, 20 mL and 25 mL of the diluted stock solution ($c(\text{Na}) = 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in 50 mL volumetric flasks. Add 10.0 mL of extraction solution BaCl_2 (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and 5.0 mL of acidified caesium chloride solution. Fill up to the mark with water. The resulting concentrations of Na are 0, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 mg L^{-1} . The resulting concentrations of K are 0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 mg L^{-1} . Prepare solutions with 0, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 mL of the stock solution ($c(\text{Ca}) 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{Mg}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) in 100 mL volumetric flasks. The resulting concentrations of Ca are 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 mg L^{-1} . The resulting concentrations of Mg are 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 mg L^{-1} .

4. Analysis: Fill 2.0 mL of the extract I and of the blank sample, respectively, into reaction tubes. Add 1.0 mL of acidified caesium chloride solution and 7.0 mL of water and mix (see Remarks). Determine bases with FAAS or ICP-EOS, with the instrument set according to the manufacturer's instructions for optimum performance.

Cleansing

1. Add 30 mL of BaCl_2 solution ($0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) to the soil pellet and shake overnight. Resulting Ba concentration in the equilibrium solution will be about 0.01 mol L^{-1} . Centrifuge tubes at 3,000 *g* for 10 min. Decant the supernatant liquid.

Re-exchange

2. Weigh the tube with its contents and cap (m^2). Add 30 mL of MgSO_4 solution (0.020 mol L^{-1}) to the soil pellet and shake overnight. Centrifuge tubes at 3,000 *g* for 10 min. Decant the supernatant through a filter paper into a new flask and store the extract II for the determination of the concentration of excess Mg.

3. Prepare blank samples without the addition of soil in parallel and follow the above described procedure completely.

Determination of CEC

1. Pipette 0.20 mL from the extracts II of the samples and blank samples into 100 mL volumetric flasks.

2. Add 0.3 mL of the BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) and additional 10 mL of acidified lanthanum solution (10 mg L^{-1}).

3. Fill up with water to the mark and mix.

4. For calibration, use dilutions of the Mg standard solution (10 mg L^{-1}). Pipette 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 mL into a series of 100 mL volumetric flasks. Add 10 mL of acidified lanthanum solution (10 mg L^{-1}) to each flask and fill up to the mark with water. Final concentration of the calibration solutions: 0, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, and 0.05 mmol L^{-1} , respectively.

5. Analyse Mg using FAAS at a wavelength of 285.2 nm or using ICPOES with instrumentation settings following the manufacturer's instructions for optimum performance of the instrument.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Shaker, rotary shaker (end-over-end) or horizontal
- Tightly locking polyethylene centrifuge tubes (ca. 50 mL)
- 50 or 100 mL polyethylene (PE) flasks
- Funnels
- Filter paper (Whatman No. 42, Schleicher & Schuell 595 1/2, Macherey-Nagel 261 G 1/4, or similar)
- Glass vacuum line (e.g., electric pump)
- Flame atomic absorption spectrometer (FAAS) or ICPOES

REAGENTS

- Deionised water (electric conductivity <math>< 0.2 \text{ mS m}^{-1}</math> at 25 °C).
- Barium chloride (BaCl_2) solution; $c(\text{BaCl}_2) = 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dissolve 24.43 g of $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ in 1000 mL of water (use volumetric flask).
- BaCl_2 solution; $c(\text{BaCl}_2) = 0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dilute 25 mL of solution BaCl_2 solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) in 1000 mL of water.
- Magnesium sulphate solution; $c(\text{MgSO}_4) = 0.020 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Dissolve 4.930 g magnesium sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in 1000 mL of water (use volumetric flask). Prepare fresh solution. Magnesium sulphate can lose crystal water during storage. Therefore, wrap the flask in an additional PE bag and store the chemical in a refrigerator
Hydrochloric acid, $c(\text{HCl}) = 12 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ ($\rho = 1.19 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$).
- Magnesium standard solution; $c(\text{Mg}) = 0.0010 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Add 50 mL of MgSO_4 solution (0.020 mol L^{-1}) to a 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up with water to the mark (see Remarks).
- Acidified lanthanum solution: $c(\text{La}) = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Preparation: Add 15.6 mg lanthanum nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] to a 500 mL volumetric flask, add 42 mL hydrochloric acid (12 mol L^{-1}), and fill up with water to 500 mL.
- Acidified caesium chloride solution: Dissolve 10 g caesium chloride in some water. Add 83 mL of hydrochloric acid (12 mol L^{-1}), and make up to 1000 mL with water.
- Sodium and potassium stock solution: $c(\text{Na}) = 400 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Dissolve 1.0168 g sodium chloride and 1.9068 g potassium chloride in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks).

- Diluted stock solution: $c(\text{Na}) = 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Pipette 25 mL of solution ($c(\text{Na}) 400 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$, $c(\text{K}) = 1000 \text{ mg/L}$) in 250 mL volumetric flask and fill up with water to the mark (see Remarks).
- Hydrochloric acid, $c(\text{HCl}) = 4 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. Add 333 mL of commercial 37% HCl ($\rho = 1.19 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) to water, to receive a total volume of 1000 mL. Calcium stock solution: $c(\text{Ca}) = 1000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Dissolve 2.497 g calcium carbonate in water. Transfer to 1000 mL volumetric flask and fill up to the mark with water (see Remarks).
- Magnesium stock solution: $c(\text{Mg})$.

CALCULATIONS

Correct the concentrations of Mg in the sample solutions for the volume of the liquid retained by the centrifuged soil after being treated with $0.0025 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ BaCl}_2$ solution:

$$c_2 = \frac{[c_1 + (30 + m_2 - m_1)]}{30}$$

Where:

c_2 is the corrected Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L^{-1}]

c_1 is the Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L^{-1}]

m_1 is the mass of the centrifuge tube with air-dried soil [g]

m_2 is the mass of the centrifuge tube with wet soil [g]

Calculate the cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soil using the following equation:

$$CEC = \frac{(c_{b1} - c_2)3000}{m}$$

Where:

- CEC is the cation exchange capacity of the soil [cmolc kg^{-1}]
- c_2 is the corrected Mg concentration in the sample [mmol L^{-1}]
- c_{b1} is the Mg concentration in the blank [mmol L^{-1}]
- m is the mass of the air-dried sample [g]

If the CEC exceeds 40 cmolc kg^{-1} , the determination should be repeated using less soil, adjusting the calculation accordingly

Calculate the soil bases as follows:

$$c(\text{Na, exchangable}) = \frac{2.1749 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{2\text{blank}})}{m[\text{cmolc Kg}^{-1}]}$$

$$c(K, \text{exchangable}) = \frac{1.2788 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}})}{m[\text{cmolc Kg}^{-1}]}$$

$$c(\text{Ca}, \text{exchangable}) = \frac{8.2288 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}})}{m[\text{cmolc Kg}^{-1}]}$$

$$c(\text{Mg}, \text{exchangable}) = \frac{4.9903 \times (c_{\text{sample}} - c_{\text{blank}})}{m[\text{cmolc Kg}^{-1}]}$$

with the measured concentrations in the diluted sample (c_{sample}) and the diluted blank sample (c_{blank}), respectively, and m as the soil mass in g.

REMARKS

If the barium chloride extract has a yellowish-brown colour, this indicates that some organic matter has been dissolved. If this occurs, record it in the test report.

As an alternative to the preparation of standards and calibration series, respectively, certified standard solutions are commercially available; aliquots are diluted as required.

For a complete analysis of exchangeable cations, it might be reasonable to additionally determine NH_4^+ in fertilised agricultural soil and exchangeable Al and Fe in very acidic soil respectively.

Any other volumes can be used as well, as long as the same concentrations are obtained and the final sample volume is sufficient for analysis with FAAS or ICP-OES.

Dilutions can be prepared much faster by pipetting or using a diluter system.

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4.4. Total Nitrogen

PRINCIPLE

Nitrogen (N) is one of the essential macronutrients for crop growth and development. However, N amounts available in the soil are not sufficient to meet the needs of

cultivated plants, so nitrogen sources need to be applied. Nitrogen is part of proteins, enzymes and chlorophyll, and is crucial in the processes of protein synthesis and photosynthesis, as well as accelerating cell division and root growth. A plant with a nitrogen deficiency will not be able to complete the metabolic processes essential for its development. In cases of extreme deficiency, plant growth can be stunted and leaves can fall off, and the plant is more vulnerable to disease (Halse et al., 1969). Total nitrogen (TN) corresponds to ammonium-N (NH_4^+), nitrate-N (NO_3^-), nitrite-N (NO_2) and organic N, around 90–95% of TN in soils is in organic form, and therefore is assimilated by plants through mineralisation. Soil N content is related to the availability of nutrients and their susceptibility to alteration due to environmental conditions, soil management and cultivation systems (Mazzoncini et al., 2011). To optimise N use efficiency in each cycle, dynamic soil and plant-based management is required. The N present is determined by a CN elemental analyser following the Dumas method, where the soil sample is combusted with the addition of pure oxygen, reduction of the oxides of nitrogen formed to molecular nitrogen which is passed through the system by means of a gas, usually helium, and its detection using a thermal conductivity detector (Bremner, 1996). The quantification is carried out with certified reference standards of different concentrations of nitrogen.

PROCEDURE

- The method used to determine the total nitrogen is the same as the method used for total carbon 3.6. Carbon sequestration (total, organic and inorganic carbon):
- Dry soil samples sieve at 2 mm.
- Grind a few grams the sample in a ball mill or agate mortar.
- About 50 mg of grinded dry soil is weighed in tin capsules and measured with the Elemental Analyzer.
- The nitrogen standards are also weighed and analysed.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Elemental Analyzer
- Micro Spatula
- Tin Capsules
- Analytical balance with a precision of 0.0001 g
- Oven
- Agate mortar or ball mill

CALCULATIONS

The results of total nitrogen are obtained in percentage by weight (g of N in 100 grams of dry soil), a unit that can be converted to grams of N per kilogram of dry soil by multiplying by 10.

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4.5. Available P in the soil

PRINCIPLE

The productivity and dynamics of agroecosystems is limited to the availability of nutrients, phosphorus (P) is one of the essential elements for plant nutrition. In plants, phosphorus is an important part of nucleic acids, stimulates root development, promotes flowering and seed formation and is necessary for biological nitrogen fixation (Raghothama, 2005). Phosphorus is present in the soil in relatively low quantities (between 0.2 and 5 g Kg⁻¹) and it appears in forms which are not usually available for plant uptake. Consequently, soluble P forms are normally used for soil fertilization due to P deficiencies in the plant cause severe damage to vegetative development, leaf growth, leaf expansion, reproductive organs, flower initiation and flower number, seed formation and seed germination (Sharma et al., 2013).

The analysis of assimilable P content can be determined using different extractant solutions (depending on soil pH). Two main methods can be distinguished depending on soil pH: the Olsen method is recommended to be applied for alkaline soils, whereas for neutral and acidic soils the Bray II method is preferred (Dari et al., 2019) The concentration of phosphorus in the solutions obtained is then generally determined by the colorimetric method.

PROCEDURE

A) Olsen

Before starting it is necessary to prepare several solutions:

1. 2.5 M sulphuric acid solution. Carefully add 140 mL of H_2SO_4 (with 96% purity) to a one-litre volumetric flask containing about 400 mL of water, and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
2. 1 M sodium hydroxide solution. Dissolve 40 mL of NaOH in distilled water. It is an exothermic solution, so it is necessary to stir and let cool before completing the volume with water.
3. Sodium bicarbonate solution. In a volume close to one litre ($\approx 0.8\text{-}0.9\text{ L}$), dissolve 42 g of sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3). The pH of the solution is adjusted to 8.5 (adding drops of the O_2 solution) before completing the volume (1 L).
4. 0.25% solution of *p*-Nitrophenol. 0.25 g of *p*-Nitrophenol ($\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}$) are dissolved with distilled water in a 100 mL volumetric flask, completing the dilution to mark with water.
5. 40 g L^{-1} ammonium molybdate solution. 40 g of ammonium molybdate [$(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}$] are weighed, dissolved in distilled water and made up to 1000 mL.
6. Potassium antimony tartrate solution. This solution should contain 1 mg of antimony per millilitre, so 0.2728 g of potassium antimony tartrate [$(\text{K}(\text{SbO}) \times \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O})$] are dissolved in distilled water and made up to 100 mL.
7. 0.1 M ascorbic acid solution. This solution must be prepared at the time of use. 1.76 g of ascorbic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_6$) are dissolved in water and made up to 100 mL.
8. Sulphomolybdic solution. This solution must be prepared at the time of use. Mix: 50 mL of O_1 solution, 15 mL of O_5 , 30 mL of O_7 and 5 mL of O_6 .
9. It is also necessary to prepare a phosphorus stock solution to make the standards. To prepare this solution weight 4.3938 g of KH_2PO_4 (dried at 40 °C), dissolve it in distilled water and make it up to 1000 mL. The phosphorus concentration in this solution is 1000 mg L^{-1} .

The phosphorus determination can be divided into two parts: extraction and measurement by spectrophotometry.

To carry out the phosphorus extraction, two grams of soil are weighed (m) in a 50 mL Greiner tube and 40 mL of the O_3 solution are added (VE). This is stirred for 30 min and filtered by a 0.45 μm filter. It is important to make a blank without soil, but following the same steps.

For the determination by spectrophotometry an aliquot of the extract is taken (the volume of this aliquot depends on the amount of P the soil has, VS), 5 drops of O_4 are added and then O_1 is added until the colour changes to yellow. This is diluted with water

and 8 mL of O_8 are added. In the end, the volume of 50 mL is completed with distilled water. Let the solution stand for 10 min and measure with a spectrophotometer, using a wavelength of 882 nm.

When measuring, it is necessary to employ the same procedure with the standards that are going to be used in the calibration, replacing the soil or blank with a known concentration of phosphorus. Standards of 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mg L⁻¹ are usually used.

B) Bray II

Before starting it is necessary to prepare several solutions:

1. Extraction solution of hydrochloric acid (0.1 N) and ammonium fluoride (0.03 N). Add 1.11 g of NH_4F and 8.28 mL of HCl (37%) to a 1 L volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
2. This solution is obtained by mixing two solutions. The first one is made dissolving 0.116 g of potassium antimony tartrate in 500 mL of distilled water, and the second results from the dissolution of 4.8 g of ammonium molybdate in 250 mL of distilled water. After mixing of both solutions in a 1 L volumetric flask, 55 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 are carefully added, and the resultant solution is diluted with distilled water to the mark.
3. Solution of p-Nitrophenol (0.25%). Weigh 0.25 g of p-Nitrophenol in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with ethanol.
4. Solution of NH_3 (5%). Add 20 mL of NH_3 in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
5. Solution of H_2SO_4 (5%). Add 5.1 mL of H_2SO_4 in a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with distilled water.
6. This solution must be prepared just before the measurement process. Dissolve 1 g of ascorbic acid in 100 mL of solution B2.
7. It is also necessary to prepare a phosphorus stock solution to make the standards. Weigh 4.3938 g of KH_2PO_4 (dried at 40 °C), dissolve it in distilled water and make it up to 1 L. The phosphorus concentration in this solution is 1 g L⁻¹.

The procedure is the following:

First, 1 g of sieved dry soil (m) is weighted in a Greiner tube and 10 mL of solution B1 is added (VE).

This suspension is shaken for 30 min and filtered by a 0.45 µm filter. In a 50 mL volumetric flask, an aliquot of the filtered suspension is added (0.1-0.5 mL). The volume used depends on the expected amount of phosphorus (VS).

The following solutions are added to the flask:

0.5 mL of boric acid.

2-3 drops of B3 solution.

2-3 drops of B4 solution (until the solution turns yellow).

2-3 drops of B5 solution (until the solution becomes colourless).

5 mL of B6 solution.

Dilute to the mark with water.

It is necessary to employ the same procedure with the blank and the standards that are going to be used in the calibration. Standards, replacing the soil with a known concentration of phosphorus of 0.04, 0.08, 0.12, 0.16 and 0.24 mg L⁻¹ are usually employed.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Magnetic stirrer
- Shaker
- Greiner tubes (50 mL)
- Dispenser
- Beakers
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- Centrifuge
- 0.45 µm Filters
- Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃)
- p-Nitrophenol (NO₂C₆H₄OH)
- Ammonium molybdate [(NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O]
- Potassium antimony tartrate [(K(SbO) x C₄H₄O₆ · ½ H₂O)]
- Ascorbic acid (C₆H₄O₆)
- Potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄)
- Spectrophotometer

CALCULATIONS

Phosphorus content is usually referred to grams of dry soil. For this, the following formula can be used:

$$C_p = (A - B) \frac{V_E}{V_S} \frac{50}{m}$$

Where:

C_p is the extractable phosphorus content in the soil (in mg of P g⁻¹ of dry soil)

A is the P concentration in the sample (mg mL⁻¹)

B is the P concentration in the blank (mg mL⁻¹)

V_E is the volume of extractant used (mL).

V_S is the volume of sample measured by spectrophotometry (mL).

m is the soil mass (g)

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4.6. Available Boron

PRINCIPLE

Boron is a microelement that has an essential role in a large number of plant physiological processes such as sugar transport, sucrose synthesis, nucleic acid metabolism, photosynthesis, etc. Boron is a relatively non-mobile element within plants and the contents are higher in the basal parts than in the upper levels (Brown et al., 1992).

Boron is found in higher amounts in sedimentary rocks than in other rock types due to its marine origin. Most of the boron in the soil is not assimilable by plants, less than 5% is in assimilable form. Sandy soils generally contain less assimilable boron than clay soils,

being easily leached in light textured soils. The assimilability of boron decreases with increasing soil pH, which leads to limestone soils prone to boron deficiency especially if there are high percentages of clays, due to the adsorption of borate ion. The correction of boron deficiency in soils is relatively easy, however it is important not to exceed the toxicity limits (above 5 ppm of assimilable boron) since this can generate serious problems for crops, and an excess of boron can limit the absorption of calcium, potassium and magnesium (Nable et al., 1997).

In available boron determination, water extraction is usually used (Berger and Truog, 1939) and measured by atomic emission spectrometry or by a colorimetric method using a reagent such as Azometin-H due to its high sensitivity (Debal et al., 1979). Azometina-H reacciona con el boro en medio ácido dando un compuesto amarillo-anaranjado que presenta su máxima absorción a 420 nm (Wolf, 1974).

PROCEDURE

- 5 g of dry soil are weighed in a beaker (m1).
- 10 mL of distilled water are added.
- 0.5 g of activated charcoal are added.
- The suspension is boiled for 5 min and filtered through No. 42 filter paper.
- Boron determination is made by using an atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS), using a wavelength of 249.7 nm, an acetylene / nitrous oxide flame and boron standards with concentrations between 1 and 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.
- Standards are prepared from $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$. At the end, a boron concentration is obtained in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ (CBM).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- Balance
- Spatula
- Distilled water
- Activated charcoal
- Heating plate
- No. 42 filter paper
- Atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS)
- $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$

CALCULATIONS

The boron concentration obtained by ASA is in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and it is necessary to convert it to μg of B per g of dry soil. Since we added 10 mL of water to the soil to extract the boron:

$$C_B = \frac{10C_{BM}}{m_1}$$

Where:

C_B is the boron concentration in μg per g of dry soil.

C_{BM} is the boron concentration measured through AAS in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

M_1 is the mass of dry soil.

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4.7. Inorganic Nitrogen (Nitrates and Ammonium)

PRINCIPLE

Soil fertilisation, organic or inorganic, is the most important source of nitrogen in agriculture, although it is also incorporated into the soil by rain or by fixation through microorganisms and plants. In the soil 90-95% of the total nitrogen is in organic form, so it is not directly assimilated by plants and has to be mineralised previously (Unkovich et al., 1998). The mineral nitrogen in the soil, is in the form of ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-) both mineral nitrogen forms can be assimilated by plants, but most of the nitrogen is absorbed in the form of nitrate (Keeney & Nelson, 1982). Ammonium is found in the

soil adsorbed in the exchange complex, fixed in the crystalline networks of certain clays or in the soil solution. Soil nitrate and ammonia are key indicators on the assessment of chemical soil fertility, however due to potential nitrogen leaching the excessive use of nitrogen inputs (synthetic or organic) could lead to an excess of nitrate and ammonia in the soil circulating solution and, thus, consequent water pollution.

In nitrate and ammonium measurement, 2 M solution of potassium chloride (KCl) is frequently adopted as extraction solution, because of its high determination coefficient (Nelson, 1983). After extraction the determination is carried out by ion chromatography (nitrate and nitrite) and spectrophotometry (ammonium). Soil samples collected for nitrate and ammonium analysis must be kept at 4 °C from the experimental field if the analysis is to be carried out within 3 days. If the analysis will be performed later than 3 days, the soil samples must be frozen at -20 °C.

PROCEDURE

Nitrate determination

1. Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred into a refrigerated container.
2. Weigh 2.5 g of sieved field-moist soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of the deionized water (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).
3. Shake on the rotating plate for 60 min.
4. Centrifuge the samples at 3000 *g* for 2 min. Filter the supernatant using syringe filters.
5. The extract obtained is measured in the ion chromatography equipment.
6. Prepare a calibration curve from the NO₃⁻ stock solution.

Ammonium determination

1. Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred in a refrigerator container.
2. Weigh 2.5 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of the 2 M KCl solution (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).
3. Shake on the rotating plate for 60 min.
4. Centrifuge the samples at 3000 *g* for 2 min.
5. Take a 5 mL aliquot of the supernatant from each sample. For samples with a high ammonium content, pipette 2.5 mL (in this case the dilution factor is 2). Pour the aliquot in a 10 mL test tube. Add 2.5 mL of deionized water to the test tube if 2.5 mL has been pipetted to have a final volume of 5 mL in all tubes.

6. Prepare tubes to determine the calibration curve. The standards will have concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5 and 5 mg L⁻¹ of NH₄⁺ and are prepared from the stock solution of 100 mg NH₄⁺ L⁻¹ (Table 6.4.1.). These concentrations will be the dependent variables and the corresponding absorbance values will be the independent variable.
7. Add 2.5 mL of Salicylate-Na/NaOH solution and 1 mL of 0.1% sodium dichloroisocyanide to all tubes.
8. Cover, shake (using the vortex shaker), and let stand in darkness for 30 min.
9. Then, turn on the spectrophotometer and adjust the wavelength (λ) to 690 nm. Perform the autozero with the 0 mg NH₄⁺ mL⁻¹ standard.
10. Measure all standards, including 0 mg NH₄⁺ mL⁻¹, to perform the calibration curve in which the NH₄⁺ concentration of the samples and blanks will be calculated.
11. Measure the absorbance of the samples in the spectrophotometer. In the event that any sample gives an absorbance greater than the maximum value of the calibration curve, it is necessary to take less volume of supernatant to make a dilution (step 5).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Nitrate determination

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Plastic vials (50 mL)
- Volumetric flask (100 mL)
- Rotating plate
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL)
- Centrifuge
- Syringe filters (0.2 μ m)
- Syringe (10 mL)
- Ion chromatography equipment

Ammonium determination

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Plastic vials (50 mL)
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL)
- Volumetric flasks (100, 500 and 1000 mL)
- Plastic buckets (2.5 mL)
- Vortex shaker
- Centrifuge
- Automatic pipette (1-5 mL)

- Rotating plate
- Visible / UV spectrophotometer

REAGENTS

Stock or commercial nitrate solution (1000 mg L⁻¹ NO₃⁻)

- Solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): dissolve 149 g of potassium chloride (KCl) in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.
- Sodium hydroxide (0.3 M NaOH): dissolve 12 g of NaOH in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionized water.
- Sodium salicylate solution: dissolve 85 g of sodium salicylate (C₇H₅NaO₃) and 600 mg of sodium nitroprusside (Na₂ [Fe (CN)₅ NO]). Fill up to 500 mL with deionized water. Store at 4 °C.
- Salicylate-Na / NaOH solution: mix equal volumes of 0.3 M NaOH, sodium salicylate and deionized water (1: 1: 1). Prepare daily.
- Solution of sodium dichloroisocyanide (0.1% C₃Cl₂N₃NaO₃) (w:v): dissolve 0.1 g of sodium dichloroisocyanide in 100 mL of deionized water. Prepare daily.
- Ammonium stock solution (100 mg L⁻¹ NH₄⁺): dissolve 0.297 g of NH₄Cl in 1000 mL of 2 M KCl

CALCULATIONS

Nitrate determination

$$NO_3^- (mg\ kg^{-1}) = \frac{(Cx\ V\ x\ df)}{m}$$

C is the concentration of nitrate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L⁻¹).

V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL).

df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1.

m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture).

Ammonium determination

$$NH_4^+ (mg\ kg^{-1}) = \frac{(Cx\ V\ x\ df)}{m}$$

C is the concentration of nitrate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L^{-1}).

V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL).

df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1.

m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture).

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4.8. Available Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn

PRINCIPLE

In the growth of crops, nutrients must be assimilated by the plants, so ideally a nutritional balance of the soil is desired for high quality and optimal production. Disturbance of the nutritional balance may create or amplify the phenomena of synergism and antagonism between the various nutrients present in the soil. Microelements of metallic nature such as Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Copper (Cu) and Zinc (Zn), are present in soils and substrates mainly as oxides or hydroxides or other fairly insoluble salts at basic or alkaline pH. The metal bioavailability depends on the solubility and adsorption capacity of metals in the colloidal fraction of soil (Shaheen et al., 2013). In addition, environmental conditions also affect the absorption of nutrients, e.g., under extreme temperature conditions, absorption decreases significantly, or under heavy or persistent rainfall, nutrient leaching may occur. These metals are nutrients that are essential however are absorbed by plants nutrition in relatively low amounts (Lambers and Oliveira, 2019).

In available Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn determination soil elements are extracted by a chelating agent, diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) or either ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) (Haq et al., 1980). The sample and chelating agent are placed in a plastic container and shaken for a specified period. After that, the vessel contents are centrifuged, or allowed to settle, and filtered, then analysed by the appropriate determinative method. The selection of extractants will depend on the pH of the soil, usually DTPA is used for neutral or alkaline soils while EDTA is used for acidic soils (Feng et al., 2005; Manouchehri et al., 2006).

PROCEDURE

For the extraction of Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn, depending on the pH value of the soil in water, DPTA (pH > 6.0) or EDTA (pH < 6.0) will be used.

A) Soil with pH > 6

First, it is necessary to prepare a DTPA solution by weighing the following reagents in a 250 mL beaker:

- 1.9667 g DTPA
- 0.0735 g CaCl₂·2H₂O
- Triethanolamine: 14 mL (98% TEA) or 15.6 mL (85% TEA).

This solution is shaken by a magnetic stirrer, and distilled water is added until it reaches a volume of 900 mL. Once this is done, the pH is measured and adjusted to 7.3 by adding 37% HCl. Then distilled water is added up to 1 L.

Once the solution has been prepared, 2 g of soil (sieved by 2 mm) are weighed in a Greiner tube and 4 mL of the DTPA solution are added (the soil:extractant ratio is 1:2). The tubes are shaken for 2 h, centrifuged at 1500 *g* for 5 min, and the supernatant filtered using a 0.45 µm filter. The filtrate is analysed by an atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

B) Soil with pH < 6.0

In this case, the process is similar but the extractant, and the ratio are different. First, it is necessary to prepare the EDTA solution, for which the following reagents must be weighed in a 250 mL beaker:

- 1.8612 g EDTA
- 77 g Ammonium acetate

This solution is shaken by a magnetic stirrer and distilled water is added until it has a volume of 900 mL. Once this is done, the pH is measured and adjusted to 4.65 by adding

37% HCl. Then distilled water is added up to 1 L. Once the solution has been prepared, 2 grams of soil (sieved with a 2 mm mesh sieve) are weighed in a Greiner tube and 10 mL of the EDTA solution are added (the soil:extractant ratio is 1:5). The tubes are shaken for 1 h, centrifuged at 1500 g for 5 min, and the supernatant filtered using a 0.45 µm filter. The filtrate is analysed by an atomic absorption spectrophotometer or using an ICP-MS.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

- Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid, DTPA, (C₁₄H₂₃N₃O₁₀)
- Calcium chloride, CaCl₂·2H₂O
- Triethanolamine, TEA (C₆H₁₅NO₃)
- Hydrochloric Acid, HCl (37%)
- Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid, EDTA (C₁₀H₁₆N₂O₈)
- Ammonium acetate (C₁₀H₁₆N₂O₈)
- Magnetic stirrer
- Shaker
- Greiner tubes (15 mL)
- Dispenser
- Beakers
- Analytical balance (0.0001 g)
- 2 mm mesh sieve
- Centrifuge
- 0.45 µm Filters
- Atomic absorption spectrophotometer
- Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS)

CALCULATIONS

The results obtained from the atomic absorption spectrophotometer are in mg mL⁻¹ and should be converted into mg g⁻¹ of dry soil. To do this, if we start from the concentration value that we obtain from the measurement of each metal, C_M (mg mL⁻¹), and assume that the concentration in the filtrate is homogeneous, for DTPA:

$$C_{DS} = \frac{4C_M}{W_{DS}}$$

Where:

C_{DS} is the metal concentration by gram of dry soil (mg of metal per g of dry soil).

C_M is the measured concentration in the spectrometer (in mg mL⁻¹)

W_{DS} is the exact amount of soil weighted (in g).

And for EDTA:

$$C_{DS} = \frac{10C_M}{W_{DS}}$$

These formulas will be applied to each measured metal (Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn).

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4.9. Total Sulphur

PRINCIPLE

Sulphur (S) is a critical nutrient for crop growth, the main original source of sulphur in soils is pyrite (FeS₂) from igneous rocks. S is found in soil in organic and inorganic forms, the amount of S in the two forms varies widely depending on depth and soil characteristics pH, drainage, organic matter content and mineralogical soil composition. The main form of S addition to the soil is through fertilisers and amendments, then the conversion of organic S to plant-available forms is done by microbiological processes. When the soil is well aerated, organic S is oxidised to SO₄⁻² which is the form in which S is taken up by plants, simultaneously, SO₄⁻² is assimilated by microorganisms and incorporated into the biomass in process of immobilisation or mineralization (Stevenson and Cole, 1999). Increases in soil organic S content will only occur when conditions are suitable for organic matter accumulation, such as frequent additions of organic residues.

Available sulphur in soil is determined by extracting soil using a 2 M potassium chloride solution. The sulphur content of extracts is then analysed by spectrophotometry ammonium (Blair et al., 1991).

PROCEDURE

Homogenize the soil sample (manually or mechanically). The soil sample must be transferred in a refrigerator container.

Weigh 2.5 g of sieved soil (< 2 mm) in a plastic vial, recording the exact weight. Add 25 mL of the 2 M KCl solution (soil / extractant ratio 1:10).

Shake on the rotating plate for 60 min.

Centrifuge the samples at 3000 *g* for 2 min.

Take a 5 mL aliquot of the supernatant from each sample. For samples with a high sulphur content, pipette 2.5 mL (in this case the dilution factor is 2). Pour the aliquot in a 10 mL test tube. Add 2.5 mL of deionized water to the test tube if 2.5 mL has been pipetted to have a final volume of 5 mL in all tubes.

Prepare tubes to determine the calibration curve. The standards will have concentrations of 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5 and 5 mg L⁻¹ of NH₄⁺ and are prepared from the stock solution of 100 mg NH₄⁺ L⁻¹. These concentrations will be the dependent variables and the corresponding absorbance values will be the independent variable.

Add 2.5 mL of Salicylate-Na/NaOH solution and 1 mL of 0.1% sodium dichloroisocyanide to all tubes.

Cover, shake (using the vortex shaker), and let stand for 30 min in darkness.

Then, turn on the spectrophotometer and adjust the wavelength (λ) to 690 nm. Perform the autozero with the 0 mg NH₄⁺ L⁻¹ standard.

Measure all standards, including 0 mg NH₄⁺ mL⁻¹, to perform the calibration curve in which the NH₄⁺ concentration of the samples and blanks will be calculated.

Measure the absorbance of the samples in the spectrophotometer. In the event that any sample gives an absorbance greater than the maximum value of the calibration curve, it is necessary to take less volume of supernatant to make a dilution (step 5).

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Plastic vials (50 mL)
- Plastic test tubes with cup (10 mL)
- Volumetric flasks (100, 500 and 1000 mL)
- Plastic buckets (2.5 mL)
- Vortex shaker

- Centrifuge
- Automatic pipette (1-5 mL)
- Rotating plate
- Visible / UV spectrophotometer

REAGENTS

- Solution of potassium chloride (2 M KCl): dissolve 149 g of potassium chloride (KCl) in a 1000 mL graduated flask containing approximately 800 mL of H₂O. Fill up to the final volume with deionised water.
- Salicylate-Na / NaOH solution: mix equal volumes of 0.3 M NaOH, sodium salicylate and deionized water (1: 1: 1). Prepare daily.
- Solution of sodium dichloroisocyanide (0.1% C₃Cl₂N₃NaO₃) (w:v): dissolve 0.1 g of sodium dichloroisocyanide in 100 mL of deionized water. Prepare daily.
- Ammonium stock solution (100 mg L⁻¹ NH₄⁺): dissolve 0.297 g of NH₄Cl in 1000 mL of 2 M KCl

CALCULATIONS

$$S(\text{mg kg}^{-1}) = \frac{(C \times V \times df)}{m}$$

Where:

C is the concentration of nitrate obtained from ion chromatography (mg L⁻¹).

V is the total volume of the added deionised water (25 mL).

df is the dilution factor. If it is not applied, it is 1.

m is the weight of the dry soil sample (g) (moisture correction is needed by determination of soil moisture).

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5. ASSESSMENT OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY

5.1. DNA extraction and purification

PRINCIPLE

In order to obtain reliable and reproducible data on microbial diversity from soil samples is highly dependent on the extraction of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in quality and quantity (Roose-Amsaleg et al., 2001). Extraction consists of the isolation and purification of DNA molecules by which DNA is separated from proteins, membranes and other cellular material contained in the cell (Robe et al., 2003). Over time, different protocols have been designed with the aim of obtaining an adequate quantity and quality of DNA, as well as ensuring the elimination of possible inhibitors that hinder the subsequent processing of the molecule.

For soil DNA extraction, different protocols are available, and the selection of the right extraction protocol or kit is essential to obtain the right results from soil samples. To extract metagenomic DNA from soil for subsequent ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, we used the DNeasy PowerSoil Kit according to the general protocol with minor deviations (Vishnivetskaya et al. 2014; Ramírez, Graham, and D'Hondt 2018). Nanodrop (ThermoFisher Scientific) and D Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen) were used for subsequent analysis of DNA yield and quantity.

PROCEDURE

DNA Extraction

1. To the PowerBead Tubes provided, add 0.25 g of soil sample.
2. Gently mix the tubes using a Ribolyzer (1 min, 5.5 m s⁻¹).
3. Check Solution C1. If Solution C1 is precipitated, heat solution to 60 °C until dissolved before use.
4. Add 60 µL of Solution C1 and invert several times or vortex briefly.
5. Secure PowerBead Tubes in the MP Fastprep-24 instrument and run the recommended program for soil samples (30 s, 5.5 m s⁻¹).
6. Make sure the PowerBead Tubes rotate freely in your centrifuge without rubbing. Centrifuge tubes at 10,000 g at room temperature for 30 s.
7. Transfer the supernatant to a clean 2 mL Collection Tube
8. Add 250 µL of Solution C2 and vortex for 5 s. Incubate at 4 °C for 5 min.
9. Centrifuge the tubes at room temperature at 10,000 g for 1 min.

10. Avoiding the pellet, transfer up to, but no more than, 600 μ L of supernatant to a clean 2 mL Collection Tube.
11. Add 200 μ L of Solution C3 and vortex briefly. Incubate at 4 °C for 5 min.
12. Centrifuge the tubes at room temperature at 10,000 *g* for 1 min.
13. Avoiding the pellet, transfer up to, but no more than, 750 μ L of supernatant into a clean 2 mL Collection Tube.
14. Shake to mix Solution C4 before use. Add 1200 μ L of Solution C4 to the supernatant and vortex for 5 seconds.
15. Load approximately 675 μ L onto a Spin Filter and centrifuge at 10,000 *g* at room temperature for 1 min. Discard the flow through add an additional 675 μ L of supernatant to the Spin Filter and centrifuge at 10,000 *g* at room temperature for 1 min. Load the remaining supernatant onto the Spin Filter and centrifuge at 10,000 *g* at room temperature for 1 min.
16. Add 500 μ L of Solution C5 and centrifuge at room temperature at 10,000 *g* for 30 s.
17. Discard the flow through.
18. Centrifuge again at room temperature at 10,000 *g* for 1 min.
19. Carefully place the spin filter in a clean 2 mL Collection Tube (provided). Avoid splashing any Solution C5 onto the Spin Filter.
20. Add 100 μ L of Solution C6 to the centre of the white filter membrane.
21. Centrifuge at room temperature at 10,000 *g* for 30 s.
22. Discard the Spin Filter. The DNA in the tube is now ready for any downstream application. No further steps are required.
23. Long-term storage of DNA at -80 °C.

Determination of DNA quantity and quality using Nanodrop

1. Make sure the measuring arm on the Nanodrop apparatus is in a down position.
2. Open the ND-1000 program by double-clicking on the NanoDrop ND1000 icon.
3. Choose “Nucleic Acid measurements” and “DNA” Lift up the measuring arm on the apparatus and remove the tissue paper. Check that both measuring surfaces are clean (if not then clean with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex)) Apply 1.5 μ L of MQ water. Close the measuring arm.
4. Click “OK” To calibrate
5. Lift up the measuring arm.
6. Clean of the measuring surface with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex)
7. Apply 1.5 μ L of solution C6 as a blank, close the measuring arm. Click on “blank”

To measure the DNA concentration:

1. Lift up the measuring arm.
2. Clean of the measuring surface with a soft piece of paper (Kleenex)
3. Apply 1.5 μ L of the extracted DNA sample, close the measuring arm.
4. Write the sample name in the field on the right-hand side of the screen.
5. Click on “measure”
6. Write down the measured concentration (or print a report after the last sample)
7. Repeat from step a) to f) for all samples.

Determination of DNA quantity using Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer

1. Prepare High Sensitive (HS) standards and DNA samples according to the manual supplied by the Invitrogen™ Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit.
2. Calibrate the Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer according to the manual using the prepared HS standards.
3. Measure the DNA concentration in all samples according to the Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer manual.

CALCULATIONS

The DNA concentration of all samples is calculated by the Nanodrop and Qubit 2.0 software. The quality of the DNA is determined by the A260/280 and A260/230 ratios quantified by the nanodrop software.

REMARKS

The use of an optimal DNA extraction protocol is crucial. The PowerSoil Kit method is the most universally applicable DNA extraction kit, resulting in high-quality data, with lower bias than other methods (Hermans et al., 2018). Nevertheless, all DNA extraction protocols will be biased to some extent. It is thus crucial to always standardize DNA extraction protocols for samples to be directly compared with each other.

*EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL***Equipment necessary (* provided with the DNeasy PowerSoil kit)**

- Analytical balance (0.01 g)
- Micropipettes
- 2 mL Collection tubes*
- PowerBead tubes*
- Spin Filter tubes*
- Distilled water

- Vortex
- Centrifuge
- Refrigerator
- Ribolyzer
- MP Fastprep-24TM instrument
- Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer
- Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer
- Invitrogen™ Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit
- 500 µL thin-walled PCR tubes

REAGENTS

- 70% ethanol
- Solutions C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, and C6*

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5.2. Bacterial and archaeal genetic diversity: ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing

PRINCIPLE

The small subunit ribosomal RNA (ssu rRNA) gene amplicon sequencing is the most widely used molecular taxonomic marker for microorganisms (Kolisko et al., 2020). The use of ssu rRNA gene amplicon sequencing allows the identification of prokaryotic taxa

in different environments, enabling cultivation-independent determination of bacterial and archaeal community composition (Caporaso et al., 2012).

The technique is based on PCR amplification of hypervariable regions of the *ssu rRNA* gene (also termed 16S rRNA gene in bacteria), which are then analysed using Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology and compared against DNA sequence databases to determine the identity and abundance of prokaryotic taxa. Within the AGROSUS Project, UCPH has opted to use a commercial next-generation sequencing provider for our sequencing needs in order to enhance our ability to meet tight deadlines for our project deliverables.

PROCEDURE

1. For amplicon sequencing, send the high-quality DNA samples obtained by DNA extraction (minimum concentration of 10 ng μL^{-1}) to NOVOGENE (HK) COMPANY LIMITED.
2. At Novogene, PCR amplification will be conducted using the modified bacterial/archaeal primer pair 515F -GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA and 806R-GGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAAT targeting the V4 region of the bacterial 16s rRNA gene (Parada et al., 2016).
3. The PCR products will subsequently be purified and used for library preparation.
4. The prepared library will be sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq2500 platform, and 250-bp paired-end reads will be generated with at least 50,000 raw reads per sample ($Q30 \geq 75\%$).
5. The obtained reads will subsequently be quality checked and analysed using the methods and software present in Table 2.

Table 2. Standard analysis and software

Standard Analysis	Software
Data split and reads merging	FLASH
Data quality control: data filtration and chimera removal	QIIME
OTUs (Operational Taxonomic Units) Clustering and Species annotation, including OTUs Heatmap, GraPhlAn display, Taxonomy Tree, KRONA results	Uparse, PyNast, Mothur
Species distribution, including Ternary plot, Species Abundance Heatmap, the evolutionary tree in genus.	RDP
Alpha-diversity Analysis, including Alpha Indices table (Observed species, God's coverage, Chao1, ACE, Shannon, Simpson, PD whole tree), Species diversity curves, Species accumulation boxplot, Venn and Flower diagram (Up to 5 figures for free)	QIIME, R
Beta-diversity Analysis, including Beta diversity heatmap,	QIIME, R

(un)weighted unifracs distance analysis, PCA (Principal Component Analysis), PCoA (Principal Co-ordinates Analysis), UPGMA (Unweighted Pair-group Method with Arithmetic Means), MetaStat, LEfSe analysis	
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5.3. Microbial functional diversity: Estimation of abundance of selected microbial gene sequences by quantitative PCR from DNA directly extracted from soil (C and N cycles)

PRINCIPLE

In the diverse ecosystems of the world, microbial communities are critical for the completion of the biogeochemical nitrogen (N) and carbon (C) cycles through their metabolic functions. Some specific taxa are the unique mediators of N processes in soils such as ammonification that control the quantities of bioavailable ammonium (NH_4^+) or nitrification that causes the biological oxidation of ammonia (NH_3) in the form of nitrate (NO_3^-) to be available for plants. In addition, through denitrification processes, a dynamic process by which N is lost and which can lead to the production of the greenhouse gas nitrous oxide (N_2O) (Ramond et al., 2022), regulate nitrogen (N) dynamics in the soil. Therefore, determining the dynamics of the microbial communities responsible for these processes through genes such as *ureC*, *amoA*, *narG*, *nirK*, and *nifH* involved in the N cycle is essential in the assessment of soil quality and health.

Similarly, C biogeochemical cycle involve the assimilation of inorganic C (CO_2) to organic compounds by living organisms. In the process of CO_2 fixation in soil by microorganisms, the Calvin-Benson-Bassham (CBB) cycle plays a key role due to most of the enzymes of the cycle are found to be encoded by *cbb* genes (Kusian and Bowien, 1997; Esparza et al., 2010). In this protocol, we choose the *cbbL* red-like genes to quantify carbon-fixing microorganisms.

Decomposition of soil organic matter and especially plant litter decomposition are key factors in carbon sequestration and storage (Cotrufo et al., 2013; Wei et al., 2021). Cellulose is the main structural component of higher plant cell walls and knowledge of microbial community actively involved in cellulose decomposition is fundamental to understand C biogeochemical cycle in soils. In this sense, the Glycoside hydrolase encoding GH7 gene is widely used to evaluate cellulose degradation (Hu et al. 2019; Tian et al. 2017).

In this protocol, microbial C and N cycling gene abundance is determined by qPCR targeting the genes ureC, amoA, narG, nirK, and nifH involved in the N cycle and the genes cbbL and GH7 involved in the C cycle.

PROCEDURE

1. qPCR standard preparation

qPCR standards targeting a sequence of the microbial gene of interest (GOI) are obtained from DNA extracted from soil samples according to chapter 5.1 of this Handbook. To select the appropriate amplicon to settle down each qPCR assay, primer pairs listed in Table 5.3.4.1 will be used for each GOI. First, using the DNA mentioned above as the template, PCR reactions will be conducted with the primer sets from Table 3, the reaction mixture described in Table 4 and the corresponding PCR cycling conditions described in Tables 5 to 11.

Table 3. Table PCR primers set for quantitative analysis.

Function	Target gene	Gene definition	Primer name	Primer sequence (5' – 3')	Annealing temp. (°C)	Amplicon size (bp)
Ammonification	ureC	urease	ureC-F	TGGGCCTTAAAATHCAYGARGAYTGGG	55°C	340
			ureC-R	GGTGGTGGCACACCATNANCATRTC		
Nitrification	amoA	ammonia monooxygenase	amoA1F	GGGGTTTCTACTGGTGGT	57°C	491
			amoA1R	CCCCTCKGSAAAGCCTTCTTC		
Denitrification	narG	nitrate reductase	narG1960m2F	TAYGTSGGGCAGGARAAACTG	56°C	110
			narG250m2R	CGTAGAAGAAGCTGGTGCTGTT		
Denitrification	nirK	nitrite reductase	nirK876F	ATYGGCGVCAYGCGCA	58°C	165
			nirK1040R	GCCTCGATCAGRTRTGTT		
N ₂ fixation	nifH	nitrogenase reductase	PolF	TGCGAYCCSAARGCBGACTC	55°C	342
Carbon fixation	cbbL	cbbL red-like gene	cbbL-RedF	AAGGAYGACGAGAACATC	57°C	
			cbbL-RedR	TCGGTCCGSGTGAGTTGAA		
Carbon degradation	GH7 (fungal)	cellulose degradation	GH7-F	GAGATCAAGCGYCTAYGTBCA	56°C	242
			GH7-R	GTCRAGCCASAGCATGTTGG		
Cloning site			SP6	ATTTAGGTGACACTATAG		
			T7	TAATACGACTCACTATAGGG		

Table 4. qPCR reaction mixture.

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (μL)	Final Conc.
Sybr Green Bioline	2x	10	1x
BSA	20 mg mL ⁻¹	0.6	0.6 mg mL ⁻¹
Forward Primer	10 μM	0.8	400
Reverse Primer	10 μM	0.8	400
DNA template	2 ng μL^{-1}	5	10
Sterile H ₂ O		2.8	
Total volume		20	

Table 5. ureC cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	30 s
Annealing		55 °C	30 s
Extension		72 °C	30 s

Table 6. amoA PCR cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	35	95 °C	25 s
Annealing		57 °C	25 s
Extension		72 °C	40 s
Extension		72 °C	10 min

Table 7. narG cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	35	95 °C	15 s
Annealing		65 to 60 °C	30 s Touchdown (annealing temperature progressively decreased by 1C by cycle)
Extension		72 °C	40 s
			30 s
Reading		80 °C	15 s
Denaturation	40	95 °C	15 s
Annealing		60 °C	30 s
Extension		72 °C	30 s

Table 8. nirK cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	6	95 °C	15 s
Annealing		63 to 58 °C	30 s Touchdown (annealing temperature progressively decreased by 1C by cycle)
Extension		72 °C	40 s
			30 s
Reading		80 °C	15 s
Denaturation	40	95 °C	15 s
Annealing		58 °C	30 s
Extension		72 °C	30 s

Table 9. nifH cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95	10 min
Denaturation	40	95	60 s
Annealing		55	60 s
Extension		72	60 s

Table 10. cbbL cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	60 s
Annealing		57 °C	2 min
Extension		72 °C	2 min

Table 11. GH7 cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	10 min
Denaturation	40	95 °C	10 s
Annealing		56 °C	30 s
Extension		72 °C	30 s

The expected size of the qPCR standard amplicons (PCR products from the above reactions) is verified by electrophoresis on 2% agarose gel in TBE buffer stained with SYBR Safe® DNA gel stain. Amplicons are purified with NucleoMag® NGS Bead Suspension according to the manufacturer instructions and quantified with Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit following the manual. Make sure you get at least 10 ng μL^{-1} of PCR product.

2. Cloning of qPCR standard

- The same day after purifying the PCR product obtained in the PCR reactions mentioned above (Tables 5 to 10), the ligation should be started. If the PCR product is stored, the A-Overhangs left by the polymerase may detach from the product and ligation efficiency will go down.

- The ligation is made using the pGEM®-T Easy Vector Systems kit from Promega following the manufacturer instructions but incubating the ligation reaction overnight instead of a few hours.
- Transform your competent cells (108 cfu µg⁻¹ DNA) that are provided with the kit, with the ligation mixture following the kit's instructions and plate 100 µL aliquots of the cell suspension onto LB/Amp/IPTG/X-Gal solid medium. Incubate the Petri dishes at 37 °C overnight in the dark for no more than 13 h. This process will facilitate white or blue colour development of the colonies.
- For screening of the recombinant clone, pick three white colonies per GOI (colonies containing the PCR product) and a blue one. Transfer them to liquid LB media with Ampicillin and incubate overnight at 37 °C.
- Extract the plasmid using the Isolate II Plasmid Mini Kit from Bioline.
- To make sure you get the desired product size, run a test PCR for the white and blue colonies for each GOI using the primers listed in Table 3 with the reaction mixture of Table 4 and the cycling conditions described in Tables 5 to 11.
- Quantify the plasmids with Qubit™ dsDNA HS Assay Kit.

3. qPCR standard curve

The qPCR standard curve is performed on serial dilution of the standard plasmid ranging from 10⁸ to 10¹ copies per reaction. The GOI is amplified by using the specific primers pair listed in Table 3, the reaction mixture described in Table 12, and the cycling program described in Tables 5 to 11 replacing the final extension by a dissociation stage (melt analysis) by gradually increasing the temperature from 60 °C to 95 °C. Standard dilutions and non-template controls (NCT) made of molecular grade water should be amplified in triplicate.

Table 12. qPCR reaction mixture.

Reagent	Initial Conc.	Vol/rxn (µL)	Final Conc.
SYBR Green	2x	10	1x
BSA	20 mg mL ⁻¹	0.6	0.6 mg mL ⁻¹
Forward Primer	10 µM	0.8	400 nM
Reverse Primer	10 µM	0.8	400 nM
Plasmid standard		2	

Sterile H ₂ O		2.8	
Total volume		20	

At the end of the assay, the results are analysed using the automatic option of the thermocycler. The qPCR is validated with the following observations:

- (1) no amplification in NTC reactions,
- (2) a single dissociation peak for each dilution of qPCR standard,
- (3) a linear calibration curve (standard curve) with R² ≥ 98%.

The qPCR calibration curve gives the number of cycle threshold (Ct) as a function of the amount of the log of the number of copies of standard sequences. The efficiency of the qPCR assay, which is calculated by the thermocycler software, is estimated from the calibration curve formula:

$$Ct = a \times q + c$$

Where,

Ct is measured cycle threshold;

α is the slope of the calibration curve;

q is the log copy number of qPCR standard;

c is the ordinate at the origin (Ct for 1 copy of qPCR standard).

$$E = 10^{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha}\right)} - 1$$

where E is the efficiency of the calibration assay and α is the slope of the calibration curve.

It shall be stated that a calibration curve having a slope equal to -3.32 is 100% efficient. Therefore, a 10-fold-dilution of a given DNA template gives a Ct difference of 3.32 for a 100% efficient qPCR assay (i.e., if 10⁸ Ct = 10, so 10⁷ Ct = 13.32).

4. DNA inhibition test

Inhibition in qPCR occurs when components used in qPCR hinder the activity of the (Taq) polymerase. Such a component is the intercalating fluorescent dye SYBR Green® itself used in qPCR. However, inhibition in qPCR usually refers to impurities, such as humic acid substances, co-purified with sample nucleic acids. These impurities may have an impact on PCR efficiency, thus delaying the amplification and therefore decreasing the samples copy number in absolute quantification. Inhibition is tested the following way:

- Spike 104 copies of plasmid DNA to soil DNA and perform a qPCR using SP6 and T7 primers.
- The amplification reaction is performed with the reaction mixture described in Table 11 including the soil DNA dilutions to be tested, three positive controls containing only plasmid DNA, and three NTC. The qPCR cycling program is shown in the following table and it will include a final dissociation stage (melt analysis).

Table 13. Inhibition test cycling conditions.

Step	# of cycles	Temperature	Time
Denaturation	1	95 °C	15 min
Denaturation	30	95 °C	15 s
Annealing		55 °C	30 s
Extension		72 °C	30 s
Melt curve	1	65-95 °C	2-5 sec/step*

*Temperature progressively increased by 0.25 °C increments

The inhibition test is validated by observing the following:

- a) no amplification for NTC,
- b) similar Ct values in qPCR performed from spiked soil DNA extract and plasmid only DNA. Soil DNA dilution showing no inhibition is chosen as the template to perform the qPCR assay.

5. qPCR assays

Once we have come out with a proper standard curve and obtained a DNA template free of inhibitors, the qPCR assay can be run for our DNA samples extracted from soil according to chapter 3.1 of this Handbook. 108 to 101 dilutions of the standard plasmid are run in every qPCR assay to create the standard curve and obtain an absolute quantification. The qPCR assay targeting the GOI will be performed on each soil DNA template at the dilution showing no inhibition exactly as described in “3. qPCR standard curve” with the only difference that both standards and DNA templates will be performed in duplicate.

CALCULATIONS

In this section the calculation of the copy number of the GOI in the soil DNA extract is described. The calibration curve and qPCR efficiency shall be calculated for each assay and recorded with the estimated number of copies of the GOI. The copy number of GOI can be calculated to the copy number per ng of soil DNA or per g of soil with the following formulas:

(I) Estimation of the number of sequences of the GOI per ng of soil DNA

$I \text{ (GOI/ng DNA)} = (\text{GOI in assay}) / (\text{volume of template in assay } (\mu\text{L}) \times \text{concentration of template in assay } (\text{ng } \mu\text{L}^{-1}))$

(II) Estimation of the number of sequences of the GOI per g of soil II ($\text{GOI g}^{-1}_{\text{soil}}$) = (I x extracted DNA from soil (ng))/(soil sample from which DNA is extracted (in g of dry mass equivalent))

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS

- PCR hood
- PCR thermocycler
- Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen™)
- Horizontal electrophoresis system
- Gel imaging system
- Water bath
- Shaking incubator
- Autoclave
- Oven
- Real-time PCR thermocycler
- Filtered tips
- Pipettes
- Low DNA binding Eppendorf tubes
- PCR tubes
- Syringe filters
- qPCR tubes
- Cold well-loading block

REAGENTS

1. Soil DNA extracted according to the method described in chapter 4.3.1 of this Handbook.
2. Ice
3. 70% Ethanol

4. PCR Buffer
5. BSA
6. Primers
7. TE buffer × 10: pH 8.0, 100 mL of 1 mol L⁻¹ Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 20 mL of 50 mmol L⁻¹ EDTA pH 8.0 in 880 mL of molecular grade water.
8. TE buffer × 1: 100 mL of TE buffer × 10 in 900 mL of H₂O.
9. Molecular-biology-grade water
10. Agarose
11. SYBR Safe DNA stain
12. DNA ladder with known lengths and concentrations of fragments.
13. NucleoMag[®] NGS Bead Suspension
14. pGEM[®]-T Easy Vector Systems with competent cells (Promega)
15. LB plates with ampicillin/IPTG/X-Gal
16. LB Broth
17. Glycerol
18. Ampicillin sodium, C₁₆H₁₈N₃NaO₄S (CAS No. 69-52-3)
19. Qubit[™] dsDNA HS Assay Kit (Invitrogen[™])
20. ISOLATE II Plasmid Mini Kit (Bioline)
21. SYBR Green[®] qPCR kit

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5.4. Microbial genetic diversity: PLFA and NLFA

PRINCIPLE

Soil microbial structure and diversity can be studied by using molecular biological techniques such as phospholipid fatty acids (PLFA). The determination of PLFA pattern of soil microorganisms has become one of the most commonly used methods to analyse microbial community structure and diversity (Frostegård et al., 2011). The edaphic microbiota, the main agent responsible for soil fertility, is also affected by these soil degradation processes that occur after the impact of management practices or environmental disturbances, hence the importance of studying several parameters related to the mass, activity and diversity of microorganisms in soils. Within the neutral lipids, the triglycerides, formed by three fatty acids linked by ester bonds to a single glycerol molecule, are the most abundant. Since the polar parts are linked (the carboxyl groups of fatty acids and the alcohol group from the glycerol) these neutral lipids are nonpolar and not soluble in water (Nelson et al., 2005).

PROCEDURE

Preparation of reagents

- 5 N NaOH solution. Weight 200 g of NaOH in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 mL with deionized water.
- 0.15 M citrate buffer, pH 4.0: dilute 28.82 g of citrate acid in 850 mL of water and add the 5 N NaOH solution to adjust the pH to 4.0 before dilute to 1000 mL with deionized water. This solution must be prepared at the time of use.
- Bligh and Dyer (B&D) reagent: mixt CHCl₃: MeOH: citrate buffer in a proportion 1:2:0.8 (v/v/v).
- Methanol: toluene: Mix both solutions in a proportion 1:1 (v/v)
- Hexane: CHCl₃ Mix both solutions in a proportion 4:1 (v/v)
- 1 M Acetic acid. Add 57.2 mL of acetic acid in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 mL with deionized water.

- 0.2 M KOH in methanol. Weight 11.22 g of KOH in a volumetric flask and bring up to 1000 mL with methanol. This solution must be prepared at the time of use.
- Standard methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0, molecular weight 312.54 g). Dissolve 115 µg of the standard in 5 mL hexane (concentration 23 µg mL⁻¹). This solution must be prepared daily.
- Detergent free of phosphates (2% in deionized water type II).

1. Lipid extraction

- Weigh between 0.5 and 6 g of dry soil (0.5-1.5 g if high OM (Organic Matter) content, 3.6 g if low OM content) and place in 50 mL Teflon tubes. Moist, air-dried, frozen or freeze-dried soil samples are used. Blanks without soil, treated under the same conditions, are prepared in each batch of samples.
- Add 10 mL of B&D reagent, shake with vortex for 1 min and keep at room temperature for 2 h to allow the compounds to be extracted.
- Centrifuge at 1,677 g for 11 min and transfer the supernatant to a 50 mL Teflon or glass tube.
- To complete the extraction, repeat the process, adding 5 mL of B&D to the residue. Add the supernatants to the 50 mL tube mixing both supernatants.
- Add 4 mL of chloroform and 4 mL of citrate buffer to the extract obtained and to shake in the vortex for 1 min.
- The suspension is left overnight at room temperature to extract the lipids in the organic phase. Another option is to centrifuge at 1,677 g for 11 min.
- The lower phase (organic) is extracted with a Pasteur pipette. An aliquot of 3 mL (high OM content soil) or 5 mL (low OM content soil) of this phase is dried at 40 °C under a flow of nitrogen in a dry block heater. The rest of the extract is stored at 4 °C until the end of the procedure.
- Dry samples are frozen at -20 °C. In case of continuing with the fractionation on the same day, it is not necessary to freeze.

2. Fractionation

The second step consists in separating the different lipid fractions.

- Dried samples (and thawed) are re-suspended using 100 µL of chloroform and agitation in the Vortex. This suspension is added to a silica column (SPE-SI), previously placed on 25 mL glass tubes. Repeat this process twice by adding 100 µL of CHCl₃.

- Once the lipids have been retained in the silica column, reagents of increasing polarity are applied successively to eluate the different lipid fractions collected in different glass tubes:

- 1.5 mL chloroform to elute the neutral lipids
- 6 mL acetone in two 3 mL steps to separate the glycolipids
- 1.5 mL methanol to eluate the polar lipids

- At the end of the fractionation, the contents of the tubes are dried at 40 °C under a flow of nitrogen in a dry block heater. In this method, the first (neutral lipids) and last (polar lipids) fractions will be analysed and the procedures detailed below are the same for both and must be performed with each of the samples.

3. Mild alkaline methanolysis (Transesterification)

The third step involves a transesterification reaction to convert the fatty acids of the phospholipids (PLFA) and neutral lipids (NLFA) into volatile derivatives that can be measured by gas chromatography.

- Add 100 µL of the Std19:0 (23 µg mL⁻¹ concentration) to all samples
- Evaporate the hexane under a flow of nitrogen.
- Add 1 mL of MeOH: toluene (1:1) mixture and shake in a vortex for 5 s.
- Add 1 mL of 0.2 M KOH in methanol, shake in a vortex 5 seconds and incubate in a bath (at 37°C) for 15 min. Let the samples cool some minutes at room temperature.
- Add 2 mL of hexane: chloroform (4:1), 0.3 mL of 1M acetic acid and 2 mL of water.
- Stir in a vortex for 1 min, check that the pH of the lower phase is around 6.0, centrifuge at 1,677 g for 11 min and remove with a Pasteur pipette the upper phase to a glass container. This step must be repeated by adding 2 mL hexane: chloroform, stirring and centrifuging again.
- Evaporate the solvents in the samples under a flow of nitrogen without heating. It is important to remove the samples when the last drop of the solvent evaporates to avoid losses of the more volatile fatty acids. Freeze the dry samples at -20 °C until its further analysis.

4. GC Analysis

The last step is the sample analysis on a gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID). A HP5 (phenylmethyl silicone) capillary column (50 m length, 0.2 mm internal diameter, 0.33 µm film thickness) is used.

- Chromatographic conditions (Frostergård et al. 1993):
 - Carrier gas was He (flow 0.8 mL min⁻¹)
 - Detector temperature: 230 °C
 - Injector temperature: 230 °C, injection was made in splitless mode
 - Oven temperature program: initial temperature 80 °C for 1 min, increasing first with 20 °C min⁻¹ to 160 °C and after with 5 °C min⁻¹ to reach 270 °C, remain at this temperature 5 min.
- The frozen sample is thawed to room temperature.
- Add 100 µL hexane to dissolve the sample and transfer to GC vials.
- 1 µL of this solution is analysed by duplicated by GC-FID.
- The PLFAs and NLFAs were separated, identified by the relative retention times compared with those obtained for the standards and the peak areas are quantified by adding, before the transesterification step, methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0) as internal standard.

CALCULATIONS

Each identified PLFA is quantified (nmol g⁻¹ dry soil) in each sample using the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 PLFA(nmol\ g^{-1}) &= \frac{Area_{19:0\ sample}}{Area_{19:0\ sample}} \times CI_{Std19:0\ added} \times R \times V \times \frac{1}{dry\ soil\ weight}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where:

Area PLFA_{sample} is the peak area of each PLFA identified in the sample.

Area 19:0_{sample} is the peak area of PLFA19:0 in the same sample.

CI_{Std19:0} is the amount of internal standard, methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0) added in step 3 to each sample, expressed in nmol.

$$\begin{aligned}
 S(mg\ kg^{-1}) &= \frac{(C \times V \times df)}{m} \\
 CI_{Std19:0\ added}(nmol) &= \frac{2300\ nm\ ml^{-1} \times 10^{-1}\ ml}{312.54\ ng\ nmol^{-1}} = 7.36\ nmol
 \end{aligned}$$

R is the correction factor determined by the recovery of the internal standard to each sample, calculated as:

$$R = \frac{Area19:0blank}{Area19:0sample}$$

Where:

Area19:0blank is the peak area of PLFA 19:0 in the blank.

Area19:0sample is the peak area of PLFA 19:0 in the sample.

V is the factor obtained from the quotient between the total volume of CHCl₃ used in the lipids' extraction, 7.95 mL, and the aliquot volume used to fractionation (3 or 5 mL) (step 1).

The procedure for the quantification of neutral lipids fatty acids (NLFAs) is the same as described for the PLFAs.

Total PLFA microbial biomass estimations

The sum of the content of all the PLFAs (around a total of 30-35 unspecific and specific to different microbial groups) identified and quantified of each sample were used to obtain the total PLFA biomass (nmol g⁻¹ of dry soil)

Microbial PLFA biomass of specific microbial groups

The content of each PLFAs biomarkers characteristic of the specific microbial groups is summed to obtain the PLFA biomass of these groups. For example, the bacterial PLFA biomass is determined following the equation (Frostegård et al., 1996)

$$TB = \sum I15:0 + a15:0 + 15:0 + i16:0 + 16:1\omega9 + 16:1\omega7t + i17:0 + a17:0 + 17:0 + cy17:0 + 18:1\omega7 + cy19:0$$

TB, is the bacterial PLFA biomass (nmol g⁻¹ of dry soil)

In the same way, the biomass of other microbial groups was obtained by the sum of their specific PLFAs biomarkers (fungi, Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria, actinobacteria, anaerobic bacteria, etc.) (see Table 5.1). It should be noticed that the criteria of the PLFAs characteristics of specific microbial groups could differ among authors (Frostegård et al., 1993; 1996; Zelles, 1999; Kaur et al., 2005; Díaz-Raviña et al., 2006); thus, in these biomass estimations the reference used should be included.

Ratios between different biomarker fatty acids

The relationships between some specific fatty acids are used to obtain information on the composition or the microbial status of soil microbial communities. The mostly used ratios are the following:

- *Fungal PLFA/Bacterial PLFA ratio*: provides information about the predominance of these main microbial groups, which play a different role in soil (Frostegård et al. 1996; 2011).
- Gram-negative to Gram-positive bacterial PLFA ratio: provides information concerning the microbial status of microorganisms (Zelles, 1999; Kirk et al., 2004; Frostegård et al., 2011)
- Ratios of PLFAs trans/PLFAs cis of monounsaturated fatty acids (16:1 ω 7t/16:1 ω 7c, 18:1 ω 7t/18:1 ω 7c) or cyclo/mono-unsaturated precursor (cy17:0/16:1 ω 7c and cy19:0/18:1 ω 7c): provides information on stress or starvation (Zelles 1999; Kirk et al. 2004).
- NLFAs/PLFAs ratios for specific fatty acids: provides information on nutrient status or physiological conditions of soil fungi (Bååth, 2003).
- PLFA or NLFA diversity indexes
- The richness (R) of the fatty acids is expressed as the total number of PLFAs or NLFAs present in each sample. The diversity of the FAs is calculated with the Shannon index H.

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^R p_i \ln p_i$$

Where p_i is the relative abundance of each fatty acid in the total sum and R is the number of detected fatty acids.

The equitability of the fatty acids is calculated with the Shannon's evenness E.

$$E = \frac{H}{\ln(R)}$$

REMARKS

Due to the high sensitivity of the method, impurities from the reagents and ineffective cleaning of the material used can cause serious contamination problems that can be detected in the blanks (without soil).

It is important to wash the material with a phosphate-free detergent. All clean and dry glass material (non-volumetric) must also undergo a heat treatment at 400 °C for at least

6 hours to eliminate any other organic matter including lipid contaminants. All reagents used are analytical grade, except the n-hexane, which is solvent to GC chromatography.

During the process, the following security measures must be taken into account: a) work in the gas extraction cabinet and, if it is not possible, use a mask with a filter to organic solvents, b) wear dust mask to weigh the powder reagents and c) use gloves and safety glasses whenever there is any possibility of splashes.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

- 50 mL Teflon centrifuge tubes with screw cap
- Glass tubes with screw cap
- Erlenmeyer flasks
- Beakers
- Volumetric flasks
- Graduated cylinder
- Pasteur pipettes
- 1.5 or 2 mL Micro-centrifugation tubes
- Petri dishes
- GC vials
- Spatulas and tweezers
- Racks
- LCR Cartridges Bond Elut SI (SPE) normal phase (polar)

REAGENTS

- Citric acid ($C_6H_8O_7$)
- Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)
- Potassium hydroxide (KOH)
- Acetone (C_3H_6O)
- Acetic acid (CH_3COOH)
- Chloroform ($CHCl_3$)
- Hexane (C_6H_{14})
- Methanol (CH_3OH)
- Toluene (C_7H_8)
- Methyl nonadecanoate (Std19:0, $C_{20}H_{40}O_2$)
- Water deionized type I (Resistivity $18 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$, C <5 ppb) used to prepare the reagents and water deionized type II (Resistivity $> 5 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$, TOC < 30 ppb) to wash the material
- Phosphate-free detergent

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6. ASSESSMENT OF ECO-TOXICOLOGICAL IMPACTS

6.1. Algae growth test with *Raphidocelis subcapitata*

PRINCIPLE

The objective of the algae growth test is to determine the effects of a substance on the growth of freshwater microalgae, *Raphidocelis subcapitata* in this case. Briefly, microalgae (with exponential growth) are exposed to the tested substance over 72 h. The expected response is the reduction of the microalgae growth in a series of algal cultures exposed to various concentrations of a test substance in comparison to control cultures (OECD 201).

Validity and applicability

The following criteria should be met for test validity:

- The biomass in the control cultures should have increased exponentially by a factor of, at least, 16 within the 72 h test period, i.e., a specific growth rate of 0.92 day^{-1} .
- The mean coefficient of variation (CV) for section-by-section specific growth rates (days 0-1, 1-2, and 2-3, for 72 h tests) in the control cultures must not exceed 35%. This criterion is applied to the mean value of CV determined for replicate control cultures.
- The CV of average specific growth rates during the whole test period in replicate control cultures must not exceed 10% in test with *Raphidocelis subcapitata*.

CALCULATIONS

The initial biomass in the test cultures must be the same in all test cultures and sufficiently low to allow exponential growth throughout the incubation period without risk of nutrient depletion. The initial biomass should not exceed 0.5 mg L^{-1} as dry weight. The recommended initial cell concentration for *Raphidocelis subcapitata* is $10^4 \text{ cell mL}^{-1}$.

1. Inoculum culture determination

- a. Two cell counts are obtained for each inoculum (one per replicate)

Example: Replicate 1: 59

Replicate 2: 74

Average = 66.5

- b. Since there is always a known volume between the coverslip and the Neubauer chamber, it is assumed that the inoculum concentration is $66.5 \cdot 10^4$ cells mL^{-1}
- c. If a fixed volume of 100 μL of inoculum will be used in each test vessel, and the recommended initial cell concentration is 10^4 cell mL^{-1} , it is necessary to calculate the dilution of the initial inoculum (e.g., $66.5 \cdot 10^4$ cell mL^{-1}).
- d. To each well of the microplate will be added 100 μL inoculum and 900 μL of the tested solution, so the diluted inoculum will have a concentration of 10^5 cell mL^{-1} .
- e. If 10 mL of diluted inoculum will be prepared:

$$C_i \cdot V_i = C_d \cdot V_d$$

$$C_i = 6.65 \cdot 10^5 \text{ cell/mL} ; V_i = ?$$

$$C_d = 10^5 \text{ cell/mL} ; V_d = 10 \text{ mL}$$

$$V_i = 1.504 \text{ mL} = \mathbf{1,504 \mu\text{L}}$$

- f. To obtain the diluted inoculum, take 1,504 μL and make up to a final volume of 10 mL.

2. Microalgae determination

- a. Two cell counts are obtained for each inoculum (one per replicate)

Example: Replicate 1: 73

Replicate 2: 85

Average = 79

- b. Since there is always a known volume between the coverslip and the Neubauer chamber, it is assumed that the inoculum concentration is $79 \cdot 10^4$ cell mL^{-1}
- c. Growth rate can be determined as:

$$\mu_{i-j} = \frac{\ln X_j - \ln X_i}{t_j - t_i} \text{ (day}^{-1}\text{)}$$

Where: μ_{i-j} is the average specific growth rate from time i to j

X_i is the biomass at time i

X_j is the biomass at time j

- d. The percent inhibition of growth rate can be determined as:

$$\% I = \frac{\mu_C - \mu_T}{\mu_C} \times 100$$

Where: %I is the percent inhibition in average specific growth rate

μ_C is the mean value for average specific growth rate (μ) in the control

μ_T is the average specific growth rate for the treatment replicate

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment

- Climatic chamber which can maintain incubation temperature (21 – 24 °C) at ± 2 °C and continuous photoperiod
- Light measurement instruments: preferably with a spherical receptor
- Microscope
- Orbital shaker
- Bunsen burner
- Centrifuge
- Laboratory balance
- pH meter

Material

- A Neubauer Chamber
- Coverslips
- Pipettes
- Test vessels (24-well microplates)
- Autoclaved glass material
- Plastic Pasteur pipette (sterile)
- 50 mL centrifuge tubes

REAGENTS

- Lugol

Growth medium for microalgae

In Table 14 are shown the reagents for each of the Stock solutions for the MBL growth medium (Nichols, 1973).

Table 14. MBL growth medium reagents.

Stock solutions	Per L distilled water (dH ₂ O)
Stock solution 1: Macronutrients	
CaCl₂·2H₂O	36.76 g
MgSO₄·7H₂O	36.97 g
NaHCO₃	12.60 g
K₂HPO₄	8.71 g
NaNO₃	85.01 g

Na₂SiO₃·9H₂O	28.42 g	
Na₂EDTA	4.36 g	
FeCl₃·6H₂O	3.15 g	
Stock solution 2: Micronutrients (Metal Mix)		
CuSO₄·5H₂O	0.01 g	Add each constituent separately to ~750 mL of dH ₂ O fully dissolving between additions. Finally make up to 1 L with dH ₂ O.
ZnSO₄·7H₂O	0.022 g	
CoCl₂·6H₂O	0.01 g	
MnCl₂·4H₂O	0.18 g	
Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O	0.0006 g	
Stock solution 3: Vitamin stock		
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B12)	0.0005 g L ⁻¹ dH ₂ O	
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B1)	0.10 g L ⁻¹ dH ₂ O	
Biotin	0.0005 g L ⁻¹ dH ₂ O	
Stock solution 4: Tris stock		
TRIS	250 g L ⁻¹ dH ₂ O	

To prepare MBL medium:

- Add 1 mL of Stock solutions 1, 2 and 4 to 1 L dH₂O.
- Adjust pH to 7.2 with HCl.
- Autoclave at 121 °C for 15 min
- Add 1 mL of Stock solution 3 (Vitamin Stock)

PROCEDURE

At least three replicates for each test concentration and control should be included

The surface where the cultures are incubated should receive continuous, uniform fluorescent illumination (cool-white or daylight type). The recommended range of light intensity is 4440 – 8880 lux for cool white light.

Procedure

1. Inoculum culture preparation: Test alga must be adapted to the test condition. An inoculum culture should be prepared 2 – 4 days before the test, to ensure the algae exponential growth phase.
 - a. Add 200 µL *R. subcapitata* concentrated solution to 75 mL MBL medium, with Bunsen burner. For example, in an autoclaved Erlenmeyer flask.
 - b. Cap the Erlenmeyer flask with air-permeable stopper, e.g., Parafilm.

- c. Shake for 3 – 4 days in the orbital shaker (100 rpm) under continuous photoperiod, at 24 ± 2 °C to ensure exponential growth.
 - d. Cell counting with Neubauer Chamber and microscope. Each sample should be counted twice.
 - e. See in CALCULATIONS Section (1. Inoculum culture determination) the instructions to prepare the diluted inoculum.
 - f. Obtain the diluted inoculum.
2. Soil elutriate obtention:
- a. Weight 5 g soil in an Erlenmeyer flask. Soil should be previously dried and sieved ($\leq 2 - 4$ mm)
 - b. Add 20 mL MBL (ratio 1:4 soil:MBL).
 - c. Orbital shaker at 100 rpm for 24 h.
 - d. 15 min rest period.
 - e. Transfer soil elutriate to 50 mL centrifuge tubes.
 - f. Centrifugate at 3900 rpm for 5 min.
3. Microalgae test:
- a. Before starting the test, please ensure that all the material is sterilized (e.g. autoclave).
 - b. All the procedure must be performed with Bunsen burner.
 - c. The first horizontal row of the microplate will be filled with 2 mL distilled water (6 wells), as the remaining wells have low volume to prevent evaporation.
 - d. The first column of the microplate will be the control (each microplate has its own control): 100 μ L diluted inoculum + 900 μ L MBL medium
 - e. The remaining wells can be filled with the soil elutriate with MBL, but always at least 3 replicates per soil elutriate: 100 μ L diluted inoculum + 900 μ L soil elutriate with MBL medium
 - f. Cap the microplates with air-permeable stopper.
 - g. 72 h under continuous photoperiod in orbital shaker (100 rpm) at 24 ± 2 °C.
 - h. After 72 h incubation, add 1 drop of Lugol in each well to stop the algal growth.
 - i. Samples can be stored in the dark at 4 °C until counting with microscope and Neubauer chamber (each sample should be counted twice)

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6.2. Avoidance test of earthworm *Eisenia fetida*

PRINCIPLE

In this test, by using a two-section test system, adult earthworms (*Eisenia fetida*) are exposed simultaneously to a control a to a test soil for 48 h. During this period, earthworms can freely experiment both soils in the system, avoiding or not the test soil. It is considered that the test soils have its habitat function deteriorated when >80% of the earthworms added to the test system are found in the control soil (ISO protocol 17512-1).

Validity criteria

The avoidance test is valid if the number of dead earthworms is <10%.

In the dual controls the distribution of worms in the test boxes should not surpass 60%: 40%.

PROCEDURE

1. Draw a line on the base and sides of each test box, creating two equal sections: one for the control soil and one for the test soil.
2. Place the divider in the middle line.
3. Cover the sides of the containers with aluminium foil to prevent lateral effects of light.
4. Add both soils to each side of the test boxes up to 50 – 60 cm depth. Fill one side with the control soil and the other with the test soil.
5. Prepare dual controls with the control soil in both sections of the test boxes.
6. At least five replicates per treatment (or soil sample) and per dual control are prepared.
7. Once the text boxes are prepared, remove the dividers.
8. Add ten adult earthworms to each box in the separation between both soils.
9. Gently join the soils, without mixing.
10. Close the test boxes, allowing gases exchange.
11. 48-hour incubation in the climatic chamber at 20 ± 2 °C with photoperiod. The boxes should not be disturbed during this 48-hour period. Earthworms are not feed during the test.
12. After 48-hour incubation, add the dividers to the test boxes within the climatic chamber.

13. The number of earthworms in each side is manually counted. Earthworms that were caught in the middle line are counted as 0.5 for each side.
14. Missing earthworms are considered to have either escaped from the test boxes or to have died and disintegrated during the test.

CALCULATIONS

The data can be expressed as avoidance percentage, determined as:

$$\% \text{ Avoidance} = \frac{nc - nt}{N} \times 100$$

Where: nc is the number of earthworms in the control soil (per box or treatment)

nt is the number of earthworms in the test soil (per box or treatment)

N is the total number of earthworms found at the end of the test (per box or treatment)

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Biological material: Adult earthworms of the specie *Eisenia fetida* from synchronized laboratorial cultures.

Soils:

- Natural soils: both potentially contaminated* with a tested substance (test soil) and a non-contaminated soil (control soil) with similar soil properties. Soils should be dried and sieved (≤ 4 mm). Prior to analysis, adjust the soil moisture to the water holding capacity (ISO 11274).
- Artificial soils: OECD artificial soil (OECD 222:2016). Composition: 75% sand (≤ 2 mm), 5% sphagnum peat, 20% kaolin clay. pH_{KCl} adjusted to 6.0 ± 0.5 with 0.3 – 1.0% CaCO_3 . Prior to analysis, adjust the soil moisture to the water holding capacity.

*Natural soil dilutions can be considered using the control soil selected for diluting the test soils.

Equipment:

- Laboratory balances with 0.001 (earthworms) and 0.1 g (soil).
- Climatic chamber with controlled temperature (20 ± 2 °C), photoperiod (12/12 h or 16/8 h light/dark), light intensity 600-800 lux.
- Magnetic Stirrer

Material

- Test boxes (glass or stainless steel preferentially) with ~ 0.02 m² and 50-60 cm depth.

- Dissection needle
- Aluminium foil
- Trails
- Small plastic boxes
- Dividers

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6.3. Reproduction test of earthworm *Eisenia fetida*

PRINCIPLE

Adult earthworms are exposed to a range of concentrations of the tested substance in soil over a period of eight weeks. After 4 weeks of exposure, adult earthworms are removed and their mortality and growth effects are assessed. The effects on earthworm reproduction are evaluated after a further 4 weeks by counting the number of juveniles in the soil.

Validity of the test

The following criteria should be met in the controls to be considered valid:

- Each replicate (containing 10 adults) to have produced ≥ 30 juveniles by the end of the test.
- The coefficient of variation of reproduction to be $\leq 30\%$.
- Adult mortality over the initial 4 weeks of the test to be $\leq 10\%$.

PROCEDURE

1. Acclimatisation of earthworms for, at least, 1 day prior to test with the artificial soil. During this period, earthworms should be fed on the same food to be used in the test.
2. Weight 500-600 g of soil in each container
 - a. 5 replicates are recommended for the artificial soil
 - b. 5 replicates are recommended for the natural control soil
 - c. 5 replicates are recommended for each of the concentrations of the tested substance
3. Wash each clitellated worm with distilled water, remove excess water, and if each worm weighs between 300-600 mg, randomly allocate to test containers until there are 10 earthworms in each container. Record the weight of the 10 earthworms in each container.
4. Weight of each test container to obtain a measure that can be used as a soil moisture basis.
5. 4-weeks incubation in the climatic chamber (20 ± 2 °C) with photoperiod (preferably 16 h light : 8 h dark) with 400-800 lux.
6. Water content in the test containers should be maintained by rewetting periodically (1-2 weeks).
7. Earthworms should be feed with oatmeal, cow or horse manure, among other. Food is first provided one day after adding the worms (~5 g of food) with 5 – 6 mL per container. Food should be provided once a week during the 4-week period.
8. After 4-weeks incubation (i.e., day 28), adults are manually removed from each container, weighted (previously washed) and counted. Any unusual behaviour (e.g., lying motionless, inability to dig into the soil) or morphology (e.g., open wounds) must be recorded.

Missing earthworms are considered to have either escaped from the test boxes or to have died and disintegrated during the test.
9. After adults removing, last 5 g of food can be added, then no further feeding is necessary.
10. 4-weeks incubation in the climatic chamber (20 ± 2 °C) with photoperiod (preferably 16 h light : 8 h dark) with 400-800 lux.
11. Water content in the test containers should be maintained by rewetting periodically (1-2 weeks).
12. After 4-weeks incubation, juveniles and cocoons can be counted. Any sign of harm or damage should be recorded.

Counting juvenile earthworms:

- a. Place the test containers in the water bath at 40 – 60 °C for 20 min
- b. After 20 min, juvenile earthworms should appear at the soil surface, facilitating their removing and counting.
- c. Transfer the surface layer of soil to a plastic tray
- d. Count the juveniles using the fine-tipped tweezers
- e. Repeat a, b, c, d until all soil has been carefully checked

CALCULATIONS

Adults

Several endpoints can be selected, but mainly mortality, i.e., percentage of adult mortality. Other endpoints changes in behaviour, weight, and morphology. Probit analysis or logistic regression can be applied to determine LC₅₀ (median lethal concentration).

Juvenils

Fecundity, i.e. number of juveniles produced, can be another endpoint. The arithmetic mean and the standard deviation per treatment and per control can be determined.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Biological material: Adult earthworms of *Eisenia fetida* from synchronized laboratorial cultures. Adult earthworms between 2 – 12 months and with clitellum, but individuals in a test group should not differ in age by more than 4 weeks.

Soils:

- Natural soils: both potentially contaminated* with a tested substance (test soil) and a non-contaminated soil (control soil) with similar soil properties. Soils should be dried and sieved (≤ 4 mm). Prior to analysis, adjust the soil moisture to the water holding capacity (ISO 11274).
- Artificial soils: OECD artificial soil (OECD 222:2016). Composition: 75% sand (≤ 2 mm), 5% sphagnum peat, 20% kaolin clay. pH_{KCl} adjusted to 6.0 ± 0.5 with 0.3 – 1.0% CaCO₃. Prior to analysis, adjust the soil moisture to the water holding capacity.

*Natural soil dilutions can be considered using the control soil selected for diluting the test soils.

Equipment

- Laboratory balances with 0.001 g (earthworms) and 0.1 g (soil)
- Climatic chamber with controlled temperature (20 ± 2 °C), photoperiod (12/12h or 16/8h light/dark), light intensity 600-800 lux.

- 40 – 60 °C bath.

Material

- Test containers made of glass/other chemically inert material, with a volume of ~2 L, cross-sectional area of ~200 cm² so that a moist substrate depth of at least 5-6 cm is achieved when 500-600 g dry mass of substrate is added. In addition, test containers should permit gaseous exchange with atmosphere and access to light (e.g. a perforated transparent cover), whilst preventing the earthworms from escape.
- (Aluminium foil: If test containers present transparent lids, then they should be covered with aluminium foil to prevent lateral effects of light.
- Plastic tray
- Fine-tipped tweezers

REFERENCES

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6.4. Germination and growth assays with *Lactuca sativa*

PRINCIPLE

The aim of the test is to evaluate the effect of the test substance exposure on seedling emergence (i.e., germination) and early growth. In this case, the test plant will be *Lactuca sativa* L. Briefly, seeds are brought into contact with the test substance. After 28 days of 50% of seedling emergence in the control group, the effects of the test substance are assessed. The endpoints are visual assessment of seedling emergence, dry/fresh shoot/seedling weight, shoot/seedling height, in addition to visible effects on different part of the plants.

Validity of the test

For validation, these criteria must be met in the controls:

- Seedling emergence is $\geq 70\%$
- Seedling must not show phytotoxic effects (e.g., chlorosis, necrosis, wilting, leaf, and stem deformations). Plants must show only normal growth and morphological variations.

- Mean survival of emerged control seedling is $\geq 90\%$ for the duration of the study.
- Environmental conditions are identical, growing media contain the same amount of soil.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Biological material: *Lactuca sativa* L. seeds. This species was proposed as test specie in terrestrial ecotoxicity standard protocol (OECD, 2006), since it is easily found in Europe, being commonly used, consumed, and cultivated. It is recommended to use certified or organic seeds.

Soils:

- Natural soils: both potentially contaminated* with a tested substance (test soil) and a non-contaminated soil (control soil) with similar soil properties. Soils should be dried and sieved (≤ 4 mm). Prior to analysis, adjust the soil moisture to the water holding capacity (ISO 11274).
- Artificial soils: OECD artificial soil (OECD 222:2016). Composition: 75% sand (≤ 2 mm), 5% sphagnum peat, 20% kaolin clay. pH_{KCl} adjusted to 6.0 ± 0.5 with $0.3 - 1.0\%$ CaCO_3 . Prior to analysis, adjust the soil moisture to the water holding capacity.

*To reduce the pollution level of the tested soil, it can be mixed with the unpolluted natural soil

Equipment:

- Laboratory balances with 0.001 g (seedling, roots) and 0.1 g (soil)
- Climatic chamber with
 - o Controlled temperature (25 ± 3 °C)
 - o Photoperiod (16/8 h light/dark) with a wavelength of 400-700 nm,
 - o Humidity control ($70 \pm 5\%$ during light period and $90 \pm$ during dark period),
 - o Luminance of $350 \pm 50 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (at the top of the canopy)
 - o Carbon dioxide concentration: 350 ± 50 ppm
- Laboratory oven at 60 °C

Material:

- Rectangular pots with 100 cm length, >10 cm wide and 30 cm depth.
- Water containers to put under the pots
- Glass wool
- Aluminium foil
- Plastic trays
- Fine-tipped tweezers
- Washing bottle with distilled water

- Brushes
- Ruler
- Cutter

Reagents

- 10% Sodium hypochlorite (v/v)

PROCEDURE

1. Pots preparation: Drill holes in the bottom to allow drainage, cover the holes with glass wool to prevent soil loss, and install a watering system at the bottom (e.g. by using glass fibre wicks).
2. Weight 2.5 – 5 kg of soil (80% field capacity) at in each pot
 - a. 3 replicates (i.e., pots) are recommended for the artificial soil.
 - b. 3 replicates are recommended for the natural control soil.
 - c. 3 replicates are recommended for each of the concentrations of the tested substance.
3. Disinfect seeds with 10% sodium hypochlorite (v/v) and rinse with distilled water.
4. Plant 20 seeds of *Lactuca sativa* in each pot to 1 cm soil depth.
5. The pots were arranged in a completely randomized design in the climatic chamber, with the conditions described above (see *Equipment*).
6. After 1 or 2 weeks of incubation period in the climatic chamber, check the artificial control replicates (i.e., OCDE soil) to ensure that $\geq 50\%$ (i.e., ≥ 10 seeds) of seeds were germinated. Record the number of germinated seeds vs. non-germinated seeds.
 - a. When > 10 seeds, then remove until there are only 10 seeds/pot.
 - b. When < 10 seeds, there may be a problem with the experiment conditions (environmental conditions, soil moisture, etc.)
7. Incubate the seedlings for 28 days.
8. After 28-days incubation, remove the seedlings from the plots. Record the number of seedlings in each plot.
9. To remove the seedlings, it is recommended to immerse the pot content in distilled water in a tray.
10. Carefully separate each seedling from the soil. Use a washing bottle with distilled water, brushes, etc. to help.
11. Once each seedling is separated, different measures can be performed:
 - a. Aerial (or aboveground) length
 - b. Root length
 - c. Fresh aboveground biomass and fresh root biomass:

Previously, aerial and root parts must be divided with the cutter. Each seedling can be weighed separately or all the seedlings in the pot can be weighed.

d. Dried aboveground biomass and dried root biomass:

To determine dried aboveground and/or root biomass, divide with the cutter aboveground and root parts. Each seedling can be weighed separately or all the seedlings in the pot can be weighed. For weighing, place the seedling in a small envelope made of aluminium foil. Drying in the oven at 60 °C to constant weight (48/72 h).

Other measures can be also performed, such as bioaccumulation, nutrient content, etc.

CALCULATIONS

Different endpoints can be determined from the experiment:

Germination index

$$\% \text{ Germination} = \frac{S_G}{S_T} \times 100$$

Where: S_G is the number of germinated seeds in each pot

S_T is the number of total seeds in each pot

Inhibition of germination

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \left(1 - \frac{N_T}{N_C}\right) \times 100$$

Where: N_T is the number of germinated seeds in the tested soil

N_C is the number of germinated seeds in the natural control soil

Aboveground and root length and biomass (fresh or dried)

The arithmetic mean, and the standard deviation per treatment and per control can be determined.

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6.5. Bacterial community growth

PRINCIPLE

The activity of soil microbial communities will be measured using the **³H-leucine incorporation technique**. First, it must be considered that radioactive material will be used (leucine labelled with ³H), and therefore: (i) the procedure must be performed in a laboratory authorized for this purpose, and (ii) all necessary precautions must be taken for the handling this type of radioactive material.

The relative measurement of the bacterial community growth can be determined by the rate of protein synthesis. This can be performed by using a radioactive precursor molecule, i.e. ³H-leucine, which is incorporated into macromolecules during a short incubation period. Hence, the amount of incorporated ³H-leucine will be a direct indicator of the growth rate. Briefly, this procedure consists of:

- (1) Obtention of bacterial community suspension from soil using homogenization-centrifugation.
- (2) Addition of ³H-leucine to the bacterial suspensions followed by a short incubation period to incorporate it into their proteins.
- (3) Measurement of incorporated ³H-leucine to estimate relative bacterial community growth: high rate of incorporation means high bacterial community growth rates, while low rate of incorporation means low growth.

Therefore, the toxic effect of a test substance can be assessed by comparing the bacterial community growth from a soil with added test substance with a unpolluted control soil.

The determination of bacterial community growth is very common in PICT assays (Pollution-Induced Community Tolerance). PICT methodology is based on expose the microbial community to a test substance in soil, i.e. PICT selection phase. During PICT selection phase, when the test substance exerts a toxic effect, the more sensitive species will disappear and the more tolerant species will be favoured, resulting in a more tolerant community. To measure the tolerance of the bacterial community (PICT

detection phase), it can be determined the bacterial community growth using ^3H -leucine incorporation technique. The measurement consists of a second exposition of the bacterial community to a range of concentrations of the test substance (for the subsequent calculation of the IC_{50} tolerance index). When the bacterial community tolerance for the soil with the test substance is higher than for the control soil, then the test substance is considered to be exerting toxicity from the point of view of the soil bacterial communities.

PROCEDURE

1. Reactivation of the microbial communities:
 - a. Calculate the necessary soil mass to perform the experiment, e.g. 20 g.
 - b. Weight 20 g of the soil.
 - c. Moisten the soil up to 60-80% of water holding capacity (ISO 11274).
 - d. Cover with parafilm to prevent moisture loss and allow gas exchange with the atmosphere.
 - e. Incubate in the climatic chamber at 22 ± 2 °C in the dark for at least 15 days.
2. Obtention of bacterial suspensions:
 - a. After incubation period, weight 1 g of studied soil in 15-mL centrifuge tubes. Each test soil and control soil must have 3 replicates.
 - b. Add 10 mL distilled water (ratio 1:10 soil:distilled water).
 - c. Multi-vortex for 3 min at maximum intensity.
 - d. Centrifuge for 10 min at 3000 rpm (1000 x g).
 - e. When necessary, the supernatant can be filtered through glass wool.
 - f. Transfer 1 mL of the supernatant to 2 mL microtubes
 - i. When PICT assay is performed, in this step, a range of concentrations (e.g., N=10) of the test substance can be added to the bacterial suspensions.
3. Incorporation of ^3H -leucine:
 - a. Add 20 μL of ^3H -leucine solution to each bacterial suspension. Record the exact time of addition of ^3H -Leu.
 - i. The 20 μL ^3H -leucine solution are composed by 0.2 μL [^3H]Leu (37 MBq/mL and 5.74 TBq/mmol Amersham) and 19.8 μL non-labelled Leu, resulting in 300 nM Leu in the bacterial suspension.
 - b. Vortex for 5 s.
 - c. Incubate in the climatic chamber 22 ± 2 °C in the dark for 2 h (incubation time can vary depending on soil properties).
 - d. After incubation period, add 75 μL 100% TCA. Record the exact time of incubation.

- e. Vortex for 5 s.
4. Washing and preparation for scintillation counting:
 - a. Microcentrifuge at 13000 x g for 8 min. Mark the "upward position" on the vial or place the hinges upwards in the centrifuge. The small (almost invisible) radioactive precipitate will be positioned in this direction after centrifugation.
 - b. Remove the supernatant with a glass Pasteur pipette connected to the Vacuum pump aspiration system. The Pasteur pipette must be carefully slid down the microtube along the side with no pellet thus avoiding contact with the pellet.
 - c. Add 1.5 mL 5% TCA.
 - d. Vortex for 5 s.
 - e. Microcentrifugation and remove supernatant again.
 - f. Add 1.5 mL 80% ethanol
 - g. Vortex for 5 s
 - h. Microcentrifugation and remove supernatant again.
 - i. Add 200 µL 1 M NaOH.
 - j. Vortex until pellet solubilization.
 - k. Laboratory oven at 90 °C for 30 min.
 - l. Let cool 5-10 min (fridge or room temperature).
 - m. Add 1 mL scintillation cocktail.
 - n. Vortex until the solution becomes clear.
 - o. Determination of DPM (disintegration per min) in the scintillation counter.

CALCULATIONS

Relative bacterial community growth

From DPM, the ³H-Leu incorporated (in pmol³Leu·g⁻¹·h⁻¹) in each soil sample can be determined as follows:

**Conversion factor: 0.000094764 pmol ³Leu/DPM*

$$\frac{\text{DPM} \times \text{Conversion factor}}{m_{\text{dry soil}}(\text{g}) \times \text{incubation time (h)}}$$

In order to compare different soils between them, obtained bacterial community growth data must be relativized with respect to control soil. For this purpose, each DPM data obtained must be divided by the DPM value for the control soil, giving values between 0 (high toxicity) and 1 (low toxicity).

For example:

	Soil 1 (raw data) DPM	Soil 2 (raw data) DPM	Soil 1 (relativized data) DPM rel	Soil 2 (relativized data) DPM rel
Control (unpolluted)	13250	58749	1.0	1.0
Dose 1 test substance	11733	38975	0.89	0.66
Dose 2 test substance	7415	26987	0.56	0.46
Dose 3 test substance	3652	9350	0.28	0.16

Bacterial community tolerance to a test substance

After DPM data are relativized with respect to control added concentration to each bacterial suspension, log IC₅₀ (the concentration that inhibits 50% of bacterial growth) can be determined from dose-response curves by adjusting to a logistic model:

$$Y = \frac{c}{1 + e^{b(X-a)}}$$

Where: Y: measured level of Leu incorporation for each test substance concentration

X: decimal logarithm of test substance concentration in the bacterial suspension

a: log IC₅₀

c: Leu incorporation without added test substance

b: slope parameter indicating inhibition rate

If bacterial community becomes tolerant in comparison to control:

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment

- Scintillation counter
- Centrifuge and micro-centrifuge
- Pipettes
- Laboratory oven 90 °C
- Vacuum pump aspiration system
- Laboratory balances
- Multi-vortex
- Vortex
- Climatic chamber at 22 ± 2 °C

Material

- Centrifuge tubes
- 2 mL microcentrifugation tubes
- Glass Pasteur pipettes
- Glassware: beakers, volumetric flasks
- Weighing spoon
- Parafilm
- Glass wool

Reagents

- 100% and 5% Trichloroacetic acid (TCA)
- 80% Ethanol
- 1 M NaOH
- Leucine labelled with ³H
- Non-labelled leucine
- Scintillation cocktail

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6.6. Fungal growth

PRINCIPLE

The fungal growth and biomass will be estimated using the **Acetate incorporation into ergosterol (Ac-in-Erg)**. First, it must be considered that radioactive material will be used (acetate labelled with ^{14}C), and therefore: (i) the procedure must be performed in a laboratory authorized for this purpose, and (ii) all necessary precautions must be taken for the handling this type of radioactive material.

Ergosterol is a lipidic membrane which is rapidly decomposed upon death of the hyphae. Sterols are a group of lipids which all present a structural formula consisting of three cyclohexane rings, a pyridine ring, and a straight C chain. Sterols present a three-dimensional structure. The conjugated double bounds of ergosterol enable the molecule to absorb UV-light, which is used when the molecule is detected using HPLC. By introducing a labelled marker (^{14}C) in acetate, a precursor to ergosterol, the amount of ergosterol produced in a defined period can be determined.

The procedure briefly: Labelled acetate is made available to the fungal community, and the soil sample is incubated for a short period (hours) to allow growth. Then, lipids are extracted from the soils with methanol, and most of lipids are saponified using hydroxide. Sterols remain unaffected by both acids and bases and will thus not be saponified. The saponified lipids are relatively hydrophilic, which means that the sterols may then be extracted with a hydrophobic solvent (cyclohexane). High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) enables use of a shorter column than can be used at atmospheric pressure and separation of substances which would otherwise be hard to separate. Methanol is used as the mobile phase and the column is a reverse-phase column which means that hydrophobic substances will eluate more rapidly than less hydrophobic ones. The ergosterol is detected using a UV lamp at 282 nm.

PROCEDURE

Some reagents in this procedure require work under a hood.

1. Reactivation of the microbial communities:
 - a. Calculate the necessary soil mass to perform the experiment, e.g. 20 g.
 - b. Weight 20 g of the soil.

- c. Moisten the soil up to 60-80% of water holding capacity (ISO 11274).
 - d. Cover with parafilm to prevent moisture loss and allow gas exchange with the atmosphere.
 - e. Incubate in the climatic chamber at 22 ± 2 °C in the dark for at least 15 days.
2. Preparation of ^{14}C -acetate for experiments:
 - a. ^{14}C -acetate is supplied in ethanol. Evaporate ethanol under a stream of N_2 (use low flow to avoid sample losses).
 - b. After evaporation, add 5 mL distilled water.
 - c. Vortex well
 3. Preparation of ^{14}C -acetate for soil samples:
 - a. For each sample: $20 \mu\text{L } ^{14}\text{C-Ac} + 30 \mu\text{L } 16 \text{ mM Ac} = 50 \mu\text{L } ^{14}\text{C-acetate}$ solution per sample
 4. Soil incubation with $^{14}\text{C-Ac}$:
 - a. Weigh 1 g soil in 10 mL test threaded glass tubes.
 - b. Add 1.95 mL of MilliQ water or ultrapure water for HPLC.
 - c. Add $50 \mu\text{L } ^{14}\text{C-Acetate}$ solution. Record the exact time of addition of $^{14}\text{C-Ac}$.
 - d. Vortex 30 s.
 - e. Incubate 2-5 h (depending on soil properties, mainly soil pH) at climatic chamber at 22 ± 2 °C in the dark.
 - f. Add $500 \mu\text{L } 5\%$ formalin. Record the exact time of incubation.
 - g. Vortex for 30 s.
 - h. Centrifuge for 5 min at 800 *g*.
 - i. Discard supernatant by Vacuum pump aspiration system with a glass Pasteur pipette connected. This step must be carefully performed to avoid aspire the pellet.
 5. Extraction:
 - a. Add 5 mL 10% KOH dissolved in methanol.
 - b. Vortex 15 s.
 - c. Sonicate the tubes for 15 min.
 - d. Vortex.
 - e. Put the tubes in the water bath at 70 °C for 60 min, with the screw caps tightened.
 - f. Vortex for 15 s.
 - g. Let the samples cool at room temperature.
 6. Phase-separation:
 - a. Add 1 mL of Milli-Q water (or ultrapure water for HPLC) and 2 mL cyclohexane to induce phase separation.
 - b. Multi-vortex for 1 min at maximum intensity to guarantee the contact between phases.

- c. Separate the phases: centrifuge for 5 min at 800 x g
- d. Transfer the hydrophobic phase, i.e. the upper phase, with a Pasteur pipette and put into new clean tubes.
- e. Add 2 mL cyclohexane to the original tube. Repeat multi-vortex and centrifugation to combine two upper phases from the same sample in the new tubes.

7. HPLC sample preparation and Scintillation:

- a. Evaporate the cyclohexane under N₂ on a heating block at 40 °C. Ergosterol is heat sensitive, remove from heat immediately when dry.
- b. Dissolve the evaporated samples in 200 µL methanol.
- c. Vortex
- d. Heat tubes with tight lids in a water bath at 40 °C for 15 min.
- e. Vortex
- f. Before HPLC analysis, filter the samples by 0.45 µm Teflon syringe filter into new 250 µL inserts in autosampler vials. Standards containing a known amount of ergosterol are treated in the same manner.
- g. Prepare and label 5 mL scintillation vials to collect the ergosterol fraction that was separated on the HPLC and install them on the automatic fraction collector.
- i. Injection volume 100 µL, HPLC column C18, mobile phase 100% methanol, flow rate 1 mL min⁻¹.
- h. Collect the ergosterol chromatograms from the HPLC (ergosterol estimates fungal biomass, the standard contains 2 µg ergosterol)

$$\mu\text{g ergosterol in sample} = \frac{\text{sample} - \text{peakheight}}{\text{std} - \text{peakheight}} \times 2 \mu\text{g}$$

- i. Add 3 mL scintillation cocktail to each scintillation vial.
- j. Vortex
- k. Determination of DPM (disintegration per min) in the scintillation counter.

CALCULATIONS

Fungal growth

From DPM, the ¹⁴C-Ac incorporated (in pmol ¹⁴C-Ac·g⁻¹·h⁻¹) in each soil sample can be determined as follows:

**Conversion factor: 0.1242331 pmol ¹⁴C-Ac/DPM*

$$\frac{\text{DPM} \times \text{Conversion factor}}{m_{\text{dry soil}}(\text{g}) \times \text{incubation time (h)}}$$

Fungal biomass

Fungal biomass can be determined from chromatogram area in relation to ergosterol patterns area.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment

- HPLC with UV detector (282 nm) and automatic fraction collector
- Scintillation counter
- N₂ generator
- Vortex
- Laboratory balances
- Climatic chamber at 22 ± 2 °C
- Vacuum pump aspiration system
- Centrifuge
- Sonicator
- Water bath at 70 °C
- Multi-vortex
- Heating block at 40 °C

Material

- Pipette
- Glass Pasteur pipette
- Glassware: beakers, volumetric flasks
- 0.45 µm Teflon syringe filters
- 1 mL syringes
- 250 µL inserts
- Autosampler vials
- 5 mL scintillation vials

Reagents

- Scintillation cocktail
- Methanol
- Hydroxide
- Cyclohexane
- ¹⁴C-acetate in ethanol
- Sodium acetate (non-labelled)
- 10% formalin (this corresponds to 4% formaldehyde solution).
- 10% KOH dissolved in methanol.
- MilliQ water or ultrapure water for HPLC.

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6.7. Soil basal respiration

PRINCIPLE

The determination of the soil basal respiration gives an estimation of the total activity of all organisms in the soil, including bacterial communities, fungal communities, animals, and roots. However, obtaining a value for a specific group of organisms is very complicated.

PROCEDURE

1. Weight soil into the 20 mL vial. The soil mass may vary depending on soil properties. For example, 2.0 g is an adequate amount for agricultural soils, while for organic soils 0.5 g is sufficient. Record the exact amount of soil.
2. Put a crimp cap with membrane (or septum) on each vial. Record the exact time.
3. Incubate at 20 ± 2 °C in the dark for ~18 – 24 h.
4. Measure the amount of evolved CO₂ on the GC. Note: include 2 of your empty standard vials at the start of the run, and one at the end (the first measurement from the GC should be discarded).

CALCULATIONS

The CO₂ peak appears at a retention time of ~1 min. The value used is the area of the CO₂ peak. Using previously determined conversion factors the following equation can be used:

$$\mu\text{g CO}_2 = \frac{1}{1.68} \times (\text{CO}_2 \text{ peak area sample} - \text{CO}_2 \text{ peak area control})$$

To determine the **respiration rate**:

$$\frac{\mu\text{g CO}_2}{m_{\text{dry soil}}(\text{g}) \times \text{incubation time (h)}} = \mu\text{g CO}_2/\text{g soil} \times \text{h}$$

Further calculations could be performed to determine, e.g. respiration rate per g of organic matter, to show how much of the soil C is respired per time unit.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment

- Laboratory balances
- Gas chromatograph (GC)
- Climatic chamber at 20 ± 2 °C

Material

- GC vials and crimp caps
- Tool for fitting and removing crimp caps

REFERENCES

Rousk, J., Hill, P.W., Jones, D., 2014. Using the concentration-dependence of respiration arising from glucose addition to estimate in situ concentrations of labile carbon in grassland soil. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 77, 81 – 88.

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6.8. Substrate-induced respiration

PRINCIPLE

Soil microorganisms are usually carbon (energy) deficient. Therefore, the addition of an easily available C source, e.g. glucose, can result in an immediate increased respiration rate. The reason is that soil microorganisms quickly increase their respiration to a stable value. During the constant period, microbial biomass is not increased. Approximately six hours after glucose addition, the respiration rate increases again with growing biomass.

When the soil is amended with, for example, glucose, the stable value also increases up to a maximum value. The value of the soil respiration under excess glucose addition, is the maximum respiration response of the soil microorganisms, and it can be considered proportional to microbial biomass.

PROCEDURE

1. Weight soil into de 20 mL vials (the soil from the Soil Basal Respiration can be used again). The soil mass may vary depending on soil properties. For example, 2.0 g is an

adequate amount for agricultural soils, while for organic soils 0.5 g is sufficient. Record the exact amount of soil.

2. Thoroughly mix glucose and talcum in the ratio 1:4 glucose:talcum. The talcum is added to facilitate the dispersion of glucose in the soil.
3. Add 15 mg of the mixture glucose-talcum per g wet weight soil.
4. Shake the vials, e.g. with the thumb on the lid (use gloves).
5. Put on (new) crimp caps with membranes/septum on the vials without tightening the caps (i.e., put them on loose).
6. After 30 min, carefully aerate the vials with compressed air using thin tubing for 30 s. Do not use high pressure of the soil will blow away.
7. Put the crimp caps on. Record the exact time.
8. Prepare 3 empty vials to be measured for starting CO₂ concentration.
9. Incubate for 2 – 4 h
10. Determine the amount of evolved CO₂ on the GC.

CALCULATIONS

A conversion factor between the SIR value and biomass-C has been calculated by comparing the results obtained using the SIR technique to the ones obtained using other methods to estimate microbial biomass in soil. It was found that a SIR respiration rate of 1 mg CO₂ per hour at 22 °C corresponded to 20 mg biomass-C.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Equipment

- Laboratory balances
- Gas chromatograph (GC)
- Climatic chamber at 20 ± 2 °C
- Compressed air with a thin tubing

Material

- GC vials and crimp caps
- Tool for fitting and removing crimp caps

Reagents

- Glucose
- Talcum

REFERENCES

Rousk, J., Hill, P.W., Jones, D., 2014. Using the concentration-dependence of respiration arising from glucose addition to estimate in situ concentrations of labile carbon in grassland soil. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 77, 81 – 88.

Handbook of Weed Management

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PROJECT ACRONYM: AGROSUS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This handbook is aimed to **the most important parameters to measure the occurrence and density of weeds in crop fields** and to measure the impact of different agroecological strategies on weed management in the eleven biogeographical regions of Europe. The parameters here listed are presented with a detailed protocol, the material needed for their measurement, the most relevant references, and the principles for why these parameters are so important for evaluating the control of weeds, and will be done by the different partners from the different eleven biogeographic regions from Europe in the agroecological and conventional farming systems established in the AGROSUS project.

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1. Case studies setup and experimental design

1.1. Experimental Units

Work packages 3 and 4 (WP3 and WP4) have been designed to develop solid and robust scientific understanding about the impacts of agroecological strategies (AE) on crop productivity, weed management and soil health and biodiversity, which is related to other ecosystem services such as soil fertility and carbon sequestration in different biogeographic regions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Biogeographical regions of Europe.

To correctly address the projects' objectives, short, medium, and long-term farm systems will be analysed, and 83 experimental units (68 short-term + 15 medium to long-term) will be considered in the 11 European biogeographical regions (Figure 2). Short, medium and long-term impact of AE on crop productivity, weed management, and soil health will be measured along the AGROSUS project. The short-term impact will be measured in experimental units developed by the different partners in conventional, organic, or mixed farm systems. However, considering the duration of the project (4 years), the medium to long-term impact of AE will be evaluated in in-course AE fields already identified in some of the different regions. Different measures to evaluate crop quality, weed control, soil health, ecotoxicological, environmental and socioeconomic impact will be recorded in the frame of AGROSUS.

Figure 2. AGROSUS short-term experimental units in the eleven biogeographic regions.

1.2. Experimental design

Experimental design is important in any scientific study, among other things involves what laboratory samples are to be taken, how they are to be collected and from where they are to be taken, in order that the objectives of the investigation programme can be achieved. In the comparison of treatments in agronomic experiments, a properly designed experimental scheme is of crucial importance to make adequate statistical inference. The two most common alternatives applied in the case studies of the project are shown below:

1.2.1. Randomized experimental design

This model assumes that the replicates of the different treatments are randomly distributed within the experiment when a randomized complete block design or a split-plot design is carried out (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of a randomized experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2.

1.2.2. Block experimental design

If a block experimental design (not randomized) is going to be carried out (Figure 4), control treatment (the one already performed in the farm as a routine basis, called “conventional”; CV) does not represent field variability since each treatment is located in different areas of the field, and some variations will be present in soil owing to different locations. So, initial conditions in each block have to be taken into account. Therefore, when a non-randomized block experimental design is implemented (Figure 4), the conventional treatment and each of the AE implemented will have their own designated area in the studied field.

Figure 4. Example of block experimental design. CV: Conventional; AE1: Agroecological Strategy 1; AE2: Agroecological Strategy 2.

2. Weeds management evaluation

2.1. Weeds in agroecosystems

Weeds play a significant role in agroecosystems, often reducing crop yield by outcompeting for resources, interfering with crop growth and development, and serving as hosts for pests and diseases (Baraibar et al., 2021). In addition to economic losses, weeds can also have ecological consequences, such as altering soil structure and nutrient cycling, and contributing to biodiversity loss (Storkey and Neve, 2018). Effective weed management strategies are essential for minimizing weed pressure and maintaining sustainable agroecosystems. These strategies often involve a combination of cultural, mechanical, physical, biological, and digital methods tailored to specific cropping systems and weed populations, with an emphasis on integrated weed management approaches that prioritize ecological sustainability and minimize environmental impact (Radicetti and Mancinelli, 2021). Weeds significantly prevail in most cases over cultivated plants in the struggle for life factors, as they have a higher reproductive capacity, better adaptation to external conditions, high competitiveness, a variety of biological features of seeds and organs of vegetative reproduction, the ability to parasitize other plants, etc. Accurate estimation of weed populations in the field is very important in order to reduce the use of pesticides in agriculture (Marshall, 1988). It is also important to know the weed threshold, as it is not necessary to eradicate weeds completely, but to keep them at levels that are not harmful to the crop, in order to benefit biodiversity in the ecosystem (Panetta and Gooden, 2017).

2.2. Timing and area of sampling

Weed sampling in agricultural fields is determined by factors such as sampling purpose, weed growth stage, and species characteristics. Sampling may target different stages of weed growth (e.g., vegetative, flowering, seed production). It often coincides with specific crop growth stages to evaluate weed-crop competition. Environmental conditions like temperature and soil moisture influence weed emergence and distribution, guiding sampling timing.

Weed sampling should be done a minimum of 2 times during the vegetation period, with a recommended total of 3 times: once before any weed management strategy is applied and twice during the growing season.

The sampling area may vary depending on the cultivation area and the type of crop. At least 3 replicates have to be done using quadrat frames of at least 50 cm x 50 cm, which may be larger in any case.

2.3. Measurements

2.3.1. Identification and quantification of weeds

Estimating the density and types of weeds present in each experimental plot help to assess the success of different weed management practices. Primary weed infestation is essential for forecasting weed infestation and economic thresholds. It is recommended to:

- Evaluate the total coverage of weeds (% of patch surface occupied by weeds).
- Evaluate separately the coverage of monocotyledonous (grasses) and dicotyledonous weeds (non-grasses).
- Evaluate the coverage of each species separately.

For the quantification of weeds, a quadrat is laid out in selected areas and the percentage of cover weeds is calculated using the Braun-Blanquet cover scale (Table 1) (Goldsmith & Harrison, 1977).

Table 1. The Braun-Blanquet cover scale

<i>Braun-Blanquet scale</i>	<i>Range of cover</i>
<i>r</i>	< 5% very few individuals
<i>+</i>	< 5% few individuals
<i>1</i>	< 5% numerous individuals
<i>2</i>	5 – 25%
<i>3</i>	25 – 50%
<i>4</i>	50 – 75%
<i>5</i>	75 – 100%

The identification of weed species and type can be done with the support of specific guides.

2.3.2. Density

Estimation of density of each weed species determine whether weeds respond differently to the different agroecological strategies or to the herbicide treatment in each experimental plot.

Density is calculated with the following formula (1) where the area corresponds to 1m².

$$(1) \text{ Species density} = \frac{\text{number of species}}{\text{area}}$$

After calculating weed density, a scale of soil coverage by weeds can be used:

0 – There are no weeds.

1 – Weeds occur singly → the degree of coverage is close to 0.1–3 weeds per 1 m²

2 – Degree of coverage up to 5% → 3–5 weeds per 1 m².

3– Cultivated plants dominate over weeds → 5–20% of weed coverage or between 5 to 15 weeds per 1 m².

4 – Cultivated plants still dominate over weeds → 20–50% of weed coverage or between 20 to 30 weeds per 1 m².

5 – The number of weeds is equal to or greater than the number of cultivated plants, the culture is under threat → 50–70% of weed coverage.

6 – Continuous clogging, weeds significantly prevail over cultivated plants → 75–100% of weed coverage.

Rating	a	b	c	d	%
I		10			
II		25			
III		50			
IV		>50			

Figure 5. The scale of projective weed coverage of the soil surface (in points and percentages). a\b – uniform scattering of weeds on the square; c– cellular coverage; d– solid coating.

2.3.3. Biomass (weight)

Knowing weed biomass is crucial for understanding effective weed management in agriculture. Weed biomass serves as a key indicator of weed pressure in crop fields, helping farmers to make informed decisions about weed control strategies. By quantifying weed biomass, farmers can assess the extent of weed competition with crops for resources like sunlight, water, and nutrients, which directly impacts crop yield. Additionally, knowledge of weed biomass enables researchers to study weed population dynamics, evaluate weed control methods, and predict potential yield losses.

After quantification, weeds are collected and the following measurements can be determined:

- The fresh weight of total weed species (g).
- The fresh weight of monocotyledonous and dicotyledonous weed species (g).
- The fresh weight of each weed species (g).
- The dry weight of samples collected: samples are placed in an oven at 70 °C for at least 48 h, until constant weight is achieved.

2.4. Evaluation of weed seeds present in the soil seedbank

Weed seed stocks in the soil are highly variable. Although a certain amount of them

germinates, and others die from aging, diseases and pests, the seed bank of weeds is constantly replenished due to the fall of new generations of weed seeds into the soil, their introduction through manure, wind, vehicles, irrigation water, etc. Therefore, farm agronomists need to determine soil contamination with weed seeds, in crop rotation fields, every year in the fall, after the main tillage or in the spring.

PROCEDURE

1. Soil sampling. The contamination of the soil with weed seeds is determined on the basis of their quantity in samples taken with the help of special augers designed by Shevelev, Kalentiev, etc. Samples (at least 10) are taken from each studied area along two diagonals at equal intervals. When taking a sample, augers should be immersed in the soil to a depth of 0-30 cm. The selection of soil samples is carried out in the fall after plowing or early spring. The number of samples on an area of up to 50 hectares is 10; up to 50-100 hectares – 20 samples, and over 150 hectares - 25-30 samples. Then, an average sample is made, for which a part of the soil is separated from each sample taken on the researched field in such a way that the average sample from one plot or field is 2 kg. The received samples are placed in pre-prepared and numbered bags. Package numbering or labelling must be done.

2. Laboratory processing of samples. The selected soil samples are transferred to the laboratory and dried to an air-dry state. Then, using one of the following methods, weed seeds are isolated, and their quantity and species composition are determined.

3. The first method of extracting weed seeds is washing the samples on sieves with a diameter of 0.25 mm. The soil is transferred to a sieve, which is two-thirds immersed in a vessel with water, and the muddy particles are washed until they pass through the sieve. The completeness of their removal is checked under the tap. When clean water flows, washing is stopped. The residue that remains on the sieve is washed into a watering can with a filter and, when the water drains, it is placed in a porcelain or aluminium cup and left in a drying cabinet to dry. Then, the remains from the filter are transferred to a collapsible board, weed seeds are separated by species with a spatula, and the number of seeds of each species is counted separately. There are no muddy particles in sandy soils, so that there is no need to wash the samples.

4. Seeds smaller than 0.25 mm pass through the holes in the sieve (spring sedum, sunflower and branched sedum, common bellflower, and some others), therefore, to extract the seeds of those weeds, the **heavy solution method** is used, which uses a solution made from zinc chloride or potash by dissolving 700 g of zinc chloride or 1.111 kg of potash in distilled water.

To isolate weed seeds using this method, a simple device consisting of a wide-mouth watering can or a bottomless bottle fixed on a tripod is used. A rubber tube with a clamp

is put on the neck of the bottle or on the end of the watering can. Half of the heavy solution is poured into the bottle. A glass is placed under it. The washed soil is transferred to a bottle with a heavy liquid, and the mixture is well stirred with a glass rod. Once all the seeds have floated, the soil that has settled to the bottom is removed by draining the liquid through an open downpipe into a beaker. A certain amount of heavy liquid is added to the latter, mixed well again, and then the seeds that floated are transferred to the bottle. This is repeated several times until all the seeds are separated. The solution with the seeds is passed through a filter paper, the filter is dried and the seeds are sorted on a sorting board.

Dried weed seeds are determined using a magnifying glass with a 10-fold increase. Only physically normal seeds are selected, i.e., those that when lightly pressed remain whole and full.

EQUIPMENT AND MATERIAL

Material:

- 700 g Zinc chloride or 1.111 kg potash
- Distilled water

Equipment:

- Auger Shevelev
- Auger Kalentieva
- Sieves with different diameters
- Tripod
- Funnel
- Bottomless bottle
- Filter paper
- Collapsible boards
- Magnifying glass

CALCULATIONS

After determining the species composition of weed seeds and the number of each of them in the sample, the number of seeds per square meter is calculated. For that, the area of the auger is determined by the formula:

$$S=x*d^2:4$$

where: S is the auger area (cm^2); $x= 3.14$; d - diameter of the auger (cm).

Then the conversion coefficient (K) is calculated, which is equal to:

$$K=10,000:S$$

where: $10,000$ - area 1 m^2 , expressed in cm^2 ; S - auger area (cm^2)

The final number of weed seeds per m² is calculated according to the formula:

$$M=K*T$$

where T is the number of weed seeds in the sample.

The number of weed seeds per hectare is calculated multiplying the obtained result by 10,000.

If the sample was taken with an auger without taking into account its cross-sectional area or with a shovel, then the number of weed seeds is calculated per unit of mass of completely dry soil (kg) according to the formula:

$$M = \frac{(100 + b) \times T}{100 + a}$$

Where: M – the number of weed seeds per 1 kg of completely dry soil;

a – Weight of the soil sample before washing (kg);

b – Moisture content of the soil in the sample at the time of its washing in water (%);

T – The number of weed seeds in the sample.

REMARKS

Table 2. Scale for assessing the potential weediness of arable land, million ha⁻¹ in the arable layer

Level	Degree of weediness	Intervals of values		
		Total number of physically normal seeds	Similar seeds	Number of buds on vegetative organs
1	Weak	< 10	< 2	< 0.1
2	Average	10-50	2-10	0.1-0.5
3	High	> 50	> 10	> 0.5

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2.5. Phytocenotic significance of weed species

PRINCIPLE

The weed community is determined using a simplified version of the phytocenotic method for determining plant communities. Its essence is that through a certain coefficient (index of phytocenotic significance) it is possible to evaluate the role and importance of each species in the weed grouping. In the previous measures, the vegetal grouping was characterized by the following indicators: number, occurrence, placement tier, development phase, or living conditions.

After evaluating these indicators, it is necessary to compare the available general species set of the weed group with the species set of already defined typical weed groups in the crops of this group of agricultural crops. If there are significant deviations in the species set of indicative species from the typical weed agrotyp, then this set of weeds is its variant.

PROCEDURE

1. All types of weeds are recorded, indicating the average number of their presence from the percentage of projective cover in units m^{-2} , and those types of weeds that are absent in the quantitative count but are only in the phytocenotic count;

2. The general level of the presence of the weed community and the share of each species as a percentage of the total application is determined;
3. The occurrence of each species is presented in percentage. This indicator is calculated based on the presence of this species in repetitions by proportion. If the species was found in all repetitions, then the level of its occurrence is equal to 100%, and if only in a few - then x.;
4. According to the level of presence and occurrence, the index of phytocenotic importance is calculated.

The index of phytocenotic significance of the species ranges from 0 to 100. According to its size, all species in the weed community are divided into dominant, subdominant and associated species. The first two groups are indicative species. The name of the variant of any agrotype is formed from the name of one or two main phytocenotically significant species, and then the words "variant of such agrotype" are added. Changes in the species set of an agrotype can primarily be caused by the reaction of this agrotype to the applied control system or the peculiarities of the climatic conditions of a given year and the peculiarity of the ground cover of a given field. Based on the results of the table, the name of the agrotype or its variant is determined and recorded below, giving an explanation for the deviations observed between the established grouping and the typical agrotype, as in the species set, level and phytocenotic value. If a weed community has a weed set that does not match any of the typical weed communities, then it will be a new agrotype. Perhaps it is common only in this area or its formation is due to other reasons.

Table 3. Determination of the agrotype of the weed component of the agrophytocenosis (crop name)

№	Type of weeds	Number of weeds		Occurrence (%)	Index of phytocenotic value	Phytocenotic role	Type of weeds
		pcs/m ²	%				
1.							
2.							
...							

CALCULATIONS

According to the level of presence and occurrence, the index of phytocenotic importance is calculated according to the formula:

$$I = C \times Z / 100$$

where

C is the abundance of the species, %;

Z is the occurrence of this species, %;

I – index of phytocenotic importance.

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